

THE INTERNATIONAL RICE RESEARCH INSTITUTE ANNUAL REPORT FOR 1975

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BIOTYPE 3

**THE
INTERNATIONAL
RICE RESEARCH
INSTITUTE
ANNUAL REPORT FOR 1975**

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The responsibility for all aspects of this publication rests with the International Rice Research Institute.

**THE
INTERNATIONAL
RICE RESEARCH
INSTITUTE
ANNUAL REPORT FOR 1975**

THE INTERNATIONAL RICE RESEARCH INSTITUTE
LOS BAÑOS, LAGUNA, PHILIPPINES P.O. BOX 933, MANILA, PHILIPPINES.

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*** On study leave.

About this report

This fourteenth annual report covers the work accomplished during the 1975 calendar year. The various sections of the report deal with the interdisciplinary approach to problem areas.

The department or departments that performed the research are identified in italics below the topic heading, i.e.

CONSEQUENCES OF THE NEW TECHNOLOGY *Agricultural Economics Department*

In collaborative work, the department that carried out one phase of the research is identified in italics in parentheses following the subtopic. For example, the Chemistry, Plant Breeding, and Plant Physiology Departments cooperated in the project FACTORS THAT AFFECT GRAIN QUALITY. Since the Chemistry Department bore responsibility for one phase of this effort, its name follows the subtopic:

Changes in grain properties during storage (*Chemistry*).

Data in this report are given in metric units, e.g. "t/ha" means metric tons per hectare. Unless otherwise stated, "control" means untreated control, grain yield is calculated as rough rice at 14 percent moisture, and protein content is calculated as a percentage of brown rice at 14 percent moisture. A single asterisk (*) means significant at the 5-percent level, two asterisks (**) mean significant at the 1-percent level, but if value for a control is given, a single asterisk means significantly different from the control at the 5-percent level and two asterisks mean significantly different from the control at the 1-percent level.

The system for indicating pedigrees uses a slant bar (/) rather than the multiplication sign ($\times$). For example IR32 $\times$ IR34 is now written IR32/IR34. The sequence of crosses is indicated by the number of slant bars: (IR32 $\times$ IR34) $\times$ Bg90-2 is now written IR32/IR34/Bg90-2. The fourth and further crosses are designated /4/, /5/, and so on. Backcrosses are indicated by a superscript numeral.

The report makes reference to three fundamental types of rice culture. Upland culture means rice grown without irrigation in fields without bunds. Rainfed paddy culture means rice grown without irrigation but in fields that are bunded, to impound rainfall. Irrigated or flooded culture means rice grown with irrigation in bunded fields.

A detailed table of contents is furnished at the beginning of the major sections in addition to the general table of contents at the beginning of the report. The thumb index on the back cover provides quick access to each section. To use it, bend the book in half and follow the margin index to the page with the black-edge marker. A subject index appears in the back of the report.

**THE
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1. One ton of rice (pictured above) will provide most of the nutrition for four adults and four children for one year. But a typical rice farmer who works from 1 to 2 hectares of land, using traditional varieties and technology, may harvest only from 1 to 1.5 tons of rice per hectare. The seven or eight members in his family may consume it all, keeping the family enmeshed in a system of subsistence agriculture. In regions where modern varieties and technology are available, farmers can produce from 3 to 6 tons of rice per hectare.

The new semidwarf tropical rices turn yellow and die in the cold of the mountainous regions, or they are stunted by icy irrigation water from melting snows. In the hottest regions, blazing temperatures render the new rices sterile in the dry season.

For all of these farmers, the best available technology consists of hardy but low-yielding local varieties and ancient farming methods.

The farmer who typifies the other three quarters of the world's rice producers is poor. His entire life and that of his family revolve around his one annual crop of rice. On his 1-hectare farm, he grows from 1 to 1.5 tons of paddy; most is consumed by his family of eight (fig. 1). Population pressure is so intense that what little rice remains will be eaten within 4 or 5 kilometers of the field where it was grown. Chances appear slim that his plight will improve in the near future.

The International Rice Research Institute is increasing its emphasis on the problems of the bypassed farmers. We are screening traditional rices from all over the world to identify those that can withstand particular adverse environments. These rugged varieties will be used as parents in our Genetic Evaluation and Utilization (GEU) program.

Some donors will contribute the genetic ability to withstand drought. Others have the capacity to elongate with floodwater or to survive submergence; any new rices that will yield better in deep water will need these traits. Centuries of evolution and farmer selection have given us parent varieties that can grow in

salty or alkaline soils, and still others that can tolerate excessively cold or hot weather.

Our scientists are working with counterparts in the national programs to jointly incorporate the ability to tolerate each of these stresses into a multitude of new rices for farmers in these harsh environments.

But we are not forgetting the fourth of the world's rice farmers who already grow the modern varieties. We know that the areas under irrigation are increasing, so we are intensifying our efforts to incorporate disease and insect resistance into the semidwarf varieties that respond so well to fertilizer. We are also selecting for varieties that produce high yields at low levels of fertilizer. The eating quality of all these rices is being improved, and their protein content is being increased.

IRRI today faces two giant challenges: to help generate the new rice technology so desperately needed in the bypassed regions, and to push still higher the remarkably high production potential of irrigated rice.

Progress in 1975

The weather in Asia was favorable in 1975, temporarily alleviating the long-term threat of severe food shortages. The monsoon rains came early and stayed late. Typhoon damage was less severe than normal and the few floods were localized. These favorable conditions permitted the modern varieties and associated technology to perform. Even though fertilizer consumption was slightly reduced, most nations produced more rice than in 1974, and several countries reached alltime records.

The 1975 production figures are refreshing and encouraging but they do not alter the long-term expectations of continued food shortages or even famine. One report suggests that by 1985 the food grain shortage in the developing world may be as high as 46 million tons, or six times the quantity of rice that moved in international trade in 1974.

IRRI continued to orient its research to the field problems of the rice farmer during 1975. We now know that conservatism—the reluctance of farmers to accept new ideas—only partly explains the low adoption of the new rice technology. The primary reason is that the new varieties are out of place in most of the diverse ecological situations under which rice is grown. They are too short for millions of hectares of deep water areas. Some still lack broad insect and disease resistance and most grow poorly on salty, alkaline, or zinc-deficient soils. They are generally susceptible to damage from excessively cold or hot weather. Few have been specifically bred to tolerate drought or to grow as a dryland crop under upland conditions.

Fortunately, the marked genetic variability in the world's rices offers hope that high-yielding varieties can be developed to tolerate the various adverse ecological environments in which rice is grown. We are using such rices as parents in our Genetic Evaluation and Utilization (GEU) program.

The reservoir of rice genetic resources was increased in 1975 as the number of accessions in the IRRI germ plasm bank reached about 35,000. IRRI scientists withdrew more than 22,000 samples to use in our breeding programs. We sent an additional 3,347 accessions to collaborating scientists in national research organizations to use in their own programs.

We made nearly 4,000 crosses in 1975 to incorporate desirable characteristics,

Table 1. More than 66,000 varieties and breeding lines were tested in field and in greenhouse screening trials in 1975 for resistance or tolerance to the major constraints that hold down rice yields. IRRI, 1975.

Resistance or tolerance to	Varieties or breeding lines tested (no.)
Blast	4942
Bacterial blight	6099
Tungro	3255
Grassy stunt	1026
Sheath blight	1048
Yellow stem borer	2520
Green leafhopper	8000
Brown planthopper	8278
Whitebacked planthopper	3892
Whorl maggot	10,000
Drought	3683
Salinity	1002
Alkalinity	1505
Zinc-deficiency	1200
Cold tolerance	8628
Heat tolerance	68
Flood tolerance	1446
Total	66,592

such as disease and insect resistance or drought or flood tolerance, into improved rices. The progeny of crosses, along with accessions from the germ plasm bank, were tested around the world and at IRRI by interdisciplinary teams of scientists (Table 1). From this gene pool, we identified new sources of resistance or tolerance to the enemies of the rice plant, including brown planthoppers, grassy stunt virus disease, and salinity.

We discontinued the official release of rice varieties during 1975, leaving this responsibility entirely in the hands of scientists in the national organizations. We will concentrate our efforts to feed genetic materials into national programs where local scientists can test and use them as parents to develop newer and better local rices, or as farmer varieties. Two such locally named varieties, IR36 and IR38, were released in early 1976 by the Philippine Seed Board, and others were named in other countries.

The potential to grow two or even three crops annually instead of one has forced greater attention to the development of early-maturing (100–115 days) rices. IR36 matures in about 110 days, is resistant to major insects and diseases, and yields about as well as IR8 and comparable varieties. But when yield is calculated in kilograms of grain per day—as it must be in regions where rice can be grown year around—IR36 yields considerably higher than medium-maturing varieties.

Research to improve the efficiency of agricultural chemical use was intensified. We found that placing chemicals into the rice root zone by hand or by simple machines doubled the efficiency of fertilizer use and quadrupled that of insecticide.

We established the existence of at least three different biotypes of the dreaded brown planthopper. The finding indicates that protection through genetic resistance will be difficult. Fortunately, sources of resistance have been found for each. These newly identified rices will be building blocks for future varieties that are resistant to all biotypes.

Evidence was found that different strains of tungro virus and of bacterial blight diseases occur. Resistant sources have been found for each strain, but genetic protection now appears much more complicated than before.

We found that inadequate use of pest control measures and of fertilizer are

the most common constraints on farmers' rice yields. Economic analyses showed that adding fertilizer was profitable, but that the cost of insecticides exceeded the value of added rice production. This emphasizes the urgency of the need to develop a wider range of varieties resistant to insect pests and diseases and of inexpensive methods of applying insecticides.

We continued to improve and broaden our working relationships with scientists in national rice research programs and encouraged the penetration of barriers that prevent the flow of genetic materials, technology, and scientific information among scientists in different nations. We helped accelerate the exchange of ideas, methodologies, and personnel among research organizations and continued to encourage networks of cooperating scientists using common methods to achieve common goals. IRRI now coordinates four such networks:

The *International Rice Testing Program* (IRTP), through which outstanding rices nominated by 15 countries were evaluated in 12 different types of nurseries at more than 450 locations in 1975;

The *Cropping Systems Network* through which research was conducted at 14 different sites in six Southeast Asian nations;

The *International Rice Agro-Economic Network* (IRAEN) through which interdisciplinary groups of scientists determined the constraints to higher yields at eight locations in six countries;

The *Farm Machinery Network* through which we helped evaluate the need for mechanization and encouraged the development and use of appropriate machines for farmers with small holdings in about 15 countries.

Major research results

New policy on naming of rice varieties. The International Rice Research Institute announced in 1975 that it will no longer officially name and release rice varieties. Instead, IRRI will concentrate its efforts on providing genetic materials, including both early and advanced breeding lines, to rice scientists everywhere, and will continue to encourage national programs to release IRRI selections as varieties under any names.

The modification of IRRI's varietal release policy reflects today's stronger national rice improvement programs, as well as increased international collaboration through the Genetic Evaluation and Utilization (GEU) program and the International Rice Testing Program.

IRRI has formally named and released 11 varieties, starting with IR8 in 1966 and ending with IR34 in 1975. More than 40 other IRRI lines have been released as varieties by national programs.

The Philippine Seed Board will continue to use the IR designation for IRRI selections released in the Philippines.

IR32 and IR34. We released the last varieties to be named by IRRI, IR32 and IR34, during 1975. Both are broadly resistant to insects and diseases (fig. 2) and have special characteristics that adapt them to regions where other IRRI varieties are not suited.

IR32 matures in 140 to 145 days—later than other IRRI varieties. The semi-dwarf rice may be particularly suited for certain rainfed areas where farmers grow only one crop. In these areas, late maturity is desirable so that farmers can harvest and dry the crop after the monsoon rains. In typhoon zones, later maturing crops may escape storm damage.

IR32 performed better than other improved rices at low fertilizer levels.

GENERAL
PROGRESS—
GEU

Resistance ratings of IRRI varieties in the Philippines.

Variety	Diseases				Insects			Soil problems			
	Blast	Bacterial blight	Grassy stunt	Tungro	Green leaf-hopper	Brown plant-hopper	Stem borer	Alkali injury	Salt injury	Zinc deficiency	Phosphorus deficiency
IR8	MR	S	S	S	R	S	MS	S	MR	S	MR
IR5	S	S	S	S	R	S	S	S	MR	R	MR
IR20	MR	R	S	R	R	S	MR	S	MR	R	R
IR22	S	R	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	MR
IR24	S	S	S	MR	R	S	S	MR	MR	S	MR
IR26	MR	R	MS	R	R	R	MR	MR	MR	S	R
IR28	R	R	R	R	R	R	MR	MR	MR	R	R
IR29	R	R	R	R	R	R	MR	S	MS	R	R
IR30	MS	R	R	R	R	R	MR	MR	MR	R	MR
IR32	MR	R	R	R	R	R	MR	S	-	-	-
IR34	R	R	R	R	R	R	MR	S	S	R	R

R = resistant; MR = moderately resistant; MS = moderately susceptible; S = susceptible

*Biotype 1

2. IRRI's newer varieties have broad ranges of resistance to diseases and insects and to certain injurious soils. IRRI, 1975.

IR34 was designed for rainfed regions where farmers prefer intermediate-statured varieties instead of semidwarfs. The first IRRI variety of intermediate stature (120–130 cm) since IR5, IR34 performs as well as semidwarfs do at low nitrogen levels but when heavily fertilized, its yields drop sharply. It may also do well in areas where water becomes too deep for semidwarfs.

IR32 and IR34 are resistant to the widespread brown planthopper, and to tungro and grassy stunt virus diseases. Both are also resistant to bacterial blight and green leafhoppers and at least moderately resistant to blast. IR32's genetic resistance to brown planthoppers stems from a different gene than that of other resistant varieties, IR26, IR28, IR29, and IR30. It carries the recessive gene (bph 2).

IRRI lines named in other countries. Six IRRI lines were named as varieties by national programs during 1975 (Table 2). This brings to at least 42 the number of IRRI lines named in other countries. Several intermediate-statured selections from the IR442 cross were named as varieties in Bihar and West Bengal states, India. One of the IR442 parents, Leb Mue Nahng, is a floating rice from Thailand. Because the IR442 progenies have some elongation ability, they are adapted to areas of moderately deep water. They also have better-than-average tolerance to drought. IR579-48-1 and IR1561-228-3 were named as varieties in Egypt, where their earliness maximizes the efficiency of water use. These selections have excellent grain quality and are extremely productive under Egyptian growing conditions.

Table 2. IRRI lines named as varieties in other countries during 1975.

IRRI line	Cross	Name	Country
IR442-2-24	Peta ² /TN1//Leb Mue Nahng	Pani Dhan 1	Bihar, India
IR442-2-58	Peta ² /TN1//Leb Mue Nahng	Pani Dhan 2	Bihar, India
IR442-2-50	Peta ² /TN1//Leb Mue Nahng	IR50	West Bengal, India
IR442-2-58	Peta ² /TN1//Leb Mue Nahng	IR58	West Bengal, India
IR579-48-1	IR8/Tadukan	Sakha 1	Egypt
IR1561-228-3	IR8/Tadukan//TKM6 ² /TN1	Sakha 2	Egypt

Exchange of germ plasm. We supplied 4,729 seed packets of elite breeding lines to scientists in more than 50 countries during 1975. More than 50,000 other seed packets of IRRI breeding lines were distributed through the International Rice Testing Program (fig. 3).

The GEU program is an interdisciplinary program that now involves 17 senior scientists from eight research departments. Coordination of activities is essential and requires careful attention. During 1975, we began to examine each nursery and screening facility and to carefully define its respective operational procedures and responsibilities in relation to the total GEU program. We also began to convert all of our procedures to computer for record keeping and data handling.

GEU
OPERATIONS

The crossing program was further expanded during 1975 (fig. 3). More than a third of the crosses were multiple crosses involving more than two parents. Other aspects of the breeding program have also expanded dramatically (fig. 3). We expect the volume of our program to stabilize at about the present level.

Germ plasm collection and preservation. IRRI staff members and national scientists jointly surveyed and collected indigenous varieties in remote areas of Bangladesh, Sri Lanka, and South Vietnam during 1975.

The scientists preserved 566 local varieties that might otherwise have disappeared—replaced by improved varieties—within the next few years.

Since the intensive field program began in 1971, IRRI has directly participated in the collection of about 5,660 seed samples from farmers' fields in 12 collaborat-

GEU PROGRAM GROWTH

3. IRRI has dramatically expanded the numbers of crosses made, the pedigree lines evaluated, and seed packets distributed to collaborating scientists in the national programs. IRRI, 1975.

Table 3. Indigenous rice varieties collected with IRRI's direct or indirect participation in 12 collaborating Asian countries. September 1971 to December 1975.

Country	Years	Indigenous varieties (no.)	
		Direct participation	Indirect participation
Bangladesh	1973-75	519	2361
Burma	1973-74	225	—
Cambodia	1973	280	—
Indonesia	1972-74	3816	2230
Laos	1972-73	—	898
Malaysia, E.	1973-74	—	375
Nepal	1971	—	907
Pakistan	1972-73	—	749
Philippines	1972-75	18	296
Sri Lanka	1972, 1975	691	167
Thailand	1973	—	127
Vietnam, S.	1972-75	108	649
Total		5657	8759

Table 4. Rices with special genetic traits needed by rice breeding programs that have been preserved in the IRRI germ plasm bank. IRRI, 1975.

Reported traits	Accessions (no.)
Tolerance to salinity	148
Tolerance to acid soils (lowland)	209
Tolerance to alkaline soils	11
Upland types	2462
Floating/flood-tolerant types	613
High-elevation/cool-tolerant types	639
Resistance to nematodes	5
Resistance to insects	3
Non-preferred by rodents	9
Aromatic types	89
Multiple tolerances	30
Total	4218

ing Asian nations. Another 8,760 samples were collected by local extension workers with indirect IRRI support (Table 3). We now have in our collection 4,218 rices with special traits such as tolerance to salinity and soil acidity or resistance to insects (Table 4).

Collaborating national and international agencies sent to IRRI for conservation samples of 5,097 Asian cultivars (*O. sativa*) and 142 African rices (*O. glaberrima*).

At the end of 1975, complete descriptions of 30,392 distinct accessions in the IRRI germ plasm bank had been obtained and recorded; another 2,757 new samples must be grown and registered. We have systematically analyzed the morphological and agronomic characteristics of 22,000 Asian rices and are recording traits for 984 African rices.

We removed from our accession books about 4,000 samples either because they were duplicates or because the seeds were dead and could not be replaced.

During 1975, we supplied 3,347 samples of Asian rices and 696 African rices and wild taxa to 168 researchers. Within IRRI, we supplied 22,155 seed samples with special traits to the GEU program—an increase of 3,000 samples since 1974.

The increased volume of requests for seeds has depleted many of our old stocks. We grew about 3,200 plots for seed rejuvenation during 1975.

Table 5. The yields of two medium-maturing varieties, IR8 and IR26, and an early-maturing line expressed as total crop yield and as average daily production. Three Bureau of Plant Industry experiment stations, Philippines, 1975 dry season.

Variety	Field duration (days)	Yield	
		Per crop (t/ha)	Av. daily (kg/ha)
IR8	110	4.6	42
IR26	109	5.8	53
IR2071-625-1 (Philippine variety IR36)	89	5.2	58

Table 6. Effects of levels of nitrogen^a on the grain yield of rice varieties and promising lines (average of 3 replications). IRRI, 1975 wet season.

Designation	Yield (t/ha)		
	0 kg N/ha	60 kg N/ha	120 kg N/ha
IR8	3.1	4.6	4.4
IR26	3.0	4.6	3.9
IR28	3.4	4.1	4.4
IR32	3.6	5.2	4.2
IR2071-586-5	5.0	5.1	5.2

^aIncludes 20 kg N/ha topdressed at panicle initiation except for the 0 kg N/ha treatment.

The vastly expanded GEU and the International Rice Testing Program, plus the large increase in seed stocks, create serious storage problems. Because of inadequate storage facilities, the viability of 12-year-old seeds of the temperate-zone varieties has been reduced to 37 percent. We began to rejuvenate 2,466 such accessions late in 1975.

We made detailed plans for a genetic resources laboratory to provide short-, medium-, and long-term storage.

We prepared a manual on the genetic conservation of rice germ plasm to assist national workers to efficiently conserve, maintain, and use indigenous cultivars and introduced germ plasm. We also prepared for seed technologists a pamphlet on the characteristics of rice cultivars.

Agronomic characteristics. We are continuing to develop rices with different lengths of growing season. Using early-maturing varieties, farmers can often grow an additional crop before or after the rice crop. The early rices are also generally more efficient producers.

An early line, IR2071-625-1, yielded as well as or better than the medium-duration varieties IR8 and IR26, especially in terms of kilograms of rice produced per day (Table 5). The Philippine Seed Board is releasing this variety as IR36.

But early varieties require more intensive care. If they are transplanted too late or spaced too widely, or if water control is improper, they yield less than the medium-duration varieties. Under such unfavorable conditions, later maturing rices such as IR32 (140–145 days) may be better.

In our search for rices that yield well at low nitrogen levels, we identified an elite GEU line, IR2071-586-5, that appeared outstanding in its ability to produce with no nitrogen added (Table 6). We will further test this characteristic.

Vigorous early growth is desired so that young rice can compete with weeds in systems where rice is seeded directly, such as early rainfed rice, upland rice, and in some areas, deep water rice before the floodwaters set in.

Rices of intermediate height may be best for medium-deep water where semi-dwarfs can not grow. They may compete with tall weeds better than the semidwarfs. But developing taller rices that do not lodge is a challenge. We are testing several fairly sturdy lines of intermediate plant stature.

Rice stubble left in the soil after the harvest of the main crop contains resting buds that, under favorable conditions, may grow into a second, or ratoon, crop of tillers. Rice is ratooned commercially in several countries but not widely in the tropics.

We have found that some rices can produce a ratoon crop in about 50 days after the main crop is harvested. The development of new virus-resistant lines opens up the possibility of ratoon cropping these rices in areas with as much as 2 months of good soil moisture after harvest of the main crop.

We evaluated the ratooning ability of several advanced lines that are resistant to tungro, grassy stunt, and other virus diseases. The line IR2061-423-1 performed best; 84 percent of its tillers ratooned. Many lines did not ratoon at all.

Yields from ratooning experiments could not be taken because rats destroyed most of the crop. Fear of rat damage may be one reason that rice farmers in the tropics do not practice ratooning.

Grain quality. Varieties differ in amylose content, the major determinant of eating quality, and in the rate of hardening of cooked rice. Taste panels can not always discern such differences in tenderness, even in cold cooked rice of samples with high amylose content. So we have developed gel consistency tests to measure this property in waxy and high-amylose rices. Cooked rices of intermediate amylose content remain soft on cooling and are generally preferred. Soft gel consistency is preferred, although rices may also be intermediate or hard. We are emphasizing intermediate amylose content and soft gel consistency as desirable grain characteristics.

Genetic studies show that the inheritance of amylose content is complicated among nonwaxy rices. In a study of a high-amylose rice, IR20, and a low-amylose variety, Fujisaka 5, we found that higher temperature during grain development decreased the amylose content only in the low-amylose rice (fig. 4). We found no consistent effect of temperature on gel consistency.

Differences in eating quality among rices are magnified in processed rice products. Even though these differences might not be detected in freshly boiled or steamed rice, they become noticeable when cooked rice is dried, stored, and reconstituted. We found that the processed quality of popped rice and of yeast-leavened rice bread was related to their amylose content.

Using a scanning electron microscope, we verified our previous findings on the structure of endosperm cells and starch granules of various rices. Physical properties of the starch, such as gelatinization temperature, are important in determining rice processing properties such as milling quality and deterioration during storage. In studies of cracked rice, we found that the nature of the cleavage plane (intercellular or intracellular) was not simply related to the compactness of the grain but was also affected by other factors.

Inheritance studies indicate that the gene that controls high gelatinization temperature is incompletely dominant over that for low gelatinization temperature.

4. High temperature during grain development decreased the amylose content of a low-amylose rice, Fujisaka 5, but not of the high-amylose IR20. IRRI, 1975.

We continued to survey changes in rice during storage. Storage makes the rice grain harder to mill but it increases the yield of high-quality head rice. It lowers the rate at which solids dissolve during cooking but it increases the volume expansion and water absorption. To determine if the changes that accompany grain aging are influenced by oxidation, we replaced air in the storage container with nitrogen gas. This had no effect on changes in rice quality. In addition, the free amino group of the lysine residues of protein remained free during storage. Hence, condensation of carbonyl compounds with free amino groups of protein probably does not occur with aging of rice. This indicates that the nutritional value of the protein does not decrease during storage.

We studied the developing grain to obtain information on factors that limit the rate of starch accumulation, which largely determines grain weight and yield. We identified an enzyme, 3-phosphoglycerate phosphatase, that controls the concentration of the substrate 3-phosphoglycerate in the developing rice grain, which in turn enhances the rate at which starch is accumulated.

Multiple resistance to diseases and insects. We have dramatically increased the proportion of our breeding materials that carry resistance to major diseases and insects.

But we know that if only a few resistant varieties are planted intensively over wide areas, new pest biotypes that could destroy varieties previously considered resistant may develop through natural selection. Therefore, we are closely studying races, strains, and biotypes of rice pests, and identifying new genes for resistance. By incorporating these genes into our elite GEU rices, we are diversifying our lines of genetic defense.

For example, varieties that carry the *Bph 1* gene are resistant to biotype 1 of the brown planthopper, which is common to the Philippines. Such varieties are being rapidly multiplied for use in Indonesia where brown planthoppers that appear identical to the Philippine biotype are becoming a severe pest. But we

expect that other biotypes of the pest will eventually arise and render these varieties susceptible, so we are now transferring two other new genes for hopper resistance into our elite lines as further insurance.

Similarly, we are incorporating new sources of bacterial blight resistance into advanced lines.

Almost all of our material is resistant to grassy stunt virus disease, but it derives its resistance from only one source. We identified during 1975 two possible new sources which we are incorporating into our program while we investigate their genetic identity.

We are diversifying our genetic resistance to green leafhopper, even though no biotypes that attack our resistant material have arisen yet.

Disease resistance. Most of our 32 elite breeding lines are resistant to three or four major diseases, and several to five. Almost all are resistant to bacterial blight and grassy stunt at IRRI. Many are moderately resistant to sheath blight. Most have low incidence of bacterial leaf streak in the field but are susceptible when inoculated in the greenhouse. Most advanced lines are resistant to tungro under field pressure at IRRI, but only a few reacted as strongly resistant when mass-screened by the rigid greenhouse test. Among them was IR34, which derives its tungro resistance from the Thai variety Gam Pai 15. Most reacted variably to blast, but a few were consistently resistant.

Blast and tungro are special problems because of their complex nature and difficulties in screening for resistance. We have made many crosses for blast resistance using varieties such as Tetep, Carreon, Dawn, Mamoriaka, Colombia 1, Ram Tulasi (sel), T1, *Oryza nivara*, and others as donors. For tungro resistance, we are using Pankhari 203, Habiganj DW8, and others.

In our search for better and more diverse sources of resistance, we have screened 4,942 new germ plasm entries for blast resistance; 6,099 for bacterial blight; 3,255 for tungro; 1,026 for grassy stunt; and 1,048 for sheath blight. Until recently the wild rice *Oryza nivara* was our only source of resistance to grassy stunt virus. But in 1975 we discovered two possible new sources of grassy stunt resistance, IR4497 (IR24//Zenith/M. Sungsong) and IR9560 (IR8³///IR8/Carreon//IR8/Tetep). Interestingly, none of their parent material is resistant to the disease.

We found further evidence of a correlation between qualitative resistance (withstands a number of races) and quantitative resistance (holds up in spite of

5. Rice varieties that were found resistant to most of the 256 races of blast disease in the Philippines (qualitative resistance) also withstood high disease pressure with few lesions (quantitative resistance). IRRI, 1975.

Variety	Reaction to strain		
	H100	PX063	PX061
Andel	MR	MR	MS
Boder	MR	MS	MS
Kolongi Bao	MS	MS	MR
DV 85	MS	R	R
ARC 6076	S	R	MS
IR8	S	S	S

6. Differential interactions between isolates of *Xanthomonas oryzae* and selected rice varieties. IRRI, 1975.

high disease intensity, or number of lesions). Of 18 rice varieties with varying degrees of resistance tested in the blast nursery, we found that those that were resistant to 90 percent of the 256 races known in the Philippines could withstand high disease pressure and had no or very few lesions, while those that were susceptible to most races had numerous lesions (fig. 5). This implies that many races of blast are found in the field, so a variety needs many resistant genes to confer stable resistance.

We found that strains of bacterial blight pathogen from Iloilo and Davao, Philippines, attack varieties with dominant genes for resistance. Further information suggested differential interactions between isolates of the bacterial pathogen and selected rice varieties (fig. 6). Such strains that are distinct in pathogenicity will complicate breeding for bacterial blight resistance.

We found that yield losses due to sheath blight were significant on the susceptible line IR1487-372-1, averaging 24 percent at three levels of disease intensity and at

Table 7. Sheath blight reduced yields significantly on the susceptible line IR1487-372-1 at all levels of disease intensity and nitrogen fertilizer, but yields were significantly reduced only at the highest levels of disease intensity and nitrogen on the moderately resistant variety, IR26. IRRI, 1975.

Inoculated hills (%)	Yield losses (%) at		Yield ^a (t/ha) at	
	0 kg N/ha	100 kg N/ha	0 kg N/ha	100 kg N/ha
<i>IR1487-372-1 (susceptible)</i>				
0	—	—	5.7 a	5.8 a
10	7.5	8.6	5.2 b	5.3 b
20	12.2	13.8	5.0 b	5.0 c
50	22.7	23.7	4.4 c	4.4 d
<i>IR26 (moderately resistant)</i>				
0	—	—	6.1 a	7.8 a
10	0.4	2.5	6.2 a	7.6 a
20	6.5	5.1	5.7 a	7.4 a
50	8.8	13.2	5.6 a	6.8 b

^aMeans followed by a common letter are not statistically different at the 5% level.

7. Scientists studied the reactions to natural infection of tungro virus disease of IRR varieties used as checks in the IRR pedigree nursery. Varieties were found to differ in resistance at different levels of disease pressure. IR34 was most resistant at all levels. IRR, 1975.

both low and high levels of nitrogen fertilizer. But with a moderately resistant variety, losses were significant only at the highest level of disease intensity and at the high nitrogen level (Table 7). This indicates that yield losses on moderately resistant varieties in ordinary field conditions will not be very high.

During a heavy natural infection of tungro in the pedigree nursery at the IRR farm, we studied the field reactions of several IRR varieties used as checks. All appeared to be more susceptible at higher disease pressure, but each variety differed in its reaction (fig. 7). The relative resistance of IR8 and IR1561 at low pressure was actually reversed at high disease pressure. IR34 was least affected and was most resistant under high pressure.

Insect resistance. Stem borers attack rice wherever it is grown, but there are no improved varieties with good levels of resistance to these pests. We increased our efforts in 1975 to screen, select, and cross for resistance to both striped and yellow stem borers, as well as to green leafhopper, brown planthopper, whitebacked planthopper, and whorl maggot.

We used a diallele breeding system to build up resistance to the striped borer, crossing seven moderately resistant varieties in every possible combination. We intercrossed progenies that showed resistance and by the third generation 30 lines were rated as resistant or moderately resistant. Some are distinctly more resistant than their parents.

We screened 2,520 rices for resistance to the yellow stem borer and identified 14 as resistant or moderately resistant; IR1820-52-2 is the most resistant line tested since the project began several years ago (fig. 8).

In 1975 we screened about 8,000 rices for resistance to the green leafhopper and selected 1,061 that are resistant. Of 8,278 lines screened against biotype 1 of the brown planthopper, we found 427 that are resistant. Of the 160 varieties tested of the African species *Oryza glaberrima*, all but three were highly resistant to the green leafhopper. Interestingly, this insect has not been reported in Africa. We found no brown planthopper resistance in *O. glaberrima*.

Out of 3,892 rices tested, we found 87 that are resistant or moderately resistant

8. The line IR1820-52-2 has the highest level of resistance to the yellow borer of any rice yet screened at IRRI. Rexoro is susceptible. Screenhouse trials. IRRI, 1975.

to the whitebacked planthopper. The most resistant were WC 1240, 41 Muskhan, IR2035-117-3, IR2071-105-9-1, and IR2071-137-5.

Of the 25,000 rices screened for whorl maggot resistance, none has been identified as distinctly resistant. We initiated a diallele crossing program using moderately resistant varieties to fortify the existing levels of resistance. The elite GEU line IR2070-414-3 had the highest whorl maggot resistance yet recorded. We field-evaluated about 20,000 F_3 plants from the IR2070 cross and are further testing those on which whorl maggot damage was low.

In studies of the biochemical nature of planthopper and leafhopper resistance, we found that the odor of stems of the variety Mudgo strongly attracted biotype 2 of the brown planthopper, to which it is susceptible. Similarly, the odor of ASD 7 attracted biotype 3, to which it is susceptible.

We found that hoppers will lay eggs on resistant as well as on susceptible rices and on barnyardgrass (thought to be an alternate host of hoppers). But the highest number of eggs was laid on the susceptible variety TN1.

We have identified three biotypes of the brown planthopper in IRRI experiments (fig. 9). Biotype 1 is the general type of brown planthopper found in the Philippines. Mudgo, IR26, IR28, IR29, IR30, and IR34 are resistant to it through the Bph 1 gene. Biotype 2 survives on plants that are resistant to biotype 1 but ASD 7, Ptb 21, and IR32 are resistant to it. Biotype 3 attacks plants that are resistant to biotype 2. Two varieties, Ptb 33 and ARC 6650, were found resistant to all three biotypes in IRRI screenhouse tests.

Hoppers of biotype 2 have been collected in farmers' fields about 40 km north of and about 800 km south of IRRI. But the population at IRRI, where resistant rices have been grown for several years, has remained of biotype 1.

We found two new genes for planthopper resistance in 1975, bringing the total resistant genes identified to five. The dominant gene in Rathu Heenati is different from and independent of Bph 1, and is designated Bph 3; the recessive gene in Babawee is different from and independent of bph 2, and is designated bph 4.

Similarly, we identified two new genes for resistance to the green leafhopper. The recessive gene in Ptb 8 segregates independently of Glh 1, Glh 2, and Glh 3,

9. Most of the recent IRRI varieties are resistant to the brown planthopper biotype 1, which is common in the Philippines. But biotype 2 attacks varieties that are resistant to biotype 1. Biotype 3 attacks plants resistant to biotype 2. IRRI, 1975.

and is designated glh 4; and the dominant gene in ASD 8 is non-allelic to Glh 1, Glh 2, and Glh 3, and is designated Glh 5.

In yield trials of the elite GEU rices bred for multiple resistance to insects and diseases, the line IR2071-586-5 performed best with and without insecticides.

Drought resistance. More than half of the world's rice is rainfed lowland—grown in paddies but depending on rainfall for moisture. Because the improved semidwarf rices are susceptible to moisture stress, they are not well suited for rainfed areas. Even on irrigated farms, the new rices often suffer when drought lowers the water level in canal systems or tube wells.

On about 10 percent of the world's riceland, including most of the rice in Africa and Latin America, upland rice is grown as a dryland crop on generally sloping, nonbunded land. The new rice technology has made virtually no impact on these regions. Drought resistance in upland rice varieties is essential if yields are to be improved.

The objective of the GEU drought resistance team (fig. 10) is to incorporate

10. In IRRI's new drought screening greenhouse, the drought resistance team hopes to screen from 1,000 to 3,000 rices per year. Left to right: Dr. Te-Tzu Chang, IRRI geneticist; Dr. Shouichi Yoshida, plant physiologist; Dr. John C. O'Toole, associate agronomist; and Dr. Surajit K. De Datta, agronomist.

the ability to withstand moisture stress into improved lowland varieties for rainfed and irrigated conditions, and into upland varieties.

We collect and screen rices from drought-prone regions, identify those that can withstand moisture stress and recover quickly, and cross them with varieties with pest resistance, good grain quality, and higher yield potential.

But single crosses of traditional upland varieties and pest-resistant semidwarfs generally produce partially sterile progeny. We are circumventing this problem by using promising breeding lines already selected from previous upland/semidwarf crosses.

During the 1975 dry season, we mass-screened in the field 3,683 rices from drought-prone regions and from IRRI, bringing the total screened to 6,340. The largest proportion of drought-resistant entries were traditional varieties from Thailand, Laos, Malaysia, Taiwan, South Vietnam, and the Philippines. Several hill rices from the Assam Rice Collection of India also responded well.

Two percent of our upland breeding lines can be classified as resistant to drought, 28 percent as moderately resistant, 56 percent as intermediate and 12 percent as moderately susceptible. The Philippine variety Salumpikit withstands drought considerably better than most other upland rices, including M1-48, which we previously used as resistant check (fig. 11). Other promising varieties include Olek Bandung and Bakka Bandjan from Indonesia, Binaritos and Malagkit Sungsong from the Philippines, and I Deng from Laos.

In the 1975 upland rice variety trials, 81 rices were tested at each of six locations

11. The Philippine variety Salumpikit has shown considerably higher drought tolerance than other upland varieties including M1-48, which we previously used as a resistant check. IRRI, 1975 dry season.

in the Philippines during the wet season. Although there was no severe drought, we were able to score the rices and observe varietal differences in response to and in recovery from drought during a few short dry periods at some locations. The late-maturing lines generally yielded higher and appeared more drought tolerant than the early and medium-maturing groups. The following lines appeared most promising: early-maturing, IR2061-522-6, IR1746-1-1; medium-maturing, IR1529-430-3, BPI 76^o/Dawn; late-maturing IR8³/Carreon, IR3273-P339-1, IR3273-P339-2, IR2053-242-1, IR3273-P339-3.

To better understand the role of root systems in combating drought, we examined the ratio of deep roots to shoots, or of the weight of the root fraction deeper than 30 cm from the soil surface to the weight of the shoot. We compared the ratios with visual ratings for drought resistance made by plant breeders under field conditions and found the measurements to be closely associated (fig. 12). This suggests that drought resistance may depend largely on avoidance mechanisms such as deep root systems that can penetrate into the soil to absorb water.

To develop the capacity to screen rice for both drought tolerance and recovery ability, we planted 12 rices in dry soil at a depth of 45 cm in four greenhouse tanks and subjected them to stress during vegetation and reproductive stages.

Our susceptible check, the African upland variety Moroberkan, was completely killed at all growth stages under high moisture stress. The most tolerant rice was IR2035-117-3, which also recovered almost completely after drought stress was relieved by watering. Other promising lines were IR1529-430-3 and IR442-2-58. Among the lines from crosses involving upland parents, IR1750 (parents, E425/IR22) performed considerably better than IR1746-226-1 (OS4/IR8).

IRRI has constructed a greenhouse to screen from 1,000 to 3,000 breeding lines per year in a similar manner (fig. 11).

We subjected seedlings of rice and sorghum to severe soil and atmospheric moisture stress to better control test conditions. We grew the seedlings in shallow trays in the IRRI phytotron. After rewatering the plants, we discovered that the percent survival was lower for many traditional upland rices than for lowland rices (fig. 13). These results indicate that rainfed lowland conditions may have enhanced

12. Varieties with high ratios of deep roots to shoots had high drought resistance in the field. IRRI, 1975.

selection for physiological tolerance to water stress. This trait may be lacking or less developed in traditional upland varieties, many of which escape drought because of their deep roots.

We compared decreases in plant height due to soil moisture stress among upland and lowland rices in the greenhouse. Generally, stress at the vegetative stage similarly reduced the height of both upland and lowland varieties. But stress at the reproductive stage killed the upland rices (fig. 14).

We found varietal differences in the incidence of leaf desiccation under severe soil moisture stress (Table 8). When we rewatered the stressed plants, we found that rices with less than 40 percent desiccated leaves at the vegetative stage recovered and resumed growth, while those with 80 percent or more desiccation did not recover.

Recent work in Australia indicates an association between drought tolerance and proline accumulation in leaves. Because leaf desiccation is a criterion for field selection, we investigated the relationship between dried leaves and their proline content. Correlation analysis indicated that tissue survival and proline accumulation in rice leaves are associated (fig. 15).

In field studies of plant-water relationships, we planted rices at different elevations down a topographical sequence, subjecting them to varying levels of moisture stress. We hope to refine the method to effectively assess the adaptability of elite lines to varying hydrological conditions. We are also quantifying the soil-plant-atmosphere water status of the upland rice environment to better

13. Relationship of percent survival to exposure to growth chamber conditions for six rice and sorghum. IRRI, 1975.

evaluate plant characteristics that will ultimately contribute better drought resistance.

Traditional upland varieties are generally tall and low tillering, with long droopy leaves that join the stem at a wide angle. We have observed that droopy leaves of upland varieties are sometimes scorched at the bend by direct noon sunlight. To study the importance of leaf angle, we grew sets of IR24, which has erect leaves, and MRC172-9, which has slightly droopy leaves. We forced the leaves of one IR24 plant to droop, and left the other as an erect control. Similarly, we supported the leaves of one MRC172-9 plant, and left the other as a droopy

14. Plant height (relative values with continuous saturation taken as 100) of four upland and nine lowland varieties of rice (average, 1974 wet and 1975 dry seasons) as affected by 18 to 19 bars of soil moisture tension. Greenhouse experiment. IRRI, 1975.

Table 8. Leaf desiccation of 6 rices as a function of soil moisture tension at the vegetative and reproductive stages. Geenhouse experiment, IRRI, 1975 dry season.

Variety/line	Desiccated leaves (%) at end of stress period ^a		
	Vegetative stage	Reproductive stage	Recovery after relief of stress
<i>Upland varieties</i>			
OS6	66	91	poor
Moroberekan	100	100	dead
<i>IRRI lines selected under upland conditions</i>			
IR1746-226-1	90	99	dead
IR1750(F ₅ B)-5	58	87	poor
<i>Varieties/lines selected under lowland conditions</i>			
IR20	56	80	fair
IR2035-117-3	29	72	good

^a 18-19 bars.

control. After moisture stress, we found that erect-leaved plants of both varieties were less affected, perhaps because the erect leaves curled and rolled while droopy leaves could not roll at the curvature. As the tissues of droopy leaves die at the bend, the entire upper leaf also begins to die. When the sun is overhead, single erect leaves probably intercept less heat than horizontal leaves. In some situations, erect leaves might be preferable to droopy leaves in upland rice.

Tolerance to injurious soils. Population pressure in Asia has forced farmers to grow rice in a number of regions of injurious soils. To help these farmers, and to possibly open new land not yet being used, we are developing varieties that can

15. Relationships between proline content in leaf and leaf desiccation at 18 to 19 bars of soil moisture tension during the vegetative stage of rice. Greenhouse experiment. IRRI, 1975 dry season.

a

b

16. a) The rugged variety Pokkali growing in fields of deep and brackish water in coastal regions of Kerala state, India. Note the boats used in the ricefields. Left, K. I. Ipathu; right, J. Chandra Mohan, rice breeder, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Tamil Nadu state, India. b) In the greenhouse at IRRI, Pokkali and an elite GEU line, IR2153-26-3, thrive in a soil amended with 0.4 percent salt while the susceptible check variety M1-48 has died. Left is Ruby Castro, assistant chemist; right, Dr. Hiroshi Ikehashi, IRRI rice breeder.

tolerate toxic soils. Such varieties will provide an inexpensive means of increasing rice yields for millions of small farmers.

Salinity is the most common injurious soil condition. Salty soils limit yields on millions of hectares of coastal regions, as well as in desert regions brought into production by irrigation. But in areas where salt water has been a problem for centuries, a few low-yielding traditional varieties grow. For example, a tall and hardy variety called Pokkali grows along the coasts of South India and Sri Lanka in deep brackish water that would kill improved rices. The genes that help Pokkali and similar rices adapt to salinity may be building blocks for improved salt-tolerant varieties (fig. 16).

During the 1975 dry season, we grew 1,946 F_3 lines from double crosses with Pokkali in an artificially amended saline field at IRRI. From these, we selected 192 lines with superior salinity tolerance.

We found 38 other rices that are even more salt-tolerant than Pokkali in our screening of 1,002 varieties and 490 breeding lines from 24 countries in greenhouses and salt-amended fields. These will be used as additional parents in the breeding program. Some will be tested for varietal potential.

Because salinity in the ricefields of both arid and coastal regions can vary widely during a cropping season, we evaluated the effect of high salt concentration on the growth and yield of three rices with different degrees of tolerance at different growth stages in the greenhouse.

IR26 (moderately susceptible) and T26 (highly susceptible) were injured most when transplanted in a salty soil (0.4% salt). Plants were less injured when subjected to the same level of salt 4 weeks later (simulating intrusion of brackish water into the coastal areas during the dry season). Plants subjected to salt at 7 weeks after transplanting had the mildest symptoms. One elite line with fair

17. IR26 and T26 were most severely injured when transplanted into a salty soil (0.4%), but were less affected at 4 weeks after transplanting (WT) and at 7 WT. The elite GEU line IR2153-26-3 tolerated salinity well under all salt treatments. IRRI, 1975.

pest resistance, IR2153, tolerated salinity well under all salt treatments (fig. 16 and 17). Yield data indicated that ratings by visual symptoms were accurate.

Our present screening technique allows us to do preliminary mass screening in the greenhouse. But promising materials may vary in their reactions to high salt levels at different growth stages. These materials should therefore be tested under actual field conditions in many countries.

The first International Rice Salinity Tolerance Observational Nursery (IRSTON) was organized in 1975 and distributed to collaborating scientists in 12 countries. Rices that were identified as tolerant to salinity in the greenhouse, such as IR2035-290-2 and IR2071-88-8, were also found tolerant under field screening in Thailand and West Bengal, India.

Alkalinity retards yields on several million hectares of irrigated soils in arid regions of India, Pakistan, Iran, and Egypt. Interestingly, the rugged Pokkali also tolerates alkaline soils.

We screened 1,946 F_3 lines from crosses involving alkali-tolerant parents in an alkali-amended field at IRRI during the 1975 dry and wet seasons and identified some promising lines.

We tested 1,505 rices in the greenhouse and in the field and found 122 as tolerant as Pokkali to alkalinity. They include 11 IRRI breeding lines; 24 selections from Tamil Nadu state, India; and 72 rices from Bangladesh, China, Egypt, Indonesia, Malaysia, Pakistan, Peru, Philippines, Portugal, Sri Lanka, Thailand, and Vietnam.

We screened 1,200 elite lines for the ability to grow well on zinc-deficient soils in a concrete tank in the screenhouse at two sites in the Philippines. Many rices were severely injured but IR30, IR34, and others performed well without added zinc. In other countries, several IRRI rices that are tolerant to phosphorus deficiency and iron toxicity were identified.

Deep water and flood tolerance. Rices from across the world's deep water regions and from the Thai and IRRI programs are being tested in Thailand through the Thai-IRRI Cooperative Deep Water Rice Research Project, established in late 1974.

The Thai-IRRI project will serve a vast region that has been bypassed by the new rice technology (fig. 18): from 20 to 30 percent of the world's riceland is

18. a) The water becomes too deep during the monsoon season for the semidwarf varieties to grow on from 20 to 30 percent of the world's riceland. Farmers grow tall varieties in such low-lying areas as parts of Orissa state, India. b) A farmer navigating a boat through fields of floating rice in Bangladesh. The floating rices grow in water from 1 to 6 meters deep on about 10 percent of the world's riceland. These varieties have the genetic ability to elongate with rising water, escaping submergence. c) Some rices from flood-prone areas can survive total submergence for at least a week. If incorporated into improved varieties, such submergence tolerance would provide flood insurance for millions of farmers. Screening rices for the ability to withstand submergence are (left) Dr. Benito S. Vergara, IRRI plant physiologist, and (right) Ms. Aurora Mazaredo, research assistant.

planted to tall varieties in water that is too deep for the semidwarfs, and another 10 percent is planted to floating rices, primarily in the densely populated river valleys and deltas of Bangladesh, India, Burma, Cambodia, Thailand, and Vietnam, and along rivers in West Africa. The floating rices can grow in water from 1 to 6 meters deep because their stems elongate as the water deepens.

Floating rices are being crossed with semidwarf and intermediate-statured varieties to produce progeny with better plant characteristics, plus the ability to grow in water too deep for our present semidwarfs.

Some rices from flood-prone regions can survive total submergence for at least a week. Such submergence tolerance, if incorporated into semidwarf varieties, would be good flood insurance for farmers everywhere (fig. 18).

Through the IRRI-Thai Deep Water Project, outstanding breeding and testing materials with deep water- and flood-tolerant characteristics are being distributed to collaborating scientists to test as farmer varieties or to use in their own breeding programs.

The Rockefeller Foundation provides a plant breeder as team leader and IRRI has stationed a core staff member in Thailand to assist with field screening.

Floating varieties produce few panicles because their tiller number is low, and the tillers spread out. We found that Matiamon 73/23 from Bangladesh has good elongation ability, erect tillers, and intermediate tillering capacity.

The adventitious roots at the upper nodes of floating rices seem to absorb nutrients from floodwaters, although we do not yet fully understand this mechanism. Using a new screening procedure developed in Thailand, we found that nodal rooting ability differs greatly among floating varieties. Because more extensive development of such roots before flowering would probably favor plant growth, we conducted tests to determine if increased rooting capacity can be incorporated into improved varieties.

More than 500 varieties from the IRRI germ plasm collection and 231 breeding lines were screened in deep water tanks at IRRI for the ability to elongate with rising water. The 35 varieties with the best elongation ability all came from Bangladesh. In Thailand, 35 F₂ and F₃ bulk progenies and 2,000 F₃ and F₄ lines were tested in deep water in farmers' fields and in artificial ponds.

We have screened 1,446 varieties at IRRI for tolerance to submergence; most of the tolerant varieties are from Sri Lanka.

We twice subjected 39 lines from Thailand to the submergence test and selected six with high survival rates that yielded well without lodging (Table 9). Only

Table 9. Outstanding lines from Thailand that were found to have good submergence tolerance both in Thailand and in the Philippines. IRRI, 1975 wet season.

Line ^a	Performance						
	Plant ht (cm)	Growth duration (days)	Yield (t/ha)	Lodging ^b	Panicles (no./hill)	Panicle wt (g)	Submergence survival (%)
BKN-6986-105-P	122	110	4.5	3	9	2.5	87
-160-P	121	110	5.0	1	9	2.5	98
-133-4-P	115	113	4.4	1	10	2.2	93
BKN-6987-118-3-P	122	110	5.2	1	11	2.8	75
-133-2-P	110	105	5.5	1	9	2.8	80
-223-2-P	114	105	5.4	1	9	2.5	62

^aBKN-6986 = IR262/Pin Gaew 56; BKN-6987 = IR262/Khao Nahng Nuey 11. ^bRated according to the Standard Evaluation System for Rice: Scale 1 = no lodging; 9 = completely lodged.

19. Seedlings being screened in special cold-water tanks at IRRI to identify materials that are tolerant to low temperature. Dr. Benito S. Vergara (right), IRRI plant physiologist, examining seedlings with Alioune Coly, research scholar from Senegal.

BKN-6986-105-P and BKN-6986-160-P, however, were resistant to tungro. Like IR442 and T442, these two lines can elongate in deep water.

In 1975, we crossed numerous floating and tall varieties with elite lines in Thailand and at IRRI to incorporate elongation ability and submergence tolerance into semidwarf and intermediate-statured rices with disease and insect resistance.

We found no strong association between elongation ability and the ability to survive total submergence in floating rices tested under natural field conditions in Thailand.

To select for the semidwarf plant type, we planted under lowland conditions 90 F_2 selections from IRRI whose ancestry includes at least one deep-water or submergence-tolerant variety. The lines selected will later go into severe elongation and submergence screening.

We have both photoperiod-sensitive and nonsensitive lines that are now in the F_7 generation. They have been tested for elongation in deep water for 3 years and were entered in preliminary yield trials and reselected for uniformity of height and maturity. We plan to enter some in international deep water observational nurseries in 1976.

Seedling growth of some semidwarf lines during the first 30 days is as rapid as that of floating rices. This may help farmers who complain that seedlings of most semidwarfs are too short.

Seed for a collaborative experiment on the flowering dates of deep-water rices was distributed to seven countries. Scientists can use comparisons as a basis for requesting seeds of new lines from other deep-water research stations.

Temperature tolerance. *Cold tolerance.* To increase production in areas of cold temperature, farmers need tolerant varieties that mature early and yield well. To develop such varieties, screening techniques must be determined for each growth stage of rice, since cold tolerance at one stage does not necessarily mean tolerance at others.

In 1975 we used new techniques recently developed at IRRI to screen 8,628 entries in the IRRI germ plasm bank. Only six indica types were found tolerant

Table 10. Six indica varieties were found tolerant of cold temperature in a screening of 8,628 varieties.^a IRRI, 1975.

Variety	Source	Spikelet sterility (%)
Pratao	Brazil	8
HR 33	India	14
C 21	Philippines	25
Leng Kwang	China	27
Azucena	Philippines	30
Do Do	Korea	31

^a Tolerance based on leaf color at seedling stage, and growth duration, plant height, and spikelet sterility at harvest. Sterility determined after screening at low temperature regimes in the IRRI phytotron.

to low temperature using as evidence of tolerance growth duration, plant height at maturity, spikelet sterility at harvest, and leaf color when screened in cold-water tanks at seedling stage (fig. 19, Table 10). They are being further evaluated and crossed with improved varieties that are resistant to blast and bacterial blight diseases, and that have good grain quality.

We evaluated more than 1,000 pedigree lines and grew 12 F₂ bulk populations under cold conditions in the mountains of northern Luzon, Philippines.

Seed of promising rices has been distributed to cooperators in national programs, mostly through the International Rice Cold Tolerance Nursery.

On the ancient Ifugao rice terraces of Banaue, Philippines, about 600 IRCTN entries from cold regions of 10 nations and from IRRI were screened in collaboration with the Philippine Bureau of Plant Industry. We also selected from about 1,300 pedigree-nursery rows, and from 11 F₂ populations of crosses between outstanding cold-tolerant parents and elite GEU lines.

An early-maturing line from a cross made by Indonesian scientists, Kn-1b-361-1-8, performed best under the unusually cold conditions of Banaue. It matures early, so farmers can grow two crops there, where they have traditionally grown only one because local varieties mature late. The Philippine Seed Board has named the Kn line as the variety RPKn-2 and is multiplying and distributing seeds to farmers in mountainous regions of the Philippines.

Heat tolerance. We have found that extremely high temperature causes sterility during the dry season in Thailand, Cambodia, Pakistan, Iran, Iraq, and Egypt. During 1975 we found that plants are most susceptible at heading (fig. 20). Thus, we know that heat-induced sterility differs in mechanism from cold-induced sterility, where the critical stage is at about 11 days before heading.

To determine how the duration of heat affects fertilization, we simulated varying periods of high temperature.

In the susceptible variety C4-63G we found that more than 4 hours daily of high temperature induces a high percentage of sterility. But with the relatively tolerant selection IR747B2-6, less than 8 hours of high temperature was not seriously detrimental. This explains why C4-63G suffers from heat-induced sterility in Thailand but not in the Philippines: in certain areas of Thailand, air temperature may be above 35°C for 4 hours or longer during the hottest months, while at Los Baños, air temperature goes as high as 35°C in April and May, but only for 1 or 2 hours a day.

We tested 68 varieties and selections in the IRRI phytotron for tolerance to heat-induced sterility. We found that tolerant and susceptible varieties differ

20. We found that rice plants are most susceptible to heat-induced sterility at heading stage in controlled studies in the IRRI phytotron. IRRI, 1975.

considerably in percent fertilization. Interestingly, all of the varieties that we found tolerant are upland rices, and six of the seven have been rated as resistant or moderately resistant to drought under field conditions. This suggests that a common mechanism may in part control tolerance to both high temperature and desiccation. Preliminary observations indicate that high temperature disturbs the opening of the anthers.

Protein content. The two objectives of the GEU protein team are to raise the protein content of improved rice varieties by at least 2 percentage points (from about 7% to about 9%) and to determine the nutritional utility and other aspects of increased protein.

The most promising experimental line for which we have long-term data is IR2153-338-3. It has consistently produced 9 percent protein and yielded about as well as IR8 in four tests conducted over 2 years at three nitrogen levels (Table 11). This increase of 1 percentage point represents 13 percent more protein in milled rice. The nutritional value of the protein of IR2153-388-3 rice was as predicted from its amino acid score.

We continued to use a modified diallele breeding scheme to concentrate genetic factors for protein content along with resistance to major diseases and insects. We found that higher protein content is less associated with lower grain yield in our progeny lines than in their parents. We have identified 14 progeny lines that have higher levels of protein than their parents.

We are continuing biological tests to determine the effect of replacing rice of average protein content with high-protein rice, particularly on growing children, who have high protein requirements. We replaced IR8 (7.5% protein) with IR480-5-9 (11.4%) in preschool Filipino children fed weaning diets of milled rice and dehulled mung bean and of rice and fish. We found that the amount of nitrogen retained with IR480 was higher—which means that the extra protein was used in body growth (fig. 21).

A cooperative study in Manila on three preschool Filipino children showed that the apparent digestibility of the protein in pearled wheat was 88 percent while that in milled rice was 78 percent. Other findings in Peru and Guatemala have been similar. But in growing rats, we have found that the true digestibility of rice protein is almost 100 percent, while that of raw wheat is about 90 percent. We are studying possible causes for the lower digestibility of rice protein in humans.

Table 11. Brown rice protein content and rough rice yield of varieties and lines grown during four seasons (mean of three nitrogen levels). IRRI, 1974-75.

Designation	1974 dry season		1974 wet season		1975 dry season		1975 wet season	
	Protein (%)	Yield (t/ha)						
IR8	8.1	4.6	7.8	4.8	7.7	5.5	7.4	5.2
IR26	7.7	7.3	8.0	5.2	7.7	6.1	8.0	4.9
IR480-5-9	9.3	5.2	8.7	3.9	8.5	4.5	8.9	3.7
IR2153-338-3	9.1	6.8	8.7	4.8	8.9	3.7	9.1	4.1

We continued to study aspects of protein accumulation in the developing rice grain. We found that high-protein rices have more ribonucleic acid complexes and protein bodies than low-protein rices. Three types of protein bodies, and little or no matrix protein, were observed in the endosperm of high-protein rices after 6 days or more after flowering. Changes in the amino acid composition and electrophoretic patterns of albumin and globulin were also studied. Both accumulated in the developing grain up to 12 days after flowering.

Eighty percent of rice protein is made up of glutelin. We have developed methods to characterize this protein fraction, which contributes so significantly to the nutritional quality of milled rice. Varietal differences in the relative amounts of the three polypeptide subunits of glutelin encourage us to further study the properties of glutelin in rices that differ widely in protein content, and in lysine content of protein.

International Rice Testing Program. The International Rice Testing Program (IRTP) was initiated early in 1975 to develop and formalize a network of scientists working with diverse germ plasm under a wide range of agroclimatic and cultural conditions. The United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) made funds available to help initiate and coordinate the program.

The IRTP was developed as an integral evaluation component of each nation's rice improvement program and of IRRI's Genetic Evaluation and Utilization (GEU) program. Leading local scientists coordinate the nurseries within each country. IRRI's GEU scientists also help develop the nurseries and provide overall

21. The amount of nitrogen retained in preschool Filipino children was higher when a low-protein rice, IR8, was replaced with a high-protein rice, IR480-5-9, in weaning diets of milled rice and mung bean and of rice and fish. This means that the extra protein was used in body growth. IRRI, 1975.

Table 12. During its first year of operation, the International Rice Testing Program prepared 457 nursery sets of the best rices from national programs and from the IRRI GEU program and distributed them to scientists around the world to test under their local conditions. IRRI, 1975.

Problem-area nursery	Sets sent to each region (no.)							Total
	E. Asia	SE Asia	S. Asia	W. Asia and N. Africa	Sub-Sahara Africa	Latin America	N. America, Europe, and Oceania	
					<i>Yield</i>			
Early lowland	2	14	23	4	4	8	—	55
Intermediate lowland	—	10	20	—	4	7	—	41
Upland	—	13	12	1	7	4	—	37
					<i>Observational</i>			
Lowland	2	21	37	9	14	8	1	93
Upland	—	16	12	1	16	4	—	49
					<i>Diseases</i>			
Blast	3	8	15	3	8	10	1	48
Sheath blight	3	7	5	—	1	—	—	16
Tungro	2	6	8	—	2	—	—	18
					<i>Insects</i>			
Brown planthopper	3	6	8	—	3	—	1	21
Gall midge	—	5	12	—	3	—	—	18
					<i>Environmental stresses</i>			
Salinity	1	7	10	1	3	—	—	22
Cold tolerance	4	12	14	1	3	1	2	39
Total (no.)	20	125	176	20	68	42	6	457
Total (%)	4	27	39	4	15	9	2	100

coordination. The testing and utilization of breeding materials and varieties from the IRRI germ plasm bank and from national programs are integrated into local GEU-type programs.

During IRTP's first year, we prepared and disseminated 457 sets of 12 different problem-area nurseries (Table 12); conducted five regional monitoring programs; initiated the GEU training program; and established communication links with country coordinators, scientists, and cooperators.

The joint coordinators, a plant pathologist stationed at IRRI and a plant breeder stationed in Indonesia with the IRRI-Central Research Institute for Agriculture team at Bogor, worked with 56 national coordinators and contact scientists in 44 countries.

IRRI coordinates the IRTP, but the policies and programs were cooperatively developed with rice scientists from various countries.

The program and the distribution of nurseries are oriented both regionally and nationally. Particular emphasis is on Asia, where most of the world's rice is grown. Attention is given to areas where existing semidwarf rices do not grow well because of environmental stresses, such as drought, cold, or injurious soils.

In 1975, we prepared and disseminated 12 types of international nursery sets: yield, 3; observational, 2; diseases, 3; insects, 2; and environmental stresses, 2. Thirty-five percent of the entries originated from the national programs, 49 percent from IRRI's breeding program, and 16 percent from the germ plasm bank.

Most nurseries were sent to Asia, but many went to Africa and Latin America and a few to Oceania, North America, and Europe (Table 12). We tried to disperse the yield and observational nurseries widely so that they would be thoroughly tested in diverse agroclimatic regions. The problem-area nurseries, such as the International Rice Gall Midge Nursery and the International Rice Tungro Nursery, were particularly concentrated in "hot spots," or areas where particular

22. Bert de la Rosa, IRRI research assistant, instructs participants in the GEU training course on how to prepare inoculum for bacterial blight inoculation. From left to right: A. Islam, Bangladesh; W. Seetanun, Thailand; N. Gopalan, India; U. O. Kjaw, Burma; A. Vivekanandan, Sri Lanka; S. Amonsilpa, Thailand; B. Thomas, India; E. Soetarwo, Indonesia; Soetjijto, Indonesia; P. Yogaratanam, Sri Lanka; N. Supapoj, Thailand; M. Abdulhamid, Indonesia; and P. Waranimman, Thailand.

stress problems are prevalent and where local scientists hope to develop varieties that are resistant to the stresses.

Through the regional monitoring program, teams of scientists from national programs and from IRRI jointly visited nurseries within regions and observed firsthand how varieties and lines from their national programs perform under different stresses and climatic conditions.

The GEU Training Program was initiated in 1975 to provide dedicated interdisciplinary teams of scientists with additional experience and diverse germ plasm needed to develop improved varieties for local farmers. Sixteen trainees from six countries attended the first GEU course (fig. 22).

The IRTP endeavored to develop an effective communication system to monitor the needs and interests of country coordinators and local cooperators, and to supply them with the appropriate nurseries and information.

A 64-page booklet, *Standard Evaluation System for Rice*, was developed by participants in the planning sessions to provide guidelines for evaluating the various traits in the nurseries on a uniform scale of 0–9. Copies have been sent to all IRTP cooperators.

We initiated an IRTP data management system to rapidly collect and analyze test results and report them to scientists in the national programs. Special color-coded fieldbooks were designed for each nursery. We supplied background information for each entry so that cooperators could closely watch promising materials. This encourages cooperators to cross elite entries with local materials during the first nursery season, shortening the time required to develop new varieties.

Diffusion of genetic materials and objectives of rice breeders in India. Through analysis of breeding records and in-depth interviews, we traced the flow of rice genetic materials among collaborating Indian research stations, through three periods over a decade: 1965–67, 1970–71, and 1974–75. We also determined

23. a) Indian rice breeders used Taichung Native 1 and IR8 intensively in the mid-1960's, but they had largely switched to locally developed semidwarfs and improved IRRI lines by 1974-75. b) Ninety-four percent of the local semidwarfs were progenies of IR8 or TN1. Analysis of 336 rices used as parents in 158 randomly selected crosses, 10 experiment stations, India, 1975.

breeding objectives of 1974-75 crosses as part of a collaborative project with Iowa State University, U.S.A., partially funded by The Rockefeller Foundation.

Diffusion of gene sources. We randomly selected and analyzed 44 crosses from the 1965-67 breeding records and 68 crosses from the 1970-71 records at seven state- and national-level research centers. For 1971-75, we analyzed 44 crosses made at 10 centers.

We found that 82 percent of the 1965-67 crosses involved at least one semidwarf parent. TN1 was used in 41 percent of the crosses; IR8, in 27 percent; and IRRI rices other than IR8, in 14 percent (fig. 23). No locally developed semidwarfs were found in the 1965-67 sample.

The percentage of total crosses that involved semidwarfs increased to 91 percent in 1970-71, and leveled off through 1974-75. By the early 1970's, the direct use of TN1 as a parent in crosses had dropped to 10 percent, and to 7 percent by 1974-75. The use of IR8 as a parent dropped 1 percent over the first 5 years, but then dropped 17 percent by 1974-75. The use of semidwarf materials from other countries increased slightly.

While other IRRI materials were used increasingly by 1974-75, locally developed semidwarfs were even more popular. They were used in almost half of the crosses by 1970-71 and in 61 percent by 1974-75. Fifty-five percent of local semidwarfs used in 1974-75 were progenies of IR8, and 39 percent of TN1 (9 percent involved both) (fig. 23).

Seventy-seven percent of the crosses in 1965-67 involved a tall parent, but only 48 percent in 1974-75. The use of intermediate-statured parents declined from 45 percent in 1965-67 to 18 percent in 1974-75. Indica formed 79 percent of the

24. The major objectives for which rice breeders made 46 randomly selected crosses in 1974–75. Ten agricultural experiment stations, India, 1975.

total parent material in the mid-1960's; 10 years later, it made up 96 percent. The use of japonicas and ponlais declined over the decade. Fifty-seven percent of the total parents were hybrids in 1965–67, and 74 percent in 1974–75.

Thus, we conclude that by the mid-1970's, the original stiff-strawed varieties were being phased out of the breeding programs as parents, but that they continued to live on through a wide range of progeny. Rice breeders have incorporated their best genetic traits into newer rices better suited to local conditions.

Breeding objectives. Yield potential was cited as a primary breeding objective for making 89 percent of the crosses; fertilizer response was a breeding objective of 80 percent; and resistance to lodging, of 80 percent (fig. 24). Semidwarfs were almost invariably used as genetic sources of these traits. Grain quality was an objective of 69 percent of the crosses. Seventy-three percent of the times that tall varieties were used, the breeders hoped to transfer a preferred type of grain into the progeny; semidwarfs were used only 49 percent for the purpose. We found that 82 percent of the semidwarfs used for grain quality were locally developed, further indicating that introduced semidwarfs were often crossed with local rices to develop high-yielding varieties with acceptable grain quality. Forty-three percent of the crosses involved resistance to at least one disease, and 37 percent involved insect resistance. Resistance to blast, bacterial blight, and tungro virus were the most frequent disease objectives. Brown planthopper and gall midge resistance were the most common insect objectives. Drought tolerance was sought in only 9% of the crosses; cold tolerance, in 9%; tolerance to waterlogged soils, in 7%; and tolerance to deep water, in 2%. Tall or intermediate-statured parents were used as donors for most of these traits.

Disease control. We identified several chemicals that effectively controlled sheath blight and increased yields of the susceptible line IR1487-372-1 by from 15 to 22 percent. But chemical protection did not increase yields of the moderately resistant variety IR26. This indicates that even moderate levels of sheath blight resistance substantially lower yield losses.

Some of the chemicals controlled *Cercospora* leaf spot as well as sheath blight, but none controlled leaf smut in the field. In upland rice, chemical control of panicle blast increased yields significantly. As foliar sprays, most chemicals controlled leaf blast for only about a week.

Incidence of tungro disease was low and scattered in Luzon during 1975—so was the population of its leafhopper vectors, *Nephotettix virescens*, *N. nigropictus*, and *Recilia dorsalis*. The percentage of vector insects that were infective was also low. Tungro incidence averaged only 3.6 percent on the highly susceptible line IR1561-228-3, which occupied about 40 percent of the study fields.

Although we found that yearly incidence of grassy stunt virus paralleled the yearly number of its vector, the brown planthopper, caught in light traps at the IRRI farm over 4 years, we found no close relationship between tungro incidence and the number of its leafhopper vectors collected (Table 13).

Using cages, we found that tungro infection of seedlings increased markedly as the number of viruliferous insects increased from 0 to 1 per seedling, but that infection increased only slightly when insect numbers increased from 1 to 3 per seedling (fig. 25).

Using the distance that a green leafhopper can travel and the duration that a viruliferous insect remains infective, we estimated that without a strong wind, tungro can be carried no more than 250 meters from a diseased to a healthy plant.

We found that tungro vectors retained the virus much longer at low than at high temperatures and as long as 22 days at 13°C. Because this makes the term “nonresistant virus” no longer appropriate, we have suggested a new term to describe the virus-vector relationship—“transitory leafhopper-borne virus.”

Blast infection is usually lower in flooded than in upland fields. We placed pots of flooded rice in an upland field, simulating lowland rice in an upland environment. The flooded plants were infected to the same degree as upland

Table 13. Incidence of grassy stunt virus disease was closely paralleled by the numbers of its brown planthopper vector captured in light traps, but no correlation was found between incidence of tungro virus disease and the numbers of its leafhopper vectors. IRRI farm, 1972-75.

Year	Insects (no./collection)	Infective insects (%)	Disease incidence
<i>Brown planthopper/grassy stunt virus</i>			
1972	4213	2.30	High
1973	8279	2.51	Very high
1974	1180	1.47	Moderate
1975	276	0.75	Trace
<i>Leafhopper vectors^a/tungro virus disease</i>			
1972	2741	0.39	Trace
1973	458	1.53	Trace
1974	1881	3.17	Trace
1975	849	2.20	Trace

^aIncludes three species: *Nephotettix virescens*, *N. nigropictus*, and *Recilia dorsalis*.

25. Tungro infection increased markedly as the numbers of its viruliferous green leafhopper vector, *Nephotettix virescens*, increased from 0 to 1 per seedling, but leveled off at higher rates. Variety, Taichung Native 1. IRRI, 1975.

plants. This indicates that the microclimate of upland rice, particularly the dew period or the duration of leaf wetness, affects the incidence of blast.

We also found that spacing rice plants closer in lowland fields encouraged the development and spread of blast disease because it lengthened the dew period (fig. 26).

26. Experiments on the spacing of rice hills showed that blast disease spreads more rapidly at closer spacing, primarily because the duration of dew period, or leaf wetness, is lengthened. Setting instruments to sample spores and to measure dew period, temperature, and relative humidity at the IRRI farm is Mohammed Ibrahim El Refaei, research fellow from Egypt.

Insect control. We evaluated new insecticides in the laboratory, greenhouse, and field during 1975. We found that a new group of insecticides, the synthetic pyrethrins or "pyrethroids," effectively controlled both green leafhoppers and brown planthoppers in laboratory tests. But their acceptance in rice culture may be hampered by their high toxicity to fish.

The rice bug is a serious pest across the rice-growing world. It reduces yields by sucking the sap from the developing grain. Foliar sprays are required to control this subtle but destructive pest. We identified two insecticides with adequate residual activity to control rice bugs for 7 days after spraying.

We tested several methods of applying insecticide to find ways to increase the efficiency of use and decrease costs. We previously found that soaking the roots of seedlings overnight in an insecticidal solution controlled green leafhoppers for a few weeks at most after transplanting. But by dipping the roots in a mixture of gelatin, water, and insecticide, we controlled green leafhoppers and tungro virus for the entire season.

We tested several new machines to speed the placement of insecticide into the rice root zone and evaluated several chemicals applied with the machines. A simple liquid injector was the most efficient machine (fig. 27). Plots that received root-zone treatments yielded three times more than those where insecticide was broadcast once, and 1.5 times more than plots that were sprayed four times. The root-zone treatment effectively controlled whorl maggot, stem borer, and green leafhopper.

We found that rates as low as 0.5 kg/ha of carbofuran applied into the root zone controlled green leafhoppers, the vector of tungro virus, as well as did 1.5 kg/ha conventionally applied.

27. a) A simple liquid injector was developed at IRRI to speed the placement of insecticide into the rice root zone where it is used more efficiently. b) Plots that received insecticide through the root-zone treatment yielded three times more than plots where insecticide was broadcast once. IRRI, 1975.

Table 14. Effect of leaf damage by the rice whorl maggot *Hydrellia philippina* during the first 32 days after transplanting on variety IR26 (transplanted at 25- × 25-cm row spacing). Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center and Visayas Rice Experiment Station, Philippines, 1975 wet season.

Insecticide treatment ^a	Yield ^b (t/ha)	Yield loss (%)
<i>Maligaya</i>		
Throughout crop period	5.9 a	—
Only after 32 DT	4.4 b	26
<i>Visayas</i>		
Throughout crop period	6.0 a	—
Only after 32 DT	5.3 b	12

^aIn the continuously treated plots, carbofuran was applied at 2 kg a.i./ha to the seedbed at 5 and 15 days after seeding and to the transplanted field at 1 and 17 days after transplanting (DT). All plots in the experiment were treated with carbofuran at 2 kg a.i./ha at 33 DT and every 16 days thereafter until harvest. ^bMeans in the same column followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Table 15. Loss of grain weight caused by simulated^a stem borer damage in the field at 40, 60, and 80 days after seeding (DS). Variety, IR26. IRRI, 1975 dry season.

Damaged tillers (%)	Grain wt ^b (g/2 hills)	Grain wt reduction (%)
<i>Damaged at 40 DS</i>		
0	73 a	—
5	70 a	5
10	70 a	5
15	58 b	21
<i>Damaged at 60 DS</i>		
0	77 a	—
2	68 b	11
6	60 c	22
<i>Damaged at 80 DS</i>		
0	78 a	—
2	66 b	16
6	63 bc	20

^aDead hearts or white heads were caused by killing the growing point of tillers with a needle. ^bMeans in the same column followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

In biological control studies, we found that the predaceous spider *Lycosa pseudoannulata* killed more nymphs of brown planthoppers than nymphs of green leafhoppers, and preyed on first-instar larvae of the yellow rice borer. Parasitoids killed about half of the yellow borer eggs at IRRI. Weekly spraying of the insecticide metalkamate (Bux) did not affect the percentage of parasitism of stem borer eggs in the field.

We measured the yield losses due to insect damage. Whorl maggot damage decreased yields from 12 to 26 percent in crops planted at 25- × 25-cm spacing at two Philippine locations (Table 14). Simulated stem borer damage in the field indicated that about 10 percent dead hearts is the economic threshold for the Philippines in a 40-day-old crop (Table 15). After 60 days from seeding, an economic threshold based on plant damage by borers is probably no longer practical and prophylactic treatments may be needed.

A density of one rice bug per 35 panicles from flowering to harvest in a greenhouse cage reduced grain weight by 14 percent. The economic threshold may be less than four rice bugs per square meter for a good crop in the Philippines.

28. Density of rice whorl maggot, *Hydrellia philippina*, on the variety IR30 transplanted at a spacing of 25 x 25 cm. IRRI, 1975 wet season.

In ecological studies, we found that the peak oviposition period of the rice whorl maggot was about 30 to 40 days after transplanting. The peak in larval density, at 30 days, roughly corresponded to the peak in leaf damage (fig. 28).

One distinct generation of the yellow rice borer was found early in the crop period with a peak in eggs at 3–14 days after transplanting, in larvae at 35–40 days, and in pupae at 50–60 days. Egg mortality, primarily due to parasitism, was always high.

The striped rice borer had one major generation during the latter half of the crop period, with a peak in egg density at about 60 days after transplanting and a larval density at about 70–80 days. Pupal density peaked beyond 80 days after transplanting.

Collaborators at the Tropical Products Institute, London, identified and synthesized female sex pheromones of the striped rice borer and of the pink borer. In IRRI field tests, the striped rice borer pheromones at a concentration of 100 μg per vial often attracted more wild male moths than did live virgin females. The synthetic pheromones remained attractive for more than 1 month (fig. 29).

In the IRRI phytotron, we found that the highest number of brown plant-hopper nymphs developed when constant relative humidity ranged from 50 to 60 percent.

Weed control. The judicious use of chemicals to help control weeds can increase the productivity of riceland without putting people out of work because most ricefields are not adequately weeded, even in labor-surplus regions.

Even so, chemicals must give better weed control that is as cheap as hand weeding to be successful in areas where wages are less than \$1 per day.

We are developing chemical-based systems of weed management that include hand weeding to minimize the buildup of herbicide-tolerant weeds. In a recent survey, we found that progressive farmers in Laguna province often combine

29. Female pheromones, or sex attractants, for the striped rice borer and the pink borer have been identified and synthesized by collaborators at the Tropical Products Institute, London, U.K. a) IRRI scientists tested the synthesized pheromones in covered water-oil traps in fields at the IRRI farm. The nightly catch of male striped borer moths using the pheromones as attractants was compared with that using live virgin females. Left, Dr. V. Arnold Dyck, IRRI associate entomologist; right, Dr. E. A. Heinrichs, entomologist. b) The synthetic sex pheromones trapped more male moths than the live virgin females. Blank traps caught nothing. Average of two locations at IRRI, 1975.

the use of chemical and manual weed control. We are also developing better methods of hand, biological, and mechanical weed control.

In transplanted and direct-seeded flooded rice, the herbicide MON 0358 continued to look outstanding at IRRI and at three Philippine Bureau of Plant Industry (BPI) stations. In transplanted rice, MON 0358 applied at 4 days after transplanting gave excellent weed control (fig. 30).

New herbicides were screened under rainfed lowland and upland conditions at IRRI and, subsequently, through advanced international trials. NTN 5810/KUE 2079a, Prefar/MCPA, and WL 29226 appeared promising for rainfed transplanted and direct-seeded rice; Antor, RH 2915, and U 44-344 looked good for upland rice.

In six Filipino farmers' fields, two hand weeding gave yields significantly higher than preemergence application of granules of 2,4-D, the most popular herbicide in the Philippines (6.1 vs. 5.6 t/ha).

But one 2,4-D treatment was much cheaper. In fact, chemical control cost less than even one hand weeding, and at least two hand weeding were necessary to adequately remove weeds (fig. 31).

International herbicide testing continued to increase in popularity (Table 16).

In weed management studies, we increased the weed-competitive ability of semidwarf varieties and boosted yields by 30 percent by spacing plants closer—at 15 × 15 cm rather than at the common 25- × 25-cm spacing. We observed no varietal differences in weed-competitive ability, but IR28 lodged at closer spacing.

We found that we could shift the weed community from perennial weeds that

30. The herbicide MON 0358 applied to IR26 rice at 4 days after transplanting gave grain yields similar to those of two hand weedings (av. of four experiments at IRRI, and Philippine Bureau of Plant Industry stations at Nueva Ecija, Bicol, and Visayas). 1975 dry and wet seasons.

are difficult to control such as *Scirpus maritimus* to easier controlled annual weeds through various practices of crop and soil management (Table 17).

IRRIGATION
AND WATER
MANAGEMENT

Irrigation water management has now been established as a separate research program to study the economic, engineering, and agronomic aspects of water use.

Analysis of Philippine data from 1950 to 1974 shows that most of the increase in rice production through the 1950's came through the expansion of farm land. But during the 1960's, the opening of new land proceeded at a much slower rate, and most of the increased production stemmed from higher yields per hectare. We found that an increase in irrigation facilities made most of the intensification

31. The cost of 2,4-D herbicide for weed control is even less than that of one hand weeding; two hand weedings are required for adequate weed control. The Philippine data are computed using the fixed exchange rate of US\$1 = P7. IRRI, 1975.

Table 16. More than 200 sets of herbicide trials were shipped to scientists in 21 nations for International Cooperative Weed Control Experiments in upland, direct-seeded, and transplanted rice during 1975.

Country	Sets (no.)
Burma	2
Ecuador	1
Egypt	3
Fiji Islands	10
Ghana	2
Guyana	2
India	131
Indonesia	6
Iraq	3
Iran	4
Korea	3
Liberia	20
Malawi	3
Malaysia	3
Nepal	18
Nigeria	1
Pakistan	4
Saudi Arabia	1
Sri Lanka	3
Taiwan	1
Tanzania	1
Total	222

possible. The government invested more heavily in irrigation during those years when the ratio of benefits to costs was favorable, and as new land for cultivation became increasingly scarce.

Because the modern rices produce more than traditional varieties in irrigated areas, their spread increased the rate of return to irrigation investment. Had no modern varieties been available in the Philippines, the benefit: cost ratio of irrigation would have been lower and irrigation systems would have expanded at a much slower rate (fig. 32, dotted lines). Thus, while irrigation is often considered essential for the new rices to express their full yield potential, the new varieties themselves have stimulated considerable irrigation construction.

We studied farmers' application of nitrogen in relation to their expectancy of drought, and measured yields and determined efficient levels of nitrogen use on 3,000 ha of an irrigation command area during the 1974 dry season. We measured actual days of drought in farmers' fields and compared the measurements with farmers' estimates of the number of years in 10 for which they anticipated major drought. Variation was considerable among farms, but nitrogen use and grain yield were lower for those farmers who considered serious drought to be more likely (Table 18).

Table 17. By changing cropping patterns, the weed population was shifted from difficult-to-control perennial to easily controlled annual weeds. IRRI, 1975.

Season	Weeds (no./sq m)		
	Annuals ^a	Perennials	
		<i>Scirpus maritimus</i>	<i>Cyperus rotundus</i>
<i>Lowland rice followed by lowland rice</i>			
Dry	725	406	0
Wet	340	325	0
<i>Corn + mung bean followed by lowland rice</i>			
Dry	1008	36	32
Wet	364	167	0
<i>Corn followed by dry-seeded rainfed banded rice</i>			
Dry	2386	35	53
Wet	1463	20	33

^aGrasses, broadleaved weeds, and sedges.

32. Irrigable areas of National Irrigation Administration for which construction was initiated (3-year moving averages), index of current prices for Thai export rice and Philippine domestic rice (1950 = 100), and benefit-to-cost ratios of new NIA systems (current prices and 3-year moving averages), with and without modern varieties, by year, Philippines, 1950-1974.

Optimum levels of nitrogen use depend partly on the adequacy of water for the growing crop. Through controlled experiments in the irrigation command area, we computed optimum rates of N use for each drought-year category. We found that the optimum rates were about double the mean rates actually used, and that N use increased significantly for farms where drought expectancy was low. About 10 percent of farmers in each drought group applied N near the optimum levels.

If all farmers in the area had applied N at the optimum rates, average yields would have increased from 2.4 to 2.8 t/ha, or 19 percent. If the expected adequacy

Table 18. Mean grain yield and nitrogen use for farms in different drought-frequency groups (years of serious drought in ten). Three thousand hectares of the service area of Lateral C, Peñaranda River Irrigation System, Gapan, Nueva Ecija Province, 1974 dry season.

Drought frequency (years/10)	Yield (t/ha)	Nitrogen use (kg N/ha)	Observations (no.)
0	2.43 a	45.2 a	130
1-2	2.39 ab	42.5 a	66
3-6	2.34 ab	38.6 a	17
7-10	2.03 b	39.1 a	13

In the same column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 0.05 level.

Table 19. Mean rates of nitrogen use and grain yield from farmers' current practices and yields if optimum levels of nitrogen were used and if water were adequate. Lateral C, Peñaranda River Irrigation System, Gapan, Nueva Ecija province, 1974 dry season.

Item	Level		
	Farmer's	Optimum	
		Nitrogen only	Nitrogen and water
Nitrogen use (kg/ha)	44	97	133
Grain yield (t/ha)	2.4	2.8	4.2

of water were improved to the level where no drought was expected, then optimum use of N would increase mean yields by 22 percent. But if moisture stress were entirely eliminated, then optimum use of N would increase yields to 4.2 t/ha, or 75 percent higher than current yields (Table 19). The data indicate that N recommendations should be flexible to meet different drought situations and that increased use of N will greatly increase yields only if drought is reduced.

We developed a technique to measure both lateral subsoil seepage and deep percolation (S&P) of water movement into rice soils. The new instrument consists simply of a meter stick placed above the paddy surface at an incline of 5:1. The technician reads it once a day and computes the difference in head, or elevation of water standing on the paddy. S&P is calculated by subtracting evapotranspiration (estimated from evaporation data) from the daily head loss on those days for which overland irrigation and drainage do not occur.

Fifteen instruments were placed in different portions of four strata based on the extent to which topsoil had been removed during land leveling the previous year. We found that the new technique gave measurements similar to those given by the older water balance technique. Mean S&P rates did not differ significantly in areas where topsoil had been removed to depths of less than 30 cm, but they more than doubled in areas cut deeper. This measurement technique appears promising because of its simplicity, low cost, and applicability to *in situ* soil conditions.

Nitrogen fixation. Nitrogen is essential for grain production. Although most nitrogen is added to the crop in the form of fertilizers, the air around us contains an unlimited supply.

Some crops, such as legumes, draw heavily on atmospheric nitrogen. IRRI scientists are searching for ways to increase the atmospheric nitrogen that is "fixed" in the soil of rice paddies to reduce the dependence of farmers on costly chemical fertilizers.

We found that yields had not declined detectably in plots where 23 successive crops of rice had been grown without fertilizer as part of IRRI's long-term fertility experiment. An *in situ* assay showed that the overall nitrogen-fixing activity of algae in nonfertilized plots was higher than that in fertilized plots, particularly near or after harvest.

Removing algae from the paddy water greatly reduced nitrogen fixation in the root zone of rice at the IRRI farm.

We isolated and classified 51 strains of bacteria that fix nitrogen under reduced oxygen pressure around rice roots and 18 that fix N under anaerobic conditions. Among these, *Enterobacta* was identified as a nitrogen fixer. The water fern

33. The water fern *Azolla* was found to fix as much as 1 kilogram of atmospheric nitrogen daily in ponds at IRRI. Left is Dr. Iwao Watanabe, IRRI soil microbiologist; right is Ms. Corazon Ramirez-Espinas, research assistant.

Azolla may be able to fix as much nitrogen as legumes; at IRRI it fixed as much as 1 kg N/ha daily (fig. 33).

Yields were increased significantly by the application of phosphorus at 30 kg/ha with no added nitrogen in eight out of 23 crops in a long-term fertility experiment. This increase averaged 0.53 t/ha over the past six harvests. But in plots that received adequate nitrogen, the crops responded to phosphorus only once in the 23 crops. These experiments confirm the suggestion of others that phosphorus stimulates biological fixation of nitrogen and is, therefore, an indirect supplier of nitrogen.

Nitrogen fixation was very low in soils of the ancient rice terraces at Banaue, Philippines, where Ifugao tribesmen have grown traditional rice varieties with no chemical fertilization for centuries. This suggests that modern rice varieties grown in these soils might respond markedly with nitrogen.

Fertilizer placement. We continued efforts to improve the efficiency of plant use of chemicals. Placing nitrogenous fertilizer in mudballs and inserting them into the root zone of the paddy can double the effect of the fertilizer. But so many mudballs are needed (62,500/ha) that the technique might be practical only in areas where landholdings are small and labor is plentiful.

To eliminate the process of making mudballs, the International Fertilizer Development Center (IFDC) at Muscle Shoals, Alabama, U.S.A., is developing super granules and briquets of varying doses of urea (fig. 34). IRRI agronomists tested them during the 1975 dry season and found that efficiency of fertilizer applied as briquets equalled that of mudballs (Table 20). In another experiment, placement of nitrogen by several methods increased yields significantly over the common broadcast-and-incorporation treatment in the intermediate-maturing variety IR26, but not in the early-maturing variety IR28. The efficiency of deep placement was greater for IR26 than for IR28.

We compared methods of applying fertilizer nitrogen in farmers' fields of clay, clay-loam, and loam soils in Central Luzon, Philippines, and at the IRRI farm (clay soil) during the 1975 dry season. In IR26, the mudball technique

34. To eliminate part of the excessively high labor requirements required to make and place the mudballs, the International Fertilizer Development Center (IFDC) at Muscle Shoals, Alabama, U. S. A., has formulated urea into briquets (center) and large granules (right).

yielded 0.5 t/ha more than the band placement and about 1.0 t/ha more than either the basal-incorporated or the split-dose treatment.

When 60 kg N/ha was applied as mudball, the average protein yields of brown rice of IR26 and IR28 were about as high as when 90 kg N/ha was applied in split doses (Table 21).

We evaluated combinations of fertilizer and insecticide placed into the root zone using Taichung Native 1 (TN1), which is highly susceptible to most insects and diseases, and IR30, which is broadly resistant.

With no fertilizer or insect control, TN1 yielded only 0.2 t/ha while IR30 yielded 1.9 t/ha. Both varieties responded to fertilizer application only when the insecticide was applied (fig. 35).

IRRI engineers have recently developed experimental applicators that place granular and liquid insecticide and fertilizer into the rice root zone (see fig. 30, 38, and 50).

We found that increasing the number of seedlings from one to five per hill reduced the adverse effects of submergence on yield.

Table 20. Yields of IR28 when nitrogen is applied at 56 and 112 kg N/ha as urea briquets, as mudballs, and in split doses. IRRI, 1975 dry season.

Application method	Yield ^a (t/ha)	
	56 kg N/ha	112 kg N/ha
Urea briquets	5.4 a	5.7 a
Mudballs	5.1 ab	5.7 a
Split application	4.4 b	5.2 ab
No nitrogen		3.4 c

^a Within a column, treatment means followed by the same letter, are not significantly different.

Table 21. The brown rice protein yield of 60 kg N/ha applied as mudballs was similar to that of 90 kg N/ha applied in split doses using IR26 and IR28 grown under lowland conditions. IRRI, 1975 dry season.

Method of nitrogen application	Rate (kg N/ha)	Increase in brown rice protein ^a (kg/ha)		
		IR26	IR28	Mean of fertilizer treatments ^b
Basal ^c	60	98	148	123 c
Split	60	104	144	124 c
Mudball	60	137	204	171 ab
Split ^d	90	152	231	192 a

^aOver no-fertilizer check. ^bWithin a column, treatment means followed by a common letter are not significantly different. ^c $\frac{2}{3}$ basal + $\frac{1}{3}$ at panicle initiation. ^d $\frac{1}{3}$ basal + $\frac{2}{3}$ at 5-7 days before panicle initiation.

Reducing soil toxicities. Iron toxicity may limit yields on 30 million hectares in Colombia, India, Liberia, Malaysia, Philippines, Senegal, Sri Lanka, Thailand, and Vietnam. Although the effects of iron toxicity on rice plants varied among soils, we found that adding organic matter to three acid soils reduced symptoms in a greenhouse study (Table 22). The organic matter seemed to accelerate reduction, increase pH, and decrease the concentration of water-soluble ferrous iron.

Peat soils cover from 20 to 30 million hectares in the tropics. We found that rice yields poorly on such soils because of deficiencies of nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, zinc, and copper. Although fertilizer corrected the deficiencies, the effects were greater on an airdried soil that had previously been submerged than on a continuously submerged soil.

35. IRRI scientists used a band applicator to place fertilizer and insecticide (carbofuran) into the root zone of Taichung Native 1 (TN1), a variety that is susceptible to insects and diseases, and IR30, a variety with considerable resistance. With neither fertilizer nor insect control, TN1 yielded only 0.2 t/ha, while the resistant IR30 yielded 1.9 t/ha. Both varieties responded to fertilizer application only when insecticide was applied. IRRI, 1975.

Table 22. Adding organic matter reduced the severity of iron toxicity on IR8 rice at from 1.5 to 6 weeks after transplanting in three acid soils. IRRI greenhouse, 1975.

Organic matter (%)	Severity ^a of iron toxicity		
	1.5 wk	2.5 wk	6.0 wk
0	3.1	4.8	4.8
0.15	2.5	4.3	3.9

^a0 = no symptoms; 9 = all plants dead.

Table 23. In transplanted variety E425, coating seeds with zinc oxide and applying zinc sulfate to the seeds with zinc oxide and applying zinc sulfate to the seedbed corrected zinc deficiency as well as dipping seedlings in zinc oxide suspension. IRRI, 1975.

Treatment	Grain yield ^a (g/pot)
No zinc	54 a
ZnO seedling dip	83 b
ZnO seed coating	75 b
ZnSO ₄ applied to seedbed	81 b

^aAny two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Zinc deficiency is a problem in calcareous soils and in continuously wet soils. Draining and drying the field is the most practical way to prevent zinc deficiency, but it is not always feasible. Dipping rice seedlings into a suspension of zinc oxide before transplanting is a common treatment in the Philippines. We found that zinc deficiency in transplanted rice could also be corrected by coating the seeds with zinc oxide at the rate of 1 percent of dry weight of seeds before sowing or by applying 50 kg ZnSO₄/ha to the seedbed (Table 23). These greenhouse results should be verified in the field.

We studied the influence of air temperature on rice yields through its effects on vegetative growth, panicle development, and ripening in the IRRI phytotron. Within a daily range of from 16° to 28°C, grains fill faster at higher temperatures. This shortens the grain filling period (fig. 36). At a mean temperature of 28°C, the upper grains of IR20 panicles mature in only 13 days, but IR20 takes 23 days to mature in fields at Los Baños. During the 10 additional days that it ordinarily takes to mature, the rest of the panicle emerges and the other spikelets flower.

For maximum grain weight, the optimum mean daily temperature is from 19° to 26°C for the indica variety IR20 and from 16° to 22°C for the japonica Fujisaka 5 (fig. 37). Thus, IR20 may be better adapted to higher temperature during ripening.

We found that grain ripens slowly at the early and late stages, and at a linear rate during the effective grain-filling period between the slow phases. The grain-filling period is 24 days for IR20 at Los Baños. Using the effective grain-filling period and appropriate conversion factors for husk weight and moisture content, and allowing for stored carbohydrate before flowering, we can estimate the maximum grain yield (Table 24). The percent of the maximum yield actually

ENVIRONMENT
AND ITS
INFLUENCE

36. Rice grains fill faster at higher temperatures within a daily air temperature range of from 16° to 28°C. IIRRI phytotron, 1975.

37. The optimum mean daily temperature to maximize grain weight is 3°C higher for the indica variety IR20 than for the japonica Fujisaka 5. This indicates that IR20 may be better adapted to higher temperature during ripening. IIRRI phytotron, 1975.

Table 24. Estimated maximum yield for wet-and dry-season crops at Los Baños, IRRI, 1975.

Season	Efficiency of solar energy use ^a (%)	Recorded yield (% of maximum yield)		Recorded yield (t/ha)		Estimated maximum yield (t/ha)
		Normal	CO ₂ ^b	Normal	with CO ₂ ^b	
Wet	3.3	63	81	6.0	7.7	9.5
Wet	2.5	82	105			7.3
Dry	3.3	53	78	9.0	13.3	17.0
Dry	2.5	67	99			13.4

^a3.3% is the highest recorded value in Japan during the International Biological Program Years from 1967 to 1971. ^bCO₂ enrichment for 30 days before flowering to increase spikelet number.

achieved is in effect a measure of the ratio of input energy to output energy. This provides a rational basis for comparing rice yields under different environments. Interestingly, rice performs better in terms of energy utilization in the wet than in the dry season. We calculated the maximum possible grain yield at Los Baños as about 7 t/ha in the wet season and 13 t/ha in the dry season.

The national averages for rice yields in Spain (6.3 t/ha) and Australia (6.2 t/ha) are higher than yields in Japan (6.0 t/ha). But on an energy efficiency basis, Japanese farmers do far better (50%) than farmers in Spain (35%) and Australia (30%).

Rice production doesn't end at harvest; the crop must be threshed, dried, milled, and stored before it reaches the consumer. At each step, both quality and quantity of grain may be impaired.

POST-
PRODUCTION
TECHNOLOGY

We surveyed both farmers and processors to determine the nature of each post-production practice in three regions of the Philippines in 1974–75. We also tested combinations of traditional and mechanical methods of harvesting, threshing, and drying to minimize grain losses and maximize profits.

We found that farmers recognize the critical nature of post-harvest operations, but that more than 35 percent of them delayed harvest beyond the maturity date because of inadequate labor or bad weather, or both (fig. 38).

Most farmers continued to harvest and thresh by the traditional methods, although about 25 percent used machines and many more expressed interest in mechanical threshing (fig. 38). Farmers indicated little interest in mechanical drying, although they were aware that timely drying could increase output, particularly in the wet season. Lack of price incentives and lack of suitable drying equipment in the villages were cited as reasons for low interest.

We found that little grain was held for speculation, largely because of inadequate storage facilities and an almost universal post-harvest demand for cash to liquidate debts.

Small rice mills have an important and continuing role in the villages. Both farmers and mill owners cited the ability to handle small lots of grain, accessibility, convenience, and low initial cost as the most important reasons for their popularity. Low milling recovery was the major complaint against village mills.

The small mills with steel hullers processed rice almost exclusively for household requirements, and performed no storage, trading, or credit functions. Milling was generally a family business to supplement earnings from farming or related

38. a) More than 35 percent of farmers surveyed in three regions of the Philippines delayed harvest beyond maturity of the crop. b) Most continued to thresh by traditional methods, although a fourth used mechanical threshers. Survey of 591 farms in Central and Southern Luzon and Camarines Sur province, Philippines, 1974-75.

occupations. In contrast, millers with the larger, disc-cono units mill primarily for commercial markets and usually store, transport, wholesale, or retail rice. Both mill types are underutilized; actual capacity averaged 64 percent of rated capacity.

In village-level trials, we found that economic return was greatest when the mechanical thresher was used in combination with manual harvesting and solar drying. This combination reduced harvesting and drying losses from 29 down to 21 percent. Mechanical threshing in combination with mechanical drying reduced losses similarly, although most of the decrease was due to more timely operations. Use of the mechanical thresher alone increased farmers' net return by almost \$25 per ton by lowering costs and increasing grain recovery.

CONSTRAINTS ON INCREASED RICE PRODUCTION

We intensified our research on the biological and socioeconomic constraints to higher yields and further strengthened our relationships with a network of collaborating agronomists and economists in Bangladesh, Sri Lanka, Indonesia, Thailand, Taiwan, and the Philippines (fig. 39). We are improving and simplifying our methodology so that it can be transferred and adapted more readily for research workers elsewhere.

In experiments at three Philippine locations, we compared yields at the farmers' level of inputs with those obtained when optimum levels of fertilizer, insect control, and weed control were used. Yields at the highest levels of these inputs were often from 1 to 2 tons greater than those that farmers were obtaining, with a larger gap in the dry than in the wet season (fig. 43). On the average in three locations, yields were 4.6 t/ha at high input level and 3.6 t/ha at farm level in the wet season, and 6.1 t/ha at high input level and 4.2 t/ha at farm level in the dry season.

39. Location of national scientists collaborating in the International Rice Agro-Economic Network (IRAEN) studying the constraints to higher rice yields on farmers' fields, 1976.

40. Proportion of difference in yield at farmers' and at high input level attributed to the increase in three inputs during the dry and wet seasons, Laguna, Nueva Ecija, and Camarines Sur provinces, Philippines, 1975.

Table 25. Added cost and added value of output for high level of fertilizer and insecticide compared with average farmers' levels in farmers' field experiments, Philippines, 1975 dry and wet seasons.

Province	Sites (no.)	From high fertilizer (\$/ha)		From high insecticide (\$/ha)	
		Added cost (\$/ha)	Added value (\$/ha)	Added cost (\$/ha)	Added value (\$/ha)
<i>Dry season</i>					
Laguna	9	21	189	294	138
Nueva Ecija	3	-4 ^a	24	97	55
Camarines Sur	3	61	170	90	56
<i>Wet season</i>					
Laguna	5	30	104	190	93
Nueva Ecija	11	24	46	76	29
Camarines Sur	6	38	60	80	75

^aNegative value because the farmers' level of fertilizer application was higher than the high level in the experiments.

Measurement of the contribution of each input to the yield gap showed that in the dry season, fertilizer and insect control accounted for more than 80 percent of the gap at all locations except Nueva Ecija (fig. 40). There is, however, considerable variation in the contribution of inputs to the yield gap by location and season.

Economic analysis of the experiments showed that despite the higher yields at high levels of inputs, the income was frequently higher at farmers' level of inputs. A breakdown of the costs by inputs explains why. The added value of output for additional fertilizer is very high relative to the added cost (Table 25). But the added cost of insecticides in general exceeds the added value. The results suggest that farmers may substantially benefit from increasing the level of fertilizer, particularly in the dry season. But developing a more profitable combination of inputs will require the identification of more cost-efficient techniques of insect control. Weeds can be controlled at relatively low cost in those cases where weed control adds significantly to yields.

CONSEQUENCES
OF NEW RICE
TECHNOLOGY

We initiated a program to assess the impact of new rice technology on income distribution during 1975.

First, we analyzed how technological changes in rice production have influenced market prices by applying a mathematical model to data collected on the Philippine rice economy. We found that improvements in technology tended to equalize incomes among farmers in the Philippines.

Table 26. Distribution of gains in economic welfare from the 10-percent increase in aggregate rice output due to technical progress among producers and consumers in the Philippines for different assumptions on market sale (r) ratio, 1969-70 and 1971-72 averages. IIRI, 1975.

Distribution	Welfare gains	
	r = 0.4 ^a	r = 1.0 ^b
<i>\$ million</i>		
Total	21.8	23.3
Consumers	17.7	44.4
Producers	4.1	-22.1
<i>%</i>		
Total	100	100
Consumers	81	199
Producers	19	-99

^aMarketable surplus ratio for a semisubsistence economy.

^bMarketable surplus ratio for a fully commercial economy.

Table 27. Estimates of the differential impacts of technological progress in rice production (10-percent increase in aggregate output) on small and large farms in the Philippines. IRRI, 1975.

Farm size	Rate of output increase due to technological progress (%)	Changes (%) in		
		Cash revenue (1)	Production cost (2)	Cash income (1) — (2)
Case 1				
Small	10	1.4	-2.9	4.3
Large	10	-7.1	-2.9	-4.2
Case 2				
Small	7	-1.4	-3.7	2.3
Large	14	-3.1	-1.7	-1.4

In developed nations, farmers themselves consume an insignificant portion of their output and the market demand is highly inelastic. When technical progress increases the supply of a food crop, market prices decline and producers' incomes drop, even if production costs are lowered. But consumers enjoy higher consumption at lower prices (Table 26).

But in semisubsistence agriculture, where only a small amount of the farmers' output is sold, reduction in the market price of rice has relatively little effect on producers' cash revenue (Table 26). Increased sales may compensate for the lower prices, resulting in higher income for producers. Similarly, lower rice prices have a more unfavorable impact on the income of large farmers who sell most of their output than on the income of subsistence farmers. As the percentage of the total output sold decreases, the reduction in production costs becomes more likely to exceed the reduction in cash revenue (Table 27).

Further, we investigated changes in the distribution of farm earnings from rice production since the introduction of modern varieties by studying data collected from sample farms in Laguna province and the Central Luzon region, Philippines. We calculated the share of output that went to landlords, to farm operators, and to hired workers, and determined how much of the output went outside of the agricultural sector to purchase inputs. The data indicate that shares of earnings going to various groups did not change radically after the introduction of modern varieties (fig. 41). Further, we found no evidence of a decline in the absolute or relative earnings to labor. Instead, the percent of earnings going to landlords appears to have declined.

At the request of the Philippine government, we examined reasons behind the recent decline in fertilizer consumption and evaluated alternate pricing policies to encourage rice self-sufficiency. Subsequently, a more detailed analytical framework was developed to evaluate the benefits and costs of rice price support vs. fertilizer subsidy. We found the input subsidy to be more efficient in terms of social benefits and costs if subsidies were applied to inputs such as fertilizers that were used at suboptimal levels. We found that the heavy financial burden to the government of subsidizing fertilizer prices can be substantially reduced by raising the sugar export tax; the fertilizer subsidy program could thus be extended to the sugar sector without increasing cost to the government.

About half of the world's rice is nonirrigated and grown under rainfed lowland conditions—in paddies but depending entirely on monsoon rain for moisture.

CROPPING
SYSTEMS

For centuries, farmers in the rainfed regions have grown only one crop per

41. The share of farm earnings that went to landlords, farm operators, hired workers, and outside the agricultural sector to purchase inputs did not change dramatically after the introduction of modern rice varieties. One hundred and fourteen sample farms, Laguna province, Philippines, 1975.

year and the land has been left fallow the rest of the time.

But when rainfed farmers use the new early-maturing varieties, they have an extra month or two of time, monsoon rain, and residual soil moisture—enough to grow another food crop.

At three sites in the Philippines, IRRI and Philippine scientists are determining cropping patterns and technology that will enable small farmers to utilize their resources to follow their first harvest of rainfed rice with an upland food crop or with another rice crop. To assure that the technology is within the management capacity of small rice farmers and to speed its development, we are bypassing experiment station trials and conducting all research on farmers' fields, under farm management. Figure 42 shows the conceptual framework of the cropping systems program.

These on-farm research methods are now applied at 14 sites representative of the most important agroclimatic regions of rice-growing Asia (Table 28).

Our site in Iloilo is representative of regions where rainfed lowland rice is grown and was selected because it has a climate that is typical of a much wider agroclimatic zone, including 72 percent of Bangladesh and 30 percent of Indonesia. From 5 to 6 months of monsoon rain (at least 200 mm/mo) is followed by a dry season (100 mm and less).

42. The conceptual framework of the cropping systems research program.

We hope that farm technology developed in Iloilo can be modified and transferred to other regions with similar agroclimatic and socioeconomic conditions.

To better evaluate the impact of the cropping technology, economists have conducted a baseline survey of the test area, and are monitoring changes in the household economics and farming systems among our farmer-cooperators.

In 1974–75, we tested 14 rice-based cropping patterns; we found that returns on heavier soils were highest from a direct-seeded crop of rice followed by transplanted rice (Table 29).

Two crops of rice are made possible by seeding the first crop of early-maturing varieties directly in rainfed lowland areas where the wet season lasts for 5 months or longer. In Iloilo, farmer cooperators harvested from 7 to 10 tons of rice per hectare from such a double cropping system.

Table 28. Collaborating scientists at 14 sites in six nations are conducting research to increase cropping intensity.

Country	Location	Description ^a
Philippines	Iloilo	U, RL, PI
Philippines	Batangas	U
Philippines	Pangasinan	RL, PI
Indonesia	Lampung	U, PI
Indonesia	Indramayu	PI
Bangladesh	Joydebpur	PI, I
Thailand	In Buri	RL, PI
Thailand	Pi Mai	RL
Thailand	Ubon	RL
Thailand	Kampangsaen	RL, PI
Sri Lanka	Siyabalagas-wewa, Paranagas wewa-Anuradhapura	PI
Sri Lanka	Walagambahuwa, Anuradhapura	PI
Sri Lanka	Alanakara, Katupota, Kurunegala	RL
Burma	Yesin	PI, RL

^aU = upland; I = irrigated; RL = Rainfed lowland (bunded); PI = Partially irrigated.

Table 29. On heavy soils, the most profitable cropping pattern was wet-seeded rice followed by transplanted rice. On medium-textured soils, several upland crops were more profitable. Rice-based cropping pattern trials conducted on farmers' fields under farmer management, Iloilo province, Philippines, 1975-76.

Cropping pattern	Crop yield (t/ha)		Variable costs (\$/ha)	Total returns (\$/ha)	Net returns over costs (\$/ha)
	1st	2nd			
<i>Heavy soils</i>					
Wet-seeded rice					
fb wet-seeded rice ^a	4.2	4.4	573	1185	612
Wet-seeded rice					
fb transplanted rice	4.4	4.4	582	1210	628
Corn					
fb transplanted rice	16,712 ^b	3.8	446	684	238
Transplanted rice					
fb ratooned rice	4.7	0.9	398	640	380
<i>Medium soils</i>					
Transplanted rice					
fb mung beans	4.2	0.2	398	640	242
Transplanted rice					
fb cowpeas	3.7	0.6	462	660	198
Transplanted rice					
fb soybeans	3.7	0.1	438	575	137
Transplanted rice					
fb peanuts	3.5	0.6	611	1274	663
Transplanted rice					
fb corn	4.1	1.5	533	825	292
Transplanted rice					
fb sorghum	4.7	1.5	491	803	312
Transplanted rice					
fb sweet potato	2.0	6.9	820	1109	289
Transplanted rice					
fb honeydew	4.6	8201 ^c	743	2262	1519
Transplanted rice					
fb corn	2.8	1.8	646	1590	944
with peanut		0.6			
Transplanted rice					
fb corn	2.0	2.0	510	688	178
with mung beans		0.2			

^aRice seeded directly onto puddled soil. Fb = followed by. ^bMarketable green ears. ^cMarketable melons.

Because climatic patterns vary from year to year, we hope to develop a range of alternate cropping patterns that farmers can "plug in" to fit the prevailing weather and market situations.

Our site in Batangas, Philippines, is representative of many areas where upland rice is grown. We found two new cropping patterns that are practical and profitable: rice followed by an intercrop combination of corn and sweet potato, and rice followed by sorghum.

The traditional intercropping pattern of upland rice and corn, common in Batangas, can produce from 30 to 40 percent more food than either crop planted as monoculture if modern technology is used. This is because the photosynthetic efficiency of corn is higher during early growth and that of rice is higher late in the season.

Corn that is widely spaced in intercrop combinations had lower infestations of both corn borer and downy mildew, the most important corn pests in Asia.

We studied cash and labor inputs and returns in six popular farming systems. The highest marginal return to labor was in systems with the highest variations in use of weekly labor. A study of the weekly cash flows showed that the financial linkages are critical among the farmer's crop, his livestock, and his household

needs. For example, farmers often sell livestock at planting time to purchase needed inputs.

Iron deficiency seriously damaged the first crop of direct-seeded rice on the calcareous soils at our site in Pangasinan province. Zinc deficiency limited yields of the second crop of transplanted rice and of the third crop of corn. Intensive cropping patterns that are adapted to these common soil problems could be widely used in Southeast Asia.

We found that direct seeding was often better than transplanting for the second crop of early-maturing varieties. But transplanting was better where water control could guarantee timeliness.

We are also studying ways to shorten the "turnabout" time or the period between the harvest of rice and the planting of subsequent crops in Pangasinan. This crucial step for intensifying systems may be related to tillage, labor, moisture, or the independent inclinations of the farmer.

The establishment of upland crops after transplanted rice on 86 farms was delayed for 56 days after rice harvest apparently because high rainfall prevented land preparation (fig. 43). Competitive labor demands for harvesting and processing rice may have also been a factor. No such turnabout difficulties were encountered by 14 farmers in the rice-rice-upland crop pattern. Turnabout coincided with low labor demand and the transition from transplanted rice to

43. In a double-cropping system of transplanted rice followed by upland crops, the establishment of the second crop was delayed for 56 days because of high rainfall. But in a triple-cropping system of dry-seeded rice followed by transplanted rice followed by upland crops, the turnabout time was considerably shorter because it coincided with periods of low labor demand and low rainfall. Pangasinan province, Philippines, 1975.

upland crops occurred during low rainfall periods. The rice-rice-upland crop pattern returned about \$350 more per hectare than the rice-upland crop pattern. These patterns were tested in fields where only one crop of transplanted rice is normally grown.

Superimposed on our cropping patterns tests are experiments in varietal screening of both rice and upland crops, weed management, insect and disease control, fertility management, and tillage. Early-maturing corn varieties escaped major attacks of corn borer in the first crop. Similarly, mung beans had fewer insect problems when planted early than when planted late.

In a cropping pattern of upland rice followed by corn, a white grub that attacks both crops was controlled most effectively by low applications of soil insecticide during weeding of the rice crop when the grubs were small and easy to kill (fig. 44).

Cooperative research with the University of the Philippines at Los Baños shows that the buildup of soil nematodes can be avoided by judiciously selecting

44. Population dynamics of the adult and three larval instars of white grub *Leucopholis irrorata* (Chev.). In a cropping pattern of upland rice followed by corn, cropping systems scientists found that the grubs were most effectively controlled by low applications of a soil insecticide during weeding of the rice crop when they were small and easy to kill. Batangas province, Philippines, 1975.

Table 30. Varietal differences were found in the competitive ability of various cultivars of cowpea. IIRRI, 1975 wet season.

Cultivar	Yield (kg/ha)		Yield reduction due to weeds (%)	Weed wt (kg/ha)
	Weeded	Unweeded		
EG # 1	249	127	49	563
EG # 2	592	241	59	687
EG # 3	763	236	69	1181
California	374	74	87	2302
Black Eye				
Virginia	564	59	89	2047

cropping sequences and managing crop residuals. Research shows that farmers need to know when pest injury reaches a level of economic importance, and what pest-control options are available to them at those levels. Because of the complexity of pest outbreaks, it may be necessary for governments to support pest warning programs.

We effectively managed weeds with little or no chemical or hand weeding by rotating lowland and upland crops in 1975 trials. Applying herbicides at a low rate followed by a single manual or mechanical weeding controlled weeds as well as, or better than, intensive mechanical or chemical control.

A new herbicide with the code number MON 0358 gave excellent weed control in most of the crops that are considered suitable for multiple cropping in Asia.

We found varietal differences in the ability of mung beans and cowpeas to compete with and suppress weeds (Table 30). Weeds reduced yields more severely in cowpeas than in mung, but we found more variation in competitive ability in cowpeas.

The reluctance of farmers to plant successive crops of legumes appears to be justified. Yields of a second crop of mung beans planted after harvest of a first crop were from 20 to 40 percent lower than yields of other crops planted after mung (which were not affected). We are studying reasons for the decrease in yields.

The more promising multiple cropping technology was tested in 140 applied research trials at 32 locations under seven rainfall patterns during 1975, in collaboration with the Philippine Council on Agricultural Research.

Birds and rats caused extensive damage at all locations. Blast disease was a major problem in rainfed and upland areas.

The early-maturing line IR1561-228-3 averaged 4 t/ha while IR30 averaged 3.5 t/ha in 51 trials.

Yields were highest in areas where the rainfall was highest throughout the growing season. Relatively small amounts of supplemental irrigation increased yields substantially in areas where it was available. Seven upland crops that have potential in multiple cropping patterns have been planted at most of the experimental sites.

IIRRI researchers collaborate with scientists in 15 nations through the Asian Network for Cropping Systems Research and Development.

IIRRI designs small farm machines to overcome bottlenecks in production and to improve the quality of rice that ultimately goes to the consumer. The designs are released free to manufacturers and small metalworking shops to produce and sell in the developing nations. This not only provides farmers with appropriate farm

MACHINERY
DEVELOPMENT
AND TESTING

Table 31. Almost 14,000 IRRI-designed machines were commercially produced in eight nations^a in 1975.

Country	Manufacturers (no.)	Machines (no.)				
		5- to 7-hp tiller	Axial flow thresher	Batch dryer	Power weeder	Multihopper seeder
Ghana	1	—	15	—	—	—
India	1	—	60	—	—	—
Japan	3	—	—	—	11,000	—
Pakistan	1	—	2	—	—	—
Philippines	14	2,178	275	33	—	56
Sri Lanka	2	60	—	—	—	—
Taiwan	1	—	—	200	—	—
Thailand	3	69	10	—	—	—
Total	26	2,307	363	233	11,000	56

^a Does not include preproduction prototype machines produced by companies in India, Indonesia, Thailand, Guyana, Colombia, Ecuador, Philippines, Bangladesh, Malaysia, Egypt, and Sri Lanka.

tools at low cost, but also creates local employment and saves scarce foreign exchange.

Almost 14,000 IRRI-designed machines were produced in eight nations in 1975, an increase of 39 percent over 1974 (Table 31). This brings the total number of IRRI machines manufactured across the world to 36,000.

Through IRRI's new industrial extension project, teams will be located at regional centers in Pakistan, Thailand, and the Philippines to encourage manufacture of IRRI-designed machines in South and Southeast Asia. These teams will service manufacturers in the host countries and surrounding areas.

We developed several new machines for small farmers and improved the designs of several previously developed machines during 1975.

45. The diaphragms of IRRI's newly developed diaphragm pump are made from automobile inner tubes. The pump is designed for low-lift irrigation from irrigation ditches, rivers, and shallow wells. To pump water, the operator stands on the two footrests and shifts his weight from one foot to the other. The diaphragm pump was developed to overcome service problems encountered with the IRRI bellows pump. IRRI, 1975.

46. IRRI engineers worked with entomologists and agronomists to develop a simple liquid applicator that places insecticides and fertilizers under the surface of puddled soils, increasing the efficiency of chemical use. Left to right are: D. Kuether, associate agricultural engineer; A. U. Khan, agricultural engineer; B. Duff, associate agricultural economist; and J. McMennamy, associate agricultural engineer. The machine is being demonstrated in the background.

A manually operated diaphragm pump was developed to overcome service problems encountered with the bellows pump. The diaphragm pump should last longer without repair because it uses inner tubes from automobiles for the diaphragms, instead of the canvas used for the bellows pump (fig. 45).

In response to requests by farmers and manufacturers, we developed steering clutches for the 5- to 7-hp tiller. The new design will soon be released for commercial production.

To lower the cost of the axial flow thresher and to improve its cleaning performance, we are evaluating three cleaning mechanisms. A simplified thresher is significantly cheaper to produce and performs as well as the current thresher.

We found that the thresher is often used for contract operations, which means that the machines are frequently moved from field to field. To improve the thresher's mobility, we designed a special hitch so that one of our power tillers can transport and power the thresher. We also developed a self-propelled thresher that can easily be separated from its motorized cart. The operator can use the cart for hauling and transport after threshing.

We developed simple granular and liquid chemical applicators to place insecticides and fertilizers under the surface of puddled soils and increase the efficiency of their use. A liquid applicator, fed by gravity flow, appears most promising (fig. 46).

We studied factors that affect the efficiency of rice-whitening machines of the friction jet air type and began work on a continuous-flow parboiling machine that directly exposes steeped paddy to a stream of hot gases.

Solar heat collectors have been developed in the industrially advanced countries, but are expensive. We continued our efforts to develop an inexpensive solar collector to use as an attachment to the IRRI batch dryer.

We developed a vertical-axis windmill using a Savonius rotor made from three 44-gal oil drums and coupled it to a tubular pump that was developed for low-lift

irrigation. We are testing this combination on irrigation ditches at IRRI.

Manufacturers are keenly interested in our project to develop an inexpensive 15- to 20-hp four-wheel tractor and a range of implements that will be light enough for wetland work, with provisions to add ballast weights for dry land use.

We reduced the weight and improved the field mobility of the PTO (power takeoff) thresher, and hope to reduce the pieces of short straw that now go with the grain.

As rice production increases in Asia, traditional wooden winnowers are often inadequate for cleaning grain. We have designed two inexpensive oscillating grain cleaners. Production prototype machines of a cleaner with a capacity of 2 tons/hour are being built in Sri Lanka and the Philippines. A smaller cleaner is being developed for farm-level operations and threshing floors. Early tests show a cleaning capacity of 1 t/h at 96 percent purity.

We are continuing to study the long-term effects of different tillage practices on the depth of soil compaction in continuously cropped paddy fields at the IRRI farm. Even with the 5- to 7-hp power tiller, the depth of the compaction has not stabilized after five cropping seasons.

Sixty representatives from 19 countries in Asia, Africa, Europe, and the Americas participated in the International Workshop on Agricultural Mechanization and Indigenous Production of Agricultural Machines, organized and held at IRRI. Twenty trainees from 10 countries received formal instruction in the manufacture and utilization of IRRI machines during 1975.

INTERNATIONAL ACTIVITIES

IRRI continued to provide services to help improve national research capacities and to participate in networks and collaborative programs to test research products and methodologies under a wide range of ecological conditions.

We further strengthened our network activities in rice testing, agroeconomic investigations, rice-based cropping systems, and machinery testing. Our close linkages with scientists in the national programs have greatly helped in the orientation of our core research program to problems on farmers' fields.

IRRI was involved in cooperative country projects designed to strengthen national capacities in Bangladesh, Indonesia, the Philippines, and Sri Lanka (fig. 47). Four IRRI-sponsored workshops and conferences brought together about 300 scientists to review and plan cooperative activities in different areas. IRRI continued to supply rice literature and publications, rice germ plasm, and improved genetic material to rice scientists around the world.

The improvement of national capabilities in rice research has enabled IRRI to begin shifting emphasis in its international activities from cooperative country projects to other appropriate mechanisms for long-term collaboration with national and regional programs.

The IRRI-India collaborative project yielded valuable information on the range of variation in the brown planthopper and helped to identify new sources of broad-spectrum resistance to its biotypes. The IRRI-Thailand collaborative program on deep-water rice is beginning to produce promising lines that have improved plant type and tolerance to moderate water depths. We developed memoranda of understanding with the International Center for Tropical Agriculture (CIAT) in Latin America and with the International Institute for Tropical Agriculture (IITA) and the West African Rice Development Association (WARDA) in Africa to provide a basis for IRRI's collaboration in rice research on a regional basis in those geographical areas.

47. a) BANGLADESH. Inspecting diseased rice plants in farmers' fields with local rice scientists is Tom Brackney, rice production specialist with the IRRI-Bangladesh collaborative project. b) SRI LANKA. At the control panel of a parboiling unit at the In-Service Training Institute of the Paddy Marketing Board (PMB), are (left to right); M. J. Perera, chairman, PMB; Jim Wimberly, rice processing advisor; and L. Velluipalli, engineer, PMB. c) INDONESIA. Plant breeders using the vacuum emasculator, which speeds the emasculating of rice anthers (a major bottleneck in rice breeding), increasing the number of potential crosses that can be made in a year. IRRI provides designs for vacuum emasculators to national programs and helps furnish the materials needed to build them. The men seated are (left to right): Darto, assistant breeder; news reporter; news reporter; Misbah, assistant breeder; Haryanto, assistant breeder in charge of hybridization and a graduate of IRRI's training program; Bambang; assistant breeder; and Suwito, assistant breeder.

During 1975, 208 scholars, fellows and production trainees from 28 countries studied at IRRI. The Institute provided 86 man-years of training during the year.

Three new training programs were first offered in 1975 in support of the Institute's international research networks: the International Rice Testing Program (IRTP); the International Rice Agro-Economic Network (IRAEN); and the Agricultural Machinery Network. The cropping systems training program was modified to train the manpower needed for the Cropping Systems Network.

ASSOCIATED
FORMAL
TRAINING

EXPERIMENTAL
FARM

We are developing the new 192-ha experimental farm that the Philippine government made available to IRRI through the University of the Philippines at Los Baños. The scientists were able to use about 35 ha of new upland fields for experiments in 1975. A new reservoir was built, roads were constructed, and about 90 percent of the perimeter fence was completed.

From our 24 ha of seed multiplication plots, we harvested almost 85,000 kg of six IRRI varieties, four elite GEU lines, and two Korean varieties.

LIBRARY AND
DOCUMENTATION
CENTER

The 1974 supplement to the *International Bibliography of Rice Research*, published in 1975, provides worldwide coverage of literature on rice research. The supplement contains 3,834 references to scientific rice literature, most of which appeared in journals in 1974. The bibliography is distributed to agricultural libraries and documentation centers for the use of rice research workers and those responsible for disseminating information on rice. The basic volume and the annual supplements list technical literature on rice published since 1951. Essentially all the citations included in these bibliographies are available in the IRRI library.

Most of the numerous requests for information and photocopying services received during 1975 came from Indonesia, India, and Malaysia. As in previous years, we received more requests for Japanese literature on genetics and breeding than for all other aspects of rice culture.

To keep the scientists informed about the latest publications on rice, the library continued to circulate the table of contents of newly received journals. This service is extended to the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project; the Bangladesh Rice Research Institute; the Lembaga Penelitian Pertanian Maros in Indonesia; the Central Rice Research Institute for Agriculture, Sukamandi Branch, Indonesia; and the West Africa Rice Development Association, Liberia.

INFORMATION
DISSEMINATION

We published four new publications in 1975: *Changes in Rice Farming in Selected Areas of Asia*, *Major Research in Upland Rice*, *Research Highlights for 1974*, and the *1974 IRRI Annual Report*. Five issues of the *IRRI Reporter* were distributed to more than 7,500 libraries, rice scientists, and researchers (fig. 48).

48. Five issues of the *IRRI Reporter* were distributed to more than 7,500 scientists, libraries, and research centers in 50 nations in 1975. Reading the *IRRI Reporter* is Dr. S. D. I. E. Gunawardene, botanist, Central Agricultural Research Institute, Peradeniya, Sri Lanka.

49. a) IRRI's new laboratory and training center will be used in 1976. Left is Brian Tierney, construction consultant from the Australian Development Assistance Agency (ADAA); right is Hugh T. Murphy, IRRI assistant director for administration. b) Aerial view of the IRRI research complex. The laboratory and training center is circled.

About 11,000 copies of the English version of *Field Problems of Tropical Rice* and 21,860 copies of 35 other IRRI publications were distributed in 1975. Most were disseminated to libraries and rice researchers and workers in rice-growing nations in South and Southeast Asia, Africa, and Latin America.

More than 70 sets of 92 color slides on the field problems of tropical rice, including insects, diseases, and nutritional disorders, were distributed in 1975. We prepared and made available a new set of color slides, *The Rices of IRRI*, with an accompanying script to explain and document IRRI's programs. We assisted the Singapore-based Centre for Production and Training for Adult Education Television (CEPTA) in preparing a 20-minute color film about our farm machinery research and development program.

We attended to about 12,000 visitors from 33 countries in 1975. Our dual-screen slide presentation on IRRI's programs was presented to visitors 433 times.

We conducted a research project on the diffusion of rice genetic materials in relation to the breeding objectives, information-seeking habits, and sociological characteristics of rice scientists in eight nations. Most of the data will be analyzed during 1976.

During 1975, we initiated eight building projects: a new laboratory/ training center complex (fig. 49); two housing projects; a greenhouse/headhouse; a farm building; two new generator sheds; and a parking lot over three cistern tanks.

We drove the first pile for the new laboratory and training center in early 1975. It is scheduled for completion in 1976 and will provide 2,800 square meters of additional laboratory and office facilities and 1,000 sq m of training facilities (fig. 49).

We initiated a new personnel classification program and a job title program for our 843 regular employees.

We moved our Manila office to a new location in Makati.

Because of our expanded training program, our dormitory space has been fully booked. We are developing plans for a new dormitory.

ADMINISTRATION

Genetic evaluation and utilization (GEU) program

Genetic evaluation and utilization (GEU) program

Germ plasm collection and preservation

Plant Breeding Department

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GERM PLASM COLLECTION AND PRESERVATION 70

SUMMARY

We collected 566 samples of indigenous rice varieties, many in danger of extinction, in South Vietnam, Sri Lanka, and Bangladesh during 1975.

Since intensive field collection began in 1972, IRRI has directly participated in the collection of about 5,660 seed samples from seven collaborating nations. Another 8,760 samples were collected with indirect IRRI support. About 4,220 of the samples are reputed to have one or more special features, such as resistance to insects, tolerance to adverse soils, or adaptation to cool temperatures.

About 33,000 accessions are now in the germ plasm bank. For additional storage space, a genetic resources laboratory is planned.

During 1975, we supplied foreign researchers with more than 4,000 seed samples in response to about 170 requests. Within IRRI, we supplied 22,155 seed samples to scientists in the GEU program.

GERM PLASM COLLECTION AND PRESERVATION

IRRI staff members joined national scientists in three Asian countries during 1975 to canvass the countryside and collect and preserve indigenous rice varieties that were threatened with extinction.

In both South Vietnam and Sri Lanka, indigenous varieties are disappearing as they are replaced by improved varieties. During January and February, 108 samples were collected in South Vietnam. In Sri Lanka, a joint collection effort netted 295 samples from the wet zone during the *yala*^a crop season in September and October.

The IRRI field advisor visited Bangladesh in late 1975 to help collect the *aman*^b varieties. Extensive travel in the northeast led to the acquisition of 163 samples.

Since the intensive field program began in 1971, IRRI has directly participated in the collection of about 5,660 seed samples from

farmers' fields in seven collaborating Asian nations. Another 8,760 samples were collected by local extension workers with indirect IRRI support (Table 1). Further, about 880 samples of the African species *Oryza glaberrima* and 2,700 samples of the Asian species *Oryza sativa* were collected from Liberia, Mali, and Ivory Coast by officers of the Food and Agriculture Organization and of the *Institut de Recherches Agronomiques Tropicales* stationed in West Africa. About 4,220 of the 14,416 samples were reputed to have one or more special features (Table 2).

During 1975 IRRI received from various sources a total of 5,097 Asian (*O. sativa*) cultivars and lines and another 142 African (*O. glaberrima*) samples. Some of the seed samples collected from Liberia were mixtures of the two cultivated species. About 1,200 Asian rice samples and all of the 1,680 West African accessions were collected in the field. The remaining 2,360 samples either came from existing national and state collections or were replacements for previously acquired dead seeds.

The registration of new accessions is greatly complicated when we receive seed samples with similar or identical variety names, often from diverse regions of the same country. In other cases, we do not have access to the variety names, but only to coded numbers, for several months. We sometimes receive purified lines of farmers' varieties that are already in the IRRI collection.

We are able to distinguish among obviously duplicate samples, ecostrains of the same varieties, morpho-agronomic variants of the same varieties, and nonidentical varieties with the same names by comparing the vernacular meaning of their names, their geographic origins, and their seed characteristics and, later, by growing side by side accessions likely to be duplicates and comparing the plant characters. Through this long and laborious process, we have identified 2,470 samples as duplicates, and also removed from our accession books 1,500 dead seed samples for which we did not receive replacements. We bulked obviously duplicate seed samples to reconstitute the new accessions.

At the end of 1975, 30,392 distinct accessions

^aLocal name in Sri Lanka for the second growing season when the rice is planted in April-May and harvested in September-October.

^bLocal name in Bangladesh for the long-duration varieties; planted in March or June, harvested in November-December.

Table 1. Indigenous rice varieties collected with IRRI's direct or indirect participation in 12 collaborating Asian countries. September 1971 to December 1975.

Country	Years	Indigenous varieties (no.)	
		Direct participation	Indirect participation
Bangladesh	1973-75	519	2361
Burma	1973-74	225	—
Cambodia	1973	280	—
Indonesia	1972-74	3816	2230
Laos	1972-73	—	898
Malaysia, E.	1973-74	—	375
Nepal	1971	—	907
Pakistan	1972-73	—	749
Philippines	1972-75	18	296
Sri Lanka	1972, 1975	691	167
Thailand	1973	—	127
Vietnam, S.	1972-75	108	649
Total		5657	8759

were in the germ plasm bank; another 2,757 newly acquired samples must be planted and investigated for probable duplication.

During 1975, we planted 6,651 plots of *O. sativa* accessions for systematic characterization. We field-recorded 30 traits for 25,426 accessions, but laboratory measurements of seven additional traits covered only 22,000 accessions.

We first began to systematically characterize the *O. glaberrima* cultivars in the 1975 wet season; 914 strains were grown and recorded.

Because many incoming seed samples have low germination rates, seed stocks must often be increased from a small number of viable seeds. Strongly photoperiod-sensitive accessions require short-day treatment to shorten the life cycle. During 1974-1975, we grew 1,320 rows for initial seed increase.

During 1975, we supplied foreign researchers with 3,347 samples of *O. sativa* cultivars in response to 150 requests. Another 696 samples of African rices and wild taxa were dispatched to 18 foreign researchers. Within IRRI, we supplied 22,155 seed samples on 151 occasions for various GEU tests—a significant increase over the 19,236 samples supplied in 1974.

The increased volume of requests for seed has depleted many of our old seed stocks. We grew 1,845 plots in the dry season for seed rejuvenation. Another 1,353 photoperiod-sensitive accessions were planted in late November for seed increase.

Table 2. Indigenous rice varieties with special traits collected and preserved in national programs and in the IRRI germ plasm bank. July 1972 to December 1975.

Reported features	Samples (no.)
Tolerance to salinity	148
Tolerance to acid soils (lowland)	209
Tolerance to alkaline soils	11
Upland-type traits	2462
Floating/flood tolerance	613
High elevation/cold tolerance	639
Resistance to nematodes	5
Resistance to insects	3
Escape from rodent damage	9
Aromatic type	89
Multiple tolerances	30
Total	4218

Seed samples stored in the medium-term storage room (2-3°C, 60-70% relative humidity) decrease in seed viability at different rates. Temperate-zone varieties from mainland China, Japan, Korea, and Taiwan lose viability much faster than do tropical varieties with strong seed dormancy. Because seed germination tests showed that control samples of the temperate-zone accessions had dropped to 37 percent viability, we planted 2,466 accessions for seed rejuvenation.

A large increase in the number of seed stocks has also created storage problems. The original medium-term storage room was completely filled with 25,000 accessions in 1975. We have temporarily stored 4,500 accessions and 135,000 IRRI breeding lines in the cold storage room of the IRRI phytotron (2-6°C, 80-90% R.H.), which will also be filled by early 1976.

A genetic resources laboratory was planned for short-, medium-, and long-term storage of germ plasm and for GEU and International Rice Testing Program (IRTP) materials.

A manual was prepared on the genetic conservation of rice germ plasm with special emphasis on evaluation and utilization. The purpose of the manual is to assist national workers to efficiently conserve, maintain, and use indigenous cultivars as well as introduced germ plasm to develop improved varieties. The manual will be printed in 1976; it will complement the *Manual for field collectors of rice*.

A paper describing the various characteristics of rice cultivars was prepared for use by seed technologists. It was distributed to participants of the first Workshop on Seed Testing for the

Tropics, sponsored by FAO and the Norwegian Agency for Development Aid, and held at the

Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center, Central Luzon, Philippines.

Genetic evaluation and utilization (GEU) program

Agronomic characteristics

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SUMMARY

A new line first tested during the 1975 wet season, IR2071-586-5 appeared outstanding even at low levels of nitrogen fertilizer. An outstanding early line, IR2071-625-1, was widely tested; its yields are comparable to those of medium-duration varieties, but it matures at least 2 weeks earlier. IR34 was released as the first IRRI variety of intermediate height since IR5. We evaluated the ability of IRRI lines to ratoon and found significant varietal differences. Agronomic investigations indicated that ra-

tooning would be preferable to a second main crop only when moisture availability is inadequate for a main crop.

YIELD PERFORMANCE AND NITROGEN RESPONSE UNDER IRRIGATED CONDITIONS *Agronomy Department*

The performance of several promising IRRI breeding lines was compared with that of IR8 and IR26 during the 1975 dry and wet seasons under protected conditions.

IRRI farm. At the IRRI farm, IR26 produced

Table 1. Yields of rice varieties and promising lines at five levels of nitrogen^a (av. of three replications). IRRI, 1975.

Designation	Dry season					Wet season						
	Maturity (days)	Yield ^b (t/ha)					Maturity (days)	Yield ^c (t/ha)				
		0 kg N/ha	60 kg N/ha	90 kg N/ha	120 kg N/ha	150 kg N/ha		0 kg N/ha	30 kg N/ha	60 kg N/ha	90 kg N/ha	120 kg N/ha
IR8	135	4.9	6.5	7.3	7.0	7.3	132	3.1	3.6	4.6	4.8	4.4
IR20	122	4.9	6.3	6.3	6.9	6.8	121	2.9	3.7	3.8	4.2	3.9
IR26	135	4.9	7.1	7.8	7.3	7.7	121	3.0	3.9	4.6	4.9	5.0
IR28	109	4.4	6.1	6.6	6.9	7.3	104	3.4	3.7	4.1	4.5	4.4
IR29	117	4.1	5.2	6.1	6.2	6.6	111	3.1	3.0	3.8	3.8	4.4
IR30	109	4.2	6.0	6.1	6.8	7.3	111	2.9	3.5	4.1	4.4	4.3
IR32	—	—	—	—	—	—	136	3.6	3.9	5.2	4.5	4.2
IR34	122	4.6	6.2	6.7	6.4	4.8	121	3.6	3.8	3.9	2.3	1.9
IR1632-93-2	—	—	—	—	—	—	114	3.4	3.6	4.5	4.4	4.4
IR2031-724-2	126	4.3	5.6	6.0	6.4	6.5	—	—	—	—	—	—
IR2035-290-2	135	4.2	5.4	6.3	6.5	6.7	132	3.4	3.8	4.3	4.6	3.6
IR2058-78-1	135	4.3	7.1	7.2	7.3	7.1	132	4.4	5.0	4.9	5.1	2.7
IR2058-328-1	117	4.3	5.4	6.8	7.0	7.0	—	—	—	—	—	—
IR2061-181-46	135	3.8	4.9	6.1	6.2	5.8	—	—	—	—	—	—
IR2061-464-2	122	3.3	5.7	6.7	6.5	5.9	111	3.2	4.1	4.2	4.5	3.4
IR2061-465-1	109	3.1	3.8	5.8	6.2	6.5	111	3.0	3.7	4.1	4.5	4.3
IR2061-522-6	—	—	—	—	—	—	104	3.4	3.8	4.0	4.6	3.8
IR2061-628-1	—	—	—	—	—	—	111	4.0	4.3	4.9	5.2	4.1
IR2070-24-2	138	4.8	5.8	6.5	5.5	6.1	—	—	—	—	—	—
IR2070-320-6	126	4.8	5.8	6.2	6.3	6.4	—	—	—	—	—	—
IR2070-414-3	—	—	—	—	—	—	114	3.1	3.7	4.4	3.3	2.2
IR2070-423-2	122	4.9	6.1	6.6	6.7	7.1	125	3.6	3.9	4.1	4.2	3.9
IR2070-747-6	140	4.5	5.7	6.3	6.1	5.5	—	—	—	—	—	—
IR2070-747-6	140	4.4	5.6	5.5	5.4	5.3	—	—	—	—	—	—
IR2070-863-1	—	—	—	—	—	—	132	3.2	3.5	3.2	3.9	2.3
IR2071-105-9	—	—	—	—	—	—	125	3.5	3.6	4.7	4.4	3.7
IR2071-176-1	138	4.4	6.0	6.0	6.3	6.6	132	3.3	4.3	4.1	4.2	3.4
IR2071-179-9	—	—	—	—	—	—	132	3.0	3.6	4.0	3.8	3.6
IR2071-586-5	—	—	—	—	—	—	136	5.0	5.0	5.1	4.0	5.2
IR2071-588-4	140	3.9	5.0	6.0	6.2	6.1	—	—	—	—	—	—
IR2071-588-5	—	—	—	—	—	—	136	3.5	4.3	4.4	3.7	4.6
IR2071-625-1	109	4.9	6.0	6.3	6.7	6.4	107	3.4	4.1	4.3	4.3	4.9
IR2071-636-5	—	—	—	—	—	—	114	3.2	3.7	3.8	4.2	5.0
IR2151-598-3	112	4.7	5.7	6.1	6.4	6.0	—	—	—	—	—	—
IR2151-957-5	112	4.4	5.4	5.6	5.9	5.6	—	—	—	—	—	—
IR2153-26-3	122	4.7	6.0	6.2	6.7	6.8	121	2.9	3.9	4.1	3.9	3.7
IR2153-43-2	122	4.1	5.0	6.6	7.1	6.2	—	—	—	—	—	—
IR2153-338-3	112	3.3	4.9	5.9	6.8	6.9	—	—	—	—	—	—
IR2681-163-5	—	—	—	—	—	—	132	3.1	3.9	4.1	3.9	2.8
Peta	140	5.0	4.0	3.3	1.6	1.5	136	2.4	2.8	1.9	1.4	1.3

^a Includes 30 kg N/ha topdressed at panicle initiation in the dry season and 20 kg N/ha in the wet season except for 0 kg N/ha treatment.

^bLSD (5%) = 1.1 t/ha. ^cLSD (5%) = 0.8 t/ha.

Table 2. Yields of rice varieties and elite lines at six levels of nitrogen^a at three locations. Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center, Bicol Rice and Corn Experiment Station, and Visayas Rice Experiment Station, Philippines, 1975 dry season.

Designation	Maturity (days)	Yield ^b (t/ha)					
		0 kg N/ha	60 kg N/ha	90 kg N/ha	120 kg N/ha	150 kg N/ha	180 kg N/ha
IR8	131	2.9	4.5	4.6	4.8	5.0	4.5
IR20	117	3.1	4.2	4.8	4.9	5.0	5.4
IR26	130	3.6	5.1	5.8	5.8	6.5	5.7
IR28	105	3.2	4.4	4.9	5.4	5.1	5.2
IR30	108	3.0	4.2	4.9	5.4	5.3	5.3
IR34	126	4.0	5.1	5.6	5.7	5.1	5.4
IR2035-290-2	137	3.7	4.9	5.3	5.5	5.3	5.2
IR2058-78-1	130	4.0	5.6	6.6	5.8	6.1	5.4
IR2058-328-1	125	3.9	5.5	5.4	6.1	6.0	6.0
IR2061-181-46	133	3.6	4.4	4.9	4.2	4.4	3.9
IR2061-464-2	115	3.6	4.8	5.4	5.2	5.7	5.3
IR2070-423-2	128	4.0	5.5	5.9	5.8	6.2	5.8
IR2070-747-6	139	4.1	4.8	5.4	5.2	5.3	4.9
IR2071-588-4	135	3.4	4.7	5.6	5.2	5.5	5.2
IR2071-625-1	110	3.3	4.6	5.2	5.5	5.2	5.3
IR2151-957-5	118	3.4	4.8	5.0	5.0	5.1	5.1
IR2153-26-3	124	3.7	4.7	5.0	5.5	5.3	5.2
Peta	143	3.7	3.8	3.1	2.4	2.4	2.1

^aIncludes 30 kg N/ha topdressed at panicle initiation except for 0 kg N/ha treatment. ^bAv. of three replications. LSD (5%) = 0.6 t/ha.

the highest yield in the dry season for the second consecutive year (Table 1). The highest yield during the 1975 dry season, 7.8 t/ha, was somewhat lower than the highest in 1974, 8.5 t/ha, because early April rains damaged the 1975 crop at ripening stage.

Among the new lines, IR2058-78-1, IR2070-423-2, and IR2058-328-1 produced 7.0 t/ha at 150 kg N/ha. Among the early-maturing rices, IR28 and IR30 yielded 7.3 t/ha (Table 1). There was no brown planthopper damage during the 1975 dry season, and IR8 (which is susceptible) produced the highest average yield, 7.3 t/ha, at both 90 and 150 kg N/ha. During the 1974 dry season, hopper infestation was heavy and IR8 yielded only 4.9 t/ha.

Solar radiation was lower than normal during the ripening period of the 1975 wet-season crop (see Crop Weather). The highest yields, 5.2 t/ha, were from IR32 at 60 kg N/ha; from the experimental line IR2061-628-1 at 90 kg N/ha; and from IR2071-586-5 at 120 kg N/ha (Table 1). As in the dry-season crop, IR26 and IR2058-78-1 produced high yields. Both the line IR2071-586-5 and Peta had significant incidence of blast at 90 and 120 kg N/ha. However, the stability of IR2071-586-5 at zero or at low nitrogen levels (30 and 60 kg N/ha) may make it valuable for areas of low soil fertility. Because

of continuous rains during the ripening period (Nov.-Dec.), many promising lines lodged; otherwise many probably would have yielded higher.

BPI stations. Eleven elite lines and three varieties were compared with IR8, IR20, IR26, and Peta during the dry and wet seasons at experiment stations of the Philippine Bureau of Plant Industry (BPI) at Maligaya, Bicol, and Visayas.

In the dry season, six nitrogen levels were used: 0, 60, 90, 120, 150, and 180 kg N/ha. IR2058-78-1 produced the highest yield, 6.6 t/ha, at 90 kg N/ha, followed by IR26 with 6.5 t/ha at 150 kg N/ha (Table 2). IR34 and IR2070-747-6 had some sheath blight infection at Maligaya. At Bicol, IR2058-328-1 and IR2058-78-1 had bacterial leaf streak. At Visayas, 50 percent of the IR8 was infected by grassy stunt virus. IR2071-625-1 had the most white heads (stem borer damage) among the 18 entries tested. Most of the early-maturing lines had from 4 to 5 percent white heads compared with 1 to 3 percent infection in the varieties of longer duration.

In the wet-season trials, six nitrogen levels were used: 0, 30, 60, 90, 120, and 150 kg N/ha. IR26 produced the highest yield, 4.9 t/ha, at 120 kg N/ha (Table 3). The experimental line

Table 3. Yields of rice varieties and elite lines at six levels of nitrogen^a at three locations. Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center, Bicol Rice and Corn Experiment Station, and Visayas Rice Experiment Station, Philippines, 1975 wet season.

Designation	Maturity (days)	Yield ^b (t/ha)					
		0 kg N/ha	30 kg N/ha	60 kg N/ha	90 kg N/ha	120 kg N/ha	150 kg N/ha
IR8	127	3.1	3.6	4.4	4.4	4.5	4.2
IR20	126	3.0	3.5	4.3	4.6	4.4	4.1
IR26	125	3.2	4.1	4.6	4.9	4.9	4.6
IR28	103	2.8	3.3	3.6	4.4	4.0	4.1
IR30	110	3.0	3.8	4.1	4.5	4.4	4.5
IR32	137	3.7	4.2	4.4	4.7	4.4	3.9
IR34	130	3.6	4.0	3.8	3.4	3.0	3.0
IR1632-93-2	119	3.3	4.1	4.2	4.2	4.3	4.2
IR2035-290-2	137	3.3	3.6	4.1	4.0	3.9	3.7
IR2058-78-1	131	4.0	4.6	4.6	4.7	4.2	3.8
IR2061-464-2	115	3.0	3.8	4.0	4.2	4.2	3.9
IR2061-465-1	112	3.4	3.8	4.4	4.6	4.6	4.1
IR2070-414-3	124	3.5	4.2	4.0	4.3	3.6	3.0
IR2070-423-2	129	3.6	4.0	4.0	4.6	4.2	3.6
IR2071-588-5	136	3.7	4.3	4.9	4.8	4.8	4.5
IR2071-625-1	113	3.4	4.0	4.7	4.8	4.5	3.7
IR2153-26-3	122	3.4	3.9	4.4	4.4	4.1	3.7
Peta	137	2.8	2.8	2.7	2.4	2.1	1.9

^aIncludes 20 kg N/ha topdressed at panicle initiation except in the 0 kg N/ha treatment. ^bAv. of three replications. LSD (5%) = 0.4 t/ha.

Table 4. Yields of rice varieties and experimental lines at four levels of nitrogen^a in a farmer's irrigated field (av. of three replications). Laguna province, Philippines, 1975 dry season.

Designation	Maturity (days)	Yield ^b (t/ha)					Mean
		0 kg N/ha	50 kg N/ha	100 kg N/ha	150 kg N/ha		
IR8	128	4.0	6.5	7.6	8.1	6.5	
IR26	128	4.3	6.1	7.9	7.8	6.5	
IR34	121	4.1	6.4	6.6	7.3	6.1	
IR2035-290-2	131	3.6	5.5	5.6	6.0	5.2	
IR2070-747-6	131	3.9	4.8	6.0	6.2	5.2	
IR2071-588-4	131	3.7	5.8	6.4	6.8	5.7	

^aIncludes 20 kg N/ha topdressed at panicle initiation except for 0 kg N/ha treatment. LSD (5%) for comparing two nitrogen means of same variety or different varieties = 0.8 t/ha; two variety means at same nitrogen level = 0.5 t/ha.

Table 5. Yields of rice varieties and elite lines at four levels of nitrogen^a in farmers' fields under irrigated and rainfed conditions (av. of three replications). Laguna province, Philippines, 1975 wet season.

Designation	Irrigated ^b						Rainfed ^c					
	Maturity (days)	Yield (t/ha)					Maturity (days)	Yield (t/ha)				
		0 kg N/ha	40 kg N/ha	80 kg N/ha	120 kg N/ha	Mean		0 kg N/ha	40 kg N/ha	80 kg N/ha	120 kg N/ha	Mean
IR8	136	4.5	4.7	4.6	4.5	4.6	123	3.9	4.2	4.6	4.4	4.3
IR26	136	4.9	5.0	5.4	4.5	5.0	123	3.9	4.6	5.5	4.5	4.6
IR32	138	5.7	5.9	3.5	2.6	4.4	131	4.6	5.6	5.4	4.2	5.0
IR34	136	3.7	3.9	2.3	1.9	3.0	123	4.4	4.3	4.3	2.7	3.9
IR2035-290-2	136	4.6	4.6	4.7	4.6	4.6	131	3.8	4.2	4.3	3.8	4.0
IR2070-423-2	—	—	—	—	—	—	123	4.1	4.6	4.8	3.8	4.3
IR2071-588-5	138	5.6	6.5	5.0	4.1	5.3	131	4.5	5.0	5.8	5.2	5.1
IR2071-625-1	—	—	—	—	—	—	105	3.0	3.3	4.2	4.1	3.7

^aIncludes 20 kg N/ha topdressed at panicle initiation except for 0 kg N/ha treatment. ^bLSD (5%) for comparing two variety means at same nitrogen level = 1.0 t/ha; two nitrogen means of same or different variety = 1.2 t/ha. Insecticide treatment: carbofuran at 9 days after transplanting; lindane at 99 days. ^cLSD (5%) for comparing two variety means at same nitrogen level = 0.6 t/ha; two nitrogen means of same or different variety = 0.9 t/ha. Insecticide treatment: carbofuran at 5 days after transplanting; lindane at 95 days.

IR2058-78-1, which produced the highest and most stable yields at up to 150 kg N/ha during the dry season, also produced stable yields of about 4 t/ha in the wet season (Table 3). Such yield stability is particularly valuable at low nitrogen levels.

At Maligaya, IR8 suffered from tungro virus and IR26, IR30, and IR2153-26-3 had some bacterial blight.

At Bicol, both the intermediate-statured IR34 and Peta lodged at most nitrogen levels, so their nitrogen response was low. At 150 kg N/ha all varieties and lines had some leaf folder damage.

Yields were generally higher at Visayas than at the two other stations; IR2058-78-1 and IR2153-26-3 yielded highest, 6.1 t/ha, followed by IR26 with 6.0 t/ha.

Farmers' fields. We tested our varieties and experimental lines at various nitrogen levels in farmers' fields under management conditions within the reach of most Asian farmers.

In the dry season under irrigated conditions, IR8 produced the highest yield, 8.1 t/ha, at 150 kg N/ha, followed by IR26, with 7.9 t/ha at 100 kg N/ha (Table 4). The highest yield of IR34 was 7.3 t/ha, but its average yield for all nitrogen levels was about the same as those of IR8 and IR26 (Table 4).

In the wet season under irrigation, IR2071-588-5 produced the highest yield of 6.5 t/ha at 40 kg N/ha; followed by IR32 with 5.9 t/ha at 40 kg N/ha (Table 5). The soil in the experimental area was fertile, so most rices did not respond much to added nitrogen. The intermediate-statured IR34 lodged severely, especially at nitrogen levels of more than 40 kg N/ha, so its yields were generally lower.

The moderately yielding but stable IR2035-290-2 again demonstrated its suitability at both low and high levels of nitrogen (Table 5).

International variety trial. The yield potentials at various levels of nitrogen of several varieties from different countries, and of three IRRI varieties were evaluated in trials at the IRRI farm.

In the dry season, BG 90-2 from Sri Lanka produced the highest yield, 7.2 t/ha, at 150 kg N/ha, as well as the highest yield without fertilizer nitrogen (Table 6). Similar high yields were also obtained with IR8, IR26, IR30,

Table 6. Yields at five levels of nitrogen^a of rice varieties from 10 countries and from IRRI (av. of three replications). IRRI, 1975.

Designation	Origin	Dry season					Wet season						
		Maturity (days)	Yield ^b (t/ha)				Maturity (days)	Yield ^c (t/ha)					
			0 kg N/ha	60 kg N/ha	90 kg N/ha	120 kg N/ha		150 kg N/ha	0 kg N/ha	30 kg N/ha	60 kg N/ha	90 kg N/ha	120 kg N/ha
IR8	IRRI	130	3.6	5.9	6.2	6.7	6.8	125	3.6	4.2	5.4	5.6	5.8
IR26	IRRI	124	3.9	6.0	6.6	6.8	7.0	125	4.3	4.5	4.7	5.1	5.8
IR30	IRRI	108	2.6	5.1	6.1	6.6	6.7	105	3.2	4.8	4.9	5.0	4.8
Ajral (IR480-5-9)	Fiji	115	3.4	4.6	5.7	5.2	5.3	116	2.9	3.5	3.3	3.8	4.4
BG 90-2	Sri Lanka	130	5.3	7.0	7.2	7.1	7.2	129	3.9	4.3	4.9	5.1	5.1
BKN 6809-74-40	Thailand	115	3.7	5.1	5.2	5.1	4.1	129	3.8	4.2	3.4	3.3	3.0
C4-63G	Philippines	130	3.3	5.7	6.0	6.1	5.1	130	3.0	3.7	3.4	3.2	3.1
Chianung Sen Yu-6	Taiwan	116	2.8	5.5	6.1	6.6	6.7	123	3.7	4.6	4.8	4.9	5.0
Jayanti (IET 1039)	India	116	3.9	5.0	5.5	5.9	5.7	129	4.0	4.3	4.7	4.1	5.0
Joachin A-74	Mexico	130	3.0	5.7	6.4	6.6	6.8	—	—	—	—	—	—
Pelita	Indonesia	134	4.1	5.8	6.5	5.9	6.3	—	—	—	—	—	—
Biplab	Bangladesh	—	—	—	—	—	—	123	3.6	4.6	5.3	5.4	6.1
B9C-md-3-3	Indonesia	—	—	—	—	—	—	102	2.5	3.1	3.4	3.6	2.6
Peta	Indonesia	137	4.3	4.4	3.0	1.7	2.0	132	2.0	2.3	1.7	0.4	1.1

^aIncludes 30 kg N/ha topdressed at panicle initiation in the dry season and 20 kg N/ha in the wet season, excludes 0 kg N/ha treatment. ^bLSD (5%) = 1.0 t/ha. ^cLSD (5%) = 1.0 t/ha.

Joachin A-74 (from Mexico), and Chianung Sen Yu-6 (Taiwan). Brown planthopper incidence was not serious during the 1975 dry season.

During the wet season, Biplab from Bangladesh gave relatively high yield at both low and high fertility levels. At 120 kg N/ha, its yield was 6.1 t/ha, comparable to that of IR8 and IR26. Lodging at high nitrogen levels caused relatively low yields in C4-63G (Philippines) and in BKN 6809-74-40 (Thailand). As in the dry season, there were no serious pest and disease problems except for bacterial blight at the heading stage on Ajral (Fiji).

YIELD PERFORMANCE AND NITROGEN RESPONSE UNDER RAINFED LOWLAND CONDITIONS

Agronomy Department

IRRI farm. Eight promising lines and eight varieties were evaluated under rainfed lowland conditions during the 1975 wet season. The rainfall distribution was good so there was no serious drought problem. During a 20-day dry spell shortly after transplanting, however, soil moisture tension rose to 13 centibars. This may have caused some nitrogen loss by nitrification and subsequent denitrification, which could explain the low tiller number and irregular growth.

IR2071-105-9 yielded highest, 4.8 t/ha, followed by IR32 and IR2071-625-1 with 4.5 t/ha each, at 120 kg N/ha (Table 7). IR5, IR2070-414-3, IR2070-423-2, and IR2071-105-9 yielded well at 60 kg N/ha. Neck rot blast of IR442-2-58 was serious at the flowering stage, but yield was 4.1 t/ha at 120 kg N/ha (Table 7).

Farmers' fields. In rainfed experiments in a farmer's field in Laguna province, Philippines, IR26, IR32, and IR2071-588-5 produced more than 5 t/ha, with IR2071-588-5 yielding 5.8 t/ha (Table 5). Rainfall distribution was very good, stands were good, and there were no serious pests problems. Insecticide was applied only twice—carbofuran at 5 days after transplanting and lindane at 95 days.

GROWTH DURATION

Plant Breeding Department

The demand for early-maturing varieties continues to increase and our breeding program appropriately emphasizes this trait. We have intercrossed many promising sources to combine earliness with strong pest resistance. IR28 (105 days duration at Los Baños) and IR30 (110 days) were released in 1974 and have been well accepted. IR2071-625-1 (105 days) is an outstanding early selection that carries resistance to brown planthopper (*bph 2*), gall midge, and all major diseases and insect pests in the

Table 7. Yields of rice varieties and elite lines at five levels of nitrogen^a under rainfed condition (av. of three replications). IRRI, 1975 wet season.

Designation	Maturity (days)	Yield ^b (t/ha)				
		0 kg N/ha	30 kg N/ha	60 kg N/ha	90 kg N/ha	120 kg N/ha
IR5	128	2.7	3.5	4.1	4.2	4.1
IR26	125	2.7	3.1	3.4	3.2	4.2
IR28	107	2.1	3.2	3.6	4.0	4.1
IR30	107	2.2	3.1	3.8	3.7	4.0
IR32	132	2.6	3.8	3.7	3.8	4.5
IR34	125	2.8	3.5	3.7	3.7	3.5
IR442-2-58	107	1.9	2.6	3.0	3.8	4.1
IR1632-93-2	118	2.3	3.6	3.5	3.9	4.2
IR2061-522-6	107	2.4	2.8	3.2	3.7	3.8
IR2070-414-3	118	2.9	3.8	4.0	3.9	3.9
IR2070-423-2	125	2.8	3.2	4.2	3.8	4.1
IR2071-105-9	128	2.6	3.7	4.1	4.1	4.8
IR2071-588-5	132	2.6	3.1	3.5	3.5	4.4
IR2071-625-1	107	2.2	3.4	3.8	3.9	4.5
IR2153-26-3	118	2.2	2.9	3.0	3.3	3.3
C4-63G	119	2.5	3.2	3.5	4.2	3.6

^aIncludes 20 kg N/ha topdressed at panicle initiation, excludes 0 kg N/ha treatment. ^bLSD (5%) for comparing two nitrogen means of same variety or different varieties = 0.7 t/ha; two variety means at same nitrogen level = 0.5 t/ha.

1. Effect of time of harvest of the main crop on grain yield of the ratoon crop of two experimental lines (av. of four replications). IRRI, 1974 wet season.

Philippines. These varieties and selections still lack the desired levels of seedling and vegetative vigor, so we are emphasizing these traits in our crossing and early-generation screening.

We are also developing photoperiod-sensitive types for the vast areas where planting and harvesting must be geared to the season to allow for drying and storage of the crop. We now have F_4 lines of dwarf and intermediate stature that are sensitive to photoperiod and have broad disease and insect resistance.

PLANT TYPE

Plant Breeding Department

We continued to emphasize the development of rices of intermediate stature. During 1975, an intermediate-height line, IR2061-213-2, was named IR34. It is highly resistant to many diseases and insects in the Philippines and is being extensively used in further crosses. Based on crosses evaluated to date (some of them now in the F_5 generation), IR34 appears to be an excellent parent. Unlike most other intermediate-statured rices, IR34 combines well for desirable agronomic type. Lines from these and other crosses involving intermediate stature were included in the International Rice Testing Program.

RATOONING ABILITY

Agronomy and Plant Breeding Departments

Rice stubble left in the soil after the harvest of the main crop contains rudimentary buds in the

Table 8. Ratooning abilities of IRRI breeding lines expressed as percent ratoon (means of four replications). IRRI, 1975 dry season.

Designation	Cross	Ratoon ^a (%)
IR2061-423-1	Peta ³ /TN1//GP 15//IR1561-149//IR24 ⁴ / <i>O. nivara</i>	84 a
IR2145-20-4	<i>O. nivara</i> /4/(IR8/3/CP 231/SLO-17//NMS 4) ⁴	65 b
IR2145-13-3	"	59 bc
IR1924-30-2	<i>O. nivara</i> /4/IR8//CP 231/SLO-17//NMS 4	53 bcd
IR2071-11-4	IR1561-228//IR24 ⁴ / <i>O. nivara</i> /3/CR94-13	44 cde
IR2070-401-3	IR20 ² / <i>O. nivara</i> /CR94-13	4 fg
IR2070-837-2	"	0 g
IR2071-588-5	IR1561-228//IR24 ⁴ / <i>O. nivara</i> /3/CR94-13	0 g
IR2071-838-4	"	0 g

$$^a \text{Ratoon (\%)} = \left(\frac{\text{Ratoon tillers/hill (no.)}}{\text{Main crop tillers/hill (no.)}} \times 100 \right)$$

Any two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

axils of the leaves, especially at the lower nodes. These resting buds are in various stages of development; most are longer at the lower nodes and shorter at the upper nodes. Under favorable conditions, these resting buds may grow into a second, or ratoon, crop of tillers.

Rice is ratooned commercially in several countries, but not widely in the tropics. If appropriate varieties were available, however, ratooning might be practical and profitable.

Ratoon varieties would have to be highly resistant to the rice virus diseases because virus at any growth stage in the first crop will render the ratoon crop useless—even though the main crop might not have been significantly damaged.

To evaluate our virus-resistant advanced lines for ratooning ability, we harvested the main crop at 5 days before optimum maturity by cutting it at 25 cm above the ground (fig. 1 and 2). We then compared the ratoon crops.

We found major differences in ratooning—from 0 to 84 percent—among the breeding lines. Table 8 lists the lines that gave a good ratoon crop, as well as several that failed to ratoon. The non-ratooning lines may be useful for minimum-tillage cropping systems where ratoon rice is undesirable.

IRRI agronomists evaluated the prospect of raising a main rice crop followed by a ratoon rice crop during a single dry season in 1975. A

2. Effect of the height at which the main crop is cut on the grain yield of the ratoon crop of two experimental lines (av. of four replications). IRRI, 1974 wet season.

Table 9. Yields and field durations of six IRRI varieties and lines grown under different management systems (av. of four replications). IRRI, 1974 dry season.

Treatment	Yield (t/ha) ^a			Field duration (days)		
	1st crop	2nd crop	Total	1st crop	2nd crop	Total
<i>Transplanted fb^b transplanted</i>						
IR2061-464-2	5.6	4.6	10.2	94	89	183
IR1561-228-3	6.4	5.3	11.7	88	89	177
IR747B ₂ -6	4.8	3.9	8.7	80	85	165
IR28	7.0	4.4	11.4	94	89	183
IR2061-465-1	4.6	4.5	9.1	85	92	177
IR2061-632-3	5.0	4.4	9.4	85	95	180
<i>Transplanted fb direct seeded</i>						
IR2061-464-2	5.6	3.7	9.3	94	103	197
IR1561-228-3	6.8	3.6	10.4	88	109	197
IR747B ₂ -6	4.4	3.2	7.6	80	94	174
IR28	6.8	2.8	9.6	94	103	197
IR2061-465-1	4.8	4.1	8.9	85	112	197
IR2061-632-3	4.9	3.8	8.7	85	112	197
<i>Transplanted fb ratoon</i>						
IR2061-464-2	4.9	1.5	6.4	94	69	163
IR1561-228-3	6.4	1.2	7.6	88	65	153
IR747B ₂ -6	4.4	0.7	5.1	80	55	135
IR28	6.6	2.1	8.7	94	73	167
IR2061-465-1	4.8	1.6	6.4	85	87	172
IR2061-632-3	5.2	2.1	7.3	85	57	142

^aLSD (5%) = 1.0 t/ha. ^bfb = followed by.

Table 10. Yields of the second crop of six IRRI varieties and lines grown under different management systems (av. of four replications). IRRI, 1974 dry season.

Second crop	Yield ^a (t/ha)					
	IR2061-464-2	IR1561-228-3	IR747B ₂ -6	IR8	IR2061-465-1	IR2061-632-3
Ratoon	1.5 c	1.2 c	0.7 b	2.1 c	1.6 b	2.1 b
Direct seeded	3.7 b	3.6 b	3.2 a	2.8 b	4.1 a	3.8 a
Transplanted	4.6 a	5.3 a	3.9 a	4.4 a	4.5 a	4.4 a

^aIn each column, any two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

first crop of 21-day-old seedlings of six IRRI varieties and lines were transplanted at 20- × 20-cm spacing. Shortly after harvesting this first crop, we produced a second crop by three methods: ratooning, transplanting, and direct seeding on zero-tillage plots. The experimental design was a split plot with four replications. The main crop was for the cropping systems (first and second crop) and the subplots were for rice cultivars.

The first crop was fertilized at 90-20-20 kg/ha of N-P₂O₅-K₂O given in three split doses, 30-20-20 kg/ha as basal and the rest broadcast in two equal split doses at panicle initiation and heading stages. For the second crop, 40-20-20 kg/ha of fertilizer was applied as a single application.

The two crops of transplanted rice yielded highest, and the transplanted-followed-by-

Table 11. Percent infection of grassy stunt virus disease in the ratoon crop of six IRRI varieties and experimental lines (av. of four replications). IRRI, 1974 dry season.

Designation	Virus infection ^a (%)
IR2061-464-2	0.4 b
IR1561-228-3	79.5 a
IR747B ₂ -6	6.8 b
IR28	0.7 b
IR2061-465-1	0.8 b
IR2061-632-3	0.6 b

^aAny two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

ratoon crops, lowest (Table 9).

We found clear varietal differences in the ability to produce grain in the ratoon crop (Table 10). The ratoon crops of all rices were infected with varying degrees of grassy stunt virus (Table 11), even though the second crops of both direct-seeded and transplanted rice were not infected. This further confirms that rice varieties selected for ratooning must have high levels of disease resistance.

The ratoon crops of IR28, IR2061-464-2, and IR2061-632-3 yielded from 1.5 to 2.0 t/ha in from 57 to 73 days. These three lines also had less virus infection (Table 11).

Genetic evaluation and utilization (GEU) program

Grain quality

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SUMMARY

We continue to emphasize intermediate amylose content as a desirable grain characteristic. Among high-amylose rices, we selected for soft rather than for hard gel consistency.

Breeders and chemists showed that gelatinization temperature, as indexed by the alkali test, is controlled by a single gene in an inheritance study of crosses between rices of low and high gelatinization temperature. The characteristic of high gelatinization temperature was incompletely dominant over that of low gelatinization temperature. Studies of dosage effect on amylose content in milled rice showed that nonwaxy (high-amylose) starch was partially dominant to waxy (no amylose) starch and that high amylose was partially dominant to low amylose in nonwaxy rices. Studies on the F_1 , F_2 , and B_1F_1 seed generations of a cross between high- and low-amylose nonwaxy rices demonstrated a more complicated mode of inheritance. The waxy gene was found to be located on chromosome 3.

Physiologists subjected grains of two varieties to various day/night temperatures during ripening, and found that high mean temperature generally resulted in lower grain weight, higher protein content of brown rice, higher gelatinization temperature, and lower amylose content. Temperature had no consistent effect on gel consistency.

A taste panel tested 12 high-amylose rices and found no correlation between gel consistency and cohesiveness and tenderness. Taste panel scores were significantly negatively correlated with amylograph setback viscosity, which in turn was highly correlated with gel consistency and viscosity.

Replacement of air with nitrogen gas did not inhibit changes during storage of rice. In addition, the *epsilon*-amino group of the lysine residues of protein remained free during storage, indicating that the nutritional value of the protein did not decrease.

Analysis by scanning electron microscope showed that the nature of the cleavage plane of the rice grain on cracking—intercellular or intracellular—was not simply related to compactness of cell contents but was affected by other factors. Native starch granules showed little surface corrosion on HCl digestion but there were varietal differences in corrosion pattern with α -amylase. The extent of HCl corrosion was negatively correlated with gelatinization temperature but was not related to α -amylolysis loss.

Amylose content was shown to be a major factor that affects volume expansion during popping of heated raw rice and the texture of yeast-leavened rice bread.

Enzymic studies in developing rice grain showed the presence of 3-phosphoglycerate phosphatase with maximum activity at 13 days after flowering. An α -hydroxy acid oxidase that utilized L-lactate better than glycolate was also demonstrated in developing rice grain and in rice roots.

BREEDING PROGRAM

Plant Breeding Department

We have emphasized intermediate amylose content in our selection work for several seasons because it is characteristic of rices that are most widely preferred. We have also selected for soft gel consistency among lines having high amylose content. We now have large numbers of

Table 1. Inheritance of gelatinization temperature in the cross IR810-13-3/IR841-55-1. IRRI, 1975.

Plant	Generation	Gelatinization temperature				χ^2 (5%)
		Observed frequency of plants ^a			Expected ratio	
		High	Segregating	Low		
F_1	F_2	0	27	0	0:1:0	
F_2	F_3	46	115	47	1:2:1	2.34
B_1F_1 to high	B_1F_2	0	33	31	0:1:1	0.06
B_1F_1 to low	B_1F_2	15	17	0	1:1:0	0.13

^aFrom analysis of 36 grains/plant.

improved lines with both of these desirable grain quality traits, along with disease and insect resistance, favorable agronomic characteristics, and other traits desirable for modern varieties. We entered many of these lines in advanced evaluation trials during 1975 and distributed them widely through the International Rice Testing Program.

We identified promising selections from the cross IR3351 (IR841-85/IR1917-3-17//CR94-13) which combine the aromatic properties of the Thai variety Khao Dawk Mali (a parent of IR841-85) with disease and insect resistance and outstanding agronomic type. These lines will enter advanced evaluation trials during 1976 and will be distributed for testing through the International Rice Observational Nursery.

FACTORS THAT AFFECT GRAIN QUALITY *Chemistry, Plant Breeding, and Plant Physiology Departments*

Inheritance studies (*Plant Breeding and Chemistry*). *Gelatinization temperature.* We studied the inheritance of BEPT (gelatinization or birefringence end-point temperature) of starch, using alkali digestibility of milled rice as the BEPT index. In a cross of the high-BEPT line IR1168-7-1 with the low-BEPT line IR1008-76-3, all 58 F₁ seeds gave intermediate BEPT reaction in the alkali test. In two crosses involving low-BEPT parents (IR1008-66-1/IR8 and IR1168-7-1/IR810-13-3), all F₁ seeds gave low BEPT reactions.

A more detailed study was made in the low BEPT/high BEPT cross IR810-13-3/IR841-55-1. Both parents have low amylose content. The results indicate single incompletely dominant gene inheritance of high BEPT (Table 1).

Amylose content. The dosage effect of waxy and nonwaxy genes on the amylose content of milled rice was studied in hybrid seeds using the lines IR933-83-4 and IR933-85-3 as nonwaxy parents and IR933-2-6 as a waxy parent. Hybrid seeds were produced by using the hot water emasculatation technique, and were analyzed for amylose content with an autoanalyzer. All three sister lines had low BEPT. For both crosses, the waxy gene was shown to be incompletely recessive to nonwaxy allele since amylose con-

Table 2. Amylose content in milled rice in reciprocal crosses of IR933 nonwaxy and waxy parent.^a IIRI, 1975.

Endosperm genotype	Seeds (no.)	Amylose (% dry basis)	
		Range	Mean ^b
		<i>IR933-83-4/IR933-2-6</i>	
WxWxWx	20	23.8-27.8	25.4 b
WxWxwx	26	17.5-24.6	21.4 d
wxwxWx	12	14.1-21.4	19.2 e
wxwxwx	20	0	0 f
		<i>IR933-85-3/IR933-2-6</i>	
WxWxWx	20	25.4-27.4	26.6a
WxWxwx	34	18.4-27.2	24.2 c
wxwxWx	39	16.0-23.9	20.8 de
wxwxwx	20	0	0 f

^aIR933-2-6 was the common waxy parent. Single-grain analysis was done with an autoanalyzer. ^bMeans followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

tent decreased in the heterozygous genotypes Wx Wx wx and wx wx Wx (Table 2).

A similar study on three sets of high-amylose and low-amylose parents showed some decrease in amylose with an increase in the low-amylose gene, also indicating only partial dominance of high amylose over low amylose (Table 3).

The inheritance of amylose content in the cross involving IR810-2-3 (high amylose) and IR810-13-3 (very low amylose), both of which had low BEPT, was more complex than the inheritance of gelatinization temperature. F₁ endosperm (milled rice) had amylose content intermediate to that of the two parents but closer to that of the high-amylose parent (fig. 1). Amylose analysis of F₂ endosperm showed a

Table 3. Amylose content in milled rice in reciprocal crosses involving high-amylose and low-amylose nonwaxy parents. IIRI, 1975.

Endosperm genotype	Seeds (no.)	Amylose ^a (% dry basis)	
		Range	Mean
		<i>IR8/IR1537-79-1^b</i>	
H	10	24.6-27.0	25.7a
H/L	20	23.2-26.8	25.0a
L/H	30	7.8-22.7	16.1 b
L	10	10.5-15.6	13.1 c
		<i>IR810-2-3/IR810-13-3^b</i>	
H	20	22.7-28.5	26.4a
H/L	20	18.9-22.5	21.2 b
L/H	19	13.6-21.2	18.2 c
L	20	2.9- 8.1	6.1 d
		<i>IR1008-66-1/IR1008-76-3^b</i>	
H	10	24.9-26.3	25.4a
H/L	20	21.2-24.6	23.3 b
L/H	20	13.8-19.2	16.9 c
L	10	10.6-13.8	12.9 d

^aSingle-grain amylose analysis with an autoanalyzer. ^bHigh-amylose (H) and low-amylose (L) parent, respectively. Any two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

1. Distribution of parents, F₁, F₂, and backcrossed grains by milled-rice amylose in the high/low amylose cross IR810-2-3/IR810-13-3. Horizontal lines show the range of the parents and F₁ samples about the means (dotted circles). IIRRI, 1975.

bimodal distribution and amylose content that ranged as widely as that of the parents. B₁F₁ to the high-amylose parent gave mostly high-amylose milled rice. B₁F₁ to the low parent showed an amylose distribution of approximately 1 low: 1 high.

Location of waxy gene (Plant Breeding). The waxy gene was found to be located on chromosome 3 using primary trisomic stocks developed at IIRRI. Nonwaxy primary trisomics were crossed with the waxy disomic variety IR29; the waxy gene in the triplo-3/IR29 cross segre-

Table 4. Segregation of the waxy gene in pollen grains of F₁ plants of 11 trisomics/IR29 crosses. IIRRI, 1975.

Trisomic parent	Observed frequency		X ² ^a (1:1)
	Nonwaxy	Waxy	
Triplo-1	376	410	1.47
Triplo-2	503	501	0.00
Triplo-3	928	225	428.63
Triplo-5	224	243	2.60
Triplo-6	794	812	0.20
Triplo-7	847	905	1.92
Triplo-8	459	518	3.56
Triplo-9	666	694	0.57
Triplo-10	799	869	2.93
Triplo-11	720	761	1.13
Triplo-12	1130	1200	2.10
Disomic	426	424	0.00

^aX² (5%) = 3.84.

gated in trisomic ratio while all others segregated in disomic ratio (Tables 4 and 5).

Ripening temperature and grain quality (Plant Physiology and Chemistry). We analyzed for grain quality samples of grain of Fujisaka 5 and IR20 that matured at various day/night temperatures in the phytotron. At a mean temperature of above 22°C, both varieties tended to have lower grain weight, higher protein content of brown rice, and lower alkali spreading and clearing values of milled rice (higher gelatinization temperature of starch). The percentage of chalky grains was high above a mean temperature of 30°C. Milled rice of Fujisaka 5 tended to have progressively lower amylose content (22% to 14%) as mean temperature increased. By contrast, IR20 was sensitive to low temperature and showed the lowering amylose trend only at above 29°C. Grains of IR20 that ripened at below 20°C had low grain weight, were chalky, and had lower amylose content and higher protein content than those that ripened at higher temperatures. Temperature did not have a consistent effect on gel consistency. IR20 is more sensitive to low temperature, probably because it is a tropical (indica) variety, while Fujisaka 5 is a temperate (japonica) rice.

Gel consistency and eating quality (Chemistry). Twelve high-amylose rices differing in gel consistency were tested by a taste panel for cohesiveness and tenderness of boiled rice at the Institute of Human Ecology, University of the Philippines at Los Baños. Neither gel

Table 5. Trisomic segregation of the waxy gene with triplo-3 stocks. IRRI, 1975.

Cross	Generation	Observed frequency		Expected ratio	χ^2
		Nonwaxy	Waxy		
Triplo-3/IR29	F ₁ pollen	928	225	4:1	0.160 ^{ns}
Triplo-3/IR29//IR29	BC ₁ seeds	100	23	4:1	0.018 ^{ns}
Triplo-3/IR29	F ₂ seeds	1876	182	11:1 ^a	0.701 ^{ns}

^aThis expected ratio is based on 33% transmission of the extra chromosome 3 through the female and zero transmission through the male.

consistency nor gel viscosity of milled rice was significantly correlated with cohesiveness or tenderness scores, nor with stickiness values (by the beam-balance method) of boiled rice. Stickiness by the beam-balance method, however, positively correlated with scores for cohesiveness ($r = 0.84^{**}$) and tenderness ($r = 0.81^{**}$). Cohesiveness and tenderness scores were positively correlated ($r = 0.97^{**}$). Gel consistency and gel viscosity values of raw rice were negatively correlated ($r = -0.85^{**}$).

Amylograph peak viscosity of rice flour significantly correlated with gel viscosity ($r = 0.62^*$). By contrast, the negative correlation of amylograph setback viscosity (a measure of gel setting during cooling) and gel consistency was highly significant ($r = -0.73^{**}$); the positive correlation with gel viscosity was also highly significant ($r = 0.72^{**}$). Amylograph setback viscosity was significantly correlated with stickiness value ($r = -0.65^*$) and with tenderness and cohesiveness scores (both $r = -0.59^*$), but was not significantly correlated with amylograph peak viscosity.

Although the taste panel could not detect textural differences of boiled rices of different gel consistency, by using a commercial food tester we were able to distinguish differences in cohesiveness and tenderness values between IR5 and IR8 rices cooked in excess water. The sample of IR8 had a harder gel consistency than that of IR5. In the cohesiveness test, IR8 gave a lower maximum load value than IR5, but it was more "rubbery" (did not crumble readily) and sustained the maximum load longer. Its cooked rice was also more resistant to compression and extrusion in the tenderness test.

Changes in grain properties during storage (Chemistry). Earlier studies showed that some changes during rice storage, such as the con-

version of unsaturated fatty acids to carbonyl compounds and of sulfhydryl groups of protein to disulfide bonds, are oxidative in nature (1974 Annual Report). Since air is 20 percent O₂, we studied the effect of excluding O₂ during storage on the changes in grain properties. Samples were stored in desiccators under N₂ and O₂ atmospheres at 0–4°C and at 29°C. The properties of samples stored for 6 mo. showed that exclusion of O₂ did not reduce the rate of change in grain properties.

Spanish workers have simulated storage changes in milled rice by exposing grains to formaldehyde vapors. Since this reaction with protein involves condensation with the free amino groups of protein, particularly with lysine, samples of stored IR480-5-9 milled rice (control and defatted) were analyzed for 2, 4-dinitrofluorobenzene-reactive (free) lysine at the Department of Applied Biology, University of Cambridge, England. The data indicated that the *epsilon*-amino groups of the lysine residues of rice protein remained free during grain storage. The results suggest that the nutritional value of rice protein remains high during storage and that the natural mechanism of rice aging does not involve condensation of carbonyl compounds with amino groups of protein.

Surface ultrastructure of cells and starch granules (Chemistry). Varietal differences in the surface ultrastructure of endosperm cells of rices that differ in endosperm translucency and of native and modified starch granules of rices that differ in amylose content and BEPT (gelatinization temperature) were studied by the Flour Milling and Baking Research Association, Chorleywood, England. Examination by a scanning electron microscope of the fracture face of the rice endosperm verified that opacity in nonwaxy rice, such as the white belly of IR5

WAXY CENTURY PATNA 231

CRUMBLY RICE

IR480-5-9 GRANULES

2. Differences in surface corrosion of rice starch granules as shown by scanning electron microscopy of: Waxy Century Patna 231; a crumbly rice; and IR480-5-9 granules. In waxy rice, the attack was characterized by many medium-sized pits and all granules were uniformly corroded. In crumbly rice, a range of patterns of attack was evident—sponge-like appearance, some medium-sized holes, and layering—while others showed little corrosion. Some IR480-5-9 granules showed layering revealed by uniform erosion of their surfaces. Specimens were coated with gold applied by sputtering. Flour Milling and Baking Research Association, Chorleywood, England, 1975.

and IR8 and the opaque endosperm of crumbly rice, was caused by the loose arrangement of cell contents (1966 Annual Report). By contrast, the endosperm of waxy rice (IR833-6-2) showed only a mealy portion in the ventral region, although the whole endosperm is opaque. The nature of the cleavage plane—intercellular or intracellular—was not simply related with compactness of cell contents but was affected by other factors. For example, crumbly rice showed predominantly intercellular cleavage planes. Also the dorsal and ventral regions of white-belly varieties IR5 and IR8 had similar ratios of the two types of cleavage planes, although opacity was mainly in the ventral (belly) region.

Native starch granules were fairly angular in all samples except for crumbly rice. They differed in degree of indentation and signs of attack by α -amylase. Corrosion with 2.2 N HCl for 4 days at 35°C resulted in little change in surface structure of the granules, although 31–47 percent of weight was lost. By contrast, α -amylolysis resulted in extensive surface corrosion and in varietal differences in corrosion pattern (fig. 2). Waxy granules showed the fastest and most uniform pitting on α -amylolysis with many holes per granule. Nonwaxy granules showed varying degrees of corrosion within a sample. Extent of acid corrosion was confirmed to be negatively correlated with BEPT of starch. Varietal differences in α -amylolysis weight loss were not simply correlated with BEPT and amylose content of the starch granule among nonwaxy rices. The contrasting effects of HCl and α -amylase on the surface of the rice starch granule may be explained by the greater steric requirement of α -amylase, a protein, compared with that of the hydronium ion, which readily diffuses throughout the granule. The steric requirements of α -amylolysis, however, seemed to be less in waxy granules than in nonwaxy granules, as indicated by the smaller pit size and the faster rate of corrosion of the waxy granule.

Processed rice products (*Chemistry*). *Amylose content and popping quality*. Waxy rice has been reported to have a greater popped volume than that of nonwaxy rice. Also we have found that amylose content correlated negatively with puffed volume of parboiled rice (1972 Annual

Report). We determined the popping quality of milled rice of 10 samples by heating the rice in vegetable oil at 215–230°C for 15–20 seconds. Waxy rices expanded most in volume when popped, but varietal differences were also noted. Immature IR29 grains expanded less than did mature grains. Freshly harvested IR29 brown rice with 24 percent moisture expanded more on popping than did IR29 milled rice at 14 percent moisture. Crumbly rice, which has a loose arrangement of cell contents, expanded less than did other nonwaxy rices. Hence, many factors affect the popping quality of raw rice. These include amylose and moisture contents of the grain and compactness of cell contents.

Yeast-leavened rice bread. Earlier studies indicated that amylose content is a major factor affecting the quality of fermented rice cake. A preliminary study was made of the effect of properties of rice starch on the texture of a yeast-leavened rice bread. The effects of various factors on bread volume were determined using IR22 milled-rice flour with the formulation developed recently by the Western Regional Research Laboratory in California, modified to include methyl cellulose rather than hydroxypropyl methyl cellulose. Wet-milled flour gave better loaf volume than did dry-milled flour, even when both were screened through a 170-mesh sieve. Increasing the water content in the formulation from 75 to 140 percent of the rice flour increased the loaf volume and improved the texture of the bread crumb. But some cracks appeared on the surface of the bread. A higher level (150%) resulted in a coarser texture (larger air spaces). Wet-milled flour of IR24 rice with 17 percent amylose gave a lower loaf volume than flour of IR480-5-9 (23.0% amylose) and IR8 (26.4% amylose).

STARCH ACCUMULATION IN DEVELOPING RICE GRAINS

Chemistry Department

Enzymic studies. *Adenosine diphosphoglucose pyrophosphorylase.* Starch accumulation in the developing corn endosperm is reported to be regulated by the enzyme adenosine diphospho (ADP) glucose pyrophosphorylase, which converts glucose-1-phosphate to ADP glucose.

This enzyme is stimulated by 3-phosphoglycerate. Ammonium sulfate fractionation of crude enzyme extract from IR26 grains at the late milky stage (11–12 days after anthesis) showed that the pyrophosphorylase was concentrated in the 40–80 percent saturation precipitate. Addition of 2 μmol 3-phosphoglycerate enhanced the pyrophosphorylase activity by 40 percent.

3-Phosphoglycerate phosphatase. 3-Phosphoglycerate is the primary reaction product of photosynthetic carbon fixation of ribulose 1,5-diphosphate carboxylase in the chloroplast and is an allosteric effector of ADP glucose pyrophosphorylase in leaves and in developing corn seeds. We found 3-phosphoglycerate phosphatase to be present in developing rice grains. The enzyme may affect 3-phosphoglycerate concentration in the developing grain. Unlike the leaf phosphatase, this enzyme was present only in the soluble fraction and was not bound to the starch granules. Also, unlike the leaf enzyme, it was neither inhibited by EDTA nor stimulated by Mg^{+2} . In the dehulled grain, the green pericarp was the major site of the phosphatase. The $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ -precipitated enzyme showed higher specificity toward 3-phosphoglycerate than did phosphoglycolate, ribose-5-phosphate, ribulose-1, 5-diphosphate, glucose-6-phosphate, fructose-6-phosphate, and glucose-1-phosphate. The hull enzyme differed from the pericarp enzyme because it had comparable activity toward 3-phosphoglycerate and phosphoglycolate.

Total activity of 3-phosphoglycerate phosphatase increased progressively in the developing IR26 grain up to 13 days after flowering, after which it decreased. On the other hand, chlorophyll content maximized at about 9 days after flowering and then progressively decreased. The optimum pH for the enzyme was from 5.5 to 6.0.

α -Hydroxy acid oxidase. Glycolate oxidase was shown to have high activity in rice leaves and in green hulls of developing rice grains. However, an α -hydroxy acid oxidase was obtained from $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ precipitates of soluble protein from developing rice caryopsis (dough stage) and from rice roots, which had lower specific activity than leaf glycolate oxidase

and utilized L-lactate better than glycolate. Oxidation of glycolate, L-lactate and D-lactate by this oxidase was at the relative ratio of 1:1:0.2. By contrast, leaf glycolate oxidase has the ratio 1:0.3-0.5:0, and α -hydroxy acid oxidase of algae has 1:0:0.5. This oxidase was stimulated by 10^{-2} M KCN. It had a K_m (Michaelis constant) (glycolate) of 2×10^{-4} M and a K_m (L-lactate or D-lactate) of about 4×10^{-4} M. It coupled to O_2 but did not link to NAD reduction during aerobic oxidation. It might function as a lactate oxidase in roots and seeds where glycolate synthesis might be nil.

Water-soluble sugars. Water-soluble sugars other than sucrose, glucose, and fructose are

present in the developing rice grain. They may also be precursors of ADP glucose. We began to study the nature of the water-soluble sugars in the developing rice grain using the nonwaxy variety IR28 and the waxy IR29. Results with IR28 indicated that water-soluble sugars decreased progressively from 9.7 percent of dry matter at 3 days after flowering to 1.1 percent at maturity in the dehulled grain. The same trend was obtained on a per-grain basis. Besides the principal sugars (fructose, sucrose, and glucose) eight other sugars of slower mobility on paper and thin layer chromatography were present in minor amounts; at least two of them gave a positive test for keto sugars.

Genetic evaluation and utilization (GEU) program

Disease Resistance

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SUMMARY

Most of our 32 elite breeding lines are resistant to three or four major diseases; several are resistant to five. Almost all are resistant to bacterial blight and grassy stunt. Many are moderately resistant to sheath blight. Most lines have low incidence of bacterial leaf streak in the field but are susceptible when inoculated in the greenhouse. Many are susceptible to tungro and blast.

We screened several thousand new entries in the germ plasm bank to identify diverse sources of resistance. Two possible new sources of grassy stunt resistance are the crosses IR4497 (IR24//Zenith/M. Sungsong) and IR9560 (IR8³ ///IR8/Carreon//IR8/Tetep).

In blast resistance, we found further evidence of a close correlation among varieties between resistance of a qualitative (resistant to a number of races) and quantitative (resistance to intense disease pressure) nature. Data show differential interactions of races to bacterial blight. In genetic studies, a dominant inhibitory gene was found for bacterial blight resistance; using trisomic lines, we identified the resistant gene *Xa 4* on chromosome 7.

We studied the effect of tungro virus disease pressure on the field reactions of several IRRI varieties and found that all appear more susceptible at higher pressure but that disease reactions relative to pressure differ for each variety. The relative reactions of IR8 and the line IR1561-228-3 at low pressure were actually inverted at high pressure. IR34 was least affected and was most resistant under high disease pressure.

EVALUATING DISEASE RESISTANCE OF BREEDING MATERIALS

Plant Pathology Department

Reaction of elite lines to major diseases. We extensively tested IRRI's 32 elite lines selected in 1975. The tests included the blast nursery; field tests for sheath blight resistance; artificial inoculation for bacterial blight; artificial inoculation and field monitoring for bacterial leaf streak; and artificial inoculation and field tests for tungro and grassy stunt viruses (Table 1).

Most of the elite lines are resistant to bacterial blight and grassy stunt. Many are moderately resistant to sheath blight. Many are susceptible to bacterial leaf streak when artificially inoculated, but the incidence of disease is low on most in the field. Most advanced lines were resistant to tungro under field pressure at IRRI, but only a few were rated as strongly resistant by the intensive mass screening test in the greenhouse. Among these was IR34, whose tungro resistance derives from the Thai variety Gam Pai 15. Most of our advanced lines reacted variably to blast, but a few were consistently resistant in all tests.

Screening breeding materials for disease resistance. We screened thousands of breeding lines at different growth stages for disease resistance. The amounts and percentages of resistant materials for each major disease are summarized below:

Blast. A low percentage of the 45,000 breeding lines screened in the blast nursery were resistant (Table 2). Many more crosses have been made using as donors such resistant varieties as Tetep, Carreon, Dawn, Mamoriaka, Colombia 1, Ram Tulasi (Sel), T1, and *Oryza nivara*.

Sheath blight. About 3,900 entries were evaluated during both dry and wet seasons; Table 3 shows that a high percentage were rated as intermediate or moderately resistant, but very few were considered resistant.

Bacterial blight. About 50,000 lines at different breeding stages were evaluated for bacterial blight resistance by the clipping method using the most common strain of the bacterium (Table 4). Among them were 1,210 F₁ populations from multiple crosses and 2,543 F₂ bulk populations from 144 single crosses. We also tested 724 upland rice selections. A high percentage of resistant lines have been found in the breeding materials, especially among advanced lines.

Tungro. We scored the natural tungro infection of more than 24,500 lines from 300 crosses in pedigree nurseries. About 20 percent were rated as 3 or less on a scale of 0 to 9, where 9 is most susceptible.

Using the improved mass screening method in the greenhouse, we artificially inoculated and tested 1,138 selections for tungro resistance.

Table 1. Reactions^a of elite breeding lines to major diseases. IRRI, 1975.

Designation	Blast	Sheath blight	Bacterial blight	Bacterial leaf streak		Tungro virus	Grassy stunt virus
				Artificial inoculation	Field observation		
IR26	S	M	R	S	R	R	M
IR28	R	S	R	M	R	R	R
IR30	S	S	R	M	R	R	R
IR1561-228-3	S	S	R	M	R	S	M
IR1529-680-3	M	M	R	M	R	M	M
IR1632-93-2	S	M	M	S	R	S	R
IR2031-724-2	M	M	M	S	R	M	R
IR2035-290-2	R	M	R	S	R	M	R
IR2058-78-1	M	S	R	M	R	S	R
IR2061-213-2	R	M	—	M	—	R	R
IR2061-464-2	R	S	—	M	M	R	R
IR2061-465-1	M	S	R	S	M	R	R
IR2061-522-6	R	M	R	S	M	R	R
IR2061-628-1	R	M	R	M	R	R	R
IR2070-24-2	S	M	R	S	R	M	R
IR2070-320-6	S	M	R	M	R	S	R
IR2070-414-3	S	M	R	M	R	M	R
IR2070-423-2	M	M	R	M	R	S	R
IR2070-747-6	S	R	—	S	—	M	R
IR2070-863-1	S	M	R	M	M	S	R
IR2071-105-9	M	M	R	M	M	M	R
IR2071-137-5	M	M	M	M	M	M	R
IR2071-176-1	M	M	—	S	R	M	R
IR2071-179-9	M	M	R	—	R	M	R
IR2071-586-5	M	M	—	M	R	S	R
IR2071-588-5-1	M	—	R	M	R	S	R
IR2071-588-54-5	M	M	R	M	R	S	R
IR2071-588-5-2	M	M	R	M	M	S	R
IR2071-625-1	M	S	R	M	M	S	R
IR2071-636-5	R	M	R	M	R	S	R
IR2153-26-3	S	M	R	M	M	M	R
IR2153-338-3	S	S	R	M	R	M	R
IR2307-64-2	S	S	R	S	R	S	M
IR2328-300-2	R	M	R	S	R	R	R
IR2681-163-5	M	M	R	S	M	S	R

^aR = resistant; MR = moderately resistant; M = intermediate; MS = moderately susceptible; S = susceptible.

Forty-three percent of the selections had less than 30 percent infected seedlings (Table 5). In 1975, we had natural infection of tungro disease in the IRRI farm. Rows of six IRRI varieties were scattered in the pedigree nurseries as checks. The reaction to tungro of each replication (row) of each variety was scored by the Standard Evaluation System for rice on a scale of from 0 to 9. We considered scales 1 to 3 as resistant, 4 to 6 as intermediate, and 7 to 9 as susceptible.

The frequency distribution of the replications by their reactions to tungro disease (fig. 1) indicates the degree of variation to tungro resistance.

The degree of each variety's tungro resistance based merely on reaction to natural infection was difficult to determine because reactions of individual rices generally varied among repli-

cations. For instance, IR26 varied in reaction from scale 1 (resistant) to scale 9 (susceptible)

Table 2. Summary of screening results for blast resistance. IRRI, 1975.

Source	Entries (no.)		
	Resistant	Intermediate	Susceptible
World collection	456	1221	2031
Pedigree lines	12437	14401	9123
Observational yield trial	491	787	775
Replicated yield trial	106	350	266
International Rice			
Observational Nursery	53	138	144
Cold tolerance	354	933	579
Upland	216	354	592
Korean materials	4	37	344
Plant pathology lines	1592	941	401
IRTP 1976 nominees	52	30	182
Philippine Atomic			
Energy Commission	0	9	62
Total (no.)	15761	19201	14499
Total (%)	30.9	37.7	28.5

Table 3. Summary of screening results for sheath blight resistance. IRRI, 1975.

Source	Entries (no.) rated ^a as					
	R	MR	M	MS	S	VS
Elite breeding lines	1	12	15	15	5	1
Replicated yield trial	0	137	426	130	55	12
Observational yield trial	0	213	631	233	100	43
Upland	1	63	189	100	55	11
Plant pathology lines	6	271	879	222	58	10
Hybridization block, 72-W selections	0	20	40	13	5	3
Assam Rice Collection-selections	3	107	67	8	2	0
All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project	0	58	31	2	3	2
3rd International Rice Sheath Blight Nursery varieties	0	37	28	11	8	5
International Blast Nursery varieties	0	16	6	6	1	0
Bacterial blight resistant varieties	0	2	8	0	0	0
Germ plasm collection, 1974 selections	15	497	539	161	38	11
Germ plasm collection, 1975	4	1073	890	104	31	13
Total (no.)	30	2506	3764	1005	361	111
Total (%)	0.4	32.2	48.4	12.9	4.7	1.4

^aR = resistant; MR = moderately resistant; M = intermediate; MS = moderately susceptible; S = susceptible; VS = very susceptible.

in various replications. If a variety's average reaction indicates its tungro resistance, then the results from many replications under different conditions should be more reliable. Based on the average reactions (shown by the solid lines in fig. 1), the resistance to tungro disease was IR34 > IR28 > IR26 > IR30 > IR5 > IR8.

The validity of this rating may be subject to question, however, since the degree of disease pressure to which each variety was subjected may have differed. An indication of this pressure is the disease reaction of rice lines in the two rows immediately adjacent to the line or variety being tested (broken lines in fig. 1). Thus, we

note that the lines adjacent to IR28 and IR5 showed a relatively low average disease rating, suggesting that IR28 and IR5 may have been subjected to lower disease pressure than IR8, IR26, IR30, and IR34. The low disease rating of IR34 in contrast to the relatively higher disease pressure of the lines adjacent to it indicates that IR34 has a high degree of resistance.

Grassy stunt. We mass-screened 69,775 seedlings of 1,008 IRRI lines from 52 crosses for resistance to grassy stunt disease in the greenhouse. Of the tested lines, 759 had less than 30 percent infected seedlings. These resistant lines,

Table 4. Proportion of breeding materials that are resistant to bacterial blight. IRRI, 1975.

Source	Rices tested (no.)	Entries (no.) rated ^a as					
		R	MR	MS	S	R/S	R/MR
Observational yield trial	1420	688	62	33	596	41	0
Replicated yield trial	300	607	34	17	20	21	1
Hybridization block varieties	201	93	3	8	86	10	1
June 1975 pedigree nursery							
F4	1958	1792	0	0	68	98	0
F5	477	449	0	0	10	18	0
F6	549	520	0	0	14	15	0
F7	45	45	0	0	0	0	0
F8	3	3	0	0	0	0	0
Aug. 1975 pedigree nursery							
F3	6271	2441	0	0	490	3340	0
F4	3878	3324	0	0	241	313	0
F5	1109	969	0	0	59	81	0
Sept. 1975 pedigree nursery							
F3	7276	4114	0	0	657	2507	0
Total (no.)	23,487	15,045	99	58	2241	6444	2
Total (%)	100	62.3	0.4	0.2	9.5	27.4	0.0

^aR = resistant; MR = moderately resistant; MS = moderately susceptible; S = susceptible; R/S = resistant/susceptible; R/MR = resistant/moderately resistant.

except IR4497 (IR24//Zenith/M. Sungsong) and IR9560 (IR8³///IR8/Carreon//IR8/Tetep), carry the resistance gene from *Oryza nivara*.

We mass-screened 12,383 seedlings of 206 lines from Indonesia for grassy stunt resistance in the greenhouse. Seventy-seven lines showed less than 30 percent infected seedlings.

Seeds from 50 plants of IR30 were mass-screened four times for resistance to grassy stunt in the greenhouse. Twenty-nine individual plants showed from 0 to 10 percent infection; 14 plants, 11 to 30 percent; 4 plants, 31 to 60 percent; and 3 plants, 61 to 90 percent. Statistical analysis revealed significant differences between plants, but not between trials of the same plants.

Monitoring minor diseases in advanced lines.

We monitored the presence and severity of *Cercospora* leaf spot and leaf scald as they appeared in the experimental fields, particularly on advanced lines. Of the 276 entries of the replicated yield trial in the wet season, we considered 123 as susceptible to leaf scald and 47 to *Cercospora* leaf spot. In the continuous-cropping plots, IR28, IR29, and IR30 were susceptible to *Cercospora* while IR3265-112-2 was resistant.

IDENTIFYING AND INCORPORATING NEW SOURCES OF RESISTANCE

Plant Pathology and Plant Breeding Departments

Blast. Of the 4,942 entries of the germ plasm collection screened in the blast nursery at IRRI, 456 exhibited resistant reactions (Table 2). These will be further exposed to various races of blast in different seasons. Those repeatedly found resistant will be included in the International Blast Nursery to test their resistance over wide geographical regions.

Many highly resistant sources have been incorporated into selected rices, either singly or in combination. Some crosses that showed blast resistance from Tetep are IR3259, IR3262, IR4493, IR4494, IR4500, IR4510, IR4528, and IR4547; from Carreon, IR9669; from combined Carreon and Tetep, IR5533, IR9559, IR9560; from Dawn, IR3271, IR4472, IR9576; from combined Dawn and Kataktara, IR4492, IR4520, IR9660, and IR9679; from Zenith,

Table 5. Reaction to tungro of selected IRRI lines (1,138 selections from 114 crosses) tested by the improved mass-screening method. IRRI, 1975.

Cross no.	Seedlings infected (no.)		
	0-30%	31-60%	61-100%
IR2031	3	0	0
IR2034	13	0	0
IR2035	9	1	2
IR2039	4	1	0
IR2053	3	2	1
IR2061	25	5	0
IR2732	19	2	0
IR2733	20	7	5
IR3179	20	5	0
IR3295	12	1	0
IR4547	124	74	18
IR5490	15	4	1
IR9561	10	1	0
IR9577	33	32	3
IR9578	24	38	1
IR9585	18	22	1
IR9593	24	52	6
Other 97 crosses	111	263	103
Total	487	510	141

IR4484, IR4530, IR4532, and IR4543; from combined Zenith and Dawn, IR4531, IR4540, and IR4544; from C46-15, IR4467, IR9670, IR9671, IR9680; from Mamoriaka, IR9678 and IR9690. Other resistant lines come from Colombia 1, Ram Tulasi (Sel), T1, and *Oryza nivara*.

1. Frequency distribution of replications of rice varieties by their reactions to natural infection of tungro disease at the IRRI farm. The number of replications is in parentheses. The solid vertical line indicates the average reaction. Broken line indicates average disease reaction of rice lines in two adjacent rows, which gives some indication of the probable disease pressure. IRRI, 1975.

Table 6. Number of varieties from the germ plasm bank with resistance to isolate PXO 61 of *X. oryzae*, Philippines, 1975.

Origin	Entries (no.) rated ^a as				
	R	MR	S	R/S	Total
Africa			2		2
Bangladesh	293	167	152	16	628
Brazil	1		263		264
British Solomon Is.	1				1
China (Mainland)	1	5	32		38
Costa Rica		1	1		2
East Asia		5			5
Egypt		3	2		5
India	14	11	58		83
Indonesia	162	80	1937	1	2180
Iraq			5		5
Laos	13	35	725	21	794
Japan			2		2
Malaysia		4	241	3	248
Madagascar			2		2
Mexico		2			2
Nepal	1	1	8		10
Pakistan	11	19	1348	1	1379
Philippines	2	2	70		74
Sri Lanka	1	2	4		7
Taiwan	2		5		7
Thailand	8	9	231		248
U.S.A.		2			2
Vietnam		1			1
Total	510	349	5088	42	5989

^aR = resistant; MR = moderately resistant; S = susceptible; R/S = segregation.

Sheath blight. We screened about 3,900 entries in the two seasons; 2,115 were new varieties from the germ plasm collection, and the rest were retested to confirm earlier results (Table 3). More than 80 percent of the entries tested showed moderate resistance (M or MR); few were resistant.

Bacterial blight. During 1975, about 5,989 new varieties from the germ plasm collection were screened; 510 (8.5 percent) were rated R to the common isolate PXO 61, and 349 (5.8 percent) were rated MR (Table 6). The varieties will be

Table 7. Reaction of 426 rice varieties to three pathogenically distinct isolates of *Xanthomonas oryzae*, IRRI, 1975.

Reaction ^a	Rice varieties (%)		
	PXO 61	PXO 63	H100
R	63.6	5.9	0.2
MR	26.1	18.1	3.3
MS	7.3	3.5	13.1
S	5.4	72.5	83.4

^aR = resistant; MR = moderately resistant; MS = moderately susceptible; S = susceptible.

further tested in the general screening nursery to confirm their resistance against PXO 61, and in the screening house or greenhouse to test resistance to several isolates that are distinct in virulence.

Up to 1974, more than 700 varieties were found resistant to the bacterial pathogen. We inoculated 426 of these with three isolates that were distinct in virulence. We found that 64 percent were resistant to PXO 61, 6 percent to PXO 63, and 0.2 percent to H100 (Table 7). We observed differential interactions between the varieties and the three isolates.

Various combinations of varieties with broad spectrums of resistance have been crossed to diversify and build up levels of resistance.

Tungro. We tested 3,255 rice varieties from the germ plasm collection for tungro resistance by the improved mass-screening method in the greenhouse. Preliminary results indicated that 28 varieties are resistant.

Grassy stunt. We tested 1,026 rice varieties for grassy stunt resistance by the mass-screening method in the greenhouse; none were found as resistant to grassy stunt as *Oryza nivara*.

However, several F₄ selections from two crosses, IR4497 (IR24//Zenith/M. Sungsong) and IR9560 (IR8³///IR8/Carreon//IR8/Tetep) were confirmed to be highly resistant (Table 8). No parents were resistant to grassy stunt. The resistance gene or genes involved are being studied in relation to the resistance gene of *O. nivara*.

Table 8. Resistance of IR4497 and IR9560 lines to grassy stunt virus disease, IRRI, 1975.

Designation	Tests (no.)	Seedlings tested (no.)	Infection (%)
<i>IR4497 lines</i>			
IR4497-285-2-1	6	140	3
IR4497-285-2-2	14	300	4
IR4497-285-2-3	22	451	6
IR4497-285-4-1	20	388	4
IR4497-285-4-2	10	199	4
IR4497-285-4-3	14	276	2
IR4497-285-4-4	16	285	9
TN1 (check)	16	256	71
<i>IR9560 lines</i>			
IR9560-860-4-1	6	105	0
IR9560-860-4-2	6	102	1
IR9560-860-4-3	6	108	12
IR9560-863-7-2	6	93	0
IR9560-863-9-1	6	118	0
IR9560-863-9-3	6	112	0
TN1 (check)	12	161	80.5

2. Monthly frequency of Philippine races in the blast nursery. IRR1, 1974-75.

STUDIES ON DISEASE RESISTANCE

Plant Pathology and Plant Breeding Departments

Races of *Pyricularia oryzae* in blast nursery and new races. To study the races that occur in the blast nursery, we inoculated 518 isolates from monthly collections (taken from April 1974 to January 1975) to the eight international differential varieties and to the 12 Philippine differentials. The isolates were grouped into 69 races based on the reaction of the 12 Philippine differentials. Seven of these were new races, bringing the total number of Philippine races to 262 (Table 9). The frequency of races is shown in fig. 2. The most prevalent race was P8, consisting of 237 isolates (45.8%); followed

by P17, 61 isolates (17.4%); P20 (15%); P21 (15%); and P68 (11%). Other races have only a few isolates. Based on the reactions of the international race differentials, the isolates were classified into 37 races according to the standard international race numbers: IA-45, IA-46, IA-65, IA-66, IA-68, IA-69, IA-70, IA-74, IA-78, IA-86, IA-90, IA-97, IA-98, IA-101, IA-102, IA-105, IA-106, IA-109, IA-110, IA-111, IA-112, IA-113, IA-118, IA-121, IA-125, IA-126, IA-128, I-C1, ID5, ID-13, ID-14, ID-16, ID-20, IG-1, IG-2, and II-1. The most prevalent race is IA-110, with 260 isolates (50.1%). IA-109 has 104 isolates (20%) and was detected in 8 of the 10 months. Fifteen races appeared once, with one isolate each. This study

Table 9. New pathogenic races of *Pyricularia oryzae*. Philippines, 1975.

Philippine differential	Reaction ^a						
	P256	P257	P258	P259	P260	P261	P262
1. Katakara Da 2	R	R	S	R	S	R	R
2. CI 5309	R	S	R	S	S	S	S
3. Chokoto	R	S	R	S	R	S	R
4. CO 25	R	R	R	R	S	R	S
5. Wagwag	R	S	R	S	R	S	S
6. Paikantao	R	R	R	R	S	R	R
7. Peta	R	S	R	S	S	S	S
8. Raminad Strain 3	S	S	R	S	S	S	S
9. Taichung Ti-chio Wu-chen	R	S	S	S	S	S	S
10. Lacrose	R	S	S	S	S	S	S
11. Sha-tiao-tsao	S	S	S	R	S	S	S
12. Khao-tah-haeng 17	R	R	S	S	S	S	S

^aR = resistant; S = susceptible.

confirms our previous findings that many races occur at the same time in the field.

Relation between qualitative and quantitative resistance to blast. We have inoculated more than 3,000 isolates of the blast fungus in the past years and have identified 262 races based on the 12 Philippine differential varieties. We have also inoculated the isolates to the eight international differentials. Thus, we know the reactions to the different races of the 18 differential varieties (two are in both sets). Some had a high percentage of resistance to most races while others were susceptible to most and others were in-between. We refer to this reaction to races as qualitative resistance. We exposed the 18 varieties to the blast nursery at the seedling stage and then counted the lesions on each. The intensity of the disease (number of lesions) is

3. Correlation between quantitative resistance (number of leaf lesions) and qualitative resistance (percentage of resistance to Philippine races) of *Pyricularia oryzae*. IRRI, 1975.

referred to as quantitative resistance. We found a close negative correlation between qualitative and quantitative resistance. Varieties with higher percentages of resistance to races had fewer lesions (fig. 3). This seems to show that many races of blast are in a field and that a variety must have many resistant genes to confer stable resistance. Further tests may show even closer correlation because not all races are present at one time in the blast nursery.

Pathogenic variability of *X. oryzae*. Among the many inoculations on many varieties, we observed differential varietal reactions to the pathogenically distinct isolates PXO 61, PXO 63, and H100. We then tried to monitor the differential patterns of the three isolates on selected varieties. We observed six of the eight possible differential patterns (Table 10), but we did not observe the other two patterns (all varieties resistant to all isolates, and varieties resistant to PXO 61 and H100 but susceptible to PXO 63). The results suggest that the pathogenicity of these three isolates is highly distinct. We are continuing studies to confirm different pathogenic races of *X. oryzae*.

Isolates from Iloilo and Davao, Philippines. During the 1975 wet season, IR30, which carries a dominant gene for bacterial blight resistance, was found susceptible in Iloilo, in Panay Island, and in Davao, Mindanao, Philippines. A pathogenicity test of the isolates in these two places suggested their comparability with the Isabela strain of the bacterial pathogen reported in 1973 (Table 11). An isolate collected from Davao in 1963, B56, demonstrated a

Table 10. Differential interaction among three isolates of *Xanthomonas oryzae* and selected rice varieties. IRRI, 1975.

Variety	Reaction ^a					
	H 100		PXO 63		PXO 61	
	Lesions (cm)	Visual rating	Lesions (cm)	Visual rating	Lesions (cm)	Visual rating
Karopak	4.8	MR	6.4	MR	14.7	MS
Andel	3.0	MR	3.1	MR	10.6	MS
Boder	3.3	MR	7.6	MS	10.6	MS
Ketan Lumbu	4.5	MR	13.4	MS	14.1	MS
IR22	11.7	MR	14.8	MS	4.3	MR
Kolongi Bao	15.6	MR	14.2	MS	4.2	MR
DV85	18.3	MS	1.5	R	1.7	R
Habigonj Deep Water	17.2	MS	2.5	R	1.7	R
ARC 6076	27.2	S	0.4	R	17.2	MR
Pala Bhir	28.4	S	2.0	R	10.8	MR
Yakadawee	18.9	S	21.6	S	20.5	S
IR8	17.7	S	21.6	S	26.5	S

^aR = resistant; MR = moderately resistant; MS = moderately susceptible; S = susceptible.

virulence pattern similar to that of the ones that attack IR30. The strain of *X. oryzae* that overcomes the resistance of IR30 and related rices seems to have been present in the Davao area long before the resistant varieties were commercialized.

Genetic studies of bacterial blight resistance.

PI-Ig (a purple pigmented and liguleless line from Japan) is susceptible to the Philippine isolate PXO 61 of *Xanthomonas oryzae*. The F₁ of PI-Ig stock crossed with IR22 (which has dominant resistance to bacterial blight) was also susceptible. This suggests that PI-Ig stock might have a dominant inhibitory gene for bacterial blight resistance. To verify this, PI-Ig stock was crossed with IR3265-193 (a susceptible line). Some resistant plants were identified from the F₂ population of this cross, suggesting

that PI-Ig stock also has a resistance gene that does not express itself in the presence of inhibitory genes in this stock. Sixty randomly selected F₂ plants of the cross PI-Ig/IR3265-193 were crossed with IR22; the resulting hybrid progenies were grown and inoculated with the PXO 61 isolate at 50 days after seeding. Ten were resistant; 39, segregating; and 11, susceptible. Hybrid progenies of all susceptible plants probably came from F₂ plants that were homozygous for the inhibitory gene, while those that showed segregating reactions probably came from F₂ plants that were heterozygous for the inhibitory gene. Hybrid progenies with all resistant plants probably came from F₂ plants that were free of the inhibitory gene. Thus, the PI-Ig stock is obviously homozygous for an inhibitory gene. The resistance gene of

Table 11. Comparison of virulence patterns of new isolates of *X. oryzae* from Davao and Iloilo, Philippines, to those of other known Philippine isolates. IRRI, 1975.

Designation	Gene action	Reaction ^a									
		PXO 78		PXO 79		B56		PXO 63		PXO 61	
		Lesions (cm)	Visual rating	Lesions (cm)	Visual rating	Lesions (cm)	Visual rating	Lesions (cm)	Visual rating	Lesions (cm)	Visual rating
IR20	<i>Xa 4</i>	14.3	S	16.5	S	10.5	S	13.3	S	4.1	MR
IR30	<i>Xa 4</i>	17.8	S	14.8	S	11.1	MS	15.4	S	6.4	MR
IR1545-339	<i>Xa 5</i>	2.4	MR	2.7	MR	3.3	MR	2.4	MR	2.4	MR
BJ1	<i>Xa 5</i>	3.4	MR	2.5	MR	3.3	MR	2.6	MR	1.5	R
TN1	—	33.2	S	24.5	S	21.4	S	25.3	S	34.3	S
IR8	—	29.5	S	25.1	S	20.7	S	22.4	S	25.8	S

^aR = resistant; MR = moderately resistant; MS = moderately susceptible; S = susceptible. ^bIsolate from Iloilo on IR30. ^cIsolate from Davao on IR30.

this stock is being transferred to an indica background through a series of backcrosses with TN1, using resistant plants from the BC F₁ populations each time.

Primary trisomics (2n + 1 types) were used to locate the dominant gene for bacterial blight resistance (*Xa 4*) of IR29. The trisomic lines developed through the backcrosses are susceptible to bacterial blight because they received the recessive *xa 4* gene from IR3265-193-3, which carries the susceptibility. Eleven trisomic lines were crossed with IR29 as a pollinator. IR29 carries the dominant gene *Xa 4* for resistance. Reaction of the F₁ plants to the bacterium (strain PXO 61) indicated that two doses of the

recessive gene *xa 4* almost neutralized the action of a single dose of *Xa 4* gene, and that triplo-7 F₁ plants were moderately susceptible. Disomic sibs of triplo-7 (*Xa 4 xa 4*) showed resistant reactions, as usual. Bacterial blight reactions of F₁ plants (PXO 61) showed that all of the disomic and trisomic F₁ plants except for triplo-7 were resistant due to the *Xa 4* genetic constitution, indicating that none of their extra chromosomes included the locus for bacterial blight resistance. Hence, the *Xa 4* gene is probably located on chromosome 7. We hope to further study this observation in BC1 and F₂ generations in 1976.

Genetic evaluation and utilization (GEU) program

Insect resistance

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SUMMARY

We used seven varieties that are moderately resistant to striped borer in a diallele crossing program, selecting and further intercrossing resistant progenies. In the third generation, some lines of the IR4791 and IR4797 crosses were found to be more resistant than any parent. IR1820-52-82 is the most resistant line to yellow borer yet identified.

We identified an additional 1,061 lines resistant to green leafhopper; 427 to brown planthopper; and 87 to white-backed planthopper. Included were 160 varieties of the African species *Oryza glaberrima* which were highly resistant to green leafhopper, but not to brown planthopper.

More than 25,500 varieties were screened against whorl maggot, but none were identified as resistant. But the elite line IR2070-414-3 was rated moderately resistant in the field. We are further testing about 20,000 progenies of the IR2070 cross.

Biochemical studies on the nature of resistance indicated that the odor of Mudgo tested as a steam distillate strongly attracted biotype 2 of the brown planthopper, to which it is susceptible. Likewise, the odor of ASD 7 attracted biotype 3, to which ASD 7 is susceptible. Sucrose and asparagine were found to stimulate ingestion by planthoppers. All of the rices tested, as well as barnyardgrass, appeared suitable for oviposition by the brown planthopper, but the highest number of eggs were laid on the susceptible variety TN1. Gravid females also laid higher number of eggs in parafilm sachets filled with 0.3M sucrose solution when in the presence of TN1 odor.

Three biotypes of brown planthopper have been identified at IRRI. In 1975, biotype 2 populations were observed in two localized areas, about 40 km north and 800 km south of IRRI. Although resistant varieties have been grown in IRRI experimental fields since 1967, the population has remained of biotype 1. Most varieties recorded as resistant to brown planthoppers at IRRI were found susceptible in southern India and Sri Lanka, indicating that hoppers there are of different biotypes. Ptb 33 and ARC 6650 were rated as resistant to hoppers

in southern India and to all other biotypes at IRRI. We systematically evaluated rices that are resistant to biotype 1 and entries in the germ plasm collection and found varietal differences in reactions to biotypes. Twenty-eight were resistant to all three biotypes.

Studies on the genetics of resistance to brown planthopper and green leafhopper showed that Rathu Heenati has a dominant gene for resistance to brown planthopper which is different from and independent of Bph 1. This gene is designated as Bph 3. Babawee has a recessive gene different from and independent of Bph 2 and is designated Bph 4. Ptb 8 has a recessive gene for green leafhopper resistance that segregates independently of Glh 1, Glh 2, and Glh 3, and is designated Glh 4. ASD 8 has a dominant gene that is non-allelic to Glh 1, Glh 2, and Glh 3, and is designated Glh 5.

IR2071-586-5 outyielded all other elite lines with multiple disease and insect resistance in both untreated and insecticide-treated plots in yield trials.

1. Distribution of dead hearts among F₃ lines and parents of the diallele crosses IR4791 and IR4794. IRRI, 1975.

SELECTION AND STUDIES ON SOURCES OF RESISTANCE

Entomology and Plant Breeding Departments

Rice stem borers. Work on varietal resistance to the striped borer *Chilo suppressalis* focused mainly on making diallele crosses and evaluating progeny lines. We used seven varieties rated as moderately resistant to the striped borer in diallele crosses, selecting and intercrossing resistant progenies in every appropriate combination. Three generations of this selective crossing system produced progenies that are distinctly more resistant than any parent (fig. 1).

In a screenhouse evaluation of 1,110 lines, we found about 30 that are resistant or moderately resistant. We are further testing these lines for consistency of resistance.

We evaluated 2,520 rice varieties and lines for resistance to the yellow borer *Tryporyza incertulas* in the screenhouse and field. The following were selected as moderately resistant: MTU-15, IRAM 1642, DM 27, Lepgu, Kwa-hwa-yuan, Kokumasari, WC1253, WC1263, IR1820-52-2, IR1514A-E666, IR2061-213-2, IR1520-823-1, IR2070-820-2, and IR2079A-2-107.

IR1820-52-2 is the most resistant rice tested since the project began several years ago (Table 1, fig. 2). Larvae that fed on this and on other resistant varieties were smaller, had lower survival rates, and caused lower percentages of dead hearts than those that fed on susceptible varieties (Table 2). The survival of the larvae was greatly influenced by the stage of plant growth, amount of nitrogen fertilizer applied, herbicide treatment, and soil salinity. Larval weights and survival rates were lowest on plants infested at 15 days before harvest. Plants treated with higher doses of nitrogen fertilizer or of 2,4-D herbicide apparently provided better conditions for oviposition and larval growth and establishment. More larvae survived when caged on plants growing in saline soils than when caged on plants growing in neutral soils. The results generally imply that yellow borer resistance is governed by factors such as antibiosis or non-preference for feeding, or both. These factors are greatly influenced by the plant's age and the agronomic practices under which it grows.

Table 1. Infestation of resistant and susceptible varieties by the yellow stem borer *Tryporyza incertulas*. Screenhouse experiment.^a IRRI, 1975.

Designation	Tillers (av. no./hill)	Damaged hills (%)	Dead heart tillers (%)
<i>63 days after transplanting</i>			
IR1820-52-2	4.6	46.8**	14**
Rexoro	4.0	99.6	64
<i>76 days after transplanting</i>			
IR1820-52-2	5.3	53.0**	14**
Rexoro	4.4	100.0	82

^aAv. of 25 replications. Each test line was planted in two alternating rows and the plants were artificially infested by placing three egg masses per row at 30 days after transplanting and 50 first-instar larvae per row at 45-50 days after transplanting.

Leafhoppers and planthoppers. About 8,000 rice varieties and lines were screened against the green leafhopper *Nephotettix virescens*; 1,061 were rated as resistant or moderately resistant. Of 160 lines of *Oryza glaberrima* screened, all but three were highly resistant. Interestingly, although the *O. glaberrima* species is from Africa, the green leafhopper has not been reported there.

We retested many of these selected rices for consistency of resistance. The survival and the population buildup of green leafhoppers were much lower on resistant than on susceptible varieties (fig. 3). Five pairs of adult insects caged on 50-day-old individual potted plants of the

2. Alternate pairs of rows of the line IR1820-52-2, which is resistant to the yellow borer, and of Rexoro, which is susceptible. IRRI, 1975.

Table 2. Resistance of selected rice varieties to yellow borer at 20 and 30 days after infestation (DAI). Greenhouse experiment.^a IRRI, 1975.

Designation	Dead hearts (no.)		Larval survival (%)		Wt (mg)		
	20 DAI	30 DAI	20 DAI	30 DAI	20 DAI	30 DAI	
						Larvae	Pupae
IR1820-52-2	12 a	20 ab	13 a	5 a	9.9 a	—	—
IR1917-3-19	15 ab	25 b	14 a	11 b	20.6 bc	56.8 a	35.9 ab
IR1712-11-6	15 ab	23 ab	15 a	11 b	18.5 b	51.2 a	44.6 bc
IR20	25 cd	37 c	13 a	18 c	23.5 de	53.9 a	48.8 c
WC1251	38 e	51 d	30 b	26 d	25.4 e	42.4 a	26.1 a
Kipusa	34 e	42 cd	15 a	29 cd	21.2 d	60.5 a	48.5 c
TKM 6	54 f	48 d	41 c	24 d	24.8 e	44.0 a	31.8 a
IR1539-823-1	30 de	47 d	26 b	26 d	14.5 a	55.2 a	54.1 c
Rexoro	48 f	65 e	28 b	34 e	19.9 bc	65.1 a	56.7 c

^aAv. of 4 replications. In each replication, each primary tiller of 8 potted plants was individually infested with a first-instar larva. Figures followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

resistant rices IR8, IR26, and IR29 produced fewer than 15 nymphs/plant in a period of 18 days, but produced 247 and 337 nymphs on the varieties IR22 and TN1, respectively.

IR26 and IR28 were found resistant to the zigzag leafhopper *Recilia dorsalis*.

Of the 3,892 rice varieties and selections evaluated, 87 were rated resistant or moderately resistant to the white-backed planthopper *Sogatella furcifera*. Insects caged on resistant

plants suffered higher mortality, were smaller, had longer nymphal periods, and laid fewer eggs than those caged on susceptible varieties. The most resistant rices were WC1240, 41 Muskhan, IR2035-117-3, IR2071-105-9, and IR2071-137-5.

We evaluated 8,278 cultivars for resistance to biotype 1 of the brown planthopper, the type found in the Philippines and much of Southeast Asia. These included 160 *O. glaberrima* varieties, which showed no brown planthopper resistance. We rated 427 of the others as resistant or as moderately resistant. We retested these for consistency of resistance to biotype 1 and also evaluated them against biotypes 2 and 3. Factors that affected resistance to and population build-up of biotype 1 are shown in Table 3. The nymphal survival of insects caged on some resistant varieties was dramatically low and the nymphal duration considerably prolonged. Not only did the insects lay fewer eggs on resistant varieties, but a significantly lower percentage hatched (Table 4).

Rice whorl maggot. The rice whorl maggot *Hydrellia philippina* is a major pest in several areas. Its natural population at IRRI being generally quite high, we can evaluate for varietal resistance in the field. We have evaluated almost 20,000 rices against this insect but have identified none that are distinctly resistant. During 1975, we screened another 5,538 rices with similar results. To fortify the existing levels of whorl maggot resistance, we initiated a diallele crossing program using seven moderately resistant

3. Number of nymphs produced by five pairs of green leafhoppers within 8 days after being caged on 50-day-old individual potted plants of selected varieties. IRRI, 1975.

Table 3. Some factors that affect resistance to and population buildup of the brown planthopper *N. lugens* on selected rice varieties.^a IRRI, 1975.

Designation	Plant damage ^b	Eggs (no./plant)	Nymphs (no./plant)	Adults (no./plant)	Survival (%) of caged nymphs at		Nymphs developed into adults (%)	Nymphal duration (days)
					3 days ^c	9 days ^c		
XB5	0.1 a	93 a	17 a	13 a	3 a	2 a	2 a	20
Ptb 20	0.1 a	72 a	21 a	15 a	9 ab	3 a	1 a	26
HR 12	0.3 a	65 a	19 a	14 a	36 b	26 bcd	14 abc	25
MCM 2	0.2 a	78 a	27 ab	15 a	44 c	37 cd	14 abc	22
Ptb 21	0.6 b	41 a	37 ab	13 a	28 bc	14 abc	3 ab	23
ARC 5785	0.3 a	147 a	23 a	20 a	43 c	29 bcd	16 abc	21
Ptb 18	0.2 a	73 a	21 a	21 a	50 c	48 d	8 abc	24
MCM 1	0.2 a	302 a	24 a	38 a	50 c	47 d	20 c	22
BKN 6809	0.2 a	92 a	27 ab	17 a	39 c	33 bcd	11 abc	22
Kentjana	2.9 c	— ^d	80 c	— ^d	85 d	84 e	58 d	19
Bathurst	3.0 c	— ^d	88 c	— ^d	82 d	79 e	57 d	17
Mudgo	0.3 a	144 a	24 a	17 a	17 ab	12 ab	6 ab	25
(resistant check)								
TN1	9.0 d	1036 b	122 d	131 b	98 e	98 f	98 e	13
(susceptible check)								

^aIn the same column, figures followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^bOn a scale of 0–9: 0 = no damage; 9 = severely damaged. Av. of 4 replications, 20 seedlings per replication. ^cAfter infestation. ^dNot tested.

varieties. We selected several of the first-generation hybrids for further testing and hybridization.

In an evaluation of elite GEU lines, IR2070-414-3 exhibited the highest level of whorl maggot resistance yet recorded (Table 5). This line was not specifically selected for its whorl maggot resistance, which suggests that other IR2070 progenies may possess similar or even greater resistance. To verify this, we field-evaluated about 20,000 seedlings from the F₃ bulk seed of the IR2070 crosses. We are now pedigree-testing a large number of plants that had low whorl maggot damage to confirm their resistance. The resistance of IR2070 progenies apparently is due to the pooling of genes of the moderately resis-

tant varieties IR20 and CR94-13. If so, prospects are bright for building up whorl maggot resistance through diallele crossing.

Greenhouse experiments on interactions between insects and host plants showed that fewer first-instar whorl maggots survived when caged on moderately resistant varieties than when caged on the susceptible check, TN1, and that they were smaller in body size. But differences in maggot damage to these varieties were less distinct than differences in survival rates of maggots caged on them, although resistant varieties were damaged significantly less (Table 6). Maggots, unlike such sucking insects as leafhoppers and planthoppers, feed on the leaves. So symptoms are not visible at low

Table 4. Population development of brown planthoppers on selected rice varieties.^a IRRI, 1975.

Designation	Insects (no.) at 30 days after infestation			Insects (no.) at 55 days after infestation		
	Nymphs	Adults	Total	Nymphs	Adults	Total
XB5	1.6 ab	0.4 ab	2.0 ab	0.0 a	0.0 a	0.0 a
Ptb 20	0.4 a	0.2 ab	0.6 a	0.0 a	0.0 a	0.0 a
HR12	4.6 bc	1.2 ab	5.8 bc	2.6 ab	0.0 a	2.6 ab
MCM2	16.0 cde	1.8 ab	17.8 cd	2.6 ab	0.0 a	2.6 ab
ARC 5785	7.2 cd	0.0 a	7.2 c	3.8 ab	1.2 abc	5.0 b
Ptb 18	22.0 de	0.8 ab	22.8 cd	7.0 bc	0.6 ab	7.6 bc
Ptb 21	48.2 e	11.8 cd	60.0 d	4.2 b	2.6 bc	6.8 bc
MCM 1	3.4 bc	2.4 bc	5.8 bc	19.8 cd	1.0 abc	20.8 cd
BKN 6809-74-40	53.4 e	13.0 d	66.4 d	27.6 d	5.3 c	32.8 d
Mudgo (resistant check)	18.6 cde	1.4 ab	20.0 cd	85.6 d	5.6 c	91.2 d
TN1 (susceptible check)	400.2 f	501.6 e	901.8 e	490.0 e	1915.6 d	2405.6 e

^aFive pairs of newly emerged adults were caged on each 35-day-old plant. Five replications per variety; four plants per replication. Any two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. Values transformed to log (x + 1).

Table 5. Reactions of elite IRRI breeding lines to common insects and diseases.^a IRRI, 1975 wet season.

Designation	Whorl maggot damage ^b	Tungro-infected hills ^c (%)	Yield (t/ha)
IR2071-586-5	8.5	13.0	4.7
IR2071-105-9	8.0	1.5	4.4
IR2071-625-1	7.5	2.7	4.1
IR2070-414-3	3.3	4.2	4.1
IR2070-423-2	5.5	5.8	4.1
IR2070-863-1	5.0	1.2	3.8
IR2061-465-1	5.5	2.8	3.6
IR2071-176-1	6.0	15.7	3.4
IR2071-588-5	6.0	3.6	3.3
IR2061-522-6	6.5	0.6	2.9
IR2307-64-2	6.5	20.2	2.9
IR2071-636-5	5.0	40.3	2.4
IR1561-288-3	9.0	70.0	1.5
IR2035-290-2	7.0	76.9	1.1
IR32			
(resistant check)	7.0	6.4	4.1
TN1			
(susceptible check)	9.0	97.6	0.9

^aA total of 44 test and check lines were tested in 4 replications. Stem borer incidence was low during the experiment. ^bRated at 25 days after transplanting on a scale of 0-9: 0 = no damage; 9 = severely damaged. ^cRated at 20 days after transplanting.

intensities—even though the maggots caged on resistant varieties eventually suffer high mortality. This is a major problem in investigating varietal resistance to all insects with chewing mouth parts.

Nature of resistance. Varietal resistance to leafhoppers and planthoppers appears to be primarily biochemical in nature, while the physiological characteristics of the plant also appear important in stem borer and rice whorl maggot resistance. In 1975, we investigated the biochemical base of leafhopper and planthopper

Table 6. Survival of larvae of the rice whorl maggot *Hydrellia philippina* at 15 days after artificial infestation on rice varieties. IRRI, 1975.

IRRI acc. no.	Variety	Larval survival (%)	Length of maggots (mm)	Damage rating ^a
4561	Ma-li-bin	23	5.1	2.1
12260	ARC 6231	57	5.0	2.8
12076	Hondarawala 378b	40	5.3	2.4
4346	Bir-co 884	40	5.5	2.4
13413	Hill Padi	57	5.8	2.3
4444	Gin-shan-tsan 18	60	—	2.4
3678	R ₃ Sultugurmatia	37	5.1	2.4
13388	SML Acorni	37	5.1	2.0
11055	WC1253	70	4.7	2.3
105	Taichung Native 1	77	6.0	3.8
LSD .05		18.5		0.9

^aOn a scale of 0-5: 0 = no damage; 5 = severely damaged.

resistance, emphasizing the green leafhopper and brown planthopper. Plant extracts were bioassayed to determine the role of various fractions in varietal resistance.

First, we analyzed the enzyme content of the salivary glands of various leafhopper and planthopper species. To do this, we dissected about 2,000 salivary glands of each insect species, and analyzed them for enzymes in batches of 100 to 200 glands. Gland homogenates were incubated for 1 hour and the activity was read at OD₂₈₀ × 10⁻³. Enzyme activities were expressed in micro-mole substrate per hour per milligram of protein. Table 7 shows enzymatic activities of three biotypes of the brown planthopper and of the green leafhopper. Additional experiments are expected to provide information on basic insect-plant interrelationships, and in some cases, on chemical differentiation of biotypes.

We conducted experiments to determine the orientation for selection, feeding, and oviposition of the brown planthopper on selected resistant and susceptible host rice varieties, using extracts of the varieties. We developed suitable procedures to extract distillable components of rice stems, as well as bioassay techniques to determine the role of odorous substances that influence orientation, feeding, and oviposition of the hopper.

We found that plants of both resistant Mudgo and susceptible TN1 varieties strongly attracted the insect. But brown planthopper responses to assays of stem distillates of varieties differed markedly. Planthoppers were not attracted by odors of varieties Babawee and Mudgo and of barnyardgrass, but were attracted by odors of the varieties Gambada Samba, Gangala, Ptb 19, Ptb 21, Ptb 33, Thirissa, IR20, IR8, and TN1. Odors of ASD7 and IR26 were only moderately attractive. Interestingly, the odor of Mudgo tested as a steam distillate strongly attracted the brown planthopper biotype 2, to which Mudgo is susceptible. The odor of ASD 7 strongly attracted biotype 3, to which ASD 7 is susceptible.

We rated the degree of brown planthopper feeding on different plants in terms of percentage proboscis response (application of the proboscis and insertion of stylets) and duration of single feedings. Proboscis response was equally high

Table 7. Enzymic activities in salivary glands of three biotypes of the adult brown planthopper and green leafhopper. IRRI, 1975.

Enzyme	Activity ($\mu\text{mol substrate}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}\cdot\text{mg}^{-1}\text{ protein}$)			
	Brown planthopper			Green leafhopper
	Biotype 1	Biotype 2	Biotype 3	
Invertase	0.282	0.128	0.111	0.124
a-D-glucosidase	0.040	0.032	0.029	0.031
B-D-glucosidase	0.095	0.075	0.080	0.070
A-D-galactosidase	0.016	0.015	0.016	0.019
B-D-galactosidase	0.070	0.121	0.068	0.249
Esterase	0.95	0.69	0.81	0.012
Phosphomonoesterase	0.116	0.113	0.120	0.238
Phosphodiesterase	0.046	0.055	0.054	0.064

on all plants tested. But the durations of single feedings on different varieties decreased in the following order: TN1, IR8, IR20, IR26, ASD 7, Mudgo, and barnyardgrass. We also studied the roles of some sugars and amino acids in feeding and determined their intake relative to distilled water. Sucrose was the strongest gustatory stimulus over a wide range of concentrations. We found glucose to be ineffective at any concentration (0.01M to 1M). Also ineffective were 1 percent aqueous solutions of aspartic acid, alanine, serine, glutamic acid, valine, and leucine, unless the pH of these amino solutions was adjusted to 6.5. Asparagine was phagostimulatory at 1 percent concentration. Odors of varieties did not influence the intake of 0.3M sucrose solution by the brown planthopper.

All of the rice varieties and the barnyardgrass appeared suitable for oviposition by the brown planthopper, but the highest number of eggs was laid on the susceptible TN1. When a parafilm sachet filled with a 0.3M sucrose solution was offered to gravid females in the presence of TN1 odor, the insects lacerated the sachets with their ovipositors and laid eggs, although not as many as on TN1 plants. The insects laid almost no eggs when there was no odor, or when odors of other rice varieties tested or of barnyardgrass were present.

Biotypes. IR26 and later IRR1 varieties, as well as most of the breeding lines, are highly resistant to the brown planthopper and the green leafhopper, and have varying degrees of resistance to other insect pests. Along with resistant varieties developed by national programs, these provide significant crop protection from insect damage. Therefore, it is important to investigate

the possibility that biotypes can develop that may render the resistant varieties susceptible. Our greatest present concern is for the brown planthopper, as varieties with high levels of monogenic resistance to this pest are now grown over large areas. Further, we now have evidence of different biotypes of the natural brown planthopper population in certain areas such as southern India and Sri Lanka.

The natural insect populations are generally believed to include small proportions of individuals that can survive on resistant varieties. Consequently, when resistant varieties are intensively planted, a population of insects builds up that can survive on them. Thus, the general population may shift to a new insect biotype. Also, insects may mutate to develop new biotypes capable of surviving on resistant plants, but this phenomenon is not common. Biotypes that can survive on resistant plants are also believed to be more likely to develop on varieties of monogenic resistance than on those of polygenic resistance. Therefore, IRR1 studies on insect biotypes are conducted under two broad categories:

- 1) The planting of different varieties in many areas to determine if a variety that is resistant at one location is susceptible at another. If so, the insects at the two areas are suspected to be of different biotypes.

- 2) The rearing of insects collected from various areas, particularly where resistant varieties are intensively planted, on resistant varieties for several generations. If a population develops that can survive on resistant plants, it is termed a new biotype.

These studies indicate that several biotypes of

4. The reactions of some IRRI varieties to different biotypes of brown planthopper. IRRI, 1975.

brown planthopper now exist, but not of green leafhopper or of white-backed planthopper. Three biotypes of brown planthopper have been identified in IRRI experiments; biotype 1, the general type of brown planthopper at IRRI; biotype 2, which can survive on plants that carry the Bph 1 gene for resistance, such as Mudgo and IR26; and biotype 3, which survives on plants carrying the bph 2 gene, such as ASD 7, Ptb 21, and IR32 (fig. 4) (1974 Annual Report).

In 1974 experiments, we isolated a population that survived on varieties that carry the Bph 1 as well as on those that contain the bph 2 gene for resistance, but we could not maintain this population and were unable to build up another one. Most brown planthopper populations tested in the Philippines appear to be of biotype 1, except for the biotype-2 hoppers in two localized areas: Santa Rosa, Laguna province, about 40 km north of IRRI, and Davao, on the island of Mindanao, 800 km south of IRRI. Significantly, the brown planthopper population at IRRI, which has grown under varying proportions of resistant varieties since 1967, has remained of biotype 1.

Most varieties recorded as resistant at IRRI, however, are susceptible in southern India and Sri Lanka, indicating that hoppers in those areas are of different biotypes. Two varieties, Ptb 33 and ARC 6650, that were recorded as resistant at Pattambi and Hyderabad, India, have also been rated resistant to all three biotypes at IRRI. The brown planthopper biotype in the Solomon Islands appears to have distinctly changed. The brown planthopper has been a severe problem there for years; hopperburn damage has been rampant and it has been usually impossible to grow good rice without effective control by the cultivation of several IRRI breeding lines that carry the Bph 1 gene. Insecticidal protection became unnecessary, but after three or four crop seasons, the brown planthopper population appeared to change and resistant varieties began to suffer hopperburn. The condition in the Solomon Islands is not typical—only about 3,000 ha of rice are grown there, and rice is continuously cropped. But it provides an interesting situation for biotype investigation; we are collaborating with local scientists in such studies.

As a first step toward identifying new sources of resistance to the biotypes at IRRI, we are systematically evaluating the lines that show resistance to biotype 1. We are also evaluating all entries in the germ plasm collection. Through these studies, rice varieties have been identified that react differentially to different biotypes, including two that are resistant to all three biotypes (Table 8).

GENETICS OF RESISTANCE

Plant Breeding and Entomology Departments

Earlier studies have shown that resistance to both the brown planthopper and the green leafhopper is of a monogenic nature. Two separate genes are responsible for brown planthopper resistance, the dominant *Bph 1* and the recessive *bph 2*. Three genes, *Glh 1*, *Glh 2*, and *Glh 3*, convey resistance to the green leafhopper (1971 Annual Report). We further investigated genetic resistance to the brown planthopper in 37 selected resistant varieties and genetic resistance to the green leafhopper in 13 varieties. We evaluated resistance in the greenhouse using the bulk seedling test.

The study of F_1 , F_2 , and F_3 populations of crosses between varieties that are resistant to the brown planthopper and the susceptible variety TN1 verified that the resistance in all of these varieties is under monogenic control.

Allele tests show that the dominant genes for brown planthopper resistance are allelic to *Bph 1* in Andaragahawewa, Balamawee, CO 10, Heenukkulama, MTU 9, Pawakkulama, Sinakayam, SLO 12, Sudhubalawee, Sudurvi 305, and Tibiriwewa. On the other hand, the recessive genes for resistance to *Bph 2* are allelic in Anbaw C7, ASD 9, Dikwee 328, Hathiel, Kosatawee, Madayal, Mahadikwee, Malkora, M.I. 329, Murungakayan, Murungakayan 3, Murungakayan 304, Ovarkaruppan, Palasithari 601, PK-1, Podimawee, Seruvellai, Sinna Karuppan, and Vellailangayan. The dominant gene in Rathu Heenati is different from and independent of *Bph 1*, and is designated *Bph 3*. Similarly, the recessive gene for resistance in Babawee is different from and independent of *bph 2* and is designated *bph 4*. Table 8 lists genes responsible for brown planthopper resistance in selected varieties.

The green leafhopper studies revealed that a single dominant gene conveys resistance in ARC 6602, ASD 8, Betong, DM 77, DNJ 97, DS 1, Godalki, H 5, Jhingasail, Khama 49/8, Lien-tsan 50, and Palasithari 601. A single recessive gene conveys resistance in Ptb 8.

Further, the dominant gene for resistance to green leafhopper in Jhingasail is allelic to *Glh 1*,

Table 8. Reactions of varieties with known genes for resistance to brown planthopper biotypes.^a IRRI, 1975.

Variety	Reaction ^b to		
	Biotype 1	Biotype 2	Biotype 3
	<i>Bph 1 gene</i>		
Andaragahawewa	R	S	R
CO 10	R	S	R
MTU 9	R	S	R
Sudhubalawee	R	S	R
Sudurvi 305	R	S	R
Tibiriwewa	R	S	R
Mudgo (check)	R	S	R
	<i>Bph 2 gene</i>		
Anbaw C7	R	R	S
H 105	MR	R	S
Malkora	R	R	S
Murungakayan	R	R	S
Palasithari 601	R	R	S
PK-1	R	R	S
Podimawee	R	R	S
Ptb 18	R	R	S
ASD 7 (check)	R	R	S
	<i>Bph 3 gene</i>		
Rathu Heenati	R	R	R
	<i>Bph 4 gene</i>		
Babawee	R	R	R
	<i>Susceptible check</i>		
Taichung Native 1	S	S	S

^aTotal of 46 varieties tested. ^bR = resistant; S = susceptible; MR = moderately resistant.

the gene that conveys resistance in Pankhari 203. The dominant gene for green leafhopper resistance in Godalki, Lien-tsan 50, and Palasithari 601 is allelic to the *Glh 2* gene, which conveys resistance in ASD 7. The dominant gene for green leafhopper resistance in Betong, DNJ 97, and H 5 is allelic to *Glh 3* gene, which governs resistance in IR8. The dominant genes for green leafhopper resistance in ASD 8, ARC 6602, DM 77, DS 1, and Khama 49/8 are non-allelic to *Glh 1*, *Glh 2*, and *Glh 3*.

The recessive gene for resistance to green leafhopper in Ptb 8 is designated *glh 4*. It segregates independently of *Glh 1*, *Glh 2*, and *Glh 3*. The dominant gene conveying resistance to green leafhoppers in ASD 8 is designated *Glh 5*. Not known are the allelic relationships to *Glh 5* of the gene that conveys resistance to green leafhopper in ARC 6602, DM 77, DS 1, and Khama 49/8. Table 9 summarizes information on the genes responsible for green leafhopper resistance.

These studies bring the total number of genes that convey brown planthopper resistance to

Table 9. Varieties that carry different genes for resistance to the green leafhopper. IRRI, 1975.

Varieties that carry				
Glh 1	Glh 2	Glh 3	glh 4 ^a	Glh 5 ^b
Pankhari 203	ASD 7	IR8	Ptb 8	ASD 8
Jhingasail	Godalki	Betong		
	Lien-Tsan 50	DNJ 97		
	Palasithari 601	H5		

^aglh 4, a single recessive gene, is inherited independently of Glh 1, Glh 2, and Glh 3. ^bGlh 5, a single dominant gene, is non-allelic to Glh 1, Glh 2, and Glh 3.

four and of those that convey green leafhopper resistance to five.

MULTIPLE INSECT RESISTANCE

Plant Breeding and Entomology Departments

For several years we have grown and selected our early-generation breeding material with no chemical protection against insects and have specifically evaluated each selection in each generation for green leafhopper and brown planthopper resistance. Entomologists carefully scrutinize advanced selections to avoid materials that are unusually susceptible to any insects, even those presently considered minor.

IRRI production specialists evaluated elite lines and varieties with and without insecticides at several locations in the Philippines during 1975 (Tables 10 and 11). Only two medium-maturing selections responded significantly to chemical protection because most are resistant to major pests. One line, IR2071-586-5, yielded significantly higher with insecticides. But even unprotected, it yielded as well as, or better than, all other lines when protected. IR2153-26-3 also responded significantly, probably because of its low tungro resistance. The line is being evaluated in advanced trials because of its superior tolerance to salinity.

Table 10. Yield of early-maturing IRRI varieties and elite lines under protected and unprotected conditions. Mean of three replications at seven locations. IRRI, 1975.

Designation	With insecticide ^a	No insecticide	Difference
IR30	4.7 a	4.2 a	0.5 ns
IR1632-93-2	4.6 ab	4.3 a	0.3 ns
IR2061-465-1	4.1 ab	4.2 a	-0.1 ns
IR2061-522-6	4.3 ab	4.1 a	0.2 ns
IR2070-414-3	4.4 ab	4.1 a	0.3 ns
IR2071-625-1	4.9 a	4.8 a	0.1 ns
IR1561-228-3 (check)	3.8 b	2.5 b	1.3*

^aSeed and seedling soak in carbofuran; 1 kg a.i./ha of gamma BHC at 6 days after transplanting (DT); 0.5 kg a.i./ha of carbofuran at 25 DT; 1 kg a.i./ha of Dolmix at 45 DT; and MIPC spray at 0.05% concentration at 70-85 DT.

Table 11. Yield of IRRI varieties and elite lines of intermediate maturity when grown with and without chemical protection. Mean of three replications at nine locations, IRRI New Selections Applied Research Trial (INSART), 1975 wet season.

Designation	With insecticide ^a (t/ha)	No insecticide (t/ha)	Difference
IR32	4.7 ab	4.6 ab	0.1
IR34	3.1 e	3.1 e	0
IR2070-423-2	4.1 bcd	3.9 bcd	0.2 ns
IR2071-586-5	5.2 a	4.7 a	0.5 ns
IR2153-26-3	3.8 d	3.4 de	0.4*
IR26 (check)	4.5 bcd	3.9 bcd	0.6*

^aSeed and seedling soak in carbofuran; 1 kg a.i./ha of gamma BHC at 6 days after transplanting (DT); 0.5 kg a.i./ha of carbofuran at 25 DT; 1 kg a.i./ha of Dolmix at 45 DT; and MIPC spray at 0.05% concentration at 70-85 DT.

We compared the early selections using the widely grown line IR1561-228-3 as the check. Although IR1561 is resistant to the brown planthopper, it is susceptible to other major pests. It responded very significantly to insecticides, while all others showed almost no response, and outyielded IR1561 with or without chemical protection.

Genetic evaluation and utilization (GEU) program

Protein content

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SUMMARY

Our objective is twofold: 1) to raise the protein content of improved rice varieties by at least 2 percentage points (from about 7% to about 9%); and 2) to determine the nutritional utility and other aspects of improved protein content.

The most promising selection for which we have long-term data is IR2153-338-3. In four tests conducted over 2 years at three nitrogen levels, this selection has consistently produced 8 percent protein at yield levels comparable to those of IR8. This increase of 1 percentage point represents 13 percent more protein in milled rice.

Work was continued on a modified diallel selective mating scheme to concentrate genetic factors for protein content along with resistance to major diseases and insects. We found that protein content of our progeny lines was less associated with lower grain yield than was protein content of the parents. Fourteen of the 64 progeny lines evaluated were superior in protein yield to their parents.

Assay of nitrogen balance in rats showed that the net protein utilization values of two high-protein lines are similar to those predicted from amino acid scores. The relative nutritive value of rice protein from a slope ratio assay in growing rats again corresponded well with amino acid score.

Nitrogen balance studies in preschool Filipino children who were fed two diets of milled rice and dehulled mung bean verified that replacing rice that is 7.5 percent protein with rice that is 11.4 percent protein increased the total amount of retained nitrogen in the children. Apparent nitrogen digestibility was 87 percent for a diet of pearled wheat and milk that was fed to three children, compared with 77 percent for a diet of milled rice and milk.

Ultrastructure studies of developing rice grain showed more ribonucleic acid complexes and protein bodies in a high-protein than in a low-protein rice. Three types of protein bodies, and little or no matrix protein, were observed in the endosperm after 6 days after flowering.

Albumin and globulin accumulated in the developing grain up to 12 days after flowering. During grain development, changes were

observed in the levels of some amino acids, including lysine and threonine, and in the electrophoretic mobility of the component proteins.

Although 8 M guanidine was a good extractant of whole-rice protein, aggregation of the extracted proteins into higher molecular weight (MW) proteins limited the usefulness of guanidine for isolating glutelin from whole rice protein by MW fractionation.

Reduced alkylated glutelin prepared by two methods from crude glutelin had three major subunits with MW of 38000, 25000, and 16000. The ratio of the subunits differed between two glutelin samples. The MW 38000 subunit was unique to glutelin since it was absent in reduced and alkylated albumin-globulin and prolamin. The subunits with MW of 38000 and 16000 were purified by ion-exchange chromatography.

EVALUATION TRIALS

Plant Breeding, Agronomy, Statistics, and Chemistry Departments

Progress is difficult to measure in the improvement of protein content because of variability associated with this trait. Our evaluation procedure consists of selection in early generations for agronomic type, disease and insect resistance, and other essential traits. We determine protein per seed (P/S) values for promising early selections and discard those with low values. The better lines are then promoted to replicated yield trials. Although a few lines that are outstanding for both yield and protein content are found every season, they are not necessarily consistent for these traits from season to season. We advance to agronomy evaluation trials the lines that consistently have higher protein content without sacrifice in yield, as well as the lines that are outstanding during a single season. These elite lines are tested at three levels of added nitrogen fertilizer. Finally, the most outstanding selections are evaluated through recently established cooperative trials in Indonesia, Thailand, and at IRRI. Thus, we attempt to determine the stability of performance for both protein content and yield over several locations.

Plant breeders evaluated 276 varieties and

1. Grain yield and protein content of 276 entries grown in yield trials (4 replications). IRRI, 1975 dry season.

lines for protein content in replicated yield trials during the 1975 dry season, and the same number during the 1975 wet season. The results were generally disappointing. Many lines that appeared outstanding in 1974 did not perform well during 1975. During both the

dry season (fig. 1) and the wet season, only a few lines appeared outstanding compared with the low-protein check IR26 and the high-protein check line IR480-5-9. Some of the better lines (Table 1) were promoted to advanced evaluation trials for further testing.

Table 1. Brown rice protein content and grain yield of promising high-protein lines grown in replicated yield trials.^a IRRI, 1975.

Designation	Cross	Dry season ^c				Wet season ^c			
		Protein		Yield		Protein		Yield	
		%	Index	t/ha	Index	%	Index	t/ha	Index
IR8	Peta/Dgwg	7.1*	90	6.5	97	8.0	94	4.5	96
IR26 (ck)	IR24/TKM 6	7.9	100	6.7	100	8.5	100	4.7	100
IR480-5-9 (ck)	NMS4 ² /TN1	9.7*	123	5.2*	78	9.8*	115	3.7*	79
IR2003-P5-3	IR1103-15/IR480//IR22//Mudgo/IR8	8.8*	111	5.5*	82	9.0	106	4.5	96
IR2006-P12-12	IR1103-15/IR1163-124//IR22//Mudgo/IR8	9.5*	120	5.3*	79	9.3*	109	4.5	96
IR2016-P7-4	IR1103-49/IR480//IR22//Mudgo/IR8	9.3*	118	5.5*	82	9.8*	115	3.2*	68
IR2031-724-2	IR1721-14/IR1416-131//IR1330-3	8.2	104	5.6*	84	8.3	98	3.9*	83
IR2070-189-3	IR20 ² /O.nivara//CR94-13	9.0*	114	6.0*	89	8.2	96	4.1*	87
IR2070-834-1	"	9.6*	122	4.9*	73	9.2*	108	3.8*	81
IR2071-137-5	IR1561-228/IR1737//CR94-13	9.2*	116	5.7*	85	8.9	105	4.2	81
IR2071-816-2	"	7.7	99	6.7	100	9.4*	110	4.8	102
IR2153-338-3	IR24/TKM 6//IR20 ⁴ /O.nivara	9.2*	116	6.0*	89	9.3*	109	4.0*	85
IR2172-64	CR94-13//IR1103-15/IR480	8.2	104	6.2	91	9.2*	108	4.4	94
IR2854-23-4	IR480//IR2015/IR480	8.6*	109	7.4*	110	8.9	105	4.3	91
IR2863-13-2	IR1529-680/CR94-13//IR480	8.4	106	5.8*	86	9.9*	116	3.5*	74
IR2863-25-3	"	8.0	101	7.0	103	9.1	107	4.1	87
IR2863-35-3	"	8.1	102	7.0	104	9.1	107	4.6	98
IR2863-38-1	"	7.4	94	7.0	104	9.7*	114	3.7*	79
IR2871-34-1	Dular/IR1163-153//IR20/IR480	8.9*	113	6.2	92	9.6*	113	3.7*	79
IR3536-31-1	IR22/IR480//BRJ1-13-B-55/IR1514A-E588	—	—	—	—	9.2*	108	4.5	96
CV (%)		5.2	—	10.2	—	6.3	—	12.1	—
LSD (.05) between IR26 or IR480 and any other entry		0.5	—	0.7	—	0.7	—	0.6	—

^a Mean of 4 replications. ^b Ratings on many of these lines for disease and insect resistance, tolerance to adverse soils, etc. can be found in the appropriate sections of this report. ^c Index is percent of IR26; * means significantly different from IR26.

Table 2. Grain yield and protein content of rices at three nitrogen treatments^a in agronomy evaluation trials. IRRI, 1975 dry season.

Designation	Yield ^b (t/ha)			Brown rice protein ^b (%)			Protein ^b (mg/seed)		
	0 kg N/ha	150 ^c kg N/ha	70 + 40 + 40 ^d kg N/ha	0 kg N/ha	150 ^c kg N/ha	70 + 40 + 40 ^d kg N/ha	0 kg N/ha	150 ^c kg N/ha	70 + 40 + 40 ^d kg N/ha
IR8	2.6*	6.7	7.1	6.3*	8.3	8.4	1.4*	2.0	2.0
IR26	3.6	7.2	7.4	6.9	7.5*	8.6	1.2*	1.3*	1.5*
IR480-5-9	2.9	5.2*	5.4*	7.7	8.7	9.1	1.7	2.1	2.1
IR2003-P5-3	3.7	6.3*	6.6*	8.4	10.7*	10.7*	1.4*	1.7*	1.8*
IR2006-P12-12	2.9	5.4*	5.3*	7.4	9.7*	10.9*	1.6*	2.1	2.3
IR2016-P7-4	2.2*	5.3*	5.7*	7.9	10.6*	11.6*	1.4*	2.1	2.2
IR2031-724-2	2.9	6.0*	6.3*	7.1	9.1	9.4	1.5*	2.2	2.2
IR2070-189-3	3.2	6.0*	6.2*	6.9	9.2	9.7	1.0*	1.4*	1.5*
IR2070-401-3	2.9	5.6*	6.3*	7.1	8.6	10.2*	1.2*	1.5*	1.8*
IR2070-834-1	2.8	5.4*	5.3*	7.2	9.7	10.6*	1.1*	1.5*	1.6*
IR2071-137-5	2.9	5.9*	5.8*	7.1	8.6	9.1	1.1*	1.3*	1.4*
IR2071-559-2	2.8*	5.3*	5.4*	6.4*	8.4	9.0	1.0*	1.4*	1.6*
IR2153-338-3	3.0	6.2*	6.1*	7.0	8.5	9.0	1.1*	1.4*	1.5*
IR2172-64	3.0	6.0*	5.6*	6.6*	8.8	9.6	1.4*	1.9	2.1

^aAv. of four replications. ^bMeans are significantly different at the 5% level from IR26 for yield and from IR480-5-9-3 for protein content or protein per seed. ^cBasal application of ammonium sulfate. ^dSplit applications: basal, at 30 days after transplanting, and at panicle initiation.

Of particular interest are lines selected from the cross IR2863. These lines are resistant to green leafhoppers and brown planthoppers; resistant to bacterial blight and tungro virus diseases; at least moderately resistant to blast; and tolerant of some adverse soil conditions such as iron toxicity. During 1975, these lines performed well in the International Rice Observational Nursery (IRON).

Agronomists evaluated the yield and protein potentials of 17 promising high-protein lines

during both dry and wet seasons using as standard controls IR8, IR26, and the line IR480-5-9. Only three entries from the 1974 wet-season trial—IR2031-724-2, IR2153-338-3, and IR 2172-64—were retested during the 1975 dry season. Eleven promising lines from the 1975 dry-season trial were retested during the 1975 wet season (Tables 2 and 3).

IR26 yielded highest during the dry season with fertilizer. IR2003-P5-3 yielded almost as well as IR26, while the other promising lines

Table 3. Grain yield and protein content of rices at three nitrogen treatments^a in agronomy evaluation trials. IRRI, 1975 wet season.

Designation	Yield ^b (t/ha)			Brown rice protein (%)			Protein (mg/seed)		
	0 kg N/ha	70 ^c kg N/ha	50 + 20 ^d kg N/ha	0 kg N/ha	70 ^c kg N/ha	50 + 20 ^d kg N/ha	0 kg N/ha	70 ^c kg N/ha	50 + 20 ^d kg N/ha
IR8	3.2	6.1	6.2	6.7*	7.6*	8.0*	1.5*	1.8*	1.9*
IR26	3.5	5.5	5.8	7.3	8.2*	8.4*	1.2*	1.4*	1.4*
IR480-5-9	2.5*	4.1*	4.5*	7.8	9.3	9.6	1.6	2.1	2.2
IR2003-P5-3	3.1	5.4	5.0*	7.5	8.6	9.0	1.2*	1.5*	1.5*
IR2006-P12-12	3.0	5.0	4.8*	7.3	8.8	9.4	1.6	2.0*	2.1
IR2016-P7-4	2.6*	4.2*	4.4*	7.4	9.7	9.4	1.4*	1.9*	1.9*
IR2031-724-2	2.9	4.6*	4.4*	7.5	8.5*	9.2	1.6	1.8*	2.0*
IR2070-189-3	3.2	4.7*	4.6*	7.6	8.7	9.0	1.2*	1.4*	1.4*
IR2070-401-3	2.6*	4.1*	4.6*	7.3	8.3*	9.2	1.2*	1.4*	1.6*
IR2070-834-1	2.8	4.1*	4.4*	7.7	9.0	9.4	1.2*	1.4*	1.5*
IR2071-137-5	3.1	4.9	4.9*	7.8	9.1	9.7	1.2*	1.4*	1.5*
IR2071-529-6	3.1	4.4*	4.7*	7.4	9.0	9.6	1.3*	1.6*	1.7*
IR2071-559-2	3.1	4.4*	4.6*	7.5	8.6	9.2	1.3*	1.4*	1.6*
IR2153-338-3	2.9	4.6*	4.8*	8.2	9.1	9.9	1.3*	1.5*	1.6*
IR2172-64	3.3	5.3	4.7*	7.2	8.0*	9.8	1.5	1.8*	2.1
IR2681-118-1	3.6	5.2	5.2	7.3	8.5*	8.5*	1.4*	1.6*	1.7*
IR2854-23-4	3.1	5.4	5.5	7.4	8.3*	9.0	1.6	1.8*	2.0*
IR2871-34-1	3.9	5.6	5.6	7.3	8.4*	9.1	1.2*	1.4*	1.5*

^aAv. of four replications. ^bMeans are significantly different at the 5% level from IR26 for yield and from IR480-5-9-3 for protein content or protein per seed. ^cBasal application of ammonium sulfate. ^dSplit application: basal and at 5-7 days before panicle initiation.

yielded somewhat lower (Table 2). At high nitrogen levels, however, IR2003-P5-3 and some other lines had significantly higher protein content. At zero nitrogen, IR2003-P5-3 produced the highest grain yield as well as the highest percent of brown rice protein; yields of most high-protein entries were somewhat lower than were those of IR2003-P5-3.

With fertilizer nitrogen, IR8 produced the highest grain yield during the wet season although yields of IR26 and IR2871-34-1 were statistically similar to those of IR8 (Table 3). Many high-yielding lines had contents of brown rice protein that were statistically similar to that of IR480-5-9.

IR2153-338-3 contained the highest percentage of brown rice protein at 50 + 20 kg N/ha. With no nitrogen fertilizer, IR2153-338-3 had the highest protein content, but all high-protein entries had protein contents statistically similar to those of IR480-5-9. The line IR2871-34-1 yielded highest at zero nitrogen, while most of the promising lines gave yields statistically similar to those of IR26.

Among the dry-season entries at zero fertilizer nitrogen, IR480-5-9 had the highest P/S values, followed by IR2006-P12-12 and IR2031-724-2. With nitrogen fertilizer, the entries with high P/S values were IR2006-P12-12, IR2016-P7-4, IR2031-724-2, IR2172-64, and IR480-5-9. Again in the 1975 wet season, IR480-5-9 produced the highest P/S without fertilizer nitrogen, followed by IR2854-23-4, IR2006-

P12-12, and IR2031-724-2. Even with nitrogen fertilizer, IR480-5-9 ranked first for P/S followed by IR2172-64, IR2006-P12-12, and IR2854-23-4.

At the time of writing of the 1975 Annual Report, only the IRRI data were available for the first IRRI-Indonesia-Thailand Cooperative High Protein Rice Yield Nursery because of differences in growing seasons. Under fertilized and non-fertilized conditions, IR8 yielded highest although IR26 produced statistically similar yields. Most high-protein lines gave yields statistically similar to those of IR26 with zero fertilizer nitrogen. The Thai variety Boon Nahk 16-1-21 contained the highest percent of brown rice protein but it yielded lowest because it is highly susceptible to lodging. Boon Nahk 16-1-21 was transplanted 2 weeks later than the other entries because of poor seed germination and rat infestation. Consequently, strong winds and rain severely damaged the crop during the reproductive stage. Without nitrogen fertilizer, IR2070-834-1, IR2153-338-3, and the Indonesian lines B2927-20-2 and B2929-5-6 gave percent protein contents that were statistically similar to that of IR480-5-9 (Table 4).

At 100 kg N/ha, only IR8, IR480-5-9, and IR2153-338-3 produced yields statistically similar to that of IR26; IR2070-834-1, the tall Indonesian lines B2926-10-10 and B2929-4-8, and the tall Thai entry Boon Nahk 16-1-21 were highly susceptible to lodging. IR26,

Table 4. Grain yield and protein content of rices from IRRI, Indonesia, and Thailand at two nitrogen treatments.^a IRRI, 1975 wet season.

Designation	Yield (t/ha)		Brown rice protein (%)		Protein (mg/seed)	
	0 kg N/ha	100 kg N/ha	0 kg N/ha	100 kg N/ha	0 kg N/ha	100 kg N/ha
IR8	4.7	6.2	8.1*	8.7*	1.8*	2.1*
IR26	4.5	6.2	8.2*	8.7*	1.4*	1.6*
IR480-5-9	4.0	5.3	9.6	10.5	2.2	2.5
IR2006-P12-12	3.4	4.9*	8.6*	10.7	1.9*	2.4
IR2031-724-2	3.5	4.7*	8.3*	9.1*	2.0*	2.2*
IR2153-338-3	3.2*	5.1	9.0	9.9	1.5*	1.7*
IR2070-834-1-2	3.7	3.7*	9.3	10.8	1.5*	1.7*
B2926-10-10	4.1	4.1*	8.3*	9.4*	1.8*	2.1*
B2927-20-2	2.9*	3.8*	9.0	9.8	1.8*	2.0*
B2929-4-8	3.8	3.2*	8.7*	10.2	1.8*	2.1*
B2929-5-6	3.8	4.0*	8.8	9.9	2.2	2.5
Boon Nahk 16-1-21	2.4*	1.7*	9.6	11.5*	2.3	2.7*

^aAv. of three replications. *Means are significantly different from IR26 for yield and from IR480-5-9-3 for protein content and protein per seed at the 5% level.

Table 5. Protein content and yield of varieties and lines grown at three nitrogen levels during four seasons. IRRI, 1974-1975.

N level (kg N/ha)	IR8		IR26		IR480-5-9		IR2153-338-3		Mean	
	Protein (%)	Yield (t/ha)								
<i>1974 dry season</i>										
0	7.8	2.7	7.0	4.3	8.5	2.9	7.9	4.2	6.8	3.2
150	8.0	5.8	7.6	8.7	9.4	6.2	9.4	7.8	8.0	5.9
70+40+40	8.4	5.4	8.6	8.9	9.9	6.6	10.0	8.5	8.4	6.0
Mean	8.1	4.6	7.7	7.3	9.3	5.2	9.1	6.8	7.8	5.0
<i>1974 wet season</i>										
0	6.4	4.1	6.8	4.2	7.5	3.4	7.4	3.8	7.0	3.9
90	8.2	5.0	8.4	5.4	8.6	3.9	9.0	5.2	1.9	6.7
60+30	8.9	5.4	8.8	5.9	10.0	4.5	9.6	5.4	8.6	7.0
Mean	7.8	4.8	8.0	5.2	8.7	3.9	8.7	4.8	7.8	5.9
<i>1975 dry season</i>										
0	6.3	2.6	6.9	3.6	7.7	2.9	7.8	2.5	7.9	2.9
150	8.3	6.7	7.5	7.2	8.7	5.2	9.3	4.1	9.0	4.8
70+40+40	8.4	7.1	8.6	7.4	9.1	5.4	9.6	4.5	9.6	5.2
Mean	7.7	5.5	7.7	6.1	8.5	4.5	8.9	3.7	8.8	4.3
<i>1975 wet season</i>										
0	6.7	3.2	7.3	3.5	7.8	2.5	8.2	2.9	7.6	3.5
70	7.6	6.1	8.2	5.5	9.3	4.1	9.1	4.6	9.0	6.0
50+20	8.0	6.2	8.4	5.8	9.6	4.5	9.9	4.8	9.6	6.2
Mean	7.4	5.2	8.0	4.9	8.9	3.7	9.1	4.1	8.8	5.2

IR2031-724-2, and IR2153-338-3 also lodged, but only at 1 week before harvest. Most high-protein lines had contents of brown rice protein statistically similar to that of IR480-5-9. Boon Nahk 16-1-21 gave the highest P/S value, both at 0 and at 100 kg N/ha, followed by IR480-5-9 and B2929-5-6 (Table 4).

Over four seasons, certain entries in the agronomy advanced evaluation trial, including the improved line IR2153-338-3, have had 1 percentage point higher content of protein than IR8 and IR26, with average yields comparable to those of IR8 (Table 5). Yields of IR26, however, averaged 0.7 t/ha higher. IR26 appears to have better yielding ability and pest resistance than does IR8, without sacrificing protein content. IR2153-338-3 appears to have an advantage of 1 percentage point in protein content at the same yield level as IR8 and a spectrum of disease and insect resistance equal to that of IR26. But for farmer acceptance, we must have yields equal to those of IR26 without sacrificing protein content. IR480-5-9 produced the same protein content as IR2153-338-3, but at a lower grain yield.

HYBRIDIZATION PROGRAM
Plant Breeding Department

We crossed all outstanding high-protein lines with the best breeding materials from other GEU problem areas. During 1975, we carried out an additional two cycles of the modified diallel selective mating scheme to concentrate genetic factors for protein content with pest resistance (1973 Annual Report) and attempted

2. Percent brown rice protein and grain yield of 11 parents and 64 progeny lines. IRRI, 1975 wet season.

Table 6. Simple correlation coefficients among grain yield, percent brown rice protein (BRP), and protein per seed (P/S) in varietal tests under fertilized and unfertilized conditions. IRRI, 1974-1975.

Nitrogen applied (kg/ha)	Simple correlation coefficient, r		
	BRP and grain yield	P/S and grain yield	BRP and P/S
	<i>Replicated yield trial^a, 1974 wet season</i>		
100	-0.467**	-0.014	0.400**
	<i>Yield potential of high-protein rices^b, 1975 dry season</i>		
0	0.159	-0.004	0.450*
150 ^c	-0.418	-0.228	0.475**
	<i>Yield potential of high-protein rices, 1975 wet season</i>		
0	-0.345	-0.228	-0.069
70	-0.737**	-0.132	0.118

^aInvolving 370 entries, each replicated four times. ^bInvolving 20 entries, each replicated four times. ^cAveraged over basal and split applications.

to evaluate the effectiveness of the diallel scheme in enforcing genetic factors for higher protein content. Based on P/S values, agronomic type, and pest reactions, we chose 64 promising uniform F₃ and F₄ selections from the first and second mating cycles and compared them for yield and protein content with their parents in replicated trials. We found highly significant differences in percent protein content, P/S, and yield. Protein content of the progeny lines was less negatively associated with grain yield than was protein content of the parents (fig. 2). Fourteen of 64 progeny lines were superior to their parents in protein yield. Diallel selective mating may be a promising tool for increasing protein content in rice while maintaining a high yield level.

PROTEIN SELECTION CRITERIA

Statistics Department

Past results indicated that protein per seed (P/S) may be an effective selection criterion for high protein and may be less influenced by environmental factors than is percent protein (1974 Annual Report). We determined that the correlation between P/S and grain yield was consistently lower than that between percent brown rice protein (BRP) and grain yield (Table 6). We also determined that while the CV (zero variance for varietal comparison) was slightly higher for P/S than for BRP (Table 7), this was more than compensated by the fact that P/S accounted for a much higher proportion of the total varietal variation. During 1975 we used P/S measurements to select in early generations

of crosses involving one or more parents thought to be high in protein content.

PROTEIN ESTIMATION

Chemistry Department

A commercial grain quality analyzer based on near infrared reflectance spectroscopy was assessed for the routine estimation of protein in ground samples of brown rice. The analyzer was calibrated with 38 samples from the 1975 dry-season replicated yield trial to estimate protein, oil, and moisture. The chemical analysis of the samples (wet basis) was: protein, 6.7–11.5 percent; oil, 2.1–3.2 percent; and moisture, 11.0–12.2 percent. After calibrating the analyzer, the protein reading differed by more than 0.22 percent (the calculated standard deviation for protein) in four of 38 samples; the maximum difference was 0.8 percent from the Kjeldahl protein analysis. The good correspondence

Table 7. Mean value ($\bar{x}$), error variance (s^2), cv, and proportion of varietal variation in varietal testing based on percent brown rice protein (BRP) and protein per seed (P/S). IRRI, 1974-1975.

	Mean	Error variance	cv (%)	Proportion of varietal variation (%)
	<i>Replicated yield trial^a, 1974 wet season</i>			
BRP	8.9	0.2763	5.9	52.6
P/S	0.0016	0.1190×10^{-7}	6.9	83.2
	<i>Yield potential of high-protein rices^b, 1975 dry season</i>			
BRP	8.5	0.3175	6.6	54.7
P/S	1.5	0.0117	7.0	85.8
	<i>Yield potential of high-protein rices^b, 1975 wet season</i>			
BRP	8.7	0.1880	5.0	41.8
P/S	1.6	0.0108	6.6	80.0

^aInvolving 370 entries, each replicated four times. ^bInvolving 20 entries, each replicated four times.

between the two sets of values ($r = 0.98^{**}$) may be partly due to the narrow range in contents of oil and moisture of the brown rice samples. But when the samples were stored in whole and ground form for several months, even at 4°C, readings tended to increase for moisture and oil, and protein values decreased. LSD (5%) was 0.4 percent protein by the Kjeldahl method and 0.3 percent by the new method.

BIOLOGICAL EVALUATION OF RICE PROTEIN

Chemistry Department

Protein quality of high-protein lines. *Nitrogen balance of high-protein lines.* Milled rice of two promising high-protein lines, IR2031-724-2 (10% protein) and IR2153-338-3 (12%), was tested for taste panel scores and protein characterization. Both rices have high amylose content, hard gel consistency, and low gelatinization temperature. Lysine content of protein in both samples was 3.5 g/16 g N, equivalent to an amino acid score of 64 percent. A taste-panel evaluation of cooked rice of these lines at the Institute of Human Ecology, University of the Philippines at Los Baños, showed that their scores for tenderness, cohesiveness, whiteness, and gloss were similar to those of IR26 with normal protein content. Data on nitrogen balance were taken at the Agricultural Research Laboratory, Copenhagen, Denmark, using five weanling rats per diet. High values were found for IR2031-724-2 for true digestibility (99.9%),

Table 8. Protein quality of four milled rices differing in protein content as determined by the slope ratio method in growing rats. IRRI, 1975.

Rice sample	Protein (%N × 6.25)	Lysine (g/16 g N)	Amino acid score ^a (%)	RNV ^b (%)	RPV ^c (%)	Utilizable protein ^d (%)
Intan	6.0	4.1	74	78	109	6.5
IR8	7.7	3.6	65	69	84	6.5
IR480-5-9	10.3	3.5	64	—	76	7.8
BPI-76-1	15.2	3.2	58	46	56	8.5

^aBased on 5.5 g lysine/16 g N as 100%. ^bRelative nutritive value data of the Department of Nutrition, Harvard University, Boston, Massachusetts, U.S.A., based on lactalbumin as 100%, and rice levels of 28%, 56%, and 84% in the diet, using 5–6 rats per diet for 3 weeks. ^cRelative protein value, set by the Department of Foods and Nutrition, University of Manitoba, Canada, based on casein as 100%; three levels of protein (preferably 2%, 5%, and 8%), and using 4 rats per diet for 2 weeks. ^dRPV × protein/100.

biological value (66.5%), and net protein utilization (66.4%). Corresponding values for IR2153-338-3 were 98.5, 69.9, and 68.8 percent. These values are comparable to earlier data on other rice varieties (1972 Annual Report).

Slope ratio assay of high-protein rices. RPV (relative protein value) of four milled rices was determined at the Department of Foods and Nutrition, University of Manitoba, Winnipeg, Canada, using the rat assay method adapted by the International Union of Nutritional Sciences. RPV was essentially similar to earlier RNV (relative nutritive value) data (1972 Annual Report), except for the much wider range of values with RPV (Table 8). A different reference protein was used for each method. The protein quality values of the four rices were ranked similarly using RNV, RPV, and amino acid scores. RNV and RPV, however, gave a wider range of values than amino acid scores. Intan again gave a higher RPV than did casein (1969 Annual Report).

Rice protein concentrate was prepared from milled rice of IR480-5-9 at the Faculty of Science of Living, Osaka City University, Japan. Digestion (α -amylase) of rice gruel yielded protein with only 0.7 percent albumin and 0.2 percent globulin compared with 2.6 and 3.3 percent in the protein of raw rice. The reduction in salt-soluble protein may be due to denaturation during boiling of the rice and loss during preparation. Amino acid score (lysine) of the protein dropped slightly (from 58% to 56%). RNV of this protein concentrate in growing rats in Osaka was 48 percent of fresh whole egg protein at protein levels of from 4 to 15 percent, and was 91 percent at from 0 to 2 percent protein. The data compared well with previous RNV data (53 and 54 percent) from Harvard University on milled rice of IR480-5-9.

Protein content and rice-mung bean diets. Nitrogen balance studies have been conducted on adults fed boiled rice (1970 Annual Report) and on preschool children fed a rice-fish diet (1974 Annual Report). Both groups were fed low- and high-protein milled rices at the same level of intake. The same percentage of N was absorbed and retained for the diets.

Filipino mothers often add mung bean *Vigna radiata* (L.) Wilczek to rice gruel as a weaning

Table 9. A comparison of mean amino acid scores and nitrogen balance of diets of milled rice-dehulled mung bean and of milled rice-milk^c diet fed to Filipino children. IRRI, 1975.

Diet	Protein (%N × 6.25) of rice	Children (no.)	Amino acid score ^b (%)	Daily N intake (mg/kg body wt)	Daily fecal N (mg/kg body wt)	Daily urine N (mg/kg body wt)	Daily N retention (mg/kg body wt)	Apparent N	
								Digesti- bility (%)	Reten- tion (%)
<i>Rice-mung bean (100:18.6 wt/wt)</i>									
IR8	7.5	4	89	197	65	90	42	67.0	21.6
IR480-5-9	11.4	4	80	256	64	111	81	75.0	31.6
Rice-milk ^c	7.4	4	100	192	45	82	65	76.6	34.0
LSD (5%)				14.4	13.3	15.1	28.0	6.7	NS
<i>Rice-mung bean (100:27.7 wt/wt)</i>									
IR8	7.5	5	97	235	56	124	55	76.3	23.3
IR480-5-9	11.4	5	90	294	65	157	72	77.8	24.4
Rice-milk ^c	7.4	5	100	198	40	98	60	79.6	30.3
LSD (5%)				2.6	15.5	13.3	13.0	NS	5.5

^aN balance determined at the Food and Nutrition Research Institute, Manila. ^bBased on 5.5 g lysine/16 g N as 100%. ^c50:50 N basis.

food. The effect of protein content of milled rice in nitrogen retention of Filipino children fed a diet of rice and mung bean was next studied at the Food and Nutrition Research Institute, Manila, Philippines. The rice samples used were IR8 with 7.5 percent protein (N × 6.25) and IR480-5-9 with 11.4 percent protein. The dehulled mung bean flour had 26 percent protein. A weight ratio of 100:18.6 was initially used to maintain the IR8 diet at 200 mg N/kg body weight. However, the IR8 diet was inferior in percent N digestibility to the IR480-5-9 diet and the rice-milk diet (Table 9). Rice-legume diets had previously been observed to give poorer digestibility than rice-milk diets at 200 mg N/kg body weight.

Increasing the N intake by adjusting the rice-to-mung bean ratio to 100:27.7 improved the digestibility of the IR8 diet but reduced the percent N retention of the IR480-5-9 diet, probably because of the already high N intake (294 mg N from 256 mg N/kg body weight). The results again supported our previous findings that replacement of low-protein rice with high-protein rice in a rice diet resulted in an increase in total amount of N retained, since percentage N absorbed and retained was maintained or improved.

Analysis of the two rices in the feeding study with rice-mung bean diets showed higher levels of thiamine, riboflavin, and phytin in the IR480-5-9 milled rice than in IR8 rice (Table 10). The two rices had the same degree of milling based on 100-grain weights, so the differences

noted may be partly due to better distribution of these nutrients in the high-protein rice; this agrees with previous results (1971 Annual Report).

Digestibility of rice and wheat proteins. The digestibility of wheat protein has been reported to be superior to that of rice protein in Guatemalan and Peruvian children, but no data have been available for children from regions of rice-based diet. Nitrogen balance was studied in three Filipino children at the Food and Nutrition Research Institute in Manila with cereal-milk diets (50:50 N source) at an intake of 200 mg N/kg body weight. Apparent N digestibility was 87.1 percent for pearled wheat and 77.2 percent for milled rice. But apparent N retention was 26.5 percent for wheat and 30.3 percent for milled rice, indicating a higher biological value of rice protein than of wheat protein. Although rice protein had a higher lysine content than wheat (3.87 vs. 2.74 g/16 g N), both cereal-milk diets were adequate in all essential amino acids.

Table 10. Chemical analysis of brown and milled rice of IR8 and of the line IR480-5-9 used in the N-balance study with mung bean. IRRI, 1975.

Sample	Protein content (% N × 5.95)	Thiamine (μg/g)	Riboflavin (μg/g)	Phytin (mg P/g)
<i>Brown rice</i>				
IR8	8.1	3.97	0.48	2.12
IR480-5-9	11.3	3.61	0.50	2.49
<i>Milled rice</i>				
IR8	7.1	0.20	0.19	0.26
IR480-5-9	10.9	0.82	0.24	0.62
LSD (5%)	0.2	0.14	0.04	0.28

3. Three forms of protein bodies in the endosperm of developing IR26 rice grain. Sample was fixed in glutaraldehyde, postfixed in OsO_4 , and stained with uranyl acetate and alkaline lead citrate. Department of Botany, University of Durham, England, 1975.

Residual rice protein bodies have been reported in the feces of Japanese adults fed a diet of boiled rice; this is being investigated as a possible explanation for the poorer digestibility of milled rice protein.

PHYSICOCHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF RICE PROTEIN

Chemistry Department

Ultrastructure of protein bodies in developing grain.

A cooperative study by transmission electron microscopy was undertaken with the Department of Botany, University of Durham, England, on the ultrastructure of endosperm protein bodies in developing grains of differing protein content. Samples of IR26 (8% protein) and IR480-5-9 (10%) were tagged, harvested, and fixed at IRRI. Formation of rough endoplasmic reticulum (ER) complexes was observed as early as 2 days after flowering (DAF) prior to protein deposition only in the higher protein grain, IR480-5-9. Single sheets of rough ER were seen in IR26. From 8 DAF, three types of protein bodies were observed in vacuoles in endosperm cells: densely stained spheres; less

densely stained spheres often characterized by more densely stained centers and granulation near the enclosing membrane; and angular, probably crystalline, protein deposition (fig. 3). The crystalline type was restricted to the two outermost endosperm cells, which had more protein bodies and fewer, smaller starch granules than did the rest of the endosperm. At 10 DAF, numerous protein bodies and large compound starch granules were found and only a few vacuoles remained. Starch granules were first observed at 4 DAF.

Whatever the precise original formation of the protein body, the extent of its development can probably be shown by the intensity of electron density: the most electron-transparent probably indicates an early stage of protein deposition, followed by a stage where the central part is electron dense but the double-membrane feature is still apparent; and, finally, a completely electron-dense body bound by a single membrane. The double-membrane feature of some protein bodies does not necessarily mean that these organelles are of plastid origin, but may mean that they originate in vacuoles (single membrane) within the lumen of the rough ER, and that the ER provides the outer membrane.

Grains of IR480-5-9 had more protein bodies and rough ER in the endosperm cells than grains of IR26 (fig. 4). This agrees with our previous findings that developing grains of high-protein rice have a higher rate of amino acid incorporation and higher content of ribonucleic acid than grains of low-protein rice (1969 Annual Report). Increase in total protein with maturity was confirmed to be the result of increased number of protein bodies rather than of increased size.

Unlike in other cereals, little or no matrix protein was observed in the endosperm of rice. In the endosperm of corn, sorghum, and barley, glutelin is the matrix protein, and protein bodies are predominantly prolamin in nature. Protein of rice endosperm, however, has less than 5 percent prolamin and more than 80 percent glutelin.

Albumin and globulin of developing grain.

Because of the importance of rice protein in human nutrition in Asia, a more detailed study

4. The high-protein rice IR480-5-9 (below) had more protein bodies in the endosperm of the developing grain than did IR26 (above). Samples were fixed in glutaraldehyde, postfixed in OsO_4 , and stained with uranyl acetate and alkaline lead citrate. Department of Botany, University of Durham, England, 1975.

was undertaken of changes in the properties of the proteins albumin (water-soluble) and globulin (salt-soluble) in the developing grain of the rice line IR1541-76-3. The proteins were extracted with 0.7 M NaCl and were separated by precipitation of globulin during dialysis against water. The level of free amino N progressively increased up to 10 days after flowering (DAF) and decreased as the grain matured (fig. 5). Total protein increased in the grain up to 20 DAF and changed slightly with grain desiccation up to maturity. The trend was the same for the protein fractions albumin, globulin, and glutelin-protein (by difference), although accumulation of albumin and globulin slowed down earlier (12 DAF) than did that of glutelin-prolamins. Globulin content was about twice the albumin content except at 2 and 4 DAF. Because of the simultaneous accumulation of starch, the percent protein content of the grain remained almost constant from 4 DAF to maturity.

Amino acid analysis of brown rice protein showed consistent trends with maturity in some of the amino acids. Among the eight essential amino acids, lysine and threonine progressively decreased during grain development (Table 11).

5. Changes in the various N fractions of the developing grain of IR1541-76-3 rice. IRRI, 1975.

Table 11. Changes in the contents of lysine and threonine of brown rice protein, albumin, and globulin during grain development of the line IR1541-78-3 (g/16 g N). IRRI, 1975.

Days after flowering	Brown rice		Albumin		Globulin	
	Lysine	Threonine	Lysine	Threonine	Lysine	Threonine
2	7.6	5.1	7.6	5.7	7.5	5.7
4	7.1	4.7	8.1	5.4	7.3	4.7
7	6.1	4.5	8.6	5.1	6.9	4.5
12	5.1	4.0	7.7	4.7	5.9	3.8
20	4.6	4.1	7.3	4.5	5.5	3.5
32	4.2	4.0	6.8	4.4	4.3	3.2
LSD (5%)	0.3	0.4	0.3	0.1	0.4	0.5

Content of aspartic acid also dropped while that of arginine and glutamic acid increased. Similar changes were noted for globulin. Albumin differed from globulin and total protein by slight changes in lysine content; glutamic acid decreased rather than increased. Albumin generally had a higher content of lysine and threonine than did globulin, but had a lower content of tryptophan and leucine.

Polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis of all samples showed a maximum of four major and six minor protein bands in albumin that were present in samples of 20-day-old and mature grain. The major albumin bands had intermediate mobility. An electrophoregram of globulin showed that mobility decreased with grain maturation; only four bands were present from 7 DAF onward that had slower mobility than did the major albumin bands. Patterns were diffused with 2- and 4-day-old grains. Storage of the mature grain decreased the intensity of all of the protein bands of albumin and globulin.

Globulin that was still soluble in water at 90°C had 2.6% lysine, 2.2% threonine, 4.8% cystine, 3.8% methionine, and 2.3% tryptophan, confirming that this major α -globulin is high in the sulfur amino acids, cystine and methionine. Only two major protein bands showed on electrophoresis.

The subunit molecular weight (MW) of protein was estimated by sodium dodecyl sulfate-polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis. Three major subunits for albumin were found with MW of 8500, 11000, and 16000 from 7 DAF onward. Subunits MW ranged from 8500 to 95000 for the 12 bands noted. The principal major subunit was MW 11000, followed by

MW 8500. For globulin, a maximum of 20 subunits was observed with MW ranging from 7900 to 110000. The major subunit had MW 20000 followed by the MW 12000 subunit.

Molecular weight fractionation of rice protein.

Serial extraction of albumin-globulin, prolamin, and glutelin with NaCl, 70 percent ethanol, and NaOH probably results in an impure glutelin since glutelin constitutes 80 percent of milled rice protein and can physically occlude the other protein fractions during protein body deposition in the developing grain. Because of differences in MW between glutelin and the other fractions, a neutral denaturing agent was sought that does not alter the primary structure of rice proteins but that facilitates their fractionation by MW through gel filtration column chromatography. Guanidine HCl (8 M) was found to extract 80 percent of rice glutelin. Various gel columns were tested at ambient temperatures using purified rice protein fractions and guanidine extracts. Elution was with 0.1 M phosphate buffer pH 7.5 which contained 1 M guanidine HCl and 0.02% sodium azide.

Glutelin eluted at the void volume (V_0) or excluded from Sepharose 4B, but not from Sepharose 6B. However, albumin and globulin were eluted together at the tyrosine elution volume (V_i). Bio-Gel P-200 gave better resolution of globulin and albumin. A Sepharose 4B column (26 × 345 mm) and a Bio-Gel P-200 column (26 × 925 mm) connected in series gave improved resolution but more than 3 days was required to complete a run. Brown rice extract gave mainly a glutelin peak at the V_0 (fig. 6). Rice bran extract gave a glutelin peak, followed by a broad peak with a hump, and then an asymmetrical broad V_i peak. Using protein

fractions, globulin was eluted before albumin but their separation was incomplete. Although prolamin had high UV absorption, its recovery was poor since it only gave a small peak at the V_0 and a small plateau in the region of albumin-globulin and tyrosine. Our previous results indicated the presence in rice prolamin of low MW UV-absorbing, polyphenolic contaminant.

When a mixture of albumin, globulin, and prolamin was used, the chromatogram showed a V_0 peak, followed by a peak corresponding to the second peak of the bran extract, and then globulin and albumin (fig. 6). The increase in MW of this mixture of protein, reflecting aggregation, was probably due to the oxidation of sulfhydryl groups of cysteine residues of protein to disulfide or cystine residues between polypeptide chains in the presence of atmospheric oxygen. Exclusion of oxygen may minimize the formation of this disulfide bond, but the addition of a reducing agent such as β -mercaptoethanol may also reduce existing disulfide bonds and may alter the primary structure of rice protein. Artifacts are probably formed in guanidine solutions depending on the concentration of denaturing agent and of protein, as earlier observed with NaOH (1968 Annual Report).

Extraction and composition of glutelin. In a cooperative study with the Department of Botany, University of Durham, England, "crude" glutelin was prepared from milled rice flour by extraction of albumin-globulin with 0.5 M NaCl and of prolamin with 70 percent ethanol containing 0.6 percent β -mercaptoethanol (ME). The solvent 0.5 percent sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) with 0.6 percent ME extracted 91 percent of glutelin without gelatinizing starch granules, whereas chaotropic solvents, such as urea and guanidine, gelatinized starch. Overnight exposure to 70 percent ethanol reduced the solubility of "crude" glutelin in SDS-ME by as much as 14 percent. The *S*-cyanoethyl glutelin, prepared from "crude" IR480-5-9 glutelin (9.5% protein) by SDS extraction and reaction with acrylonitrile, showed three major subunits with MW 38000, 25000, and 16000 in the ratio of 2:1:1 (based on dye absorption of the protein bands) by

6. Molecular weight fractionation of guanidine-HCl extracts of brown rice and bran and solutions of rice albumin, globulin, and prolamin on Sepharose 4B (26 × 345 mm) and Bio-Gel P-200 (26 × 925 mm) columns in series. Elution rate was 12 ml/h using 0.1 M phosphate buffer pH 7.5 containing 1 M guanidine-HCl and 0.02% sodium azide. IRRI, 1975.

SDS-polyacrylamide gel (PAG) electrophoresis. The preparation from "crude" glutelin (4.8% protein) of commercial rice flour had a corresponding subunit ratio of 16:3:1. The MW 38000 subunit was unique to glutelin since it was not present in *S*-cyanoethyl albumin-globulin and prolamin. The subunits were only partially purified by SDS-Sephadex G-150 filtration of *S*-cyanoethyl glutelin (fig. 7). Only the MW 25000 subunit was obtained relatively free of other subunits.

The *S*-cyanoethyl glutelin was also prepared from crude IR480-5-9 glutelin-prolamin by

7. Molecular weight fractionation of *S*-cyanoethyl rice glutelin prepared from IR480-5-9 rice "crude" glutelin by the SDS (sodium dodecyl sulfate)- β -mercaptoethanol method on a Sephadex G-150 column (30 $\times$ 600 mm) with 0.05 M Tris-HCl pH 8.6 with 0.5% SDS as eluent. The numbers 38, 25, and 16 refer to MW $\times 10^{-3}$ of the three major subunits of the reduced glutelin as determined by SDS-polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis. IIRRI, 1975.

NaOH extraction followed by precipitation from NaCl solution at pH 10, ethanol washing, and alkylation. It gave the same three major subunits in the same ratio on SDS-PAGE electrophoresis as did that prepared by the SDS-ME method. Some contaminating protein subunits were, however, removed during glutel-

8. Chromatography of *S*-cyanoethyl rice glutelin prepared from IR480-5-9 "crude" glutelin-prolamin by the NaOH-NaCl method on a carboxymethyl-Sephadex C-50 column (25 $\times$ 400 mm) using a nonlinear pH gradient. The numbers above the peaks refer to MW $\times 10^{-3}$ as estimated by sodium dodecyl sulfate-polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis. IIRRI, 1975.

9. Disc electrophoretic pattern of soluble protein and zymogram of nitrate reductase, nitrite reductase, glutamate dehydrogenase, and catalase in 10-day-old IR22 rice seedling grown in Hoagland solution containing 40 ppm NH_4^+ or NO_3^- N. IIRRI, 1975.

lin precipitation at pH 10 in 0.14 M NaCl. Fractionation of this *S*-cyanoethyl glutelin on a carboxymethyl-Sephadex C-50 column by a pH gradient separated two of the three major subunits (fig. 8). The MW 38000 subunit eluted at pH 6.2-8.5 and the MW 16000 subunit, at pH 8.6-9.2; the MW 25000 subunit eluted impure at above pH 9. On rechromatography, the MW 38000 subunit eluted mainly at pH 6.5-7.0 and the MW 16000 subunit at pH 8.7.

Isozymes in IR22 rice seedlings. Soluble protein of shoot and root of 10-day-old IR22 seedlings grown in Hoagland solution containing NH_4^+ or NO_3^- N were analyzed for

qualitative differences in the activities of their nitrate reductase, nitrite reductase, glutamate dehydrogenase, and catalase. Differences in the electrophoregram of soluble protein and in the zymograms of nitrate reductase, glutamate dehydrogenase, and catalase were mainly be-

tween shoot and roots and were not from N source (fig. 9). The major protein of the shoot must be Fraction I protein. Nitrite reductase bands were observed only in plants grown in NO_3^- . Nitrate reductase bands were not detected in the root.

Genetic evaluation and utilization (GEU) program

Drought tolerance

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SUMMARY

During 1975, we made 160 single crosses, 263 top crosses, and 9 double crosses to combine drought resistance, quick recovery, resistance to major diseases and insects, and popular grain quality.

In the past, single crosses involving a traditional upland variety and a pest-resistant semidwarf generally produced partially sterile hybrids. We made a genetic study to determine if restricted recombination was a limiting factor in such crosses and would thus explain our failure to find desired progenies in hundreds of earlier crosses. Five of the eight upland/semidwarf crosses showed aberrant segregation for one or two loci of the concerned marker genes whereas all three upland/upland crosses gave normal ratios of recombinants.

We are circumventing the problem of low genetic affinity between the upland and lowland types by using promising breeding lines selected from previous upland/semidwarf crosses.

During the 1975 dry season, we mass-screened in the field 3,683 varieties and selections from Asia, Africa, and Latin America, and from IRRI. The largest proportion of resistant or moderately resistant entries were traditional varieties from Thailand, Laos, Malaysia, Taiwan, South Vietnam, and the Philippines. Several varieties from the Assam Rice Collection of India also responded well.

Continuing greenhouse studies revealed large differences in drought tolerance and recovery among rices subjected to severe soil moisture stress in containers. We have continued this investigation using seedlings in the phytotron to better control the test conditions.

In the 1975 upland rice variety trials, 81 rices were tested at each of six locations in the Philippines. In the wet season, rainfall was sufficient and well distributed at most locations, but short dry periods allowed scoring at some locations. We observed variation in response to and recovery from drought during these periods.

Two hundred and thirty-one varieties were examined for total deep-root-to-shoot ratio, or the ratio of weight of root fraction below 30 cm from the soil surface to weight of the shoot. Among rices tested, the ratio varied from

10 to 90 mg/g. We examined the relationship between deep-root-to-shoot ratio and visual scoring for drought resistance under field conditions for 194 varieties and found a close association between these measurements. This relationship suggests that field evaluations of drought resistance may depend largely on "avoidance" mechanisms such as deep root systems that can absorb water stored in deep soil horizons.

Soil-water-plant relations studies revealed distinct varietal differences in the reactions of rice to water stress as observed in leaf desiccation, proline content in the leaves, and diffusive resistance. Varieties and lines accumulating high amounts of proline showed low leaf desiccation at high soil moisture tension (18 and 19 bars) during vegetative stage. This suggests a positive association between tissue survival and the accumulation of proline in rice leaves.

Field evaluation of rices under a selected topographic sequence allowed their adaptability to different hydrological conditions to be assessed.

HYBRIDIZATION AND SELECTION

Plant Breeding Department

During 1975, we made 160 single crosses, 263 top crosses, and 9 double crosses. Promising breeding lines from both upland and lowland nurseries were used to combine drought resistance with other desired agronomic traits. The lowland lines used have either good pest resistance or quick recovery from water stress. Most of the upland parents were resistant to blast.

For tolerance to cool nights in hilly areas, we used Halan, a photoperiod-sensitive upland variety from the South Vietnam highlands. Preliminary phytotron studies showed that Halan tolerates both high (35°/27°C) and low (29°/21°C) day/night temperature regimes.

During the dry season, the F₂ populations were grown under simulated upland conditions on the IRRI farm. Only 278 plants were selected from 117 single crosses, while 795 plants were saved from 37 top crosses, and 323 plants from 14 double crosses.

Table 1. The mode of F_2 segregation of three marker genes in upland/upland and upland/semidwarf crosses. IRRI, 1975.

Marker gene	Type of cross	Crosses (no.)	
		Normal	Aberrant
<i>gh</i>	Upland/upland	—	—
	Upland/semidwarf	2	2
<i>gl</i>	Upland/upland	3	—
	Upland/semidwarf	—	4
<i>wx</i>	Upland/upland	1	1
	Upland/semidwarf	1	5

To grow our expanding nurseries, we rented a 1-ha field from a farmer in Santo Tomas, Batangas province, Philippines, during the wet season. The field was planted to 278 single cross F_2 populations and two yield nurseries. We also planted a 3-ha field at IRRI's new farm to a replicated yield trial, an observational yield trial, a pedigree nursery, and 54 F_2 populations from 3-way crosses. Even so, we could accommodate only a third of the F_2 populations during 1974–75.

From the 278 single crosses grown in Santo Tomas, 1,396 plants were saved. At IRRI's new farm, 1,057 F_2 plants were selected from the top crosses and double crosses. Many progenies with other desirable agronomic traits have rather thin culms, so the plants lodged badly on the fertile soil (as more insect-resistant varieties are used as parents, thin-culmed progenies tend to increase).

So that local scientists can select locally suited progenies, we continued to distribute F_2 bulk populations to Thailand, Liberia, and the International Institute of Tropical Agriculture, Nigeria.

Genetic study on upland/lowland crosses. In previous years, we often found that single crosses of traditional upland varieties and pest-resistant semidwarfs resulted in nonviable F_1 seeds, spikelet sterility in F_1 plants, and a deficiency of intermediate- or short-statured F_2 plants. Consequently, only a few desirable F_2 plants were recovered from each cross (1973 Annual Report). We investigated 11 F_2 populations in a genetic study initiated in 1974 to compare the mode of segregation of three marker genes (*gh* for gold hull; *gl* for glabrous; *wx* for waxy or glutinous) in upland/semidwarf crosses with that of upland/upland crosses.

In the progeny of the eight upland/semidwarf crosses, 75 percent of the spikelets were fertile; 94 percent were fertile from the three upland/upland crosses. Since all three marker-genes are simple recessive loci, it was relatively easy to detect aberrant ratios of F_2 segregation. The upland/upland crosses gave normal F_2 ratios except in one case involving the *wx* locus. Most of the upland/semidwarf crosses gave aberrant ratios for either *gl* or *wx*, where the homozygous recessive genotypes were short of the expected frequency (Table 1). For the gold hull locus, normal and aberrant segregation ratios appeared in an equal number of crosses. In the course of cultivation and selection, the traditional upland varieties have obviously differentiated far from the tropical lowland types. The partial sterility and aberrant segregation could also partly explain our recent failures to obtain certain desired recombinants. But after further crossing upland/semidwarf progenies with either upland or semidwarf parents, the F_1 progenies improved in both panicle fertility and frequency of desired recombinations.

VARIETAL SCREENING

Agronomy and Plant Breeding Departments

Field screening for drought tolerance (*Agronomy*).

We direct-seeded 1,003 rices in furrows and screened them during the 1975 dry season for drought tolerance. The area was irrigated to saturation (0 cb) with overhead sprinklers at 3 days after seeding, and three subsequent times at weekly intervals until the seedlings were fully established. Irrigation water was withheld at 20 days after rice emergence. We daily measured soil moisture tension using tensio-

Table 2. Promising varieties screened in the field for drought tolerance. Date seeded: Jan. 25, 1975. IRRI, 1975.

Designation	Origin	IRRI acc. no.	Rating at 49 days after rice emergence			Rating at 76 days after rice emergence		
			Growth stage ^a	Drought tolerance ^b	Recovery ^c	Growth stage ^a	Drought tolerance ^b	Recovery ^c
ARC 7327	India	12368	2	1	1	2	3	1
C 8485	Brunei	13481	2	1	1	2	3	1
Bakka Bandjar	Indonesia	13508	2	1	1	2	3	1
Sabah	Brunei	13800	2	1	1	2	3	1
Lua Ngu	Vietnam	16852	2	1	1	2	3	1
Bandja Ili	Indonesia	17216	2	3	1	2	3	1
Olek Bandung	Indonesia	18337	2	3	1	2	3	1
Arya 66	India	19925	3	3	1	3	3	3
ARC 6565	India	20400	3	1	1	8	3	1
ARC 7001	India	20436	3	1	1	4	1	1
ARC 7046	India	20461	2	1	1	4	3	1
ARC 7060	India	20471	4	1	1	8	1	1
ARC 10372	India	20884	2	1	1	5	3	1
Binaritos	Philippines		2	1	1	3	3	1
Dular	India	636	3	3	1	7	3	1
Malagkit Sungsong	Philippines	755	2	3	1	2	3	1
Salumpikit	Philippines	5423	2	1	1	4	1	1
DJ 29	—	8505	2	3	1	3	3	1
DV 110	Bangladesh	8855	2	1	1	4	3	1
Vunam	—	12070	2	3	1	3	3	1
I Deng	Laos	12935	2	3	1	4	3	1
Tally	Nepal	16146	2	1	1	5	3	1
ARC 7102	India	20501	2	3	1	5	3	1
Carreon	Philippines	5993	2	3	1	4	3	1
ASD 7 (Karsamba Red)	India	6303	2	1	1	4	3	1
Surjankuhi	India	8256	2	1	1	4	3	1
DZ 41	Bangladesh	8563	3	1	1	6	3	1
DD-6	Pakistan	8608	3	1	1	7	3	1
Ctg 1516	Pakistan	8704	2	1	1	2	3	1
DM 59	Pakistan	8779	2	1	1	2	3	1
Seri Biru 111	Malaysia	1388	2	1	1	2	3	1
IR442-2-58 (check)	Philippines		2	1	1	2	3	1

^aUsing Standard Evaluation System (SES) for rice on a scale of 0–9: 0 = no germination; 2 = tillering; 5 = heading; 7 = milk stage; 9 = ripe/mature. ^bUsing SES scale of 1–9: 1 = no to very slight effects of stress; 9 = all plants apparently dead. ^cUsing SES scale of 1–9: 1 = 90% plants fully recovered; 9 = no plants recovered.

meters and gypsum blocks installed at 10- and 20-cm soil depths.

Rices were initially scored for drought tolerance at 49 days after rice emergence (29 days after irrigation water was withheld) using the Standard Evaluation System for Rice (1 = no symptoms; 9 = dead). The soil moisture tension at 20-cm soil depth was from 3 to 4 bars. Growth stages of the different lines were also noted at scoring time. The day after the first scoring, 21 mm of rain fell; 6 days later, the rices were scored for recovery, also using the SES for Rice (1 = full recovery; 9 = no recovery).

The trial was scored a second time at 76 days after rice emergence, when most of the rices were at the reproductive stage, at a soil moisture tension of 9–10 bars.

Several varieties from the Assam Rice Collection (ARC numbers) were found highly tolerant to drought (Table 2). The Philippine variety Salumpikit has considerably higher drought tolerance than several Philippine upland varieties, including M1-48 (fig. 1). At IRRI, Dular, which has been reported as drought tolerant in India, showed good drought tolerance at 3–4 bars soil moisture tension during the vegetative stage and at 9–10 bars during the reproductive stage. Other promising varieties include Binaritos and Malagkit Sungsong from the Philippines, Olek Bandung and Bakka Bandjan from Indonesia, and I Deng from Laos (Table 2).

Field screening (Plant Breeding). During the 1975 dry season, the plant breeders mass-screened 2,680 varieties and lines for field

resistance to drought under simulated upland culture. Included in the test materials were 1,004 traditional upland varieties from Africa, Asia, and Latin America; 319 breeding lines from upland nurseries; 635 breeding lines from lowland nurseries; 16 breeding lines from Maligaya Rice Research Station, Philippines; three lines from *Institut de Recherches de Agricultures Tropicales* (IRAT), Ivory Coast; 60 TOX and TOS lines from the International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA), Nigeria; 60 floating varieties; 115 varieties with multiple pest resistance; 475 *Oryza glaberrima* (African) varieties; and four strains of *O. nivara* (Asian) wild rices. Two sister lines of Early Short Peta and Early Tall Peta were also tested.

Land preparation of the test fields was delayed by continuous and late rains in December and January. The test materials were sown in the first week of February. Rices reacted distinctly during the vegetative phase. Showers in mid-to-late April coincided with the reproductive stages of most varieties, preventing measurement of reactions to drought at this stage.

As in previous tests, the largest proportion of resistant (R) or moderately resistant (MR) rices were traditional upland varieties of Thailand, Laos, Malaysia, and South Vietnam. Most upland varieties from Taiwan also reacted as MR.

The *aus*^a and deep-water *aman*^b varieties from Bangladesh were mostly I (intermediate) in their reactions to drought. About 30 percent of the Bangladesh varieties gave MR reactions.

IRAT 8 and IRAT 10 from Ivory Coast gave MR reactions. The new TOX and TOS lines from IITA gave MS to MR reactions. Of the 16 breeding lines from the Maligaya Rice Research Station, Philippines, 3 were MR; 8, I; and 5, MS.

The floating varieties of Southeast Asia were nearly equally divided between MR and I types. Our mass-screening tests over the last 3 years have shown that floating varieties have fairly good levels of drought resistance at the vegetative phase, supporting other scientists' reports. Since most of these varieties are photoperiod sensitive, we could not assess their drought

1. The Philippine variety, Salumpikit, has shown considerably higher drought tolerance than several Philippine varieties, including M1-48. IRR1, 1975 dry season.

reactions at the reproductive phase during the dry season.

The African rices (*O. glaberrima*) were distributed as 25 percent MR; 32 percent I; and 12 percent MS. The remaining 31 percent of the strains gave questionable reactions because of uneven distribution of soil moisture in the field.

Among the four *O. nivara* strains, two were MR and two MS. Distribution of breeding lines from the lowland nurseries was: 9% MR, 38% I, 19% MS, 13% S, and 21% questionable reactions. Among the lowland crosses, those lines that gave MR reactions had IR5 as a parent.

But after a light shower or brief watering, most lowland breeding lines quickly recovered from drought stress. Similar recovery ability was found in some of our upland breeding lines selected from multiple or three-way crosses. Some of our progenies have both quick recovery ability and fairly high drought resistance. Such lines came from crosses involving IR5, Sigadis, or C22 as a parent.

Lowland varieties with multiple resistances to insects and diseases, including the ARC varieties from Assam, India, were: 1% R; 53% MR; 40% I; and 5% MS. An early-maturing variety, ARC 11964, showed a resistant reaction at both the vegetative and reproductive

^aLocal name in Bangladesh for early-maturing varieties of the summer season.

^bLocal name in Bangladesh for the varieties of long growth duration.

Table 3. The distribution of F_2 - F_8 upland breeding lines by their field reactions to drought. IRRI, 1975 dry season.

Type of cross	Lines (no.)	Frequency of reaction ^a					
		R	MR	I	MS	S	X ^b
Upland/lowland	138	9	64	50	10		5
Upland/lowland//upland	2		2				
Upland/lowland//lowland	14		11	3			
Lowland/upland//upland/lowland	4		3	1			
Dual-purpose/upland//lowland/upland	10		7	2			1
Dual-purpose/upland///upland/lowland//lowland	3		1		2		
Dual-purpose/lowland//dual-purpose/upland	2			2			
Dual-purpose/lowland//lowland/upland	71		24	12			35
Lowland/lowland//upland/lowland	24		7	9			8
Lowland/lowland//lowland/lowland	8			2			6
Lowland/lowland	46		17	29			

^aR = resistant; MR = moderately resistant; I = intermediate; MS = moderately susceptible; S = susceptible. ^bQuestionable reaction due to unevenness in soil moisture distribution as indicated by the control varieties.

phases. An escape mechanism involving extreme earliness may have been involved.

Our upland breeding lines showed a wide array of reactions to drought. Three percent of the test materials were resistant; these came from our earlier crosses involving OS 4 as a parent. Those lines that gave the MR reaction have at least one upland variety as a parent (Table 3). About 48 percent of the lines that showed R and MR reactions had at least one upland parent while only 31 percent of the progeny of crosses that did not involve an upland parent were rated MR.

Over the past years, the distribution of our upland breeding lines when mass-screened was: 2% R, 28% MR, 56% I, and 12% MS.

Early Short Peta and Early Tall Peta, both sister lines from Peta⁴/TN1, were S to drought

under field conditions, confirming previous findings that height alone is not directly related to drought resistance (1974 Annual Report). But intermediate or tall varieties that are susceptible to drought have an advantage over short varieties because their plant height is relatively less reduced by water stress than that of the shorter varieties.

Since 1973, we have mass-screened 6,346 entries during three dry seasons. Table 4 shows their distribution by field reaction.

In mass field screening during the 1975 wet season, a 10-day dry spell in August reconfirmed the dry season reactions to drought. The stress period coincided with the panicle initiation stage of many lines. Those that showed I to MS reactions in the dry-season test also reacted similarly during the dry period of the wet season. IR28, IR30, IR2043-104-3, and other lowland breeding lines had severe leaf drying, stunted growth, and high panicle sterility. The duration from seeding to flowering was markedly lengthened. Most of the breeding lines that had an upland parent had less reduction in height, few or no dead leaves, good grain filling, full panicle exertion, and high panicle fertility.

Seedling test for drought resistance (*Agro-nomy*). Drought may occur at any stage of growth. The probability of drought associated with erratic beginning of the monsoon is relatively high in many rainfed cultural systems. Thus, we have developed a systematic procedure for drought screening, using the phytotron to control light, temperature, and evaporative demand.

Pregerminated seeds are sown in trays with 15 cm of well-fertilized mixture of clay loam and rice straw. Seedlings are grown in a glass-house under well-watered conditions to the

Table 4. Mass screening for field resistance to drought. IRRI, dry seasons of 1973-75.

Year	Entries tested (no.)	Reaction ^a				
		R	MR	I	MS	S
1973	1383	35	149	382	577	239
1974	2270	107	677	1091	329	62
1975	2693	38	929	935	304	89
Total	6346	180	1755	2408	1210	370

^aR = resistant; MR = moderately resistant; I = intermediate; MS = moderately susceptible; S = susceptible.

2. Relationship of percent survival and exposure to growth chamber conditions for six rices and sorghum. Photo at right illustrates variation in survival at seedling growth stages. IRRI, 1975.

three-leaf stage (10–12 days). The trays are then placed in a growth chamber regulated to simulate soil and atmospheric drought conditions. The degree and duration of water stress are manipulated by altering the temperature, vapor pressure deficit, and duration of exposure. After a specified exposure, the trays are returned to the greenhouse and rewatered. Two to three days later, we rate the percent survival. To develop the systematic screening procedure, we conducted preliminary experiments under various combinations of physical and biological factors. We have found large differences in percent survival using this test (fig. 2).

Although the absolute values for percent survival among rices may be altered by changing the physical test conditions or the duration of exposure, the relative survival trend among rices appears to be an inherent varietal characteristic.

Interestingly, the percent survival is lower for many traditional upland rices than for rices from lowland origins. It is interesting to note from previous research that these upland types have well-developed root systems. Such a

drought-resistance characteristic would be of little benefit under these test conditions.

Seedling survival is high in Leb Mue Nahng 111, a floating rice from Thailand, and low in Moroberekan, a West African upland variety. Figure 3 illustrates a basic difference in tissue water relations between the two varieties. Leaf water potential decreases in both varieties when exposed to soil and atmospheric conditions of drought. But the two types of rice differ markedly in the maintenance of relative water content. Percent relative water content is higher in Leb Mue Nahng 111 in the latter part of the exposure period, which may be critical to its survival at low leaf-water potentials. Thus the mechanism exploited in this test may be primarily one of "drought tolerance," compared with the "drought avoidance" characteristic of deeply penetrating root systems. The incorporation of mechanisms for both drought avoidance and drought tolerance may strengthen future improved rices for drought-prone cultural systems.

Methodology studies in the greenhouse (*Agromony*). We continued to improve techniques for screening rices for tolerance and ability to

3. Relationship between relative water content and leaf water potential for two varieties that differ in percent survival at seedling stage (percent survival is high in Leb Mue Nahng 111, and low in Moroberekan). IRRI, 1975.

recover as part of the drought tolerance/resistance complex.

Twelve rices were planted in dry soil in four tanks with a rooting depth of 45 cm. The first tank was the control, where rices were grown under continuous saturation. In the second tank, rices were grown for the first 9 days under adequate moisture supplied through perforated PVC pipe installed at the bottom. After 9 days, moisture supply was discontinued from the PVC pipe and rices were grown for 73 days with no additional moisture until soil moisture tension (recorded by gypsum blocks at depths of 15 and 30 cm) rose to more than 19 bars (fig. 4). Moisture content was gravimetrically determined and data were then converted to soil moisture tension using the desorption curve. Moisture was then resupplied so that we could study the recovery ability of rices.

In the third tank, moisture was cut off at 45 days after seeding for 37 days. In the fourth, moisture supply was cut off at 60 days after seeding. The third and fourth tanks were used to determine drought tolerance at the reproductive stage. Depending on the treatments, moisture supply was resupplied to evaluate the ability of rices to recover.

The upland variety Moroberekan was the susceptible check; it was completely killed at all growth stages when soil moisture tension exceeded 16 bars. Drought tolerance was most outstanding with IR2035-117-3, which also recovered almost completely after drought stress was relieved. This semidwarf line may be highly valuable for rainfed lowland conditions, but not for upland culture. Other promising lines from this trial were IR1529-430-3 and IR442-2-58.

Between the two lines from the crosses involving an upland parent, IR1750-F5B-5 (parents, E 425/IR22) was considerably better than IR1746-226-1 (OS 4/IR8).

This technique seems promising for screening rices for tolerance to severe drought and recovery ability. Based on this technique, a greenhouse has been built at IRRI to screen from 1,000 to 3,000 breeding lines/year (fig. 5).

Implications of drought field screening in dry season (Agronomy). In a lysimeter study at the IRRI farm during the 1975 dry season, the growth performances of three rices, OS 6, IR442-2-58, and IR1545-339, were compared at various levels of solar energy and soil moisture tension. Seeds were dibbled into the dry granulated soil in the lysimeters every 10 cm at a 20-cm row spacing. At 10 days after germination, the seedlings were thinned to 1 plant/hill. The fertilizer rate was 100-60-60 kg/ha of N-P₂O₅-K₂O. The nitrogen fertilizer was applied in split doses and phosphorus and potassium were applied as basal treatments. The design was 3 × 3 × 3 factorial with two replications.

Levels of solar energy in terms of percentage of intercepted light or light intensity were adjusted by shading the lysimeters with one or two layers of thin cloth at 30 cm above the plant canopy. Levels of soil moisture were maintained either at continuous saturation (0 bar) or under natural drying at as high as 1 bar or 5 bars of soil moisture tension. The stressed plots were controlled by monitoring the readings of pre-calibrated cylindrical gypsum blocks buried 20 cm below the soil surface. Soil moisture tension was relieved by rewatering the lysimeters when the tension reached 5 bars (20–40 ohms electrical resistance meter).

Weekly changes in plant height and tiller

4. Desorption curve for the soil used in the greenhouse experiment (above) and changes in soil moisture tension at the three growth stages of rice (below). Greenhouse experiment, IRRI, 1975 wet season.

number were recorded. Leaf area and dry-matter production were measured only once prior to panicle initiation (data not presented).

The plant height increased when plants were subjected to lower solar energy under continuously saturated conditions. Both the intermediate-statured line IR442-2-58 and the semi-dwarf line IR1545-339 were about 7 percent taller at 70–75 percent solar energy and 11 percent taller at 45–60 percent. But the plant height of the tall upland variety OS 6 remained about the same at light intensities of from 70 to 75 and from 45 to 50 percent. We made no effort to separate the effects of light quality and light intensity.

Table 5. Effects of moisture stress and solar energy, and of their interaction, on the percent increase or decrease in plant height^a of three rices. Field lysimeter study, IRRI, 1975 dry season.

Soil moisture tension (bars)	Solar energy (%)	Increase or decrease in plant ht ^a (%)			
		OS 6	IR442-2-58	IR1545-339	Av.
5	100	-27	-32	-26	-28
0	70-75	12	7	11	10
0	45-50	7	11	17	12
5	70-75	-5	-18	-17	-14
5	45-50	-4	-5	-18	-9

^aPositive value means taller than the check (100% and 0 bar); negative value means shorter than the check.

At low moisture stress, plant height increased somewhat within a 2-week period. The plant heights decreased when the soil moisture tension became higher, indicating that moisture stress limits plant height, offsetting the effects of low light intensity. But the low sunlight also decreased the rate of drought damage (Table 5). These results partially explain why some farmers

5. Greenhouse tanks showing method of supplying moisture through perforated PVC pipes from the bottom of the tanks to screen rices for drought tolerance. IRRI drought screening greenhouse, 1975.

grow upland rice under coconut groves under low solar energy. Further, severe moisture stress overwhelmed the stimulating effect on plant height of low light intensity. Under severe moisture stress and high solar energy (simulating drought screening during the dry season), plant height was markedly lower than under high moisture stress and low solar energy conditions (wet-season screening). These results indicate that even after initial drought screening in the dry season, the final screening should be carried out during the wet season under natural drought conditions. This could be done by planting screening nurseries at predetermined intervals at different sites, similar to the International Upland Rice Observation Nursery (IURON).

FIELD PERFORMANCE OF RICES UNDER UPLAND CULTURE

Agronomy and Plant Breeding Departments

Field studies (Agronomy). The 1975 upland rice variety trials were conducted in six locations in the Philippines: IRRI; Bureau of Plant Industry (BPI) stations at La Granja, Negros Occidental, and Tupi, South Cotabato; Central Mindanao State University (CMSU), Bukidnon; and farmers' fields in Cuenca and Santo Tomas, Batangas. The objective was to select, for upland rice culture, outstanding lines with high yield potential, tolerance to and good recovery from drought, and pest resistance.

At each location, we tested 81 rices, consisting of lines found promising in previous tests and of upland varieties recommended by the Philippine seedboard. Two seeding dates were used: at the start of the region's rainy season and a month later at IRRI, the two Batangas sites, South Cotabato, Bukidnon, and Negros Occidental.

The entries were planted in 15-sq-m plots arranged in triple lattice design and were replicated three times. Seeding rate was 100 kg/ha. A total of 80 kg N/ha was applied in three split doses (every 30 days) starting at 10 days after seedling emergence. Phosphorus at 30 kg P₂O₅/ha and potassium at 30 kg K₂O/ha were also applied as a basal treatment.

Data on rainfall and soil moisture tension

6. Rainfall distribution, drought tolerance, and growth stage of crop at Santo Tomas, Batangas, Philippines. IRRI Upland Rice Yield Trial, 1975 wet season.

were collected at all sites. Data on solar radiation only were collected at IRRI; Cuenca, Batangas; and Negros Occidental.

Drought tolerance. Since rainfall was sufficient throughout the wet season at Cuenca, Batangas, and at IRRI, we could not rate rices for drought tolerance. Seedings at Santo Tomas, Batangas, were exposed to two 7-day dry periods. The first was during the second and third weeks of July (when first-seeding entries were at maximum tillering stage). Soil moisture tension rose to 65 cb (fig. 6), but no significant symptoms of water stress were observed. During the second 7-day dry spell in the third week of August, soil moisture tension reached 51 cb. Most first-seeding entries were at the early reproductive stages (panicle initiation and booting) and differential effects of drought were noted. Following this dry period, adequate rain fell and each entry was rated for recovery from drought.

To describe the effects of moisture stress, we divided the varieties into three maturity groups: 1) early maturing (120 days or less); 2) medium maturing (121 to 130 days); and 3) late maturing (131 days or more). Rices were rated for tolerance to and recovery from drought stress by the SES scale.

Of the 13 rices grouped as early maturing, seven had drought tolerance scores of 3; the rest had scores of 5 (Table 6).

In the medium-maturing group, 18 lines yielded 2.5 t/ha or more. Ten had drought-tolerance scores of 3 as well as good ability to recover from drought (Table 7).

The higher yielding, late-maturing lines appeared to be more drought tolerant than the early and medium-maturing groups in Santo Tomas; 13 were rated favorably for both drought tolerance and recovery (Table 8). IR2035-197-3 showed no sign of water stress, while IR937-76-2 reacted poorly to and recovered poorly from drought. The late-maturing check variety IR5 reacted favorably to both (Table 8).

We observed at Santo Tomas that growth duration of varieties was generally longer in the first seeding than in the second seeding (Tables 6, 7, and 8), probably because the second dry period occurred when first-seeding varieties were in the early reproductive stage, while second-seeding varieties were still in the vegetative phase.

Diseases. The important diseases at IIRRI and Batangas were sheath blight, brown spot, bacterial leaf streak, false smut, and leaf blast. IR442-2-58 was severely infected with leaf blast at both locations in Batangas and at IIRRI. The following entries had the lowest rates of disease infection: early group, IR1746-226-1 and FH 109; medium-maturing group, IR1693-P36-197, IR2031-729-3; late-maturing group, IR3273-P339-1.

Yield. The highest yielding lines in the early-maturing group were IR2061-522-6, IR1746-226-1, and IR1545-339; all averaged 2.9 t/ha, while the early-maturing check averaged 2.3 t/ha (Table 6).

Of the medium-maturing group, IR1529-430-3 yielded highest, with 3.6 t/ha; 18 lines yielded 2.5 t/ha or more (Table 7).

Most of the highest yielders in the 1975 upland variety trial were late in maturity (Table 8). Twenty-four varieties, including the check IR5, yielded 3.0 t/ha or more. The top yielder in this group, and also the highest overall yielder, was IR8³/Carreon, which averaged 4.2 t/ha.

Based on yielding ability, drought tolerance, and recovery ratings, the following lines appeared promising: early-maturing, IR2061-522-6, IR1746-1-1-3; medium-maturing, IR-1529-430-3, BPI 76⁹/Dawn; late-maturing, IR8³/Carreon, IR3273-P339-1, IR3273-P339-2, IR2035-353-2, IR2035-242-1, and IR3273-P339-3.

IR1529-430-3 has consistently yielded well in the field in both years of drought and of good moisture supply. Further greenhouse and field studies indicate that it has good drought tolerance.

Field studies (Plant Breeding). At IIRRI. The yields obtained at a well-drained site at IIRRI were highly variable (fig. 7). The total precipitation during the growth period was only 969 mm. A dry spell occurred in July, and in mid-August, during the maximum tillering, panicle initiation, and booting stages. Both IR28 and IR30, which flowered shortly after the dry spell in mid-August, yielded low (0.8 and 0.2 t/ha). The plants were greatly reduced in height, the panicles highly sterile, and the 100-grain weights very light (1.7 g and 1.9 g). But breeding lines selected for higher resistance levels from upland nurseries, such as the IR1746 lines, had stable yields that averaged 2.2 t/ha. The flowering time was greatly delayed in many semidwarfs from the lowland breeding nursery; the line IR2053-442-1, for example, flowered 35 days later than when planted on a wet soil (Table 9). The yields of the semidwarfs varied from 1.8 t/ha for IR2053-522-2 to 4.8 t/ha for IR3260-91-100. IR3260-91-100 recovered quickly by producing new tillers and benefited from late rains because of its late maturity (fig. 7).

At the wet-fertile site on IIRRI's newly acquired farm, the vegetative growth of all test materials was higher because precipitation was heavier and more evenly distributed during the growing season and soil was more fertile. The yield data from the wet-fertile site might serve as the higher limit for the potential yield of

Table 6. Growth duration, tolerance to and recovery from drought, resistance to important diseases, and yield of early-maturing rice under upland conditions in the Philippines. IRRI; Santo Tomas and Cuenca, Batangas province; La Granja, Negros Occidental province; and Tupi, South Cotabato province. IRRI, 1975 wet season.

Designation	Growth duration ^a (days)	Drought tolerance ^b	Recovery from drought ^c	Affected by ^d	Yield ^e (t/ha)											
					IRRI					Cuenca					La Granja	Tupi
					Jun 14 seeding	July 9 seeding	May 7 seeding	Jun 7 seeding	Apr 29 seeding	May 30 seeding	May 7 seeding	Jun 7 seeding	Apr 29 seeding	May 30 seeding		
IR2061-522-6	120	3	1	ShB BLS BS FS	2.1*	4.0	2.2	4.4**	2.9	3.2	—	—	—	—		
IR1746-226-1	120	3	1	ShB FS	—	2.1	2.9*	3.5	3.5*	3.7	2.1**	1.7	2.3	2.0		
IR1545-339	120	3	3	ShB BS	1.8	2.9	3.0*	4.4**	2.9	3.8*	1.5	2.0	2.0	1.9		
IR1746-226-1	120	3	3	BS	2.7*	—	2.7	—	3.3	—	—	—	—	—		
IR1750-F5B-3	114	5	3	ShB BS	1.3	2.6	2.8	3.0	2.9	3.8*	2.1**	2.4	2.4	2.4		
IR1746-226-1	120	5	3	ShB BS FS	2.0*	2.2	2.2	3.1	3.3	4.3**	1.4	1.9	1.9	1.9		
IR1750-F5B-5	117	5	5	ShB CLS	1.2	2.5	2.7	3.2	3.0	3.3	1.2	2.8	2.8	2.8		
IR1746-88-1	120	5	1	ShB BS FS	1.4	—	2.5	2.9	2.4	3.4	1.2	2.1	2.1	2.1		
IET 1444	112	—	—	ShB BS	1.2	3.1	—	3.0	—	2.7	1.4	—	—	—		
IR1750-F5B-2	119	3	1	ShB BS CLS FS	1.7	1.9	2.2	2.0	2.9	2.7	1.4	1.8	—	—		
FH 109	110	5	3	ShB	1.3	2.5	1.2	1.7	2.6	2.2	2.0**	—	—	—		
Aus 177	116	3	1	ShB BLS BS CLS	2.5**	2.2	1.8	0.3	2.0	0.8	1.5	—	—	—		
M1-48 (check)	118	3	1	ShB BLS FS	1.0	3.2	1.9	2.8	2.5	2.8	1.4	1.4	2.5	2.5		

^aAv. growth duration for two seedlings each at IRRI and Santo Tomas, Batangas. ^bScored by the Standard Evaluation System (SES) for rice on a scale of 1 to 9:1 = none to slight effects of stress; 9 = all plants dead. ^cScored by SES on a scale of 1 to 9:1 = 90% fully recovered; 9 = no plant fully recovered. ^dShB = sheath blight; BLS = bacterial leaf streak; BS = brown spot; CLS = *Cercospora* leaf spot; FS = false smut. ^e*, ** = Significantly higher than M1-48 (check) at 5% and 1% level, respectively.

Table 7. Growth duration, tolerance to and recovery from drought, resistance to important diseases, and yield of medium-maturing rice under upland conditions in the Philippines. IRRI: Santo Tomas and Cuenca, Batangas province; La Granja, Negros Occidental province; and Tupi, South Cotabato province. IRRI, 1975 wet season.

Designation	Growth duration ^a (days)	Drought tolerance ^b	Recovery from drought ^c	Affected by ^d	IRRI													
					New farm					Santo Tomas					Cuenca		La Granja	Tupi
					Jun 14 seeding	July 9 seeding	May 7 seeding	Jun 7 seeding	Apr 29 seeding	May 30 seeding								
IR1529-430-3	130	3	1	ShB BLS BS FS	3.3	4.6**	4.3**	4.7**	3.2*	4.3**	1.9	2.6**						
BPI 76/9 × Dawn	121	3	1	Shb BS FS	3.1	3.9**	3.2**	3.9**	3.5**	3.4**	2.1*	4.3**						
C46-15/IR24 ^e	127	3	3	BS FS	2.6	3.9**	3.7**	4.8**	2.4	4.0**	2.0	—						
IR577-24-1	130	5	3	ShB BLS CLS	2.8	4.5**	3.2**	3.8**	3.6**	3.8**	1.9	2.8**						
IR661-1-170	126	3	1	ShB BS FS	2.9	4.1**	3.6**	3.9**	3.4*	4.3**	1.4	2.0**						
IR2035-227-1	123	3	1	ShB BS	3.3	3.4*	3.3**	3.4*	3.4*	4.0**	1.8	2.7**						
IR1480-147-3	127	3	1	ShB BS	2.8	3.9**	3.0**	3.7**	3.5**	3.9**	0.2	2.6**						
B541b/Kn/19/3/4	123	—	—	ShB, BS B	4.0**	4.0**	—	3.0*	—	2.2**	1.5	—						
IR1693-P36-197	128	3	1	ShB	2.9	3.7**	2.5**	3.5**	2.9	2.8**	1.8	—						
IR2031-729-3	124	5	3	BS	2.6	3.9**	2.5**	4.0**	3.3*	2.9**	1.3	2.6**						
IR1487-141-6	127	3	1	ShB BLS BS FS	2.6	3.1	3.0**	4.0**	3.2**	3.8**	1.2	1.9						
IR2734-F3B-20	129	3	1	ShB BS FS	2.6	3.3*	2.5**	3.1**	2.3	3.2**	1.9	3.2**						
IR1697-P22-102	129	5	3	ShB BS FS B	3.4	4.2**	2.0	2.9**	2.6	2.4*	1.4	—						
IR2053-261-2	129	5	3	BS FS	2.1	2.1	2.7**	3.5**	2.8	3.0**	2.6**	—						
IR2043-104-3	123	3	3	ShB BS CLS	3.2	4.4**	1.4	2.2	2.8	3.6**	2.2*	1.3						
IR1154-243-1	123	3	1	ShB BLS FS	1.3	4.3**	3.0**	3.8**	1.9	2.0	1.8	2.7**						
Aus 8	124	3	1	BLS CLS FS	2.4	3.4*	1.8	3.1**	2.7	3.4**	1.2	—						
C-22 (check)	129	5	1	BS CLS FS	2.2	2.0	3.0**	3.2**	3.8**	3.4**	3.0**	3.6**						
IR442-2-58 (check)	126	5	3	BS CLS FS B	2.7	2.2	1.2	1.4	2.2	1.3	1.7	1.1						

^aAv. growth duration for two seedlings each at IRRI and Santo Tomas, Batangas. ^bScored by the Standard Evaluation System (SES) for rice on a scale of 1 to 9; 1 = none to slight effects of stress; 9 = all plants dead. ^cScored by SES on a scale of 1 to 9; 1 = 90% fully recovered; 9 = no plant fully recovered. ^dShB = sheath blight; BLS = bacterial leaf streak; BS = brown spot; CLS = *Cercospora* leaf spot; FS = false smut. ^e*, ** = Significantly higher than IR442-2-58 (check) at 5% and 1% level, respectively.

Table 8. Growth duration, tolerance to and recovery from drought, resistance to important diseases, and yield of late-maturing rices under upland conditions in the Philippines. IRR1: Santo Tomas and Cuenca, Batangas province; La Granja, Negros Occidental province; and Tupi, South Cotabato province. IRR1, 1975 wet season.

Designation	Growth duration ^d (days)	Drought tolerance ^b	Recovery from drought ^c	Affected by ^d	Yield ^e (t/ha)													
					IRR1					Santo Tomas					Cuenca		La Granja	Tupi
					Jun 14 seeding	July 9 seeding	May 7 seeding	Jun 7 seeding	Apr 29 seeding	May 7 seeding	Jun 7 seeding	Apr 29 seeding	May 30 seeding	May 7 seeding	Apr 29 seeding	May 30 seeding	May 7 seeding	Apr 29 seeding
IR8 ⁹ /Carreon	135	3	1	ShB BS	4.1	5.3	4.4**	5.0**	4.5	5.9**	2.1**	2.4						
IR3273-P339-1	138	3	1	BS	3.8	4.6	3.5	4.7**	4.1	5.4*	1.3	—						
IR3273-P339-2	139	3	1	ShB BS	3.8	4.1	3.4	4.8**	3.5	5.5*	2.0**	2.1						
IR2035-353-2	136	3	1	ShB BS	2.9	4.5	3.8	4.2	3.9	4.5*	1.6*	3.6**						
IR2035-242-1	131	3	1	ShB BS FS	3.5	4.0	3.5	4.4	3.9	3.7	1.6*	3.9**						
IR3273-P339-3	144	3	1	ShB BS FS	3.7	4.8	3.6	4.8**	3.2	4.1	1.8**	2.5						
IR26	136	5	3	ShB BS	4.2	4.2	3.2	4.3	2.2	4.3	1.7**	—						
IR3260-91-100	138	3	1	ShB BS	3.6	4.3	3.1	4.8**	3.6	4.4	1.3	2.2						
IR3259-P5-160	140	5	1	BLS BS FS	3.6	4.2	3.8	4.3	4.6	4.4	0.5	1.9						
IR2035-108-2	133	3	3	ShB BLS BS FS	3.1	3.7	3.8	4.2	3.8	4.3	1.2	2.8						
IR2035-178-1	132	3	1	ShB BS FS	3.7	4.2	3.0	4.0	3.4	4.0	1.9**	2.5						
IR2035-197-3	143	1	1	ShB BLS BS	3.0	3.6	2.9	4.1	3.2	3.8	1.8**	4.0**						
IR8 ⁷ /Dawn	139	3	3	BS FS	3.8	4.4	3.5	3.8	2.8	3.7	1.6*	2.9*						
C46-15/IR22 ²	133	5	3	ShB BS	2.6	4.6	3.6	3.6	3.4	3.7	1.6*	—						
IR1529-677-1	131	3	1	ShB BS FS	3.7	3.6	3.5	4.3	3.3	4.2	1.6*	2.0						
IR4520-76-90	140	3	3	ShB BS	3.4	3.3	3.3	4.2	3.5	4.8	1.4	2.3						
IR3273-P272-3	137	5	1	BLS BS	4.1	3.4	3.4	4.4	3.3	3.9	1.6*	1.8						
IR8 ¹¹ /IR8/Tetep//																		
IR8/Carreon	138	3	1	ShB BLS BS	3.3	3.8	3.2	4.6*	3.1	4.6	0.8	2.3						
IR879-314-2	132	3	3	ShB BLS BS	3.2	3.4	3.2	4.6*	3.3	3.7	1.5*	2.6						
IR2035-730-3	139	3	1	ShB BS	3.1	3.6	4.1*	3.8	3.2	4.2	1.4	2.1						
IR1544-238-2	132	3	1	ShB BS FS	3.1	4.0	2.8	4.6*	3.3	3.5	1.3	2.5						
MRC 172-9	133	5	3	ShB BS FS	2.8	4.2	2.6	4.5*	2.6	3.3	0.9	4.1**						
IR1163-135-2	133	5	3	BLS BS FS	3.7	2.9	3.4	3.7	3.1	3.4	1.8**	2.0						
IR937-76-2	134	5	5	ShB BLS BS FS	3.1	4.1	2.8	4.0	2.7	3.6	1.6*	1.8						
IR1529-680-3	133	3	3	ShB BLS BS FS	3.7	4.0	2.7	3.6	2.8	3.3	2.0**	1.6						
IR5 (check)	142	3	1	ShB BS	3.8	4.5	3.0	3.6	4.1	4.4	1.1	2.0						

^aAv. growth duration for two seedings each at IRR1 and Santo Tomas, Batangas. ^bScored by the Standard Evaluation System (SES) for rice on a scale of 1-9: 1 = none to slight effects of stress; 9 = all plants dead. ^cScored by SES on a scale of 1 to 9: 1 = 90% fully recovered; 9 = no plant fully recovered. ^dShB = sheath blight; BLS = bacterial leaf streak; BS = brown spot; CLS = *Cercospora* leaf spot; FS = false smut. ^e*, **, *** = Significantly higher than IR5 (check) at 5% and 1% level, respectively.

breeding lines (Table 9). Among the semidwarfs, IR30 yielded 4.7 and IR3260-91-100, 4.1 t/ha, almost equal to yields under lowland culture. The upland selections from IR1746 averaged 3.0 t/ha, equal to or higher than yields of the improved Philippine upland variety C22 (2.4 t/ha). The local upland check varieties, M1-48 and Kinandang Patong, produced 1.4 and 1.8 t/ha because of early and severe lodging.

At Santo Tomas. This Batangas province site was intermediate in soil fertility and rainfall distribution between the dry and the wet sites at IRRI. During the growth period, 1,041 mm of rain fell. A 2-week dry spell occurred at the flowering stage of the early- and medium-maturing varieties. Among the early maturing entries, the upland breeding lines IR1746-88-1 and IR1750-F5B-5 produced 2.6 and 2.4 t/ha, respectively, while the semidwarfs IR28 and IR30 both gave 1.3 t/ha. The medium-maturing lines averaged 2.4 t/ha (Table 9). The local upland check varieties, M1-48 and Kinandang Patong, gave 1.6 and 1.2 t/ha. Their yields were lower partly because of serious sheath blight infection. On the other hand, the semidwarf IR2053-442-1, which matured in 151 days, benefited from late rains and produced the highest yield, 3.2 t/ha (fig. 8).

Comparison at three sites. The relationship between field reaction to drought and yield performance can be assessed by comparing the yield data at three sites (Table 9).

Although the dry spell at the IRRI dry site lasted for only 9 days during August, yields were reduced and maturity was delayed compared with the yields in the wet-fertile site. The rices rated in the dry season as lower in field resistance to drought were more reduced in yield and more delayed in maturity than the upland rices. IR28, rated as MS (moderately susceptible), yielded only 0.8 t/ha; IR30, I (intermediate)-MS, yielded 0.2 t/ha. Another semidwarf, IR2053-522-2, had an I reaction to water stress at the vegetative growth stage, and yielded only 1.7 t/ha despite its late flowering (which coincided with the late rains).

Generally, lines with relatively long growth duration and quick recovery will produce relatively high yields at Los Baños, even if their field resistance to drought is rather low, because

7. Yield performance of three upland varieties, five breeding lines from upland nurseries, and six breeding lines from lowland nurseries in relation to field resistance to drought, growth duration, and rainfall distribution. Well-drained site, IRRI, 1975 wet season.

the precipitation is usually adequate at the grain-filling stage. IR1529-680-3 and IR3260-91-100, which matured at 145 days, produced high yields of 3.6 and 4.8 t/ha at the drier IRRI site. But they matured outside of the crop season of upland farmers in neighboring areas such as Batangas.

But at three sites yields of lines with higher levels of drought resistance, such as IR1746-226-1 (OS 4/IR8) and IR2734-F3B-20 (E425/IR8//IR5), were more stable.

We identified several experimental lines as promising for upland culture from a compilation of the replicated yield trials at three locations and from the upland observational yield nurseries at two sites (Table 10). Lines

Table 9. Yield and maturity of upland and lowland rices at three sites. IRRI, 1975 wet season.

Designation	Reaction to drought ^a	Yield (t/ha) and maturity (days)					
		IRRI dry site		IRRI wet-fertile site		Santo Tomas ^b	
		Yield	Days	Yield	Days	Yield	Days
<i>Upland rices</i>							
M1-48	MR	2.7	139	1.4	117	1.6	135
C22	I	2.4	145	2.4	124	2.5	141
Kinandang Patong	MR-R	2.4	134	1.8 ^c	117	1.2	135
IR1746-88-1	I-MR	2.1	134	3.3	110	2.6	118
IR1746-226-1-1-2	I-MR	2.1	136	3.4	113	2.4	125
IR1746-226-1-1-3	R-MR	2.3	134	2.4	111	2.4	130
IR1746-226-1-1-4	MR	2.2	134	3.1	110	2.4	127
IR1750-F5B-5	I	0.9 ^d	134	3.6	105	2.4	120
IR2734-F3B-20	I-MR	2.7	144	2.3	120	2.4	138
<i>Lowland rices</i>							
IR28	MS	0.8	119	3.9	100	1.3	111
IR30	I-MS	0.2	129	4.7	107	1.3	119
IR1529-680-3	I	3.6	146	3.3	125	2.3	140
IR2053-442-1	I	2.9	157	3.3	125	3.2	151
IR2053-522-2	I	1.7	150	3.3	122	2.9	143
IR3260-91-100	MS	4.8	145	4.1	130	2.9	140

^aRated in field test, 1974-75 dry season. R = resistant; MR = moderately resistant; I = intermediate; MS = moderately susceptible. ^bIntermediate in wetness and fertility. ^cLodged. ^dSeverely affected by sheath blight.

from our early crosses of OS 4/IR8 and E425/IR22 generally lacked resistance to insects and diseases. But newer lines selected from multiple crosses have resistance to at least one or more major pests.

Breeding lines with intermediate to moderate field resistance to drought yielded from 3.5 to 6.0 t/ha in the observational yield nurseries at the IRRI new farm. The highest yielder was IR3867-2, a line from the cross IR442-2-58/C22//IR442-2-58/Rikuto Norin 21. It is resistant to blast but not to bacterial blight, brown planthoppers, and green leafhoppers. We have combined drought and pest resistance in selected lines from the cross IR3880 (IR841-67/C22//Pelita I-2/IR1541-76). The yield potential of such lines must now be tested at different sites.

Grain quality tests also showed that most of the lines are of intermediate amylose content, ranging from 14.9 to 25.5 percent, and that gel consistency varies from soft to hard.

As we combine drought resistance with other desirable agronomic traits, such as high tillering ability, quick recovery from drought, stiff culms, pest resistance, and grain quality, we monitor the root systems of promising lines to insure that the deep and thick root systems are retained.

Yield stability under upland conditions (*Agromony*). In the upland rice program, we hope to

increase yield potential without losing the yield stability of traditional varieties. But "stability" is difficult to measure. Through the International Upland Rice Yield Nursery (IURYN) in 1974, 81 varieties and lines were evaluated across a range of environments. We examined rainfall distributions and found them somewhat similar—within three distinct periods of low rainfall—across much of monsoon Asia. Thus, we used the 1974 IURYN results to evaluate varietal stability with special emphasis on drought.

After evaluating location and pest descriptions, we selected 13 location/date-of-seeding environments in four countries. Each variety's mean yield was regressed on the mean yield of all varieties at that particular location. The latter served as an "environmental index" of rice growth conditions for the location.

The regression coefficient (slope) of this relationship is interpreted as a measure of yield stability. Figure 9 illustrates the diversity of slope relationships among the 81 varieties and lines used for the analysis. An evaluation of the slope statistics for selected lines (Table 11) demonstrates the value of knowing more than only average yields. The slope parameter gives some indication of yield stability. Other useful parameters are statistics such as the standard

8. Yield performance of three upland varieties, five breeding lines from upland nurseries, and six breeding lines from lowland nurseries in relation to field resistance to drought, growth duration, and rainfall distribution. Santo Tomas, Batangas province, Philippines, 1975 wet season.

error associated with the slope estimate and the residual variance. This type of analysis may be beneficially used to augment the current average-oriented interpretations of results of multi-locality yield testing.

In our search for drought resistance traits, we have used this procedure to identify varieties for more specialized investigation. In this effort, we used the stability index for yield (a small regression coefficient) as well as measures of other plant characters known to respond to drought, such as plant height, tiller number, and days to heading. Identification of varieties with relatively stable responses across en-

Table 10. Promising upland lines with data on agronomic traits and grain quality. IIRRI, 1975.

Line	Cross	Plant ht (cm)	Yield (t/ha)	Maturity (days)	Drought rating	Resistance ^a to				Grain quality			
						Diseases		Insects		Gel temp.	Amylose (%)	Gel consistency	
						BI	ShB	BB	BPH	GLH			
IR1746-88-1	OS4/IR8	130	2.7	110-120	I/MR	S	M	S	S	S	L	24.7	Hard
IR1746-226-1	"	130	2.6	117-127	I/MR	MS	M	S	S	R/S	L	21.1	Med.
IR1746-226-1	"	125	2.6	110-120	MR	MS	MS	S	S	S	L	21.1	Soft
IR1750-F5B-5	F 425/IR22	85	2.3	110	I	S	S	S	S	S	I/L	21.2	Med.
IR3839-1	Pelita 1-2/IR1529-680-3/IR442-2-58/RN21	118 ^b	3.6	110	MR	MS	—	R	S	R/S	I/L	25.5	Soft
IR3867-2	IR442-2-58/C22//IR442-2-58/RN21	156 ^b	6.1	110	MR	R	—	S	S	S	L	21.2	Hard
IR3880-2	IR841-67/C22//Pelita 1-2/IR1541-76	131 ^b	3.5	115	MR	MS	—	R	R	R	L	25.5	Soft
IR3880-13	"	120 ^b	3.5	110-115	I	MS	—	MR	R	S	H/L	18.0	Med.
IR3880-17	"	126 ^b	3.9	115-120	I	S	—	S	R	R	L	14.9	Soft

^aRated by plant pathologists. BI = blast; ShB = sheath blight; BB = bacterial blight; BPH = brown planthopper; GLH = green leafhopper. ^bFrom 1975 dry-season lowland planting.

9. The relationship of stability index (regression coefficient) and variety mean yield for 81 rice varieties and lines entered in the first International Upland Rice Yield Nursery (IURYN), 1974.

vironments and examination of the parental lines may lead to the identification of new mechanisms for resistance to environmental stress.

ROOT STUDIES

Plant Physiology Department

Varietal differences in root-to-shoot ratio. We examined 231 varieties for total root-to-shoot ratio and deep-root-to-shoot ratio (mg/g). Deep-

10. Frequency distribution of deep-root-to-shoot ratio to total root-to-shoot ratio. IRRI, 1975.

root-to-shoot ratio is the ratio of weight of a root fraction below 30 cm from the soil surface to the weight of the shoot. Figure 10 shows that the deep-root-to-shoot ratio ranged from less than 10 to 90 mg/g and is well correlated with total root-to-shoot ratio. Such large varietal differences in root depth suggest that rice varieties differ in their ability to absorb water stored in deep soil horizons.

Deep-root-to-shoot ratio and drought resistance. We examined the relationship between deep-root-to-shoot ratio and drought resistance under field conditions for 194 varieties. Drought resistance was visually rated by the Plant Breeding Department. Figure 11 shows that drought resistance of rice varieties correlated well with deep-root-to-shoot ratio. No shallow-rooted varieties are resistant to drought and no deep-rooted varieties are susceptible. Such close correlation between root depth and drought resistance suggests that drought resistance, as evaluated by the Plant Breeding Department,

Table 11. Yield stability parameters associated with selected varieties and lines from the 1974 International Upland Rice Yield Nursery (IURYN).^a IRRI, 1975.

Designation	no.	Mean yield (t/ha)	Regression coefficient (b)	Standard error (S_b)	Correlation coefficient (r)	Residual variance ($S^2_{b_0}$)
IR2042-178-1	9	2.44	2.04	± 0.36	0.91	0.139
IR577-24-1-1	9	2.84	1.06	± 0.51	0.62	0.189
IR1541-102-7	9	2.40	0.63	± 0.43	0.48	0.137
IR2031-352-3	9	1.74	0.89	± 0.40	0.65	0.283

^aThe relationship of stability index (regression coefficient) and variety mean yield for the four selected lines can be found in figure 9.

11. Relationship between deep-root-to-shoot ratio and field evaluation of drought resistance. IRRI, 1975.

largely depends on an "avoidance" mechanism by deep root systems.

Donors of deep root systems. Table 12 lists donors of deep root systems screened from 231 varieties for deep-root-to-shoot ratio. All except Atlai are rated as R (resistant) or MR (moderately resistant) to drought under field conditions.

Factors affecting root growth. Growth duration. Figure 12 shows the relationship between days to flowering and deep-root-to-shoot ratio. No definite trend can be detected within a range of growth durations from 49 to 98 days, possibly implying that early-maturing varieties could have deep root systems. Early-maturing varieties can escape drought under some agroclimatic environments such as those in Brazil. Therefore, a combination of early maturity and deep root systems should stabilize performance in such environments.

Nitrogen, water supply, light, and plant density. Some agronomic practices and environmental factors affect root growth (fig. 13). A low supply of nitrogen and water stimulates higher root growth relative to shoot growth, while low light intensity decreases root growth. Such behavior may be better understood in terms of competition between the two organs. Shoots and roots compete for nitrogen, water, and carbohydrate. Nitrogen, for instance, is absorbed by roots and translocated to shoots. Thus, when nitrogen supply is limited, roots take nitrogen in the necessary quantities for

Table 12. Varieties identified as donors of deep root systems (rated resistant or moderately resistant in IRRI field screening). IRRI, 1975.

Variety	Origin
Atlai ^a	Bangladesh
E 425	West Africa
Hashikalmi	Surinam
Kataktara	Bangladesh
Khao Lo	Laos
Kinandang Patong	Philippines
KU 70-1	Thailand
Moroberekan	Guinea
M1-48	Philippines
N22	India
OS 4	West Africa
OS 6	West Africa
Palawan	Philippines
Rikuto Norin 21	Japan
RP79-14	India
Tiale	Philippines
Tres Marias	Philippines
1-EB	Liberia
7-B	Liberia
9-D	Liberia
19-C	Liberia
20-A	Liberia
28-A	Liberia
30-C	Liberia
30-E	Liberia

^aRated as intermediate.

growth. As a result, shoots may suffer nitrogen deficiency, resulting in decreased shoot growth relative to root growth. The reverse may be true for light, which affects carbohydrate production.

12. Relationship between days to flowering and deep-root-to-shoot ratio. IRRI, 1975.

13. Effects of nitrogen level, water supply, light intensity, and plant density on root-to-shoot ratio of varieties OS4 and IR20. IRRI, 1975.

Generally, a plant organ nearer to the source has priority in obtaining nutrients to meet its growth requirements. It has been demonstrated that the proximity of sink and source governs the direction in the translocation of assimilates.

The effect of plant density on the root-to-shoot ratio appears to be more complicated with simultaneous competition for light, nitrogen, and water.

Growth performance at different water table depths. A major function of deep root systems is to absorb water stored in the deep soil horizons, helping the plant to avoid drought. One way to relate root depth to drought resistance, therefore, is to assess the plant's performance at different water table depths. Nine varieties were grown in 160- × 160- × 120-cm tanks where the water table was maintained at 30, 45, 60, and 100 cm from the soil surface. The soil was saturated with water at the start of the experiment. The tanks were placed in the glasshouse. In addition, 50 mm of rainfall was simulated once per week. Soil water and the

simulated rainfall were sufficient to support normal growth until about panicle initiation time. Then, water stress gradually set in and became severe at about flowering stage.

Figure 14 shows that out of nine varieties, only two—Dular and Rikuto Norin 21—performed well at different water table depths. At water table depths of 30 and 45 cm, the grain-to-straw ratio of Dular and Rikuto Norin 21 was 1:1, indicating that grain production and vegetative growth were well balanced. Even at water table depths of 60 and 100 cm, these two varieties produced fairly substantial amounts of grain. In other varieties, water stress severely reduced grain production (largely because of high sterility) but not straw weight. In this experiment, grain-to-straw ratio appears to be a good index for measuring water stress. IR5 at water table depths of 30 and 45 cm, for instance, produced large amounts of straw but small amounts of grain, resulting in a low grain-to-straw ratio. Since the grain-to-straw ratio of IR5 with no water stress is about 1:1 (1968 Annual Report), the decrease implies that IR5 suffered water stress even at 30-cm water table depth. To better understand how water stress during panicle development and ripening affect yield, we examined yield components. Figure 15 shows that percentage filled grain was most affected, followed by spikelet number. The 1,000-grain weight was reduced only slightly by water stress. These data indicate that the detrimental effect of water stress on yield is most pronounced at flowering and less (but significantly) pronounced during panicle development. Varietal differences in drought resistance in this experiment are very conspicuous.

Absorption of soil and fertilizer nitrogen. A major function of roots is to absorb nutrients from soil. Nitrogen is usually the most limiting nutrient to growth and yield of rice under both lowland and upland conditions.

To study the effect of root depth on absorption of soil nitrogen, a shallow-rooted and a deep-rooted variety were grown without added nitrogen in root boxes in which available soil depth was varied by placing a polyethylene sheet at from 10 to 90 cm.

At 10 and 20 cm of soil depth, little or no difference was found in dry weight and nitrogen

14. Grain yield and straw weight of nine varieties grown under different water table depths. IRRI, 1975.

absorption between OS 4 and IR20 (fig. 16). At 90 cm, however, the dry weight and nitrogen uptake of OS 4 was more than twice that of IR20. These data indicate that: 1) when soil depth is shallow, there is no difference in absorption of soil nitrogen between shallow-rooted and deep-rooted varieties; and 2) when soil depth is deep, deep-rooted varieties develop their roots in deep soil horizons and thus absorb more soil nitrogen, while shallow-rooted varieties, because of their own restriction on root depth, cannot fully utilize soil nitrogen in deep soil horizons.

Under field conditions, applied fertilizer nitrogen tends to move downward, primarily because of rainfall and soil texture. In sandy

soils with adequate rainfall, rice plants do not suffer from drought but they may suffer from nitrogen deficiency. To study the ability of rice varieties to recover fertilizer nitrogen placed at different soil depths, three varieties were grown in root boxes in which ammonium sulfate labeled with ^{15}N was placed at 10, 40, and 70 cm from the soil surface. Nitrification inhibitor was mixed with the tagged fertilizer to minimize its conversion to nitrate and its subsequent downward movement.

Table 13 shows that a shallow-rooted variety, IR20, recovered 31 percent of the fertilizer nitrogen from the soil at 70 cm depth, while the deep-rooted varieties Khao Lo and OS 4 recovered 46 and 58 percent.

15. Effects of water table depth on yield and yield components of resistant and susceptible rice. IRRI, 1975.

These two experiments show clearly that deeper root depths of rice varieties relate to greater ability of the plants to absorb soil or fertilizer nitrogen from deep soil horizons.

Thus, under water stress, a deep root system helps the plant avoid drought by absorbing

16. Growth and nitrogen uptake of two varieties grown on unfertilized Maahas clay. IRRI, 1975.

water stored in deep soil horizons. When rainfall is adequate, deep roots help the plant absorb soil or fertilizer nitrogen from deep soil horizons. These functions of a deep root system should be particularly beneficial for upland culture with low inputs.

Table 13. Recovery of tagged fertilizer nitrogen placed at different depths under upland conditions in root boxes. IRRI, 1975.

Variety ^a	Depth of placement (cm)	Dry wt (g)	N absorbed (g)			Contribution of fertilizer N-15 to plant N (%)	Recovery of fertilizer N-15 (%)
			N-15 from fertilizer	Soil-N	Total		
IR20	10	77.6	0.61	1.30	1.91	32	61
	40	55.5	0.50	0.95	1.45	34	50
	70	55.9	0.31	0.98	1.29	24	31
Khao Lo	10	87.3	0.57	1.27	1.84	31	57
	40	74.2	0.56	1.07	1.63	34	56
	70	74.8	0.46	1.09	1.55	30	46
OS 4	10	103.4	0.76	1.67	2.43	31	76
	40	90.8	0.69	1.54	2.23	31	69
	70	95.0	0.58	1.72	2.30	25	58

^aDeep-root-to-shoot ratio of IR20 = 10; of Khao Lo = 47; of OS 4 = 47.

DESIRABLE CHARACTERISTICS FOR UPLAND RICE VARIETIES

Plant Physiology Department

Growth duration. Early-maturing varieties are often preferred for upland conditions because they require less water to complete their life cycles and may escape periods of drought during later growth stages. When water stress occurs during early growth, however, such varieties may suffer more than those of longer duration. We conducted experiments on the relationship between growth duration and the mechanisms of drought resistance.

Photoperiod response. The growth duration of a variety is greatly influenced by its response to photoperiod. Upland rice is grown under a wide range of day lengths. Among 30 upland varieties tested, 17 were found insensitive to photoperiod, 5 weakly sensitive, and 8 strongly sensitive (Table 14). The varieties tested generally had long basic vegetative phases (BVP's). However, the Thai varieties KU 70-1, KU 104, and KU 113-1, and the Laotian varieties Khao Lo and Khao Phe, had short BVP's (19 to 29 days) and short growth durations. Pate Blanc MN3 had the longest BVP (78 days) ever recorded at IRRI. It was also the most insensitive to photoperiod.

Most upland varieties are insensitive to photoperiod, but KU 113-1, TD 47, TD 48, and TD 51 from Thailand are strongly sensitive. They are planted in northern Thailand in April

or May and harvested in September or October, when days are short.

In such areas, varieties of longer growth duration (140 to 180 days) might be required. If so, photoperiod sensitivity will be needed.

Growth duration and recovery from moisture stress. Differences in grain yield reductions as a result of moisture stress at different growth stages can be partly attributed to variations in growth duration. The influence of growth duration on the drought-resistance mechanism was studied using a photoperiod-sensitive variety, BPI-76. Moisture stress was imposed at 20 days after sowing (DAS) and growth duration was modified by subjecting the plants to different photoperiods. The plants with longer growth durations gave higher grain yields (Table 15). The optimum growth duration was 138 days.

Analysis of the yield components showed that the plants of different growth durations did not statistically differ in number of panicles per pot at harvest. The treatments differed significantly, however, in number of spikelets per pot because of the larger differences in panicle size or in number of spikelets per panicle.

The percentage of filled spikelets was fairly high (86 to 90%) in all plants, except in those with the shortest growth durations (76%). Short-duration plants had small panicles, averaging 109 spikelets compared with 189 for the 138-day plants.

Table 14. Response of upland rice varieties to different photoperiods. IRRI, 1975.

Designation	Origin	Days to flowering		Basic vegetative phase (days)	Photoperiod-sensitive phase (days)
		10-h photo-period	14-h photo-period		
<i>Photoperiod insensitive</i>					
Pate Blanc MN3	Ivory Coast	113	113	78	0
Colombia 1	Colombia	98	101	63	3
IAC 1246	Brazil	85	91	50	6
Seratus Molam	Indonesia	93	99	58	6
E 425	W. Africa	93	100	58	7
Perola	Brazil	82	89	47	7
Azmil	Philippines	90	98	55	8
Miltex	Philippines	95	104	60	9
Moroberekan	Guinea	94	104	59	10
Yasai	Ivory Coast	99	110	64	11
OS 4	W. Africa	88	100	53	12
Palawan	Philippines	99	112	64	13
63-83	Ivory Coast	84	98	49	14
Lac 5	Liberia	96	111	61	15
Cartuna	Indonesia	72	89	37	17
Lac 23	Liberia	98	119	63	21
IR442-2-58	Philippines	84	108	49	24
<i>Weakly sensitive</i>					
M1-48	Philippines	78	112	43	34
IR5	Philippines	93	128	58	35
KU 70-1	Thailand	58	105	23	48
Khao Lo	Laos	54	130	19	76
KU 104	Thailand	55	205	20	150
<i>Strongly sensitive</i>					
Khao Phe	Laos	59	a	24	200+
KU 113-1	Thailand	64	a	29	200+
Moddai Karuppan	Sri Lanka	84	a	49	200+
TD-47	Thailand	75	a	40	200+
TD-48	Thailand	71	a	36	200+
TD-51	Thailand	70	a	35	200+
Thiorno	Senegal	77	a	42	200+
Vanam Villai	Sri Lanka	84	a	49	200+

^aNo panicle primordia after 200 days of growth.

Table 15. Changes in yield and yield components of BPI-76 plants, varying in growth duration, as a result of moisture stress at 20 days after sowing. IRRI, 1975.

Growth duration (days)	Grain yield (g/pot)	Straw yield (g/pot)	Panicles (no./pot)	Spikelets (no./pot)	Spikelets (no./panicle)	Filled spikelets (%/panicle)
94	35	38	25.7	2797	109	76
113	54	66	24.0	3640	154	90
138	63	92	23.2	4367	189	86
152	58	138	24.7	3448	140	87
LSD (5%)	5	6	ns	296	13	3

This experiment suggests that varieties with longer duration have more time to recover from the effects of moisture stress and that the growth gained by the plants contributes substantially to the total dry matter production.

Optimum growth duration. Early-maturing varieties have been selected in most countries

where upland rice is grown. Early varieties have an advantage where the rainfall distribution is monomodal and of short duration, such as in areas of Senegal (fig. 17).

In areas where the rainfall is barely sufficient but evenly distributed throughout the growing season, such as Balikpapan, Indonesia, and

Mean precipitation (mm)

17. Mean monthly precipitation in eight countries. IRRI, 1975.

Davao, Philippines, medium- to long-duration varieties (120–140 days) would be optimum for upland conditions.

In areas where the rainfall is short and its distribution bimodal, such as Ivory Coast, Liberia, Sri Lanka, and parts of Thailand, varieties of early growth duration may suffer from moisture stress at the critical reproductive stage and may have poor recovery. For these conditions, varieties of longer growth duration may be better.

In Lampang, Thailand, the rainfall patterns in 1971 and 1973 were definitely bimodal, with depressions around June-July, which might explain why photoperiod-sensitive varieties of long growth duration are planted there. In such areas, the photoperiod sensitivity of the upland varieties enables the farmer to seed whenever the monsoon begins with assurance of sufficient moisture during the vulnerable reproductive stage.

When selecting upland varieties, appropriate growth durations should be considered to suit

the local rainfall pattern. Thus, varieties of short- to medium-growth duration are recommended for areas with short, evenly distributed monomodal rainfall patterns, while varieties of medium to long duration are recommended for areas of bimodal rainfall distribution.

Leaf angle. Traditional upland varieties are generally tall and low tillering, with long, droopy leaves that have a wide stem-leaf angle. These characteristics may be advantageous for weed competition. But chemicals have been identified that effectively and economically control weeds in upland rice. So such long, droopy leaves may no longer be so important. Therefore, we studied the importance of leaf angle in drought resistance in upland rice.

We grew in pots IR24, which has erect leaves, and MRC172-9, which has slightly droopy leaves. Two seeds of each variety were sown 10 cm apart in each pot. Fifty days later, we forced the leaves of one plant to droop, changing the leaf angle by attaching putty at the leaf tips. The other plant in each pot served as the erect

Table 16. Leaf angle and response to moisture stress. IRRI, 1975.

Treatment	Before stress			After stress	
	Leaf area (sq cm/hill)	Tillers (no.)	Leaf area (sq cm/tiller)	Leaf area (sq cm/tiller)	Completely rolled (no./hill)
			<i>IR24</i>		
Control—Droopy	2061			229	0
—Erect	2033	19	107	242	0
Stress—Droopy	—	19	—	91	28
—Erect	—	18	—	110	72
			<i>MRC 172-9</i>		
Control—Droopy	2906			162	0
—Erect	2993	26	114	166	0
Stress—Droopy	—	27	—	63	66
—Erect	—	28	—	79	95
LSD (5%)	335	3	ns	12	9

control. Moisture stress was then imposed until half of the youngest mature leaf was dry in the erect-leaved control. Drought resistance was based on the residual green leaf area after rewatering.

In both IR24 and MRC172-9, moisture stress caused a significant decrease in leaf area per tiller (Table 16). Plants of both varieties with erect leaves retained a higher leaf area per tiller after moisture stress than plants with droopy leaves, perhaps because more of the erect leaves curled and rolled. Droopy leaves failed to completely roll and, when subjected to moisture stress, did not roll at the curvature because of the opposite force exerted there. Droopy leaves that were actually scorched at the bend were observed under upland field conditions in Batangas province, Philippines. The leaf curvature is scorched when subjected to direct noon sunlight under moisture stress. As the leaf tissues die at the curvature, the entire upper leaf also begins to die. The inability of the plant leaf to roll completely may also mean greater transpiratory area and therefore more water loss—a more severe effect of moisture stress.

Greater loss of water was indicated in our study with detached leaves of IR442-2-58. Leaf blades of similar physiological age were detached, weighed immediately, and placed in test tubes. Some leaves were forced to droop by attaching masking tape at the tips, while the others served as erect controls. When placed under the sun at a mean temperature of 33°C

for 3 hours the droopy leaves, not being able to roll completely, lost water at a higher rate than the erect leaves, again indicating that erect leaves may be better under conditions where moisture is limiting.

At hours of high light intensity (when the sun is overhead), probably much less energy is intercepted per unit area of leaf in erect than in horizontal leaves. This would mean that erect leaves have less heat load to dissipate than droopy ones, hence the apparent tolerance to moisture stress.

Under favorable moisture conditions, small and erect leaves have better capacity to receive light and higher response to nitrogen than droopy leaves. Their ability to roll easily and withstand drought is also better than that of droopy leaves. Even under moisture stress, the erect-leaved plants may have an advantage over droopy-leaved plants in their photosynthetic ability, dry matter production, and grain yield. In upland rice, the ability of the leaves to roll in response to moisture stress appears desirable for drought resistance. Hence, the drought resistance of upland rices may be improved by incorporating into them the erect-leaf feature of improved semidwarf varieties.

SOIL-WATER RELATIONS IN RICE

Agronomy Department

Selection criteria for drought tolerance screening.

Research was continued to ascertain and improve selection criteria for screening rices for

18. Plant height (relative values with continuous saturation taken as 100) of four upland and nine lowland varieties of rice (average, 1974 wet and 1975 dry seasons) as affected by 18 to 19 bars of soil moisture tension. Greenhouse experiment, IRRI.

19. Tiller number per plant (relative values with continuous saturation taken as 100) of four upland and nine lowland varieties of rice (average, 1974 wet and 1975 dry seasons) as affected by 18 to 19 bars of soil moisture tension. Greenhouse experiment, IRRI.

drought tolerance. During the 1975 dry season, the effect of water stress on 21 rices was studied with the use of a single cycle of water with two levels of soil moisture tension in the greenhouse.

Plant characters. Plant height and tiller number per plant were recorded at the end of the stress period to determine the drought tolerance of different rices and were also measured before harvest to ascertain the capacity of the rices to recover from drought stress. The height of plants exposed to 18 and 19 bars of soil moisture tension during the vegetative stage was markedly lower than that of plants grown in soil with continuous saturation. The percent reduction in plant height for two upland breeding lines, TOX 6-14-2-B₁-B and IR1750-F5B-5, and an upland variety, M1-48, was lower than that of other rices during the vegetative stage. Some lowland breeding lines, on the other hand, exhibited less reduction in plant height when subjected to moisture stress during the reproductive stage. Generally, the upland varieties exhibited a similar reduction in plant height during the vegetative stage and a greater reduction in plant height during the reproductive stage than did the lowland rices

at 18 and 19 bars of soil moisture tension (fig. 18).

Moisture stress only during the vegetative stage caused a reduction in the number of tillers per plant in lowland varieties and lines (fig. 19), but not on upland varieties. This is expected since the lowland varieties, in general, have high tillering capacities when the moisture supply is adequate and they continue to tiller even when the upland rices cease to produce new tillers. A marked reduction in tiller number per plant for lowland rices caused by moisture stress during the vegetative stage of growth would appear to be more deleterious to the lowland cultivars than to the upland rices because of their high tillering capacities. However, this reduction in the number of tillers per plant caused by moisture stress was due primarily to a lack of production of new tillers and not to the death of old tillers. The final recovery during harvest in plant height and number of tillers per plant indicated that many lowland rices have greater ability to recover from moisture stress than the upland rices (figs. 18 and 19).

Three lowland rices (IR442-2-58, IR937-55-3,

and IR5) exhibited excellent recovery in plant height after moisture stress was relieved. The reduction in the number of tillers caused by moisture stress during the vegetative stage was greater for the upland rices than for the other varieties. In fact, at harvest, the reduction in the number of tillers per plant reached 22 percent for upland varieties with 18 and 19 bars of soil moisture stress. This was because many of the late tillers of upland varieties which survived the moisture stress eventually died following relief of the moisture stress, indicating a low capacity for recovery from severe moisture stress damage. Lowland rices, on the other hand, showed a high ability to recover from drought stress. For example, when stressed at 18 and 19 bars of soil moisture tension during the vegetative stage, lowland rices showed less than 3 percent reduction in the number of tillers at harvest. At the same level of soil moisture stress during the reproductive stage, lowland varieties had 11 percent more tillers per plant than rices with continuous saturation because new tillers were produced when the moisture stress was terminated.

PROLINE ASSAY

Agronomy Department

Researchers in Australia recently suggested that proline accumulation in barley might be positively associated with drought resistance and rate of recovery from water stress. To explore the possibility that such associations exist in rice, the proline content of rice leaves was measured during the reproductive stage up to only 13 and 14 bars of soil moisture tension (Table 17) because leaf desiccation was considerable at higher levels (18 and 19 bars) of soil moisture stress. At continuous saturation, the proline content of leaves was constant at all stages of growth. All the varieties and lines accumulated higher amounts of proline with increasing levels of soil moisture tension, with the proline content of leaves increasing rapidly around 7 bars of soil moisture tension. During the 1975 dry season, IR1539-823-1 accumulated the most leaf proline (28 mg/g dry leaves) at 18 and 19 bars of soil moisture tension, followed by IR2035-117-3 (23 mg/g dry leaves), which at 13 and 14 bars of soil moisture tension during

Table 17. Effects of soil moisture tension on leaf proline content of 20 rices. Greenhouse experiment, IRRI, 1975 dry season.

Variety or line	Proline content (mg/g dry leaves)						
	Vegetative stage			Reproductive stage			
	Continuous saturation	Stress			Continuous saturation	Stress	
	7-8 bars	13-14 bars	18-19 bars		7-8 bars	13-14 bars	
		<i>Upland varieties</i>					
Saovina	0.1	0.2	17	12	0.1	0.3	21
M1-48	0.1	0.2	11	7	0.1	0.4	10
E 425	0.1	0.1	8	3	0.1	0.2	7
OS 6	0.1	0.2	10	7	0.1	0.2	7
Moroberekan	0.2	0.2	6	-	0.1	0.3	4
		<i>Experimental lines selected under upland conditions</i>					
IR1746-226-1	0.1	0.3	11	2	0.1	0.3	10
IR1750-F5B-5	0.1	0.4	10	16	0.1	0.2	17
TOX 6-14-2	0.2	0.2	14	14	0.1	0.2	19
		<i>Varieties and experimental lines selected under lowland conditions</i>					
IR20	0.2	0.3	12	14	0.1	0.2	18
IR1529-430-3	0.1	0.2	19	19	0.1	0.1	17
IR1545-339	0.1	0.1	13	15	0.1	0.1	15
IR1480-147-3	0.2	0.2	15	3	0.1	0.2	18
IR442-2-58	0.1	0.1	14	9	0.1	0.1	12
IR5	0.1	0.1	16	9	0.1	0.1	16
IR1646-623-2	0.1	0.1	22	14	0.1	0.1	18
IR1539-823-1	0.2	0.2	18	28	0.1	0.3	22
IR937-55-3	0.1	0.1	17	12	0.1	0.1	16
IR2035-353-2	0.1	0.2	20	10	0.1	0.1	17
IR2035-117-3	0.1	0.2	16	23	0.1	0.1	23
IR2035-197-3	0.1	0.1	20	11	0.1	0.1	22

the reproductive stage had the highest concentration of leaf proline (Table 17).

As a group, upland varieties accumulated more proline than lowland varieties at lower levels of soil moisture tension, but lowland rices accumulated a greater amount of proline at higher levels of soil moisture tension. The proline content of leaf tissue decreased gradually when the stressed plants were watered, with a greater decrease for the lowland rices than for the upland varieties within 7 days after the stress was relieved. Since the proline that accumulates in water-stressed plants may serve as a compound for storing the energy and nitrogen that plant cells need to recover from the effects of drought, perhaps lowland varieties generally use a higher percentage of the accumulated proline within 7 days after the end of moisture stress.

The proline contents of different rices were compared at different levels of moisture stress. When the crop was subjected to 18 and 19 bars of soil moisture tension at the vegetative stage, only Moroberekan, an upland variety from Africa, and IR1746-226-1, a selection bred for upland areas, died. Three upland rices, M1-48, E 425, and OS 6, and a lowland breeding line, IR442-2-58, were partially damaged by moisture stress. In either the vegetative or reproductive stage, the maximum amount of proline accumulated in M1-48, E 425, and OS 6 was 10 mg/g of dry leaves. Furthermore, the results confirm that most rice varieties are more susceptible to moisture stress at the reproductive stage than at the vegetative stage, and that distinct differences in moisture stress among rice varieties exist not only within a particular stage of growth, but also among the various stages of growth. Further studies are needed to correlate proline accumulation in individual rice varieties and lines with their drought tolerance and also with their capacity to recover from moisture stress upon rewatering at different stages of growth.

LEAF DESICCATION

Agronomy Department

In all varieties and lines, desiccation started in the older leaves as the soil moisture tension

20. Leaf desiccation in rice (average of 5 upland and 12 lowland varieties) at 18 to 19 bars of soil moisture tension during the vegetative and reproductive stages. Greenhouse experiment, IRR1.

gradually increased. The percentages of leaves completely desiccated were higher during the reproductive stage than during the vegetative stage, verifying the rice plant's greater susceptibility to soil moisture stress during the reproductive stage than during the vegetative stage. As a group, upland varieties had a higher percentage of desiccated leaves than the lowland rices regardless of the stage of plant growth (fig. 20).

Because severe moisture stress generally causes senescence in cereal grains, it has been suggested that selection of cereal grains for drought tolerance should be based on the plant's ability to promote growth under moderately dry conditions and a minimal tendency towards senescence under conditions of severe drought. For the latter characteristic, a low incidence of leaf desiccation at high levels of soil moisture stress serves as one criterion by which to select drought-tolerant lines. Four lowland varieties and lines exhibited less than 40 percent desiccated leaves during the vegetative stage: IR1529-430-3, IR1646-623-2, IR1539-823-1, and IR2035-117-3. At the reproductive stage, the leaf desiccation in one upland rice, TOX 6-14-2-B₁-B, and four lowland rices,

Table 18. Leaf desiccation of 20 rices as a function of soil moisture tension at the vegetative and reproductive stages. Greenhouse experiment, IRRI, 1975 dry season.

Variety or line	Apparently fully desiccated leaves (%) at the time of stress relief	
	Vegetative stage (18-19 bars)	Reproductive stage (18-19 bars)
<i>Upland varieties</i>		
Saovina	48	88
M1-48	70	83
E 425	83	85
OS 6	66	91
Moroberekan	100	100
<i>Experimental lines selected under upland conditions</i>		
IR1746-226-1	90	99
IR1750-F5B-5	58	87
TOX 6-14-2- B 1 -B	47	69
<i>Varieties and experimental lines selected under lowland conditions</i>		
IR20	56	80
IR1529-430-3	37	60
IR1545-339	43	80
IR1480-174-3	79	86
IR442-2-58	51	76
IR5	65	87
IR1646-623-2	32	68
IR1539-823-1	25	72
IR937-55-3	52	82
IR2035-353-2	47	56
IR2035-117-3	29	72
IR2035-197-3	61	61

IR1529-430-3, IR1646-623-2, IR2035-353-2, and IR2035-197-3, was low (Table 18). All the varieties and lines with 80 percent or more desiccated leaves either failed to recover or recovered only partially after moisture stress relief.

Using low leaf senescence as a criterion by which to select superior drought performance in rice, it appears that some lowland rices and upland breeding lines can withstand severe soil moisture stress with minimal desiccation damage. Additionally, if leaf desiccation can serve as an indicator of drought stress in rice, the percentage of desiccated leaves in a variety caused by a sustained drought can serve as a useful criterion in selecting rices for drought tolerance.

Relationship between proline content in leaf and leaf desiccation. Varieties and lines accumulating higher amounts of proline showed less leaf desiccation at 18 and 19 bars of soil moisture tension during the vegetative stage. A correlation analysis between these two characteristics revealed a direct inverse relationship

21. Relationships between proline content in leaf and leaf desiccation at 18 to 19 bars of soil moisture tension during the vegetative stage of rice. Greenhouse experiment, IRRI, 1975 dry season.

(fig. 21), indicating an association between tissue survival and the accumulation of proline in rice leaves.

Diffusive resistance. Leaf diffusive resistance includes both stomatal and cuticular resistances and is expressed as seconds per centimeter. In continuous saturation, diffusive resistance ranged from 3 to 7 s/cm. A higher diffusive resistance occurred for all cultivars around 4 to 5 bars of soil moisture tension, indicating the beginning of physiological stress. The diffusive resistance could not be measured above 12 and 13 bars of soil moisture tension because of the folding and rolling of the leaves.

As in the 1974 wet season, the diffusive resistance increased for all cultivars as the soil moisture tension increased in the 1975 dry season. During the 1975 dry season at 10 to 11 bars of soil moisture tension, IR1750-F5B-5, a line bred for upland areas, had the highest diffusive resistance at both the vegetative stage (40 s/cm) and the reproductive stage (66 s/cm)

Table 19. Effect of soil moisture tension on diffusive resistance^a and leaf desiccation of 20 rices. Greenhouse experiment, IRRI, 1975 dry season.

Variety or line	Vegetative stage			Fully desiccated leaves (%) 18–19 bars	Reproductive			Fully desiccated leaves (%) 18–19 bars
	Diffusive resistance (s/cm)				Diffusive resistance (s/cm)			
	Continuous saturation	Stress 7–8 bars	10–11 bars		Continuous saturation	Stress 7–8 bars	10–11 bars	
	<i>Upland varieties</i>							
Saovina	3	24	29	48	6	37	37	88
M1-48	5	16	25	70	6	31	34	83
E 425	3	18	26	83	7	22	27	85
OS 6	5	22	27	66	6	22	27	91
Moroberekan	4	20	27	100	6	25	34	100
	<i>Experimental lines selected under upland conditions</i>							
IR1746-226-1	3	24	31	90	5	30	36	99
IR1750-F5B-5	4	15	40	58	4	28	66	87
TOX 6-14-2	4	17	20	47	5	28	38	69
	<i>Varieties and experimental lines selected under lowland conditions</i>							
IR20	4	16	26	56	4	17	28	80
IR1529-430-3	3	28	29	37	6	41	48	60
IR1545-339	3	14	26	43	7	26	26	80
IR1480-147-3	3	18	22	79	6	31	45	86
IR442-2-58	3	22	31	51	6	28	60	76
IR5	4	21	38	65	6	26	38	87
IR1646-623-2	3	16	26	32	6	38	54	68
IR1539-823-1	5	15	27	25	7	39	40	72
IR937-55-3	3	30	30	52	7	32	34	82
IR2035-353-2	4	18	25	47	6	36	52	56
IR2035-117-3	3	28	30	29	7	38	38	72
IR2035-197-3	4	16	20	61	5	30	60	61

^aAv. of both sides of second leaf on mother tiller recorded between 1000 and 1200 hours.

(Table 19). IR5, a lowland variety, had a high diffusive resistance, 38 s/cm, during the vegetative stage. At the reproductive stage, however, the diffusive resistance of five lowland rices—IR442-2-58, IR2035-197-3, IR1646-623-2, IR2035-353-2, and IR1529-430-3—exceeded 45 s/cm. At any level of soil moisture tension, the diffusive resistance value of a rice variety or line was generally higher at the reproductive stage than at the vegetative stage. This offers further evidence that in rice, sensitivity to soil moisture stress is greater at the reproductive stage than at the vegetative stage.

Classification of rices for drought tolerance.

The majority of the rice varieties and lines tested were classified into four groups according to their response to 18 and 19 bars soil moisture tension and recovery capability following moisture stress:

- Susceptible at the vegetative and reproductive stages: Moroberekan, IR1746-226-1
- Moderately tolerant at the vegetative stage

and susceptible at the reproductive stage: M1-48, E 425, OS 6

- Tolerant at the vegetative stage and susceptible at the reproductive stage: Saovina, IR1545-339, IR20, IR5
- Tolerant at the vegetative stage and moderately tolerant at the reproductive stage: IR1646-623-2, IR1529-430-3, IR442-2-58, IR1750-F5B-5, IR937-55-3, IR2035-117-3, IR2035-353-2, IR1480-147-3

FIELD EVALUATION OF RICE VARIETIES UNDER DIFFERENT WATER TABLE LEVELS *Agronomy Department*

Since the differential effect of a constant water table depth on growth and development was demonstrated in previous greenhouse studies, a field study was undertaken to: 1) investigate the effects of a fluctuating water table on rice growth, development, and yield, and 2) assess the stability of yield across varying hydrological

22. Daily rainfall, water table depth and soil moisture tension fluctuations at the bottom and top slope positions of the toposequence from date of seeding to harvest. (Dotted lines indicate water table depth below 125 cm.) New IIRRI farm, 1975 wet season.

conditions for a select group of rice varieties.

A selected topographic sequence created a gradient of water table levels in an area of uniform macroclimate. The water table depth below the surface was monitored daily with the use of water table observation wells. Rainfall data were collected at the center of the plot.

Rice varieties (34) were selected from data on their yield under upland conditions, plant height, and rooting characteristics. They were direct seeded (4 rows/variety) down a 100-m slope, with a check variety, MI-48, after every five varieties across the slope. Basal fertilizer applied per hectare was 40 kg each of P_2O_5

23. Crop response to slope position on the toposequence. GY = grain yield. PHT = plant height at maturity. DTF = days to flowering, and SP = slope position.

and K_2O . Nitrogen was applied in three split doses—30, 30, and 20 kg N/ha—at 10, 40, and 75 days after emergence, respectively. Weed and insect pest control was optimal.

The rainfall over the plot, subsequent water table, and soil moisture tension fluctuations at bottom and top slope locations are summarized in fig. 22.

The change in plant height and days-to-flowering along the toposequence for the check variety MI-48 demonstrates the growth and development response of the crop to the changing hydrological conditions (fig. 23). Although the regression of plant response on the average water table depth was more highly correlated than that on slope position, the varietal performance was more uniformly evaluated in terms of slope position.

Much of the yield response may be attribut-

Table 20. Yield stability statistics for 8 selected varieties/lines and check variety M1-48 grown under varying water table conditions, $Y = a + bX$ where Y = variety yield at a slope position, X = mean yield of all varieties at the slope position. Index number refers to fig. 25.

Index no.	Variety or line	n	Mean yield	b	$\pm S_b$	Residual variance
1	M1-48	10	1.18	1.65746	± 0.166	0.043739
2	IR 1529-430-3	10	2.79	1.56836	± 0.276	0.120525
10	IR 2035-120-3	10	2.78	1.22033	± 0.164	0.042785
11	IR 2035-197-3	10	2.20	0.86306	± 0.454	0.327206
18	IR 26	10	2.74	1.97883	± 0.230	0.083567
24	IR 5	10	2.24	0.39406	± 0.515	0.420147
27	BPI 76 ⁹ /Dawn	9	1.88	0.05393	± 0.377	0.175769
32	Palawan	10	0.39	0.13501	± 0.225	0.080550

able to water stress, as evidenced by soil moisture tension, reduced plant height, and delayed flowering. Changes in disease, insect occurrence, and degree of lodging in susceptible varieties, noted along the transect, also contributed to the change in yield. Thus, when the results of this field evaluation technique are assessed, the impact of the changing water table conditions may be considered a salient factor.

In analyzing the data, the average yield was considered first; then, the stability of the yield on this hydrological sequence was estimated by regressing a variety's response at a particular slope location on the mean of all

rice varieties at the same slope position. The variation in mean yield and stability parameters of yield response for selected rices is shown in Table 20.

The variation in the regression coefficient (slope) among four diverse rices was marked (fig. 24). IR26 was a notable exception from the mean response and exhibited a high mean yield and a relatively high regression coefficient. IR2035-120-3 also had a high mean yield (above average) and a lower regression coefficient. BPI 76⁹/Dawn and Palawan exhibited yield stability; each had a low regression coefficient, but their mean yields differed markedly. Figure 25 shows the relationship

24. Yield response of four diverse rices regressed on average of all varieties at each location on the toposequence. New IRRI farm, 1975 wet season.

25. Distribution of regression coefficients (stability index) and variety mean yield for 34 varieties and lines grown on the toposequence. New IRRI farm, 1975 wet season.

between the regression coefficient, often called "stability index," and the mean yield for the 34 rices tested.

"Base yield" is another characteristic that should be considered. Varieties that have a high regression coefficient often have a very low base yield. They respond well under optimal conditions, but may yield poorly under stress conditions. The base yield of IR2035-120-3 is similar to that of BPI 76⁹/Dawn (stable yields) under the most limiting conditions tested. It may be possible to select varieties which combine good base yield with a high yield potential.

The interpretation and final evaluation of this field technique at a given location will depend on many factors which are location specific.

If the water supply was not limiting, a high average yield might be the principal selection criterion. When a variety is considered for an area with an undependable water supply, emphasis may be placed on the lower regression coefficient and higher base yield level.

The method of analysis of such data is of primary importance. Decreased emphasis on average yield and increased awareness of the manner in which a variety responds over a continuum of changing conditions should be more useful in evaluating rices for release to farmers.

Generally, evaluations of the response of rice to water regimes are performed at locations that represent only a small percentage of the hydrological conditions of rice culture in the region. This present technique of evaluation may serve as an improved method to assess the adaptability of a rice variety across changes in the topography or climatic variation through seasons. This concept could be extended to include "water logging" or submerged conditions depending on the toposequence selected.

SOIL-PLANT-ATMOSPHERE WATER RELATIONS STUDIES

Agronomy Department

Because studies describing crop responses to water deficits are generally based on rainfall or soil moisture characteristics alone, studies

26. Relationship between soil, plant, and atmospheric water statuses. Upland field, Cuenca, Batangas, 1975 wet season.

were undertaken to understand the water status in and around the rice crop. Primarily, this requires quantification of the soil, plant, and atmospheric water statuses and the environmental factors influencing these highly dynamic variables.

In upland experimental fields near Cuenca, Batangas, Philippines, the soil moisture tension was monitored daily (at 1300 hours) at 15, 30, and 45 cm below the crop. The leaf xylem potential, as estimated by the pressure chamber, was measured at 1300 hours on a 4-day interval and when special weather or soil moisture conditions prevailed. The water vapor pressure deficit was ascertained from the continuous records of temperature and relative humidity. Solar radiation and rainfall were recorded daily. The interaction of these factors determined the degree and duration of plant water deficits (fig. 26).

The leaf xylem potential responds not only to the soil moisture levels but also to solar radiation and evaporative demand. The daily minimum leaf xylem potential of all three varieties was correlated with daily vapor pressure deficit, rainfall, and soil moisture tension in that order.

During the period represented in fig. 26, the soil moisture levels became increasingly drier. M1-48 maintained higher leaf xylem potential values than did IR1529-680-3 and IR20 when the soil moisture conditions were

favorable. However, when soil moisture levels decreased at all depths, M1-48 responded in a manner similar to that of the two IRRI lines. M1-48 is known to have a high deep-root-to-shoot ratio (mg/g) of 40 to 50, while this ratio was below 20 for each of the two IRRI lines studied.

Similar studies were initiated in rainfed lowland rice at IRRI. Because of climatic conditions at IRRI, the rainfed lowland rice plots were well supplied with water, and consequently they were sampled only to determine basic relationships. Since the lowland rice varieties grown in these plots experienced no substantial moisture stress, the leaf xylem potentials were relatively high (-4 to -7 bars). The varieties showed similar trends in the fluctuations of the xylem potential through the day, reaching the lowest values about 1200 to 1400 hours. Closure of stomata and an increase in the water status occurred primarily in response to decreased solar radiation between 1500 and 1700 hours.

These studies are part of continuing research on the water relations of upland and lowland rainfed rice.

Genetic evaluation and utilization (GEU) program

Tolerance to injurious soils

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SUMMARY

We have improved our techniques of screening rices for tolerance to adverse soil problems. Several IRRI rices are highly tolerant to salinity, alkalinity, zinc deficiency, phosphorus deficiency, and iron toxicity. Salinity tolerance receives the greatest attention. Rice appears most vulnerable to salinity at transplanting, less at 4 weeks later, and still less vulnerable at 7 weeks after transplanting. The first International Rice Salinity Tolerance Observational Nursery has been screened at 22 locations in 12 nations.

BACKGROUND

In the tropics and subtropics, the modern varieties will not grow or cannot fully express their yield potential on more than 40 million hectares of current and potential ricelands because of one or more of the following soil problems: salinity, alkalinity, strong acidity, iron toxicity, zinc deficiency, and phosphorus deficiency. Improving such adverse soils by adding chemicals or by water management is beyond the means of most countries in South and Southeast Asia. The development of varieties that can tolerate adverse soils would increase the productive capacity of these regions, and would enable vast areas of unused land to be brought into production.

TOLERANCE TO SALINITY

Plant Breeding and Soil Chemistry Departments

Excess salt appears to be the most important soil problem; it is the main obstacle to higher yields or to cultivation itself on about 30 million ha that are otherwise well suited to rice culture. In 1975, we continued to study factors that affect varietal tolerance to salinity; intensified our search for tolerant sources in the germ plasm bank; and emphasized salt tolerance in the breeding program.

Effect of time of salt concentration on growth and yield (*Soil Chemistry*). Salinity in ricefields of both arid and coastal regions can vary widely during a cropping season. In arid regions, salinity may not be a problem during the wet

season, but may become severe during the dry season. In coastal areas, tidal action as well as rainfall pattern may cause the salt level to vary.

Although we have found that varieties differ markedly in their tolerance to salinity, we have not known the effect of high salt concentration on the growth and yield of rice at different growth stages. We screened in the greenhouse three rices previously identified as having different degrees of tolerance: the line IR2153-26-3 (salt tolerant); IR26 (moderately susceptible); and T26 (highly susceptible). The rices were planted on Maahas clay subjected to four salt regimes: 0 salt; 0.15% salt at transplanting, increased 7 weeks later to 0.4%; 0.15% salt at transplanting, increased 4 weeks later to 0.4%; and 0.4% salt continuously from transplanting to harvest.

Salt reduced the growth and yield of all three rices. The degree of salt injury varied with the variety and the growth stage at which salt concentration was increased. Within a variety, the straw yields at harvest were in the order: 0 salt > 0.15% salt at transplanting, increased to 0.4% 7 weeks later > 0.15% salt at transplanting, increased to 0.4% 4 weeks later > 0.4% salt continuously from transplanting to harvest. Grain yields also followed this order for IR26 and T26. The differences among the salt regimes were pronounced in the highly susceptible T26 and the moderately susceptible IR26. T26 gave negligible yields of straw and grain with 0.4% salt at transplanting. IR2153-26-3 was least affected by 0.4% salt at transplanting and showed a small but consistent reduction in grain yield due to 0.4% salt regardless of the growth stage at which it was exposed (Table 1).

The visual symptoms of salt injury agreed with the yield data; IR26 and T26 plants that were subjected to 0.4% salt at planting exhibited the most severe symptoms of salt injury; those that received 0.4% salt at 4 weeks after transplanting showed less severe symptoms; and those subjected to 0.4% salt at 7 weeks after transplanting had the mildest symptoms. The IR2153 plants showed mild symptoms of salinity in all salt treatments (fig. 1).

The two least tolerant rices, IR26 and T26, were most vulnerable to salinity at trans-

Table 1. Influence of four salt regimes on the growth and yield of three varieties on Maahas clay. IRRI greenhouse study,^a 1975 dry season.

Salt regime	Tillers (no.) at harvest	Straw yield (g/pot)	Grain yield (g/pot)
<i>IR2153-26-3</i>			
0 salt	47 b	100 a	84 a
0.15% at transplanting; 0.4% 7 wk later	53 ab	85 ab	64 b
0.15% at transplanting; 0.4% 4 wk later	61 a	70 ab	63 b
0.4% from transplanting to harvest	52 ab	63 b	66 b
<i>IR26</i>			
0 salt	44 b	104 a	92 a
0.15% at transplanting; 0.4% 7 wk later	54 a	77 ab	80 a
0.15% at transplanting; 0.4% 4 wk later	46 ab	53 b	62 b
0.4% from transplanting to harvest	14 c	17 c	13 c
<i>T26</i>			
0 salt	44 a	280 a	44 a
0.15% at transplanting; 0.4% 7 wk later	35 b	194 b	44 a
0.15% at transplanting; 0.4% 4 wk later	10 c	110 c	11 b
0.4% from transplanting to harvest	0.25 d	6 d	0.4 b

^aIn each column, any two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

planting, less vulnerable at 4 weeks after transplanting, and least vulnerable at 7 weeks after transplanting. Although IR2153-26-3 was not affected by the time of exposure to high salt concentration, we do not know what the reactions of other salt-tolerant varieties would be.

The effects of high salt concentration also need to be studied on salt-tolerant rices at important reproductive stages, such as panicle initiation and flowering. If rices that are found tolerant by our greenhouse screening technique vary in their reactions to high salt levels at different stages, then varieties should be screened under the specific environments of different saline tracts in different countries.

Mass screening for salt tolerance (*Soil Chemistry*). In 1975, we screened 1,002 varieties and 490 breeding lines from 24 countries for salt tolerance on a nearly neutral saline soil in the greenhouse using the procedure described in the 1974 Annual Report. We rated them according to the Standard Evaluation System for Rice (SES). Thirty-eight rices were identified as more tolerant than the check variety Pokkali and were rated as 1. Included were eight IRRI lines,

1. Performance of IR2153-26-3, IR26, and T26 on a neutral soil subjected to four salt regimes. IRRI, 1975.

eight varieties from Indonesia, and 22 from Bangladesh. Three hundred and eight-six varieties from 19 countries and 176 IRRI lines were found to be as salt tolerant as Pokkali and were rated as 3. Although we selected the 490 IRRI breeding lines tested on the basis of characters other than salt tolerance, 38 percent were rated as 1 and 3.

Table 2. Rices identified as tolerant to salinity. International Rice Salinity Tolerance Observational Nursery (IRSTON), 1975.

Bang Pa Kong Thailand	Port Canning West Bengal, India ^a	IRRI
BG33-2	Nona sail selection	Nona Bokra
Khao tao oo	MUT 1	Urarkondam
Kha Ta Haeng	BG11-11	BG11-11
Pokkali	BG33-2	BG33-2
IR4-11	Getu	Getu
IR22	IR4-11	IR20
IR2071-88-8	IR2031-114-2	IR4-11
IR2153-26-3	IR2035-290-2	IR2070-747-4
Khao Dok Mali	Patnai 23	IR2071-88-8
Khao Pak Moh 148	Pokkali	IR2071-625-1
Khao 500 Nak	Annapurna	IR2153-26-3-5-1
Kumarangair	BG69-4	IR2153-26-3-5-4
Maled Lek Nak	DA-29	IR2153-26-3-5-5
Nona Bokra	IR30	IR2153-43-2-5-1
Niew Pu Wiang	IR1008-14-1	IR2153-43-2-5-2
SR 26 B	IR2070-747-4	IR2153-43-2-5-3
RD 4	IR2071-88-8	Kumarangair
IR2153-43-2	IR2153-26-3-5-1	Orkayama
Pennai	IR2153-26-3-5-2	Patnai 23
	IR2153-43-2-5-3	Pokkali
	IR2153-43-2-5-4	Ptb 2
	IR2153-96-1	Ptb 5
	Kumarangair	Rajasail
	Pennai	SR 26 B
	Ptb-1	
	PVR 1	
	Triveni	

^aRice is kept in nursery seedbeds for longer periods at Bang Pa Kong; some semidwarf entries were lost, and local varieties were substituted.

The rices rated from 1 to 3 were re-evaluated in the greenhouse in soil culture containing 0.5% salt. Of the 140 rices so far screened, 13 were confirmed to be highly tolerant to salinity (rated 1) and 47 were as tolerant as Pokkali (rated 3). The 13 highly tolerant rices are: IR841-36-2, IR1154-243-1, IR1529-430-3, IR1529-677-2, IR1820-210-2, IR2031-729-3, IR2055-481-2, Banih Kuning (Acc. 17229), Kuantik Putih (Acc. 18037), Kuantik Serai Rendah (Acc. 24739), Kuantik Serai (Acc. 18035), Merak (Acc. 25457), and Pulut Daeng Maradka (Acc. 24788).

Breeding and selecting for salt tolerance (*Plant Breeding and Soil Chemistry*). Within the GEU adverse soil tolerance program, major emphasis is on breeding for salt tolerance. During the 1975 dry season, 32 crosses were made from BR4-10, KR1-24, Nona Bokra, SR 26B, MI 273, Bazar, and the elite GEU breeding lines. In the wet season, the single crosses were topcrossed with the salt-tolerant breeding lines

IR2035-290-7 and IR2153-26-3. More crosses were also made using Patnai 23 and MUT 1 as sources of tolerance.

During the 1975 dry season, 1,946 F₃ lines from double crosses with Pokkali were grown in an artificially amended saline field at IRRI; 192 lines were selected. During the wet season, we grew three replications of each line and found some progenies tolerant to salinity. Figure 2 shows the distribution of salt-tolerance ratings of these lines.

International Rice Salinity Tolerance Observational Nursery (IRSTON). The first IRSTON was organized in 1975; 27 varieties and 23 IRRI breeding lines were tested at 22 locations in 12 countries (Table 2). Rices that were identified as tolerant to salinity in the greenhouse, such as IR2035-290-2 and IR2071-88-8, were also found tolerant under field screening in Thailand and West Bengal, India. Some of the lines that had high levels of tolerance to salinity under actual field conditions had not been selected under saline conditions and did not derive from special crosses involving salt-tolerant parents.

The elite breeding lines and IRRI varieties are being evaluated in salt-affected farmers' fields in the Philippines through the BPI's Farmers Evaluation of New Selections Applied Research Trial (FENSART).

TOLERANCE TO ALKALINITY

Soil Chemistry and Plant Breeding Departments

Alkalinity retards yields on several million hectares of irrigated soils in arid regions of India, Pakistan, Iran, and Egypt. Screening and breeding for alkali tolerance are given high priority.

Mass screening for alkalinity tolerance (*Soil Chemistry*). We continued to screen rices in the greenhouse and in the field for tolerance to alkalinity. In the greenhouse, 1.4% Na₂CO₃ was used to amend Maahas clay to bring the soil pH to 8.6. Rices were rated at 4 weeks after transplanting, based on the SES. Of the 1,505 rices tested, 122 were found as tolerant to alkalinity as the check variety Pokkali. Included among the tolerant rices were 11 IRRI breeding lines, 24 selections from Tamil Nadu, India, and 72 rices from Bangladesh, China, Egypt,

Indonesia, Malaysia, Pakistan, Peru, Philippines, Portugal, Sri Lanka, Thailand, and Vietnam. The number of IRRI breeding lines that were comparable to Pokkali in alkali tolerance represents 2 percent of the total number of lines tested.

Breeding and selecting for alkali tolerance (*Plant Breeding and Soil Chemistry*). During the 1975 dry season, 1,946 F₃ lines from crosses involving alkali-tolerant sources were planted in an alkali-amended field at IRRI. Pokkali was used as the tolerant check and IR2153-26-3 as the susceptible check. Due to severe alkalinity and zinc deficiency, the checks and all lines were killed within 4 weeks after transplanting. Before the plants completely died, however, we evaluated them for tolerance to alkalinity.

During the 1975 wet season, 576 F₄ lines were planted in the same alkali-amended field. Because of severe zinc deficiency, Pokkali did poorly in these tests. The 11 best lines were: IR4573-4-1, IR4573-4-3, IR4573-22-3, IR4573-29-2, IR4573-76-2, IR4595-4-1, IR4610-56-2, IR4619-48-3, IR4630-22-2, IR4763-73-1, and

IR4763-141-1. Figure 3 shows the distribution of alkali-tolerance ratings of the F₄ lines from alkali-tolerant sources.

TOLERANCE TO ZINC DEFICIENCY

Soil Chemistry and Plant Breeding Departments

After nitrogen and phosphorus deficiencies, zinc deficiency may be the most important factor limiting yields of lowland rice. Millions of hectares of low-lying land in the humid tropics, well supplied with water, may be brought into rice cultivation if improved varieties that can tolerate zinc deficiency are developed.

Mass screening for tolerance to zinc deficiency.

In concrete tanks (Soil Chemistry). During the 1975 wet season, we screened 683 rices for tolerance to zinc deficiency by growing them in a zinc-deficient soil from Guisguis, Sariaya, Quezon province, Philippines (pH 7.5; O.M. 15.3%; available Zn, 0.68 ppm), placed in a 27- × 2.5-m concrete tank. We used the line IR1514A-E666 as the tolerant check and E425 as the susceptible check. Among the 200 rices

2. Distribution of ratings of salt tolerance of breeding lines tested in a salt-amended field. 2 = slight retardation; 5 = stunted growth, no tillering; 9 = dead. IRRI, 1975 wet season.

3. Distribution of ratings of alkali tolerance of breeding lines tested in an alkali-amended field. 2 = slight retardation; 5 = stunted growth, no tillering; 9 = dead. IRRI, 1975 wet season.

found tolerant were: TKM 6, IR30, IR32, IR1529-680-3, IR1561-228-3, IR1632-93-2, IR2031-724-2, IR2070-228-2, IR2070-423-2, IR2071-176-1, IR2071-625-1, and IR2153-26-3.

In farmers' fields (Soil Chemistry and Plant Breeding). In the 1975 dry season, 1,427 rices from IRRI's Replicated Yield Trial (RYT) and Observational Yield Trial (OYT) were evaluated on a soil with an available zinc content of 0.48 ppm in a farmer's field in San Pablo, Laguna province, Philippines. We found marked differences in tolerance to zinc deficiency. Of the 209 rices that showed some tolerance, the most notable were IR2153-550-2, IR2061-181-1, and IR2061-181-8.

During the wet season, 275 rices from IRRI's Replicated Yield Trial were screened in a zinc-deficient field with available zinc content of 0.04 ppm and pH of 8.2 in Quezon province, Philippines. Symptoms of zinc deficiency were recorded at 3 weeks after transplanting. In this soil, even the tolerant check IR1514A-E666 was severely affected by zinc deficiency. Only three rices were rated as moderately tolerant: IR2061-628-1, BRJ1-13-13, and C4-63.

At the same site, we planted 175 rices from the IRRI Observational Yield Trial. Only four were scored as tolerant: IR2153-550-2, IR2061-139-3, IR2061-181-1, and IR2061-181-8. Nine lines were scored as moderately tolerant: IR2061-181-11, IR2151-529-1, IR2151-598-3, IR2681-34-5, IR2681-108-2, IR2701-89-3, IR2701-114-5, IR2701-159-6, and IR2701-261-5.

Table 3. Yields of 10 rices with and without treatment in a zinc-deficient soil. Farmer's field, Laguna province, Philippines, 1975.

Designation	Yield (t/ha)		Difference
	With ZnO	Without ZnO ^a	
E425	0.3 e	0.7 e	0.4
IR1514A-E666	3.4 bc	4.0 bc	0.6*
IR26	3.9 ab	4.4 ab	0.5*
IR28	3.0 c	2.5 d	-0.5*
IR29	3.2 c	3.6 c	0.4
IR30	4.1 a	4.6 ab	0.5*
IR2151-598-3	2.3 d	2.7 d	0.4*
IR2035-290-2	2.4 d	2.6 d	0.2
IR2071-625-1	3.4 bc	4.6 a	1.2**
IR2151-918-1	4.0 ab	4.4 ab	0.4

^aSeedlings dipped in a 2% suspension of zinc oxide.

In 1975, 1,200 breeding lines and varieties from the RYT and OYT were evaluated on a zinc-deficient soil near Butuan, Agusan del Norte province, Philippines. IR30 and IR34 were among the varieties that performed well without zinc application. Many rices were severely injured.

Yield potential on a zinc-deficient soil (Soil Chemistry). Ten rices were planted in a zinc-deficient soil (available Zn, 0.48 ppm) in a farmer's field near San Pablo, Laguna province, Philippines. Half of the 3-week-old seedlings were dipped in a 2% suspension of zinc oxide before transplanting; the others were transplanted without treatment. Plants were observed weekly and scored on a scale of 0-9.

Symptoms of zinc deficiency were observed at 2 weeks after transplanting in IR26 and IR2071-625-1 without the zinc oxide seedling dip. At 4 weeks after transplanting, zinc deficiency symptoms became severe on E425, IR26, and IR2071-625-1. Plant height and tiller number did not vary with zinc treatment. But yield differences were significant between plots of treated and untreated rice. In the plots with no zinc treatment, IR30, IR26, and IR2151-918-1 produced the highest yields, about 4.0 t/ha (Table 3). IR2071-625-1 responded best to zinc oxide treatment, yielding 1.2 t/ha more than without the treatment.

Breeding (Plant Breeding). Because IR20 and several IR1514 lines were observed to be tolerant to zinc deficiency and seemed to generate progenies that have this trait, we attempted to identify the source of tolerance in these selections. We traced the source of tolerance to TKM 6 and its parents, GEB 24 and CO 18 (fig. 4).

TOLERANCE TO PHOSPHORUS DEFICIENCY *Soil Chemistry and Plant Breeding Departments*

Mass screening technique (Soil Chemistry). To simplify and improve the greenhouse technique for screening rices for tolerance to phosphorus deficiency, we studied the following factors: level of phosphorus, method of planting, and age of seedling at transplanting. We found that a good index of a rice's tolerance to phosphorus deficiency is its performance when direct seeded

4. Ancestry of sources of tolerance to zinc deficiency. T = tolerant; MT = moderately tolerant; MS = moderately susceptible; S = susceptible. IRRI, 1975.

and grown in culture solution with 1 ppm P for 4 weeks relative to its performance when grown in culture solution with 10 ppm P.

The procedure was adapted to screen rices for phosphorus deficiency, as follows: four pregerminated seeds of each variety to be tested were arranged in a square, 7.5 cm apart, on a nylon net float placed on the surface of culture solution (Table 4) with 1 ppm P maintained at pH 4.5 and contained in a 4-liter porcelain pot. A second pot containing culture solution with 10 ppm P and maintained at pH 6.0 was planted with another set of four seeds of each variety. The pH of the culture solution was daily checked and maintained at 4.5 for treatment at 1 ppm P and at 6.0 for the 10-ppm-P treatment. The culture solution in each pot was changed weekly. Four weeks later we determined the number of plant tillers at 1 ppm P relative to the tiller number at 10 ppm P, expressed as relative tiller percent.

Twenty varieties with known response to phosphorus were tested in the greenhouse using this method. Table 5 shows the reactions of some of these varieties based on tiller number and compared with a previous field rating.

Field screening (Soil Chemistry). Thirty rices were screened for tolerance to deficiency on flooded Pangil clay with no P and with 25 kg P/ha in a farmer's field in Pangil, Laguna province, Philippines. The yields and ratings of 20 of these rices are shown in Table 6.

Table 4. Composition of culture solution used for screening rices for tolerance to phosphorus deficiency. IRRI, 1975.

Element	Concn (ppm)
N	40
K	40
Ca	40
Mg	4.0
Fe	5.0
Mn	0.5
Mo	0.05
Zn	0.01
B	0.02
Cu	0.01
P	1 or 10 ^a

^a1 ppm P was used to create severe phosphorus deficiency; 10 ppm for normal culture solution.

Table 5. Response of rice varieties to phosphorus deficiency in culture solution and in the field. IRRI, 1975.

Designation	Relative tillering (%)	Field response ^a	
		Culture solution	Field
IR4-11	81	T	T
CAS 209	63	MT	T
Doc Phung Lun AR	57	MT	T
H4	62	MT	MT
IR26	56	MT	T
M1-48	42	MS	S
Pokkali	50	MS	S
T26	40	MS	S
Nagpili	20	S	S

^aRated by percent relative tillers. 1 to 25 = S (susceptible); 26 to 50 = MS (moderately susceptible); 51 to 75 = MT (moderately tolerant); 76 to 100 = T (tolerant).

Table 6. Yield and tolerance ratings to phosphorus deficiency of 20 rices on a phosphorus-deficient soil with and without added phosphorus. Farmer's field, Laguna province, Philippines, 1975 wet season.

Designation	Yield (t/ha)		Response (%)	Rating ^a
	0 kg P/ha	25 kg P/ha		
IR1529-680-3	1.8	3.5	94	7
IR1561-228-3	1.9	2.5	32	5
IR1632-93-2	3.5	4.2	20	1
IR2031-724-2	1.5	3.0	100	7
IR2035-290-2	4.0	4.8	20	1
IR2061-213-2	4.2	5.2	24	1
IR2061-465-1	2.2	3.4	55	5
IR2061-522-6	2.2	3.2	45	5
IR2061-628-1	2.4	4.0	67	7
IR2070-414-3-9	4.1	4.6	12	1
IR2070-423-2	4.1	5.1	24	1
IR2071-105-9	4.8	5.2	8	1
IR2071-586-5	3.4	5.2	53	5
IR2071-588-5	2.9	4.3	48	5
IR2071-625-1	1.8	3.7	105	7
IR2153-26-3	3.4	4.2	24	1
IR2681-163-5	3.6	4.2	17	1
IR26	3.7	4.5	22	1
IR28	2.9	3.2	10	3
IR30	2.6	3.7	42	3

^aStandard Evaluation System for Rice: 1 = tolerant; 3 = moderately tolerant; 5 = moderately susceptible; 7 = susceptible; 9 = dead.

In the untreated plots, all varieties showed symptoms of phosphorus deficiency at 4 weeks after transplanting. The range in tiller count at maximum tillering in plots without phosphorus fertilizer was from 2 to 4, while that in plots fertilized with phosphorus was from 11 to 18.

Rices that yielded more than 3.5 t/ha without phosphate fertilizer and gave less than 25 percent increase due to added phosphate fertilizer were considered tolerant; those that yielded less than 2 t/ha and gave about 100 percent increase in yield due to added phosphate fertilizer were considered susceptible.

TOLERANCE TO IRON TOXICITY

Soil Chemistry Department

Screening for tolerance to iron toxicity. Sixty rices from IRRI's 1975 elite breeding lines and from the Philippine government's FENSART trials were tested for tolerance to iron toxicity, along with a tolerant check, Dewareddi, and a susceptible check, Peta. The soil used was a lateritic clay from Taiwan, which releases more than 400 ppm water-soluble iron during the greater part of the growing season. Using plant symptoms as the main criterion, the following were found tolerant: IR30, IR34, IR2151-598-3, IR2681-163-5, IR1529-680-3, IR2031-724-2, IR2035-290-2, IR2070-320-6, IR2071-137-5, IR2071-588-5, C131-129, C4-67-2, IR2070-414-3, and IR2070-464-1. IRRI varieties IR28 and IR32 were moderately tolerant. IR2061-427-1, IR2061-464-2, IR2061-522-6, IR2061-628-1, IR2071-588-5, IR2070-820-2, and MRC 8 were found susceptible.

Genetic evaluation and utilization (GEU) program

Deep water and flood tolerance

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SUMMARY

A cooperative research and training agreement concentrating on the culture of deep-water rice was signed by the Government of Thailand and IRRI in late 1974.

We continued to study at Los Baños and in Thailand the factors that limit yields of deep-water rice. We developed methods to screen germ plasm for plant characters needed in floating rice culture and in flood tolerance, such as the abilities to elongate to avoid submergence; to survive when submerged; and to produce adventitious roots at the upper nodes.

We continued to cross elongating and flood-tolerant varieties with improved semidwarfs.

Breeding lines of varying heights with and without sensitivity to photoperiod have advanced to the point where international testing can begin in 1976. These lines have elongation ability, good seedling vigor, and bacterial blight resistance.

International cooperation among the countries where deep-water rice is grown was initiated primarily through collaborative experiments and the exchange of breeding materials.

NEW PROGRAM IN THAILAND

Thai-IRRI Cooperative Deep Water Rice Research Project

The Government of Thailand and IRRI have informally collaborated in rice research for years. In late 1974, a joint memorandum of understanding was signed for a research and training program concentrating on the culture of deep-water rice. The Rockefeller Foundation is providing a plant breeder as team leader and IRRI has stationed a core staff member in Thailand to assist with field testing.

In Thailand, the collaborative work is conducted on 6 ha of naturally flooded land and in 11 ponds where water depth can be controlled at the Huntra Deep Water Rice Research Station. Other stations are used for ordinary lowland planting of deep-water rice. A deep pond at the Klong Luang station is used to test for submergence tolerance. The Thai Rice Division recently provided 60 ha of land for research in water depths of more than 2 m.

SCREENING FOR ELONGATION ABILITY

Thai-IRRI Cooperative Deep Water Rice Research Project

More than 500 varieties from the IRRI germ plasm collection were screened for their ability to elongate when subjected to rising water. The 35 varieties with the best elongation ability all came from Bangladesh (Table 1). Varieties tested from Thailand, India, Cambodia, and Vietnam elongated rather poorly compared with the Bangladesh varieties.

Floating varieties generally have low tillering capacity and spreading tillers, which are partly responsible for the low panicle number per unit area at harvest. Therefore, we measured the

Table 1. The tiller angles, plant heights, and tiller numbers of 35 rice varieties from Bangladesh that were found to have rapid rates of internode elongation (measurements taken before the water level was increased in deep-water screening pit). Screened from 573 varieties. IRRI, 1975.

Variety	Tiller angle ^a (°)	Plant ht (cm)	Tillers (no.)
Aswina	20	111	7
Badal 106	23	107	3
Badal 672/2	28	99	4
Bawoi Jhak	24	110	7
Bhoro Diga	24	92	3
Dholamon 39/3	19	82	5
Dholamon 51/1	22	80	5
Dholamon 64/3	19	81	5
Fulkari 368	30	86	4
Fulkari 715	30	97	4
Gowai 38/13	20	85	5
Gowai 50/9	24	79	5
Gowai 84	20	79	6
Gowai 476	21	77	6
Habiganj Deep Water 1	23	109	6
Hybrid 10/1	20	89	4
Kalamon 21/7	21	76	4
Kalamon 113	18	75	4
Kalamon 243	15	75	4
Kalimekri 77/5 (6527)	20	103	3
Kalimekri 391	19	90	4
Karkati 87	14	108	3
Khama 49/2	20	92	4
Khama 49/8	18	92	4
Khama 55/22	16	78	6
Khama 380	20	84	8
Laki 192	27	137	6
Laki 491	31	118	6
Laki 544	23	120	5
Lal Amon	18	128	6
Matia Amon	17	95	—
Matiamon 73/23	19	122	7
Rayada R16-10	31	90	—
Shuli (26527)	26	103	—
Sungwala	24	108	—

^aSmaller angles mean that tillers are more erect.

number of tillers and the degree of erectness in the varieties that were screened.

Several of the varieties with good elongation ability had erect tillers but few had high tiller number (Table 1). Matiamon 73/23 had good elongation ability, erect tillers, and medium tillering ability.

Two hundred and thirty-one lines from four crosses were also screened for elongation ability and pest resistance in Thailand.

We screened for elongation ability 35 F_2 and F_3 bulk progenies of Thai origin under naturally flooded conditions in Thailand. The water reached a depth of 170 cm, providing adequate selection pressure.

Two thousand F_3 and F_4 lines from 37 crosses were tested for elongation ability at 4 weeks after sowing in deep ponds where the water was increased 10 cm every 2 days to a maximum depth of 150 cm. Interspersed in the selection materials were check rows of Pin Gaew 56, a floating variety; T442-57, a semidwarf with intermediate floating ability; and RD1, a semidwarf that tolerates no more than 50 cm of water.

One thousand plants from the IRRI deep-water composite (a bulk of crosses made at IRRI) were mass screened, using the same water regime described above. The surviving plants

were transplanted in bulk through stem cuttings for further selection.

In a study of the elongation ability of traditional tall and floating varieties that are indigenous to Thailand, scientists found that floating varieties could much better cope with rising water. The 23-day-old plants were grown in pits where the water level was continuously increased to a maximum depth of 1 m. Figure 1 shows that all of the traditional tall varieties had low rates of survival, from 0 to 40 percent, while survival rates of most floating rices ranged from 45 to 75 percent. No traditional tall type in our sample had strong ability to elongate.

An elongation test involving floating varieties introduced from India, Bangladesh, and other countries was badly damaged by premature floods at the Huntra station but it will be repeated in 1976.

SCREENING FOR SUBMERGENCE TOLERANCE

Plant Physiology Department

We screened 1,446 varieties at IRRI for tolerance to submergence; the best 22 are shown in Table 2. Most of the tolerant varieties are from Sri Lanka, but SML Temerin from Surinam has consistently performed well. New crosses have been made with SML Temerin as a parent.

Crosses have been made using as a parent Nam Sagui 19 (the most tolerant variety identified at the time). Of the 328 progenies screened, only 14 were found to have both high tolerance to submergence and reasonable pest resistance.

We twice subjected 39 lines from Thailand to the submergence test. We selected six lines with high degrees of survival and that yielded well without lodging (Table 3). Only BKN 6986-105-P and BKN 6986-160-P, however, had field resistance to tungro. These two lines, like IR442 and T442, have the ability to elongate in deep water.

In Thailand, the submergence tolerance was compared for 61 semidwarf, tall, and floating rice varieties. Survival was measured by the percentage of plants that were able to elongate through 45 cm of water when covered at 7 days of age. We found that few of the semidwarfs were capable of growing through water.

1. Survival of 72 lowland and 32 indigenous tall and floating varieties screened at 100-cm water depth. Co-operative Thailand-IRRI Rice Research Project, Huntra Deep Water Rice Research Station, Thailand, 1975.

Table 2. Varieties found tolerant to 8 days of submergence screened^a from 1,446 varieties. IRRI, 1975.

Variety	Origin	Survival (%)	Bacterial blight ^b	Blast ^b
Kurkaruppan	Sri Lanka	78	S	S
Kaharamana	Sri Lanka	73	S	M
Kalu Gires	Sri Lanka	73	S	M
SML Temerin	Surinam	73	S	—
Weli Handiran	Sri Lanka	70	S	M
Goda Heenati	Sri Lanka	65	S	M
Sudu Gires	Sri Lanka	65	S	S
Thavalu (15314)	Sri Lanka	65	S	M/S
ARC 10288	India	63	S	—
FR 13A	India	63	MR	S
Pokuru Samba (15337)	Sri Lanka	63	S	S
Ratawee	Sri Lanka	63	—	S
Thavalu (15325)	Sri Lanka	63	R/S	M
ARC 5938	India	60	M	—
ARC 10661	India	60	S	—
Naalumoli Karuppan	Sri Lanka	60	S	M
Anlong Phnom	Cambodia	58	S	—
Kottamalli	Sri Lanka	58	S	S
Venam Vellai	Sri Lanka	58	S	S
Kalukanda	Sri Lanka	55	S	M
Madebaru	Sri Lanka	53	S	S
Periya Karuppan	Sri Lanka	53	S	S
T442-57 (ck)	Thailand	48	—	M
Leb Mue Nahng 111 (ck)	Thailand	27	MR	M/S
Nam Sagui 19 (ck)	Thailand	25	R/S	M/S

^aRetested from varieties previously screened at 7 days of submergence. Only those equal to or better than Nam Sagui 19 were included in this test. ^bR = resistant; MR = moderately resistant; M = intermediate; MS = moderately susceptible; S = susceptible. (ck) = check

Figure 2 shows that although some floating varieties survived no better than did the semi-dwarfs (0–5%), from 40 to 50 percent of a few traditional tall and floating types survived. The check variety Nam Sagui 19 performed poorly; only 32 percent of its plants were above the water at 7 days after submergence (in other submergence tests, however, Nam Sagui 19 performed as well as the best hybrids).

2. Percent emergence and survival of rices when submerged in 45 cm of water at 7 days of age. Cooperative Thailand-IRRI Rice Research Project, Huntra Deep Water Rice Research Station, Thailand, 1975.

NODAL ROOTING ABILITY

Thai-IRRI Cooperative Deep Water Rice Research Project

We have little data on the importance of the adventitious roots at the upper nodes of floating rices in absorbing nutrients from flood waters, but more extensive development of such roots before flowering would probably favor plant growth.

Preliminary tests are conducted in Thailand to determine if floating varieties differ in nodal rooting ability and if increased rooting capacity can be incorporated into improved varieties for areas of deep water. A screening procedure was

Table 3. Outstanding lines from Thailand with good submergence tolerance both in Thailand and at IRRI. IRRI, 1975 wet season.

Line ^a	Plant ht (cm)	Growth duration (days)	Yield (t/ha)	Performance			Submergence survival (%)
				Lodging ^b	Panicles (no./hill)	Panicle wt (g)	
BKN 6986-105-P	122	110	4.5	3	9	2.5	87
-160-P	121	110	5.0	1	9	2.5	98
-133-4-P	115	113	4.4	1	10	2.2	93
BKN 6987-118-3-P	122	110	5.2	1	11	2.8	75
-133-2-P	110	105	5.5	1	9	2.8	80
-223-2-P	114	105	5.4	1	9	2.5	62

^aBKN 6986 = IR262/Pin Gaew 56; BKN 6987 = IR262/Khao Nahng Nuey 11. ^bRated according to the Standard Evaluation System for Rice (IRRI): Scale 1 = no lodging; 9 = completely lodged.

Table 4. Ability of deep-water rice varieties to produce adventitious roots at nodes. Thai-IRRI Cooperative Deep Water Rice Research Project, Thailand, 1975.

Variety	Reaction ^a in	
	1974	1975
Kalar Harsall	1.0	1.0
Puang Tawng	1.4	2.0
Po Ngern	1.8	3.6
Khao Med Lek (Acc. 24226)	2.6	1.8
Leb Mue Nahng 111	3.0	2.4
Pin Gaew 56	3.0	1.4
Sran Kraham (Acc. 16959)	3.2	3.8
Khao Hawm (Acc. 17112)	3.8	1.6
Gawd Pawm	4.2	4.2
Mali Thong (Acc. 5820)	4.2	3.6
Anlong Phuom No. 4	4.6	2.6
Khao Nahng Nuey 11	4.6	2.0
Mohos Soth	4.6	5.2
Sai Bur	4.6	4.4
Suon Lory (Acc. 16960)	4.6	2.8
Jampah Nak	5.0	4.6
Khao Puang 32	5.8	3.8
Ng Khien	5.8	4.2
Vear Sar (Acc. 16962)	6.0	5.4
Mali Awng 55-202-1	6.2	3.4
Vear Krachak	6.2	3.6
Saleth Guon Vear 5	6.4	5.4
Ng Lay	6.6	5.0

^aRooting ability scores: 1 = many roots more than 10 mm in length; 3 = many roots but most are less than 10 mm in length; 5 = few roots but most are less than 2 mm; 7 = no roots.

developed to determine the ability to produce adventitious roots.

At 110 days after transplanting, tillers were sampled from plants growing in a pond of water 200 cm in depth. Five tillers per replicate were cut just below the node at the point of attachment of the second matured leaf, placed in water for 65 hours, and scored for rooting ability.

The ability to produce adventitious roots differed greatly; that of Kalar Harsall and Puang Tawng was consistently high (Table 4). Although Kalar Harsall has the best rooting ability of any variety tested, it also has the thinnest stem. We found a high correlation ($r = 0.68^{**}$) between our 1974 and 1975 tests, using the same varieties. The coefficient of variability of this test was 33.7. Sampling variance was low for some varieties.

We conducted another test with the same set of varieties to determine the effect of removing the blades, because leaf removal would facilitate handling and might reduce sampling variance. The differences were not significant between sampling variance of rices with and without leaves. Other factors that affect the rooting

ability of varieties should be tested to determine limitations of this screening method.

BREEDING PROGRAM AT THAILAND AND IRRI

Thai-IRRI Cooperative Deep Water Rice Research Project and IRRI Plant Breeding Department

In Thailand, we are using two hybrid populations to study the heritability of the ability to elongate and to produce nodal roots, and to study the association of height and other characters with elongation.

In 1975, we made numerous crosses in Thailand and at IRRI of promising lines and deep-water varieties to incorporate elongation ability and submergence tolerance into semi-dwarf and intermediate-statured rices with disease and insect resistance.

To select for the semidwarf plant type, we planted under ordinary lowland conditions 90 F_2 selections from IRRI whose ancestry includes at least one deep-water or submergence-tolerant variety.

Table 5. List of promising lines that are nonsensitive to photoperiod and that have elongation ability. Thai-IRRI Cooperative Deep Water Rice Research Project, Thailand 1975.

Designation ^a	Seedling ht ^b at 30 days	Elongation ability compared with T442-57	Bacterial blight rating ^c
<i>Semidwarf ht (approx. 120 cm)^d</i>			
BKN 6987-52-1	medium	similar	R
BKN 6987-66	medium	similar	MR
BKN 6987-136	tall	similar	MR
BKN 6987-128-2	tall	similar	MR
BKN 6987-155-4	short	greater	S
BKN 6987-161-4	medium	similar	S
BKN 6987-225	tall	greater	S
<i>Tall ht (approx. 150 cm)^d</i>			
BKN 6986-3	tall	less	R
BKN 6986-42	short	similar	S
BKN 6986-59	tall	similar	MR
BKN 6986-70	tall	similar	MR
BKN 6986-108	medium	greater	MR
BKN 6987-50-4	tall	greater	MR
BKN 6987-68	tall	similar	MR
BKN 6987-120	tall	greater	R
BKN 6987-160-1	tall	greater	R
BKN 6987-171-3	tall	greater	MR

^aBKN 6986 = IR262/Pin Gaew 56; BKN 6987 = IR262/Khao Nahng Nuey 11. ^bShort = similar to that of RD1; medium = similar to T442-57; tall = similar to Pin Gaew 56. ^cR = resistant; MR = moderately resistant; S = susceptible. ^dWhen grown under shallow water conditions.

Table 6. List of promising lines that are sensitive to photoperiod and that have elongation ability. Thai-IRRI Cooperative Deep Water Rice Research Project, Thailand, 1975.

Designation ^a	Seedling ht ^b at 30 days	Elongation ability		Bacterial blight rating ^c	Flowering date ^d
		compared with T442-57			
<i>Semidwarf ht (approx. 120 cm)</i>					
BKN 6986-38-1	short	less		MR	Nov. 4
BKN 6986-71	medium	similar		S	Oct. 10
BKN 6986-119-12	short	less		S	Oct. 15
BKN 6986-147-2	short	similar		MR	Nov. 8
BKN 6987-37-3	short	greater		S	Oct. 15
BKN 6987-92-2	medium	greater		S	Nov. 4
BKN 6987-161-3	short	similar		S	Oct. 9
<i>Tall ht (approx. 150 cm)</i>					
BKN 6986-81-5	tall	greater		MR	Nov. 4
BKN 6986-173-5	tall	less		MR	Nov. 20
BKN 6986-167	tall	greater		S	Nov. 8
BKN 6987-108	tall	similar		R	Nov. 8
BKN 6987-191	tall	greater		MR	Nov. 6

^aBKN 6986: IR262/Pin Gaew 56; BKN 6987: IR262/Khao Nahng Nuey 11. ^bShort = similar to that of RD1; medium = similar to T442-57; tall = similar to Pin Gaew 56. ^cS = susceptible; MR = moderately resistant; R = resistant. ^dSeeded in March.

We continued to select and to test advanced lines from two crosses made in 1969, IR262/Pin Gaew 56 (BKN 6986) and IR262/Khao Nahng Nuey 11 (BKN 6987). These lines, now in the F₇ generation, include both photoperiod-

sensitive and nonsensitive lines of semidwarf and intermediate height. The lines have been tested for elongation in deep water for 3 years; in 1975 we entered them in preliminary yield trials and reselected for uniformity of height and maturity (Tables 5 and 6). We plan to enter some in international deep-water observational nurseries in 1976. The seedling growth of some semidwarf lines for the first 30 days was as rapid as that of floating rices. This may be of particular interest since farmers often complain that seedlings of most semidwarf varieties are too short.

Table 7 lists floating and tall rices that are sensitive to photoperiod and that have been found to have good yielding ability in 13 tests.

INTERNATIONAL COOPERATION

Thai-IRRI Cooperative Deep Water Rice Research Project

At the 1975 International Rice Research Conference at IRRI, deep-water rice scientists held a special meeting to plan strategies for increased cooperation. To formalize and facilitate seed exchange, seeds for a collaborative experiment on the flowering date of deep-water rice were distributed to seven countries. Scientists can use

Table 7. Floating rice varieties and tall hybrid lines with photoperiod sensitivity and elongation ability. Thirteen experiments, Thai-IRRI Cooperative Deep Water Rice Research Project, Thailand, 1975.

Designation	Origin or cross	Flowering period	Survival depth ^a (cm)
Nahng Chalawng	Thailand	late Oct.	150 ^b
BKN 6988-21	IR262/LMN 111	late Oct.	210
BKN 6988-21-50	IR262/LMN 111	early Nov.	150 ^b
BKN 6988-21-4	IR262/LMN 111	early Nov.	150 ^b
Mali Awng	Thailand	mid Nov.	190
Leb Mue Nahng 111	Thailand	mid Nov.	270
Khao Med Lek	Thailand	mid Nov.	270
Anlong Phuom	Cambodia	mid Nov.	270
Soun Lory	Cambodia	mid Nov.	210
SPT 6738-25	TPG161/Sigadis	mid Nov.	210
BKN 6004-295	KTH17/LMN 111	mid Nov.	150 ^b
SPT 6849-14	PG56/Sigadis	mid Nov.	150 ^b
Khao Tah Prae	Thailand	late Nov.	270
SPT 6849-61	PG56/Sigadis	late Nov.	150 ^b
SPT 6849-63	PG56/Sigadis	late Nov.	150 ^b
SPT 6848-40	KP32/Sigadis	late Nov.	150 ^b
SPT 6849-47	PG56/Sigadis	late Nov.	150 ^b
Mali Sawn	Thailand	late Nov.	150
Pin Gaew 56	Thailand	late Nov.	270
Puang Mah Lai	Thailand	late Nov.	150 ^b
Puang Ngern	Thailand	late Nov.	150
Hing Hoy	Cambodia	late Nov.	190

^aNumbers in this column reflect the maximum depth of water attained in experiments. ^bThe height of the water table was close to the maximum potential height of the rice being tested.

Table 8. Flowering dates of entries in the deep-water rice flowering date experiment, planted at Bangkhen, Thailand, on May 19, 1975. Thai-IRRI Cooperative Deep-Water Rice Research Project, Thailand, 1975.

Variety	Origin	Flowering date
DM 53	Bangladesh	July 5
ARC 5955	India	July 30
Habiganj A 1	Bangladesh	Sept. 25
Laki 192	India	Sept. 26
Kekowa Bao	India	Oct. 3
Habiganj A 2	Bangladesh	Oct. 4
Baisbish	Bangladesh	Oct. 6
Gowai 84	Bangladesh	Oct. 12
Habiganj A 8	Bangladesh	Oct. 13
Tau Binh C	Vietnam	Oct. 19
Kalar Harsall	India	Nov. 2
Sran Kraham (Acc. 16959)	Cambodia	Nov. 6
Sai Bur	Thailand	Nov. 12
Leb Mue Nahng 111	Thailand	Nov. 13
Nang Tay C	Vietnam	Nov. 13
Khao Med Lek	Thailand	Nov. 15
Po Ngern	Thailand	Dec. 3

comparisons as a basis for requesting seeds of new lines from other deep-water research stations.

The results from Thailand may serve as a reference for predicting flowering dates at other locations (Table 8).

Genetic evaluation and utilization (GEU) program

Temperature tolerance

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SUMMARY

In the cold tolerance project, we have emphasized the screening of IRRI germ plasm at different growth stages, making new crosses, and evaluating progeny lines. Several selections from Kn 361 and IR3941 performed well in the International Rice Cold Tolerance Nursery. A cold-tolerant selection of Kn 361 was multiplied for distribution in high-elevation areas of the Philippines. It matures early, so farmers can grow two crops in areas where they have traditionally grown only one.

Sterility induced by high temperature was found to be most serious when the heat occurred at heading. Such problems are likely in areas where daily maximum temperature is 40°C or higher at flowering. Large varietal differences were noted in tolerance to heat-induced sterility.

LOW TEMPERATURE

Plant Physiology and Plant Breeding Departments

To increase the yield potential of varieties for areas of low temperature, cold tolerance must be combined with traits of modern rice varieties. Screening techniques must be developed for each growth stage, since low temperature often affects the rice plant differently at different stages of maturity, and tolerance at one stage does not necessarily mean tolerance at others.

In 1975 we emphasized using new techniques to screen the IRRI germ plasm, making new crosses with the best material, and evaluating progeny lines. Cooperative country trials have been started in more than 15 countries.

Germ plasm evaluation (*Plant Physiology*). Our previous studies showed that plant height and growth duration can be used to select varieties or lines that are resistant to low temperature. The plants that mature in more than 110 days at Los Baños will be very late when grown in cold areas. Similarly, plants that have culm length of less than 120 cm at Los Baños will be very short in cold areas. Therefore, we used as selection criteria growth duration of less than 110 days and culm length of more than 120 cm to screen the germ plasm collection (fig. 1).

1. Stages in the screening of the IRRI germ plasm collection for cold tolerance.

Only 147 out of 8,628 entries were selected, of which only 109 were indica types. After these varieties were screened for cold tolerance at the seedling stage, only 16 remained.

We tested the 16 varieties for cold tolerance at the critical and susceptible spikelet differentiation stage in the controlled glasshouses of the IRRI phytotron.

The varieties were grown at 20/20°C day/night temperatures until the collars appeared on the flag leaves. Afterwards, the plants were grown for 5 consecutive days at 20/15°C day/night

Table 1. Six indica varieties found tolerant of low temperature in a screening of 8,628 varieties.^a IRRI, 1975.

Cultivar	Source	Spikelet sterility (%)
Pratao	Brazil	8
HR 33	India	14
C 21	Philippines	25
Leng Kwang	China	27
Azucena	Philippines	30
Do Do	Korea	31

^aTolerance based on leaf color at seedling stage, and growth duration, plant height, and spikelet sterility at harvest. Sterility determined after screening at low temperature regimes in the IRRI phytotron.

temperatures. After treatment, the plants were grown at 29/21°C day/night temperatures until harvest. We found these temperature regimes effective.

From 16 varieties, only six were less than 35 percent sterile (Table 1). Pratao from Brazil and HR 33 from India had the lowest percentages of sterility. However, the grains of HR 33 shatter, or shed, easily. The six varieties are tolerant of low temperature based on growth duration, plant height, spikelet sterility at harvest, and leaf color at seedling stage. They are now being further evaluated in the observational nursery and may be crossed with improved materials.

Breeding work (Plant Breeding). During the 1975 dry season, we grew a pedigree nursery of approximately 1,000 lines as well as 12 F₂ populations at Tublay, Benguet Province, Philippines (elevation 1,070 m). During the 1975 wet season, we shifted our nurseries to Banaue, Ifugao province, where we work in collaboration with scientists from the Philippine Bureau of Plant Industry (BPI). The elevation is 1,200 m.

At Banaue, we evaluated the first International Rice Cold Tolerance Nursery (IRCTN) (448 entries) plus about 150 varieties and lines submitted to us by cooperators from other countries. We also evaluated and selected from a pedigree nursery of some 1,300 rows, and from 11 F₂ populations of crosses between outstanding cold-tolerant parents and elite GEU lines. Field ratings and selections emphasized early maturity, disease and insect resistance, fertility, intermediate plant height, good panicle exertion, and other desirable agronomic char-

acteristics. The most promising varieties and lines were included in the second IRCTN, which will be distributed early in 1976.

The most outstanding selections were from the cross IR3941 (CR126-42-5/IR2061-213) and from the Indonesian cross Kn 361 (IR8/Jerak). Preliminary IRCTN results from cooperators also indicated that the performance of these lines was outstanding at other locations (results of the first IRCTN are available from the International Rice Testing Program, IRRI).

Because of its early maturity and cold tolerance, Kn 361-1-8 was identified by BPI as the most promising selection for high-elevation areas of the Philippines. It was extensively tested in replicated trials throughout the high areas and was multiplied on a large hectareage for distribution during 1975. This line should permit farmers to grow two crops in many high-elevation areas such as Banaue, where they have traditionally grown only one crop because the only available varieties matured late and were not tolerant of cold.

HIGH TEMPERATURE

Plant Physiology Department

In 1974 we found that sterility is the most dramatic plant response to high temperature within a day temperature range of 26–35°C (1974 Annual Report). Consequently, we concentrated on sterility induced by high temperature in 1975.

Critical stage for sterility. To identify the critical stage for heat-induced sterility, plants were subjected to temperatures of 35°C for 5 days (8 h/day) at different stages of growth.

Figure 2 shows that high temperature affects to different degrees the percentage of spikelet fertility during panicle development. The plants are most susceptible to high temperature at heading time. In cold-induced sterility, on the other hand, the critical stage is about 11 days before heading, at the meiotic stage. Thus, heat-induced sterility probably differs in mechanism from cold-induced sterility.

Duration of high temperature to induce sterility. In natural environments, the daily duration of high temperature varies with location; in our phytotron studies, however, the high tempera-

2. Percentage of spikelet fertility when rice plants are subjected to high temperature at different stages of panicle growth. IRRI phytotron, 1975.

ture is maintained for 8 hours daily. Thus, if phytotron information is to be useful for field problems, we must examine the effect of temperature not only in terms of magnitude but also in terms of duration.

In natural environments, diurnal changes in air temperature approximately follow a sine curve with maximum temperature at around 1200 hours (noon).

Table 2 shows how the duration of high-temperature hours affects the percent fertility of two rices. In the susceptible variety, C4-63G, more than 4 h/day of high temperature induces a high percentage of sterility. But in the relatively tolerant selection, IR747B2-6, high temperature of less than 8 hours duration was not seriously detrimental. This explains why C4-63G suffers

Table 2. Effects on sterility of duration of high temperature stress at the flowering stage of two rices. IRRI phytotron, 1975.

Duration (h) of high temperature ^a	Sterility (%)	
	C4-63G	IR747B2-6
8 (0900-1700)	69	20
6 (1000-1600)	55	11
4 (1100-1500)	38	10
2 (1200-1400)	13	8
0	10	8

^a35°C for 5 days (normal growing temperature 29/21°C day/night).

Table 3. List of varieties found to be tolerant of and susceptible to high temperature. IRRI phytotron, 1975.

Designation	Fertility (%) at high temperature
<i>Tolerant</i>	
Agbede	88
Carreon	90
Dular	86
N22	92
OS4	86
PI 215936	88
Sintiane Diofor	86
<i>Susceptible</i>	
Basmati-370	4
BKN 6624-46-2	3
C4-63G	8
H4	2
Pelita 1/1	7

from heat-induced sterility in Thailand but not in the Philippines: in certain areas of Thailand, air temperature of above 35°C may last for 4 hours or longer during the hottest months, while at Los Baños, air temperature goes as high as 35°C in April and May, but only for 1 or 2 hours.

The duration of high-temperature hours can be estimated by using daily maximum temperature from a meteorological handbook and a sine curve. The simulation of high-temperature hours for different daily maximum temperatures suggests that sterility induced by high temperature is likely to be a serious problem in areas where the daily maximum temperature is about 40°C or higher at flowering.

Varietal differences. Sixty-eight varieties and selections were tested in the IRRI phytotron for tolerance to sterility induced by high temperature. Table 3 shows that large differences exist in percent fertility between tolerant and susceptible varieties. Interestingly, all of the tolerant varieties are upland rices, and six of the seven have been rated as resistant or moderately resistant to drought under field conditions. This suggests that a common mechanism may in part control tolerance to both high temperature and desiccation. Preliminary observations indicate that high temperature disturbs the opening of the anthers.

Genetic evaluation and utilization (GEU) program

International rice testing program

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SUMMARY

The International Rice Testing Program (IRTP) was initiated early in 1975 to develop and formalize a network of scientists working with diverse germ plasm under a wide range of agroclimatic and cultural conditions. The United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) made funds available to help initiate and coordinate the program.

The IRTP was developed as an integral evaluation component of each nation's rice improvement program and of IRRI's Genetic Evaluation and Utilization (GEU) program. Leading local scientists coordinate the nurseries within each country. IRRI's GEU scientists also help develop the nurseries and provide overall coordination. The testing and utilization of breeding materials and varieties from the IRRI germ plasm bank and from national programs are integrated into local GEU-type programs.

During the first year of the IRTP, 12 types of nursery sets were prepared and distributed across the world, five regional monitoring programs were conducted, and a GEU training program was initiated which was attended by 16 trainees from six countries. Communication links were established with country coordi-

nators, contact scientists, and cooperators in Asia, Africa, and Latin America.

The joint coordinators—a plant pathologist headquartered in the Philippines and an IRRI plant breeder stationed in Indonesia with the Central Research Institute for Agriculture at Bogor—were assisted by 58 national coordinators and contact scientists in 46 countries.

IRRI coordinates the IRTP; the policies and programs of action are developed cooperatively with rice scientists from various countries.

INTERNATIONAL NURSERIES

The program and the distribution of nurseries are both regionally and nationally oriented. The heaviest concentration of nurseries is in Asia, where most of the world's rice is grown. High priority is placed on areas where existing semidwarf rices are not well suited to local growing conditions.

In 1975, 12 types of international nursery sets were prepared and disseminated: yield, 3; observational, 2; diseases, 3; insects, 2; and adverse soils and environmental stresses, 2.

Breeding material generated both by national programs and by IRRI were distributed through the testing network. Thirty-five percent of the

Table 1. Numbers and sources of almost 82,000 seed packets of varieties and lines distributed through the International Rice Testing Program nurseries in 1975.

Nursery ^a	Sets (no.)		Entries (no./nursery)	Entries (no.) from			Packets (no.) from		
	Prepared	Dispatched		National programs ^b	IRRI		National programs	IRRI	
					Improved lines/varieties	Germ plasm bank		Improved lines/varieties	Germ plasm bank
IRYN-E	75	55	16	7	9	—	385	495	—
IRYN-M	60	41	32	21	11	—	861	451	—
IURYN	37	37	25	5	20	—	185	740	—
IRON	200	93	336	120	200	5	11,160	18,600	465
IURON	49	49	146	34	91	20	1,666	4,459	980
IRBN	50	48	463	129	129	105	6,192	6,192	5,040
IRSHBN	20	16	124	21	58	43	336	928	688
IRTN	20	18	166	62	62	45	1,116	1,116	810
IRBPHN	30	21	41	8	9	24	168	189	504
IRGMN	30	20	70	37	31	2	740	540	40
IRSTON	22	22	50	22	23	3	484	506	66
IRCTN	50	37	448	156	230	39	5,772	8,510	1,443
Total				622 (35%)	873 (49%)	286 (16%)	29,065	42,726	10,036

^aIRYN-E = International Rice Yield Nursery — Early; IRYN-M = International Rice Yield Nursery — Medium; IURYN = International Upland Rice Yield Nursery; IRON = International Rice Observational Nursery; IURON = International Upland Rice Observational Nursery; IRBN = International Rice Blast Nursery; IRSHBN = International Rice Sheath Blight Nursery; IRTN = International Rice Tungro Nursery; IRBPHN = International Rice Brown Planthopper Nursery; IRGMN = International Rice Gall Midge Nursery; IRSTON = International Rice Salinity Tolerance Observational Nursery; IRCTN = International Rice Cold Tolerance Nursery. ^bEntries were mostly improved lines.

Table 2. Regional distribution of nurseries through the International Rice Testing Program, 1975.

Region	IRTP nurseries ^a (no.)												Total	No. (%)
	Yield		Observational		Diseases			Insects		Env. stress				
	IRYN-E	IRYN-M	IURYN	IRON	IURON	IRBN	IRSHBN	IRTN	IRBPHN	IRGMN	IRSTON	IRCTN		
East Asia	2	—	—	2	—	3	3	2	3	—	1	4	20 (4)	
Southeast Asia	14	10	13	21	16	8	7	6	6	5	7	12	125 (27)	
South Asia	23	20	12	37	12	15	5	8	8	12	10	14	176 (39)	
W. Asia & N. Africa	4	—	1	9	1	3	—	—	—	—	1	1	20 (4)	
Sub-Sahara Africa	4	4	7	14	16	8	1	2	3	3	3	3	68 (15)	
Latin America	8	7	4	8	4	10	—	—	—	—	—	1	42 (9)	
North America	—	—	—	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	1	2 (1)	
Europe	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	1	1 (—)	
Oceania	—	—	—	1	—	1	—	—	1	—	—	—	3 (1)	
Total	55	41	37	93	49	48	16	18	21	20	22	39	457 100	

^aIRYN-E = International Rice Yield Nursery — Early; IRYN-M = International Rice Yield Nursery — Medium; IURYN = International Upland Rice Yield Nursery; IRON = International Rice Observational Nursery; IURON = International Upland Rice Observational Nursery; IRBN = International Rice Blast Nursery; IRSHBN = International Rice Sheath Blight Nursery; IRTN = International Rice Tungro Nursery; IRBPHN = International Rice Brown Planthopper Nursery; IRGMN = International Rice Gall Midge Nursery; IRSTON = International Rice Salinity Tolerance Observational Nursery; IRCTN = International Rice Cold Tolerance Nursery.

entries originated from the national programs, 49 percent from IRRI's breeding program, and 16 percent from the germ plasm bank (Table 1).

Most nurseries were sent to Asia, but many went to Africa and Latin America, and a few to Oceania, North America, and Europe (Table 2). Efforts were made to widely disperse the yield and observational nurseries so that they would be tested in many diverse agroclimatic regions. The problem-area nurseries, such as the International Rice Gall Midge Nursery and the International Rice Tungro Nursery, were particularly concentrated in "hot spots" or areas where particular stress problems are prevalent and where scientists in local breeding programs hope to develop resistant varieties.

Most nurseries were put together, distributed, and received by participating programs in time for the monsoon planting. But a few, particularly the International Rice Observational Nursery (IRON), were received late in some countries. In some nations, entries must be grown in quarantine before they can be disseminated in trials, which delayed by one season their use by cooperators.

REGIONAL MONITORING PROGRAM

Through the regional monitoring program, teams of scientists from national programs and from IRRI jointly visited nurseries within a region and observed firsthand how varieties and

lines from their national programs perform under different stresses and climatic conditions.

Scientists who joined these tours recommended improved screening methodologies and discussed future collaborative research. Both the participants and the hosts became more aware of how, through international cooperation and genetic utilization, yield constraints in rice production can be overcome. Table 3 presents significant results of the 1975 monitoring tours.

TRAINING PROGRAM

The GEU Training Program was initiated in 1975 to train enthusiastic, dedicated scientists who will work at the national and provincial levels to utilize the improved germ plasm and modify it as needed for farmers' use.

Sixteen trainees from six countries attended the first GEU Training Course at IRRI, March 1-June 30, 1975. The course provided them with instruction and experience in the basic skills essential to the operation of rice improvement programs and emphasized the importance of interdisciplinary cooperation.

COMMUNICATION AND DATA MANAGEMENT

The IRTP endeavored to develop an effective communication system to monitor the needs

Table 3. The IRTP monitoring tours and their accomplishments. International Rice Testing Program, 1975.

Focus of tour	Parti- cipants (no.)	Coun- tries repre- sented (no.)	Coun- tries visited (no.)	Research insti- tutes and stations visited (no.)	Nur- series ob- served (no.)	Significant accomplishments
Cold tolerance and hill rice	12	4	3	5	6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Identified desirable traits for cold tolerance and hill rices. — Identified elite germ plasm with cold tolerance. — Developed strategy for breeding for cold tolerance.
Problem soils	4	3	2	7	15	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Identified several varieties tolerant to salinity. — Observed tolerance to other problem soils. — Recommended improved screening methods.
Gall midge and brown planthopper	10	4	2	6	20	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Observed heavy natural screening pressures for gall midge. — Identified several varieties with broad resistance to gall midge and brown planthopper. — Observed distinct biotype of the brown planthopper. — Recommended improved screening methods.
Deep-water and upland rice	13	4	1	5	15	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Discussed and characterized desired traits of upland and deep-water rice. — Identified several varieties with good traits for upland rice. — Discussed methodologies in studying drought tolerance.
Tungro virus and green leafhopper	18	5	2	8	16	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Observed distinct differential varietal reaction to the virus (likely caused by virus strains). — Adopted standard field screening techniques. — Identified varieties with broad-spectrum resistance.

and interests of country coordinators and local cooperators and to supply them with the appropriate nurseries and information. Communication links were established through planning sessions, correspondence, and monitoring tours, creating an "esprit de corps" among the cooperators.

Results of the discussions and planning sessions, as well as preliminary nursery results, were published as separate reports in the *Rice Pathology Newsletter* or in the *Rice Entomology Newsletter*. Observations and recommendations of the monitoring tour groups were sent to leading rice scientists and administrators.

A 64-page booklet, *Standard Evaluation System for Rice*, was developed by participants in the planning sessions to provide guidelines for evaluating the various traits in the nurseries on a uniform scale of 0-9. Copies have been sent to all IRTP cooperators.

The objective of the data management system

is to rapidly collect and analyze results of the testing program and report to scientists interested in using the data in national program planning. Special color-coded fieldbooks were designed for each nursery. Background information was supplied for each entry so that cooperators could closely watch promising materials. This encouraged cooperators to cross elite entries with local materials during the first nursery season, shortening the time required to develop improved varieties with specific characteristics.

Close ties developed by IRTP coordinators with the cooperators resulted in a high standard of nursery management and in prompt return of data. For example, results of the International Rice Tungro Nursery were received from cooperators within 1 month after the nursery was completed in all locations where tungro was prevalent.

Genetic evaluation and utilization (GEU) program

Integrated breeding program

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SUMMARY

Two new varieties, IR32 and IR34, were named during 1975. Both are broadly resistant to insects and diseases and have special characteristics that adapt them to regions where other varieties are not suited. We decided to discontinue releasing varieties during 1975, so IR34 was the last officially named IRRI variety.

We sent 4,729 seed packets of breeding lines in response to special requests from scientists in more than 50 countries during 1975. More than 50,000 other seed packets of IRRI breeding lines were distributed through the International Rice Testing Program.

Six IRRI lines were named as varieties by national programs during 1975. This brings to at least 42 the number of IRRI lines named in other countries.

The crossing program was further expanded. More than a third of the crosses were multiple crosses involving more than two parents. Other aspects of the breeding program have also expanded rather dramatically. We anticipate that the volume of our program will stabilize at about the present level.

During the past several years, we have dramatically increased the proportion of our breeding materials that carry resistance to most major diseases and insects. These have been extensively tested in the Philippines and are being evaluated in the International Rice Testing Program. We have several hundred lines that we consider promising for the various traits emphasized in the GEU program.

NEW VARIETIES

Plant Breeding Department

Two new varieties, IR32 and IR34, were named during 1975. Both are broadly resistant to insects and diseases and have special characteristics that adapt them to regions where other IRRI varieties are not suited.

IR32 matures in 140 to 145 days—later than other IRRI varieties. The semidwarf rice may be particularly suited for certain rainfed areas where farmers grow only one crop. In these areas, late maturity is desirable so that farmers can harvest and dry the crop after the monsoon

rains. In typhoon zones, later maturing crops may escape storm damage.

Because IR34 is intermediate in height (120–130 cm), it may be suited for rainfed regions or areas where the water becomes too deep for semidwarfs during the monsoon season. Farmers in Malaysia, Indonesia, and other countries often prefer such intermediate-statured rice varieties.

IR32 and IR34 yield about like other IRRI varieties (1975 yield data are summarized in the Agronomic Characteristics section of this report).

IR32 and IR34 are resistant to the widespread brown planthopper, and to tungro and grassy stunt virus diseases. Both are also resistant to bacterial blight and green leafhoppers and at least moderately resistant to blast. IR32's genetic resistance to brown planthoppers stems from a different gene than that of other resistant varieties, IR26, IR28, IR29, and IR30. It carries the recessive gene (bph 2). Similarly, both IR32 and IR34 are thought to carry different genes for green leafhopper resistance, although detailed genetic studies have not yet been conducted. The increased genetic diversity lessens the danger of new insect biotypes multiplying that can survive on and attack resistant varieties. IR32 is moderately resistant to the stem borer (about like IR20). IR34 is slightly less resistant than IR20. IR32 was found resistant to the gall midge by scientists at the Central Rice Research Institute (CRRRI), Cuttack, India.

IR32 has long, slender grains with excellent appearance. It has a high amylose content and soft gel consistency, which may make it desirable for consumers in areas such as Indonesia and the Philippines. IR34 is a high-amylose type with long, slender grains. Because of its hard gel consistency, its eating quality may be somewhat less desirable than that of IR32.

IR34 was found to be tolerant to zinc-deficient soils in greenhouse tests at IRRI.

IR32 was previously known by its experimental line number, IR2070-747-6-3-2. It is a progeny of the cross IR20²/*Oryza nivara*//CR94-13.

IR34 was previously known by its experimental line number, IR2061-213-2-17. It is a

Table 1. Resistance ratings^a of IRRI varieties. IRRI, 1975.

Variety	Diseases				Insects				Soil problems			
	Blast	Bacterial blight	Grassy stunt	Tungro	Green leafhopper	Brown planthopper	Stem borer	Gall ^b midge	Alkali injury	Salt injury	Zinc deficiency	Phosphorus deficiency
IR8	MR	S	S	S	R	S	MS	S	S	MR	S	MR
IR5	S	S	S	S	R	S	S	S	S	MR	R	MR
IR20	MR	R	S	R	R	S	MR	S	S	MR	R	R
IR22	S	R	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	MR
IR24	S	S	S	MR	R	S	S	S	MR	MR	S	MR
IR26	MR	R	MS	R	R	R	MR	S	MR	MR	S	R
IR28	R	R	R	R	R	R	MR	S	MR	MR	R	R
IR29	R	R	R	R	R	R	MR	S	S	MS	R	R
IR30	MS	R	R	R	R	R	MR	S	MR	MR	R	MR
IR32	MR	R	R	R	R	R	MR	R	S	MR	MR	MR
IR34	R	R	R	R	R	R	MR	S	S	S	R	R

^aR = resistant; MR = moderately resistant; MS = moderately susceptible; S = susceptible. Rated in the Philippines. ^bRated in India.

progeny of the cross Peta³/Taichung Native 1//Gam Pai 15/4/IR8/Tadukan//TKM6²/TN1 ///IR24⁴/O. nivara.

Before releasing the two new varieties, scientists at IRRI and in national programs studied yield data and insect and disease reactions from tests at experiment stations and in farmers' fields in the Philippines, Bangladesh, India, Thailand, and several other countries.

We decided to discontinue releasing varieties during 1975, so IR34 was the last officially named IRRI variety.

The resistance ratings and the major characteristics of all IRRI varieties are summarized in Tables 1 and 2.

EXCHANGE OF GERM PLASM

Plant Breeding Department

We continued to supply improved breeding lines to scientists across the rice-growing world. We sent 4,729 seed packets of breeding lines in response to special requests from scientists in more than 50 countries during 1975. More than 50,000 other seed packets of IRRI breeding lines were distributed through the International Rice Testing Program.

IRRI LINES NAMED IN OTHER COUNTRIES

Plant Breeding Department

Six IRRI lines were named as varieties by national programs during 1975 (Table 3). This brings to at least 42 the number of IRRI lines named in other countries. Several intermediate-statured selections from the IR442 cross were

named as varieties in Bihar and West Bengal states, India. One of the IR442 parents, Leb Mue Nahng, is a floating rice from Thailand. Because the IR442 selections have some elongation ability, they are adapted to areas of deeper-than-normal water. The IR442 selections also have better-than-average tolerance to drought. IR579-48-1 and IR1561-228-3 were named as varieties in Egypt; their earliness is desirable there to maximize the efficiency of water use. These selections have excellent grain quality and are extremely productive under Egyptian growing conditions.

BREEDING OPERATIONS

Plant Breeding Department

The crossing program was further expanded during 1975 (fig. 1). More than a third of the crosses were multiple crosses involving more than two parents. Other aspects of the breeding program have also expanded rather dramatically (Table 4). We anticipate that the volume of our program will stabilize at about the present level.

Essentially all of our F₂ populations and pedigree rows were grown without chemical protection during 1975. During the 1974 dry season severe natural pressure from brown planthoppers and the associated grassy stunt virus disease almost completely eliminated susceptible genotypes. During the wet season, however, farmers in neighboring Laguna province widely planted the resistant variety IR26, which apparently caused a decline in brown planthopper numbers in farmers' fields as well as at IRRI. Because the situation was similar

Table 2. Major characteristics of varieties named by IRII, 1966-1975.

Character	IR8	IR5	IR20	IR22	IR24	IR26	IR28	IR29	IR30	IR32	IR34
Growth duration											
Dry season (Dec. seeding)	125 days	135 days	120 days	115 days	125 days	130 days	105 days	115 days	106 days	140 days	120 days
Wet season (June seeding)	130 days	145 days	135 days	130 days	125 days	130 days	105 days	115 days	109 days	145 days	125 days
Sensitive to photoperiod	no	weakly	weakly	weakly	no	no	no	no	no	no	no
Grain											
Length	medium	medium	medium	long	long	medium	long	medium	medium	long	long
Width	bold	bold	slender	slender	slender	slender	slender	slender	slender	slender	slender
Appearance	some white belly	some white belly	translucent	translucent	translucent	translucent	translucent	opaque	translucent	translucent	some white belly
Head rice recovery	low	high	moderately high	high	high	high	high	high waxy	high	high	high
Amylose content	high	high	high	high	low	high	high	high	high	high	high
Gel consistency	hard	soft	medium	hard	soft	medium-soft	hard	soft	soft	soft	hard
Gelatinization temperature	low	inter-mediate	inter-mediate	low	low	low	low	low	inter-mediate	low	low
Seed dormancy	moderate	moderate	moderate	moderate	moderate	moderate	moderate	moderate	moderate	moderate	high
Seedling vigor	very good	very good	very good	good	good	good	good	very good	very good	very good	very good
Height	90-105 cm	130-140 cm	110-115 cm	95-105 cm	100-110 cm	100-110 cm	100-110 cm	90-100 cm	95-105 cm	100-110 cm	120-130 cm
Tillering ability	high	high	high	high	moderate	high	moderate	high	high	high	high
Lodging	resistant	moderately resistant	moderately resistant	resistant	resistant	moderately resistant	moderately resistant	moderately resistant	moderately resistant	resistant	moderately resistant

Table 3. IRII lines named as varieties in other countries during 1975.

IRII line	Cross	Name	Country
IR442-2-24	Peta ² /TN1//Leb. Mue Nahng	Pani Dhan 1	Bihar, India
IR442-2-58	"	Pani Dhan 2	Bihar, India
IR442-2-50	"	IR50	West Bengal, India
IR442-2-58	"	IR58	West Bengal, India
IR579-48-1-2	IR8/Tadukan	Sakha 1	Egypt
IR1561-228-3	IR8/Tadukan//TKM6 ² /TN1	Sakha 2	Egypt

in 1975, we could not screen under natural conditions for brown planthopper and grassy stunt resistance. All lines that were potentially resistant to the brown planthopper, however, were evaluated in the greenhouse under artificial conditions.

During the 1975 dry season, the incidence of tungro virus was relatively heavy on the IRRI farm, so we were able to eliminate susceptible genotypes from our F_2 populations and pedigree rows. As far as we know, this is the first time in the history of the Institute that tungro virus has been heavy during the dry season. Virus incidence in our nurseries was augmented by heavy plantings of the highly susceptible variety Taichung Native 1 in alleys and in border plots. Virus incidence continued into the wet season and we effectively screened our materials for tungro resistance throughout the year.

Grain yield was relatively poor in replicated trials during the dry season due to unseasonably heavy rains during the period of grain filling. During the wet season, lodging was extremely heavy in our replicated trials, even though no major depressions passed through the Los Baños area and weather conditions were relatively mild. We think that excessive lodging may have been due to unusually heavy incidences of sheath rot and stem rot. Even varieties that are normally sturdy, such as IR8, lodged significantly at high fertility levels during the wet season.

The Genetic Evaluation and Utilization program is an interdisciplinary program that now involves 17 senior scientists from eight research departments. Coordination of activities is essential and requires careful attention. During 1975, we began to examine each nursery and screening facility and to carefully define its respective operational procedures and respon-

1. Crosses accomplished in the IRRI breeding program.

sibilities in relation to the total GEU program. We also began to convert to computer all of our procedures for record keeping and data handling.

PROGRESS IN DEVELOPING LINES WITH MULTIPLE ATTRIBUTES

All GEU Departments

During the past several years, we have dramatically increased the proportion of our breeding materials that carry resistance to most major disease and insect pests in the Philippines (fig. 2 and 3). We are now accumulating information on the races, strains, and biotypes of these pests. We have differentiated and are now

Table 4. Expansion of breeding activities. IRRI, 1970-1975.

Year	Crosses (no.)	F_2 combinations	Pedigree lines (no.)	Seed packets dispatched (no.)
1970	175	134	27320	10386
1971	375	130	33188	10973
1972	1150	280	42886	11473
1973	2175	350	35446	11172
1974	2850	373	38354	36492
1975	3597	536	50356	58428

2. Changes in proportion of F_2 populations and entries in the replicated yield trials with resistance, and different sources of resistance, to important insects and diseases in the Philippines.

3. Changes in proportion of entries in IRRIs annual replicated yield trials with multiple resistance to important diseases and pests in the Philippines (blast, bacterial blight, tungro, grassy stunt, brown planthopper, and green leafhopper). Each year's trials consisted of at least 185 entries.

incorporating into our program several genetic sources of resistance to bacterial blight and brown planthoppers (fig. 2). Varieties carrying the *Bph 1* gene for brown planthopper resistance, such as IR26, are now widely grown in the Philippines. Such varieties are rapidly being multiplied for use in Indonesia where brown planthoppers of a biotype that appears identical to the Philippines biotype are becoming a severe pest. Because we expect a second biotype to arise that will render these varieties susceptible, we are incorporating a second source of resistance, *bph 2*, into our materials. IR32 carries this source of resistance. Several elite lines carrying the *bph 2* source of resistance are now being considered for release by Philippine scientists. We have identified two other sources of brown planthopper resistance and as further insurance we are backcrossing them into our elite lines.

Most of our advanced lines and all of the varieties so far carry the *Xa 4* gene for bacterial blight resistance. This gene does not convey resistance to all strains of the pathogen in the Philippines, nor is it resistant to all of the international isolates. We now have several excellent advanced lines that have the recessive source of resistance (*xa 5*), which conveys resistance to important Philippine strains.

Although practically all of our material is resistant to grassy stunt virus disease, it derives from only one source. During 1975, pathologists identified a possible second source of resistance. We are incorporating it into our program while we investigate its genetic nature. As far as we know, the source of resistance used in our program withstands grassy stunt wherever it occurs.

We are diversifying our material for different genetic sources of green leafhopper resistance. Almost all of our advanced lines are resistant; the dominant source of resistance is *Glh 3*. But several other sources have been identified and employed in the program, and several advanced lines carry genes other than *Glh 3* although in many cases the exact resistance source has not been determined. Because green leafhopper resistance appears stable, we have not placed heavy emphasis on monitoring the various sources of resistance. Varieties carrying the

Table 5. Important characteristics of selected promising lines. IRRI, 1975.

Designation	Cross	Growth duration (days)	Amylose content (%)	Reaction ^a to							Special traits	
				Bacterial blight		Grassy stunt	Green leaf-hopper	Brown plant-hopper		Stem borer		
				Blast	Tungro			Bio-type 1	Bio-type 2			
IR1632-93-2	IR24/Co 13	115	28	S	R	R	R	R	S	MR	Seedling vigor	
IR1820-52-2	IR24//Mudgo//IR8/3//Peta ³ //TN1//Tetep	135	24	MR	S	S	R	R	S	R	Resistance to <i>Tryporyzae</i>	
IR2035-117-3	Peta ³ //TN1//Tetep/3//Peta ³ //TN1//HR 21/4/ IR24//Mudgo//IR8/3//IR24 ³ // <i>O. nivara</i>	130	27	MR	S	R	R	R	S	MR	Drought tolerance	
IR2061-465-1	Peta ³ //TN1//Gam Pai 15/4//IR8//Tadukan// TKM6 ² //TN1/3//IR24 ⁴ // <i>O. nivara</i>	105	27	MR	R	R	R	R	S	MR		
IR2061-522-6	"	105	27	R	R	R	R	R	S	MR	Intermed. ht	
IR2070-414-3	"	110	27	R	R	R	R	R	S	MR		
IR2070-423-2	IR20 ² // <i>O. nivara</i> //CR94-13	115	26	MR	R	R	R	R	MR	MR	Resistance to whorl maggot	
IR2071-586-5	IR8//Tadukan//TKM6 ² //TN1/3//IR24 ⁴ // <i>O. nivara</i> /4//CR94-13	120	25	MR	R	R	R	R	S	MR	Soft gel consistency	
IR2071-625-1	"	130	26	MR	R	R	R	R	S	MR	High stable yield	
IR2153-26-3	IR24//TKM6 ² //IR20 ³ // <i>O. nivara</i>	105	25	MR	R	R	R	R	R	MR	High yield & early maturity	
IR2153-338-3	"	125	25	MS	R	R	R	R	S	MR	Salt tolerance	
IR2823-399-5	CR94-13/3//Sigadis ² //TN1//IR24/4//IR24 ³ / <i>O. nivara</i> /3//Peta ³ //TN1//Tetep	115	25	S	R	R	R	R	S	MR	High protein	
IR2863-38-1	Sigadis ² //TN1//IR24/3//CR94-13/4// NMS4 ² //TN1	125	24	R	R	R	R	R	R	MR	Excellent plant type	
IR3351-38-3	Peta ³ //TN1//Khao Dawk Mali/3//IR20 ³ / <i>O. nivara</i> /4//CR94-13	125	26	MS	R	R	R	R	R	MR	High protein	
IR3839-1	Pelita 1-2/3//Sigadis ² //TN1//IR24/4//Peta ³ / TN1//Leb Mue Nahng/3//RN21	130	15	MR	R	R	R	R	R	MR	Aromatic	
IR3880-2	Peta ³ //TN1//Khao Dawk Mali/3//C22/4/ Pelita 1-2//IR24//TKM6	115	25	MS	R	R	R	R	R	—	Drought resistance	
IR3941-58-3	CR126-42-5//IR34	105	25	MR	R	R	R	R	S	—	Soft gel consistency	
IR4422-51-1	IR24//Mudgo//IR8/3//BPI121-407/5//Peta ³ / TN1/4//IR8//Tadukan//TKM6 ² //TN1/3/ IR24 ⁴ // <i>O. nivara</i>	125	22	R	R	R	R	R	S	MR	Cold tolerance	
IR4683-54-2	IR24//DZ192//IR24 ³ // <i>O. nivara</i> /5//Peta ⁴ / TN1//Tetep/3//Peta ³ //TN1//HR21/4/ IR24//Mudgo//IR8/3//IR24 ³ // <i>O. nivara</i>	115	28	R	R	R	R	R	R	—	Intermed. amylose	
IR5853-67	Nam Sagui/5//IR8//Tadukan//TKM6 ² / TN1/3//IR24 ⁴ // <i>O. nivara</i> /4//CR94-13/6/ Peta ³ //TN1/4//IR8//Tadukan//TKM6 ² / TN1/3//IR24 ⁴ // <i>O. nivara</i>	110	27	—	R	R	R	R	R	—	MR	<i>xa5</i> /Blb resistance
IR4816-70-1	IR24 ⁴ // <i>O. nivara</i> /4//BRJ1-13-B-10//IR24/ TKM6/3//IR8//Chowsung//IR20//TKM6	125	27	MR	R	R	R	R	S	—	MR	Tolerance to submergence

^aR = resistant; MR = moderately resistant; S = susceptible; MS = moderately susceptible. Rated in the Philippines. ^bRated in India.

Glh 3 gene have been grown in the Philippines and several other countries for many years, yet no biotypes have developed that render this source susceptible.

Table 5 shows a few representative lines of several hundred advanced GEU lines that we consider promising. IR1632-93-2 has outstanding seedling vigor and may represent a different source of tungro resistance. IR1820-52-2 has outstanding resistance to the stem borer. Although it does not possess the necessary spectrum of pest resistance for use in the Philippines, it may be useful in other countries where the stem borer is a major constraint to rice yields. IR2035-117-3 has proven outstanding for drought tolerance and is now being carefully evaluated and purified for possible use in rainfed areas. IR2070-414-3 appeared uniquely resistant to the rice whorl maggot. The performance of IR2071-586-5 has been outstanding in all advanced evaluation trials at IRRI. Among all selections in agronomy nitrogen-response trials it gave the highest and most stable yields; it was also the top performer in rice production trials at several locations in the Philippines. It was the top yielder in the routine replicated evaluation trials and in a replicated trial conducted by entomologists for evaluation of field resistance to pests. IR2071-625-1 is a high-yielding, early line that is resistant to gall midge in India as well as to a broad spectrum of major pests. IR2153-26-3 is only moderately resistant to certain important diseases such as tungro and blast, but it is outstanding in tolerance to salinity. The pest

resistance of IR2153-338-3 is similar, and its protein content is significantly higher. The sturdy IR2823-399-5 is the first line developed through our program that has an outstanding plant type and a complete spectrum of disease and insect resistance. IR2863-38-1 is promising for high protein content and it appeared outstanding in the preliminary results from the second International Rice Observational Nursery. It appears widely adapted to different edaphic and bioclimatic conditions of Southeast Asia. IR3839-1 and IR3880-2 are drought-resistant selections derived from lowland/upland crosses; both have cooking characteristics popular for upland rice as well as pest resistance. IR3351-38-3 is our first high-yielding aromatic line with a complete spectrum of pest resistance. IR3941-58-3 is tolerant to low temperatures and does well in areas of high elevation. In addition, it matures very early and may also be suited to lowland areas. IR4683-54-2 is an outstanding line that carries a new source (*xa 5*) for bacterial blight resistance. IR5853-67 has appeared outstanding for submergence tolerance in preliminary evaluation trials and carries a complete spectrum of disease and insect resistance. IR4816-70-1 has intermediate stature and represents our best prototype for use in rainfed areas. It has wide leaves and a high level of resistance to the major diseases and insects.

All of the lines discussed above have been tested in the Philippines for resistance to pests. They are being evaluated in the International Rice Testing Program and the results will be published as soon as possible.

Genetic evaluation and utilization (GEU) program

Diffusion of genetic materials and breeding objectives of rice breeders in India

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SUMMARY

Through analysis of breeding records and in-depth interviews at 10 Indian research stations, we traced the flow of rice genetic materials through three periods within a decade: 1965–1967, 1970–71, and 1974–75. We also determined the breeding objectives of 1974–75 crosses.

We randomly selected and analyzed 44 crosses from the 1965–67 breeding records and 68 crosses from the 1970–71 records at seven state- and national-level experiment stations. For 1974–75, we analyzed 44 crosses made at 10 centers.

We found that 82 percent of the 1965–67 crosses involved at least one semidwarf. TN1 was used in 41 percent of the crosses; IR8 in 27 percent; and IRRI rices other than IR8 in 14 percent. No locally developed semidwarfs were found in the 1965–67 sample.

The percentage of total crosses that involved semidwarfs increased to 91 percent in 1970–71 and leveled off through 1974–75. By the early 1970's, the direct use of TN1 as a parent in crosses had dropped to 10 percent, and by 1974–75 to 7 percent. The use of IR8 as a parent dropped 1 percent over the first 5 years, but then dropped to 17 percent by 1974–75. The use of semidwarf materials from other countries increased slightly.

While other IRRI materials were used increasingly by 1974–75, locally developed semidwarfs were even more popular. They were used in almost half of the crosses by 1970–71 and in 61 percent by 1974–75. Fifty-five percent of the local semidwarfs used in 1974–75 were progeny of IR8, and 39 percent were progeny of TN1 (9 percent involved both).

Seventy-seven percent of the crosses in 1965–67 involved a tall parent, but only 48 percent did so in 1974–75. The use of intermediate-statured parents declined from 45 percent in 1965–67 to 11 percent in 1974–75. Seventy-nine percent of the total parent material was indica in the mid-1960's; 10 years later, 96 percent was indica. The use of japonicas and ponlais declined over the decade. Hybrids made up 57 percent of the parents in 1965–67, and 74 percent in 1974–75.

Yield potential was cited as a primary breeding objective for making 89 percent of the crosses; fertilizer response was an objective of 80 percent; and resistance to lodging, of 80 percent. Semidwarfs were almost invariably used as genetic sources of these traits. Grain quality was an objective of 67 percent of the crosses. Seventy-three percent of the time that tall varieties were used, the breeders hoped to transfer a preferred type of grain into the progeny, but this was the objective only 49 percent of the time that the semidwarfs were used. We found that 80 percent of the semidwarfs used for grain quality were locally developed, further indicating that introduced semidwarfs were often crossed with local rices to develop HYV's with acceptable grain quality. Fifty-nine percent of the crosses had growth duration as an objective. Forty-three percent of the crosses involved resistance to at least one disease, and 37 percent involved insect resistance. Resistance to blast, bacterial blight, tungro virus, and grassy stunt virus were the most frequent disease objectives. Brown planthopper resistance and gall midge resistance were the most common insect objectives. Drought tolerance was sought in only 9% of the crosses, cold tolerance in 9%, tolerance to waterlogged soils in 7%, and tolerance to deep water in 2%. Tall or intermediate-statured parents were used as donors for most of these traits.

DIFFUSION OF GENETIC MATERIALS *Office of Information Services*

As a major supplier of genetic materials to more than 50 countries, IRRI is interested in the diffusion of new gene sources into national breeding programs where they are incorporated into new, better adapted varieties and fed into farmers' production channels.

Through analysis of breeding records and in-depth interviews, we traced the flow of rice genetic materials over a 10-year period, from the mid-1960's through the mid-1970's, and determined current breeding objectives of scientists, as part of a collaborative research project of IRRI and Iowa State University, U.S.A. The project was partially funded by The Rocke-

feller Foundation. Thirty-six rice breeders were interviewed in 1975 at 23 experiment stations in Bangladesh, India, Iran, Nepal, Pakistan, Philippines, Sri Lanka, and Thailand.

Eighteen of the 36 breeders were from 12 experiment stations and agricultural universities in different regions of India. Three of these stations were at national level; the others were at state level. To refine our methodology for analysis and interpretation, we are first compiling and analyzing data collected in India.

Adoption of semidwarf rices as parental material. We analyzed randomly selected crosses made by rice breeders during three periods over the past 10 years: 1965–67, 1970–71, and 1974–75.

To determine what types of rices were being used over the decade, 44 crosses were analyzed from the 1965–67 breeding records and 68 crosses from the 1970–71 records of seven rice research stations across India—four at state and three at national level; for 1974–75, 46 crosses were analyzed at 10 stations.

We found that 38 percent of the 102 parents used in the 1965–67 crosses were semidwarfs; 80 percent of the crosses made during this period involved at least one semidwarf parent used to shorten the height of the tropical plant (Table 1).

The most popular single gene source used in 1965–67 was the Taiwanese variety Taichung Native 1 (TN1), the first semidwarf to be widely grown in India. TN1 was used in 41 percent of the crosses; IR8 was already used in 27 percent of the 1965–67 crosses (fig. 1). IRRI experi-

mental lines other than IR8 were used in another 14 percent of the crosses. Semidwarf-statured rices from China, Japan, and Taiwan were used in another 7 percent. No locally developed semidwarfs were reported as parents during the 1965–67 period.

The percentage of total crosses in which a semidwarf parent was used increased to 91% by 1970–71, and remained at that level through 1974–75 (Table 1).

The composition of the semidwarf varieties being used as parents has changed far more significantly than the number of crosses that involved semidwarfs.

By the early 1970's, the direct use of TN1 as a parent in crosses had dropped dramatically—from 41 percent down to 10 percent (fig. 1). By mid-1975, TN1 was being used as a parent in only about 7 percent of the crosses.

The use of IR8 as a parent remained relatively stable at from 26 to 27 percent through the first 5 years, but it dropped sharply—down to 17 percent—between 1970–71 and 1974–75. The use of other IRRI materials remained constant through 1970–71, but rose sharply by 1974–75, as newer material became available.

Semidwarf-statured materials from other countries have increased slightly.

But a new trend had emerged by 1970–71. While no locally developed semidwarfs were being used as sources of the dwarf gene in 1965–67, we found that almost half of the crosses involved a local semidwarf by 1970–71. By 1974–75, 61 percent of the crosses involved

Table 1. Plant height of 336 rices used as parents in 158 crosses made during a 10-year period. Ten agricultural experiment stations, India, 1975.

Plant height	Frequency of use in 1965–67 ^a		Frequency of use in 1970–71 ^a		Frequency of use in 1974–75 ^b	
	(no.)	(%)	(no.)	(%)	(no.)	(%)
	<i>102 individual parents</i>		<i>138 individual parents</i>		<i>96 individual parents</i>	
Tall	38	37	52	38	26	27
Intermediate	25	25	13	9	5	5
Semidwarf	39	38	73	53	65	68
	<i>Use in 44 crosses</i>		<i>Use in 68 crosses</i>		<i>Use in 46 crosses</i>	
Tall	34	77	50	74	22	48
Intermediate	20	45	12	18	5	11
Semidwarf	36	80	63	91	42	91

^a Compiled from crossing records at four state-level rice research stations and agricultural universities in Kashmir, Maharashtra, Orissa, and Punjab, and at three national centers, the Central Rice Research Institute (CRRI), Cuttack; the Indian Agricultural Research Institute (IARI), New Delhi; and the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project (AICRIP), Hyderabad.

^b Compiled from personal interviews and analysis of crossing records at all rice research stations analyzed for 1965–67 and 1970–71, plus three other state-level stations in Bihar, Kerala, and Tamil Nadu.

1. a) Use of semidwarf parents. Indian rice breeders used Taichung Native 1 (TN1) and IR8 intensively in the mid-1960's, but they had largely switched to locally developed semidwarfs and improved IRRI lines by 1974-75. b) Ninety-four percent of the local semidwarfs used in 1974-75 were progeny of IR8 or TN1. Analysis of 336 rice used as parents in 158 randomly selected crosses, 10 agricultural experiment stations, India, 1975.

at least one locally developed semidwarf.

Jaya was a dwarf gene source for 9 percent of the local semidwarfs. Interestingly, Jaya itself is a locally developed semidwarf, selected from the cross TN1/T141.

Genetic composition of local semidwarfs. Our next step was to determine the genetic composition of the locally developed semidwarfs now being used as donor parents in the local breeding programs.

Analysis of the parents and the ancestors of the locally developed semidwarfs used in the 1974-75 crosses shows that 55 percent were progeny of IR8, and another 39 percent were progeny of TN1 (fig. 1). There is a 9-percent

overlap—crosses in which both IR8 and TN1 and Jaya were used.

Virtually all the semidwarf materials, including IR8 and TN1, have as a source of dwarfism the Chinese rice *Dee-geo-woo-gen* (DGW), so we may assume that the DGW gene was in the ancestry of about 90 percent of the crosses that were being made in 1974-75.

Thus, we conclude that by the mid-1970's the original hardy, stiff-strawed varieties were being phased out of the breeding programs as parents, but that they continued to live on through a wide range of progeny. Rice breeders in India have adopted these first semidwarf varieties and incorporated their best genetic

traits into newer rices better suited to local conditions.

Tall and intermediate-statured parents. As the use of locally developed semidwarf varieties increased over the decade, the use of tall varieties declined.

Thirty-seven percent of the total parent materials used in 1965–67 crosses were tall varieties (Table 1). By 1974–75, tall varieties made up only 27 percent.

In the 1965–67 period, 77 percent of the crosses involved a tall parent and 80 percent involved a semidwarf. But tall varieties were used in only 48 percent of the 1974–75 crosses.

Similarly, 25 percent of the parents used in 1965–67 were of intermediate stature. By 1974–75, only 5 percent were intermediate. Forty-five percent of the mid-1960 crosses involved an intermediate-statured parent, but only 18 percent by the early 1970's, and 11 percent by the mid-1970's (Table 1).

Over the same period, the percentage of semidwarfs used as parent material increased from 38 percent to 68 percent of all rices. The percentage of crosses that involved semidwarfs increased from 80 to 91 percent (Table 1).

Origin of parental materials. We also found a corresponding upward trend in locally developed materials. In 1965–67, 32 percent of the parent material used in the randomly selected crosses was local or locally developed. This had increased to 60 percent by 1970–71 and to 64 percent by 1974–75 (fig. 2). The percentage of

2. Origin of 336 parents used in 158 randomly selected crosses in 1965–67, 1970–71, and 1974–75. Ten agricultural experiment stations, India, 1975.

3. Types of rices used as 336 parents in 158 randomly selected crosses in 1965–67, 1970–71, and 1974–75. Ten agricultural experiment stations, India, 1975.

plant materials introduced from other countries dropped from 50 to 12 percent as breeders switched from the use of TN1 to locally developed semidwarfs. The use of all IRRI materials increased from 18 percent in the mid-1960's to 24 percent in the mid-1970's.

Use of indicas, japonicas, javanicas, and ponlais. Tropical rices are of the indica type. But rice breeders have long been interested in crossbreeding indica with japonica (temperate-zone) rices. In fact, IRRI's early plant breeding strategy to develop a short-statured rice plant included the crossing of indica and japonica rices (1961–1962 Annual Report).

Analysis of the type of parent materials used in crosses indicated that the semidwarf indicas such as TN1, IR8, and locally developed semidwarfs largely pushed the japonica, javanica, and ponlai materials out of the programs. In the mid-1960's, 79 percent of the parent material was indica; by 1974–75, 96 percent was indica (fig. 3). The use of japonicas dropped from 7 percent in 1965–67 to 3 percent in 1974–75. Ponlai varieties (mostly from Taiwan) were used in 8 percent of the 1965–67 crosses, but none were found in the 1974–75 analysis.

Method of development of parents. The use of hybrid materials as parents in crosses increased from 57 percent of all materials in 1965–67 to 62 percent in 1970–71 and to 74 percent in 1974–75 (fig. 4). Mutants decreased from 3 to 1 percent over the decade, and pureline selections from 30 percent down to 18 percent.

4. The method of development of 336 parents used in 158 randomly selected crosses in 1965-67, 1970-71, and 1974-75. Ten agricultural experiment stations, India, 1975.

Interestingly, the use of varieties classified as "unimproved" increased. This may indicate a stronger trend toward going back to the original traditional sources of specific genetic traits as the programs become increasingly problem oriented.

FACTORS ASSOCIATED WITH ADOPTION

Office of Information Services

Time to adoption. For 31 of the rices used in the 1974-75 crosses, the breeders could recall both

Table 2. The time lag from the year that a variety or line was developed until its adoption in a breeding program, or from the year that a breeder first heard of the rice until its adoption. Sixteen breeders at 12 agricultural experiment stations, India, 1975.

	Time lag (yr) from	
	Development to adoption	First awareness to adoption
	3.7	1.7

Table 3. Methods by which rice breeders acquired 83 parents used in 46 randomly selected crosses. Ten agricultural experiment stations, India, 1975.

Source	Parents	
	(No.)	(%)
Local traditional, locally developed, or in local germ plasm collection	53	64
Sent in trials (AICRIP and IRRI)	19	23
Requested from germ plasm bank		
by trait	2	2
Others	9	11
Total	83	100

the year in which the particular variety or line was developed (to the fixed line stage) and the year in which they first used it as a parent in a cross. For 18 rices, the breeders could recall the year in which they first heard of a particular rice, and the year of its adoption as a parent.

We found an average time lag of 3.7 years from the time a variety or line was developed until adoption (Table 2). The time lag from first awareness of a particular rice until its adoption in the breeding program was 1.7 years.

Method of acquisition. The breeders could recall how they acquired 83 of the 96 rices used in the 1974-75 crosses. Sixty-four percent were locally available—traditional or locally developed varieties or rices that were already in the rice collection at that station (Table 3). The most common method of acquisition of outside materials was through AICRIP or IRRI trials (23%).

BREEDING OBJECTIVES

Office of Information Services

To determine the overall breeding objectives of the 10 programs, we compiled the reasons that the breeders themselves gave for using each parent in each of the 46 crosses made in 1974-75. We then determined the characteristics for which the breeders were using each type of rice, and each variety or line.

Yield potential was the most frequent objective; it was cited as the reason why one of the parents was used in 89 percent of the crosses (fig. 5). Yield was closely associated with fertilizer response (80%), and with resistance to lodging (80%). The semidwarfs were almost invariably used for the yield/fertilizer response/nonlodging complex (Table 4).

Grain quality was cited as an objective of 67 percent of the crosses (fig. 5). We found that 19 of the 26 times (73%) that tall varieties were used, the breeders hoped to transfer a preferred type of grain from the tall donor into the progeny (Table 4). But specific grain quality objectives varied considerably, indicating that consumer preferences varied widely. Long, slender, and aromatic grains seemed to be most popular. Among the semidwarfs, grain quality was an objective 49 percent of the time.

5. The objectives for which rice breeders made 46 randomly selected crosses in 1974–75. Ten agricultural experiment stations, India, 1975.

Since grain quality has been such a consistent objective, we next determined the origin of the 26 individual semidwarf parents that were used for grain quality. Although 55 percent of all semidwarfs used as parents were developed in India, 80 percent of all semidwarfs used for preferred grain characteristics were locally developed (fig. 6). These data further indicate that a primary reason why breeders cross the introduced semidwarfs such as IR8 and TN1 with local varieties is to develop high-yielding semidwarf varieties with grain quality that is acceptable to local tastes.

Growth duration was an objective of 59 percent of the crosses. Most of the crosses were for earliness, but some were for long growth duration. The long-duration crosses were made

for single-cropped regions where the monsoon season is long and farmers want varieties that will mature late enough to be harvested and dried after the rains have ended. Tall rices were more frequently used as donors for preferred growth duration.

Forty-three percent of the crosses involved resistance to at least one disease, and 37 percent involved insect resistance. The breeders tended to use semidwarf rices for both characters. Resistance to blast, bacterial blight, and tungro virus were the most frequently sought disease objectives. Brown planthopper and gall midge resistance were the most commonly cited insect objectives.

Among other biological stresses, drought tolerance was sought in 9% of the crosses;

Table 4. The frequency with which rice breeders sought desired genetic traits from semidwarf, intermediate, and tall parents in crosses. Ninety-six experiment stations, India, 1975.

Breeding objective	Relative frequency of use (%) ^a as parents		
	Semidwarf	Intermediate	Tall
Yield potential	83		4
Fertilizer response	74		
Non-lodging	75		
Grain quality	49	60	73
Growth duration	31	20	50
Disease resistance	42	40	27
Insect resistance	28		12
Tillering	8		
Adaptability	6	20	
Drought	3		8
Cold temperature tolerance		20	15
Non-shattering			4
Alternate gene source		20	
Photoperiod sensitivity	3		8
Waterlogged soils tolerance	5	20	8
Heavy grains/panicle characteristics	3	40	
Seed dormancy	3		4
Seedling vigor	3		
Threshability	2		
Milling recovery	3		
Deep water		20	
Yield stability	2		
Others	2	20	8

^aPercentage of total times that each type of rice was used as a genetic source for each desired trait.

cold tolerance, in 9%; waterlogged soils tolerance, in 7%; and deep water tolerance, in 2%. Tall or intermediate-statured parents were used as donors for most of these characteristics.

6. a) Fifty-five percent of all 65 semidwarf parents used in 1974-75 crosses were locally developed. b) Twenty-eight of the 65 semidwarf parents were used to transfer a preferred grain type into progeny. Eighty percent of these semidwarfs with good grain quality were locally developed. Ten agricultural experiment stations, India, 1975.

Information was also collected on the varieties most widely grown in farmers' fields in the areas served by each experiment station, and on the latest varieties released by each station. The names of these varieties, their genetic makeup, and their favorable and unfavorable characteristics are being compiled. Other data will be analyzed during 1976 on the sociological characteristics, information-seeking habits, and exposure to scientific literature of scientists in India and other rice-growing nations.

Control and management of rice pests

Control and management of rice pests

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SUMMARY

We have identified several chemicals that have strong systemic action against blast, including Homai, Hoe 17411, Hoe 22843, Hoe 22845, Hoe 25985, Benlate, and Topsin M. Some of them also effectively controlled *Cercospora* leaf spot. Closer spacing of rice hills produced more blast lesions than wider spacing because of longer dew period. We used a modified Hrushovertz's method to stain nuclei of *Pyricularia oryzae* and confirmed that most cells were uninucleate; but the irregular or club-shaped mycelial cells had from two to six nuclei and the appressoria had as many as 64 nuclei.

Estimated yield losses to sheath blight were significant on a susceptible variety, averaging 24 percent at highest levels of disease intensity and nitrogen application. Losses were significant (about 13%) on a moderately resistant variety at the highest levels of both disease and nitrogen. Several chemicals effectively controlled sheath blight and increased yields from 15 to 22 percent. Benlate, Topsin M, Hoe 22843, and Hoe 25985 also controlled *Cercospora* and increased yields.

Tungro incidence was low in Luzon, Philippines, in 1975. Incidence was highest on the line IR1561-228-3. The vector population was generally low. Of the 5,818 vector insects collected, about 46 percent were *Nephotettix virescens* and about 1.5 percent were infective; 48 percent were *N. nigropictus* with 0.3 percent infective; and 6 percent, *Recilia dorsalis* with 0.2 percent infective.

We have found no close relationship between tungro incidence and the number of insect vectors collected in light traps at the IRRI farm over 4 years. But yearly incidence of grassy stunt virus at the farm was parallel to the yearly number of its vector, *N. lugens*, trapped by light.

Using cages, we found that infection of seedlings increased markedly as the number of viruliferous insects increased from 0 to 1 per seedling, but infection increased only slightly when insect numbers increased from 1 to 3 per seedling.

The distance between a healthy and a diseased plant that may serve as a direct source of virus is estimated to be about 250 m. This is based on the distance that a viruliferous insect can travel, and the duration that it can remain infective.

The retention period of tungro virus vectors was found to be much longer at low than at high temperature, and to be as long as 22 days at 13°C. The term "non-persistent virus" is therefore no longer appropriate to describe the virus-vector relationship. Rice tungro is now designated as a "transitory leafhopper-transmitted virus."

The infectivity of tungro vectors that moved frequently seemed to be less than that of those that moved less frequently.

BLAST

Plant Pathology Department

Chemical control. We tested 13 chemicals for control of leaf blast disease as seed and soil treatments in wooden flats, and as foliar sprays. Table 1 shows results of soil-treatment experiments. Foliar sprays of many chemicals also controlled leaf blast but only for about a week under the highly infective conditions of the blast nursery.

Our earlier experiments in lowland fields showed that chemical control of neck blast at the critical stage may significantly increase yields. In similar tests on upland plots, some chemicals increased yields by 30 percent. The percentage of neck blast in these treatments, however, did not exactly coincide with the yield because *Cercospora* leaf spot was present. Some chemicals controlled the disease, but others did not (Table 2).

Epidemiological studies. We conducted a preliminary experiment on the relationship of spacing to blast in lowland plots. We found more blast lesions at plant spacings of 10 × 10 cm than at 20 × 20 cm; the least lesions were at 40 × 40 cm. Differences in temperature and relative humidity were slight among the plots, but favorable dew periods (11 hours or more) were more frequent in the 10- × 10-cm plots than in the 40- × 40-cm plots (fig. 1). Dew

Table 1. Results of tests in the systemic control of leaf blast using 13 chemicals applied as soil treatment. IRRI, 1975.

Treatment	Rate/sq m	Lesions (no./leaf ^a)					Av. ^b	
		Rep. 1	Rep. 2	Rep. 3	Rep. 4	Rep. 5		
Hoe 17411	5.7 g	0	0	0	0	0	0	a
Homai	5.7 g	0	0	0	0	0	0	a
Hoe 22845	5.7 g	0	0	0	0	0	0	a
Hoe 25985	5.7 g	0	0	0	0	0	0	a
Hoe 22843	5.7 g	0	0	0	0	0	0	a
Topsin M	5.7 g	0	0	0	0	0	0	a
Benlate	5.7 g	0	0	0	0	0	0.4	a
F ₁	5.7 ml	54	47	42	55	64	52.4	b
Saprol	5.7 ml	79	72	84	79	79	78.6	c
MKS 103	5.7 ml	107	93	102	105	96	100.6	d
Panactine	5.7 ml	109	102	119	121	107	111.62	e
LS 65.255	5.7 g	111	115	108	124	114	114.4	e
Sankel	5.7 g	105	125	121	125	113	117.8	e
Control	0	97	101	104	106	98	101.2	d

^aThe average number of lesions from 10 seedlings randomly selected from a 46- × 46- cm seedbox. ^bMeans followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

periods lasted longer than 11 hours during only three of the 21 nights in plots where plants were spaced 40 × 40 cm, but dew periods favored blast development during 12 nights in the 10- × 10-cm plots. This emphasizes the importance of dew period in blast development.

In earlier experiments, rice had less blast under flooded than under upland conditions at the same rates of inoculation. But when rice was grown in the same soils and at the same fertilization rates in flooded pots and in an upland rice field, we found as many lesions on the flooded as on the neighboring upland plants. This shows that flooding alone does not prevent blast and that the upland microclimate also plays an important role.

Nuclei staining of *P. oryzae*. In cytogenetic studies, we successfully used a modification

of the Hrushovertz cellophane square method to stain the nuclei of conidia and mycelia of *P. oryzae*. Squares of cellulose tubing, 2 cm in area, were sterilized by boiling in distilled water for 20–30 minutes. The sterile squares (3–4 per petri dish) were transferred aseptically onto the surface of the potato-sucrose or prune-agar medium. We placed the inoculum and spores of mycelium on the medium near the sides of the bits, and incubated the dishes at 28°C for 4–6 days. We gently removed the cellulose squares with the fully grown mycelia and conidia and fixed them for 10 minutes in a 3:1 mixture of absolute ethyl alcohol and glacial acetate. Acid hydrolysis in IN HCl at 63–65°C for 8–10 minutes was followed by staining with Giemsa according to Hrushovertz at 28–30°C. We uniformly stained the nuclei

Table 2. Chemical control of neck blast and *Cercospora* leaf spot by foliar spray in upland rice. IRRI, 1975.

Treatment	Rate (per ha)	Neck blast (%)	Av. yield (kg/plot) ^a	<i>Cercospora</i> leaf spot ^b
Benlate (50% WP)	1.0 kg	5.1	1.5 a	0.3 a
Topsin M (50% WP)	1.0 kg	4.8	1.5 a	0.3 a
Panactine (40% EC)	1.5 l	10.8	1.5 a	3.8 c
NF 48 (70% WP)	1.0 kg	3.9	1.5 ab	0.4 a
F ₁ (40% EC)	1.5 l	1.0	1.4 abc	10.5 de
Hoe 17411 (20% dispersion)	3.0 kg	9.5	1.3 bcd	1.7 b
Saprol (20% EC)	2.5 kg	24.6	1.3 cd	6.7 cd
EL 291 (75% WP)	1.0 kg	1.3	1.3 cd	13.4 e
LS 72.1828 (50% WP)	2.0 kg	17.2	1.3 cd	11.4 de
Control	0	32.1	1.2 d	21.5 e

^aAv. of 4 replications; each plot had an area of 8 sq m. Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^bAv. no. of spots from 20 randomly selected flag leaves.

1. Relation among the spacing of rice hills, dew periods, and blast development. IRRI, 1975.

of conidia, conidiophores, and mycelia reddish-purple with Giemsa. Most of the conidia and mycelial cells were uninucleate. A few conidial cells had no or two nuclei. The number of cells

per conidium was generally three, but it was occasionally two, four, or six. The mycelial cells of six isolates of *P. oryzae* were found to be both uninucleate and multinucleate. The normal long, thin mycelial cells, 1.0–1.9 and 2.0–4.4 μ m in width, were uninucleate. The irregular or club-shaped mycelial cells were multinucleate, with two to six nuclei in each cell. The appressoria had as many as 64 nuclei (fig. 2).

SHEATH BLIGHT

Plant Pathology Department

Yield losses. To estimate yield losses due to sheath blight, we inoculated a moderately resistant variety, IR26, and a susceptible line, IR1487-372-1, with three levels of disease intensity, 10, 20, and 50 percent inoculated hills. The experiment was conducted in randomized plots fertilized with 0 and 100 kg N/ha. The results from the dry and wet season tests were essentially the same, so only one set of data is shown (Table 3). For the susceptible variety, differences were significant among the levels of disease intensity and between the nitrogen levels. Losses were about 24 percent at the highest disease intensity and under heavy nitrogen application. But the yields of the moderately resistant IR26 were significantly lower only at the higher level of nitrogen and at the highest disease intensity; losses were about 13 percent. This suggests that moderately resistant varieties may not suffer great losses

2. Hyphal cells of *Pyricularia oryzae* showing (left) uninucleate (long, slender hyphae) and multinucleate (short, club-shaped cells) and (right) an appressorium showing multinucleate condition. IRRI, 1975.

Table 3. Yield losses to sheath blight disease. IRRI, 1975.

Hills inoculated (%)	Final disease reading ^a		Yield (t/ha)	Loss (%)
	Infected hills (%)	Disease rating ^b		
IR1487-372-1 (susceptible)				
0 kg N/ha				
0	54.5 a	1.2 a	5.7 a	—
10	86.8 a	5.2 b	5.2 b	7.5
20	98.3 c	7.2 c	5.0 b	12.2
50	100.0 c	8.2 d	4.4 c	22.7
100 kg N/ha				
0	60.8 a	1.5 a	5.8 a	—
10	93.5 b	6.1 b	5.3 b	8.6
20	99.0 c	7.4 c	5.0 c	13.8
50	100.0 c	8.3 d	4.4 d	23.7
IR26 (moderately resistant)				
0 kg N/ha				
0	35.0 a	0.4 a	6.1 a	—
10	75.0 b	2.4 b	6.2 a	0.4
20	88.8 bc	3.4 c	5.7 a	6.5
50	100.0 c	4.7 d	5.6 a	8.8
100 kg N/ha				
0	65.0 a	0.8 a	7.8 a	—
10	100.0 b	3.7 b	7.6 a	2.5
20	98.8 b	4.5 c	7.4 a	5.0
50	100.0 b	4.9 c	6.8 b	13.2

^aMeans followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^bRated on scale of 0-9: 0 = no disease observed; 9 = all leaves dead.

in ordinary fields. Yields of the susceptible variety were very sensitive to disease pressure, decreasing rapidly with increasing disease incidence in both the 0 and 100 kg N/ha plots. The moderately resistant variety, however, was affected much less (fig. 3).

Chemical control. We tried three applications each of eight chemicals for the control of sheath blight, using a susceptible rice line, IR1487. Applications were started at late booting stage in four randomized plots. Yield increases ranged from about 12 to 21 percent (Table 4). Considerable *Cercospora* leaf spot and leaf smut also occurred in the same field. Some chemicals controlled both sheath blight and *Cercospora*, but none controlled leaf smut. Yield increases, therefore, were not entirely due to sheath blight control. Yields were higher on plots where chemicals controlled *Cercospora* leaf spot than on those where chemicals controlled only sheath blight. Increased yield

Table 4. Chemical control of sheath blight and *Cercospora* leaf spot. IRRI, 1975.

Treatment	Yield ^a (t/ha)	Av. sheath blight rating ^b	Av. <i>Cercospora</i> leaf spot rating ^c
Benlate	4.0 a	5.3 c	3.4 b
Hoe 22843	4.0 a	4.8 bc	2.3 a
Hoe 25985	3.9 a	5.4 c	1.8 a
Topsin M	3.9 a	5.5 c	3.2 b
Validacin dust	3.8 a	4.4 ab	7.9 cd
Validacin (microgranules)	3.8 a	4.0 a	7.9 cd
Validacin solution	3.8 a	4.4 a	8.0 cd
Neozocin	3.7 a	4.0 a	7.8 c
Control	3.3 b	7.0 d	8.6 d

^aAv. of four replications. Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^bRated on a scale of 0-9: 0 = no disease observed; 9 = all leaves dead. ^cRated on scale 0-9 of the International Rice Testing Program: 0 = no disease observed; 9 = most severely diseased.

from the control plots also indicated the yield losses of the susceptible variety.

VIRUS DISEASES

Plant Pathology Department

Tungro disease in Luzon. We continued an epidemiological study of rice tungro disease in 37 farmers' fields in 19 municipalities in

3. Correlation between incidence of sheath blight and rice grain yields. IRRI, 1975.

Table 5. Tungro incidence and insect vectors observed in Luzon, Philippines, from November 1974 to December 1975. IRRI, 1975.

Designation	Observations (no.)	Fields with tungro (%)	Tungro incidence (%)	Vectors			Infective insects (%)
				Collections (no.)	Insects/10 sweeps (no.)	Tested (no.)	
<i>Province</i>							
Bulacan	232	72	1.13	195	9.6	3629	0.77
Laguna	180	36	0.89	132	7.2	2428	0.49
Nueva Ecija	115	52	0.39	98	6.8	1449	0.69
Pampanga	117	44	0.92	87	6.8	1276	0.86
Tarlac	179	61	5.55	138	12.6	2961	1.52
<i>Type of field</i>							
Seedbed	82	11	0.55	82	20.6	2218	0.41
Paddy	497	57	2.21	270	5.8	4019	1.07
Stubble	244	65	1.90	244	10.3	5321	1.01
Idle	147	0	0	54	0.8	185	0
<i>Rice cultivar</i>							
C4-636	36	44	1.03	27	6.5	412	0.49
C12	20	40	2.60	15	1.9	166	1.20
IR20	66	64	0.41	56	7.4	930	1.08
IR26	113	38	0.42	82	5.6	1215	0.49
IR30	48	44	0.36	29	4.8	544	0
IR1561-228-3	338	64	3.63	241	12.6	5074	1.38
Others	202	52	0.80	146	10.4	3217	0.50

Bulacan, Laguna, Nueva Ecija, Pampanga, and Tarlac provinces, Luzon, Philippines. We collected insect vectors and studied their infectivity. Disease incidence was observed every 2 weeks.

The fields were classified into four groups: 1) seedbed; 2) paddy field (after transplanting until harvest); 3) stubble field (after harvest until all stubble was dried); and 4) idle field (no rice plants or regenerated growth of rice stubble). These data include 971 field observations made between November 1974 and October 1975. About 9% of the observations were in the seedbed; 51% in the paddy field; 25% in the stubble field; and 15% in the idle field.

We made 650 insect vector collections in all fields in this study. The rice line IR1561-228-3 accounted for 41% of the fields observed; IR26 accounted for 14%; IR20, 8%; IR30, 6%; C4-63G, 4%; C12, 2%; and others, 25%.

Disease incidence. The incidence of tungro in the observed area was low; the overall average was 1.9 percent in 823 observations. But the disease was much more scattered than in the previous study period (between Nov. 1973 and Oct. 1974). Fifty-five percent of the fields had tungro in the 1975 study period;

25 percent had tungro during the previous study period. The disease appeared every month; the highest incidence was 5.1 percent in September, the lowest was 0.4 percent in February.

Tungro incidence also varied among the provinces. The highest incidence, in Tarlac, may be related to the high incidence in seedbeds (Table 5). Increasingly, the ratio of overall percentages of tungro in seedbeds, paddy fields, and stubble fields was about 1:5:6, similar to that of the previous study period.

The incidence of tungro disease varied among rices. It was highest in IR1561-228-3, next highest in C12 (Table 5). In the 1973-74 study period, the highest incidence was in C12 and the second highest in IR1561-228-3. The reason for C12's lower rating could be that no C12 was planted in the province with the highest incidence, Tarlac, in 1975.

Number of insect vectors. Forty-six percent of the 5,818 tungro vectors collected were *Nephotettix virescens*; 48 percent, *N. nigropictus*; and 6 percent, *Recilia dorsalis*. The ratio among the three species differed from that in the 1973-74 period (1974 Annual Report), mainly because more *N. nigropictus* were collected in

Table 6. Tungro vectors collected weekly by light trap from 1700 h until 2 h after sunset, and incidence of tungro disease. IRRI farm, August 1972 to October 1975.

Period	Collections (no.)	Insect vectors		Insects tested (no.)	Infective insects		Disease incidence
		(no./collection)	(ratio ^a)		(%)	(ratio ^a)	
Aug.-Oct. 1972	14	2741	63:28: 9	1501	0.39	87: 5: 8	Trace
Nov. 1972-Oct. 1973	52	458	56:36: 8	3618	1.53	28:60:12	Trace
Nov. 1973-Oct. 1974	52	1881	50:40:10	4454	3.17	63:37: 0	Trace
Nov. 1974-Oct. 1975	52	849	61:29:10	6829	2.20	92: 6: 2	Positive

^a*Nephotettix virescens*: *N. nigropictus*: *Recilia dorsalis*.

the stubble fields in 1975. Although more *N. virescens* insects were collected in seedbeds and paddy fields, more *N. nigropictus* were collected in stubble and idle fields.

The number of tungro vectors was generally low, averaging nine per 10 sweeps. This might be responsible for the low tungro incidence even though about 40 percent of the study fields were planted to the highly susceptible IR1561-228-3.

The number of insects was lowest in November, December, and January, and highest in September. But the highest numbers varied among the fields. The highest number in seedbeds was collected in May; in paddy fields, in September; in stubble fields, in April; and in idle fields, in February. The number of *N. virescens* was highest in September; that of *N. nigropictus*, in April; and that of *R. dorsalis*, in June.

The highest number of insect vectors was collected in Tarlac, where tungro incidence was highest. The highest number was collected in fields of IR1561-228-3, which also had the highest incidence of tungro among the rices (Table 5).

Infective insects. Of the 11,743 insect vectors studied for infectivity, 49% were *N. virescens*; 43%, *N. nigropictus*; and 8%, *R. dorsalis*. The percentages of infective insects of *N. virescens*, *N. nigropictus*, and *R. dorsalis* were 1.52, 0.32, and 0.22, respectively.

The percentage of infective insects was very low, averaging 0.90 throughout the study period. But infective insects were found every month, with the highest percentage in August.

The percentage of infective insects varied

among the provinces, the fields, and the rices (Table 5). So far, no infective insect has been found in idle fields.

Light trap. We first began to collect insect vectors with the objective of forecasting rice virus diseases at the IRRI farm in August, 1972. The insects were collected weekly by light trap from 1700 hours until 2 hours after sunset. We tested portions of the trapped insects for infectivity by daily serial transmission for 3 days for the tungro vectors *Nephotettix virescens*, *N. nigropictus*, and *Recilia dorsalis*, and for 5 days for the grassy stunt vector *Nilaparvata lugens*.

The number of insects trapped by light varied among collections. But often, when the number of one species was high, the numbers of others were also high. *N. virescens* accounted for more than 50 percent of the total tungro vectors captured (Table 6). Over the last 3 years, the number of trapped tungro vectors was generally lower in November, December, January, and February, and lowest in December and January. From March to October, the number of trapped insects was generally high, except in April; it was highest in May, June, August, and September, but it varied among years.

The percentages of infective insects of different types also varied among the collections. Most of the infective insects were *N. virescens* except during the period from November 1972 to October 1973 (Table 6).

Tungro incidence at the IRRI farm did not seem closely related to the number of trapped insects or to the percentage of infective insects. On the other hand, yearly incidence of grassy

Table 7. The numbers of disease vectors *Nilaparvata lugens* collected weekly by light trap from 1700 h to 2 h after sunset and the incidence of grassy stunt virus disease. IRRI farm, 1972-75.

Period	Collections (no.)	Insects (no./collection)	Insects tested (no.)	Infective insects (%)	Disease incidence
Aug.-Oct. 1972	14	4213	678	2.30	High
Nov. 1972-Oct. 1973	52	8279	2766	2.51	Very high
Nov. 1973-Oct. 1974	52	1180	1907	1.47	Moderate
Nov. 1974-Oct. 1975	52	276	2130	0.75	Trace

stunt disease in the IRRI farm was paralleled by yearly number of *N. lugens* trapped by light, and by the percentage of the trapped insects that were infective. But the difference among years in the number of trapped insects was greater than the difference in percentages of infective insects (Table 7).

Viruliferous insects and seedling infection. To determine whether or not tungro symptoms can be developed in a seedbed, we grew 100 seedlings of Taichung Native 1 (TN1) in individual wooden boxes at a spacing of 1.1 × 1.1 cm. They were inoculated with tungro virus by introducing viruliferous insects into small tubes covering individual seedlings for 24 hours. About 2 weeks later, the seedlings developed tungro symptoms. But when only a few of the 100 seedlings were inoculated, we had to closely examine the inoculated seedlings to observe symptoms.

We used TN1 to study the effect of number of incoming viruliferous insects on the degree of

seedling infection by the cage method (1972 Annual Report). To simulate seedlings in seedbeds, each cage contained about 720 seedlings in a wooden tray.

When the seedlings were 14 days old, from 0 to 1,000 viruliferous adults of *N. virescens* were introduced into each cage and confined for 2 weeks. About 62 percent of the insects died, but some nymphs developed from the eggs laid on the seedlings. The insects were then killed by insecticides, and the seedlings were transferred to the greenhouse for the symptoms to develop. More than 87,000 seedlings in 120 trays were tested with more than 33,000 viruliferous insects.

The percentage of infected seedlings (*Y*) was affected very much by the number of viruliferous insects, either per cage (*X*₁) or per seedling (*X*₂) (fig. 4). Their relationship can be described as:

$$\hat{Y} = 100 - 100e^{-0.0043X_1}$$

$$\hat{Y} = 100 - 100e^{-2.8X_2}$$

4. The effect of the number of tungro-viruliferous *Nephotettix virescens* on the percentage of tungro infection of TN1 seedlings. Viruliferous insects were introduced and confined for 2 weeks on 14-day-old seedlings. IRRI, 1975.

where $e = 2.718$.

We found that the percentage of infected seedlings increased rapidly as the number of viruliferous insects increased from 0 to 1 per seedling, but it increased only slightly with an increase of from 1 to 3 per seedling. Hence, reducing the viruliferous insects from 1 to 0 per seedling in a seedbed would greatly reduce seedling infection. But reducing the viruliferous insects from 3 to 1 per seedling would reduce the seedling infection less.

The results indicated that the eggs of viruliferous insects laid on seedlings could be carried to a rice field at transplanting. Once hatched, the nymphs could readily acquire the virus from the infected seedlings and spread the disease to adjacent seedlings early after transplanting.

Arrangement of diseased plants and seedling infection. Using the cage method, we found that the amount of virus source surrounding seedlings influenced infection. In the upper portion of fig. 5, the pots at four corners of the cage had significantly lower percentages of infected seedlings than those at the side or the center of the cage, although the difference only averaged from 4 to 6 percent. The pots at four corners were adjacent to only one pot of diseased plants, while the others were adjacent to two pots.

The distance from the virus sources to the test seedlings also influenced seedling infection. The bottom portion of fig. 5 shows that the distance between the test seedlings and the diseased plants was $A > B > C$. But the percentage of infected seedlings was $C > B > A$, and differences were statistically significant. This could be related to the dispersal of the insects from the diseased plants and to the frequency with which viruliferous insects moved between two adjacent seedlings (1974 Annual Report).

Based on available information on the movement of the green leafhopper and on the period it retains the tungro virus, the maximum distance at which a direct virus source can infect a healthy plant is estimated to be about 250 m.

Retention of tungro virus by vectors. Previous studies indicated that much less infectivity of tungro-viruliferous *N. virescens* was lost at 7°C than at room temperature (1974 Annual Report). This suggests that the retention period of tungro virus by the insect vector may be

Location	Seedlings	
	Tested (no.)	Infected (%)
○ Corner	8042	52a
● Side	8008	56b
⊙ Center	8015	58b

Location	Seedlings	
	Tested (no.)	Infected (%)
● A	2121	48a
○ B	4255	57b
⊙ C	6277	65c

VS = Virus source (diseased plants)

5. Percentage of tungro-infected seedlings of pots at different distances from virus sources in cages. IRRI, 1975.

extended at low temperature. Therefore, we determined the retention period of tungro virus by *N. virescens* at two temperatures by feeding a colony of insects on infected plants at room temperature and then distributing them to test tubes containing healthy rice seedlings. The temperatures of the tubes were maintained at 13° and 32°C. We sampled insects from each temperature regime, and tested their infectivity at 32°C for an inoculation access time of 24 hours. The test was conducted once daily until no insects remained. To prevent the insects from reacquiring the virus from the seedlings in the test tubes, the surviving insects were transferred to new, healthy seedlings each day.

The longest retention period of tungro virus was 22 days after acquisition feeding for 4,378 insects that were kept at 13°C; the longest period was only 6 days for 2,517 insects kept at 32°C. We suspect that the retention period could be lengthened if a large sample of viruliferous insects were tested under a low temperature regime that is more favorable for virus retention by the insect vector. But the infectivity at both temperatures gradually decreased with time after acquisition feeding (fig. 6).

The retention period is a major criterion for grouping insect-borne viruses. Persistent viruses survive in their vectors for long periods, sometimes for weeks or months, while nonpersistent viruses survive for only short periods. The rice tungro virus was earlier categorized as non-persistent (1965 Annual Report) with the con-

6. Retention of infectivity of *Nephrotettix virescens* that transmit rice tungro virus at two different temperatures. IRRI, 1975.

dition that “short” retention period referred to one of no longer than 1 week, since no other character of the virus-vector interaction precluded such a grouping. But the present findings indicate that the retention period of tungro

Table 8. The effect of induced movement on the infectivity of tungro-viruliferous *Nephrotettix virescens*. IRRI, 1975.

Treatment	Infective insects ^a (%)	
	1-h treatment	4-h treatment
Insects on healthy plants	84 ab	77 ab
Insects not on rice plant	84 a	75 bc
Insects not on plant but induced to move once every 3 min.	75 ab	66 c

^aMeans followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

virus by *N. virescens* is longer than 3 weeks at 13°C, so the term “nonpersistent” no longer seems appropriate.

We propose a new term—“transitory”—for leafhopper-borne viruses that have the following characteristics of virus-vector interaction: 1) The virus does not persist in its leafhopper vector (the infectivity or percentage of infective insects decreases with time after acquisition feeding); 2) The retention period is generally short but can exceed a week, particularly at a low temperature; 3) There is no demonstrable latent period in the insect vector; 4) The infectivity is lost due to molting, or transstadial blockage; and 5) The insect can become re-infective after reacquisition on a diseased plant. Thus we recommend that the leafhopper-borne viruses be categorized as transitory and persistent rather than as nonpersistent, semi-persistent, and persistent. Rice tungro would then be designated as a transitory leafhopper-transmitted virus, and its virus-vector interaction would be categorized as transitory instead of nonpersistent.

Activity and infectivity. The infectivity of tungro-viruliferous *N. virescens* decreases gradually with time after acquisition feeding. The reason for the decrease is not clear, although experiments have indicated that feeding the viruliferous insects on chemical solutions can reduce their infectivity (1967 and 1970 annual reports), and that keeping the viruliferous insects at 7°C can reduce the loss of infectivity (1974 Annual Report).

The green leafhopper seemed to be less active at low temperature, leading us to suspect that infectivity loss might be related to the insects’ activity. Although activity is difficult to define, it should be related to the motion of the insect. Therefore, we confined tungro-viruliferous insects in a cage and artificially induced them to move once every 3 minutes to increase their activity. By seedling infection, we determined that these insects’ infectivity was lower than that of insects that were confined in screen cages or on healthy plants, particularly at longer durations of treatment (Table 8). Hence, the insects’ infectivity lessens faster when the insects are more active.

Both starvation and induced movement

caused a high mortality of the tungro-viruliferous *N. virescens*. About 16 percent of the insects died due to starvation and 42 percent

due to starvation and induced movement. No insect confined on healthy plants died during the 4-hour test period.

Control and management of rice pests

Insects

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SUMMARY

We screened new insecticides in the laboratory, greenhouse, and field during 1975. Several recently developed synthetic pyrethrins or "pyrethroids," which have low levels of mammalian toxicity, when applied as foliar sprays effectively controlled both the green leafhopper and the brown planthopper. Several new systemic compounds effectively controlled both insects when sprayed, broadcast in the paddy water, or applied to the root zone.

IRRI engineers designed machines to inject insecticide into the root zone of rice plants. A gravity-fed liquid injector was most efficient and easiest to operate. Carbofuran applied with the injector once at transplanting provided excellent control of the whorl maggot and season-long control of the green leafhopper.

Gelatin provided longer residual activity than previously tested stickers in a root-coat treatment with carbofuran.

In biological control studies, a predaceous spider killed more nymphs of brown planthoppers than of green leafhoppers, and preyed on first-instar larvae of the yellow rice borer. Parasitoids killed about half of the yellow borer eggs. Weekly spraying of the insecticide metal-kamate (Bux) did not affect the percentage of parasitism of stem borer eggs in the field.

Whorl maggot damage decreased yields by from 12 to 26 percent in crops planted at 25- × 25-cm spacing at two Philippine locations. Simulated stem borer damage in the field indicated that about 10 percent dead hearts in a 40-day-old crop is the economic threshold for the Philippines.

One rice bug caged on 35 panicles from flowering to harvest reduced grain weight by 14 percent in a greenhouse study. The economic threshold may be less than four rice bugs per square meter for a good crop in the Philippines.

One distinct generation of the yellow rice borer was found early in the crop period, with a peak in eggs at 3-14 days after transplanting. Egg mortality, primarily due to parasitism, was always high. The striped rice borer had one major generation during the latter half of the crop period, with a peak in egg density at about 60 days after transplanting.

Female sex pheromones of the striped rice borer and of the pink borer were identified and synthesized by collaborators at the Tropical Products Institute, London. In IRRI field tests, the striped rice borer pheromones, at a concentration of 100 µg/vial often attracted more wild male moths than did live virgin females, and remained attractive for more than 1 month.

INSECTICIDES

Entomology Department

New insecticides and insecticidal combinations are first screened in the laboratory and greenhouse to determine their effectiveness against the green leafhopper *Nephotettix virescens* and the brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens*. Their insecticidal activities are determined by applying each as a contact spray, a foliar spray, a broadcast treatment, and a root-zone treatment. Compounds that effectively control insects in these tests are further evaluated under field conditions as the following treatments: foliar spray, broadcast, root zone, root soak, and root coat.

Because of its ability to transmit tungro virus, the green leafhopper is considered a particularly serious pest. Most of the compounds tested for contact toxicity provided 80 percent or better control of the green leafhopper at 48 hours after treatment (Table 1). Carbofuran and FMC 31768 provided a rapid knockdown effect. Permethrin is a recently developed synthetic pyrethrin or "pyrethroid" which appeared to be extremely effective against the green leafhopper. Due to light sensitivity, pyrethrins have not been used much in agriculture, but light-stable pyrethrins have now been developed. They are particularly attractive because of their low mammalian toxicity but their acceptance in rice culture may be hampered by their high toxicity to fish.

The brown planthopper, which is one of the most serious pests in Asia, is generally less susceptible to insecticides than the green leafhopper. The knockdown effect of FMC 31768 was excellent at 1 hour after treatment (Table 2). Permethrin, carbofuran, MIPC, FMC 27289, and FMC 35023 provided satisfactory control at 48 hours. Most of the chemicals tested,

Table 1. Contact toxicity of 0.04% insecticidal sprays on adult green leafhoppers treated in a Potter's spray tower at 1 and 48 hours after treatment. Variety, Taichung Native 1. IRRI greenhouse, 1975.

Insecticide	Formulation ^a	Mortality ^b (%)	
		1 h	48 h
FMC 31768	24 EC	100 a	100 a
Carbofuran	41 F	100 a	100 a
FMC 27289	24 EC	87 b	100 a
FMC 35023	24 EC	83 b	100 a
Permethrin	25 EC	77 b	100 a
MIPC	50 WP	39 c	100 a
FMC 35001	24 EC	20 cd	100 a
Monocrotophos + mevinphos ^c	25 EC	28 c	96 ab
Monocrotophos ^c	17 EC	1 e	100 a
WC 2127	40 EC	8 de	76 d
RH 218	60 EC	1 e	90 c
Vamidothion	40 EC	1 e	90 c
Chlorpyrifos + trichlorfon	30 EC	2 e	69 d
Hosdon	30 EC	0 e	45 e
WC 2138/3	40 EC	1 e	36 e

^aEC = emulsifiable concentrate; F = flowable; WP = wettable powder. ^bAv. of 4 replications each consisting of 25 insects treated and caged on a plant. In a column, any two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^cApplied at 0.05%.

however, did not adequately control the brown planthopper.

Foliar sprays. Even though foliar sprays are not extremely effective, especially during the rainy season, they are still one of the most common methods of insecticide application in rice. We are continuing laboratory and field evaluation of new compounds to determine their

effectiveness as foliar sprays in the control of rice pests. When applied as foliar spray on potted plants, all but one insecticide, including the pyrethroids NRDC 167, Permethrin, S 3206, JF 5474, and RU 22950, adequately controlled the green leafhopper (Table 3).

Brown planthopper control was again generally poorer than green leafhopper control. But

Table 2. Contact toxicity of 0.04% insecticidal sprays on adult brown planthoppers treated in a Potter's spray tower at 1 and 48 hours after treatment. Variety, Taichung Native 1. IRRI greenhouse, 1975.

Insecticide	Formulation ^a	Mortality ^b (%)	
		1 h	48 h
FMC 31768	24 EC	100 a	100 a
Carbofuran	41 F	87 b	100 a
Permethrin	25 EC	50 c	86 b
MIPC	50 WP	32 d	83 bc
FMC 27289	24 EC	19 def	87 b
FMC 35023	24 EC	17 def	82 bc
WC 2127	40 EC	16 def	59 ef
WC 2138/3	40 EC	12 efg	58 ef
Monocrotophos + mevinphos ^c	25 EC	11 fgh	79 bcd
FMC 35001	24 EC	9 fghi	74 bcde
RU 22950	2 EC	4 ghij	37 fg
Chlorpyrifos + trichlorfon	30 EC	4 ghij	64 def
Vamidothion	40 EC	3 hij	63 def
Monocrotophos ^c	17 EC	0 j	83 bc
Phenthoate	50 EC	1 ij	79 bcd
RH 218	60 EC	1 ij	55 f
Quinalphos	25 EC	0 j	34 fg
EPN	45 EC	0 j	65 def
Ofunack	40 EC	1 ij	40 f
Endosulfan + dimethoate	38 EC	1 ij	35 fg
RU 19053-8-408	50 WP	1 ij	34 fg
Ofunack + MTMC	40 WP	1 ij	22 g
Mecarbam	25 EC	0 j	22 g
Hosdon	30 EC	1 ij	22 g

^aEC = emulsifiable concentrate; F = flowable; WP = wettable powder; ^bAv. of 4 replications each consisting of 25 insects treated and caged on a plant. In a column, any two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^cApplied at 0.05%.

Table 3. Knockdown effect of insecticides applied as 0.04% foliar sprays at rate of 12.5 ml solution/plant on potted plants of Taichung Native 1. IRRI greenhouse, 1975.

Insecticide	Formulation ^a	Mortality ^b (%)	
		Green leafhoppers	Brown planthoppers
NRDC 167 ^c	5 EC	100	100
Carbofuran	41 F	100	100
Permethrin	25 EC	100	100
Monocrotophos + mevinphos	25 EC	100	100
Quinalphos	25 EC	100	100
Phenthoate	50 EC	100	100
Endosulfan + dimethoate	39 EC	100	100
S 3206	20 EC	100	100
Monocrotophos	17 EC	100	100
Vamidothion	40 EC	100	100
Chlorpyrifos + trichlorfon	30 EC	100	100
Mecarbam	25 EC	100	94
Ofunack	40 EC	100	85
Ofunack + MTMC	40 WP	100	73
RH 218	60 EC	100	71
EPN	45 EC	100	55
RU 22950 ^c	3 EC	100	49
Hosdon	30 EC	97	21
RU 19053-8-408	50 WP	95	6
WC 2138/3	40 EC	90	37
WC 2127	40 EC	60	42

^aEC = emulsifiable concentrate; F = flowable; WP = wettable powder. ^bInsects caged on plants 1 h after spraying; mortality based on counts taken 48 h later. Four replications each consisting of 10 insects. ^cApplied as 0.004% spray.

Table 4. Mortality of adult rice bugs *Leptocorisa* sp. collected in the field and caged on rice plants that had been treated 1 hour and 7 days previously with 0.06 % foliar sprays of selected insecticides. Mortality ratings were taken at 24 and 48 hours after caging insects on the treated plants. IRRI greenhouse, 1975.

Insecticide	Formulation ^a	Mortality ^b (%)	
		1 h after treatment	7 days after treatment
Monocrotophos	17 EC	100 a	98 a
Carbofuran	41 F	100 a	93 ab
Phenthoate	50 EC	100 a	48 bc
Methyl parathion	50 EC	97 a	55 bc
Mecarbam	25 EC	84 b	38 c
Mipcin	50 WP	59 c	45 bc
Carbaryl	85 WP	51 c	19 c

^aEC = emulsifiable concentrate; F = flowable; WP = wettable powder. ^bAv. of 4 replications, each consisting of 10 insects caged on a plant. Mortality counts made 48 h after treatment. In a column, any two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

NRDC 167 applied at a low rate of 0.004 percent provided excellent control of both species.

Rice bugs are a common problem across the rice-growing world. Their attacks can be subtle but devastating. The only means of chemical control is by foliar spray.

Insects were collected in the field and placed on plants at 1 hour and at 7 days after treatment with 0.06 percent foliar spray of various insecticides (Table 4). Most provided a rapid knockdown of the rice bug. Residual activity, determined by placing rice bugs on treated

plants at 7 days after treatment, was satisfactory only in the monocrotophos and carbofuran treatments. This indicates that commonly used insecticides such as methyl parathion must be applied frequently for satisfactory protection because their residual activity in the field is probably lower than in the greenhouse.

In a dry-season field experiment, we determined the effectiveness of various insecticides applied as 0.05 percent spray at 15-day intervals in the control of stem borers and of green leafhoppers as virus vectors (Table 5). Monocrotophos was effective against stem borers.

Table 5. Effects of foliar sprays of selected insecticides applied at 0.05% for the control of stem borers and green leafhoppers as virus vectors. Variety, Taichung Native 1. IRRI, 1975 dry season.

Insecticide ^a	Dead hearts ^b (%)		Virus ^b (%)	
	34 DT	45 DT	34 DT	45 DT
Rangado	0.6 ab	1.7 cde	10 a	42 abc
Padan + MIPC	0.4 b	1.5 de	10 a	50 ab
Quinalphos	1.1 ab	1.6 cde	8 a	28 bcd
PPDB 11	0.6 ab	2.9 bcd	9 a	40 bc
Mecarbam	1.1 ab	4.8 b	9 a	23 cd
Ofunack	0.7 ab	1.4 de	7 a	29 bcd
Monocrotophos	0.6 ab	0.5 e	5 a	16 d
Phenthoate	0.8 ab	3.4 bc	10 a	41 bc
EPN	0.3 b	1.1 e	9 a	39 bc
Control	1.5 a	7.4 a	8 a	65 a

^aFive applications at 15-day intervals beginning 5 days after transplanting (DT). ^b34 DT = 14 days after second application; 45 DT = 10 days after third application. In a column, any two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Plants treated with it had the least amount of virus attack, but no insecticide adequately controlled the vectors.

Paddy water application. The broadcasting of insecticides into paddy water is becoming more popular because of the ease and effectiveness of application. But only a limited number of suitable insecticides are commercially available. We screen compounds in the laboratory and

field to identify new ones that are effective for broadcast application.

We applied insecticides at the rate of 1 kg/ha to the water of potted plants to determine initial and residual control of the green leafhopper and brown planthopper. Insect mortality was determined at from 1 to 29 days later (Table 6). The mortality of the green leafhopper was generally higher than that of the brown planthopper. Carbofuran 5 G and 10 G and FMC 27289 controlled green leafhoppers at 29 days after treatment, but adequately controlled brown planthoppers for only 15 days. Although chlordimeform was previously found to effectively control the brown planthopper at 2 kg/ha in the field as a root-zone treatment and as a paddy water application (1973 and 1974 annual reports), it was not effective in 1974 and 1975 greenhouse experiments.

We field-evaluated insecticides by applying them four times at 20-day intervals to paddy water at the rate of 2 kg/ha (Table 7). Carbofuran most effectively controlled whorl maggots and virus vectors and produced the highest yield. Several compounds appeared promising for stem borer control.

Table 6. Control of the green leafhopper and brown planthopper by paddy water application of insecticides at the rate of 1 kg a.i./ha. Ratings taken at from 1 to 29 days after treatment. Variety, Taichung Native 1. IRRI greenhouse, 1975.

Insecticide	Formulation ^a	Mortality ^b (%)					
		Green leafhoppers			Brown planthoppers		
		1 day	15 days	29 days	1 day	15 days	29 days
Carbofuran	5 G	100 a	100 a	100 a	100 a	88 ab	17 ab
Carbofuran	10 G	100 a	100 a	100 a	100 a	95 a	11 ab
FMC 27289	5 G	100 a	100 a	91 a	89 a	81 b	12 ab
FMC 35001	5 G	100 a	96 ab	39 b	96 a	35 c	29 a
FMC 35023	5 G	100 a	84 b	16 bc	96 a	35 c	17 ab
Carbofuran	3 G	100 a	52 c	32 b	91 a	16 cd	2 b
FMC 31768	5 G	100 a	100 a	36 b	100 a	33 c	17 ab
JF 5599	5 G	51 bcd	7 de	0 d	25 bcde	5 bc	14 ab
JF 5600	5 G	36 bcde	24 d	0 d	25 bcde	4 d	9 ab
Padan + MIPC	50 WP	71 ab	2 de	2 cd	52 b	12 cd	17 ab
SAN 155	90 SP	40 bcde	11 de	8 bcd	43 bc	14 cd	7 ab
Chlordimeform + carbaryl	9 G	58 bc	11 de	5 bcd	41 bcd	12 cd	21 ab
RH 812	9 G	20 cde	2 e	0 d	7 e	9 cd	2 b
Hosdon	4 G	40 bcde	0 e	0 d	29 bcde	0 d	17 ab
Monocrotophos	5 G	16 cdef	5 e	0 d	18 cde	5 d	7 ab
Padan	4 G	16 cdef	0 e	0 d	11 de	2 d	7 ab
Ofunack + lindane	10 G	9 def	2 e	1 cd	36 bcd	0 d	7 ab
RU 19053	5 G	4 ef	5 de	0 d	16 cde	2 d	12 ab
Chlordimeform	5 G	0 f	2 e	—	23 bcde	2 d	—

^aG = granules; WP = wettable powder; SP = soluble powder. Carbofuran 5 G and 10 G are formulated in the U.S., 3 G in the Philippines. ^bMortality based on av. of 3 replications. In a column, any two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. Observations taken at 48 h after caging insects on plants.

Table 7. Field evaluation of insecticides applied to paddy water at 20-day intervals for the control of rice insects.^a Variety, IR22. IRRI, 1975 dry season.

Insecticide ^b (2 kg a.i./ha)	Whorl maggot damage ^c	Dead hearts (%)	Virus (%)		Yield (t/ha)
	28 DT	40 DT	57 DT	87 DT	
Carbofuran	0.5 a	0.0 a	0.2 a	0.2 a	5.3 a
AC 92100	1.8 b	0.2 abcd	0.5 a	2.2 abc	4.5 b
SAN 201	1.8 b	0.1 ab	1.3 ab	1.7 abc	4.3 b
AC 64475 ^d	1.8 b	0.3 ab	2.0 abc	1.6 abc	4.5 b
JF 4089	2.1 bc	0.6 bcd	3.8 bcd	5.3 cd	4.7 b
Imidan + Dyfonate	2.2 bcd	0.2 abcd	2.0 abc	2.5 bc	4.3 b
Monocrotophos	2.3 bcd	1.4 de	1.7 abc	1.4 abc	4.3 b
Acephate	2.5 bcde	2.0 ef	4.8 cd	5.0 cd	4.1 b
Bux	2.7 cde	2.1 ef	2.5 abc	1.9 abc	4.1 b
RH 812	2.9 de	0.2 abcd	3.4 bcd	4.7 cd	4.6 b
PFL 812	5.3 e	0.6 abc	0.1 a	0.8 ab	4.4 b
Thiocarb	5.4 e	0.1 ab	0.5 a	1.1 ab	4.7 b
SAN 155	3.9 f	0.5 abcd	4.8 cd	7.4 d	4.2 b
Cartap + MIPC	7.2 f	0.8 cde	1.3 abc	1.7 abc	4.9 b
Control	7.6 f	4.0 f	6.6 d	15.8 e	3.5 c

^aIn a column, any two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^bAll applications made 5, 25, 45, and 65 days after transplanting (DT). ^cRated on scale of 0–5: 0 = no damage; 5 = most severely damaged. ^dApplied at 1 kg/ha since it is phytotoxic at 2 kg.

Table 8. Effects on green leafhopper control of soaking rice seedlings in a carbofuran solution for varying durations. Insect mortality was rated from 15 to 40 days after treatment. Variety, IR22. IRRI greenhouse, 1975.

Soaking duration (h)	Uptake (kg a.i./ha)	Mortality ^a (%)				
		15 days	20 days	25 days	30 days	40 days
8 (day only)	0.26	98 a	78 a	28 a	25 a	1 a
12 (night)	0.16	98 a	94 b	74 b	37 a	11 b
24 (night + day)	0.49	100 a	99 b	79 b	61 b	6 ab
48 (2 nights + 2 days)	0.89	100 a	100 b	87 b	85 c	22 c

^aMortality values in 24 h adjusted using Abbott's formula and are averages of 10 replications with 10 insects/replication. In a column, any two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Root-soak treatment. Foliar sprays do not effectively control the virus vectors (Table 5). Since green leafhoppers often attack shortly after transplanting, the seedling-soak method has been used as an inexpensive treatment for early protection. In previous tests, the effectiveness of the seedling-soak method varied with the concentration of the insecticide solution (1973 Annual Report). Research was conducted at IRRI in 1975 to determine the relationship among duration of soaking, uptake, and residual activity (Table 8).

Carbofuran uptake generally increased as duration of root-soak period was lengthened. For the 48-hour soak treatment, absorption of the solution was highest and residual activity was longest (up to 30 days' control of the green leafhopper). The 12-hour soak required less insecticide and provided more effective control

than the 8-hour soak; it appears effective and inexpensive for green leafhopper control for at least 25 days under greenhouse conditions.

Equipment for root-zone application. We continued intensive root-zone studies in 1975. Previous research has indicated that the root-zone method of insecticide application is extremely efficient (1972, 1973, and 1974 annual reports). But the lack of application equipment hinders its use. In 1975, IRRI entomologists field-tested the effectiveness of several application machines designed by IRRI engineers, including a slurry-band, a water-band, and a granular-band applicator. Using carbofuran, we found that insect control was excellent and equal with all applicators tested (Table 9). One root-zone application at 5 days after transplanting provided insect control and yield equal to that of four broadcast applications, each at

Table 9. Effects on rice insects of method and time of root-zone and broadcast application of carbofuran.^a Variety, Taichung Native 1. IRRI, 1975 dry season.

Treatment ^b	Time (DT)	Whorl maggot damage ^c	Dead hearts (%)	Virus (%)		Yield (t/ha)
		28 DT	40 DT	40 DT	87 DT	
<i>Root-zone application</i>						
Slurry-band injection	5	0.3 a	0.1 a	0.3 ab	0.5 a	5.0 ab
Water-band injection	5	0.4 a	0.0 a	0.0 a	0.5 a	5.2 a
Granular-band injection	5	0.7 b	0.2 a	0.3 ab	1.6 a	4.9 ab
Slurry-band injection	30	4.6 d	3.6 b	3.6 bc	14.8 b	4.0 b
Water-band injection	30	4.7 d	4.4 bc	2.7 abc	15.3 b	4.4 ab
<i>Broadcast</i>						
0.5 kg a.i./ha every 20 days		2.1 c	2.3 b	0.8 ab	1.6 a	5.1 a
2.0 kg a.i./ha every 20 days		0.5 ab	0.2 a	0.2 ab	0.3 a	5.0 ab
Control		4.8 d	7.1 c	8.5 c	90.6 c	1.2 c

^aIn a column, any two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^bWettable powder (75%) used. Root-zone treatment applied once at 2 kg a.i./ha. Paddy water treatments applied 4 times at 20-day intervals as 3% granules beginning at 2 days after transplanting (DT). ^cRated on a scale of 0–5: 0 = no damage; 5 = most severely damaged.

0.5 or 2.0 kg/ha. If applications were delayed to 30 days after transplanting, however, insect damage was significantly higher.

The granular applicator appeared best adapted for farmer use.

Field screening of root-zone insecticides. Four insecticides were tested as one root-zone application at 2 kg/ha and as four broadcast applications at 2 kg/ha every 20 days (Table 10). Only carbofuran provided whorl maggot control and season-long protection against virus vectors equal to that of the four broadcast applications. Only carbofuran and cartap + MIPC treatments had less white heads than the control. SAN 201 controlled whorl maggots more

effectively as a broadcast than as a root-zone application.

Using the granular applicator, we tested additional insecticides along with granular urea fertilizer as root-zone applications. Insect control and yield again equalled that of four broadcast applications. Of the insecticides tested, none equalled carbofuran in the control of whorl maggots and of virus vectors, and in grain yield (Table 11).

Acephate as a root-zone application provided moderate control of green leafhoppers, but not of stem borers. So we mixed acephate with either cartap or chlordimeform to control both insects. Both mixtures controlled the stem borer (Table

Table 10. Evaluation of insecticides^a applied once in combination with urea fertilizer as a root-zone treatment with a granular applicator and four times at 20-day intervals as a broadcast treatment for the control of rice insects. Variety, Taichung Native 1. IRRI, 1975 dry season.

Insecticide	Whorl maggot damage ^b	White heads (%)	Virus (%)			Yield (t/ha)
	21 DT	90 DT	33 DT	55 DT	90 DT	
<i>Root zone^c</i>						
SAN 201	4.8 a	6 a	4 a	54 a	82 ab	1.1 cd
Carbofuran	1.3 b	1 a	0 a	0 d	1 e	4.9 a
Cartap + MIPC	4.4 a	3 a	0 a	6 cd	26 d	3.2 b
Monocrotophos	4.7 a	4 a	3 a	63 a	78 ab	1.1 cd
Untreated control	5.0 a	8 a	7 a	67 a	95 a	0.7 d
<i>Broadcast^d</i>						
SAN 201	1.5 b	7 b	4 a	46 a	74 abc	1.3 cd
Carbofuran	1.2 b	0 c	0 a	1 d	0 e	4.0 ab
Cartap + MIPC	5.0 a	2 bc	0 a	11 cd	46 cd	2.0 c
Monocrotophos	4.5 a	4 abc	1 a	15 bc	50 bcd	2.0 c
Untreated control	5.0 a	8 a	1 a	39 ab	84 a	1.0 cd

^aIn a column, any two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^bRated on scale of 0–5: 0 = no damage; 5 = most severely damaged. DT = days after transplanting. ^cApplied once at 3 DT at the rate of 2 kg a.i./ha in combination with 60 kg N/ha. ^dApplied at 2 kg a.i./ha 4 times at 20-day intervals with first application at 3 DT.

Table 11. Control of rice insects^a by placing insecticides and nitrogen fertilizer into the root zone with a granular applicator. Variety, Taichung Native 1. IRRI, 1975 dry season.

Insecticide	Whorl maggot damage ^b	Virus ^c (%)		Dead hearts ^c (%)		White heads ^c (%)		Yield (t/ha)
		37 DT	87 DT	59 DT	87 DT			
<i>Root zone application^d</i>								
Carbaryl + chlordimeform	3.7 b	3 a	22 b	4 a	1 a	3.0 b		
Carbofuran	0.6 c	1 a	0 c	0 b	1 a	6.0 a		
RH 812	3.4 b	8 a	69 a	6 a	2 a	1.3 c		
Thiocarb	4.6 a	8 a	26 b	5 a	2 a	3.0 b		
AC 92100	4.8 a	10 a	64 a	7 a	2 a	1.1 c		
Acephate	4.7 a	8 a	77 a	7 a	4 a	1.0 c		
PFL 812	4.8 a	9 a	34 b	5 a	2 a	2.0 b		
Bux	4.7 a	6 a	81 a	3 a	5 a	1.1 c		
<i>Broadcast 4 times^e</i>								
Carbofuran	0.2 c	1 a	2 c	1 b	0 a	6.0 a		
Untreated control	4.5 a	11 a	88 a	6 a	3 a	1.0 c		

^aIn a column, any two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^bRated at 25 days after treatment on a scale of 0–5: 0 = no damage; 5 = most severely damaged. ^cDT = days after transplanting. ^dInsecticides at the rate of 2.0 kg a.i./ha combined with 60 kg N/ha were applied at 3 DT. ^eCarbofuran was broadcast 4 times at 20-day intervals beginning at 3 DT.

Table 12. Insect control^a through root-zone application of acephate combinations, along with urea fertilizer, using a granular applicator. Variety, Taichung Native 1. IRRI, 1975 dry season.

Insecticide ^b	Whorl maggot damage ^c	Dead hearts ^d (%)		Virus ^d (%)	
		35 DT	56 DT	35 DT	56 DT
Acephate	2.6 b	6 a	17 a	7 abc	34 b
Carbofuran	0.3 c	0 c	1 c	0 c	0 c
Acephate + cartap	2.1 b	2 b	6 b	5 bc	20 b
Acephate + chlordimeform	2.2 b	0 c	0 c	15 ab	25 b
Control	3.6 a	5 ab	12 a	20 a	73 a

^aIn a column, any two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^bInsecticides at the rate of 2.0 kg a.i./ha combined with 60 kg N/ha were applied at 3 days after transplanting. ^cRated at 21 days after treatment on a scale of 0–5: 0 = no damage; 5 = most severely damaged. ^dDT = days after transplanting.

12), but no treatment gave a high level of green leafhopper control (indicated by percent of virus attack) or of whorl maggot control.

Root-zone application of insecticide + fertilizer. We conducted additional research with direct-seeded and transplanted rice to determine if the method of fertilizer placement—incorporated with soil or by root-zone application—affects the uptake of carbofuran. Results in the direct-seeded and transplanted experiments, indicated by degree of insect control, were similar. In the transplanted IR22 (Table 13), we found no apparent relationship between degree of insect control and method of nitrogen fertilizer application. Whorl maggot damage in plots where nitrogen had been applied to the root zone was similar to that in plots where nitrogen was incorporated into the soil. Recovery from whorl maggot damage, however,

was higher in treatments that received nitrogen than in those that received no fertilizer.

Root-zone application on insect-resistant varieties. Carbofuran at the rate of 1 kg/ha was applied as a root-zone and as a broadcast treatment to four varieties that are resistant to the green leafhopper, IR28, IR30, IR32, and IR34, and to the susceptible variety, Taichung Native 1 (TN1) (Table 14). All varieties are susceptible to whorl maggots.

The broadcast treatment acted fastest, controlling the whorl maggot at 10 days after treatment. At 30 days, however, the root-zone treatment provided better control. Whorl maggot control is delayed in the root-zone treatment because the granular applicator places the insecticide between two rows 12 cm from the plants, and uptake is minimal until the roots grow long enough to reach the insecticide.

Table 13. Control of rice pests^a using carbofuran and nitrogen fertilizer applied to the root zone of transplanted IR22 18 to 100 days after treatment. IRRI, 1975 wet season.

Insecticide ^b (kg carbofuran/ha)	Fertilizer ^c (kg N/ha)	Whorl maggot damage ^d			Green leafhoppers (no./10 sweeps)		Virus (%)	Yield (t/ha)
		18 days	28 days	38 days	51 days			
					Adults	Nymphs	100 days	
2	60 RZ	2.5 a	1.0 a	0.0 a	1 a	0 a	1 a	4.1 a
2	0 RZ	3.5 a	3.0 b	2.5 bc	3 a	0 a	4 ab	3.0 c
1	60 RZ	5.0 b	3.5 b	1.5 ab	2 a	0 a	5 ab	4.0 a
1	0 RZ	6.0 bc	5.5 cd	4.0 c	3 a	0 a	6 b	3.0 bc
1	60 SI	7.0 c	6.5 d	4.0 c	3 a	0 a	16 c	3.2 b
2	60 SI	5.0 b	4.0 bc	1.5 ab	3 a	0 a	9 bc	4.0 a
2 ^e	60 SI	2.5 a	3.5 b	0.8 a	1 a	0 a	4 ab	4.4 a
0	60 SI	9.0 d	9.0 e	9.0 d	117 b	47 c	95 d	0.1 d
0	0	9.0 d	9.0 e	9.0 d	111 b	26 b	95 d	0.1 d

^aIn a column, any two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^bAll insecticides applied in root zone unless otherwise indicated. ^cRZ = root zone; SI = soil incorporation. ^dRated on a scale of 0–9: 0 = no damage; 9 = most severely damaged. ^eInsecticide applied as a broadcast treatment every 20 days.

Table 14. Effects of method of insecticide application in combination with root-zone application of fertilizer at 46 kg N/ha on the performances of a susceptible variety and four resistant IRRI varieties 10 to 40 days after treatment.^a IRRI, 1975 wet season.

Method of application ^b (1 kg carbofuran/ha)	Whorl maggot incidence ^c			Dead hearts (%)	Green leafhopper adults/10 sweeps	Virus incidence (%)	Yield (t/ha)
	10 days	20 days	30 days	30 days	40 days	30 days	
<i>Taichung Native 1</i>							
Root-zone	7.0 bc	6.3 b	4.3 a	0.1 a	0.3 a	2.9 c	3.1 bcd
Broadcast	1.7 a	5.7 b	7.0 c	0.7 b	1.3 ab	1.3 b	2.6 b
No insecticide	9.0 d	9.0 c	9.0 d	2.1 c	15.3 c	76.9 d	0.0 a
<i>Resistant varieties^d</i>							
Root-zone	5.8 b	6.3 b	5.3 ab	0.1 a	0.3 a	0.1 a	3.2 cd
Broadcast	1.0 a	3.5 a	5.7 b	0.1 a	0.3 a	0.1 a	3.3 d
No insecticide	7.5 c	8.8 c	9.0 d	0.9 b	1.4 b	0.2 a	3.0 c

^aIn a column, any two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^bAll treatments applied once at 3 days after transplanting. Root-zone treatments applied with a granular applicator. In the no-insecticide control treatments, only fertilizer was applied to root zone. Rated on a scale of 0–9: 0 = no damage; 9 = most severely damaged. ^cResistant varieties tested were IR28, IR30, IR32, and IR34. Data represent averages of these 4 varieties.

Green leafhopper number and virus incidence were high only in plots of TN1; root-zone and broadcast treatments provided equal control. One broadcast application does not usually provide season-long leafhopper control. In this experiment, however, leafhopper populations decreased to low levels after 40 days. As the yield data indicate, insecticidal treatments are not necessary for the green leafhopper on resistant varieties when no other pests were abundant. Whorl maggot control was poor, so we could not determine the insects' effect on yields.

We obtained similar results in an experiment to determine the rates of carbofuran necessary to control pests on the green leafhopper-resistant varieties IR20 and IR26 and on the susceptible TN1 (Table 15). Incidence of tungro

Table 15. Insect control^a using three rates of carbofuran applied with 60 kg N/ha into the root zone at 3 days after transplanting with a granular applicator. IRRI, 1975 dry season.

Carbofuran (kg/ha)	Dead hearts ^b (%)		Virus ^b (%)		Yield (t/ha)
	45 DT	59 DT	59 DT	87 DT	
<i>Taichung Native 1</i>					
0.5	3.8 c	4.6 b	2.9 b	3.5 b	4.1 b
1.0	1.2 b	2.0 a	1.2 ab	1.9 b	4.7 a
1.5	0.7 ab	0.9 a	1.0 ab	1.7 b	4.5 a
0.0	3.5 c	4.0 b	87.9 c	89.0 c	0.6 c
<i>IR20</i>					
0.5	0.3 a	0.8 a	1.2 ab	1.3 a	5.1 a
1.0	0.5 a	0.7 a	0.5 a	0.4 a	5.0 a
1.5	0.1 a	0.4 a	1.2 ab	1.3 a	5.1 a
0.0	0.8 a	0.7 a	3.3 b	7.1 b	4.3 b
<i>IR26</i>					
0.5	0.6 ab	1.0 a	0.2 a	0.2 a	5.4 b
1.0	0.5 ab	0.7 a	1.0 ab	0.4 a	5.5 ab
1.5	0.2 a	0.5 a	1.0 a	0.0 a	5.5 ab
0.0	1.0 b	1.4 a	2.7 b	0.2 a	5.5 ab

^aIn a column, any two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^bDT = days after transplanting.

Table 16. Comparison of single application of carbofuran as a broadcast, root-zone liquid injection, and gel root-coat treatment with four foliar sprays of monocrotophos for rice pest control^a 20 to 76 days after treatment. IRRI, wet season, 1975.

Treatment ^b	Rate (kg a.i./ha)	Green leafhoppers/10 sweeps ^d										Yield (t/ha)	
		Whorl maggot ^c damage					Virus (%)		30 days		50 days		
		20 days	30 days	42 days	61 days	33 days	76 days	Adults	Nymphs	Adults	Nymphs		
Carbofuran (broadcast)	1.00	7.3	6.3	3	2	8	78	4.3	8.8	12.3	14.0	1.1	
Carbofuran (RZ—liquid)	1.00	2.3	0.3	0	0	0	1	0.0	0.3	1.0	0.0	3.1	
Carbofuran (root coat)	2.00	0.5	0.5	3	4	0	0	0.5	0.3	1.5	0.0	2.7	
Monocrotophos (foliar)	0.75	6.5	4.3	1	1	10	28	1.8	3.3	1.5	4.8	2.2	
Control		8.5	8.5	3	3	12	93	4.5	9.3	25.5	20.5	0.7	

^aIn a column, any two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^bCarbofuran treatments were applied only once. Monocrotophos was applied every 20 days at 750 g/ha. ^cRated on a scale of 0–9; 0 = no damage; 9 = most severely damaged. ^dGreen leafhoppers were sampled on monocrotophos treatment at 10 days after application.

1. Yield of IR22 rice as affected by various methods of insecticide application. Carbofuran at 1 kg a.i./ha was applied 3 days after transplanting into the root zone and as broadcast treatment. Monocrotophos was applied four times at 20-day intervals as a foliar spray at 0.75 kg a.i./ha. IRRI, 1975 wet season.

virus was extremely high in the plots of untreated TN1. Insecticidal rates of 0.5 to 1.5 kg/ha controlled the virus vectors equally well. Stem borer attack was low, but results indicate that rates greater than 0.5 kg/ha may be necessary to control the borers in susceptible varieties such as TN1. In IR20, applications of 0.5 kg/ha increased yields by almost 1 t/ha, probably at least partially due to virus control.

Liquid injector for root-zone application. We experimented in 1975 with a new hand-held liquid applicator for root-zone placement. The experimental machine operates by gravity flow and slides along the soil surface. Control of the virus vector, the green leafhopper, was more effective in the root-zone than in the broadcast and foliar-spray treatments (Table 16). Heavy rains washed foliar sprays off the plants and flooded granules out of the field. Insecticide applied in the root zone was protected and did not wash away. Because insecticide is injected much closer to the roots with the liquid applicator than with the granular applicator, uptake is faster, chemical use is more efficient, and control of the early season pests, such as whorl maggot, is more effective. The time required to treat 1 ha is a fourth of that with the granular applicator. Emulsifiable concentrates or wet-

table-powder formulations, which have higher percentages of active ingredient than granules, can be used with this machine. Such use could cut freight costs considerably for insecticide imports.

We are continuing to test this machine.

Root-coat method. Because the residual activity of the root-soak method is relatively short, we are conducting research on the root-coat procedure (1972 and 1973 annual reports). Root coating involves dipping the seedling roots into a mixture of insecticide and water that contains a sticking agent. A coat of additional insecticide sticks to the roots and is absorbed by the plant for several days after transplanting. In previous research, no sticker provided protection against virus attack at 50 days after treatment. In 1975, we field-tested gelatin (pigskin extract) as a sticker. The gel was made by mixing 5 parts gelatin and 6 parts 40.6 flowable carbofuran in 89 parts of water. Forty-three liters of the mixture will treat 1 ha at 160,000 seedlings/ha. The gel root-coat method was compared with broadcast, foliar spray, and root-zone injection with the new liquid injector.

The root-coat treatment at 2 kg/ha controlled the green leafhopper throughout the season (Table 16)—longer than the seedling-soak method. Due to leafhopper control, there was no virus incidence at 76 days after treatment compared with 93 percent in the control. Whorl maggot control was also excellent.

Insect control in direct-seeded rainfed rice. We applied several insecticide treatments to the line IR1561-228-3, which had been broadcast in puddled soil in a farmer's field.

The major pests were stem borers and rice bugs during the latter crop period; minor pests included brown planthoppers and leaf folders. Insect damage cut yields by at least 1.5 t/ha (Table 17). Insecticidal protection against stem borers and rice bugs, and possibly against brown planthoppers and leaf folders, was beneficial, suggesting that even in the absence of tungro disease and whorl maggots, this selection can benefit from relatively frequent treatment.

Insect control in upland rice. We tested several insecticidal treatments in 1975 to learn when, during a crop period protection is needed against pests of upland rice. Sites in three villages in Batangas province, in one town (Pili) in Camarines Sur province, and at IRRI were selected for the experiment.

At all sites except IRRI, seedling density increased markedly when furrows contained carbofuran (Table 18). Protection against seed pests apparently increased yield at Pili.

Insecticidal application before panicle initiation reduced leaf folder damage at all sites and reduced stem borer damage at IRRI, where white head losses were high.

At three out of four sites in Batangas and at IRRI, continuous protection significantly increased yields. These data suggest that an inexpensive insecticide treatment is needed to protect the seeds and seedlings of upland rice at least until panicle initiation.

BIOLOGICAL CONTROL OF INSECTS

Entomology Department

Predators. To measure the capacity of the predatory spider *Lycosa pseudoannulata* to kill

Table 17. Effects of insecticidal treatments on insect infestation and damage and grain yield of direct-seeded rainfed rice (selection, IR1561-228-3) at from 13 to 101 days after seedling emergence. Santa Barbara, Iloilo province, Philippines, 1975 wet season.

Treatment (days)			Effect ^a					
Carbofuran granules (2 kg a.i./ha)	Gamma-BHC granules (1.5 kg a.i./ha)	MIPC spray (0.75 kg a.i./ha)	Brown planthoppers (no./hill) 70 days	Leaf folder larvae (no./sq m) 76 days	Dead hearts (%) 66 days	White heads (%) 101 days	Rice bugs (no./sq m) 81 days	Yield (t/ha)
13, 30, 48, 58, 89	—	—	1 c	0.1 a	0 b	1.5 b	3 c	4.7 a
13, 58	—	31, 71	4 b	0.5 a	0 b	1.4 b	3 bc	4.2 b
—	58	31, 71	9 a	0.9 a	0 b	2.7 b	6 ab	3.8 c
—	—	31, 71	14 a	1.2 a	14 a	7.4 a	9 a	3.1 d

^aIn a column, any two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Table 18. Effects of insecticidal treatments on seedling density, insect damage, and grain yield of upland rice.^a Cale and San Pedro, Batangas province; Pili, Camarines Sur province; and IRRI, Philippines, 1975 wet season.

Treatment			Seedling density (no./m-row)		Leaf folder damage ^b (grade)	White heads (%)		Yield (t/ha)			
Carbofuran granules in furrow (2 kg/ha)	Monocrotophos weekly spray (0.06%)	Methyl parathion weekly spray (0.06%)			San Pedro			Cale	San Pedro	IRRI	Pili
			Cale	Pili		Cale	IRRI				
Seeding	Seeding to heading	Flowering to maturity	96 a	—	1.5 b	1.1 b	4.0 b	3.5 a	3.6 a	2.9 a	—
—	Seeding to heading	Flowering to maturity	51 b	—	2.0 b	2.9 a	4.5 b	2.4 c	3.4 a	2.3 ab	—
—	Panicle initiation to heading	Flowering to maturity	54 b	—	4.0 a	2.9 a	7.2 a	3.0 abc	3.2 ab	2.8 ab	—
—	—	Flowering to maturity	53 b	—	4.5 a	2.3 a	7.3 a	3.2 ab	2.5 b	2.5 ab	—
Seeding	—	—	—	57	—	—	—	—	—	—	1.4
Untreated control	—	—	52 b	25	4.0 a	3.0 a	7.2 a	2.7 bc	2.7 b	2.1 b	1.0

^aRice variety at Cale was Dagge; at San Pedro, Kinanda; at IRRI, C22; and at Pili, Bursiging puti. In a column, any two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^bRated on a scale of 0–9: 0 = no damage; 9 = most severely damaged. Observation made 60 days after seeding.

first-instar larvae of the yellow rice borer *Tryporyza incertulas*, we caged adult spiders with the larvae in a petri dish. For 3 consecutive days, spiders consumed almost all of the larvae offered, up to more than 100 per day. However, the spiders ate only larvae that moved.

We previously reported that *L. pseudoannulata* was a good predator of the brown planthopper (1974 Annual Report). We caged one adult spider on a potted plant with 50 planthopper nymphs (second and third instars) and daily restored the initial number of nymphs. The spider killed an average of 24 nymphs/day (a range of 13–35) for 9 days, a remarkable feeding rate. In another experiment, the spider killed an average of 17 nymphs/day (a range of 10–25) for 14 days.

In a similar experiment, one adult spider was caged with 25 or 50 second- and third-instar green leafhopper nymphs for 13 days. When 25

nymphs/day were offered, daily leafhopper mortality averaged 4 and ranged from 2 to 6; when 50 nymphs were offered, daily mortality averaged 6, and ranged from 2 to 10. As spider prey, leafhoppers apparently were not as good as planthoppers.

We tested this conclusion in another experiment, caging 25 nymphs of each prey species with the spider predator. Over 12 days, the spider killed three times as many brown planthoppers as green leafhoppers, confirming the spider's preference.

The bug *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis* is a predator not only of the eggs of the stem borer *Chilo suppressalis* (1972 Annual Report), but also of those of the yellow rice borer *Tryporyza incertulas*. Even one predatory bug confined in a petri dish with an egg mass of *Tryporyza incertulas* killed all the eggs. But we do not know the extent of egg predation by sucking

Table 19. Average percent parasitism per crop by parasitoids of eggs, larvae, and pupae of the yellow rice borer *Tryporyza incertulas* and the striped rice borer *Chilo suppressalis* collected from different rice selections. IRRI, 1974–1975.

Season	Rice selection	Parasitism (%)					
		<i>T. incertulas</i>			<i>C. suppressalis</i>		
		Eggs	Larvae	Pupae	Eggs	Larvae	Pupae
1974 wet season	IR127-80-1	62	8	0	12	1	1
1974 wet to 1975 dry season	IR1529-680-3-2	50	11	30	11	7	0
1975 dry season	IR127-80-1	43	10	63	2	1	1

insects in the field. We know, however, that chewing predators in the field affect less than 10 percent of egg masses.

Parasitoids. Parasitic insects can kill 50 percent or more of the eggs of *Tryporyza incertulas*, but larval parasitism is low (1974 Annual Report). Recent studies show that parasitism of pupae fluctuates over time, varying from 0 to 63 percent over 9 months. Parasitism at all stages of *C. suppressalis* was found to be low during the same period (Table 19).

PLANT INJURY BY INSECTS AND ECONOMIC THRESHOLDS

Entomology Department

The economic importance of insects is measured by the plant injury and yield losses that they cause. Knowing the extent and time of damage is important to maximize the efficiency of pest control.

We determined by the insecticidal check method the yield loss to an insect-susceptible selection of IR20 from direct damage by insects, primarily the rice whorl maggot, *Hydrellia philippina*, at IRRI during 1975. Losses varied from 0.4 to 1.3 t/ha, averaging 0.9 t/ha.

Rice whorl maggot. We previously found significant yield losses due to whorl maggot damage only in the greenhouse or in field experiments using wide plant spacings (1973 and 1974 annual reports). In 1975, we conducted field experiments at 25- × 25-cm spacing in cooperation with the Philippine Bureau of Plant Industry at the Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center and at the Visayas Rice

Experiment Station. We compared the yields of two treatments, one protected throughout the crop period and the other only from 33 days after transplanting until harvest. Almost all of the substantial and significant yield differences were caused by maggot injury during early crop growth (Table 20). Stem borers caused little damage.

As the infestation of whorl maggots increases in intensity, more hills and more leaves are damaged, the severity of the damage increases, and tillering may be reduced. At harvest, however, the tiller number of damaged hills may be similar to that of undamaged hills (Table 20).

We previously found that broadcasting the seed reduces whorl maggot damage (1974 Annual Report). This was confirmed in 1975, but insecticidal treatment was still required to reduce the damage to a low level (Table 21). Broadcast crops apparently grow taller than transplanted crops because of less maggot damage. But the yield gained by broadcasting in this experiment appears to have been due more to agronomic than to entomological factors.

Stem borers. The major visible plant damage caused by the feeding of stem borer larvae is dead hearts or white heads. The amount of grain lost by such damage has been estimated in previous field experiments (1963 and 1966 annual reports). But such data only imply conclusions, since other pests that reduce the yield and bias the results are always present. The range and the timing of damage are also limited.

We measured the yield losses caused by simulated dead hearts and white heads in both

Table 20. Effects of damage by the rice whorl maggot *Hydrellia philippina* on IR26 transplanted at 25- × 25- cm row spacing.^a Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center and Visayas Rice Experiment Station, Philippines, 1975 wet season.

Insecticidal treatment ^b	Leaf damage ^c 33 DT	Leaves damaged (%) 33 DT	Hills damaged (%) 33 DT	Tillers (no./hill)		Dead hearts (%) 35 DT	Yield (t/ha)	Yield loss (%)
				33 DT	77 DT			
<i>Maligaya</i>								
Continuous	0.05 b	4 b	74 b	20 a	16 a	0	5.9 a	—
After 32 DT	0.16 a	11 a	100 a	15 b	16 a	4	4.4 b	26
<i>Visayas</i>								
Continuous	0.20 b	12 b	98 a	23 a	22 a	0	6.0 a	—
After 32 DT	0.90 a	44 a	100 a	16 a	23 a	3	5.3 b	12

^aIn a column, any two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^bIn the continuously treated plots, carbofuran was applied at 2 kg a.i./ha to the seedbed 5 and 15 days after seeding and to the transplanted field 1 and 17 days after transplanting (DT). All plots in the experiment were treated with carbofuran at 2 kg a.i./ha at 33 DT and every 16 days thereafter until harvest. ^cRated on a scale of 0 to 3: 0 = no damage; 3 = severe damage.

Table 21. Effects of planting method on damage by the rice whorl maggot *Hydrellia philippina* and plant responses to the damage. ^aVariety, IR30. IIRRI, 1975 wet season.

Planting method	Insecticidal treatment ^b	Leaf damage ^c 40 DS	Plant ht (cm) 65 DS	Yield (t/ha)
Transplant (25 × 25 cm)	After 54 DS	4.9 a	65 c	4.4 c
Broadcast ^d	After 54 DS	2.7 b	75 ab	5.7 a
Transplant	Continuous	1.4 c	74 b	4.6 bc
Broadcast ^d	Continuous	0.2 d	80 a	5.4 ab

^aIn a column, any two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. In the continuously treated plots, carbofuran was applied at 2 kg a.i./ha at 0, 14, 28, 42, 56, 70, and 84 days after seeding (DS). Other plots were treated at 55, 69, and 83 DS. ^cRated on a scale of 0 to 9: 0 = no damage; 9 = severe damage. ^dSeeds were broadcast on the same date that seeds were sown in seedbed for transplanting 20 days later.

the greenhouse and the field. We simulated the damage by killing the growing points of tillers with a needle. We usually damaged mother or productive tillers since borers in the field probably first damage the bigger tillers. Typical dead hearts or white heads soon appeared. Using this technique, we were able to replicate exact percentages of damaged tillers from 7 to 10 times; unlike in actual borer damage, percentages did not increase with time.

In the greenhouse, the relationship between damage and reduction in grain weight appears to be linear (Table 22). Damage at 40 days after seeding did not reduce grain weight as much as expected because the plants could still

Table 22. Loss of grain weight caused by simulated^a stem borer damage at two plant ages. Variety, IR26. Greenhouse study, IIRRI, 1975.

Damaged tillers		Grain wt ^b (g)	Grain wt reduction (%)
(% of total)	(% of productive tillers)		
<i>Damaged at 40 days after seeding</i>			
0	0	38 a	—
10	4	34 b	10
20	8	32 c	15
30	11	32 c	15
50	21	28 d	25
<i>Damaged at 60 days after seeding</i>			
0	0	74 a	—
2	4	69 b	7
6	7	63 bc	16
10	10	55 cd	26
16	18	46 d	38
26	36	34 e	54

^aDead hearts were caused by killing the growing point of tillers with a needle. ^bMeasured for single hills 40 days after seeding and for two hills at 60 days. Any two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

produce more tillers to compensate somewhat for damaged ones. These data suggest, however, that 10 percent damaged tillers is above the economic threshold, since crop protection usually costs less than 10 percent of the crop value. But damage at 60 days after seeding is too late for compensation. If only final productive tillers are considered, then the grain reduction is even greater than indicated by the percent of damaged tillers. Apparently, tiller damage during the reproductive period reduces not only the grain that would be produced by the damaged tillers, but also the grain weight of tillers that are not directly affected, probably by decreasing the grain number or percent of grains filled. The use of an economic threshold after 60 days from seeding is probably impractical since damage is so low (possibly about 2% tillers) and counting the damaged tillers in the field would be laborious. In areas where such damage is common, prophylactic treatments are probably appropriate.

The field results (Table 23) were rather similar to greenhouse results, except that at 40 days after seeding, damage to 10 percent of all tillers decreased grain weight by only 5 percent. Since it is probably economical to protect a crop against more than 5 percent dead hearts, an economic threshold of about 10 percent dead hearts up to about 40 days after seeding appears suitable. This is somewhat higher than suggested by the greenhouse experiment, but plants can probably compensate better in the field than indoors. Slight tiller damage during the reproductive period caused considerable reduction in grain weight, demonstrating again that insecticidal treatment could be economical during this period even if damage is low.

In the greenhouse, we attempted to relate the density of larvae of yellow rice borer on plants to subsequent symptoms of plant damage and reductions in grain weight. We selected high densities, from 0.1 to 10 first-instar larvae per tiller. All treatments at 40, 60, or 80 days after seeding resulted in more than 20 percent loss of grain weight. In almost all cases, more than 15 percent of the tillers were killed. The relationship of density to damage and reduction in grain weight was clearly positive and curvilinear. Through future experiments, we hope to

Table 23. Loss of grain weight caused by simulated^a stem borer damage in the field at three plant ages. Variety, IR26. IRRI, 1975 dry season.

Damaged tillers		Grain wt ^b (g/2 hills)	Grain wt reduction (%)
(% of total)	(% of productive tillers)		
<i>Damaged at 40 days after seeding</i>			
0	0	73 a	—
5	5	70 a	5
10	11	70 a	5
15	17	58 b	21
25	31	53 b	28
50	77	48 b	34
<i>Damaged at 60 days after seeding</i>			
0	0	77 a	—
2	3	68 b	11
6	8	60 c	22
10	14	57 c	25
16	22	54 c	30
26	38	44 d	42
<i>Damaged at 80 days after seeding</i>			
0	0	78 a	—
2	3	66 b	16
6	8	63 bc	20
10	15	58 cd	26
16	22	52 d	34
26	40	41 e	48

^aDead hearts or white heads were caused by killing the growing point of tillers with a needle. ^bAny two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

develop a capability to predict yield loss based on the density of insects rather than on the damage that they have inflicted.

Rice leaf folder. The larvae of the rice leaf folder *Cnaphalocrosis medinalis* feed on the leaves of plants primarily during the reproductive and maturing periods of crop growth. For the first time, we attempted to measure the effect of this leaf damage on grain weight. We noted the percentage of damaged flag leaves shortly before harvest of a damaged field of the rice selection IR1561-228-3. At harvest, we took the grain weight of tillers with and without damaged flag leaves. Weight loss due to leaf damage was significant, about 9 percent. It could reduce yields of the entire crop by about 6 percent, since 72 percent of the flag leaves of the crop were damaged.

In the greenhouse, we infested plants at 76 and 91 days after seeding with different densities of leaf folder larvae, which damaged leaves to varying degrees. Loss in grain weight was surprisingly high in some cases, as much as 36 percent in plants infested at 91 days (Table 24). Grain weight dropped significantly when only four leaves per hill were damaged at about

Table 24. Effect of density of various instars of larvae of the rice leaf folder *Cnaphalocrosis medinalis* on leaf damage and grain weight. Rice variety, IR26. Greenhouse study, IRRI, 1975.

Larval density (tillers/larva)	Damaged leaves ^a (no./hill)	Grain wt ^b (g/hill)
<i>Infested at 76 DS</i>		
No infestation	0	22 b
10	2	23 b
4	4	28 a
1	11	15 c
<i>Infested at 91 DS</i>		
No infestation	0	30 a
10	1	27 a
4	4	22 b
1	14	19 b

^aMeasured at 105 days after seeding (DS). ^bHarvested at 118 DS. Any two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

flowering time. An economic threshold for leaf folder damage has not yet been specified, but these data suggest that it could be less than four damaged leaves per hill at flowering.

Rice bug. For 2 years, we have attempted to measure reduction of grain weight by damage from rice bugs *Leptocorisa* spp. In 1975, we eliminated experimental errors enough to show a significant reduction, 14 percent, when one adult bug was caged from flowering to harvest on 35 panicles (fig. 2). The 14-percent reduction represents an actual grain weight loss of 2.2 g/hill. The effect of lower infestation levels should be further investigated. Assuming, however, that 10 percent of the crop is worth about two to four times as much as the cost of

2. Effect of density of the adult rice bug *Leptocorisa* spp. on grain weight reduction. Bugs were caged on IR20 plants from flowering to harvest. IRRI greenhouse, 1975.

insecticidal protection, an extrapolation of the curve suggests that the economic threshold is lower than 60 panicles/bug, or lower than 4 bugs/sq m for a good crop.

In preliminary field trials, we attempted to determine a field threshold. The field infestation reached 10 bugs/sq m, but our insecticidal check, foliar spray, did not sufficiently decrease bug density to measure yield differences. Field studies, using insect cages, are needed to determine the threshold.

PEST MANAGEMENT (INTEGRATION OF CONTROL METHODS)

Entomology Department

Insecticides and predators. We previously found that sprayable insecticides differ in their contact toxicity to adults of the predatory spider *Lycosa pseudoannulata* (1974 Annual Report). In 1975, we compared the toxicity of several chemicals to spiderlings and adult spiders by placing them inside vials previously coated with an insecticidal solution. We found that spiderlings were usually more susceptible to the insecticides; adults could tolerate higher concentrations of given chemicals.

We reported earlier (1973 Annual Report) that root-zone applications of insecticide probably did not directly affect predators. But that conclusion was based on indirect evidence: if we found no predators or prey, we assumed that the predators were absent because the prey were absent, not because the predators were killed by insecticide. In a 1975 field experiment, we again found that *L. pseudoannulata* spiders as well as the prey were absent from plots where carbofuran at 2 kg/ha was broadcast every 14 days.

To determine the real influence of root-zone insecticidal treatment on spiders, we placed by hand either carbofuran or gamma-BHC + MIPC granules into the root zones of potted rice seedlings at 1 kg/ha. Next we placed *L. pseudoannulata* adults on the potted seedlings in plastic cages in the greenhouse. Spider mortality was virtually total with gamma-BHC + MIPC at 1 day, and reached 87 percent with carbofuran at 4 days. We caged brown planthopper prey with the spiders to test the indirect

effect of the insecticide, and found the same or slightly higher spider mortality. We repeated the carbofuran part of the experiment with similar results: 60–70 percent mortality in 2 days, and 90–100 percent in 3 days.

Since we did not know how the insecticide affects spiders, we conducted a similar experiment using cages with screen barriers inside to prevent the spiders from contacting either the water or the soil in the pot. Again, 50 percent of the spiders died in 2 days, and 90 percent in 4 days. The insecticide seems to kill spiders through fumigation.

We tested the toxicity of carbofuran in the field against *L. pseudoannulata* by placing plastic cages over plants in field plots and introducing one spider per cage. In plots where carbofuran was placed into the root zone at 1 kg/ha with a granular applicator, only 30 percent of the spiders died within 5 days. In plots where carbofuran had been broadcast at 1 kg/ha 6 days earlier, 8 days were required to kill 30 percent of the spiders placed in nylon screen cages.

These preliminary data suggest that broadcasting carbofuran granules into the paddy water or applying carbofuran into the root zone with an applicator does not kill a large percentage of the spiders in the field. Further field work will be conducted to confirm these findings and to assess the interaction of predators with the methods, times, and rates of application of different insecticides.

Insecticides and parasitoids. We compared the susceptibility to insecticidal toxicity of two parasitic species, *Telenomus* sp. and *Tetrastichus* sp. Egg masses of the stem borer *Tryporyza incertulas* were dipped in insecticidal solutions, dried, and placed in vials with adult parasites of one of the species. In the control, both species parasitized the eggs to the same degree. However, for egg masses treated with any of several insecticides tested, *Telenomus* sp. parasitized fewer eggs than *Tetrastichus* sp., suggesting that *Telenomus* sp. was more susceptible to insecticidal toxicity. The percentage parasitism of eggs of *T. incertulas* and *Chilo suppressalis* in the field was not affected when the plants were subjected to weekly spraying with the insecticide metalkamate (Bux).

ECOLOGY AND BEHAVIOR OF RICE
INSECTS

Entomology Department

Rice whorl maggot. Leaf feeding by the rice whorl maggot *Hydrellia philippina* damages young plants more than old plants, especially soon after transplanting. We monitored for the first time the insect density during the first half of a rice crop period (fig. 3). The peak oviposition period was at about 30–40 days after transplanting. The larval peak was at 30 days, about the same time as, or just after, the peak in average grade of leaf damage. We found far fewer larvae than eggs, suggesting that many eggs do not hatch, or that newly hatched larvae have a high mortality rate, or both. Evidently, the eggs laid after 30 days do not produce many larvae that mature. The low pupal density indicates that many larvae die before pupation. Despite overlapping generations during the first 50 days after transplanting, peaks in insect density are still evident. This information is useful in planning a maggot control strategy.

Stem borers. We previously described the population fluctuations of the yellow rice borer *Tryporyza incertulas* in one crop period (1974 Annual Report). In two crops in 1975, we again recorded the weekly number of eggs, larvae, and pupae. Egg density peaked at 3–14 days after transplanting; larvae peaked at about 30–40 days; and pupae peaked at 50–60 days. Thus, there was one distinct generation early in the crop period. Low numbers of larvae and pupae were found in the remainder of the crop period, apparently representing small, partly overlapping generations.

In both crops, density was reduced most from the egg to the larval stage; density also dropped from the larval to the pupal stage, indicating mortality at each stage (fig. 4). Egg survival was low from the beginning of the crop, primarily because of parasitism (Table 19), and, to a lesser degree, because of predation and some unknown factor that prevents eggs from developing or hatching. In one crop, almost no eggs survived beyond 14 days after transplanting. Larval mortality appeared to be low in all cases studied, but larval sampling and rearing

3. Density of the rice whorl maggot *Hydrellia philippina* on rice variety IR30 transplanted at 25- × 25-cm spacing, IRRI, 1975 wet season.

4. Population graph showing density changes of different stages of *Tryporyza incertulas* and the mortality at each stage on a crop of the rice selection IR127-80-1. IRRI, 1975 dry season.

5. Density of stem borer *Chilo suppressalis* per 750 hills (30 sq m) on the rice selection IR127-80-1. IRRI, 1975 wet season.

efficiency were probably poor, biasing the results. In some crops, pupal mortality was substantial, especially in the dry season (fig. 4).

The population density of *Chilo suppressalis* was studied using the same methods as for *T. incertulas*. The *C. suppressalis* population develops in the latter half of the crop period, with a peak in egg density at about 60 days after transplanting, a larval peak 10 to 20 days later, and a peak in pupal density beyond 80 days after transplanting (fig. 5). Thus, there was one major generation per crop period, but it was not always sharply defined.

The data from three crops grown in 1974 and 1975 all indicate that egg samples of *C. suppressalis* were inadequate since more larvae than eggs were collected per 30 sq m; therefore, egg mortality is difficult to assess (fig. 5). The egg-sampling procedure can possibly be intensified to increase the number collected. Larval mortality, however, appears to be high because of the few pupae found, and was possibly due to larval predation since parasitism of larvae was low (Table 19).

Sex pheromones. We previously discovered that the female adult of *Chilo suppressalis* produces a sex pheromone, a chemical that attracts the males for mating (1966 and 1968

annual reports). In 1975, collaborators at the Tropical Products Institute, London, identified and synthesized the pheromone complex. It consists of two olefinic aldehydes, (Z)-11-hexadecenal and (Z)-13-octadecenal, in the ratio of approximately 5:1. We tested the synthetic pheromones in the IRRI fields to confirm their attractiveness to wild male moths. In initial trials using covered water traps, polyethylene vials containing the pheromones at a concentration of 1 mg/vial attracted males but did not remain attractive for long. But when we reduced the dosage to about 100 µg/vial, the attractiveness increased and sustained catches continued for at least 30 days. We found that both components of the pheromone complex are needed to attract males. The vials often attract more males than do live virgin females. Pheromone traps may possibly be used to monitor abundance of moths in areas where generations are distinct. Perhaps insecticidal applications can be timed according to trap catches.

Scientists at the Tropical Products Institute also identified and synthesized the sex pheromone (Z)-11-hexadecenyl acetate of the pink

6. Nymphal density of four generations of the brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* when reared on 70- to 90-day-old IR22 rice plants at approximately 40-55%, 50-60%, 70%, or 80% relative humidity and 29°C in a controlled environmental chamber. Population initiated with three pairs of adults. IRRI phytotron, 1975.

borer *Sesamia inferens*. Initial field tests suggest that the pheromone attracts male moths; tests for confirmation will be conducted.

Brown planthoppers and green leafhoppers. We weekly sampled the population densities of the brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* and the green leafhopper *Nephotettix* spp. on wetbed seedbeds for 3 weeks using sweep net and quadrat sampling methods. Pests tended to be most abundant in the third week, when the seedlings were almost ready for transplanting. Leafhoppers reached a maximum density of 36/sq m according to the quadrat sampling technique, but the highest planthopper density was 4/sq m.

Green leafhopper catches in the light traps at IRRI were the highest on record for a dry season, but were low for the remainder of the year. Brown planthopper populations were relatively low throughout the year.

Scientists often suggest that rainfall and

relative humidity affect the population dynamics of planthoppers and leafhoppers. To test the influence of relative humidity on *Nilaparvata lugens* and *Nephotettix virescens*, we reared each species separately for three or four generations on plants in the IRRI phytotron at different constant relative humidities ranging from 40 to 80 percent. For the brown planthopper, the highest number of nymphs developed when the relative humidity in the insects microenvironment ranged from 50 to 60 percent (fig. 6). A continuous relative humidity of 80 percent was detrimental to population growth. Moderate relative humidities appeared to be the most favorable, at least under constant conditions. Preliminary data suggest that a relative humidity of 80 percent is conducive to population growth of green leafhoppers. Apparently the green leafhoppers and brown planthoppers differ in their responses to a constant relative humidity.

Control and management of rice pests

Weeds

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SUMMARY

Most of our research has focused on direct control of weeds by hand, mechanical, and chemical methods. We continued weed management studies to minimize dependence on high rates of herbicide application, which has been found to favor the buildup of perennial weeds.

The herbicide MON 0358 gave outstanding control of annual weeds in transplanted, direct-seeded flooded, and upland rice. Among new herbicides screened for the first time under rainfed transplanted and direct-seeded flooded rice, MT-B-3015, NTN 5810/KUE 2079a, Prefar/MCPA, and WL 29226 appeared promising. For upland rice, Antor, RH 2512, and RH 2915 looked promising when applied before emergence of crop and weeds, while U-44,344 showed promise if applied shortly after emergence.

In our zero- and minimum-tillage studies, yields were highest when glyphosate was used in the zero-tillage plots in transplanted rice and when glyphosate spray was followed by one plowing in the direct-seeded flooded rice.

We found that weed competition decreases appreciably when the plant spacing is decreased from 25 × 25 cm to 15 × 15 cm. But varieties must be quite resistant to lodging if planted at close spacings.

WEED CONTROL IN RICE

Agronomy Department

Under the existing conditions of high weed density and relatively low cost of labor and of some chemicals, the elimination of weeds in rice fields is more important than the method of weed control.

Most of our research has focused on direct control of weeds, including hand, mechanical, and chemical methods. In most of Asia, labor is ample and wages are low (less than US \$1/day). Therefore, chemical weed control must compete with inexpensive hand weeding.

Experiments to identify suitable herbicides were continued at the IRRI farm; at the Maligaya, Bicol, and Visayas Rice Research Stations of the Philippine Bureau of Plant

Industry (BPI); and in Philippine farmers' fields during the 1975 dry and wet seasons.

Transplanted rice. During the 1975 dry season, the yield differences in IR26 between herbicide-treated and nontreated plots ranged from 2.1 t/ha at the Visayas station to 5.8 t/ha at Maligaya. At all sites, the yield differences between weed control and no weed control were highly significant.

At all experimental sites, *Echinochloa crusgalli*, *Monochoria vaginalis*, and *Cyperus difformis* were common. *Scirpus maritimus* was present at the IRRI farm and *Sphenochlea zeylanica* in Bicol.

The only herbicide that consistently gave yields statistically similar to those of hand-weeded controls at all sites was MON 0358 (Table 1). Granular 2,4-D and perfluidone/2,4-D gave yields comparable to those of hand-weeded checks in two of four sites (Table 1). C-288 effectively controlled most annual weeds and gave yields statistically similar to those of hand-weeded checks, except at IRRI where it failed to control *Scirpus maritimus*.

During the 1975 wet season, most herbicides adequately controlled weeds and the treated plots yielded from 3 to 4 t/ha more rice than did the untreated controls (Table 2). MON 0358 at 0.3 kg a.i./ha continued to look promising at all four sites. Adding 2,4-D to MON 0358 gave no advantage over applying MON 0358 alone. MON 0358 appears to effectively control broad-leaved and sedge weeds in transplanted rice. Use of perfluidone/2,4-D gave significantly lower yields than did hand weeding (controls) at the three BPI stations, but not at the IRRI farm.

WEED CONTROL IN TRANSPLANTED RICE IN FARMERS' FIELDS

Agronomy Department

Methods of weed control were compared at various nitrogen levels in six farmers' fields in Laguna. Because we found no significant interaction between weed-control methods and fertilizer practices, we have summarized data for only the weed-control treatments.

At six sites, two treatments gave yields significantly higher than yields of the untreated

Table 1. Effects of granular herbicides applied before weed emergence (4 days after transplanting) on yield of transplanted IR26 rice at IRRI and three Bureau of Plant Industry (BPI) stations in the Philippines. 1975 dry season.

Herbicide treatment	Rate (kg a.i./ha)	Yield ^a (t/ha)				
		IRRI	Maligaya	Bicol	Visayas	Av.
MON 0358	0.5	7.1	6.9	7.6	5.4	6.8
MON 0358 + 2,4-D IPE	0.5 + 0.5	7.5	6.6	7.0	4.8*	6.5
C-288	0.5	6.0**	6.1	7.3	5.5	6.2
C-19490/2,4-D IPE	0.5	5.0**	5.3**	7.0	4.7**	5.5
Perfluidone/2,4-D IPE	1.0/0.25	6.5	4.1**	6.7	4.2**	5.4
Dinitramine + 2,4-D IPE	0.5 + 0.5	6.0**	5.9	7.4	5.1	6.1
Butachlor + 2,4-D IPE	0.75 + 0.5	5.9**	6.2	7.1	4.6**	6.0
2,4-D IPE	0.8	6.5	4.1**	7.2	4.0**	5.4
Bifenox	3.0	7.6	^b	^b	^b	^b
Hand weeded twice ^c		7.7	6.7	7.2	5.8	6.8
Untreated control ^d		2.7	0	2.7	2.8	2.0
Av.		6.1	5.2	6.7	4.7	

^a*, **Significantly higher or lower than in the hand-weeded check at the 5% and the 1% level, respectively. ^bNot tested. ^cAt 20 and 40 days after transplanting. ^dAll herbicide treatments gave significantly higher yields than did the untreated controls.

controls (hand weeded twice and 2,4-D granules applied at pre-emergence). Average yields were significantly higher for hand-weeded plots than for plots treated with a pre-emergence application of 2,4-D at the six sites (Table 3). The cost of the 2,4-D herbicide treatment is less, however, than the cost of two hand weedings. The average grain yield of 5.2 t/ha with no weed control is clear evidence of the thorough land preparation and good water management generally practiced by Laguna farmers.

Direct-seeded flooded rice. Weed control is more critical and difficult in broadcast rice than in transplanted rice. But the problems of weed control depend on how the rice is seeded. For example, weed problems can be minimized by

broadcasting seeds onto a puddled and flooded field. Chemical weed control is still essential, however, to establish good stands and harvest high yields.

During the 1975 dry season, all herbicide treatments gave significantly higher yields of IR26 than did untreated controls at Bicol and Visayas, but not at IRRI and Maligaya (Table 4).

Yields were comparably high with all chemicals except dinitramine, dinitramine + 2,4-D, and benthocarb/2,4-D at Visayas (Table 4). MON-0358 continued to consistently give good results at all sites.

During the 1975 wet season, IR26 generally yielded well at IRRI, but not at Maligaya and

Table 2. Effects of granular herbicides applied before weed emergence (4 days after transplanting) on yield of transplanted IR26 rice at IRRI and three Bureau of Plant Industry (BPI) stations in the Philippines. 1975 wet season.

Herbicide treatment	Rate (kg a.i./ha)	Yield ^a (t/ha)				
		IRRI	Maligaya	Bicol	Visayas	Av.
MON 0358	0.3	4.8	4.1	3.9	4.5	4.3
MON 0358 + 2,4-D IPE	0.3 + 0.5	5.0	3.7	3.8	4.0	4.1
C-288	0.5	5.1	3.9	3.8	4.6	4.4
C-19490/2,4-D IPE	0.5	4.3	4.1	3.5**	4.9*	4.2
Perfluidone/2,4-D IPE	1.0/0.25	5.1	3.6*	3.2**	3.4*	3.8
Dinitramine + 2,4-D IPE	0.5 + 0.5	5.1	4.0	3.3**	4.6	4.2
Butachlor + 2,4-D IPE	0.75 + 0.5	4.9	4.0	3.7	4.4	4.2
2,4-D IPE	0.8	5.0	3.6*	3.8	4.0	4.0
Hand weeded twice ^b	—	5.0	4.2	3.8	4.4	4.4
Untreated control ^c	—	0.8	3.0	2.8	2.7	2.3
Av.		4.5	3.8	3.6	4.2	

^a*, **Significantly higher or lower than in hand-weeded check at the 5% and 1% level, respectively. ^bAt 20 and 40 days after transplanting. ^cAll herbicide treatments gave significantly higher yields than did the untreated control.

Table 3. Effects of weed control methods on rice yields in farmers' fields. Laguna province, Philippines, 1975 dry season.

Weed control method	Yield ^a (t/ha)						Av. ^b
	Santa Rosa	San Pedro	Famy	Lumban	Santa Cruz	Cabuyao	
No weeding	4.8	3.4	5.4	4.8	6.0	4.7	5.2 c
Hand weeding	5.0	4.5	6.0	5.6**	6.9**	5.8**	6.1 a
2,4-D IPE	4.3	3.8	5.4	5.3*	6.9**	4.7	5.6 b

*, **Significantly higher or lower than in the hand-weeded check at the 5% and 1% level, respectively. ^b Any two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Table 4. Effects of granular herbicides applied at early post-emergence of weeds (6 days after seeding) on yield of direct-seeded flooded IR26 rice at IRRI and three Bureau of Plant Industry (BPI) stations in the Philippines. 1975 dry season.

Herbicide treatment	Rate (kg a.i./ha)	Yield ^a (t/ha)				Av.
		IRRI	Maligaya	Bicol	Visayas	
MON 0358	0.5	5.2 ab	5.8 a	5.6 a	6.0 a	5.6
MON 0358 + 2,4-D IPE	0.5 + 0.5	6.1 ab	5.4 a	5.8 a	5.8 a	5.8
C-288	0.5	5.6 ab	5.2 a	6.0 a	6.1 a	5.7
C-19490/2,4-D IPE	0.75	6.0 ab	6.2 a	6.2 a	5.3 a	5.9
Perfluidone/2,4-D IPE	1.0/0.25	6.9 a	6.0 a	6.2 a	5.2 a	6.1
Dinitramine	0.75	5.9 ab	5.0 a	5.2 a	3.6 b	4.9
Dinitramine + 2,4-D IPE	0.5 + 0.5	6.3 ab	5.5 a	5.7 a	3.5 b	5.3
Butachlor + 2,4-D IPE	0.75 + 0.5	6.8 ab	5.7 a	5.0 a	5.6 a	5.8
Benthiocarb/2,4-D IPE	1.0/0.5	6.4 ab	6.5 a	6.0 a	4.2 b	5.8
Untreated control	—	4.4 b	5.4 a	3.7 b	0.7 c	3.6
Av.		6.0	5.7	5.5	4.6	

^a Av. of four replications. In each column, any two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Table 5. Effects of granular herbicides applied at early post-emergence of weeds (6 days after seeding) on yield of direct-seeded flooded IR26 rice at IRRI and three Bureau of Plant Industry (BPI) stations in the Philippines. 1975 wet season.

Herbicide treatment	Rate (kg a.i./ha)	Yield ^a (t/ha)				Av.
		IRRI	Maligaya	Bicol	Visayas	
MON 0358	0.3	6.2 a	3.6 ab	3.6 a	5.2 a	4.6
MON 0358 + 2,4-D IPE	0.3 + 0.5	5.3 a	3.3 ab	3.5 a	4.7 ab	4.2
C-288	0.5	5.7 a	4.4 ab	3.6 a	3.4 cd	4.3
C-19490/2,4-D IPE	0.75	5.4 a	4.0 ab	3.3 ab	4.8 ab	4.4
Perfluidone/2,4-D IPE	1.0/0.25	5.2 a	4.6 a	3.2 ab	4.3 abc	4.3
Dinitramine	0.75	5.4 a	1.6 c	3.4 ab	4.3 abc	3.7
Dinitramine + 2,4-D IPE	0.5 + 0.5	5.4 a	3.9 ab	3.5 a	4.3 abc	4.3
Butachlor + 2,4-D IPE	0.75 + 0.5	5.8 a	3.1 b	3.6 a	3.8 bcd	4.1
Benthiocarb/2,4-D IPE	1.0/0.5	5.0 a	4.2 ab	3.5 a	4.2 abcd	4.2
Untreated control	—	1.7 b	0.6 c	2.7 b	3.1 d	2.0
Av.		5.1	3.3	3.4	4.2	

^a Av. of four replications. In each column, any two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Bicol. At IRRI, there were no differences in grain yield as affected by the herbicides used. At Maligaya, dinitramine gave yields no higher than were seen in untreated controls (Table 5). At Bicol, use of C-19490/ 2,4-D, perfluidone/ 2,4-D, and dinitramine + 2,4-D gave yields not significantly higher than those of controls. At Visayas, C-288, butachlor + 2,4-D, and ben-

thiocarb/2,4-D gave poor weed control and low yields.

Two seasons' data show that MON 0358 provides excellent weed control under a wide range of testing conditions.

Upland rice. About 15 percent of the world's rice is upland. Upland rice yields are low because of many factors, of which heavy weed

Table 6. Effects of liquid herbicides applied before crop and weed emergence (2 days after seeding) on weed control, crop tolerance, and yield of the intermediate-statured line BPI 76/Dawn grown under upland conditions. IRRI, 1975 wet season.

Treatment	Rate (kg a.i./ha)	Control rating ^a			Toxicity rating ^b	Yield ^c (t/ha)
		Grasses	Sedges	Broadleaved		
Butralin	2.0	3	1	8	0	0.9 def
Penoxalin	2.0	8	0	8	0	1.4 cde
Butachlor	2.0	2	4	8	0	1.4 cde
C-288	2.0	0	3	8	0	0 f
MON 0358	0.5	2	2	8	0	1.2 de
MON 0358	1.0	5	3	8	0	2.4 abc
Oxadiazon	1.0	4	2	8	0	1.9 bcd
Fluorodifen	2.0	1	4	8	0	0.8 ef
USB 3153	2.0	10	1	9	4	2.4 abc
Dinitramine	2.0	9	1	8	2	2.5 ab
Hand weeded twice ^d	—	8	6	8	0	2.9 a
Untreated check	—	0	0	8	0	0 f

^aTaken at 60 days after rice emergence. Control scale of 0–10: 0 = no control; 10 = complete control. ^bToxicity scale of 0–10: 0 = no toxicity, 10 = complete crop kill. ^cAv. of four replications. Any two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^dWeeded at 15 and 30 days after rice emergence.

infestation is one of the most serious.

At the IRRI farm using an intermediate-statured experimental line (BPI 76/Dawn), the untreated control was completely taken over by the heavy infestation of grassy weeds, such as *Echinochloa colona*, *Digitaria sanguinalis*, *Eleusine indica*, *Ischaemum rugosum*, the annual sedge *Cyperus iria*, and the perennial nutsedge *Cyperus rotundus*. Plots treated with C-288 gave zero grain yield (Table 6). Yields of 2.4 t/ha were harvested in plots treated with MON 0358 at 1 kg a.i./ha and with USB 3153 and dinitramine at 2 kg a.i./ha—statistically similar to the yields obtained with two hand weedings (Table 6).

Because infestation of both annual grasses and *Cyperus rotundus* was quite heavy, plots treated with oxadiazon, butachlor, and penoxalin gave relatively low yields; butralin and fluorodifen, which did not adequately control annuals and perennials, gave severely reduced yields. BPI 76/Dawn had an excellent stand until 10 days before harvest when it lodged severely due to heavy rains.

In a farmer's field in Batangas province, Philippines, the initial stand of BPI 76/Dawn was good due to early April rains. When the seedlings were about 10 cm tall, a dry spell of 3 weeks considerably reduced tiller production.

Predominant weed species in the experimental site were *Echinochloa colona*, *Ageratum conyzoides*, *Ipomea triloba*, *Celosia argentea*, *Bidens pilosa*, and *Cyperus rotundus*.

All herbicides gave yields similar to those of the hand-weeded check except for butachlor, fluorodifen, and propanil, which gave low yields because of poor grass control (Table 7). When propanil was applied at 15 days after rice emergence, grassy weeds were at the three- to four-leaf stage. Some rice was scorched, and the drought aggravated the burning effects. *Echinochloa colona* weeds recovered when the next rain fell, but rice could not quickly recover. As a result, grasses took over the propanil-treated plots to the same degree that they did the untreated control, indicating that, under unpredictable monsoon weather, propanil does not provide consistent weed control in upland rice.

Butachlor inhibits growth of direct-seeded rice. Butachlor is commonly recommended for weed control in upland and direct-seeded flooded rice. In preliminary greenhouse trials under simulated upland and lowland conditions, butachlor reduced the growth of IR28, IR30, and the line IR1561-228-3 at the low rates of 1 and 2 kg a.i./ha; at higher rates, growth was reduced more (Table 8).

Reductions in height and weight of tops and roots of the three rices were similar under upland and lowland conditions. In some instances, more tillers were produced when the herbicide was applied; in others, fewer were produced. Responses of the three varieties to the herbicide were similar, so results were averaged.

Table 7. Effects of liquid herbicides applied before crop and weed emergence (3 days after seeding) on weed control and yield of direct-seeded BPI 76/9/Dawn rice grown under upland conditions in a farmer's field. Cuenca, Batangas province, Philippines, 1975 wet season.

Treatment	Rate (kg a.i./ha)	Control rating ^a			Yield ^b (t/ha)
		Grasses	Sedges	Broadleaved	
Butralin	2.0	7	7	5	1.7 a
Penoxalin	2.0	9	9	8	2.6 a
Butachlor	2.0	2	2	5	0.5 b
C-288	2.0	5	7	5	2.0 a
MON 0358	1.0	4	5	5	1.8 a
Oxadiazon	1.0	5	6	8	1.9 a
Fluorodifen	2.0	2	4	8	0.7 b
USB 3153	2.0	8	8	7	2.4 a
Dinitramine	2.0	8	8	5	2.0 a
Propanil ^c	2.0	1	2	8	0.6 b
Hand weeded twice ^d	—	9	8	8	2.0 a
Untreated check	—	1	3	2	0.3 b

^aTaken at 60 days after rice emergence. Scale of 0–10: 0 = no control; 10 = complete control. ^bAv. of four replications. Any two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^cApplied at 15 days after rice emergence. ^dWeeded at 15 and 30 days after rice emergence.

SCREENING NEW HERBICIDES

Agronomy Department

We screen new herbicides to identify safe and effective ones for transplanted, direct-seeded flooded, and rainfed upland rice. As we evaluate more herbicides through initial screening and subsequent advanced international trials, the chances of developing low-cost chemical weed control will improve.

Transplanted and direct-seeded flooded rice.

During the 1975 wet season, several new chemicals looked promising for both transplanted (Table 9) and direct-seeded flooded rice (Table 10). Of the various chemicals tested for the first time, MT-B-3015, NTN 5810/KUE 2079a, Prefar/MCPA, and WL 29226 appeared

promising. Using them, yields increased from 1 to 3 t/ha more than yields of the untreated controls. The combination herbicide benthio-carb + KUE 2079a adequately controlled weeds with no crop injury in both transplanted and direct-seeded flooded rice.

The important weed species in the test sites were annuals such as *Echinochloa crusgalli*, *Echinochloa crusgavonis*, *Monochoria vaginalis*, *Cyperus difformis*, *Leptochloa chinensis*, *Fimbristylis littoralis*, and *Sphenochlea zeylanica*. Among the perennials were *Paspalum scrobiculatum* and *Scirpus maritimus*. Infestations of *Cyperus iria* and *Cyperus rotundus* were minor. The distribution of rainfall was excellent during the season, so neither the transplanted nor the direct-seeded crops suffered from lack of water. Because the direct-seeded crops had somewhat more standing water than did the transplanted crops, most herbicides, except MT-B-3015 and WL 29226, were toxic to 6-day-old rice seedlings.

Severe grassy stunt infection explains the somewhat lower yields in transplanted IR26 rice.

Upland rice. Heavy weed infestation in the experimental site consisted of *Echinochloa colona*, *Eleusine indica*, *Digitaria sanguinalis*, *Commelina diffusa*, *Cyperus iria*, *Eclipta alba*, and *Cyperus rotundus*. Antor, RH 2512, and RH 2915 applied before crop and weeds emerged looked promising for upland rice (Table 11). The herbicide U-44,344 if applied shortly after emergence of rice and weeds showed promise for use in upland rice. The tall, leafy selection

Table 8. Effects of different rates of butachlor on growth characteristics^a of direct-seeded rice grown under different soil conditions. IRRI, 1975.

Butachlor rate (kg a.i./ha)	Plant ht (cm)		Tillers (no./plant)	Dry wt (g) 34 DS		
	16 DS ^b	34 DS		Tops	Roots	Total
<i>Well-drained soil (upland)</i>						
0	17.7	54.9	2.5	0.74	0.24	0.98
1	15.0	52.4	2.7	0.73	0.20	0.93
2	14.2	49.5	2.1	0.59	0.19	0.78
<i>Saturated soil (lowland)</i>						
0	18.5	66.1	2.8	0.89	0.23	1.12
1	14.9	63.7	2.0	0.77	0.21	0.98
2	12.7	60.3	2.9	0.71	0.21	0.92

^aResults are averages for three cultivars, IR28, IR30, and IR1561-228-3. ^bDS = days after seeding.

Table 9. Effects of promising new herbicides on weed control, crop tolerance, and yield of transplanted IR26 rice grown under rainfed conditions. IIRRI, 1975 wet season.

Treatment ^a	Application		Visual rating ^b				Yield ^d (t/ha)
	Rate (kg a.i./ha)	Time (DT)	Control			Toxicity ^c	
			Grasses	Sedges	Broadleaved		
MT-B-3015 (G)	2.0/1.4	4	3	2	8	0	2.4
WL 29226 (G)	2.0	4	6	6	8	0	3.0
Trifluralin R (G)	0.6/0.8	4	6	4	8	0	2.0
TBA/MCPA (L)	0.75/0.25	10	5	10	8	0	2.4
TBA/MCPA (L)	1.5/0.5	10	5	7	10	0	2.6
NTN 5810/KUE 2079a (G)	3.0/1.0	4	8	4	9	0	2.4
Butachlor + KUE 2079a (G)	1.0 + 0.5	4	6	6	10	0	2.8
Benthiocarb + KUE 2079a (G)	1.0 + 0.5	4	5	4	9	0	2.3
Prefar/MCPA (G)	1.2/0.45	4	4	6	8	0	2.2
Butachlor + 2,4-D IPE ^e (G)	0.75 + 0.5	4	7	4	8	0	2.0
2,4-D IPE ^e (G)	0.8	4	4	5	8	0	2.3
Hand weeded twice	—	20 & 40	8	10	8	0	2.6
Untreated check	—	—	2	2	6	0	0.9

^aG = granular; L = liquid; + = chemicals were applied in immediate succession. ^bAt 60 days after transplanting (DT). Control scale of 0–10: 0 = no control; 10 = complete control. ^cToxicity scale of 0–10: 0 = no toxicity; 10 = complete crop kill. ^dAv. of two replications expressed at 14% moisture. ^eStandard chemical controls.

Table 10. Effects of promising new herbicides on weed control, crop tolerance, and yield of direct-seeded IR26 rice grown under rainfed conditions. IIRRI, 1975 wet season.

Treatment ^a	Application		Visual rating ^c				Yield ^e (t/ha)
	Rate (kg a.i./ha)	Time ^b (DS)	Control			Toxicity ^d	
			Grasses	Sedges	Broadleaved		
MT-B-3015 (G)	1.0/0.7	6	6	6	4	0	3.5
MT-B-3015 (G)	2.0/1.4	6	6	5	8	0	3.8
MT-B-3015 (G)	2.0/1.4	10	6	7	5	0	4.2
WL 29226 (G)	1.0	6	4	6	6	0	3.4
Trifluralin R (G)	0.6/0.8	10	5	7	10	4	3.4
Ethofumesate (EC)	2.0	6	6	2	4	4	3.5
Ethofumesate (EC)	2.0	10	4	5	2	0	3.5
NTN 5810/KUE 2079a (G)	1.5/0.5	6	6	6	8	3	4.0
Benthiocarb + KUE 2079a (G)	1.0 + 0.5	6	7	8	8	4	4.3
Prefar/MCPA (G)	1.2/0.45	6	6	6	6	4	2.9
Benthiocarb/2,4-D IPE ^f (G)	1.0/0.5	6	6	4	6	0	3.7
C-288 ^f (G)	0.5	6	8	6	7	0	4.1
Untreated control	—	—	1	2	1	0	0.8

^aG = granular; EC = emulsifiable concentrate; + = chemicals were applied in immediate succession. ^bDS = days after seeding. ^cAt 60 days after seeding. Control scale of 0–10: 0 = no control; 10 = complete control. ^dToxicity scale of 0–10: 0 = no toxicity; 10 = complete crop kill. ^eAv. of two replications expressed at 14% moisture. ^fStandard chemical controls.

Table 11. Effects of promising new herbicides on weed control, crop tolerance, and yield of the line IR2053-419-3 grown under upland conditions. IIRRI, 1975 wet season.

Treatment ^a	Application		Visual rating ^c				Yield ^e (t/ha)
	Rate (kg a.i./ha)	Time ^b	Control			Toxicity ^d	
			Grasses	Sedges	Broadleaved		
Antor (L)	1.0	2 DS	6	8	4	2	2.0
U-44,344 (WP)	2.0	1–2 1sg	6	8	4	0	2.2
RH 2512 (WP)	1.0	2 DS	4	7	6	0	2.0
RH 2915 (EC)	1.0	2 DS	6	6	6	2	1.6
Butachlor ^f	2.0	2 DS	6	8	8	0	1.6
Hand weeded twice	—	15 & 30 DRE	8	8	9	0	1.9
Untreated check	—	—	3	0	2	0	0.4

^aL = liquid; WP = wettable powder; EC = emulsifiable concentrate. ^bDS = days after seeding; 1sg = leaf stage of grasses; DRE = days after rice emergence. ^cTaken at 60 DRE. Control scale of 0–10: 0 = no control; 10 = complete control. ^dToxicity scale of 0–10: 0 = no toxicity; 10 = complete crop kill. ^eAv. of two replications expressed at 14% moisture. ^fStandard chemical control.

IR2053-419-3 lodged severely at the heading stage, explaining the generally low yields (Table 11).

ZERO AND MINIMUM TILLAGE IN RICE

Agronomy Department

Zero and minimum tillage in transplanted and broadcast-seeded flooded rice were evaluated in field experiments at the IRRI farm during the 1975 wet season using IR30 as the test variety.

Yields were highest when glyphosate was applied at 7 days before transplanting on zero-tillage plots in an area where *Paspalum scrobiculatum* was the predominant weed (Table 12). The highest yield with glyphosate, 4.5 t/ha, was statistically similar to the 4.1 t/ha yield of conventional tillage (one plowing followed by two harrowings). Yields were significantly lower, 2.5 t/ha, when glyphosate was applied at 12 instead of 7 days before transplanting. But rain fell 4 hours after glyphosate was sprayed at 12 days before transplanting, so it is not clear whether the yield was lower because some of the chemical washed away, or because weeds regrew when glyphosate was applied earlier. Similarly, paraquat followed by one plowing did not successfully control *Paspalum* sp., possibly because rain fell shortly after spraying, which might have washed away the chemical. Yield was significantly lower than with one plowing and two harrowings (Table 12).

In the direct-seeded rice, the highest yield, 3.9 t/ha, was obtained with glyphosate sprayed at 7 days before seeding followed by one plowing at 2 days before seeding (Table 12). Applying glyphosate alone at 7 days before seeding, how-

ever, gave yields statistically similar to those of one plowing followed by two harrowings.

Yields were generally lower with direct-seeded than with transplanted rice because weed competition was more severe.

These studies indicate that the success of minimum or zero tillage techniques will largely depend on the degree of infestation of perennial weeds such as *Paspalum scrobiculatum*, and on the rainfall distribution if the crop is grown during the wet season.

EFFECT OF PLANT SPACING ON WEED GROWTH

Agronomy Department

When the distance between hills of transplanted IR28 and IR30 was decreased from 25 × 25 cm to 15 × 15 cm, yields increased by an average of 30 percent. The most marked differences were observed in the no-weeding plots (Table 13). Average yields of IR28 were only 3 percent higher than yields of IR30.

We found no significant differences in yield among post-transplanting treatments for weed control. The average yields differed by only 9 percent between the highest yielding treatment (2,4-D followed by rotary weeding) and the lowest (two rotary weedings). All weeding treatments, however, yielded significantly higher than did the unweeded checks at all plant spacings.

Decreases in yield due to weeds for the two varieties, compared with yields of the weed-free check plots, averaged 18.1, 29.5, and 51.6 percent for plant spacings of 15 × 15, 20 × 20, and 25 × 25 cm, respectively.

Table 12. Effects of chemical substitution for tillage on yields of transplanted and broadcast-seeded flooded IR30 rice. IRRI, 1975 wet season.

Treatment ^a	Application		Yield ^c (t/ha)		
	Rate (kg a.i./ha)	Time ^b (DBT/DBS)	Transplanted	Broadcast	Av.
Glyphosate	2.0	7	4.5 a	3.4 b	4.0
Glyphosate	2.0	12	2.5 c	1.5 d	2.0
Glyphosate fb 1 plowing	2.0	7 fb 2	4.6 a	3.9 a	4.2
Glyphosate fb 1 plowing	2.0	12 fb 2	4.4 a	3.3 bc	3.8
Paraquat fb 1 plowing	2.0	7 fb 2	3.6 b	3.1 c	3.4
1 plowing + 2 harrowings	—	2	4.1 a	3.4 b	3.8
Av.	—	—	4.0	3.1	

^afb = followed by. ^bDBT = days before transplanting; DBS = days before seeding. ^cAv. of four replications. In each column, any two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Table 13. Effects of variety and plant spacing on weed growth and yield of transplanted rice. IRRI, 1975 wet season.

Variety	Weed wt (kg/ha)			Yield ^a (t/ha)		
	15 x 15 cm	20 x 20 cm	25 x 25 cm	15 x 15 cm	20 x 20 cm	25 x 25 cm
			<i>2,4-D fb rotary weeding^b</i>			
IR28	0	60	30	3.9	3.8	3.5
IR30	20	20	10	4.1	3.6	3.3
			<i>Benthiocarb + 2,4-D^c</i>			
IR28	0	45	105	4.1	3.8	3.3
IR30	20	5	55	4.0	3.5	3.2
			<i>2,4-D^d</i>			
IR28	30	35	130	3.9	3.8	3.2
IR30	85	0	105	3.9	3.4	3.2
			<i>Weed-free^e</i>			
IR28	75	140	90	3.6	3.3	3.2
IR30	30	180	105	4.2	3.1	2.9
			<i>Two rotary weeding^f</i>			
IR28	0	0	0	4.0	3.5	3.3
IR30	0	0	0	4.1	3.3	3.0
			<i>No weeding</i>			
IR28	735	790	820	3.1	2.8	1.5
IR30	460	650	610	3.5	2.1	1.5

^aLSD = 0.4 t/ha. ^b0.8 kg a.i./ha at 4 days after transplanting (DT) followed by (fb) rotary weeding at 40 DT. ^c1.0 + 0.5 kg a.i./ha at 4 DT. ^d0.8 kg a.i./ha at 4 DT. ^eWeeded when necessary. ^f20 fb 40 DT.

In the unweeded plots at 56 days after transplanting, weed weights were lower when the distances between plants were less. Thus, weeds probably could have been controlled in these plots with less time or with lower amounts of chemicals. These data indicate that yields of the semidwarf varieties can be significantly increased and weed-competitive ability appreciably improved by decreasing the plant spacing from 25 × 25 cm to 15 × 15 cm. No varietal differences in competitive ability were observed.

Lodging was a problem at closer plant spacings. IR30 did not lodge at any planting distance. But an average of 5.5 percent of the IR28 plants lodged at 20 × 20 cm spacing, and 17.5 percent at 15 × 15 cm. Weeds in the plots did not increase lodging.

STUDIES ON *SCIRPUS MARITIMUS* L.

Agronomy and Plant Physiology Departments

Effect of temperature regimes (*Plant Physiology*).

S. maritimus grows across a broad latitudinal range, suggesting that it has wide adaptability to temperature. To confirm this, plants were grown in the glasshouses of the phytotron under five different temperature regimes, but at constant relative humidity. Day temperatures in the glasshouses were maintained from 0900 to 1700 hours.

Plant height. During the first 40 days of growth, plant height was about the same under the different temperature regimes (fig. 1). At

I. Height of *S. maritimus* L. at 40 and 80 days after seeding (DS) under various temperature regimes.

Table 14. Number of tubers and shoots per pot and dry weight per tuber of *S. maritimus* L. under various temperature regimes. IRRI, 1975.

Day/night temp. (°C)	Av. temp. (°C)	Shoots (no./pot)	Tubers (no./pot)	Dry wt (mg/tuber)
35/27	29.7	67	126	190
32/24	26.7	59	108	237
29/21	23.7	52	99	295
26/18	20.7	50	99	391
20/20	20.0	58	115	497
LSD (.05)	—	—	15	59
CV (%)	—	—	11	14

80 days after seeding, however, we observed two distinct responses to temperature in terms of height. The plants under high average temperatures (35/27°C, 32/24°C, 29/21°C day/night temperatures) were taller than those under lower temperatures (26/18°C, 20/20°C). Among the higher temperature treatments, however, the plants under 29/21°C regimes were taller than were those under 35/27°C or 32/24°C regimes. This indicates that the average optimum temperature for extension growth in this species is between 23 and 25°C. Previous experiments have shown that *S. maritimus* grows taller and, therefore, competes better than do most semi-dwarf rice varieties in the tropics.

Shoot and tuber production. High average temperature definitely favors shoot production of *S. maritimus* (Table 14).

The number of tubers also increased with temperature except at the lowest temperature regime, 20/20°C. The tubers that developed at high temperatures, however, were much smaller both in size and in weight than the tubers developed at low temperatures (Table 14). Total dry matter production generally increased as temperature increased, although the underground parts increased in dry weight as temperature decreased. Food reserves accumulate better in the tubers under lower temperatures.

The results indicate that this species may be more competitive with rice in the tropical than in the temperate regions in terms of plant height, shoot number, and number of tubers.

Effect of drying on tuber germination (*Plant Physiology*). Under traditional rice culture, farmers fallow the field after harvesting the main crop. From harvest until land preparation

for the next crop, many of the *Scirpus* tubers near the ground surface become desiccated. When the rain comes, the field is plowed and harrowed and the desiccated tubers float. These tubers are either removed from the field or allowed to rot.

The most important source of *Scirpus* infestation is probably tubers buried deep in the moist portion of the soil profile and brought to the soil surface at plowing. Fallowing and drying of the field probably reduce the natural population of *S. maritimus*.

But as rice production is intensified and irrigation facilities are improved, this fallow period is being minimized. Knowing the critical number of drying days or the moisture content at which the tubers lose their ability to germinate would provide a basis for recommendations for *Scirpus* control.

To obtain such information, we selected tubers of uniform size and kept them in trays in the greenhouse. Every 2 days, the tubers were sampled for moisture content and tested for germination.

Within the range of 30.5 to 57.7 percent moisture content, we found no difference in percent germination of the tubers. At 30 percent moisture and below, germination was slowed down and greatly reduced (fig. 2). At 16 percent, the tubers were no longer viable. This moisture content was reached after 20 days of air-drying in the greenhouse.

This experiment showed that the viable tubers, if exposed to desiccating conditions, may be greatly reduced in number, which may explain why *Scirpus* is more common in irrigated than in rainfed rice fields. This also suggests that draining and plowing the field after harvest, exposing the tubers to dry air, might significantly reduce the population in the next crop.

IRRI agronomists have shown that shifting from lowland to upland soil management greatly reduced the population of *S. maritimus*.

Management and control of *Scirpus maritimus* L. (*Agronomy*). Field experiments initiated during the 1974 dry season (1974 Annual report) were continued through the 1975 dry and wet seasons at IRRI in an area of naturally heavy *S. maritimus* infestation.

The three cropping patterns were generally

2. Effect of drying on the germination of *S. maritimus* L. tubers.

the same as those in the 1974 crop seasons except that corn was intercropped with mung beans instead of peanuts.

During the 1975 dry season, the yields from the plots treated with herbicides in all three cropping systems were significantly higher than those from the untreated controls (Table 15). For continuous lowland rice, the highest yields were 5.6 t/ha from rotary-weeded plots, followed by 5 t/ha from plots treated with bentazon. Because of *Scirpus maritimus* infestation, the untreated control produced 4.0 t/ha less than did the rotary-weeded plots and 3.4 t/ha less than did the herbicide-treated plots (Table 15). Bentazon did not control the annual grassy weeds.

For corn planted alone, the highest yield, 36,500 marketable ears/ha, came from the plots that were hand weeded twice (Table 15). This yield was significantly higher than the 31,000 marketable ears/ha from the plots treated with butachlor followed by bentazon. Again, butachlor failed to efficiently control annual grasses. Yield from the untreated control was low, 13,000 marketable ears/ha, because of heavy grass population (*Echinochloa* spp.).

When corn was intercropped with mung bean, the corn yield was not numerically higher than when corn was planted alone (Table 15). The yield of the hand-weeded crop was significantly higher than that of intercropped corn and mung beans treated with herbicide because butachlor

Table 15. Effects of weeding methods on yield and population density of *Scirpus maritimus* L. and other weeds on three irrigated cropping patterns. IIRI, 1975 dry season.

Cropping pattern, treatment	Yield ^a (1 ha)	Weeds (no./sq m)				
		Grasses	Broad-leaved	Annual sedges	<i>Scirpus maritimus</i>	<i>Cyperus rotundus</i>
<i>Continuous lowland rice</i>	(tons)					
Bentazon	5.0 a	157	37	26	1	—
Rotary weeding	5.6 a	4	11	16	27	—
No weeding	1.6 b	7	78	640	406	—
<i>Corn</i>	(marketable ears)					
Butachlor fb bentazon	31,000 b	425	10	3	4	57
Hand weeding twice	36,500 a	15	0	0	0	4
No weeding	13,000 c	2360	20	6	35	53
<i>Corn + mung beans</i>	corn (ears) mung beans (kg)					
Butachlor fb bentazon	27,000 b 367 b	624	1	1	5	20
Hand weeding twice	31,500 a 501 a	23	0	0	0	3
No weeding	10,500 c 207 c	999	9	0	36	32

^aAv. of two replications. In each column, any two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Table 16. Effects of weeding methods and population density of *Scirpus maritimus* L. and other weeds on the yield of lowland and dry-sown rainfed banded rice. IRRI, 1975 wet season.

Cropping pattern, treatment	Yield ^a (t/ha)	Weeds (no./sq m)				
		Grasses	Broad- leaved	Annual sedges	<i>Scirpus maritimus</i>	<i>Cyperus rotundus</i>
<i>Continuous lowland rice</i>						
Bentazon	3.7 a	195	97	0	3	0
Rotary weeding	3.9 a	10	5	5	25	0
No weeding	1.7 b	115	90	135	325	0
<i>Lowland rice^b</i>						
Bentazon	4.1 a	117	22	10	15	0
Rotary weeding	4.3 a	7	7	12	5	0
No weeding	2.2 b	62	67	235	167	0
<i>Dry-sown rainfed banded rice^c</i>						
Oxadiazon	3.0 b	153	0	0	23	110
Hand weeding	4.0 a	138	3	23	17	22
No weeding	0 c	1430	28	5	20	33

^a Av. of two replications. Any two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^b Previously planted to corn + mung beans. ^c Previously planted to corn.

failed to adequately control annual grasses. Herbicide-treated plots yielded significantly higher, however, than did the untreated control.

Where rice was continuously grown, the yields from rotary-weeded and bentazon-treated plots were statistically similar and significantly higher than were the yields of nonweeded plots during the 1975 wet season (Table 16). Yields were 2 t/ha lower in the nonweeded plots because of heavy *S. maritimus* populations. Plots were also lightly infested with other lowland weed species, especially annual grasses and sedges.

In the lowland plots that had previously been planted to a corn-mung intercrop combination, yield increases were highly significant—4.3 t/ha—with rotary weeding. These were similar

to the yield increases from the bentazon treatment. The nonweeded treatment yielded only 2.2 t/ha—0.5 t/ha higher than did the nonweeded treatment in the continuous lowland plots—because weed density in the corn-mung rotation was only 167 plants/sq m while it was 325 plants/sq m in the continuous lowland rice (Table 16).

In the dry-sown, rainfed banded rice, the yields in the hand-weeded plots differed statistically from those in the oxadiazon-treated plots (Table 16). Populations of nutsedge (*Cyperus rotundus*) and annual grasses (*Echinochloa* spp.) were heavy on the oxadiazon-treated plots (Table 16). The untreated plots yielded nothing, due to a high buildup of annual grasses.

Irrigation and Water Management

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SUMMARY

A study of Philippine government investment in irrigation systems indicates that expansion in irrigated area in the late 1950's and early 1960's was a key factor in the shift from an area-increasing to a yield-increasing form of agricultural development which has continued up to the present. Before this shift, computed benefit:cost ratios for irrigation systems were gradually declining as the more attractive investment opportunities were exploited. But in the 1960's, this ratio was sharply increased by the higher yields of modern varieties. Year-to-year variation in the area programmed by government for new irrigation can be explained by the benefit:cost ratios during each year and the increasing scarcity of land that could be cultivated. The spread of modern varieties is a critical factor in the profitability of this investment, and has stimulated the expansion of irrigation far beyond what could have been expected without them.

A field study of a 5,000-ha irrigated area in Central Luzon revealed significantly lower nitrogen use by farmers who expected frequent and serious droughts. Optimum rates of N use were about double the mean rates actually used. Optimum N rates for farms with little likelihood of drought were much higher than for those farms where drought expectancy was greater. The mean rate of N use of the highest 10 percent of farmers closely approximated experimentally derived optimum values for all drought-susceptibility levels. If all farmers were to shift to the optimum N level, yields would increase by about 0.5 t/ha (19%) over the entire area. But if water adequacy were improved so that all farmers could apply optimum N rates with no moisture stress, yields would increase by 75 percent.

A study of a 1,000-ha rainfed watershed area in Central Luzon, Philippines, showed no significant differences in date of planting, age of seedlings, fertilizer use, days of drained fields, and grain yield among those farms located on high, intermediate, or low terraces. But highly significant differences in almost all of these variables were found between the rainfed farms and farms within an adjacent irrigation system.

A system to estimate *in situ* the daily rate of seepage and percolation of water into lowland rice fields was developed. The technique proved accurate relative to a check, and indicated that seepage and percolation rates for some areas where topsoil had been removed by land leveling were more than double the mean rate. We also developed a means of estimating grain yield by counting and weighing selected panicles. This technique does not require the harvest of a significant area.

INDUCEMENTS TO INVESTMENT IN PHILIPPINE IRRIGATION SYSTEMS

Inadequate water has often been identified as a major constraint to high yields of modern rice varieties. For the Philippines, we have investigated government trends in investment in irrigation systems, the relative profitability of these investments, and the influence of the new rice technology on both the trends and profitability.

Irrigation and agricultural development. In the late 1950's and early 1960's the source of agricultural growth in the Philippines changed significantly. Until then, Philippine agriculture followed the traditional growth pattern of Southeast Asia in which output increased primarily through the expansion of cultivated area. Around 1960, area expansion began to stagnate, and increased productivity of the land emerged as the more important factor accounting for output growth (Table 1).

Table 1. Contributions of area and of land productivity to growth in output of Philippine agriculture during two periods, 1948 to 1972.

Source of output growth by period	Av. annual growth (%)	Relative contribution (% of total)
Cultivated land area		
1948-62	3.4	83
1958-72	1.8	50
Output/ha of cultivated land area		
1948-62	0.7	17
1958-72	1.8	50
Total (both sources)		
1948-62	4.1	100
1958-72	3.6	100

Irrigation played a key role in this process. The expansion of irrigation infrastructure, measured by the ratio of irrigated area to total cultivated area, accelerated in the late 1950's as area growth began to stagnate. Philippine irrigation systems were built primarily to supply water for rice production which was also stimulated in the 1960's by the adoption of modern rice varieties and the increased use of fertilizer. For these combined reasons, land productivity has increased substantially since the mid-1960's (fig. 1).

Government has played the major role in irrigation development. The area reported as irrigated by major gravity systems of the National Irrigation Administration (NIA) increased from 110,800 ha in 1952 to 260,900 ha in 1960, and to 561,300 ha in 1975 (Table 2). The share of the NIA systems in total irrigable area also increased from about 20 percent to 35 percent. Meanwhile, the share of communal systems substantially declined. But government-assisted communal and pump irrigation expanded rapidly.

Inducements to irrigation expansion. A major question is whether the acceleration of government investment in irrigation in the late 1950's was in response to the increasing scarcity of newly cultivated land. Although the expansion of area under cultivation decelerated in the 1960's, the number of workers in agriculture continued to increase at about the same rate (fig. 1). As a result, cultivated area per worker began to decline toward the end of the 1950's, while irrigation development began to accelerate.

1. Trends from 1950 to 1970 of the ratio of irrigated to total cultivated area; the use of fertilizer (kg NPK/ha); the ratio of area planted in modern varieties to total rice crop area; and indices of rice yield per hectare and cultivated area per worker (1950 = 100). Philippines, 1950-1972.

These relationships lead to two hypotheses: 1) As land for agricultural production became increasingly scarce in the late 1950's, and as

Table 2. Irrigated areas under different types of systems. Philippines, selected years.

Date	National gravity systems ^a		Govt. assisted communal systems		Private communal systems		Pump irrigation systems		Others ^b		Total	
	(1000 ha)	(%)	(1000 ha)	(%)	(1000 ha)	(%)	(1000 ha)	(%)	(1000 ha)	(%)	(1000 ha)	(%)
1952	111	23	n.a. ^c	n.a. ^c	334	69	12	2	27	6	484	100
1955	138	25	37	7	334	60	18	3	28	5	554	100
1960	261	35	84	11	334	45	32	4	28	4	739	100
1965	319	34	154	16	374	40	60	6	29	3	935	100
1970	420	36	200	17	418	36	89	8	30	3	1158	100
1975	561	35	321	20	469	29	226	14	31	2	1607	100

^aFrom National Irrigation Administration reports. ^bIncludes Friar Land Irrigation Systems and municipal systems. ^cData not available.

Table 3. Estimates of benefit to cost (B:C) ratios for investment in irrigation development and in the opening of new land at 1970 constant prices.^a Philippines, selected periods.

Period	B:C for irrigation		B:C for land opening ^d	
	Traditional varieties ^b	Modern varieties ^c	Rice case	Corn case
1948-53	2.6	—	—	—
1953-57	2.4	—	—	—
1958-62	1.9	—	—	—
1963-67	1.9	—	—	—
1968-72	1.7	3.4	—	—
1970-74	1.5	3.1	0.9	1.3

^aBenefit flows are measured in terms of increased value added to agricultural production due to irrigation construction, by subtracting the increases in the value of current production inputs from the increased rice output. Both capital investment and reported operations and maintenance expenditures are included as costs. Capital costs are those of building National Irrigation Administration gravity systems during each 5-year period. The costs of opening new land are those of land resettlement projects of the Department of Agrarian Reform. ^bAssuming 15 kg N/ha. ^cAssuming 60 kg N/ha, and no modern varieties prior to 1968. ^dRice case assumes one crop of upland rice/year planted in newly settled area. Corn case assumes two crops of corn/year planted in newly settled areas.

the marginal cost of bringing additional land into cultivation rose sharply, it became cheaper to increase agricultural output by improving the quality of land than by external expansion of the area of cultivation; and 2) The diffusion of modern varieties and associated technology, which perform better in well-irrigated conditions, increased the relative advantage of developing irrigation infrastructure over opening new land, thereby increasing the incentive for irrigation investment.

As a partial test of these hypotheses, we estimated the benefit:cost (B:C) ratios and the internal rates of return for investments in irrigation construction and in the opening of new land. Trends were similar for these two criteria, so only the B:C data are reported here (Table 3). The calculations are based on estimates of yield response for traditional and modern varieties at different levels of nitrogen fertilizer.

Profitability decreased over time for investment in irrigation with a fixed agricultural technology, such as varietal type. This trend reflects the increasing difficulty and expense of developing irrigation projects because the less costly sites have gradually been developed. But this trend has been more than compensated for

by the development and diffusion of modern rice technology.

Because no time-series data are available, we could not analyze changes over time in costs and returns to investment in the opening of new land. But Table 3 clearly shows that the modern rice technology has made investment in irrigation much more profitable than opening new land, at least in the 1970's. Considering the deceleration in the expansion of cultivated area and the declining ratio of land to labor (fig. 1), it seems reasonable to infer that the costs of opening land have risen more rapidly than those of developing irrigation.

Causes of short-run fluctuations. The increasing profitability of irrigation development explains the secular trend in irrigation investment in the Philippines, but it does not sufficiently explain short-run fluctuations in that investment.

Annual government expenditure on irrigation has varied considerably. The initiation of new construction tends to be concentrated in those years during which world rice prices were rising, which we represent by the index of Thai export prices (fig. 2).

The first spurt in irrigation construction in the mid-1950's was clearly associated with sharp increases in the world price of rice due to the Korean War. The second spurt in the late 1960's was associated with the price rise due to the 1965-66 Indian famine. The third and most recent spurt was triggered by the poor worldwide crop in 1972. These associations suggest that the Philippine government has sought to stimulate domestic production through increased investment in irrigation to counteract high costs of rice imports in years of high rice prices.

The Philippine Government has achieved a major policy goal of supplying rice to domestic consumers at stable prices primarily by directly controlling importation and distribution. During years of low world prices, the government could import rice at a profit. But when world prices were high, rice was imported at a loss, seriously draining foreign exchange. As a result, the domestic price of rice in the Philippines has been more stable than the world price,

relative to the consumer price index (fig. 2). Considering the scarcity of funds and of foreign exchange in developing countries such as the Philippines, governments have strong incentives to increase domestic rice output to offset the rising cost of imports when prices are high.

We have estimated the B:C ratios for new NIA systems by incorporating the effects of improvements in rice varieties and technology and computing the increased value of the rice yield at current Thai export prices. These estimates are compared with increments in the area commanded by newly constructed NIA systems (fig. 2). The area is based on the year that the projects were initiated, while the B:C data are computed for projects completed in the year shown; both are 3-year moving averages.

Benefit:cost calculations for years prior to 1964 were based entirely on responses of traditional varieties. After 1964, the ratios are calculated separately for traditional and modern varieties, and their weighted means are taken as a single series, with estimated areas planted in the respective groups of varieties as weights. The dotted line shows what the trends in B:C ratios would have been if the improved rice varieties and technology had not been developed, assuming that actual prices would still prevail (fig. 2).

The remarkably close association between yearly movements in the newly constructed areas and the B:C ratios strongly support the hypothesis that short-run fluctuations in the allocation of government funds for irrigation infrastructure were induced by changes in the nominal rates of return to investment in irrigation, which in turn are subject to current price fluctuations.

Regression tests. From the above observations, we tested by regression analysis the hypothesis that variation in Philippine government investment in irrigation beginning in the late 1950's can be attributed to: a) an increasingly profitable trend in that investment relative to opening new land; and b) variation in the short-run profitability of irrigation investment due largely to year-to-year fluctuations in the world price of rice. We therefore related government investment in irrigation to an index of land scarcity and to the current

2. Irrigated areas for which construction was initiated by the National Irrigation Administration (3-year moving averages); index of current prices for Thai export rice and Philippine domestic rice (1950 = 100); and benefit:cost ratios of new NIA systems (current prices and 3-year moving averages), with and without modern varieties, by year. Philippines, 1950-1974.

rates of return to that investment.

The data used for the analysis include as the index of level of investment the yearly increment in irrigated area (Z) when new irrigation systems were initiated and, as the measure of rate of return, the corresponding B:C data used in fig. 2. The index of scarcity of land for cultivation (S) is calculated by:

$$S_t = \frac{M}{M - A_t}$$

where A_t is the area already cultivated in year t and M is the maximum area that can potentially be brought into cultivation. This formula assumes that the marginal cost of increasing a unit of cultivated area, which reflects the scarcity of land, rises exponentially with in-

creased area already under cultivation. M is assumed to be 14.2 million ha for the Philippines.

The estimation of a simple linear regression by ordinary least squares using 25 time-series observations for the years 1950–1974 is

$$Z_t = -90.5 + 16.9 (B/C)_t + 28.1 (S)_t$$

(7.43) (4.38)

$$R^2 = 0.74, \quad d = 1.13$$

where the t -values are enclosed by parentheses, R^2 is the coefficient of determination adjusted for degrees of freedom, and d is the Durban-Watson statistic. Both the $B:C$ ratio and the land scarcity index S were highly significant and together explained almost three fourths of the variation in the yearly increment of irrigated area constructed by NIA. The test of residual serial correlation was inconclusive at the 5-percent level of significance.

To consider possible distributed lag effects, a Koyck-Nerlove model was also estimated:

$$Z_t = -74.1 + 13.5 (B/C)_t + 22.3 (S)_t$$

(5.14) (3.25)

$$+ 0.34 (Z)_{t-1}$$

(2.25)

$$R^2 = 0.78, \quad d = 1.54.$$

The lag specification resulted in relatively minor improvement in overall goodness of fit and in modest changes in the estimates of the regression coefficients, but it significantly reduced the residual serial correlation. These results, together with a relatively large estimate of the adjustment coefficient (one minus the coefficient of Z_{t-1}), indicate rather quick responses in government investment to changes in the relative profitability of irrigation construction.

We should point out that while the results offer convincing explanations of variation in irrigation investment, they do not imply that the Philippine government always makes conscious decisions regarding yearly irrigation investment based on computed values of these variables. Although this direct mechanism may be used to some extent, the indirect ways in which a change in the $B:C$ ratio of irrigation investment affects the level of that investment are probably more important. Two examples of

indirect inducement are the public pressures for more rice to be produced in the Philippines during years of substantial purchases of costly imported rice, and the extent to which Philippine government financing of irrigation investment is contingent on the willingness of international lenders to underwrite the investment.

Inducement effects of modern varieties. To assess the effect of the modern varieties on irrigation investment, we compared the regression results with different $B:C$ ratios derived from data for traditional varieties. Our analysis assumes that the historical price of rice accurately reflects the price levels that could be expected if only traditional varieties were grown, since government policy has been to supplement reduced domestic supplies with imported rice at subsidized prices. Reductions in the $B:C$ ratios due to these assumptions are multiplied by the coefficient of the ratio in the first model to produce estimates of reduction in area for which NIA irrigation construction was initiated (Z). These hypothetical $B:C$ ratios and the area results are shown by dotted lines (fig. 2). If modern rice varieties and technology had not been developed, the predicted area for which construction was initiated since 1965 would have been 192,000 ha less, which is almost 35 percent of the total area commanded by NIA systems in 1975.

The results of these calculations illustrate the high degree of complementarity between irrigation and improved rice technology. Investment in irrigation has been an important stimulant for the diffusion of modern varieties, but the modern varieties and associated rice technology have also induced irrigation investment by raising its rate of return.

NITROGEN USE IN AREAS OF UNSTABLE IRRIGATION

Water supply varies widely among farms within the command area of major irrigation systems, depending on year-to-year availability of water to the system and on topographic and spatial factors associated with each farm's location within the system. We previously reported the variable incidence of drought in a pilot project within the Peñaranda River Irrigation System

(1974 Annual Report). In 1975, we investigated along with drought incidence the differential use of nitrogen fertilizer by farmers who expect droughts of different severity.

Nitrogen use was selected for study because of its importance in achieving high yields, and the well-developed methodology for computing N response. Nitrogen also costs more than any other cash production item for most farms.

Our hypothesis is that farmers use more N in areas where they expect plentiful water, and apply less where they expect major droughts. This is consistent with the general understanding that N and water are complementary inputs for high yields, and that higher nitrogen applications do not greatly increase the yields of crops stunted by drought. If the hypothesis is true, increased use of N is an important source of yield benefit attributable to better irrigation, in addition to the direct physiologic effect of adequate water on rice growth and yield (1973 Annual Report).

The objectives of this study were to determine whether farmers who expect more severe droughts tend to use less nitrogen; to estimate current and optimum levels of N use and water adequacy; and to estimate how much production would increase if all farmers applied N at optimum rates.

The study was undertaken jointly with the Upper Pampanga River Project of the Philippine National Irrigation Administration during the 1973–74 wet and dry seasons on a pilot area of approximately 5,700 ha irrigated by lateral C of the Peñaranda River Irrigation System, Gapan, Nueva Ecija province, Philippines. A total of 411 sample paddies were selected within the area on a grid basis at spacing of 360 m (fig. 3).

Those farmers whose paddies were observed were interviewed during both seasons to determine their expectations of drought, their use of N and other inputs, and their attitudes on how adequacy of water affects their N use. As a measure of water adequacy, we used the number of years in 10 for which the respondent expected a serious drought, which was defined as a shortage of irrigation supply resulting in complete crop loss on at least part of his farm.

Farmers' estimates were checked by monitoring the water status of the sample paddies

3. Observation paddies in the service area of Lateral C, Peñaranda River Irrigation System, Gapan, Nueva Ecija province, Philippines.

throughout both seasons of 1973–74. Field personnel of the irrigation system took three readings per week from a short piezometer tube to measure the depth of water above or below the soil surface. The data were then converted to stress days, or days for which the paddy had no standing water. Crop cuts were also taken to estimate yield from the same paddies.

In the wet season, relatively few farmers expected serious drought; we are therefore reporting only the dry season results. Data from only 226 of the 411 sample farms were available for analysis for the dry season, however, because the water supply was not sufficient for farmers to plant a second crop on the remainder of the area.

Nitrogen use and drought years. Data for the dry season were grouped into mean responses of farmers who expected 0 drought years

Table 4. Nitrogen use, yield, and total rice production by expected frequency of drought year, mean recorded values, and efficiency levels. Lateral C, Peñaranda River Irrigation System, Gapan, Nueva Ecija province, Philippines. 1974 dry season.

Frequency of expected drought years (yr in 10)	Observations (no.)	Area (ha)	Nitrogen use (kg N/ha)			Yield (t/ha)			Production (1000 t)		
			Actual	Effic ₁ ^a	Effic ₂ ^b	Actual	Effic ₁ ^a	Effic ₂ ^b	Actual	Effic ₁ ^a	Effic ₂ ^b
0	130	1685	45	100	118	2.43	2.91	3.00	4.09	4.90	5.06
1-2	66	855	43	96	92	2.39	2.79	2.77	2.04	2.39	2.37
3-6	17	220	39	91	84	2.34	2.64	2.59	0.51	0.58	0.57
7-10	13	168	39	77	70	2.03	2.22	2.17	0.34	0.37	0.36
Av. or total	226	2929	44	97	105	2.39	2.81	2.85	6.99	8.24	8.35

^aEfficiency₁ is based on N production functions derived from farm-level experiments in the 1974 dry season. ^bEfficiency₂ is based on mean rates of use for the highest 10% N users in each drought group, 1974 dry season.

(DY) in 10 years, 1 DY, 2 DY, 3-6 DY, and 7-10 DY. More than half of the respondents were in the 0 DY group. We combined the responses for four yearly intervals into the 3-6 and 7-10 DY groups because the number of observations for those expected frequencies was limited.

Both mean N use and yields decreased as the number of expected drought years increased. To test the significance of these trends, we computed the regression of N use on DY. To reduce variation due to causes other than drought expectancy, we used the means for each DY group (5 observations) rather than individual data for each farm (226 observations). Since the number of observations and the variance of N use are different for each DY group, the contribution of each mean was weighted in the computations by the number of observations divided by the variance.

Mean N use ranged from 45 kg N/ha for the 0 DY group to 39 kg N/ha for the 7-10 DY group (Table 4). Essentially all this difference is accounted for between 0 and 3-6 DY; drought expectancy in excess of the latter group was not reflected in less N use. We therefore fitted a cube root function (fig. 4) to account for the curved relationship, and computed

$$N = 45 - 3.3(DY)^{1/3} \\ (2.91)$$

$$r^2 = 0.78; \text{ No.} = 5; F_{1,3} = 10.4^*$$

where N is N use, DY is drought years in 10, and F is the test of the hypothesis that the change in N use with increasing DY is signi-

ficantly different from zero. We concluded that N use in 1974 was significantly less for farmers whose drought expectancy was higher, but only up to 3-6 DY in 10.

The definition of DY in the farmer interviews was the relatively severe one of complete loss of at least part of one's crop. Using other definitions, we also interviewed to see whether less severe drought expectancy confirmed the same trend. Reclassification of the sample according to expected frequency of "major drought," defined as periods of water shortage of 25 days or more, leading only to reduced yield, resulted in slightly greater N use at higher DY levels. This was not expected, but it could mean that farmers recognize that one effect of a major drought is the loss through volatilization and subsequent leaching of much of the N already applied, and that they will get high yields only if they apply additional N after the drought to compensate for the loss (1972 Annual Report). But for the more severe droughts leading to crop failure, farmers do not buy additional N because crop recovery is doubtful.

A factor that probably reduced the variation in N use by DY was a vigorous extension program launched in 1974 through which farmers received production credit loans for inputs such as N. The portion of these loans intended for N was given in the form of coupons redeemable only for fertilizer at the rate of 60 kg N/ha, a condition which resulted in more uniform N use in the area.

The assessment of stress days during the 1974 dry season showed higher stress levels than expected for all DY levels. This was partly due

to the yearly rotation of priority among different subsystems of the Peñaranda River Irrigation System. In 1974 the study area did not have first priority for available water, and water was insufficient on many of its farms. This also explains why only slightly more than half of the area was planted during that dry season. Mean stress days recorded for the 0 DY group was 24.7, and for the 7–10 DY group, 36.2.

Mean grain yield declined consistently from 2.43 to 2.03 t/ha from the 0 to the 7–10 DY groups (Table 4).

Optimum levels of N use. Our analysis of mean rates of N use obscures the wide range of variation in individual farmers' use. Some farmers applied none at all, while others, usually those in well-irrigated areas, applied much more than that recommended by the national extension program. We therefore estimated economically optimum levels of N use for the different drought year conditions, and compared these levels with the mean rates actually used.

Determination of an optimum point requires a production function relating yield to N input and a price ratio relating the cost of N to the price of rice. A production function was fitted from the data collected for the 226 sample paddies, but the uncontrolled nature of the survey resulted in excessive variation for some variables and in correlation among several independent variables resulting in a loss of significance for key coefficients in the model. We therefore used the production function computed from a series of controlled experiments conducted by IRRI economists in the same pilot area and in a nearby system during the same 1973–74 seasons (1974 Annual Report). In these experiments, controlled N treatments were 0, 50, 100, and 150 kg N/ha on plots that otherwise received the same levels of inputs found on farms in the area. The effect of drought was measured by stress days as defined earlier. An adequate range of drought was assured by duplicating the experiment at 11 locations for which water adequacy was quite varied. Thus, although the data were derived from controlled experiments, they were collected from on-farm plots and represented well-managed farm-level conditions. The variety used was IR20, the

dominant variety in the area.

The complete production function estimated from these data was a multiple regression model incorporating the combined yield effects of N, N², stress days during vegetative growth (S₁), stress days during reproductive growth (S₂), interactions of S₁, S₂, and solar radiation with N, and other factors such as weed control, seedling age, insect damage, soil texture, and phosphorus fertilizer use. More than 67 percent of yield variation was explained by the model.

Preliminary fitting of the model to the farm-level N-use data collected from Lateral C in the 1974 dry season revealed that the experimentally derived functions overestimated mean yields in each DY group by about 300 kg/ha. This is not surprising in view of the better management exercised over the plots, even though the quantities of inputs used were similar to farmers' use. This difference would bias our computations of yield gain derived from farmers' shifting from actual to efficiency levels of N use, however, so we have deflated the intercept of the model by 300 kg/ha. Substituting mean values of the other factors into the model, it can thus be simplified to:

$$Y = 2520 + 19.5(N) - 0.051(N^2) - 2.6(S_1) - 46.0(S_2) + 0.62(NS_1) - 0.63(NS_2).$$

This equation can in turn be reduced to a family of nitrogen responses when the appropriate stress-day values are substituted corresponding to the means found for the different DY groups. This was done using 9.7 and 15.0 for S₁ and S₂ for the 0 DY group, and 13.6 and 22.5 for the 7–10 DY group. The intermediate functions were fit using stress-day values interpolated between those of the two extreme DY groups to simplify further analysis. Another function was computed for S₁ = S₂ = 0 to reflect N response in the absence of any stress days.

The resulting curves (fig. 4) support our assumption that N response is steeper and that higher levels of N are justified for the lower DY frequencies. There is not as much spread between the curves as expected, however, due to the relatively small difference in mean stress days found for the different DY groups. The reason for this is that stress days recorded in

4. Nitrogen response functions for different drought-year conditions with efficiency levels of N indicated by broken line. Lateral C, Peñaranda River Irrigation Systems, Gapan, Nueva Ecija province, Philippines, 1974 dry season.

the 1974 dry season were relatively high, and were found in all DY categories, including the 0 DY group. To some extent this was due to a simultaneous pilot project designed to distribute the limited water supply as equitably as possible among all farms planted in the area. If the study area had received higher water priority within the system in 1974, the mean number of stress days would have been substantially less, and one or more of the DY groups would have approached the curve derived from 0 stress days (fig. 4).

Optimum levels of N use can now be calculated from these curves. The theoretical point of optimum return is that point where the marginal cost of additional N is equal to the value of the additional rice produced. This can be calculated once the price ratio of N to rice is specified. That ratio was estimated as 3:1 based on 1973-74 data. But the theoretical optimum does not take into account the costs of securing and applying the N, nor the uncertainty of response. Thus, more realistic optimum points can be found at lower levels than those specified by the theoretical optimum. We determined for each DY group an "efficiency level" of N use by calculating the point at which the marginal value of rice production is two

times the marginal cost of additional N. These N efficiency use levels are indicated on the production functions (fig. 4), and are plotted as efficiency₁ against DY (fig. 5).

The production function analysis provides a rigorous derivation of efficiency levels of N use for different DY groups, but a careful analysis of the N-use data for the 1974 dry season suggests an alternate method of estimating efficient N levels. We observed that mean N use did not decline more sharply with increased DY because many farmers in all drought groups applied no N at all. This depressed the mean value, particularly for the lower DY categories which also included some high N use data. Thus, if only the higher N users in each group are considered, the trend in N use would more strongly confirm the original hypothesis, and it might more closely relate to efficiency levels of N use. To explore this, we computed the average N use for each DY group based on the mean for only those 10 percent of farmers using the most nitrogen in each group. In all cases we used at least three observations, however, to reduce the instability caused by means from only one or two farmers. The results can be fitted to the cube root model to give

$$N = 118 - 22.5(DY)^{1/3}; \quad (3.03)$$

$$r^2 = 0.82; \quad \text{no.} = 4.$$

This alternate efficiency function, or efficiency₂, can be plotted and compared with actual N use and with the production function estimates, or efficiency₁ (fig. 5). Both efficiency estimates have steeper slopes than the mean recorded data. Actual N use averages about half the efficiency amounts, and is particularly low at the 0 DY level. The two measures of efficiency are reasonably close to each other, although efficiency₂ combines a steeper response at low DY levels with a more modest slope at the higher levels. One cause of the difference between the two efficiency curves is that efficiency₁ is based on stress-day data for one season—a season for which the number of stress days was quite high and uniform across all DY groups—while efficiency₂ reflects what we assume to be efficient N use based on the

experience of a select group of farmers over many years.

Comparison of reported and efficient production levels. Using the estimates of actual and efficient levels of N use (fig. 5), we can now trace the yield and production changes attributable to a shift from actual to efficient N use. In this analysis 1 DY and 2 DY are combined into a single DY group since there is little difference between the two individual categories. Yields are computed from the N responses (fig. 4), and production is computed as yield times area, where each observation represents approximately 13 ha in our sample.

Shifting from actual to efficient N use levels, but assuming the same water adequacy as that of 1974, would result in an increase in the crop-cut yield data of about 0.5 t/ha over the entire area (Table 4). Among the different DY groups, 0 DY would produce the largest yield increase, and 7–10 DY the smallest. Efficiency defined by the three highest N users resulted in slightly higher estimates of yield, particularly for 0 DY, than efficiency derived from the production functions.

Total rice production from the 2,929-ha area farmed in the 1974 dry season would thus increase from about 7,000 t to about 8,300 t, an increase of 19 percent. Most of this gain in production is contributed by the lowest DY groups, which have the greatest yield increases and largest area planted.

If N were used at efficiency levels and, simultaneously, water adequacy were improved, the production gain would be still larger. In this case, all production would shift from the several DY functions to one function which represents efficient water management. For the 1974 dry season, the most efficient water-use function is that of the 0 DY case, but ideal water adequacy is reflected in the 0 stress-day function (fig. 4). Zero stress days may not be attainable in the short run because of structural and management problems not yet solved in large systems, but dry-season data from other systems indicate that stress days can be reduced to levels near zero. We therefore present computed yields and total production for both the 0 DY case and for 0 stress days (Table 5).

The results indicate that yields and produc-

5. Alternate approximations of efficiency levels of N use and mean actual N use by expected drought years in 10. Efficiency₁ derived from experimental production functions, and efficiency₂ from highest 10 percent of N users. Lateral C, Peñaranda River Irrigation System, Gapan, Nueva Ecija province, Philippines, 1974 dry season.

tion would increase only marginally, about 5 percent, beyond mean yields with efficient N if water adequacy over the whole area were improved to the 0 DY level. But if zero stress day is the criterion of efficient water use, yields would increase to 4.2 t/ha, and production to more than 12,200 t, an increase over efficient N and variable water of 48 percent, and 75 percent greater than actual production in the 1974 dry season.

Table 5. Comparison of mean nitrogen use, grain yield, and rice production from 2,929 ha based on actual data, efficient use of nitrogen with actual water management, and efficient use of both nitrogen and water combined. Lateral C, Peñaranda River Irrigation System, Gapan, Nueva Ecija province, Philippines, 1974 dry season.

Basis of comparison	N use (kg N/ha)	Yield (t/ha)	Production (1000 t)
<i>Actual data</i>	44	2.39	6.99
<i>Efficient nitrogen use based on:</i>			
Highest 10% of N users	105	2.85	8.35
Optima from functions	97	2.81	8.24
<i>Efficient N and water use combined based on:</i>			
Highest 10% of N users	118	3.00	8.79
Optima from functions:			
0 drought years	100	2.91	8.52
0 stress days	133	4.18	12.24

This analysis includes only the yield effects of more efficient distribution of water on land that is currently irrigated. If we assume that efficient use of water results in increases in the area irrigated as well as in yields, the gain in production would be far greater. But since there are trade-offs between more adequately irrigating a given area and expanding the area irrigated, we believe this is a conservative estimate of the increase in production that is possible on currently irrigated land.

Nitrogen policy will be an essential tool to achieve rates of N use more nearly equal to efficiency levels. As long as water adequacy continues to be highly variable among farms, N policy must also be flexible to permit each farmer to approach the best rate for his specific conditions of land and water.

Although important production gains can be expected from higher rates of N use, these gains will be four times greater if combined with adequate water throughout the dry season.

RAINFED AREA OBSERVATIONS

The command area of Lateral C of the Peñaranda River Irrigation System is adjacent to a series of rainfed terraces draining from the foothills of the Sierra Madre mountains. While collecting irrigation data, we also monitored for comparative purposes the farm management and water status of a 1-km wide portion of this rainfed area just east of Lateral C in Gapan, Nueva Ecija province (fig. 3). We analyzed differences within the rainfed area due to topography, and compared some of these findings with the 1973 wet-season data from the irrigated area.

Numerous creeks intersect the gently rolling area and drain excess rainfall from the fields. Although the general slope is toward the west, water drains overland from one paddy to the next in many directions and for varying distances before finally reaching a creek. We therefore selected sample paddies from three strata along the watershed: paddies near the top of a series, which receive relatively little water from higher fields; those in an intermediate regime; and paddies far down the slope, which receive excess water from the

larger watershed above. We thus considered relative rather than absolute elevation in selecting 44 observation paddies within these strata. By rough estimates aided by aerial photographs we located the higher group of paddies within the top 10–20 percent of the slopes, and the lower group within the bottom 10–20 percent. The intermediate sample paddies were located within the 40–60 percent range. Every week we estimated the number of stress days, or days during which each observation paddy had no standing water on the soil surface. We also interviewed those who farmed the observation sites to collect data on management practices. At harvest, we collected crop-cut yield samples.

The results show modest differences among the three groups, but they are not significant at the 5-percent level for any variable measured (Table 6). The top group had slightly more stress days and slightly lower yield than the others, but date of planting and nitrogen use were about average. In the intermediate group, values were intermediate for most variables.

One reason that the differences were not greater was that the distribution of rainfall was relatively even during the 1973 wet season, and about average for the area (fig. 6). The level of rainfall was approximately equal to the mean over the past several years. The few weeks when rainfall was less than 50 mm were generally followed by weeks of plentiful rainfall. A season with less rainfall might bring out greater mean differences. But from this study, we cannot conclude that the water environment of lower terraces is significantly better for rainfed rice production than that of intermediate or higher terraces.

Highly significant differences in the same factors were found, however, between the irrigated and rainfed areas (Table 6). Although irrigated farms had almost as many stress days as rainfed farms, their yields were significantly higher because nitrogen use was significantly greater and soil conditions were better. The irrigated area immediately adjacent to the rainfed study site (the first half of the lateral C command area) had significantly fewer stress days than the downstream half or the rainfed study area. But in other respects, mean dif-

Table 6. Mean dates of transplanting, fertilizer use, days of moisture stress, and yields for rainfed farms at different elevations and for irrigated farms at different locations with an irrigation system.^a Gapan, Nueva Ecija province, 1973 wet season.

Location	Observations (no.)	Seedling age (days)	Date of transplanting	Nitrogen use (kg N/ha)	Phosphorus use (kg P ₂ O ₅ /ha)	Stress days			Yield (t/ha)
						Early	Late	Total	
Rainfed: relative elevation									
High	14	34 a	Aug. 6 a	41 ab	30 abc	2.4 abc	18.9 a	21.2 b	1.2 a
Intermediate	16	29 a	Jul. 28 a	40 a	35 a	0.7 ab	17.4 a	18.1 b	1.4 a
Low	14	31 a	Aug. 14 a	40 a	36 a	0.2 a	12.6 abc	12.8 ab	1.4 a
Irrigated: portion of system									
Upstream	174	30 a	Jul. 25 a	55 b	34 ab	1.5 b	9.2 b	10.7 a	3.2 b
Downstream	232	31 a	Aug. 10 a	51 b	19 d	3.4 c	13.8 c	17.2 b	3.2 b
Both (av.)	406	31 a	Aug. 3 a	53 b	26 c	2.6 c	11.8 bc	14.4 ab	3.2 b

^aMeans in the same column followed by the same letter are not significantly different.

ferences between the two irrigated portions were not significant during the 1973 wet season.

MEASUREMENT SYSTEMS FOR IRRIGATION

Seepage and percolation instrumentation. Water supplied to lowland rice fields can be accounted for by evapotranspiration (ET) into the atmosphere, by surface drainage (DR) from the fields, and by seepage and percolation (S&P) into the soil. ET cannot easily be measured in the field, but relatively accurate methods have been developed for estimating potential ET from evaporation pan data. Surface drainage can be measured, although usually with difficulty, by conventional measuring devices such as flumes.

Methods of measuring S&P include lysimeter techniques in which the crop is planted in small tanks filled with soil. The percolate can be collected from the bottom of the tanks and measured. Two or more tanks are sometimes used, one with an impervious bottom to eliminate all S&P, and the other open at the bottom. When the two are independently supplied to a common reference, the difference in total water use can be taken as a measure of water movement into the soil.

The chief problems with lysimeters are discontinuities caused by the tank walls, the disturbed and unrepresentative condition of the soil after filling the tanks, and the tendency to measure only the percolation to deeper depths. Seepage, the lateral movement of water in the soil, is often more important than percolation.

For these reasons, S&P is usually not measured directly but is computed as a residual after measuring or estimating all other components of the water balance for rice. This method has revealed mean daily S&P rates of about 2–4 and 3–6 mm/day under Philippine wet and dry season conditions, respectively, but individual locations have been found with rates of more than 17 mm/day (1972 Annual Report).

One advantage of the water balance accounting of S&P is that the estimate is a weighted average over a large area. Point measurements are useful in finding the effects of local soil or topographical conditions, but they are difficult to integrate into a mean value representative of large areas. Collecting data for the complete water balance is, however, very arduous and expensive, since one must account for all water

6. Weekly rainfall for the rainfed study areas adjacent to Lateral C, Gapan, Nueva Ecija province, Philippines, 1973 wet season.

entering and leaving a site. The wide and unpredictable fluctuations in flow of the many irrigation sources and drains serving typical lowland areas make these measurements difficult and inaccurate. Furthermore, S&P values are often less than 5 percent of the total water accounted for, so that inaccuracies in the irrigation or drainage measurements could easily result in individual S&P values that are too high or too low by an order of magnitude.

The purpose of this project was to develop and test an instrument that will estimate S&P without requiring flow measurement, and that can be applied to undisturbed soils *in situ*. We tested the instrument by comparing the mean values for S&P from it with S&P values computed as a residual from the complete water balance for the same area. We also measured differences in S&P in areas where the topsoil had been removed to different depths.

The study was carried out in the 1975 dry season at the pilot land consolidation area of 123 ha previously reported on which topsoil had been removed to varying depths up to 50 cm by land leveling (1974 Annual Report). Ten sources of water and drains serving the area were fitted with Parshall flumes and recorders for continuous flow measurement. Personnel of the Philippine National Irrigation Administration helped collect the data.

The principle underlying the test instrument is simply that the water loss from a rice paddy can be accounted for through ET, DR, and S&P. If no water were added to nor drained from the system, then total water used would be $ET + S\&P$, and would be reflected by a corresponding subsidence or loss of head of the water on the paddy surface. Assuming that daily ET were computed from evaporation pan data and subtracted from this head loss, the remainder of the daily fall in water level would be equal to the S&P rate. The principal operating assumption is negligible flow of overland water into or out of the paddy (fig. 7).

Since the daily head loss of paddy water averages less than 1 cm, we inclined a meter stick at a 5:1 slope above the soil surface to permit magnified and more accurate readings of head loss by the formula:

$$S\&P_t = \frac{(WD_{t-1} - WD_t)}{0.5} - ET_t, \text{ and}$$

$$ET_t = 0.5 + a(EV_t)$$

where t refers to the day of measurement; WD is the water depth measurement in millimeters on the meter stick; ET is the daily rate of evapotranspiration; EV is the daily rate of evaporation in millimeters per day; and a is 0.8 for the first 6 weeks of crop growth and 0.9 for the remaining weeks (1972 Annual Report). If

7. Technique used to estimate field losses due to seepage and percolation. IRRI, 1975.

Table 7. Water balance components on a 123-ha land consolidation site. Sibul, Talavera, Nueva Ecija province, Philippines, 1975 dry season.

	Component (mm)					
	Irrigation	Rainfall	Drainage	Net water use	Evapo-transpiration ^a	Seepage and percolation ^b
April	444	0	-53	391	-161	-230
May	471	105	-165	411	-166	-246
June	237	168	-127	277	-104	-173
Total	1151	273	-344	1080	-431	-649
Daily mean	12.6	3.0	-3.8	11.8	-4.7	-7.1

^aCalculated from evaporation data (see text for equation). ^bResidual of net water used minus estimated evapotranspiration.

rainfall is added to the system, its value should be added to the calculated S&P rate, provided the rain does not result in flow across the paddy dikes that form the system's borders (fig. 7).

There are, of course, many days when farmers irrigate or drain their fields, or heavy rains result in flow over paddy dikes. We still recorded WD on such days, but noted that water spillage occurred so that the S&P rate would not be calculated. Thus, S&P values are computed only for days when no spillage could be detected (from 20% to 50% of all days in this study). Since it is often difficult to know whether or not spillage has occurred during the previous 24 hours, brightly colored corks can be placed on the spillways of the paddy dikes surrounding the test paddies. Any corks missing from their spillways can be presumed to have been washed away by overland flow.

The water balance for the 3 months following transplanting showed that more than 1 m net of water was applied to the area after subtracting surface drainage (Table 7). About 649 mm could be attributed to S&P, a rate of 7.1 mm/day. Water use efficiency (the sum of ET + S&P divided by total water supplied) averaged 76 percent, which is similar to other findings for the dry season (1972 Annual Report). The area was adequately supplied with water throughout the period of study.

Fifteen test instruments were installed in four areas stratified according to the depth to which the topsoil had been removed. Mean S&P values and their weighted mean were computed for each stratum. Weights were assigned according to the number of instruments per stratum (Table 8). The weighted mean was 6.4 mm/day, which is within 10 percent of the

corresponding value derived from the water balance. No significant difference was found in mean S&P rates for depths of topsoil removal between 0 and 30 cm, but for those areas where the topsoil had been removed to a depth greater than 30 cm, the S&P rate was more than double that for the other strata, a significant increase.

The sampling problem inherent in point measurement could be one reason for the minor difference in mean rates between the two techniques. For example, if the deeply scraped areas are actually greater in extent than indicated on maps, then the high S&P rate for that stratum should have more weight in computing the weighted mean, which would then be higher and closer to 7.1 mm/day.

These instruments for measuring S&P are accurate enough for most field applications, particularly where soil conditions are relatively homogeneous. They are inexpensive to build and install, and much simpler to read than the flow devices used with the complete water balance. They provide estimates of seepage as

Table 8. Daily seepage and percolation rates for areas in which topsoil had been removed to different depths. Land consolidation project, Sibul, Talavera, Nueva Ecija province, Philippines, 1975 dry season.

Depth of topsoil removal (cm)	Instruments (no.)	Usable daily observations (no.)	Mean seepage and percolation rate ^a (mm/day)
0	5	118	5.6 a
0-15	3	68	5.4 a
15-30	5	96	5.1 a
30-50	2	26	12.9 b
Av. or total	15	308	6.4

^aMean S&P values followed by the same letter are not significantly different.

well as of percolation and can be applied directly to an undisturbed soil system. Care must be taken, however, to place the instruments in soil and topographic strata that represent the area properly.

Measurement of water flow in open canals. We previously reported difficulties in measuring water flow in irrigation canals, and described a measuring device designed to accommodate these problems (1973 Annual Report). In 1975, we developed another technique to cheaply and reliably measure canal flow.

The principle of this device is that water loses head or elevation in passing through a constricted section such as a culvert. If the section is filled entirely with water, the flow of water through it is proportional to the square root of the difference in water head between the inlet and outlet, provided the approach conditions remain constant. Inverted siphons, a type of canal structure, possess most of these properties. An inverted siphon is a large concrete structure designed to carry water underneath a highway or other obstruction that intersects a canal route. The ends of the siphon are open at both sides of the road so that water can enter and flow through. Head loss is usually con-

siderable when large volumes of water pass through a siphon, and the approach geometry is roughly similar for different elevations of water. Almost all siphons in Philippine canal systems are fully submerged, i.e. the culvert under the highway is always completely full of water even when the flow rate is zero.

Instrumentation is based on the equation $Q = K (H_1 - H_2)^{0.5}$ where Q is the flow rate (cu m/s), and H_1 and H_2 are the surface elevations of water (cm) at the inlet and outlet, respectively. The velocity and friction head losses are not independently evaluated but are included in the overall constant, K .

The chief problems in measuring head loss are to accurately measure the two water stages and to accurately relate one to the other. Separate measuring systems at the inlet and outlet must be carefully pre-set to a common reference elevation, which is difficult to maintain over time. Therefore we constructed a pulley system to measure directly the difference in head between the inlet and outlet elevations (fig. 8). The system has these advantages: only one water-level recorder is required for continuous measurement; reference bias is eliminated since there is no necessity to make independent zero settings for inlet and outlet elevations and calculations are simplified through direct reading of $(H_1 - H_2)$.

Two adjacent stilling wells that can be connected by pipe to the two ends of the siphon are required. The instrument can be zeroed by opening a valve to equilibrate the water elevations in the two stilling wells.

We attached this measuring system to the 45-year-old concrete siphon at the 12.9-km station of lateral C, Peñaranda River Irrigation System. This 2-bay siphon carries water for 40 m underneath a creek bed.

The coefficient of discharge K was determined through field calibration by current meter. Data from 13 trials over 12 months resulted in a best fit relationship that does not conform closely to the expected square root relationship, although it does explain more than 91 percent of the variation in discharge (fig. 9). The computed equation is

$$Q = 0.312 (H_1 - H_2)^{0.75}.$$

8. Pulley arrangement for continuous recording of the difference in two water elevations in a standard inverted siphon. IRRI, 1975.

Further research is needed on the velocities of approach and discharge to explain why the exponent was not closer to 0.5. Also, the device was not capable of accurately measuring flows of less than 0.2 cu m/s due to the small head loss associated with such low rates of flow.

The principal advantages of this instrument are its compactness and low cost, its suitability for continuous recording instruments, its adaptability to existing structures, and its continuing accuracy over time. Installation requires a minimum of plumbing and housing, and the measuring system is closed and protected from passers-by. Weeds and debris floating in the canal do not affect measurement since the water carries them through the siphon. A major drawback is the laborious flow measurement by current meter required to accurately calibrate each installation. Initial calibration should remain constant over many years, however, since the internal roughness and the cross-section of a concrete siphon will not change much over time.

Yield estimates over large areas. The two techniques for estimating grain yield now most commonly used are crop-cut sampling and farmer interviews. Crop cuts involve actual harvesting of at least 8 sq m of standing crop taken from two or more locations within a paddy; threshing the sample; weighing the grain; and expressing the weight, corrected to 14 percent moisture, per unit area sampled. Although this technique is well adapted to plot experiments in which most of each plot is harvested, it is expensive and time-consuming when applied to several thousand hectares, such as specially irrigated areas where we assess grain yield to gauge the performance of different methods of irrigation.

Surveys in which farmers are asked their production and the area that they farm are much easier to implement and to apply to broader areas, such as entire farms, rather than to individual plots or paddies. Farmers are usually quite willing to discuss these questions, but there is evidence that reported yields are significantly low relative to data obtained from crop cutting, even after accounting for normal post-harvest losses (1973 Annual Report). Therefore, we are investigating new methods of

9. Discharge flow (cu m/s) as a function of head loss (cm) through an inverted siphon with calibration points. Lateral C, Peñaranda River Irrigation System, Gapan, Nueva Ecija province, Philippines, 1973-1975.

estimating grain yield that are relatively accurate but less expensive and less time-consuming than crop cutting when applied to large areas.

Our most promising technique at present is similar to crop cutting except that we harvest selected panicles rather than complete plots. The procedure is: 1) X - Y axes of about 2 m in length are laid out in the field; 2) the number of panicles along the X axis is computed by adding the number of effective panicles for each hill along the axis; 3) a specified number of panicles (usually six) are randomly harvested from each hill along the X axis; 4) these panicles are threshed and the mean corrected grain weight per panicle is computed; 5) the sample weight per panicle is multiplied by the total number of panicles along the X axis to compute the total grain weight for that row of hills; 6) this total weight per row along the X axis is then multiplied by the number of hills, i.e. rows, along the Y axis to compute the total weight over the 2- x 2-m sample area; 7) the procedure is repeated by sampling panicles along the Y rather than the X axis, and the plot estimate is the mean of these two yield calculations; 8) two such plot estimates are made for each paddy, and their mean is the final yield estimate for each observation.

This procedure was relatively easy to follow in the field. Some modifications were made, such as using a variable length of X and Y to more accurately account for hill spacing. A portable

10. Comparison of estimates of grain yield by crop-cut and panicle-sample methods. Gapan. Nueva Ecija province. Philippines, 1973 dry season.

moisture meter and weighing balance were used at a nearby field office.

To check this technique, complete crop-cut samples were also harvested from the panicle-sampled plots, using a common X—Y axis for both. The paired t-test did not reveal significant differences at the 5-percent level between the two methods of yield estimation, but the panicle-sample means were somewhat higher than the crop-cut means. Therefore, we plotted the data and computed the prediction equations

by which the panicle samples could be related to the crop-cut estimates without bias (fig. 10). Separate regression estimates were made for the four seasons in which the study was conducted (Table 9).

Analyzing the data, we see that the panicle-sampling technique clearly overestimates grain yield, especially at high yield levels, although this effect can be controlled by the prediction equations. Overestimation is probably caused by the tendency to sample taller, and therefore heavier, panicles from each hill. A partial solution to this problem is to increase the number of panicles sampled per hill. Goodness of fit was considerably improved for those seasons when the sampling density was increased from 4 to 6 panicles/hill (Table 9), when one varietal type was widely grown, and when we carefully trained people to do the sampling.

The technique appears to be a workable compromise between the estimates of grain yield by complete crop cut and by farm interview. It does not require the field man to pay the farmer for the sample, as in crop cuts; in fact, for large-scale work, census-type enumerators would not necessarily have to locate the farmer and secure his permission for the sampling since very little grain is removed.

Table 9. Regression estimates of grain yield sampled by complete crop cut (Y) from panicle samples (X). Selected seasons. Gapan, Nueva Ecija province, Philippines.

Period	Regression equation	Panicles sampled (no./hill)	R ²	Observations (no.)
1973 dry season	$Y = 0.35 + 0.71 X$	6	0.82	158
1973 wet season	$Y = 1.21 + 0.54 X$	4	0.50	126
	$Y = 0.10 + 1.18 X - 0.09 X^2$	4	0.52	126
1974 dry season	$Y = 0.40 + 0.67 X$	6	0.73	135
	$Y = 1.30 - 0.10 X - 0.44 X^2$	6	0.78	135
1975 dry season	$Y = 0.74 + 0.58 X$	5 & 6	0.61	143
	$Y = 0.31 + 0.81 X - 0.29 X^2$	5 & 6	0.67	143

Soil and crop management

Soil and crop management

Soil characterization

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SUMMARY

In 1975, research on soil and crop management focused on soil characterization, microbiological investigations of soil fertility management, soil fertility and fertilizer management, and soil and crop culture.

Factors that were found to limit the growth of rice on a peat soil were deficiencies of NPK; these could be corrected with an application of NPK fertilizer. However, the effects were greater when the fertilizer was applied to an air-dried soil presubmerged for 2 weeks than when applied to a soil that had been continuously submerged. Both zinc and copper were found to be deficient in the peat soil studied.

The nitrogen-fixing activity in soils of the Banaue, Philippines, rice terraces was very low, suggesting the possibility of a marked response to nitrogen fertilizer by modern rice varieties grown in these soils. At the IRRI farm, the nitrogen-fixing activity in the root zone of rice growing in paddies was greatly reduced when algae were removed from the paddy water.

Among the nitrogen-fixing bacteria isolated from rice roots under reduced oxygen pressure and under anaerobic conditions, 51 and 18 strains, respectively, were identified and classified according to their cultural characteristics. These strains resemble *Alkaligenes* and *Enterobacter*. Using the acetylene-reduction method, the water fern *Azolla* was found to fix up to 1.0 kg N/ha daily, indicating its potential as a nitrogen-fixing agent in lowland rice soils.

Efforts were continued to develop a suitable technique for fertilizer nitrogen placement to improve the efficiency with which the rice plant

uses this element. Urea briquets (super granules) and gelatin capsules containing urea and band placement of fertilizer using granular and liquid applicators provided similarly high efficiency of nitrogen usage by an intermediate-maturing rice variety IR26, but not by the early-maturing variety IR28. Similar trends were noted with the slow-release fertilizer sulfur-coated urea.

The protein yield of brown rice when 60 kg N/ha was applied as mudball was similar to that when 90 kg N/ha was applied in split doses, indicating that the mudball technique for fertilizer application can be used to maintain the protein yield in rice.

Monitoring changes in soil fertility of rice soils appeared to be highly important for maintaining stable high yields of rice. Water management and the incorporation of straw into rice soils were found to be important fertilizer-saving cultural practices.

Studies to explore the potential of ratooning rice to improve productivity showed that varietal resistance to diseases, particularly virus diseases, is essential for achieving a successful ratoon crop.

Four cultural practices found to promote relatively high grain yields of ratoon rice were: 1) a cutting height of 15 cm, 2) the application of 60 kg N/ha, 3) thorough land preparation, and 4) closer spacing (15 × 15 cm) of rice plants.

An investigation of methods to reduce rice crop losses caused by submergence damage to rice showed that increasing the number of seedlings from one to five plants per hill prevented the adverse effect of submergence on grain yield.

ORGANIC MATTER AS A POSSIBLE
AMELIORANT FOR IRON-TOXIC SOILS
Soil Chemistry Department

Iron toxicity, a nutritional disorder of lowland rice associated with excess water-soluble iron, is probably the most important single soil factor limiting the yield of the new rice varieties on vast areas of acid tropical soils, especially acid sulfate soils. It has been identified in the Philippines, Vietnam, Thailand, Malaysia, India, Sri Lanka, Liberia, Senegal, and Colombia. There may be up to 30 million ha of iron-toxic soils. Iron toxicity can be corrected by liming the soil, but lime is not readily available in the acid regions in which the problem occurs and it is not economically feasible to lime acid sulfate soils. Thus alternate practical methods of ameliorating iron toxicity in soils need to be found.

Although iron toxicity has been associated with low pH, poor drainage, and excessive amounts of organic matter, a carefully controlled greenhouse experiment at IRRI showed that the addition of organic matter reduces the severity of iron toxicity.

The effect of organic matter on the kinetics of Eh, pH, and water-soluble ferrous iron was studied on three acid soils, a lateritic clay from Taiwan (pH 4.8), Albay clay (pH 3.8), and an acid sulfate soil from Camarines Sur, Philippines (pH 3.4), and on the growth of IR8 in a pot experiment in the greenhouse. A 1:1 mixture of chopped straw and *Glycidia sepium* leaves was added at 0 and 0.15% to 12-kg portions of soil, and 50, 25, and 50 ppm each of N, P, and K fertilizers were placed in pots

1. Kinetics of Eh, pH, and water soluble ferrous iron in the soil solution.

Table 1. Influence of organic matter on the severity of iron toxicity on IR8 rice in 3 acid soils from 1.5 to 6 weeks after transplanting.

Soil	O.M. ^a	Severity of iron toxicity ^b		
		1.5 wk	2.5 wk	6.0 wk
Taiwan	No	2.5	2.8	0.8
	Yes	2.2	2.9	0.5
Malinao	No	1.5	4.0	5.0
	Yes	0.2	3.0	3.5
Kalalahan	No	5.4	7.6	8.7
	Yes	5.1	6.9	7.8

^a0.15% organic matter (O.M.) added. ^b0 = no symptoms; 9 = plants died.

with drainage outlets at the base. The soil solution was sampled weekly for 6 weeks and analyzed in the laboratory. Two 2-week-old IR8 seedlings were transplanted in each pot 1 week after flooding.

The severity of iron toxicity exhibited by the rice plant varied among the soils, but for each soil the symptoms of iron toxicity was less when organic matter was added to the soil (Table 1). Organic matter appeared to have accelerated the reduction of each soil, increased the pH, and decreased the concentration of water-soluble ferrous iron (fig. 1a, 1b, and 1c).

Apparently, organic matter, e.g., straw, can

serve as an ameliorant for iron-toxic soils. Thus, organic matter should not be used in experiments designed to amplify iron toxicity, as when screening rice varieties for tolerance to iron toxicity.

FACTORS THAT LIMIT THE GROWTH OF RICE ON A PEAT SOIL

Soil Chemistry Department

In the tropics, peat soils cover vast areas that are climatically and physiographically suited to rice. However, millions of hectares of peat soils remain uncultivated because rice grows either poorly or not at all on such soils. One area bordering Laguna de Bay in the Philippines was converted to fishponds because of repeated crop failure. In this area, rice appears normal for 3 to 4 weeks, then the leaves start to dry from the tips, turn brown, and die, killing the plant. In 1975, a preliminary experiment was undertaken to ascertain the factors that inhibit the growth of rice on this Philippine peat soil.

Peat soil from Barrio Lalakay, Los Baños, Laguna, in the Philippines (pH 5.5; O.M.: 26.7%; total N: 0.40%; active Fe: 0.21%; active Mn: 0.031%; available Zn: 2.0 ppm; soluble B: 120 ppm) was used in a greenhouse study with IR26 rice. Some of the soil was air-dried and some was kept submerged continuously. Ten-kilogram portions of the soil were mixed with 50 ppm N as urea, 25 ppm P as superphosphate, and 50 ppm K as muriate of potash, and placed in 16-liter pots fitted with sampling tubes at the bottom for drawing soil solution. The pots were flooded with demineralized water. The NPK and various soil amendments used are summarized in Table 2. Each treatment was replicated twice. Two IR26 seedlings (2 weeks old) were transplanted in each pot. The soil solution was collected anaerobically by gravity. The Eh, pH, electrical conductivity, major ions plus copper, zinc, boron, sulfur, reducing substances, organic acids, and P_{CO_2} were measured. The straw was analyzed for nutrient elements at harvest.

Drying of this peat soil effected: (1) a buildup of toxic amounts of sulfate, reducing substances, boron, P_{CO_2} , and chloride; (2) an increase in the availability of nutrients such as iron, manganese,

Table 2. Yield of straw and grain of IR26 rice on peat soil.

Treatment	Yield (g/pot)	
	Straw	Grain
<i>Dried, 2 weeks presubmergence</i>		
Control	23.8	7.6
NPK ^a	46.3	35.4
NPK + Si	43.8	35.9
NPK + Si + Zn	47.1	34.6
NPK + Si + Zn + Cu	44.4	43.8
NPK + Si + Zn + Cu + B	43.1	32.9
NPK + Si + Zn + Cu + B + Mo	48.1	36.1
<i>Continuously submerged</i>		
Control	2.1	—
NPK	8.8	1.4
NPK + Si	10.1	2.9
NPK + Si + Zn	19.5	14.1
NPK + Si + Zn + Cu	23.7	14.7
NPK + Si + Zn + Cu + B	23.1	14.3
NPK + Si + Zn + Cu + B + Mo	30.1	16.3

^a50 ppm N (as urea), 25 ppm P (as superphosphate), and 50 ppm K (as K_2SO_4).

ammonia, phosphate, and silica; (3) a decrease in pH and Eh; and (4) an increase in specific conductivity. Seedlings transplanted on the air-dried soil on the day of flooding, regardless of amendment, wilted, withered, and died while those in the continuously submerged pots survived. The plants did not survive on the air-dried soil probably because of the high specific conductance (7.0 mmho/cm) and the high concentration of boron (55 ppm), sulfate (3,000 ppm), reducing substances (22 meq/l), and P_{CO_2} (0.5 atm).

Two weeks later, another set of 2-week-old seedlings were replanted in the pots with the air-dried soils. These plants survived and exhibited better growth and a higher yield than the plants grown on the continuously submerged soils (Table 2). However, from the sixth week after transplanting, brown spots were observed on the old leaves and stalks. NPK fertilizer improved the growth and increased the yield of rice in the peat soil but the effect was greater with the air-dried soil presubmerged for 2 weeks than with the continuously submerged soil. The application of zinc, copper, and molybdenum appeared to benefit rice on this soil.

This study provides evidence that rice can be grown on soils that are markedly deficient in nitrogen, zinc, and copper if the deficient plant nutrients are supplied.

In another study different rice varieties grown on this peat soil differed in their tolerance

to the toxic factors. IR2061-213-2, IR1632-93-2, IR30, and Pokkali, all tolerant of zinc deficiency, were moderately susceptible to the growth-limiting factors of this soil. Perhaps, rice can be grown on this peat soil if rice varieties tolerant to these growth-limiting factors are planted and proper amendments and management are used.

AMELIORATION OF ZINC DEFICIENCY

Soil Chemistry Department

Zinc deficiency is the third most important nutritional factor that limits the grain yield of lowland rice. Draining and drying the field is the most practical method of preventing zinc deficiency in rice caused by continuous wetting of the soil, but it is not always feasible. Dipping rice seedlings into a suspension of zinc oxide before transplanting is widely used, but this is not possible with direct-seeded rice. The application of zinc sulfate at 40 kg/ha is a standard practice in zinc-deficient areas in India and Pakistan, but this may be too expensive for many small farmers.

A greenhouse study using a zinc-deficient dark brown clay from Laguna, Philippines, and E 425, a variety susceptible to zinc deficiency, was undertaken to examine the feasibility of preventing zinc deficiency in rice by coating the seed with zinc oxide before sowing for direct seeding or for transplanting, and by applying zinc sulfate to the seedbed before transplanting. The results (Table 3) showed that zinc deficiency in transplanted rice can be corrected with an application of 50 kg ZnSO₄/ha to the seedbed or by coating the seeds with zinc oxide at the rate of 1 percent by dry weight of

the seeds before sowing. Zinc deficiency can be avoided in direct-seeded rice by coating the germinated seeds with zinc oxide. The cost of correcting zinc deficiency by applying zinc sulfate to the seedbed is only 5 percent of the cost of applying zinc sulfate to the field. In addition, seedbed application requires less time and labor. Coating seeds with zinc oxide costs half as much as using zinc oxide as a seedling dip and requires less time and labor.

Field studies are planned to verify these findings.

TRACE ELEMENTS IN FLOODED SOILS

Soil Chemistry Department

Nutritional disorders in rice due to toxicities and deficiencies of trace elements observed in previous years are copper deficiency on peat soils, boron toxicity on saline and sodic soils, molybdenum deficiency on acidic soils, and zinc deficiency on calcareous, sodic, and peat soils. Although data have been gathered extensively on the effects of trace elements, little information is available on the behavior of these elements in flooded soils.

The kinetics of boron, copper, zinc, and molybdenum was studied in 26 soils of varying characteristics that were flooded for up to 8 weeks in the greenhouse.

Copper. Copper toxicity reported from mining areas has been alleviated by lime. Positive responses in rice to the application of copper sulfate have been reported. As with zinc, the solubility of copper in the soil solution decreases with the duration of soil submergence (Table 4). This may be caused by the precipitation of copper as cuprous sulfide or cupric sulfide, but copper in the solution of submerged soils is considerably greater than can be accounted for through the solubility of cuprous sulfide and cupric sulfide.

Zinc. Zinc deficiency in wetland rice is widely recognized as a field problem in Pakistan, in most areas of India, in the Philippines, in Japan, in the United States, in Colombia, in Chad, and in Nigeria. It was first identified on an alkali soil, but now is known to occur on calcareous soils, marsh soils, peat soils, and sandy soils low in total zinc. A strongly acid

Table 3. Influence of four methods of zinc application on the yield of straw and grain of E 425 rice on a zinc-deficient soil.

Treatment	Yield ^a (g/pot)	
	Straw	Grain
No zinc; transplanting	62 d	54 b
ZnO dip; transplanting	74 bc	83 a
ZnO as seed coating; transplanting	71 c	75 a
ZnSO ₄ to seedbed; transplanting	79 ab	81 a
ZnO as seed coating; direct seeding	83 a	67 ab

^aAny two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Table 4. Kinetics of water-soluble Cu, Zn, B, and Mo in four soils submerged for 0 to 8 weeks.

Element	Concn (ppm)				
	0 wk	2 wk	4 wk	6 wk	8 wk
<i>Kalalahan sandy loam (pH:3.5; O.M.:2.70%)</i>					
B	0.48	0.16	0.01	0.01	0.08
Cu	0.15	0.03	0.02	0.02	0.01
Mo	0.02	0.10	0.12	0.12	0.10
Zn	1.70	0.17	0.14	0.11	0.36
<i>Luisiana clay (pH:4.5; O.M.:2.59%)</i>					
B	0.58	0.49	0.46	0.30	0.25
Cu	0.02	0.17	0.04	0.03	0.00
Mo	0.06	0.06	0.15	0.24	0.11
Zn	0.08	0.07	0.10	0.07	0.07
<i>Maahas clay (pH:6.6; O.M.:1.61%)</i>					
B	1.10	1.01	1.15	1.18	0.78
Cu	0.06	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.00
Mo	0.03	0.09	0.17	0.02	0.12
Zn	0.09	0.08	0.18	0.12	0.12
<i>Silo silt loam (pH:7.6; O.M.:1.99%)</i>					
B	3.41	3.55	3.20	3.50	3.00
Cu	0.20	0.07	0.06	0.05	0.00
Mo	0.02	0.20	0.45	0.15	0.10
Zn	0.12	0.03	0.12	0.18	0.09

soil (Kalalahan sandy loam) had the highest concentration of water-soluble zinc (Table 4).

Boron. Excess boron in irrigation water has been reported to damage rice plants. Although the change in concentration of boron in the soil solution differed with time among the four soils studied the general trend was a reduction in the level of boron in solution with the duration of flooding between 0 and 8 weeks. Kalalahan sandy loam, with the lowest pH (3.5), had the lowest concentration of water-soluble boron, while Silo silt loam with the highest pH (7.6) had the highest.

Molybdenum. Among the four trace elements studied, molybdenum concentrations were generally lower in the sample soil solutions. In three of the four soils studied, the amount of water-soluble molybdenum increased up to the sixth week of flooding and then declined by the eighth week of submergence (Table 4).

The lowest peak value (0.12 ppm molybdenum) occurred in the soil with the lowest pH (3.5), while the highest peak value (0.45 ppm) was found in the soil with the alkaline pH (7.6).

Soil and crop management

Soil fertility management: microbiological studies

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BIOLOGICAL NITROGEN FIXATION IN RICE FIELDS

Soil Microbiology and Agronomy Departments

In situ nitrogen fixation assay in lowland rice fields (*Soil Microbiology*). Biological fixation of nitrogen is indispensable in the maintenance of nitrogen fertility in lowland rice. The amount of nitrogen fixed in the field could not be accurately estimated by extrapolating the findings from laboratory assays or those from balance sheet studies.

In situ acetylene reduction (AR) assay using plastic bags was used to estimate the rate of nitrogen fixation occurring in rice fields and, specifically, to determine the amount of nitrogen fixed heterotrophically in the rice root zone as compared with nitrogen fixed by autotrophic algae in paddy water. After 24 hours in situ AR assay in the field at the IRRI farm and at two farmers' fields, the photosynthetic nitrogen fixation by algae in water, floating algae, and algae adhering to the aquatic weeds was assayed under 4 to 5 klux light and at 30° to 32°C. The nitrogen-fixing (NF) activity of surface soil was also assayed in darkness at 30°C. In some cases, the population of diazotrophs, such as aerobic NF bacteria, anaerobic NF bacteria, blue-green algae, nonsulfur photosynthetic bacteria, and sulfur photosynthetic bacteria was counted.

Nitrogen fixation in long-term fertilizer experimental plots of IRRI—Agronomy (*Soil Microbiology*). The nitrogen-fixing activity of plots that received no fertilizer and of those that received NPK fertilizer were assayed during the 1975 wet season. The yield of the 23rd crop of rice grown on the "no-fertilizer" plots showed no detectable decline after 12 years of continuous cropping.

The assay was started 1 day before transplanting IR26 rice and was continued every 3 weeks. The experiment will be continued in the ensuing years.

The in situ assay showed that the NF activity in fertilized plots was higher at the earlier stages of growth of rice, but that later, particularly near and after rice harvest, the NF activity in non-fertilized plots was higher (fig. 1).

The NF activity of the soil and of flooding

water and the sum of the NF activities of flooding water, floating algal mass, and algae adhering to aquatic weeds are shown in fig. 2. In fertilized plots, while the photosynthetic NF activity of algae in flooding water was higher at the earlier stage of rice growth, at the later stage of crop growth, the NF activity was nearly negligible. However, the nitrogen fixation continued during the later stage of plant growth. Apparently, the NF activity of algae in nonfertilized plots is important, particularly during the later stages of rice growth.

Effect of molybdenum and phosphorus (*Soil Microbiology*). Phosphorus and molybdenum, known to enhance the biological fixation of nitrogen, were applied at 50 kg P₂O₅/ha and 1 kg Mo/ha. The application of phosphorus, molybdenum, or both enhanced the NF activity only during the initial stages of crop growth.

1. Change of the in situ acetylene-reducing activity in long-term fertilizer experiments at IRRI, 1975 wet season.

Effect of spacing on nitrogen fixation (*Soil Microbiology*). In situ acetylene reduction assays were carried out on IRRI field plots without rice plants and with rice transplanted at 20- × 20-cm spacing and at 40- × 40-cm spacing. In the 40- × 40-cm-spaced plots, one 20- × 20-cm square assay chamber was placed over one rice hill and another chamber in the middle of four adjacent hills.

The rice plants appeared to have only a minor enhancing effect on the NF activity. There was no significant difference in the effect of the two types of spacing studied.

Of more than 200 in situ as well as in vitro assays performed at three sites in IRRI fields, only nine yielded NF values exceeding 77 $\mu\text{mol C}_2\text{H}_4 \cdot \text{day}^{-1} \cdot \text{chamber}^{-1}$ (0.2 kg N/ha daily) (Table 1). Seven of the nine assays gave a high value of in vitro activity of photosynthetic algae under light. Two did not show high phototrophic fixation of nitrogen.

Nitrogen fixation in Banaue rice terrace soil and Pangil phosphorus-deficient oxisol (*Soil Microbiology*). Rice has been cultivated continuously for more than 1,000 years without the application of inorganic fertilizer in the rice terrace soils of Banaue, Ifugao province, Philippines. In situ assays at this location at two sites (higher and lower) and in vitro assays of these soils were performed.

At the April sampling time, about two-thirds of the field was covered by *Azolla* (water fern). The in situ assay value, which was low in all cases (7.3–125.0 g N/ha daily), correlated with the in vitro activity of the paddy water exposed to light, but did not consistently correlate with

2. The in vitro acetylene-reducing activity of soil and flooding water and the sum of algal activity from long-term fertilizers experiment plots. IRRI, 1975 wet season.

the in vitro activity of *Azolla*. At the May sampling, *Azolla* was not found at either of the two sites and the in situ NF activity was very low (13.3–25.8 g N/ha daily). Among the diazotrophs counted in Banaue soil, the population of *Thiorodaceae* was markedly high.

Rice varieties that can grow well in a phosphorus-deficient soil were tested in the field on a phosphorus-deficient oxisol in Pangil, Laguna, Philippines. In situ assays were conducted on plots of IR26 and M1-48 rices with and without phosphorus fertilizer to ascertain

Table 1. The highest value of in situ N_2 (C_2H_2 - C_2H_4)-fixing activities more than 0.2 kg N/ha daily. IRRI, 1975.

Location at IRRI	In situ N_2 fixing activity ($\mu\text{mol} \cdot \text{chamber}^{-1} \cdot \text{day}^{-1}$)	In vitro photo-synthetic N_2 fixing activity by algae in water ($\mu\text{mol} \cdot \text{chamber}^{-1} \cdot \text{day}^{-1}$)	Growth stage ^a of rice	Type of fixation ^b
Agronomy N-14	160	93	after harvest	A
	150	0.01	43 days after TR	H
	111	84	after harvest	A
Upper MN	159	64	14 days after TR	A
	157	22	"	A
	130	7	"	A, H
Lower MN	134	34	just before harvest	A
	99	31	"	A
	78	0.7	after harvest	H

^a TR = transplanting. ^b A = algal N_2 fixation; H = heterotrophic N_2 fixation.

any varietal differences in N₂ fixation. IR26 rice grew better in the phosphorus-deficient soil.

The NF activity in the phosphorus-deficient soil was extremely low (7–15 g N/ha daily). The NF activity of the root zones of the two rice varieties did not differ. The low in vitro NF activity of the soil under light suggested that the algal fixation of nitrogen in the field was negligible.

Nitrogen fixation of the rice root zone in the field. To ascertain the quantitative contribution of nitrogen fixation in the rice root zone to the total gain of nitrogen in a rice field, the flooding water and floating algal mass were removed and the flooding water was replaced with distilled water in the assay chamber. Then, the NF activity of the root zone was assayed. The removal of the algae from the paddy water greatly reduced the in situ NF activity in the rice field (from 117 $\mu\text{mol C}_2\text{H}_4/24\text{ h}$ to 19 μmol) at the earlier growth stage when the algae bloomed. At the later stage of rice growth, the removal of algae from the flooding water did not affect the in situ NF activity, because the activity of the blue-green algae was already very low. At both stages of growth, after the algae were removed, the NF activity was very low (19–11 μmol), indicating that the amount of nitrogen fixed in the root zone of rice was only minor.

Changes in the nitrogen-fixing activity in leftover rice stubbles. In situ assays in IRR1 fields revealed that the NF activity around the hill after the rice is harvested was higher than that around intact rice plants. For further evidence, the change in the NF activity around leftover stubbles (ratoon) in the field was studied.

Mature rice plants were cut at about 5 cm above the ground and the stubble was left in the flooded field. Some rice plants were left uncut in the field to serve as controls. Acetylene reduction assays were carried out periodically around the leftover stubbles and around the rice plants with aerial parts.

To exclude the activity of floating algae, the floating algal mass was removed from around the hills to be assayed. The rice regrew from the ratoon.

After the aerial parts of the mature rice were

cut, the NF activity gradually increased and reached a maximum level at 37 days. Cutting the aerial parts of the rice plants may have released a source of energy from the decomposing rice roots that could be used by the NF organisms.

BACTERIAL NITROGEN FIXATION IN RICE ROOT ZONE

Soil Microbiology Department

Nitrogen-fixing bacteria isolated from rice roots. Nitrogen-fixing bacteria were isolated from rice roots and were identified.

Roots from 50-day-old IR26 plants grown on submerged soil were washed thoroughly with sterilized water and cut into 2- to 5-mm segments. The root segments were placed on nitrogen-free glucose mineral agar media and incubated either under ambient air with shaking, under microaerophilic conditions ($p\text{O}_2$, 0.03) or under anaerobic conditions. Most of the isolates grew well under limited oxygen pressure, but not under the anaerobic conditions. The majority of the isolated bacteria showed the highest NF activity under a limited supply of oxygen ($p\text{O}_2$, 0.03).

Among the bacteria originally isolated under reduced oxygen pressure and under anaerobic conditions, 51 and 18 strains, respectively, were classified into 10 types, according to their cultural characteristics. They were tentatively considered to resemble *Alkaligenes* and *Enterobacter*.

Inoculation of nitrogen-fixing bacteria on rice seedlings. To ascertain whether the NF bacteria isolated from rice roots have the ability to establish themselves in the rice root zone or roots and to fix nitrogen to improve the supply of nitrogen to growing rice plants, the bacteria were inoculated on rice seedlings raised under sterile conditions.

Two strains of NF bacteria from the isolates from rice roots and *Azotobacter chroococcum* isolated from Maahas clay soil were used.

IR26 rice grains were dehulled, sterilized, and sown on agar media. After 7 days, the sterilized germinated seed was transferred to a 0.8-percent agar media supplemented with nitrogen-free mineral nutrients in a test tube.

The endosperm of the rice seedlings were removed and the seedlings were placed in a test tube and inoculated with a bacterial suspension. Mineral nitrogen at 40 ppm N (NH_4NO_3) was added to some tubes. The tubes were incubated in a KG growth cabinet, using a 12-hour day with 10 klux and at 30°C with a 12-hour night at 23°C.

The plants without nitrogen showed symptoms of nitrogen deficiency regardless of bacterial inoculation. When assayed after 3 weeks of incubation, the rice plants inoculated with bacteria showed acetylene reduction activity, indicating NF activity of the isolated bacteria in the rice root zone. But no improvement of plant growth and nitrogen uptake could be detected, probably because even the maximum NF activity (0.2 μg N/plant daily) was too low to meet the plant's nitrogen uptake (400 μg N for 3 weeks).

NITROGEN FIXATION BY AN *AZOLLA-ANABAENA* ASSOCIATION

Soil Microbiology Department

The water fern *Azolla* can grow in nitrogen-free media because of the NF activity of the blue-green algae *Anabaena azollae* that live in the leaf cavity of *Azolla*. This combination is designated as an *Azolla-Anabaena* association.

Azolla was recognized as a green manure crop in rice culture in the 1930's in North Vietnam. These water ferns are widely distributed in rice fields from tropical to temperate regions.

A study of the potential value of *Azolla* as a partial substitute for nitrogen fertilizer in rice fields using *Azolla* (species not yet identified) from Bicol, Philippines, showed that the NF rate is about 0.45 to 0.57 mg N/g fresh weight daily under greenhouse conditions. *Azolla* doubled their weight between the fourth and fifth day of growth.

About 1 kg fresh-weight *Azolla* previously grown in a small pond was spread on a rice field (25 sq m) at IRRI after the wet-season crop harvest. After about 15 days, *Azolla* almost covered the surface of the paddy field and after 20 days, the NF activity was about 1.0 kg N/ha daily. After 24 days, the *Azolla* (beginning to

disintegrate) was harvested. The fresh weight was about 1.2 kg/sq m and the nitrogen content was 3.6 g/sq m.

Azolla was grown for 24 hours under 4 klux 32°C condition. Acetylene reduction activity and nitrogen increase by Kjeldahl method were measured. The conversion rate was 3.4, 1.6, and 2.4 mol of N_2 fixed/mol of C_2H_4 produced for the three trials.

ALGAL NITROGEN FIXATION

Soil Microbiology Department

Phosphorus and algal nitrogen fixation. Phosphorus is perhaps the most effective factor known to promote the fixation of nitrogen by algae.

Four kinds of soils in the Philippines (Banaue, Puro, Maahas, and Santo Domingo) were used to study the effects of phosphorus on the nitrogenase activities of blue-green algae. Forty grams of air-dried soil, to which 40 ml of distilled water was added, was incubated under continuous 4 to 5 klux light at 29° to 31°C. Phosphorus was added to some cultures at 25 and 50 ppm. The acetylene-reducing activity of each of the soils was assayed at weekly intervals under light (2 klux).

Phosphorus stimulated the nitrogenase activity in all four soils, but had the greatest effect on the Banaue and Maahas soils (fig. 3). With the 50-ppm phosphorus treatment, after 4 weeks, a total increase of 1.4 and 2.5 mg N occurred with the Maahas and Banaue soils, respectively. The increase in nitrogen fixation in response to applied phosphorus was estimated to be 0.7 to 1.2 g N/ P_2O_5 applied. This value was slightly higher than those obtained by Nishigaki and Shioiri in 1959 (0.5 g) and by De and Mandal in 1956 (0.3 to 0.5 g).

Effect of light intensity. The NF activity of microorganisms living on surface water in an in situ assay chamber, measured under 4 klux light in the laboratory, was lower than that measured in situ in the field (Table 1). This may have been due, in part, to a lower light intensity in the laboratory as compared with field conditions. The light intensity in the field is higher at the earlier stages of rice growth when the soil surface is not shaded by a leaf

3. The effect of phosphorus on the acetylene-reducing activity of four Philippine lowland rice soils.

canopy. A laboratory study of the effect of light intensity on the NF activity of blue-green algae in rice paddy showed that regardless of the age of the culture, the maximum NF activity was obtained at 10 klux. At 5 klux, the NF activity was about 80 percent of the maximum activity.

A study in which the NF activity of a field-grown *Gloetrichia* algal mass was measured in response to light intensity showed that the NF activity was saturated at about 10 klux. At 5 klux, 87 percent of the maximum NF activity was obtained, suggesting that the NF activity of blue-green algae under 4 to 5 klux light is similar to the NF activity under light-saturated conditions. The fact that saturation light inten-

sity for photosynthesis is related to carbon dioxide concentration suggests the merit of investigating the relation between carbon dioxide concentration and saturation light intensity for photoreductive nitrogen fixation.

NITROGEN TRANSFORMATION IN RAINFED AND UPLAND RICE SOIL

Soil Microbiology Department

Vertical distribution of inorganic nitrogen after fertilizer application. In upland soil, nitrate is formed from applied ammonium nitrogen and it either percolates to lower layers of the soil with rains during the wet season or accumulates on the soil surface due to the upward movement of water caused by evaporation during the dry season. In the humid tropics the rate of nitrification of fertilizer ammonium is undoubtedly rapid and concomitantly the nitrate is also leached rapidly because of ambient high temperatures and heavy rains. The majority of reports on the movement of nitrogen in the humid tropics describe conditions in Africa and Latin America; there is a dearth of such reports dealing with Southeast and Southern Asia. Information on the transformation of nitrogen and its movement in the soil profile may suggest ways to maximize the efficiency of fertilizer usage in upland or rainfed rice soils.

In experiments at the IRRI farm (upper MN), no fertilizer was applied to one split plot, while 50 kg N/ha and 100 kg N/ha of ammonium fertilizer were applied to two other split plots. The three split plots were each divided into three replicates. In the fertilized plots, one-half of the plots were treated with a nitrification inhibitor, N-serve, at 4 percent of the added nitrogen to verify the effectiveness of the nitrification inhibitor. Both planted and unplanted subplots were set up for each treatment. The fertilizer was placed in furrows that were spaced 75 cm apart. IR5 rice seeds were sown in the furrows in the third week of May 1975.

Soil samples were collected with a soil auger (15-cm diameter) every 15 cm to a depth of 75 cm (fifth layer) before fertilizer application, just after application, 1, 2, 3 months after application, and at harvest time (5 months after planting).

Counts of *Nitrosomonas* in soil before fertilizer application showed that the number of ammonia oxidizers per gram of dry soil in the soil profile from the surface to a 75-cm depth in 15-cm layers was 950, 240, 2,900, 22, and 68, respectively. The partly weathered parent material, tuff, was visible at about 50 cm and below.

The ammonium nitrogen content of the surface 15-cm layer of soil decreased markedly in both planted and unplanted plots where 50 and 100 kg N/ha were applied (fig. 4). In unplanted plots, to which no N-serve was added, about 50 percent of the ammonium was nitrified after 1 month and more than 90 percent was nitrified after 2 months. N-serve retarded this activity for 2 months, but after 2 to 3 months, the nitrifying activity was restored with 20-fold to 200-fold increase in the number of *Nitrosomonas* in plots to which nitrogen had been applied.

After 3 months, the amount of ammonium nitrogen in all plots, except in the N-serve plots to which 100 kg N/ha had been applied, was low; after 5 months the ammonium nitrogen level in all plots was lower than that before the fertilizer was applied.

The markedly lower level of ammonium nitrogen after 2 months in the planted plots, as compared with the unplanted plots, indicated a vigorous uptake of nitrogen by the rice plants.

The vertical distribution of nitrogen through the soil profile 3 months after nitrogen application (fig. 5), when nitrification was complete, showed that in plots without N-serve the nitrate was highest at the 30- to 45-cm layer. In the plots treated with N-serve, the delay of nitrification caused the nitrate to be highest at the surface layer. However, the nitrate level was lower than expected from the ammonium content just after fertilizer application. The cumulative value of mineral nitrogen in the soil profile from the soil surface to 60 cm below (Table 2) decreased even in the unplanted plots. After 5 months, the mineral nitrogen decreased to the level in soil before fertilizer application. The fact that the horizontal movement of nitrogen was found to be negligible after 5 months, and the evidence of the retarding effect of N-serve on the loss of mineral nitrogen

4. Changes in the amount of ammonium nitrogen in the surface 15-cm soil layer. IRRI, 1975 wet season.

suggest that the applied fertilizer nitrogen was lost because of denitrification.

Because the soil used in this experiment had low water permeability, temporary surface flooding after rainfall was not unusual. Between the beginning of the experiment and harvest time, 1,014 mm of rain fell. The water table frequently rose to 20 to 30 cm beneath the soil surface.

Because of this poor drainage, the denitrification occurs either at the surface or at the lower layer where the soil was submerged beneath the water table. Apparently, in poorly drained upland fields, applied ammonium nitrogen is likely to be lost because of denitrification, and nitrate does not accumulate in the lower soil layers due to leaching, particularly during the wet season.

5. Vertical distribution of nitrate nitrogen in the soil profile 3 months after fertilizer application.

Table 2. Total amount of inorganic nitrogen in soil profile (0–60 cm) beneath the rows in unplanted and planted plots. IRRI, 1975.

Plot	Inorganic N ^a (g N/sq m)			
	0 day	1 month	2 months	3 months
<i>Unplanted plots</i>				
Without N-serve				
Non-N	13	15	13	11
50 kg N/ha	41	31	18	13
100 kg N/ha	91	62	43	12
With N-serve				
50 kg N/ha	50	46	40	16
100 kg N/ha	81	61	46	32
<i>Planted plots</i>				
Without N-serve				
Non-N	11	13	6	5
50 kg N/ha	58	33	9	5
100 kg N/ha	80	43	15	5
With N-serve				
50 kg N/ha	46	44	8	4
100 kg N/ha	89	60	15	6

^aIf the fertilizer rows are 10 cm, the amount of nitrogen to be supplied should be 7.5 times higher than on the total area of the plots.

EFFECT OF DIFFERENT MOISTURE TENSIONS ON NITROGEN TRANSFORMATION IN THE SOIL

Soil Microbiology Department

The previously reported studies (Annual Report 1972) on the effect of soil moisture stress on rice growth and nitrogen transformation were extended by increasing the moisture-stress conditions to 59 and 75 centibars. IR20 and Rikuto Norin 21 rices were grown on Maahas clay soil containing 100 ppm nitrogen [(NH₄)₂SO₄, labeled with ¹⁵N] in the greenhouse.

With both varieties, growth was maximum under submerged conditions and decreased commensurately with an increase in the soil moisture stress; grain filling was decreased at 75 centibars. The relation of nitrogen uptake to plant growth in both rice varieties was positive and direct; the more growth, the more nitrogen was taken up by the plant.

The contributions of fertilizer nitrogen to the total amount of nitrogen taken up by plants were similar regardless of soil moisture stress. The availabilities of fertilizer nitrogen and soil nitrogen were similar under all of the soil moisture conditions used. After 4 weeks, the amount of ammonium nitrogen in the soil decreased markedly, and the amount of nitrate

nitrogen increased, except in the submerged soil. Apparently, nitrification occurred under upland conditions, regardless of the extent of the soil moisture stress, suggesting that the nitrifying bacteria were more resistant to soil moisture stress than were the rice plants.

HORIZONTAL DISTRIBUTION OF ¹⁵N-LABELED FERTILIZER IN LOWLAND RICE SOIL

Soil Microbiology Department

During the 1974 wet season, plots at the IRRI farm were fertilized with 60 kg N/ha, using (NH₄)₂SO₄ (some ¹⁵N-labeled) using one of four methods: 1) basal incorporation, 2) basal deep placement as 3-cm-size mudballs, 3) topdressing at 39 days before heading, and 4) deep placement of mudballs 39 days before heading. Two IR26 rice seedlings at the fourth leaf stage were transplanted at 20- × 20-cm spacing in 25-sq m plots.

All ¹⁵N-labeled fertilizers were applied at the center of each plot. For basal incorporation, non-labeled ammonium sulfate was mixed thoroughly with puddled soil a day before transplanting except in the 20- × 20-cm center of the plot which was separated by a bottomless box. After transplanting, ¹⁵N-labeled fertilizer was applied and mixed thoroughly with the soil inside the box surrounded by four plant hills. Mudballs were placed 12 cm beneath the soil surface at the center of four hills, with one ball for every two hills in the plot. At the center of the plot one ¹⁵N-labeled mudball was placed at the center of the four hills. At 39 days before heading unlabeled ammonium sulfate was broadcast evenly on the soil surface except at the center where ¹⁵N-labeled ammonium sulfate was applied. After the ¹⁵N-labeled fertilizers were applied, the soil box was removed.

The efficiency of nitrogen usage by the rice plant when the nitrogen was basally incorporated was lower than when the nitrogen was applied by any of the other three methods (Table 3). The efficiencies of plant usage of applied nitrogen were similar for these other three methods used.

When the fertilizer was applied in the form of a mudball or incorporated in the puddled layer,

Table 3. Recovery of applied fertilizer by rice plants and effect of distance from fertilizer placement on the uptake of ¹⁵N-labeled fertilizer nitrogen. IRRI, 1975.

Treatment ^a	Total N uptake (kg/ha)	Applied N recovered (%) (difference method)	Labeled fertilizer uptake ^b (mg N)						
			First circle ^c			Second circle ^d			
			Straw	Grain	Total	Straw	Grain	Total	
O N	101.1								
60 N basal	118.0	28.2	79.4	95.1	174.6	2.9	2.9	5.8	
60 B basal	132.9	53.0	89.8	123.2	213.0	5.7	14.7	20.4	
O N + 60 N (39 DBH)	133.5	54.0	6.2	10.1	16.3	7.1	9.7	16.8	
O N + 60 B (39 DBH)	133.9	54.7	155.7	154.3	310.0	3.9	4.0	7.9	

^aN = ordinary ammonium sulfate. ^bTotal uptake of plant hills in the circle; B = handmade mudball fertilizer from Maahas clay; DBH = days before heading. ^c4 adjacent plant hills from the site of labeled fertilizer placement. ^d8 plant hills 20 cm from the site of labeled fertilizer placement.

only plants close to the site of placement absorbed the fertilizer nitrogen. A small amount of the fertilizer was distributed to as far as 20 cm from the site of application.

When the fertilizer was applied on the soil surface 39 days before heading, the ¹⁵N-labeled

fertilizer was probably mixed with the non-labeled fertilizer, causing a rapid decrease in the amount of ¹⁵N taken up by the rice plants. This rapid exchange between ¹⁵N and ¹⁴N indicates a wider distribution of fertilizer by topdressing.

Soil and crop management

Soil fertility and fertilizer management

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NITROGEN FERTILITY OF SOILS

Agronomy Department

Under diverse systems of rice culture, fertilizer, particularly nitrogen, must be properly managed to achieve the maximum rice yields possible with low rates of application.

Rice is grown on all major soil groups in South and Southeast Asia, and thus, stable high yields can only be obtained when deficiencies of nutrients in the soil are alleviated with proper management.

Placement of fertilizer nitrogen. A deep placement technique has been tested in several experiments at the IRRI farm and in farmers' fields in the Philippines.

At the IRRI farm, to determine the best method of nitrogen application to achieve maximum plant efficiency, low rates of fertilizer were used to minimize nitrogen losses from the soil through denitrification and other processes.

During the 1975 dry season, IR26, of intermediate maturation (130 to 135 days), and IR28, of early maturation (102 to 105 days), were used in trials to test different sources of nitrogen fertilizer at different rates of application: urea (46 percent N), sulfur-coated urea (34 percent N), ammonium sulfate (21 percent N), and leaves of ipil-ipil (*Leucaena latisiliqua* L.) (4 percent N). In one experiment, nitrogen was applied at 0, 60, and 100 kg N/ha and at 0, 56, and 112 kg N/ha in the other experiments.

Twenty-one-day-old seedlings were transplanted at 2 or 3 seedlings/hill at 20- × 20-cm spacing. A split-plot design was used in two

experiments, and a randomized complete block design was employed in two other experiments.

For deep placement of fertilizer, mudballs containing a prescribed amount of nitrogen fertilizer were prepared 3 days before transplanting with soil collected from the experimental fields. The mudballs were placed at 10 to 12 cm deep in the soil between four hills.

Urea briquets (super granules) and gelatin capsules containing urea were also placed at 10 to 12 cm deep in the soil just after transplanting.

Band placement of fertilizer in each row was accomplished with an IRRI band applicator (granular) 2 days after transplanting.

Plant height and tiller number were measured at 20, 40, and 60 days after transplanting (DT) and before harvest. Management practices, such as weed control and water management, were optimum.

The grain yields of both IR26 and IR28 rice receiving 60 kg N/ha and 100 kg N/ha were significantly higher than the yields of these two rice varieties grown without applied nitrogen (Table 1).

With both varieties, 60 kg N/ha when applied as mudballs and as band placement (granular and liquid) gave higher grain yields than when the nitrogen was broadcast and incorporated into the soil. However, with IR28, the yields from plots where nitrogen was applied by the broadcast and incorporated method and by deep placement were similar (Table 1). The yields of IR26 were higher in each of the deep placement treatments than in the plots on which the fertilizer was broadcast and plowed in.

In both varieties, the grain yields with deep placement of 60 kg N/ha and with the broadcast and incorporated method at 100 kg N/ha were not significantly different. Deep placement of nitrogen fertilizer may have reduced nitrogen losses under flooded conditions, thereby increasing the efficiency of fertilizer use by rice.

With IR26, sulfur-coated urea gave a significantly higher grain yield than ordinary urea, 1 t/ha more yields with 60 kg N/ha and 0.5 t/ha more yields with 100 kg N/ha (Table 2). However, the grain yields of IR28 were not significantly different for these two sources of nitrogen. With early-maturing IR28, sulfur-

Table 1. Effects of different methods of nitrogen application on the grain yield of IR26 and IR28 rices with optimum insect protection. IRRI, 1975 dry season.

Method of nitrogen application	Grain yield* (t/ha)		
	IR26	IR28	T-mean
No nitrogen	4.6 c	4.1 b	4.3 c
	60 kg N/ha		
Broadcast and incorporated	5.3 b	5.4 a	5.4 b
Placement as mudball	6.5 a	5.6 a	6.0 a
Band placement (granular)	6.5 a	5.4 a	5.9 a
Band placement (liquid)	6.3 a	5.8 a	6.0 a
Placement as coin envelope	6.3 a	5.6 a	5.9 a
	100 kg N/ha		
Broadcast and incorporated	6.2 a	5.6 a	5.8 a

*In the same column, any two means followed by a common letter are not significantly different from each other.

Table 2. Comparative yield of two rice varieties when urea and sulfur-coated urea at 60 kg N/ha and 100 kg N/ha are applied as a single basal dose. IRRI, 1975 dry season.

Nitrogen application rate (kg/ha)	Yield (t/ha)	
	Urea	Sulfur-coated urea
	<i>IR26</i>	
0		4.6
60	5.3	6.3
100	6.2	6.7
	<i>IR28</i>	
0		4.1
60	5.4	5.4
100	5.6	5.9

LSD_{0.05} = 0.4 t/ha

coated urea had no clear advantage over urea.

Different sulfur-coated ureas have different rates of fertilizer release and thus each should be evaluated thoroughly before any generalization can be made. An increase in grain yield with urea and sulfur-coated urea will depend on the release rates and the growth duration of the rice variety. The faster the release rate of the fertilizer, the greater is the yield advantage of varieties with a short growth duration over those with a long growth duration.

Plant height and tiller number per hill were increased by deep placement of fertilizer using either the mudball technique or the band placement method (granular and liquid) at 60 kg N/ha and the basal application of 100 kg N/ha.

For both IR26 and IR28, the plant height and tiller number were increased more by the broadcast and incorporated method during the last land preparation than by the deep placement up to 20 days after transplanting, after which they were increased rapidly by deep placement. Of the various methods tested, the mudball technique effected a greater increase in plant height and tiller number than did the other deep placement methods. The changes in plant height and tiller number caused by the fertilizer application treatments were significantly greater than those of the plants in the unfertilized treatments.

The efficiency of 60 kg N/ha with IR26 and IR28 was greater with deep placement (27 kg rice/kg N) than with a single basal application (17 kg rice/kg N). The efficiency with deep

Table 3. Efficiency of nitrogen use by IR26 and IR28 rices when 60 kg N/ha is applied via different methods. IRRI, 1975 dry season.

Method of application	Fertilizer N efficiency (kg rice/kg N)		
	IR26	IR28	Av.
Broadcast and incorporated	12	23	17
Placement as mudball	32	25	28
Granular band placement	32	21	27
Placement as coin envelope	28	26	27
Liquid band placement	28	28	28

placement was greater with IR26 than with IR28 rice (Table 3). Of the various methods tested, urea at 60 kg N/ha applied as band placement (liquid) and by the mudball technique provided the greatest efficiency of fertilizer nitrogen, 28 kg rice/kg N. The nitrogen efficiency was similar among the deep placement methods.

When urea was applied at 56 kg N/ha via deep placement as a briquet, 2.0 t/ha more grain was harvested than with the unfertilized control (fig. 1). Urea briquets gave yields comparable to those obtained through the mudball technique or split application.

Effects of nitrogen placement on protein yield. The protein yields of brown rice (average for two varieties) with 60 kg N/ha applied as

1. Grain yield of IR28 with different methods of nitrogen application and with optimum insect protection. IRRI, 1975 dry season.

Table 4. Effects of different methods of nitrogen application on the protein content of brown rice of IR26 and IR28 grown under lowland conditions. IRRI, 1975 dry season.

Method of N ⁹ application	Brown rice protein yield (kg/ha)		
	IR26	IR28	Mean ^c (fertilizer)
All basal	390	339	364 c
2/3 basal + 1/3 PI	396	335	365 c
1/3 basal + 1/3 30 DT + 1/3 PI	383	332	357 c
All 5-7 days before PI	414	353	384 bc
1/3 10 DT + 1/3 40 DT + 1/3 PI	395	323	359 c
Placement as mudball	429	395	412 ab
1/3 basal + 2/3 5-7 days before PI ^b	444	422	433 a
Without fertilizer	292	191	241 d
Mean (variety)	393	313	

^a60 kg N/ha. ^b90 kg N/ha (standard control). PI = panicle initiation stage; DT = days after transplanting. ^cMeans followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

mudball and with 90 kg N/ha applied in split doses—one third as basal plus two thirds applied 5 to 7 days before panicle initiation—were similar, indicating that the mudball technique for fertilizer placement can be used to maintain the protein yield of rice (Table 4).

When the experiment was repeated during the wet season, the protein content of brown rice with mudball placement was at least equal to

2. Relative grain yield (average of four experiments) of IR26 rice grown at IRRI farm (clay soil) and in three farmers' fields in Nueva Ecija, Philippines (clay, clay loam, and loam soil), without fertilizer nitrogen and with 60 kg N/ha as urea under different methods of application. 1975 dry season.

that with the other methods of nitrogen application tested. Mudball placement of nitrogen fertilizer appears to effect no reduction in the protein content of brown rice, and can increase the protein yield of brown rice when the grain yield response to nitrogen placement is higher.

Efficiency of fertilizer nitrogen on different soil types. During the 1975 dry season using IR26 rice, experiments were conducted: one each in three farmers' fields in Nueva Ecija, Central Luzon, Philippines (clay, clay loam, and loam), and another at the IRRI farm (clay soil) to compare methods of fertilizer nitrogen application. Averaging the four experiments, the mudball technique yielded 0.5 t/ha more than did the band placement and about 1.0 t/ha more grain than either basal incorporated or split-dose application (fig. 2).

During the 1975 wet season, when the effects of soil type on fertilizer nitrogen efficiency (28, 56, and 100 kg N/ha) were further evaluated at the IRRI farm on Maahas clay (vertisol, pH 7.0) and on Luisiana clay at Cavinti, Laguna, Philippines (oxisol, pH 4.6), the yield response to 28 kg N/ha on the Maahas clay was not significantly greater than the yield response to the no-fertilizer nitrogen treatment. The grain yields were not significantly different between no-fertilizer nitrogen and a split application of 56 kg N/ha. The placement of 56 kg N/ha either as a mudball or with a band applicator and sulfur-coated urea broadcast and incorporated gave similar grain yields, indicating that these techniques or materials are interchangeable. These three treatments gave significantly higher grain yields than did the unfertilized control.

On Luisiana clay, the grain yield was significantly greater when 28 kg N/ha was applied either by split application (3.9 t/ha) or by mudball placement (4.0 t/ha) as compared with the no-fertilizer control (3.4 t/ha). At 56 kg N/ha, the grain yields of the four methods of fertilizer application were, in general, similar. Sulfur-coated urea produced grain yields (3.5 t/ha) similar to yields produced by urea applied as mudball (4.0 t/ha) or as band placement (3.7 t/ha), but lower than yields produced by urea applied in split doses (4.0 t/ha).

The placement of fertilizer nitrogen gave

significantly higher yields only on Maahas clay and not on Luisiana clay. These findings are being checked using other oxisols of South and Southeast Asia.

Time of nitrogen application in farmers' fields.

The optimum time for applying 60 kg N/ha, which is half the optimum rate for a dry season crop, was investigated in six farmers' fields in Laguna, Philippines: Cabuyao, Famy, Lumban, San Pedro, Santa Cruz, and Santa Rosa. The grain yields of all treatments with added nitrogen were similar (5.6–6.0 t/ha), but significantly higher than the grain yields of the no-fertilizer control (4.3 t/ha). At the Cabuyao, Lumban, and Santa Rosa sites, basal incorporated treatments and split application of nitrogen at 10 and 40 days after transplanting and at panicle initiation gave statistically similar grain yields. The highest grain yield of 7.3 t/ha with a productivity of 33 kg rice/kg N (a high efficiency for a crop in farmer's field) was achieved at the Santa Cruz site.

FERTILIZER NITROGEN AND INSECTICIDE EFFICIENCY STUDIES

Agronomy Department

IRRI farm. During the 1975 dry season, the average yields of IR26, IR28, and IR1480-147-3 rices, achieved when carbofuran was applied as mudball, were similar (5.4 t/ha) to the yields realized with conventional insect protection (5.0 t/ha), but were significantly higher than the grain yields (4.5 t/ha) produced without insect protection. The yields of IR26 and IR28 were similar without insect protection (5.1 and 4.6 t/ha, respectively) and with both the conventional insect protection (5.7 and 4.8 t/ha, respectively) and carbofuran applied as mudball (5.7 and 4.8 t/ha, respectively). The yield of IR1480-147-3 without insect protection was 3.8 t/ha and was increased to only 4.4 t/ha with conventional insect protection; however, when carbofuran was applied as mudball the yield was 5.7 t/ha. Insecticide placement as mudball appears to be a feasible method by which to maintain sustained insect control in rice.

A field experiment at the IRRI farm during the 1975 wet season to assess seasonal effects on nitrogen fertilizer efficiency included considera-

tion of the effects of combining fertilizer and insecticide application, using the deep placement concept. The two rice varieties used were Taichung Native 1 (TN1), which is highly susceptible to most insects and diseases, and IR30, which is resistant to certain insects and diseases.

Without fertilizer nitrogen and insect control, TN1 yielded 0.2 t/ha while IR30 yielded 1.9 t/ha. The grain yield of TN1 improved progressively with good insect control measures; this was true for IR30 only when fertilizer nitrogen was applied. Without insect control, both TN1 and IR30 had stable low yields at 0, 28, and 56 kg N/ha rates, with the yields of IR30 being about 2 t/ha, while TN1 yielded about 0.2 t/ha, demonstrating the superior insect resistance of IR30. Under optimum insect control, both TN1 and IR30 responded to increased levels of applied nitrogen, with IR30 producing 4.6 t/ha and TN1 yielding 1.8 t/ha with 56 kg N/ha applied as band placement. With band placement of both fertilizer nitrogen and insecticides, the grain yields of both TN1 and IR30 were markedly similar: 3.6 and 3.7 t/ha with 28 kg N/ha, and 4.1 and 4.2 t/ha with 56 kg N/ha (Table 5). Apparently, when adequate insect control is achieved by a suitable placement technique, both varieties have similar nitrogen response and yield potential.

Results from the 1975 wet-season experiment demonstrate that the use of varieties resistant to certain virus diseases and insects cannot completely substitute for insecticides. An integrated program for the management of insects and virus diseases might well include a suitable combination of rice varieties having a high level of inherent insect and disease resistance and minimal use of insecticides.

Farmers' fields. In the 1975 dry season, in a series of experiments using IR28 rice (resistant to certain insects and diseases), the relative efficiency of fertilizer nitrogen and insecticide as applied with conventional methods was compared with deep placement of these chemicals in mudballs and in gelatin capsules. Two experiments were conducted in farmers' fields (Tiaong and Candelaria) in Quezon province, Philippines, and one was carried out at the IRRI farm.

Table 5. Effects of deep placement, using a band applicator, on the efficiency of fertilizer and insecticide with two rice varieties. IRRI, 1975 wet season.

	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)					
	No insect control		Optimum insect control ^b		Band placement with machine ^c	
	TN1	IR30	TN1	IR30	TN1	IR30
No nitrogen	0.2	1.9	1.1	2.2	1.7	1.8
Band placement (28 kg N/ha)	0.3	2.2	1.4	3.1	3.6	3.7
Band placement (56 kg N/ha)	0	2.0	1.8	4.6	4.1	4.2

^aData are averages of four replications. LSD (5%) for comparing any 2 means is 1.1 t/ha. ^bTwo applications of carbofuran 2.0 kg a.i. (active ingredient)/ha each, plus one application with 0.5 carbofuran + 0.5 lindane. ^cSingle application of carbofuran 2.0 kg a.i./ha.

Without fertilizer nitrogen, grain yields were low, without and with conventional insect protection (about 3.2 t/ha). Under conventional insect protection, grain yields did not differ between 60 kg N/ha applied with deep placement (as mudballs or in capsules) and 100 kg N/ha using split application. These results confirm previous findings at IRRI that indicate the superiority of deep placement over conventional methods of nitrogen application. Because the insect pressure was low in these experiments, the grain yield with 60 kg N/ha as mudball was 5.5 t/ha and 5.3 t/ha without insect protection and with conventional insect protection, respectively. However, deep placement of carbofuran with 60 kg N/ha as mudballs or in capsules increased the grain yield by 0.6 t/ha over conventional insect protection. There was no yield difference between carbofuran applied as mudballs and carbofuran applied in gelatin capsules. These data offer further evidence that the efficiency of fertilizer nitrogen and insecticides can be improved with a practical method of placement.

LONG-TERM FERTILITY EXPERIMENT

Agronomy Department

The 22nd and 23rd crops in the long-term fertility experiment were grown at the IRRI farm in 1975. None of the three rice varieties tested (IR8, IR26, and IR30) yielded a significant response to phosphorus (30 kg P₂O₅/ha) or potassium (30 kg K₂O/ha) when compared with the no-fertilizer control in either the dry or the wet season. In either season, the application of

30 kg P₂O₅/ha gave higher (about 0.4 to 0.5 t/ha) grain yields than the nonfertilized control (Table 6). In both seasons, the yields of IR30 were lower than the yields of IR8 and IR26 which were similar.

Another series of long-term fertility experiments was initiated in 1968 at three experiment stations of the Philippine Bureau of Plant Industry (BP1) as an IRRI-BPI cooperative project.

During the 1975 dry and wet seasons, complete fertilizers gave significantly higher grain yields than did nitrogen alone in all three sites (Table 7). A highly significant phosphorus response was detected at all three locations and in both seasons except during the dry season at the Maligaya and Bicol sites where the grain yields did not differ between these two treatments. The yield response to complete fertilizer (NPK) was not significantly higher than that to nitrogen and phosphorus (NP) at all three sites except during the wet season at the Maligaya site where the grain yield did not differ between the two treatments (Table 7).

Among the three varieties tested, IR8 tended to respond the least to applied phosphorus; the varietal differences to applied phosphorus were significant only at the Bicol and Visayas sites.

During the dry season, potassium response was significant at Maligaya and Bicol. In the wet season, however, it was significant only at Bicol. It was greatest with IR8, the grain yield increase of which was 1.4 t/ha compared with 0.2 t/ha for IR26 and 0.4 t/ha for IR30. On the average, in the dry season in Maligaya and during the dry and wet seasons in Bicol,

Table 6. Effects of NPK fertilization on the grain yields of IR8, IR26, and IR30 rices in the 22nd (dry season) and 23rd (wet season) consecutive crops. IRRI, 1975.

Fertilizer treatment ^a (kg/ha)			Yield ^b (t/ha)			
N	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O	IR8	IR26	IR30	Mean
<i>Dry season</i>						
0	0	0	4.4 b	4.3 c	4.1 b	4.2
140 ^a	0	0	7.9 a	7.0 b	6.3 a	7.1
0	30	0	5.0 b	4.7 c	4.4 b	4.7
0	0	30	4.5 b	4.5 c	4.3 b	4.4
140 ^a	30	0	8.0 a	7.9 a	6.5 a	7.5
140 ^a	0	30	8.0 a	7.9 a	6.0 a	7.3
140 ^a	30	30	8.0 a	7.3 ab	6.3 a	7.2
140 ^{ac}	30	30	7.7 a	7.8 a	6.3 a	7.3
<i>Wet season</i>						
0	0	0	3.9	3.4	3.7	3.7 b
60 ^a	0	0	5.5	5.9	5.4	5.6 a
0	30	0	4.1	4.5	3.8	4.1 b
0	0	30	4.0	4.3	3.3	3.9 b
60 ^a	30	0	5.5	6.0	5.1	5.5 a
60 ^a	0	30	5.3	5.8	5.4	5.5 a
60 ^a	30	30	5.2	5.5	5.4	5.3 a
60 ^{ac}	30	30	5.3	5.7	5.2	5.4 a

^aIncludes 40 kg N/ha topdressed at panicle initiation in the dry season and 20 kg N/ha in the wet season. ^bIn a column means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level; average of four replications. ^cCompost (10 t/ha) plus inorganic (24 kg N/ha compost + 116 kg N/ha inorganic, dry season; 24 kg N/ha + 36 kg N/ha inorganic, wet season).

potassium (with NP) increased the grain yield of IR8 by 1.7 t/ha and that of IR26 and of IR30 by 0.8 t/ha each.

Clearly, IR8 demonstrated a higher response to applied potassium than did IR26 and IR28.

Monitoring soil fertility appears to be essential to maintain stable high yields with a practical program of soil fertility management.

FERTILIZER-SAVING CULTURAL PRACTICES

Soil Chemistry Department

Water management. Studies on the long-term effects of continuous submergence (flood fallow)

and soil drying between crops (dry fallow), with and without midseason soil drying, on the growth and yield of rice were continued in the 1975 dry and wet seasons with minor management alterations. In 1974, the increase in yield of rice in continuously flooded soils was shown to be caused mainly by nitrogen effects, and drying the soil at midseason was found to be beneficial because it causes extra nitrogen to be released. Since the rice plant needs the released nitrogen at an early stage of growth, soil drying was initiated soon after transplanting, instead of at midseason, and was continued for 2 weeks.

The results of the 1975 IR26 rice crop confirmed the significant benefits of flood fallowing

Table 7. Effects of NPK fertilization on the grain yield of IR8, IR26, and IR30 rices in the 15th (dry season) and 16th (wet season) crop in long-term fertility experiments at three locations (av. of three replications). Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center, Bicol Rice and Corn Experiment Station, and Visayas Rice Experiment Station, Philippines. IRRI-BPI cooperative experiments, 1975.

Fertilizer (kg/ha)			Yield ^b (t/ha)						Av.
N ^a	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O	Maligaya		Bicol		Visayas		
			Dry	Wet	Dry	Wet	Dry	Wet	
0	0	0	2.9 d	2.3 c	3.5 d	2.7 d	2.1 d	2.4 d	2.7
140/70	0	0	3.9 c	3.1 b	4.7 c	3.2 c	3.5 c	3.0 c	3.6
140/70	60	0	4.1 bc	3.5 a	5.0 c	4.0 b	4.8 b	5.1 b	4.4
140/70	0	60	4.4 b	3.0 b	5.8 b	3.7 b	3.4 c	2.8 c	3.8
140/70	60	60	5.4 a	3.6 a	7.2 a	4.8 a	5.3 a	5.7 a	5.3
140/70	60	30 + 30 ^c	5.7 a	3.6 a	7.1 a	4.8 a	4.9 ab	5.2 b	5.2

^a140 kg N/ha in the dry season; 70 kg N/ha in the wet season, including 40 kg N/ha in the dry season and 30 kg N/ha in the wet season topdressed at panicle initiation. ^bAv. of three varieties. In a column means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^cApplied in split doses: basal + panicle initiation.

Table 8. Response of rices (av. of two varieties) to liming, with and without phosphorus, on an acid Luisiana clay in a farmer's field, Philippines.^a

NPV treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)		
	L ₀	L ₁	NPV means ^b
N ₀ P ₀ V ₁	2.46	2.55	2.50 c
N ₀ P ₀ V ₂	1.67	1.87	1.77 d
N ₀ P ₁ V ₁	3.22	3.49	3.36 b
N ₀ P ₀ V ₂	2.22	2.63	2.42 c
N ₁ P ₀ V ₁	3.11	3.50	3.32 b
N ₀ P ₀ V ₂	2.34	2.65	2.50 c
N ₀ P ₁ V ₁	3.71	4.12	3.92 a
N ₀ P ₀ V ₂	2.64	2.67	2.66 c

^aL₀: 0 t lime/ha; N₀: 0 kg N/ha; P₀: 0 kg P/ha; V₁: IR26; L₁: 10 t lime/ha; N₁: 50 kg N/ha; P₁: 25 kg P/ha; V₂: MI-48.
^bMeans followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

over dry fallowing even without fertilization. Soil drying after transplanting was shown to be beneficial as evidenced by the fact that the plants became green on resubmergence and gave a higher grain yield.

Effect of straw incorporation. Luisiana clay, Maahas clay, and Pila clay loam were placed separately in 200-liter drums, and compacted until the surface was 25 cm below the rim. A basal dressing of 50 ppm N as ammonium sulfate was applied to the top 20-cm portion of soil and 125 g of chopped rice straw was added to some of the soils. The soils were kept continuously submerged during the cropping season.

The incorporation of straw to the soil increased the straw and grain yields of IR26 grown on all three soils; this increase was highly significant in Luisiana clay for both the straw and grain yields and for the grain yield achieved on the Pila clay loam. The increase in straw yield due to the incorporation of straw into the soil was significant on both the Maahas clay and the Pila clay loam.

Straw as a source of nutrients. When the long-term response of four rice varieties to three water regimes (dry fallow, wet fallow, and dry fallow with midseason soil drying) with and without incorporation of straw was studied, straw incorporation was found to decrease the soil pH regardless of the water treatment. Additionally, it increased the nitrogen content, available P, exchangeable K, grain yield, plant height, and the tiller number.

During the dry season, straw application with the wet fallow treatment gave an increase of 0.93

t/ha for IR26 and 0.69 t/ha for IR2071-625-3.

A long-term experiment was used to investigate the effect on soil composition and yield of rice of four methods of applying straw: removed, burned in situ, plowed in, and composted and incorporated.

For the past seven croppings, all four methods of straw application increased the nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, and organic matter contents, as well as the grain yield. The straw compost, however, had the greatest effect on the soil nutrients and organic matter; it increased the organic matter by 0.78 percent, nitrogen by 0.049 percent, the available phosphorus by 18.4 ppm, and the exchangeable potassium by 0.21 meq/100 g.

Forms of nitrogen fertilizer and compost. A long-term study of the effects of 100 kg N/ha as ammonium sulfate and as urea in the presence and absence of 10 t compost/ha on the yield of rice and on soil composition showed that the continuous use of ammonium sulfate reduced the pH of the soil after seven cropping seasons. The application of straw compost substantially increased the content of nitrogen, available phosphorus, and exchangeable potassium.

During the dry season, compost application increased grain yield by an average of 0.67 t/ha and 0.38 t/ha during the wet season. Neither the ammonium sulfate nor the urea affected significantly the grain yield.

LIMING OF RICE SOILS

Agronomy Department

An experiment was carried out in a farmer's field on flooded Luisiana clay, an acid soil (pH 4.7), to observe the response of IR26 and MI-48 rice varieties to added lime (10 t/ha), nitrogen (50 kg/ha), and phosphorus (25 kg/ha).

The plants responded to the applied phosphorus at maximum tillering when they were taller and had more tillers. Lime did not cause any difference in plant appearance at this stage, although it did raise the pH from 4.7 to 5.9. Additionally, during the wet season, liming effected a significant increase in the grain yield, but no significant interaction was observed among the lime, nitrogen, and phosphorus treatments (Table 8).

Soil and crop management

Soil and crop culture

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PROSPECTS FOR RAISING PRODUCTIVITY OF RICE BY RATOONING

Agronomy Department

To explore the potential of ratooning rice after the dry-season crop in irrigated areas and after the rainy-season crop in rainfed areas for increasing the productivity of the land, a series of experiments was conducted at the IRRI farm between December 1973 and December 1975.

Cutting height and nitrogen level. The effects of the height at which the main crop is cut (cutting height) and the nitrogen level of the ratoon crop on the grain yield of IR28 rice grown as ratoon were studied during the 1975 dry season.

The main crop was fertilized in a split dose with 120-30-30 kg (N-P₂O₅-K₂O)/ha, by broadcasting one third of the nitrogen and all of the phosphorus and potassium shortly before the last land preparation, and by applying the rest of the nitrogen at panicle initiation.

The four cutting heights used were ground level, 5, 15, and 20 cm. Shortly after the main crop was harvested, nitrogen was broadcast in a single application at 20, 40, 60, or 80 kg/ha; one plot received no nitrogen.

The optimum cutting height in relation to grain yield production was found to be 15 or

20 cm above ground level (fig. 1). The percentage of missing hills was low when the cutting height was 15 cm (12%) and 20 cm (5%) but reached a high of 37 percent when the cutting height was 5 cm. The percentage of missing hills was significantly lower when the cutting height was 15 cm or 20 cm as compared with a cutting height of 5 cm. Thus, lowering the cutting height from 15 to 5 cm increased the percentage of missing hills by 24 percent and prolonged the growth duration by 13 days. The ground-level cutting reduced the stand of the ratoon crop when the water depth was 5 to 7 cm.

Neither the cutting height nor the level of applied nitrogen significantly affected the tiller number of the ratoon crop because the tillers were produced either by continuation of the previous shoot or by emergence from the nodes.

As the rate of nitrogen applied to the ratoon crop increased, the grain yield, number of filled grains per panicle, panicle length, and plant height increased, while the number of unfilled grains declined. The grain yield at 0, 20, 40, 60, and 80 kg N/ha was 1.0, 1.0, 1.1, 1.5, and 1.5 t/ha, respectively, with the optimum rate of nitrogen being 60 kg/ha. The grain yield at 60 kg N/ha was significantly higher than that achieved with lower levels of applied nitrogen. However, there was no significant difference in the grain yields between the 60 kg N/ha and the 80 kg N/ha treatments.

Grassy stunt occurred in all treatments in the ratoon crop, but it was only about 1 percent and did not vary with treatment or among the plots.

Plant spacing and cutting height. The effects of plant spacing and cutting height on the grain yield of the ratoon crop of IR28 and IR2061-464-2 were studied during the 1975 dry season in a split-split plot experiment with four replications. Rice variety and lines were placed on the main plots, while 15- × 15-cm, 20- × 20-cm, and 25- × 25-cm plant spacings and the four cutting heights (ground level, 5, 10, and 20 cm above the ground) were placed on the subplots.

The main crop, 21-day-old seedlings transplanted at three different spacings, was fertilized with NPK at 90-30-30 kg/ha, applied in two split doses as described previously.

1. Effect of cutting height of the main crop and nitrogen level in the ratoon crop on grain yield of IR28. IRRI, 1975 dry season.

Nitrogen was applied to the ratoon crop at 60 kg/ha shortly after the main crop was harvested.

The effect of spacing on the yield of the main crop tended to decline as spacing increased (fig. 2). However, plant spacing had no significant effect on the ratoon crop.

IR28 rice had a significantly higher grain yield (1.3 t/ha) than IR2061-464-2 (0.9 t/ha). Cutting the main crop at 15 and 20 cm above ground level produced a significantly higher grain yield and a shorter growth duration in the ratoon crop than did cutting at 5 cm. Ratoons were not produced on the majority of the hills when the main crop was cut at ground level and 5 to 7 cm water was maintained.

The number of tillers declined in the ratoon crop with wider plant spacing. The height at which the main crop was cut affected the number of tillers in the ratoon crop; more tillers were produced in the ratoon crop when the cutting height was 5 cm than when the cutting height was 15 or 20 cm. The ratoon crop had more tillers than the main crop, because generally more tillers grow from a previous shoot or from a node which may produce more than one new tiller in every shoot.

Both plant spacing and cutting height significantly affected the number of missing hills. The plants spaced at 15 × 15 cm had significantly more missing hills than plants spaced at 20 × 20 cm or at 25 × 25 cm. There were more missing hills when the cutting height was 5 cm than when it was 15 or 20 cm above the ground level.

The ratoon crop of both IR28 and IR2061-464-2 rices became infected with a virus; 4 percent of the IR2061-464-2 hills were infected while only 1 percent of the IR28 hills became infected.

Cutting height and water management. In the 1975 dry-season study of the effect of cutting height of the main crop and water management in the ratoon crop on the grain yield of a IR2061-632-3 ratoon crop, the five irrigation treatments were continuous flooding and irrigation at 4, 8, 12, and 16 days after harvest. The main crop was cut at ground level or at least 15 cm above the ground. The ratoon crop was

2. Effect of plant spacing and cutting height on grain yields of main and ratoon crops. IRR1, 1975 dry season.

fertilized with 60 kg N/ha shortly after the main crop was harvested.

The grain yield and other plant characters in the ratoon crop in general declined compared with the main crop. The grain yield of rices cut at ground level was lower than the yield of rices cut at 15 cm, but these differences were only significant with continuously flooded rices.

Cutting the main crop at ground level should enable the ratoon plants, except those continuously flooded, to produce more panicles and more filled grains per panicle and hence, theoretically, result in increased grain yields. However, cutting at the ground level resulted in more missing hills, with the percentage of missing hills increasing as the time of irrigation from harvesting was shortened (16 to 33 percent). Thus, the grain yield of the ratoon crop was lower when the main crop was cut at ground level than when it was cut at 15 cm above the soil surface.

Plants cut at ground level produced thicker roots and more tillers, but they matured 9 days later than did plants cut at 15 cm.

Since there were more weeds in the fields drained during harvesting of the main crop to promote tillering of the ratoon crop when the main crop was cut at ground level, it appears advisable to keep the field flooded (5 to 7 cm depth) and to cut the main crop at 15 cm above the soil surface. Also, when the main crop is cut at 15 cm above the ground level, the ratoon

plants were found to have a higher daily productivity per hectare (40 kg rice/ha daily) than when the main crop is cut at ground level (maximum of 35 kg rice/ha daily).

The maximum grain yield (2.6 t/ha) was obtained from the ratoon crop within 62 days in the crop cut at 15 cm.

The grassy stunt infection (about 0.5 percent) was found only in the ratoon crop. Generally, a higher degree of infection occurred at the higher cutting height.

Tillage method and nitrogen level. The effects of tillage method and nitrogen level of the main crop on the grain yield of IR28 ratoons were studied during the 1975 wet season.

The three tillage methods were zero tillage with the application of paraquat (1.0 kg active ingredient/ha), paraquat followed by harrowing, and plowing followed by harrowing. Nitrogen at 0, 30, 60, 90, and 120 kg/ha was broadcast in two split doses. Phosphorus and potassium were also applied each at 30 kg/ha.

The main crop was harvested by cutting at 15 cm, and shortly afterwards 60 kg N/ha was applied.

Grain yields in the main crop under zero tillage was significantly lower (2.2 t/ha) than those obtained under the three methods of tillage employed, which were similar, ranging between 3.2 and 3.7. However, among the three tillage methods, the yields increased with an increased intensity of land preparation; plowing followed by harrowing gave the maximum yield (3.7 t/ha).

The effect of different methods of tillage on the main crop was even more clear on the ratoon crop, where, as was the case with the main crop, plants under zero tillage produced the lowest grain yield (0.3 t/ha), while the plots prepared by plowing followed by harrowing produced the highest (1.1 t/ha).

The method of tillage had no significant effect on the tiller number in the main crop, but in the ratoon crop, regular land preparation was associated with the production of a higher number of tillers.

While the method of tillage did not affect the number of filled grains per panicle in either the main crop (40 to 44 percent) or the ratoon (13 to 17 percent) crop, there were less filled grains

per panicle and a greater percentage of unfilled grains in the ratoon crop.

Nitrogen fertilizer is necessary for improved grain yields in both the main crop and the ratoon crop. With an increase in the rate of applied nitrogen to the main crop, a gradual increase in grain yield of both the main crop (2.69 to 3.46 t/ha) and the ratoon crop (0.36 to 0.99 t/ha) and an increase in the number of filled grains per panicle (11 to 19) in only the ratoon crop occurred. The range of increase in the number of filled grains per panicle over the applied nitrogen range in the main crop was only from 41 to 45.

An increase in the level of applied nitrogen caused a similar increase in the number of tillers in both the main crop and the ratoon crop.

While the decision to raise a ratoon crop will depend on many factors, a good stand of the main crop is shown to be essential for the success of the ratoon crop.

These studies indicate that the prospect for raising a successful ratoon crop will largely depend on the ratooning ability of a variety, the level of resistance to insects and diseases of the variety, the judgment on the stand of the main crop, the condition of the moisture supply from rain or irrigation, and the cultural practices such as proper cutting height, nitrogen level, and water management. The feasibility of a ratoon crop depends upon the entire cropping system adopted rather than on the individual ratoon crop.

MANAGEMENT FOR SUBMERGENCE TOLERANCE

Plant Physiology Department

Improving the resistance of rice seedlings to complete submergence. The rice plant is usually flooded or completely submerged during the seedling stage when it is most susceptible to flooding injury. The fact that not all the seedlings of a variety die when submerged for 7 to 10 days suggests the possibility of increasing plant survival per unit area by increasing the seedling rate per hill, which results in less missing hills per unit area. In a field trial in which 20-day-old IR30 seedlings were planted at 1 and 5 seedlings/

Table 1. Effect of submergence on IR30 rice seedlings planted at the rate of 1 and 5 seedlings/hill.

Treatment	Seedlings (no./hill)	Missing hills (%)	Tillers (no./sq m)			Grain yield (t/ha)
			Before submergence	5 days after submergence	Harvest	
Control	1	0	69	359	258	4.75
	5	0	219	540	325	4.30
Submerged	1	22	58	41	174	2.43
	5	2	257	201	328	4.00

LSD (.05) for grain yield = 0.42.

hill, the seedlings were completely submerged 10 days after transplanting. The water was removed 10 days later and kept at a 5 cm depth.

Increasing the number of seedlings per hill considerably reduced the number of missing hills per unit area after submergence (Table 1). The difference between the control and treated plots of 5 seedlings/hill was small but significant.

Tolerance to submergence includes both the ability to survive submergence and the ability to recover from submergence. Submergence reduced the number of tillers. The 1 seedling/hill plots were not able to recover in terms of number of panicles per square meter at harvest. Submergence reduced the number of tillers per unit area of the 5 seedlings/hill plots, but at harvest the number of panicles was similar to that of the nonsubmerged plants of 5 seedlings/hill and was larger than that of the nonsubmerged plants of 1 seedling/hill.

At 5 plants/hill, the grain yield of the submerged plants did not differ significantly from

that of the unsubmerged plants, indicating that increasing the number of seedlings per hill prevented the adverse effect of submergence on grain yield. However, unsubmerged 1 seedling/hill plots gave the highest grain yield (4.75 t/ha) which was significantly higher than the yield from the submerged and unsubmerged plants.

Increasing the number of seedlings per hill may decrease the yield in an area not flooded. However, planting more seedlings (five versus one) per hill in areas where inundation is a yearly occurrence can preclude yield losses caused by submergence damage to rice.

The possibility that a variety of a slightly longer duration may give even better results, since it will have a longer time to recover from the flood, will be examined in future trials at IRRI. A variety that is tolerant of submergence and has a rapid recovery rate will also lessen the deleterious effect of submergence on rice yields. Such rices are being screened and developed.

Environment and its influence

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SUMMARY

The influence of air temperature on the ripening of rice was studied on two varieties of rice cultured in artificially lighted growth cabinets. The duration of the grain-filling period was markedly affected by the ambient air temperature. Within the mean temperature range of 16° through 28°C, the higher the temperature, the faster the grain filled and matured. At a mean temperature of 28°C, only 13 days were required for the upper grains of IR20 rice to mature.

The effective grain-filling period was 24 days for a field crop of IR20 at Los Baños, Philippines. By using the effective grain-filling period, the maximum possible yields were estimated to be 7 t/ha for the wet season and 13 t/ha for the dry season at Los Baños. The optimum daily mean temperature for ripening was 19 to 25°C for IR20 rice and 16 to 22°C for Fujisaka 5 rice. Temperature can be described in several ways, such as daily mean temperature, night temperature, and day-night temperature difference. Among these, the daily mean temperature was found to be the most meaningful expression by which to describe the effect of temperature on ripening of rice.

Low light intensity had a marked effect on the percentage of filled grains on the low primary branches of the rice plant, but not on the high primary branches. High light intensity with low temperature appeared to be the combination having the greatest positive effect on the ripening of IR20 and Fujisaka 5 rices.

EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE ON THE DURATION OF THE GRAIN-FILLING PERIOD

Plant Physiology Department

The duration of the grain-filling period (GFP), or the time required to reach the maximum grain weight, greatly affects the total amount of solar radiation available during grain filling, and hence is a powerful determinant of yield. The durations of the GFP of an indica rice (IR20) and a japonica rice (Fujisaka 5) were studied in artificially lighted growth cabinets.

IR20 and Fujisaka 5 plants were grown in the glasshouse room at 29/21°C (day/night) until 3 days after anthesis. The plants were then transferred to artificially lighted growth cabinets and cultured under five temperature regimes: 20°/12°C, 23°/15°C, 26°/18°C, 29°/21°C, and 32°/24°C. Sample grains were taken from three upper branches. For brevity, data will be presented for only three temperature regimes: 20°/12°C, 26°/18°C, and 32°/24°C.

The rate of grain filling was faster and the GFP was shorter at higher temperatures in both rice varieties (fig. 1). IR20 leaves turned yellow within 24 hours after the plants were subjected to 20/12°C, indicating that this temperature range is subnormal for normal leaf activity. Grain filling at this temperature was very slow, but the final grain weight was

1. Effects of temperature on grain growth of IR20 and Fujisaka 5.

similar to that achieved under the 26/18°C and 32/24°C regimes. The duration of the GFP was 13 days at 32/24°C and 33 days at 20/12°C.

Leaves of Fujisaka 5 rice remained green even at 20/12°C. The grain weight at 32/24°C declined after the peak weight was reached. The final grain weight at 32/24°C was about 15 percent less than that at 20/12°C. The duration of the GFP was 18 days at 32/24°C and 43 days at 20/12°C. Temperature appeared to affect markedly the GFP. Varietal differences in the duration of grain filling were observed. This subject is now being investigated in greater detail.

EFFECTIVE GRAIN-FILLING PERIOD IN THE FIELD

Plant Physiology Department

The difference in the duration of the GFP in the field between 30 days at Los Baños, Philippines, and 65 days at Sapporo, Japan, and Yanco, Australia is due, in large part, to a difference in the temperature during the ripening period in these diverse locations.

However, as mentioned previously, the upper grains of IR20 rice matured in 13 days after anthesis at 32/24°C which is comparable to the daily mean temperature at Los Baños during the time of grain ripening. Thus, something besides ambient temperature must be responsible for the difference in the duration of the GFP of a rice crop in the field and that of the grains on the upper branches of a rice panicle.

Within the same panicle it takes about 3 days for all the spikelets to complete anthesis.

Additionally, 14 days are required for all the panicles to emerge in the same field (fig. 2, upper graph). Thus, a total of 13 days for the duration of the GFP for the upper grains, 3 days for the anthesis of all the spikelets on the same panicle, and 14 days for panicle emergence in the same field yields 30 days as the total duration of the GFP for IR20 rice in the field. This was substantiated by measuring the grain weight at sequential stages during ripening (fig. 2, bottom graph). Flowering (or heading) is defined in agronomic terms as the time when 50 percent of the panicles of a rice crop has

2. Grain growth of IR20 in the fields, wet season, 1975, IRRI.

emerged. Using this definition, the duration of the GFP for IR20 rice at Los Baños, Philippines is 23 days. In other words, IR20 rice matures 23 days after flowering under Los Baños conditions.

The grain growth curve of rice (fig. 2) has three components: a slow growth phase at the early stage of ripening, a linear growth phase, and another slow growth phase during the late stage of ripening. The increase in grain weight is substantial only during the linear growth phase; it is almost negligible during the two slow growth phases. The effective GFP for IR20 rice is 24 days (fig. 2). The effective GFP can be used to estimate a possible maximum grain yield.

Dry matter production (ΔW , g/sq m) of a crop can be estimated by the following formula:

$$\Delta W = \frac{Eu \times T \times \bar{S}}{K} \times 10^4$$

where Eu is efficiency of solar energy utilization (in percent), T is effective GFP (days), $\bar{S}$ is mean

Table 1. Estimated maximum yield for wet and dry season rice crops at Los Baños, Philippines.

Season	Efficiency of solar energy use ^a (%)	Estimated maximum yield (t/ha)	Recorded yield (t/ha)		Percentage achieved ^c	
			Normal	CO ₂ enriched	Normal	CO ₂ enriched ^b
Wet	3.3	9.5			63	81
Wet	2.5	7.3	6.0	7.7	82	105
Dry	3.3	17.0			53	78
Dry	2.5	13.4	9.0	13.3	67	99

^a3.3% is the highest recorded value in Japan during the International Biological Program Years from 1967 to 1971. ^bFor 30 days before flowering to increase spikelet number. ^cRecorded yield divided by the estimated maximum yield times 100.

solar radiation ($\text{cal}\cdot\text{sq cm}^{-1}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$), and K is heat of combustion for brown rice (4 kcal/g). The dry matter produced during the ripening period is assumed to be used for grain production. The maximum grain yield was estimated (Table 1) by using conversion factors for husk weight and moisture content and estimating the contribution of the carbohydrate stored before flowering to the grain yield.

The percentage achieved (last column of Table 1) is the ratio of input energy to the output energy. This provides a rational basis for comparing rice yields under different environments. Rice performs better (higher percentage achieved) in the wet season than in the dry season. The percentage achieved for the carbon dioxide-enriched rice crops is about 100 percent, suggesting that the maximum grain yield to be achieved under realistic situations is 7 t/ha for the wet season and 13 t/ha for the dry season.

Table 2. Effects of daily mean temperature on grain weight and grain quality of IR20 and Fujisaka 5 rices.

Mean temperature (°C)	Grain wt ^a (mg/grain)	Grain quality	
		Chalky ^b grains (%)	Green grains (%)
<i>IR20</i>			
16	14.3 (86)	83	11
19	16.3 (98)	16	9
22	16.6 (100)	11	8
25	16.3 (98)	12	8
28	15.5 (93)	31	9
<i>Fujisaka 5</i>			
16	23.7 (100)	14	8
19	23.6 (100)	9	0
22	23.7 (100)	11	0
25	22.5 (95)	14	0
28	21.2 (89)	58	0

^aFigures in parentheses represent percentages in relation to the maximum value. ^bIncluding chalky, white center, white belly, and white back grains.

EFFECT OF DAILY MEAN, NIGHT, AND DAY TEMPERATURES ON GRAIN WEIGHT AND QUALITY

Plant Physiology Department

Once the percentage of fertilization is established at flowering, the weight per grain is another important determinant of yield in the rice plant. A daily mean temperature (DMT) of 20° to 22°C is reported to be the optimum for ripening in Japan. Low night temperatures are believed to result in greater grain weight with better quality. Since low night temperatures are concomitant with a lower DMT, it is not clear whether a low night temperature per se or a low DMT improves grain yield and quality in rice.

The effect of temperature regimes on ripening of rice was studied in a series of experiments with an indica rice (IR20) and a japonica rice (Fujisaka 5) cultured in artificially lighted growth cabinets.

Daily mean temperature. The DMT (mean of the day/night temperature regime) was varied from 16 to 28°C with a constant day-night temperature difference of 8°C. Thus, when the daily mean temperature was 28°C, the day temperature was held at 32°C and the night temperature at 24°C.

The two varieties of rice responded to temperature in different ways (Table 2). The weight of the IR20 grain (milligrams per grain) was greatest when the DMT was 19 and 25°C, but when the DMT was 16°C, the grain weight decreased by 14 percent. The weight of the Fujisaka 5 grain was highest when the DMT was between 16 and 22°C, while the grain weight decreased by 11 percent when the DMT was

Table 3. Effects of night temperature on grain weight and grain quality of IR20 and Fujisaka 5 rices at a constant day temperature of 32°C.

Night temperature (°C)	Mean temperature (°C)	Grain wt ^a (mg/grain)	Grain quality	
			Chalky grains (%)	Green grains (%)
<i>IR20</i>				
14	23	15.8 (98)	42	5
20	26	16.2 (100)	24	5
26	29	15.9 (98)	33	5
32	32	15.4 (95)	81	5
<i>Fujisaka 5</i>				
14	23	19.9 (90)	89	0
20	26	22.0 (100)	25	0
26	29	21.6 (98)	51	0
32	32	20.6 (94)	93	0

^aFigures in parentheses represent percentages in relation to the maximum value.

28°C. Thus, the optimum temperature for ripening was higher for IR20 (an indica rice) than for Fujisaka 5 (a japonica rice); IR20 was more sensitive to lower temperatures.

The incidence of chalky grains (poorer quality) in both rice varieties was associated with divergence from the optimum temperature for maximum grain weight since their percentage increased sharply when the DMT was above or below the optimum temperature.

Night temperature. Night temperature was varied from 14° to 32°C, while the day temperature was held constant at 32°C. Thus, the daily mean temperature ranged from 23° to 32°C. Within this range of temperature regimes there was not much difference in grain weight among the different temperature regimes, except when the night temperature for Fujisaka 5 rice was 14 C (Table 3). Apparently, the large difference (18 C) between day and night temperatures had an adverse effect on the ripening of Fujisaka 5 rice plants. The 32°/14°C temperature regime gave a DMT of 23°C which should have been optimum for ripening of Fujisaka 5 rice.

Day temperature. The day temperature was varied from 16 to 34°C, and the night temperature was kept constant at 16°C. Hence, the DMT ranged between 16 and 25°C. The weight of IR20 grains was lowest when the day temperature was 16°C (Table 4), which is below the optimum for leaf photosynthesis in this variety of rice. The grain weight of Fujisaka 5 rice was lowest when the day temperature was 34 C. Again, the differential response of the two

Table 4. Effects of day temperature on grain weight and grain quality of IR20 and Fujisaka 5 rices at a constant night temperature of 16°C.

Day temperature (°C)	Mean temperature (°C)	Grain wt ^a (mg/grain)	Grain quality	
			Chalky grains (%)	Green grains (%)
<i>IR20</i>				
16	16	13.3 (82)	87	3
22	19	15.9 (98)	7	21
28	22	16.2 (100)	12	11
34	25	15.0 (93)	82	2
<i>Fujisaka 5</i>				
16	16	22.4 (97)	10	0
22	19	23.2 (100)	2	0
28	22	22.8 (98)	14	0
34	25	18.7 (81)	99	0

^aFigures in parentheses represent percentages in relation to the maximum value.

rice varieties to temperature was obvious; IR20 rice was sensitive to a low temperature and Fujisaka 5 rice was sensitive to a high temperature.

Overall examination of the temperature effect. The relationship between grain weight and daily mean temperature of IR20 and Fujisaka 5 rices, regardless of the difference in the day and night temperatures, is graphically summarized in fig. 3. For both IR20 and Fujisaka 5, there are smooth and consistent trends in changes in grain weight as affected by the DMT, except when the difference between the day and night temperature was 18°C in Fujisaka 5 rice. Maximum grain weight of Fujisaka 5 rice was achieved at the low temperature range, while the grain weight of IR20 remained high and

3. Relationship between 1,000-grain weight and mean temperature.

stable at the high temperature range. Thus, within the temperature range between 14 and 34°C, the DMT appears to be the most meaningful expression by which to describe the effect of temperature on ripening of rice.

A difference of 18°C in the day and night temperature during ripening may have a deleterious effect on some varieties of rice. In the continent type of climate, large differences in the day and night temperatures are common. A night temperature of 15°C has been reported to prevent or delay panicle initiation of rice even when the day temperature is maintained at 33°C. In this experiment, however, it is the large difference between day and night temperatures that had an adverse effect on the ripening of rice rather than a low night temperature per se.

EFFECT OF LIGHT AND TEMPERATURE ON GRAIN WEIGHT

Plant Physiology Department

In a field crop, low light intensities were found to decrease the grain yield of rice by decreasing the percentage of filled grain (1973 Annual Report). It is not possible, however, to study in the field the effect of interactions between light and temperature on ripening of rice grains. Thus, the effect of light and temperature on the ripening of rice was studied in artificially lighted growth cabinets.

Since the final grain yield is determined by grain weight (W) and filled grain percentage

Table 5. Effects of light and temperature on the grain growth of IR20 and Fujisaka 5 rices.

Light ^a	Temperature ^b	Grain wt (W) (mg)	Filled grains (F) (%)	Ripening grade (W × F)
<i>IR20</i>				
Low	Low	15.5	65	1014 (71)
Low	High	14.8	62	910 (64)
High	Low	16.3	87	1423 (100)
High	High	16.0	86	1370 (96)
<i>Fujisaka 5</i>				
Low	Low	22.0	86	1890 (90)
Low	High	20.4	84	1718 (82)
High	Low	23.0	91	2102 (100)
High	High	21.9	92	2013 (96)

^aLow: 36 cal·sq cm⁻¹·day⁻¹ photosynthetically active radiation (PAR); high: 114 cal·sq cm⁻¹·day⁻¹ PAR. ^bLow: 23°/15°C (day/night); high: 32°/24°C (day/night). ^cFigures in parentheses represent percentages in relation to the maximum value.

4. Effects of light on grain filling of IR20 at 32/24°C. (Low light = 36 cal·sq cm⁻¹·day⁻¹; high light = 114 cal·sq cm⁻¹·day⁻¹ PAR.)

(F), and since temperature and light affect both of these factors (W) and (F), the temperature-light interactions can be best assessed by computing the ripening grade (W × F). A combination of high light intensity and low temperature gives the highest yield, while that of low light intensity and high temperature gives the lowest yield (Table 5). The yield could be decreased by as much as 36 percent in IR20 rice and 18 percent in Fujisaka 5 rice with manipulation of the light and temperature regimes.

Light intensity has a different effect on the grain weight and the filled grain percentage at different positions on the same panicle of rice (fig. 4). Low light intensity decreased markedly

the percentage of filled grains on the lower primary branches, but had no such effect on the grains of higher primary branches. Thus, low light intensity decreased grain yield by affecting

the ripening of grains on the lower portion of the rice panicle. The effect of light intensity on the percentage of filled grains is greater than its effect on grain weight.

Constraints on rice yields

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SUMMARY

We conducted biological experiments and socio-economic surveys to identify constraints to higher yields in four areas of the Philippines.

In the dry season, a higher level of nitrogen fertilizer can usually be profitably applied. It was difficult to identify an economically optimum package of inputs for the wet season that consistently gave yields higher than about 3.5 t/ha, which many farmers were already producing. To develop a more profitable combination of inputs, scientists will have to identify insect control measures that are more cost efficient.

In an evaluation of alternate experimental techniques, we found that, for conducting yield constraints-experiments in farmers' fields, non-leveled plots may be more desirable in terms of operation and cost than the traditional leveled plots.

Research on constraints to high yields using a similar methodology is currently being conducted by rice research workers at six other locations in Bangladesh, Indonesia, Sri Lanka, Taiwan, and Thailand. We are continuing to test and improve both the agronomic and socioeconomic methodology so that the procedures can easily be adopted by scientists in other institutions.

BIOLOGICAL CONSTRAINTS

Agronomy and Statistics Departments

In 1975, we expanded our research into the yield reductions that result from farmers' use of low levels of inputs. Experiments were conducted in four areas of the Philippines (Table 1). The results of these experiments are

reported in this section. Economic analysis of experimental results is reported in the following section.

The *yield-constraints* experiment consisted of a factorial combination of fertilizer, insect control, weed control, and in some cases, land preparation. Each input was tested at two levels: the *farmer's level* and the *high level*. At the farmer's level, we attempted to simulate the rate and method of application of each input used by the farmer on whose field the experiment was located. The high level was the level of each input that was expected to give maximum yield. Through experiments on a sample of farms, we identified the difference or gap between farmers' actual yields and the farm yields possible with high inputs. The same experiments measured how much each tested input contributed to the difference.

At most sites, we conducted *management package* experiments in which the inputs tested in the yield-constraints experiment were applied at intermediate levels between the farmer's level and the high level, with all other *cultural practices* held at the *farmer's level*. These experiments permitted us to measure the effects of incremental increases on the level of the input "package" and provided a basis for economic evaluation.

In addition, we examined the effect on yields of using 30 kg P₂O₅/ha in Laguna province (most farmers presently use little or no phosphorus). We evaluated the contribution of incremental levels of the management package, holding all other *cultural practices* at the *high level* believed necessary for maximum yields, at sites in Nueva Ecija, Camarines Sur, and Iloilo provinces. These experiments provided additional information on the effect on yield of other

Table 1. Number and types of experiments to measure and identify components of yield gaps on farmers' fields. Laguna, Nueva Ecija, Camarines Sur, and Iloilo provinces, Philippines, 1975 dry and wet seasons.

Type of experiment	Experiments (no.) in							
	Laguna		Nueva Ecija		Camarines Sur		Iloilo	
	Dry	Wet	Dry	Wet	Dry	Wet	Dry	Wet
Yield constraints	9	20	3	11	3	6	—	—
Management package—farmer's cultural practices	9	5	3	11	3	6	—	—
Management package—optimal cultural practices	—	—	3	11	3	6	2	3

Table 2. Average levels of inputs used by farmers, and levels of four input management packages, at three experimental locations. Philippines, 1975 dry and wet seasons.

Province	Package level ^a	Fertilizer (kg/ha)		Insect control ^b				Weed control ^c			
				Seedbed		Field		RW	HW	C	
		N	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O	F	G	F				G
<i>Dry season</i>											
Laguna	M ₁	63	5	1	1.7	0.0	2.3	0.2	0.9	1.0	0.0
Nueva Ecija	M ₁	118	52	0	0.3	0.3	1.0	1.0	0.0	0.7	0.3
Camarines Sur	M ₁	36	16	16	0.7	0.0	1.7	0.0	0.3	0.3	0.3
All three	M ₂	40	10	0	0.0	0.0	2.0	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.0
All three	M ₃	80	20	20	1.0	0.0	2.0	1.0	0.0	0.0	1.0
All three	M ₄	120	30	30	2.0	0.0	3.0	2.0	0.0	0.0	1.0
All three	M ₅	160	40	40	2.0	1.0	5.0	3.0	0.0	1.0	1.0
<i>Wet season</i>											
Laguna	M ₁	74	3	2	0.0	0.0	2.3	0.4	1.2	1.2	0.3
Nueva Ecija	M ₁	79	22	2	0.8	0.3	0.9	0.4	0.1	0.2	0.4
Camarines Sur	M ₁	28	15	8	1.0	0.0	3.3	0.0	0.2	0.2	1.0
All three	M ₂	25	10	0	0.0	0.0	2.0	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.0
All three	M ₃	50	20	10	1.0	0.0	2.0	1.0	0.0	0.0	1.0
All three	M ₄	75	30	20	3.0	0.0	3.0	2.0	0.0	0.0	1.0
All three	M ₅	100	40	30	4.0	1.0	5.0	4.0	0.0	1.0	1.0

^aM₁ = Av. of farmer's levels of application of the three inputs and their varieties by site. Other management packages, M₂ through M₅, include the levels of fertilizer, insect control, and weed control listed in this table for dry and wet seasons for Nueva Ecija and Camarines Sur provinces. Nitrogen levels on M₂ to M₅ in Laguna are 20, 40, 60, 80 kg N/ha for dry season, and 25, 50, 75, 100 kg N/ha for wet season. Phosphorus levels in both seasons are zero for M₂ and M₃, and 30 kg P₂O₅/ha for M₄ and M₅. No potassium was applied. ^bData show the av. no. of foliar (F) sprays or granular (G) applications. ^cData show the av. no. of rotary weeding (RW), handweeding (HW), and chemical weedicide (C) applications.

cultural practices not initially hypothesized as among the three or four most important.

Table 2 summarizes the average levels of inputs used by farmers (M₁) and the input levels tested in the management package experiments (M₂, M₃, M₄, and M₅). The high level of inputs evaluated in the yield-constraints experiments was for input level M₄ at some locations and for M₅ at others. However, since these experiments were conducted independently of the management-package experiments, the yields at the farmer's level and at the high level of

inputs were not identical to those obtained at the farmer's level and M₄ (or M₅) in the management-package experiments.

Laguna province, dry season (Statistics). Yields at the farmers' levels of inputs, ranked in ascending order in Table 3, ranged from 2.7 to 5.6 t/ha during the dry season, reflecting a considerable range among farmers in input use, management, and cultural practices. Increases in yields obtained by applying the high levels of fertilizer, insect control, and weed control, ranged from 1.8 to 3.6 t/ha with an average of

Table 3. Average contribution of insect control, fertilizer, and weed control to increased yields in experiments on nine farmers' fields. Laguna province, Philippines, 1975 dry season.

Farm no.	Farmer's cultivar	Irrigation method	Yield (t/ha)			Contribution (t/ha) of			
			Farmer's inputs	High inputs ^a	Difference	Insect control	Fertilizer	Weed control	Residual
1	C4-137	pump	2.7	5.2	2.5	0.7*	1.1**	0.4**	0.3
2	IR26	pump	3.2	5.9	2.7	1.1*	1.5**	0.1	0.0
3	C4-137	pump	3.3	6.2	2.9	1.2*	1.6**	0.2**	-0.1
4	IR1561	pump	3.8	6.2	2.4	1.0	1.3**	0.1	0.0
5	IR26	pump	3.9	7.5	3.6	1.3	1.9**	0.3*	0.1
6	IR1561	canal	4.9	7.1	2.2	0.9	1.0**	0.2*	0.1
7	IR26	pump	4.9	7.3	2.4	0.9*	1.2**	0.2	0.1
8	IR26	pump	5.6	8.6	3.0	1.1	1.6**	0.3*	0.0
9	IR26	canal	5.6	7.4	1.8	0.7*	0.9**	0.1*	0.1
Av.			4.2	6.8	2.6	1.0	1.3	0.2	0.1

^aM₅ level as shown in Table 2, except 120 instead of 80 kg N/ha.

Table 4. Yield of rice for five input management packages with other cultural practices at farmers' levels. Laguna province, 1975 dry and wet seasons.

Package level ^a	Yield ^b (t/ha)	
	Dry season	Wet season
M ₁ ^c	4.2	4.0
M ₂	3.5**	3.0**
M ₃	4.1	2.7**
M ₄	5.5**	4.1
M ₅	5.7**	5.3**

^aManagement packages contain varying levels of fertilizer, insect control, and weed control as shown in Table 2. ^bAv. of nine sites for dry season and five for wet season. ^cFarmers' level.

2.6 t/ha for the nine farmers. Because the high-level inputs were uniform across farms, the considerable yield variation from farm to farm (from 5.2 to 8.6 t/ha) appears due to differences in soils, water management, other environmental factors, and to a certain extent, cultural practices.

On the average, fertilizer contributed half of the increase in yield, and insect control contributed 38 percent. The levels and patterns of increase were remarkably consistent across farms. Weed control contributed less than 10 percent of the increase, indicating that the cooperating farmers generally used adequate weed control. These farmers averaged almost one rotary weeding plus one hand weeding each. By contrast, their average levels of fertilizer application and insect control were considerably below the M₄ level, which apparently accounts for the contribution of those inputs.

Average dry-season yield using farmers' inputs, 4.2 t/ha, was approximately equal to the

yield of M₃, 4.1 t/ha (Table 4). Raising the level of inputs from M₃ to M₄ increased yields by 1.4 t/ha. The M₅ yields in the management-package experiments (Table 4) were well below the high-level yields in the factorial experiments shown in Table 3 (5.7 vs 6.8 t/ha), reflecting the difference in nitrogen level applied (80 kg N/ha at M₅ and 120 kg N/ha at high level).

A number of farmers were selected for supplemental studies of the impact of added phosphorus (Table 5). The treatments were zero P₂O₅ and 30 kg/ha P₂O₅ on plots with the farmers' levels and the high level of other inputs. The response was consistent from farm to farm, but rather slight, averaging 0.3 t/ha at the farmers' level of other inputs, and 0.4 t/ha at the high level.

Laguna province, wet season (Statistics). We expanded the number of farms on which the factorial experiments were conducted to 20 in the wet season (Table 6). The results were remarkably similar to those in the dry season; the major difference was that both the level of yields using farmer inputs and the gain in yield using high inputs were less than for the dry season. Yields at the farmers' level of inputs ranged from 1.2 t/ha to 5.8 t/ha. The high level of inputs increased yields by 1 t/ha or more on all but four farms, and by more than 2 t/ha on a third of the farms. The average increase was 1.7 t/ha.

Both the high level of fertilizer and the high level of insect control increased yields by 0.7 t/ha. As in the dry season, weed control contributed little, indicating that the Laguna farmers effectively control weeds.

Laguna farmers were using most inputs in the range of the M₃ to the M₄ level (Table 2) and obtained comparable yields (Table 4). The main difference between the input packages in the wet and dry seasons is in the quantity of nitrogen. The addition of 30 kg P₂O₅/ha resulted in essentially the same yield gain in the wet as in the dry season (Table 5).

Nueva Ecija province, dry season (Agronomy). During the dry season, experiments were conducted on three farms in Nueva Ecija province. Land preparation was evaluated in addition to the three inputs tested in Laguna. The three cooperating farmers applied levels of fertilizer

Table 5. Contribution of 30 kg/ha of applied phosphorus to yield measured experimentally at two levels of other inputs, Laguna province, 1974 wet season and 1975 dry season.

Level of other inputs	Yield ^a (t/ha)		
	With P ₂ O ₅	Without P ₂ O ₅	Difference
	<i>1974 wet season</i>		
Farmer's	4.8	4.5	0.3**
High	5.9	5.5	0.4**
	<i>1975 dry season^b</i>		
Farmer's	5.4	5.1	0.3**
High	6.8	6.3	0.5**

^aAv. of 10 sites in the wet and nine in the dry season. ^bHigh (M₅) and farmer's level of nitrogen, weed control, and insect control as shown in Table 2.

Table 6. Contribution of insect control, fertilizer, and weed control to increased yields in experiments on 20 farmers' fields. Laguna province, Philippines, 1975 wet season.

Farm no.	Farmer's cultivar	Irrigation method	Yield (t/ha)			Contribution (t/ha) of			
			Farmer's inputs	High inputs ^a	Difference	Insect control	Fertilizer	Weed control	Residual
1	IR28	pump	1.2	3.1	1.9	0.4	1.0	0.2	0.3
2	C22	pump	1.5	4.1	2.6	1.7	0.8	0.6	-0.5
3	C4-137	pump	2.4	5.8	3.4	0.8	2.0	0.4	0.2
4	IR1561	canal	3.1	4.1	1.0	0.2	0.5	0.3	0.0
5	IR28	pump	3.2	4.6	1.4	0.5	0.6	0.3	0.0
6	C4-137	pump	3.2	5.4	2.2	1.2	0.5	0.3	0.2
7	IR26	pump	3.3	4.2	0.9	0.3	0.4	0.1	0.1
8	IR26	canal	3.3	5.2	1.9	0.6	0.3	0.4	0.6
9	IR28	pump	3.3	6.2	2.9	1.1	1.4	0.3	0.1
10	IR26	canal	3.5	5.3	1.8	0.8	0.7	0.3	0.0
11	IR1514	pump	3.6	5.7	2.1	0.8	1.0	0.3	0.0
12	IR30	pump	3.6	4.2	0.6	0.7	-0.2	0.2	-0.1
13	IR1561	canal	3.8	6.0	2.2	0.5	1.1	0.6	0.0
14	IR26	pump	3.9	5.7	1.8	0.6	1.0	0.3	-0.1
15	C4-137	pump	4.2	4.7	0.5	0.2	0.3	0.1	-0.1
16	IR26	pump	4.4	7.2	2.8	0.8	1.4	0.4	0.2
17	IR1514	pump	4.7	5.9	1.2	0.6	0.3	0.3	0.0
18	IR26	pump	4.8	5.8	1.0	0.3	0.5	0.1	0.1
19	IR1561	pump	5.0	6.4	1.4	0.7	0.5	0.1	0.1
20	IR1514	pump	5.8	6.7	0.9	0.3	0.6	0.2	-0.2
Av.			3.6	5.3	1.7	0.7	0.7	0.3	0.0

^aM₄ level as shown in Table 2.

approximately equal to the M₄ level, but their insect- and weed-control inputs were at the M₂ level or lower (Table 2).

On two of the three farms during the dry season, the high-input level (in this case M₄) increased yields by more than 1 t/ha and on

those two farms weed control and insect control accounted for most of the yield gain (Table 7).

Yields rose steadily as the package of inputs was increased from M₂ to M₅ (Table 8). Yield at the farmers' level (M₁) was between that at M₃ and that at M₄ for two farms, but below

Table 7. Contribution of insect control, fertilizer, weed control, and land preparation to yields in experiments on 14 farmers' fields. Nueva Ecija province, Philippines, 1975 dry and wet seasons.

Farm no.	Farmer's cultivar	Irrigation method	Yield (t/ha)			Contribution (t/ha) of				
			Farmer's input	High inputs ^a	Difference	Insect control	Fertilizer	Weed control	Land preparation	Residual
<i>Dry season</i>										
1	IR1561	pump	3.0	4.1	1.1	0.5	0.3	0.9**	-0.6	0.0
2	IR26	pump	4.4	4.5	0.1	-0.2	0.2	0.0	0.5	-0.4
3	IR26	pump	5.4	6.9	1.5	0.4**	0.0	0.7**	0.2	0.2
Av.			4.3	5.2	0.9	0.2	0.2	0.5	0.0	0.0
<i>Wet season</i>										
1	C4-137	canal	1.8	4.6	2.8	1.0*	1.2**	0.5	—	0.1
2	IR1529	canal	2.2	3.3	1.1	0.3	1.0**	0.1	—	-0.3
3	IR26	rainfed	2.3	3.5	1.2	0.4*	0.7**	0.2	—	-0.1
4	IR20	rainfed	2.8	3.2	0.4	0.0	0.3	0.3	—	-0.2
5	IR26	rainfed	3.1	4.5	1.4	0.3	0.5**	0.3	—	0.3
6	IR30	pump	3.1	3.8	0.7	0.2	-0.3	0.8**	—	0.0
7	IR1529	rainfed	3.1	3.9	0.8	0.4	0.0	0.4	—	0.0
8	IR26	pump	3.4	3.7	0.3	0.1	0.3*	-0.3	—	0.2
9	IR1561	rainfed	4.2	4.0	-0.2	0.0	-0.2	0.4**	—	-0.4
10	IR26	pump	4.4	4.6	0.2	0.8*	0.0	-0.6*	—	0.0
11	IR26	canal	5.1	3.4	-1.7	-1.4	0.0	-0.7*	—	0.4
Av.			3.2	3.9	0.7	0.2	0.3	0.1	—	0.1

^aThe high level of inputs equalled M₄ (see Table 2) during the dry and wet seasons.

Table 8. Yield of rice for five packages of input management with cultural practices at farmers' level and at high level. Three farms, dry season and 11 farms, wet season. Nueva Ecija province, 1975.

Farm no.	Level of cultural practices	Yield ^a (t/ha)					
		M ₁ ^b	M ₂	M ₃	M ₄	M ₅	Av.
<i>Dry season</i>							
1	Farmer's	3.5	3.1	4.7**	5.4**	6.3**	4.6
	High ^c	3.8	4.3*	5.4**	6.3**	7.3**	5.4
2	Farmer's	4.4	3.6	3.5	4.9	5.6	4.4
	High ^c	4.3	3.0	3.3	6.1	7.5**	4.8
3	Farmer's	5.7	4.1	4.4	6.2	8.1*	5.7
	High ^c	5.2	4.2	3.4*	4.1	6.1	4.6
Av.	Farmer's	4.5	3.6	4.2	5.5	6.7	4.9
	High ^c	4.4	3.8	4.0	5.6	7.0	4.9
<i>Wet season^d</i>							
Av.	Farmer's	3.2	3.4	3.7**	3.8**	4.4**	3.7
	High ^c	— ^e	3.1	3.2	3.3	4.3	3.4

^aManagement packages contain varying levels of fertilizer, insect control, weed control, and land preparation as shown in Table 2 for respective seasons. ^bFarmer's level. ^cHigh cultural practices include IRRI seed, 20- × 20-cm spacing, and seedlings of about 21 days of age at transplanting. ^dAv. of 11 sites in wet season. ^eThere was no M₁ for high cultural practices.

that at M₃ for the third. Yield gains from M₃ to M₄ and M₄ to M₅ were substantial, ranging from 0.7 t/ha to 2.8 t/ha.

We hypothesized that yields may be held down by factors not controlled in the management packages, such as source of seed, age of seedling, and spacing. Management package experiments were run first with farmers' cultural practices, and then using IRRI seeds and planting seedlings that were approximately 21 days old at a spacing of 20 × 20 cm. The grain yields for the packages of high cultural practices were higher at M₄ and M₅ on two of the three

farms in the dry season (Table 8). In farm 3, the yields using the farmer's cultural practices were higher because the plots with high cultural practices were harvested late, after the irrigation was cut off.

We further hypothesized that farmers might not be using the varieties with the highest yield potential. To investigate this possibility, we conducted a series of management package experiments in farmers' fields comparing a second variety with the one grown by farmers. On two out of three farms, the farmer's variety was IR26; on the third, it was the line IR1561.

Table 9. Yield (t/ha) of farmers' (F) varieties and test (T) varieties compared at five input management packages and grown under high levels of cultural practices. Nueva Ecija province, Philippines, 1975 dry and wet seasons.

Farm no. ^a	Variety	Yield ^b (t/ha)					
		M ₁ ^c	M ₂	M ₃	M ₄	M ₅	Av. ^d
<i>Dry season</i>							
1	IR1561 (F)	4.6	3.8	5.4	6.3**	7.1**	5.4
	IR26 (T)	5.2	4.5	5.2	6.0	7.8**	5.7
2	IR26 (F)	4.2	2.5**	2.2**	4.3	7.2**	4.1
	IR30 (T)	3.2	2.2*	1.2**	3.7	5.8**	3.2
3	IR26 (F)	4.8	3.6**	4.1	5.8**	7.4**	5.1
	IR30 (T)	4.2	2.6**	3.7	4.4	6.8**	4.3
<i>Wet season</i>							
4	IR20 (F)	2.2	3.2**	2.8*	3.1**	3.6**	3.0
	IR30 (T)	1.6	2.4*	1.7	1.9	2.2*	2.0
9	IR1561 (F)	3.1	2.7	3.9**	4.2**	4.7**	3.7
	IR30 (T)	2.6	3.0	3.6**	4.3**	4.8**	3.7
10	IR26 (F)	3.7	3.4	4.4*	4.5*	4.8**	4.2
	IR30 (T)	3.0	3.5	3.5	3.8*	3.7*	3.5
11	IR26 (F)	4.9	3.7**	4.4	3.8**	4.8	4.3
	IR30 (T)	3.8	3.7	3.8	3.2	4.4	3.8

^aFarm numbers correspond to those in Table 7. ^bManagement packages contain varying levels of fertilizer, insect control, weed control, and land preparation as shown in Table 2 for respective seasons. ^cFarmers' level. ^dMeans in italics are significantly different from the corresponding mean of the farmer's variety.

Table 10. Contributions of insect control, fertilizer, weed control, and land preparation to increased yields in experiments on nine farmers' fields. Camarines Sur province, Philippines, 1975 dry and wet seasons.

Farm no.	Farmer's cultivar	Irrigation method	Yield (t/ha)			Contribution (t/ha) of				
			Farmer's inputs	High inputs ^a	Difference	Insect control	Fertilizer	Weed control	Land preparation	Residual
<i>Dry season</i>										
1	IR1561	canal	2.1	4.8	2.7	0.8	1.0*	0.2	0.2	0.5
2	IR26	canal	4.4	5.1	0.7	0.4	1.2*	-0.4	0.0	-0.5
3	IR747	canal	5.1	7.1	2.0	0.0	1.4**	0.2	0.3	0.1
Av.			3.9	5.6	1.7	0.4	1.1	0.1	0.1	0.0
<i>Wet season</i>										
1	IR26	canal	2.6	3.9	1.3	0.1	0.1	0.5	—	0.6
2	IR747	canal	2.7	4.6	1.9	0.9	0.2	0.5	—	0.3
3	IR1561	rainfed	3.5	5.0	1.5	1.2*	0.6*	-0.1	—	-0.2
4	BPI 76	canal	4.0	4.8	0.8	0.9	-0.1	0.1	—	-0.1
5	IR28	canal	4.2	4.5	0.3	-0.6	1.4**	-0.1	—	-0.4
6	IR1561	rainfed	4.4	5.0	0.6	0.9*	0.1	-0.1	—	-0.3
Av.			3.6	4.6	1.1	0.6	0.4	0.1	—	-0.1

^aM₄ level as shown in Table 2.

At varying levels of inputs, IR26 gave consistently higher yields than the early-maturing IR30, the difference averaging 0.8 t/ha (Table 9). However, the yields of IR26 and IR1561 on farm 1 were approximately the same.

Nueva Ecija province, wet season (Agronomy). During the wet season, experiments were conducted on 11 farms with different degrees of water control. Farmers applied substantially less fertilizer than during the dry season, but used about the same levels of insect and weed control (Table 2).

Yields at the farmers' levels of inputs ranged from 1.8 to 5.1 t/ha (Table 7). Significantly, the farmers with the two lowest yields (1.8 and 2.2 t/ha) applied no fertilizer, or insect- or weed-control inputs. Application of the high level of inputs (M₄) increased yields by an average of 0.7 t/ha, although the effect varied considerably from farm to farm. On four farms, the gain exceeded 1 t/ha, but on two other farms, the yield at farmers' level of inputs exceeded the yield at high level. Rainfall conditions were favorable, and there appeared to be no distinguishable difference in response between rainfed and irrigated farms.

Factors accounting for the yield differences also varied from farm to farm. For the first three farms with the lowest yield with farmers' inputs, however, the yield gap was relatively large and all three inputs contributed to the gain in yield. Fertilizer was the most important element. On those farms where yields with farmers' inputs

were already high (between 4 and 5 t/ha), we were unable to further raise yields.

The average farm yield, 3.2 t/ha, was approximately equivalent to that at the M₂ level (Table 8). At the M₅ level, the average yield from 11 sites was 4.4 t/ha. There was little difference between yields at farm levels and at high levels of cultural practices in all sites. Hence, only the average data for 11 sites are shown.

On four farms, yields of the farmers' varieties were compared with those of a test variety. Two farmers were growing IR26, one was growing IR20, and another the line IR1561. The test variety was IR30 in all cases. As in the dry season, IR26 performed better than IR30 throughout the range of management packages except at the M₂ level. IR20 also outperformed IR30 on farm 4, but IR1561 yielded about the same as IR30 on farm 9.

Camarines Sur province, dry season (Agronomy). In Camarines Sur, the level of nitrogen used by farms 2 and 3 in the dry season was below the M₂ level (i.e., less than 40 kg N/ha). Two of the three farms showed a very large gain in yield of 2.0 and 2.7 t/ha at the high-input level (Table 10). Fertilizer contributed a yield gain of 1 t/ha or more in all three cases. But with only one exception for insecticide, the other three inputs contributed less than 0.5 t/ha on all three farms.

The yield of rice using the farmers' level of inputs was 4 t/ha or between the yields at the M₂ and M₃ levels (Table 11). Yields were

Table 11. Yield of rice for five input management packages^a with cultural practices at farmers' level and at optimal level. Camarines Sur province, 1975 dry and wet seasons.

Level of cultural practices	Yield ^b (t/ha)					
	M ₁ ^c	M ₂	M ₃	M ₄	M ₅	Av.
	<i>Dry season</i>					
Farmers'	4.0	3.5	4.8	5.5	6.0	4.8
High ^d	4.1	3.6	5.4	5.2	6.2	4.9
	<i>Wet season</i>					
Farmers'	3.6	3.9	4.7	4.3	4.1	4.1
High ^d	^e	3.5	4.5	4.5	5.1	4.2

^aManagement practices include varying levels of fertilizer, insect control, weed control, and land preparation. Av. of three sites in dry season and six in the wet season. ^bLSD (5%): 0.7 t/ha for dry season and 0.6 t/ha for wet season. ^cFarmers' level. ^dHigh cultural practices include IRRI seed, 20- x 20-cm spacing, and seedlings of about 21 days age at transplanting. ^eThere was no M₁ for high cultural practices in the wet season.

increased by the management packages from a low of 3.5 t/ha at M₂ to a high of 6.0 t/ha at M₅. On two of the three farms, the M₅ yield was 6.7 and 6.8 t/ha, but for the third, it was only 4.5 t/ha. Applying high-level cultural practices instead of those used by the farmer did not significantly increase yields.

IR26 and IR30 were grown as alternate varieties under high cultural practices at three sites in the dry season to determine if either would perform better than the varieties that farmers were using (Table 12). One farmer was growing the line IR1561, another the line IR747, and the third the variety IR26. IR26 was planted as the alternate variety on farms 1 and 3, and IR30 on farm 2. IR26 performed somewhat

better than the early-maturing selections IR1561, IR747, and IR30. The yield advantage of IR26 was highest at high levels of inputs, yielding more than 1 t/ha above IR747 and IR30 at M₅.

Camarines Sur province, wet season (*Agronomy*). Wet-season experiments were conducted at six sites. Again, the farmers' fertilizer levels were considerably lower than in the two other regions. But insect control and chemical weed control were slightly more intensive than in the other areas (Table 2). The two farmers with rainfed fields used lower levels of fertilizer and insect control than those used on the irrigated fields.

Yields at farmers' levels of inputs ranged from 2.6 t/ha to 4.4 t/ha, averaging 3.6 t/ha (Table 10). High levels of inputs increased yields by more than 1 t/ha for the three farms with the lowest yields. On two of the three farms, insect control was the most important element contributing to the yield increase. Insect control contributed almost a 1-t/ha increase in yield on four of the six farms. Several fields were attacked by case worms, brown planthoppers, rice hispa, and rice bugs.

For management-package experiments, yields rose from 3.5 t/ha at M₁ to 4.7 t/ha at M₃, but seemed to taper off from M₃ to M₅. Except at the M₅ level, the packages using high-level cultural practices gave no higher yields.

Varietal performance was tested on an irrigated and a rainfed farm. IR26 and IR1561

Table 12. Yield (t/ha) of farmers' (F) and test (T) varieties compared at five input management packages and grown under high levels of cultural practices. Camarines Sur province, 1975 dry and wet seasons.

Farm no. ^a	Variety	Yield ^b (t/ha)					
		M ₁ ^c	M ₂	M ₃	M ₄	M ₅	Av. ^d
		<i>Dry season</i>					
1	IR1561 (F)	3.1	3.3	4.1**	4.6**	4.8**	4.0
	IR26 (T)	3.3	3.5	5.0**	4.8**	5.1**	4.3
2	IR26 (F)	5.2	4.2	4.6	5.2	7.7**	5.4
	IR30 (T)	4.5	3.8	4.0	4.9	6.6**	4.8
3	IR747 (F)	5.4	5.0	5.9	6.6*	7.4**	6.1
	IR26 (T)	5.6	5.2	7.2**	7.5**	8.7**	6.8
		<i>Wet season</i>					
1	IR26 (F)	3.5	4.2	4.2	4.4	5.1**	4.3
	IR30 (T)	3.9	3.9	4.6	5.1*	5.5**	4.6
3	IR1561 (F)	3.8	4.1	4.6**	4.6**	5.0**	4.4
	IR30 (T)	3.9	3.9	4.4**	4.5*	4.8**	4.3

^aFarm numbers correspond to those in Table 10. ^bManagement packages contain varying levels of fertilizer, insect control, weed control, and land preparation as shown in Table 2 for respective seasons. ^cFarmers' level. ^dMeans in italics are significantly different from the corresponding mean of the farmer's variety.

Table 13. Yields of farmers' (F) and test (T) varieties compared at five input management packages and grown under high levels of cultural practices. Iloilo province, 1975 dry and wet seasons.

Farm no.	Variety	Yield ^a (t/ha)					Av. ^c
		M ₁ ^b	M ₂	M ₃	M ₄	M ₅	
1	IR26 (F)	5.5	<i>3.5**</i>	5.1	6.0	6.1*	5.2
	IR30 (T)	6.1	4.8**	5.9	6.7*	6.8*	6.1
2	IR26 (F)	3.5	3.3	3.7	4.1	4.1	3.7
	IR30 (T)	5.9	5.4	5.6	6.8*	6.4	6.0
<i>Wet season</i>							
1	IR30 (F)	4.4	<i>3.2**</i>	4.2	5.2*	5.6**	4.5
	IR26 (T)	5.0	3.3**	4.7	5.6*	6.3**	5.0
2	IR26 (F)	4.4	2.7**	3.6**	4.6	5.5**	4.2
	IR30 (T)	4.8	3.1**	3.9**	4.3	5.7**	4.4
3	IR26 (F)	3.8	3.3	3.7	4.5*	5.0**	4.1
	IR30 (T)	3.6	2.7**	3.6	4.1	5.1**	3.8

^aManagement packages contain varying levels of fertilizer, insect control, weed control, and land preparation as shown in Table 2 for respective seasons. ^bFarmers' level. ^cMeans in italics are significantly different from the corresponding mean of the farmer's variety.

were grown in the 1975 wet season on these farms, with IR30 as the test variety (Table 12). The early-maturing variety IR30 seemed to have the same yield potential as the two other varieties in the wet season. Yields rose from less than 4 t/ha at M₂ to a high of 5 t/ha at M₅.

Iloilo province, dry season (Agronomy). At Ajuy, Iloilo, two farmers were selected for comparison of the effect on yields of different management packages using the farmers' variety, IR26, and our test variety, IR30 (Table 13).

Examining first the effect of the management packages, we observed that yields at the farmers' level of inputs were close to those of the M₃ level. On farm 1, yields at M₅ were 2 t/ha higher than those at M₂; on farm 2, they were about 1 t/ha higher.

IR30, the test variety, consistently yielded higher than IR26, at all management-package levels, yielding about 6 t/ha at the farmers' level of inputs. After IR30 was harvested, IR26 remained as the only crop in the field; rats seriously damaged it on farm 2.

Iloilo province, wet season (Agronomy). Three farms were selected for the wet-season experiments, and the effect of different management packages on yield was examined using the farmers' varieties, and our test variety (Table 13). At the farmers' input levels, yields ranged from 3.6 to 5 t/ha, close to the M₃ level. Yields rose from about 3 t/ha at M₂ to 5.5 t/ha at M₅.

The farmers' varieties were IR30 on farm 1 and IR26 on farms 2 and 3. On farm 1, IR26 consistently outyielded IR30 at all management

levels. On farm 2, however, the yields of IR26 were lower than those of IR30. IR26 was attacked by the rice bug when it was the only crop remaining in the field. On farm 3, the rice bug also damaged the IR26 crop, although yields exceeded those of IR30 at four out of five management-package levels.

ECONOMIC CONSTRAINTS

Agricultural Economics Department

The second broad objective of our research on yield constraints is to understand why farmers use modern rice technology as they do. In other words: why do they use only certain components of the new technology; why do they use their current levels of inputs; and why do they apply the inputs in the current manner? We believe that these issues can be fully understood only by knowing how modern technology performs under farmers' conditions and by analyzing the economic, social, and institutional forces that affect the farmers' use of new technology. The experimental work in farmers' fields provides an estimate of the performance of modern technology under farmers' conditions. A larger sample of farmers in the same areas was surveyed to determine the economic conditions under which farmers operate in the study areas and the representativeness of the farms with experiments.

Representativeness of experimental sites. The fields in which the biological constraints were measured provide insights into the factors con-

Table 14. Comparison of characteristics of farms where constraints experiments were conducted and a random sample of farms in the same villages. Philippines, 1975 dry and wet seasons.

Season	Farm	Farm (no.)	Farm size (ha)	Tenure (no.)		Irrigation status (no.)	
				Share tenants	Owners or renters	Irrigated	Rainfed
<i>Laguna province</i>							
Wet	Experiment	20	1.7	8	12	20	0
	No experiment	30	2.1	10	20	30	0
<i>Nueva Ecija province</i>							
Dry	Experiment	3	1.5	0	3	3	0
	No experiment	43	1.5	1	42	43	0
Wet	Experiment	11	2.4	0	11	6	5
	No experiment	60	2.1	2	58	47	13
<i>Camarines Sur province</i>							
Dry	Experiment	3	n.a. ^a	n.a. ^a	n.a. ^a	3	0
	No experiment	15	1.8	6	9	15	0
Wet	Experiment	6	1.6	2	4	4	2
	No experiment	39	1.4	11	28	29	10

^aData not available.

straining rice yields only to the extent that they are representative of conditions on a wider spectrum of farmers' fields. To determine the similarity of these fields to other farms, we interviewed a random sample of farmers from the same villages in which the experiments were conducted. The size, tenure, and irrigation situations of the farms with experiments were quite similar to those of the random sample of farms (Table 14).

We collected data on input use and yields for both sets of farms through interviews. In addition, we kept a careful record of input use on a "comparable paddy" that was managed completely by the farmer on each experimental farm throughout the season. Crop-cut yield estimates were obtained from these comparable paddies at the end of the season (Table 15). Crop-cut yields on the comparable paddies were consistently higher than yields reported by farmers

Table 15. Comparison of yields and inputs on farms with constraints experiments and a random sample of farms in the same villages. Philippines, 1975 dry and wet seasons.

Type of farm	Farm (no.)	Yield ^a (t/ha)	Fertilizer applied (kg/ha)		Weed control (\$/ha)	Insect control (\$/ha)
			N	P ₂ O ₅		
<i>Laguna province, wet season</i>						
Comparable paddy	10 ^b	3.6	79	5	18	17
Experiments	10	2.5	62	2	14	11
No experiment	30	2.5	42	3	7	10
<i>Nueva Ecija province, dry season</i>						
Comparable paddy	3	4.3	118	52	10	18
Experiments	3	4.8	147	80	13	28
No experiment	43	3.0	74	39	6	20
<i>Nueva Ecija province, wet season</i>						
Comparable paddy	11	3.2	79	22	5	14
Experiments	11	2.4	48	19	2	9
No experiment	60	2.1	34	17	3	9
<i>Camarines Sur province, dry season</i>						
Comparable paddy	3	3.9	36	16	6	26
Experiments	3	n.a. ^c	n.a. ^c	n.a. ^c	n.a. ^c	n.a. ^c
No experiment	15	2.1	25	13	2	8
<i>Camarines Sur province, wet season</i>						
Comparable paddy	6	3.6	28	15	7	11
Experiments	6	2.7	30	15	9	13
No experiment	35	2.1	19	8	6	7

^aYields from the comparable paddies were estimated by crop cutting; other yields, by farm interviews. ^bExperiments were conducted on 20 farms, but interviews were conducted on only 10 of these farms. ^cNot available.

Table 16. Economic comparison of four levels of input management packages with farmers' cultural practices in experiments on farmers' fields. Philippines, 1975 dry season.

Input package level	Av. increase over farmers' level ^a				Sites (no.) with net return	
	Gross return (\$/ha)	Cost (\$/ha)	Net return (\$/ha)	\$ return/\$ invested	Lower than farmers' practices	Higher than farmers' practices
	<i>Laguna province</i>					
M ₂	-100	-1	-95	+ ^b	8	1
M ₃	-14	85	-99	+	9	0
M ₄	186	198	-12	0.9	5	4
M ₅	214	328	-114	0.7	9	0
	<i>Nueva Ecija province</i>					
M ₂	-128	-63	-65	+	3	0
M ₃	-43	26	-69	+	2	1
M ₄	143	102	41	1.4	1	2
M ₅	300	250	50	1.2	1	2
	<i>Camarines Sur province</i>					
M ₂	-72	4	-76	+	2	1
M ₃	114	93	21	1.2	1	2
M ₄	214	173	41	1.2	0	3
M ₅	285	310	-24	0.9	1	2

^aAv. of nine sites in Laguna, three in Nueva Ecija, and three in Camarines Sur. ^bReturn per dollar invested above the farmers' investment is not a meaningful concept when gross return from the package is less than the farmers' investment.

without experiments. This appears to be due to the method of obtaining yields (crop cut vs. interview) and, in Nueva Ecija and Camarines Sur in the dry season, to the higher levels of inputs on the farms with experiments. In the latter case, the results may underestimate the gap between potential and actual yields because the gap increases on farms where inputs and yields are rather low (Tables 7 and 10). The yield data reported emphasize the importance not only of selecting representative farms, but also of using the same procedure for yield measurement in identifying the size of the yield gap.

Economic evaluation of experiments in farmers' fields. We used the prices of inputs prevailing in the study areas to analyze the costs and returns of the different levels of inputs tested in the input-management packages. In the analysis, we measured economic incentives using net return above input cost, which we calculated as the value of output minus the cost of the inputs studied in the experiments (fertilizer, weed control, insect control, and, where appropriate, land preparation).

We found substantial variation in the average levels of inputs used by cooperating farmers in the three regions (Table 2). This variation is reflected in the input costs and the additional costs of the tested input packages. Farmers in

Laguna and Camarines Sur spent an amount roughly equal to the cost of M₂ on the tested inputs in the dry season, while cooperating farmers in Nueva Ecija spent almost the cost of M₃ (Table 16). During the wet season, the larger group of Nueva Ecija and Camarines Sur farmers spent an amount about equal to M₂ (Table 17). Laguna farmers spent slightly more. In almost all cases, however, farmers spent less than a third the cost of M₄ and less than a fourth that of M₅.

In Laguna during the dry season, the cost of the higher levels of inputs, M₂ through M₅, exceeded the value of increased output on most farms (Table 16), even though M₄ and M₅ gave higher yields. Surprisingly, even though M₃ cost more than the farmers' treatments, it yielded less and so was less economical. The M₄ level was economical on almost half of the farms.

In Nueva Ecija, M₄ and M₅ gave higher net returns than the farmers' practices on two of three farms. The same was true for M₃ and M₅ in Camarines Sur. On the average, the high-input packages gave a low rate of return for the expenditures despite the attractive yields.

Wet-season results were similar to dry-season results (Table 17). In Laguna, no package gave higher net returns than the farmers' practices—not an unexpected result because the yields of M₂ and M₃ were lower than those of M₁, and

Table 17. Economic comparison of four levels of input management packages with farmers' cultural practices in experiments on farmers' fields. Philippines, 1975 wet season.

Input package level	Av. increase over farmers' level ^a				Site (no.) with net return	
	Gross return (\$/ha)	Cost (\$/ha)	Net return (\$/ha)	\$ return/\$ invested ^b	Lower than farmers' practices	Higher than farmers' practices
<i>Laguna province</i>						
M ₂	-143	-24	-119	+ ^b	5	0
M ₃	-185	72	-258	+	5	0
M ₄	14	196	-182	0.1	5	0
M ₅	186	342	-156	0.5	5	0
<i>Nueva Ecija province</i>						
M ₂	28	1	27	28.0	4	7
M ₃	71	44	27	1.6	4	7
M ₄	86	111	-25	0.8	6	5
M ₅	171	198	-27	0.9	8	3
<i>Camarines Sur province</i>						
M ₂	57	1	56	57.0	1	5
M ₃	171	68	103	2.5	0	6
M ₄	114	122	-8	0.9	2	4
M ₅	86	193	-107	0.4	6	0

^aAv. of five sites in Laguna, 11 in Nueva Ecija, and six in Camarines Sur. ^bReturn per dollar invested above the farmers' investment is not a meaningful concept when gross return from the package is less than the farmers' investment.

the yield of M₄ was only slightly higher. On some farms in Nueva Ecija, the high packages gave somewhat higher net returns than M₁, but the average difference was small for M₂ and M₃, and was negative for M₄ and M₅. The pattern was the same in Camarines Sur.

Table 18 breaks down the costs and returns of the three inputs used in the experiments, and may indicate why the high packages were not profitable. In all three regions, and at nearly all sites, the increased cost of the high level of insect control far exceeded the increased value of output from that input. But the high level of fertilizer nearly always increased the value of output by more than it increased the costs. The same was true for the high level of weed control,

although the absolute increase in net income from fertilizer averaged nearly six times as much as from weed control. The pattern held during both seasons.

Of course, no one expected the high level of inputs to maximize profit, or even necessarily to be profitable; the high level of each input was chosen solely to maximize yield. However, the difference between increased cost and return from fertilizer and from insect control is so dramatic and overriding in its implications that it is probably important for understanding why farmers use inputs as they do.

Understanding farmers' use of inputs. Table 18 suggests that the farmers with experiments could have profitably used more fertilizer, and that

Table 18. Farmers' costs, increased cost, and increased value of output from high levels of three inputs compared with average farmers' levels in experiments on farmers' fields. Philippines, 1975 dry and wet seasons.

Province	Site (no.)	Cost or value (\$/ha)								
		Farmers' fertilizer	Increase from high fertilizer		Farmers' insect control	Increase from high insect control		Farmers' weed control	Increase from high weed control	
			Cost	Value		Cost	Value		Cost	Value
<i>Dry season</i>										
Laguna	9	35	21	189	3	294	138	15	13	32
Nueva Ecija	3	88	-4	24	18	97	55	10	6	74
Camarines Sur	3	35	61	170	26	90	56	15	1	0
<i>Wet season</i>										
Laguna	5	44	30	104	23	190	93	21	15	40
Nueva Ecija	11	41	24	46	14	76	29	4	11	18
Camarines Sur	6	29	38	60	11	80	75	13	4	27

Table 19. Reasons given by 150 farmers for not using higher rates of fertilizer. Philippines, 1975 wet season.

Province	Farmers interviewed (no.)	Farmer responses (no.)						
		Lack of money	Inadequate supply	Applying enough	Applying recommended amount	Landlord decides	Excess or deficit of water	Others/no response
Laguna	40	5	0	15	3	3	4	10
Nueva Ecija	70	45	4	14	3	0	0	4
Camarines Sur	40	24	1	1	3	0	5	6

Table 20. Insect problems and control reported by 150 farmers. Philippines, 1975 wet season.

Province	Farmers interviewed (no.)	Farmers (no.) reporting			Insecticide investment (\$/ha)	
		Significant insect attack	Attempted control	Successful control	Farmers with insect attack	Farmers without insect attack
Laguna	40	33	30	11	10	9
Nueva Ecija	70	56	47	31	9	7
Camarines Sur	40	35	33	24	8	8

Table 21. Weed problems and their control, as reported by 150 farmers. Philippines, 1975 wet season.

Province	Farmers interviewed	Farmers (no.)				Weed control investment (\$/ha)	
		Citing weeds as a problem	Citing weeds and		Farmers reporting weed problems	Farmers reporting no weed problems	
			Using hand weeding	Using herbicide			
Laguna	40	15	15	6	10	9	
Nueva Ecija	70	51	38	17	4	1	
Camarines Sur	40	22	21	17	9	5	

the average farmers in the areas were using even less than those with experiments. Farmers were asked why they did not use more fertilizer during the 1975 wet season. Most of the Laguna farmers and a substantial number of Nueva Ecija farmers believed that they were already applying enough fertilizer (Table 19). A substantial proportion of farmers in Camarines Sur and in Nueva Ecija indicated a lack of capital to purchase more fertilizer. Further, these farmers did not appear convinced of the benefit of higher rates of fertilizer than they currently use.

Farmers were also questioned about their insect- and weed-control problems. More than three-fourths reported a significant level of insect attack, and most reported that they had attempted to control the insects (Table 20). Most Laguna farmers believed they were not successful in controlling the insects, while two-thirds of the others reported success. Perhaps most revealing is the observation that those who

reported attacks and attempted control spent no more on insect control than those who reported no significant insect attack.

Weeds were cited as a problem most frequently in Nueva Ecija, and least frequently in Laguna (Table 21). Nearly all farmers who had weed problems used some control measure; hand weeding was almost twice as popular as herbicides. In Laguna, laborers carry out the weeding and sometimes other operations without cost in exchange for the privilege of harvesting the crop for the standard share, one-sixth. This seems to encourage thorough weeding and probably discourages farmers from using chemical weed-control measures.

IMPLICATIONS

Agricultural Economics, Agronomy, and Statistics Departments

This section summarizes findings at the three

locations in Laguna, Nueva Ecija, and Camarines Sur provinces. Conclusions are based not only on 1975 data, but also on 1974 wet-season data (1974 Annual Report).

Laguna province. Results are consistent from experiments from two wet seasons and one dry season in Laguna. The yield gap between the farmers' level and high level of inputs was 2.0 t/ha in the 1974 wet season; 1.7 t/ha in the 1975 wet season; and 2.6 t/ha in the 1975 dry season. Fertilizer accounted for about 50 percent of the yield gap; insect control, for about 33 percent; and weed control, for less than 20 percent.

Economic analysis of the management-package experiments shows that none of the four packages give higher returns than those that farmers now obtain. A breakdown of the costs by input explains this. The profit for additional fertilizer is very high. But the cost of insecticides generally exceeds their benefits at the high level of inputs. Although insects are recognized as a problem in Laguna, farmers attempt control with rather low expenditures and little success. It is not clear if some level of insect control, higher than farmers' current practices but lower than the extremely high levels tested, would raise yields and profits. More research is needed on this question.

The yield gains due to high weed control are modest, but the added cost above what farmers currently pay is negligible. But herbicides probably would not be accepted because of the widespread practice of contracting the weeding with the harvest. Because this practice probably provides employment during a slack period, and the level of weeding seems adequate, it would be inappropriate to encourage its replacement by herbicide use.

We conclude that additional fertilizer can be applied at substantial profit in Laguna, particularly in the dry season, despite the farmers' contention that they now use adequate amounts. Perhaps more education and demonstration to farmers of the economic value of fertilizer are appropriate in Laguna.

Nueva Ecija province. Results were contrasting from 2 years of wet-season experiments. During the 1974 wet season, typhoon damage was heavy and high inputs increased yields by

0.7 t/ha above the farmers' yields of 1.7 t/ha. In the 1975 wet season, weather was favorable and farmers' yields were generally higher (3.2 t/ha), but the yield gap was still only 0.7 t/ha. Yield gains were variable not only from season to season, but also from farm to farm. Only on farms with yields of less than 3 t/ha did the use of high inputs increase yields by more than 1 t/ha. Added fertilizer and weed control should be profitable on these farms. "Lack of money" is the major reason farmers gave for not using more fertilizer. Although this statement is difficult to interpret, it seems to reflect credit problems as well as a feeling that fertilizer is too expensive.

During the dry season, the three farms chosen for experiments seem to have used a level of nitrogen fertilizer well above that of their neighbors (118 vs. 74 kg N/ha). To determine if a higher level of fertilizer would be widely profitable, the experiments should be run on a larger number of farms.

A comparison of the performance of farmers' and test varieties over the past three seasons, including the 1974 wet season (1974 Annual Report), shows that the test variety was superior in four of the 10 experiments conducted. IR26 was included as either a farmer's or a test variety in eight out of 10 cases, and in all eight cases outyielded the other variety.

Camarines Sur province. Results of experiments conducted in Camarines Sur indicate that the level of fertilizer could be profitably increased on cooperating farms in the dry season. As in Nueva Ecija, farmers again report lack of money as the main reason for not applying more fertilizer. As in the two other locations, yield level and yield increases were lower in the wet than in the dry season. Only farms with low yield (3.5 t/ha or less) showed a yield gain at high inputs of more than 1 t/ha. But on these farms, insect and weed control accounted for more of the yield difference than fertilizer.

Over the three seasons' experiments, the test variety consistently yielded higher than the farmers' varieties at three of the seven experimental sites. In two of the three cases where the farmers' varieties gave lower yields, the test variety was IR26.

Summary of implications. On many farms in

all three locations, a substantial increase in nitrogen input in the dry season can raise yields by about 1 t/ha. In the wet season, yields can probably be profitably increased on farms where yields are now less than 3 t/ha. Although maximum yields are from 4.5 to 5 t/ha in the wet season, yields of more than 3.5 t/ha do not appear profitable. This may be partly because of the high cost of insecticides. More cost-effective methods of insect control are needed. Weeds can be controlled at a relatively modest cost in areas where better weed control adds significantly to yields.

EVALUATION OF EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUES

Statistics Department

We have two objectives in our efforts to develop suitable experimental techniques to identify and quantify yield constraints in farmers' fields: 1) to keep the size of the experiment small; and 2) to simplify the technique for simulating farmers' practices in experimental plots.

Earlier, we reported difficulty in simulating farmers' practices of insect control (1973 Annual Report). In 1974 and 1975 trials, we compared the same insect control practices when applied by the researcher and by the farmer. Evaluation is based on the practicality of the field operation and on any effects on the estimates of the farmer's yield. We earlier found that if the farmer maintains all plots receiving his insect control practices in one portion of the field, he can treat these plots similarly to the rest of his field (1974 Annual Report). Hence the farmer, instead of the researcher, could administer the farmer's insect-control practices. But an experimental design, such as a split-plot design with insect control as the main plots, must be used.

In the 1974 wet season and in the 1975 dry and wet seasons, we followed this procedure in our Laguna trials and found it workable. Further, it not only simplifies the practical field operation of the experiment but also gives an experimentally derived farmer's yield (M_1) closer to what the farmer actually gets in his fields.

Another problem encountered earlier was the use of leveed (or banded) plots. Such plots are

desirable for maintaining the specified levels of inputs, especially fertilizers and granular herbicides, but the levees make it difficult for the researcher to accurately simulate some farmers' management practices, particularly land preparation and water management. An alternative to the use of leveed plots would be to use large plots to minimize any effect of chemical movement. We compared the conventional leveed system (plan A) with two alternate plans:

1) *Plan B*—Only plots receiving high fertilizer levels are leveed, and the farmer administers all farmers' practices (fig. 1).

2) *Plan C*—No plots are leveed. An area of about 300 sq m is used to represent the high fertilizer level. Part of the area (shown by x-x-x) receives a high level of insect control, and the

F_f - Fertilizer at farmers' land W_h - Weed control at high level
 F_h - Fertilizer at high level l_f - Insect control at farmers' land
 W_f - Weed control at farmers' land l_h - Insect control at high level

1. Two alternate plot layouts for studying yield constraints in farmers' fields. IIRRI, 1975.

Table 22. Comparison of alternate plans for conducting studies on yield constraints in farmers' fields. ^aLaguna province, Philippines, 1975 dry and wet seasons.

Plot plan ^b	Yield (t/ha)			Contribution (t/ha) from			
	Farmers' level	High level	Difference	Insect control	Fertilizer	Weed control	Residual
				<i>Dry season</i>			
A	4.2	6.8	2.6	1.0	1.3	0.2	0.1
B	4.1	6.5	2.5	1.0	1.1	0.3	0.1
				<i>Wet season</i>			
A	4.0	6.2	2.2	0.9	1.0	0.2	0.1
C	3.6	5.7	2.1	0.8	1.0	0.3	0.0

^aAv. of nine sites in the dry season and five in the wet season. ^bPlan A is the conventional leveed plots; see fig. 1 for plans B and C.

other receives the farmer's level. Plots that are 5 × 8 sq m in size are then superimposed on these subareas to receive high weed control practices. These plots are larger than the 3- × 6-sq m plots generally used for leveed plots in farmers' fields. In all cases, the harvest area per plot is about 10 sq m.

Results from the conventional experimental procedure, plan A, and the two alternatives were compared (Table 22). The estimates of yield gap were similar among the different plans. Estimates of relative contribution of individual inputs varied slightly among plans on several farms, but there was no consistent deviation. The absolute yields, both at farmers' and at high levels of inputs, were slightly lower in plans B and C than in plan A, perhaps because of the

lack of levees.

In the 1975 wet season, we tested six input combinations on five farms and obtained slightly higher yields in leveed than in nonleveed plots. Although the difference was significant in two out of five farms, it averaged less than 0.1 t/ha. In these experiments, however, we tried to keep all farmers' practices in the leveed plots as similar as possible to those of outside areas. Since such efforts could not be expected in wider practice, larger differences could be expected.

Considering the practicality of operation and the costs, nonleveed plots seem more desirable. Hence, plan C, being most practical and least costly, seems to be a strong candidate for future use in studying yield constraints in farmers' fields.

Consequences of new technology

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SUMMARY

During 1975, we initiated a program to assess the impact of new rice technology on income distribution.

First, we analyzed how technological changes in rice production have influenced market prices, and in turn, farmers' incomes, by applying a mathematical model to data collected on the Philippine rice economy. Our analysis showed that improvements in technology tended to equalize incomes among farmers in the Philippines.

Further, in two areas of the Philippines, we investigated changes in the distribution of farm earnings from rice production since the introduction of modern varieties. We found that the share of output that went to landlords, farm operators, hired workers, and other than the agricultural sector for purchased inputs did not change radically after the introduction of modern varieties. Further, we found no evidence of a decline in either absolute or relative earnings to labor. Instead, the percent of earnings going to landlords appears to have declined.

At the request of the Philippine government, we examined reasons behind the recent decline in fertilizer consumption and evaluated alternate pricing policies to encourage rice self-sufficiency. Subsequently, a more detailed analytical framework was developed to evaluate the benefits and costs of rice price support vs. fertilizer subsidy. We found the input subsidy to be more efficient in terms of social benefits and costs if subsidies were applied to inputs such as fertilizers that are used at suboptimal levels. We found that the heavy financial burden to the government of subsidizing fertilizer prices can be substantially reduced by raising the sugar export tax; the fertilizer subsidy program could thus be extended to the sugar sector without increasing cost to the government.

MARKET EFFECTS OF NEW RICE TECHNOLOGY ON INCOME DISTRIBUTION *Agricultural Economics Department*

Since the emergence of the new rice technology, its impact on income distribution has been of major public concern. The effect of changes in

market prices is an important consideration that has generally been neglected. Technological progress implies a larger output of given resources, which normally results in an increase in economic welfare through higher consumption at a lower cost. The distribution of gains in economic welfare from technological progress in the production of a staple food crop, such as rice, is critically different between commercialized agriculture in developed countries and partially monetized semi-subsistence agriculture in developing countries. We attempted to evaluate the distribution of welfare gains among different classes of consumers and producers in the semisubsistence Asian economy by applying a relatively simple mathematical model to Philippine data.

A model of income distribution. In commercialized agriculture in developed countries, farmers themselves consume only a minor fraction of output. Technical progress in the production of a staple food crop results in a corresponding shift in the supply curve. When confronted with a highly inelastic market demand schedule, output prices decline more than output increases, which decreases producers' incomes despite the reduction in per unit production costs. But consumers enjoy higher consumption at lower prices. Such technical progress in commodities with low elasticities of demand implies an income transfer from producers to consumers—the economic force behind income protection plans for farmers in the developed countries.

In subsistence agriculture where only a minor portion of output is sold, however, the reduction in market prices due to the rightward shift in the supply curve has relatively little influence on producers' incomes. As the ratio of sale to total output decreases, so does the likelihood that the reduction in cash revenue would exceed the reduction in production cost.

The diagram on the left of fig. 1 illustrates such a relationship, showing the demand and supply schedules of a subsistence crop in the market. The vertical line D_H represents the demand curve of producers for home consumption. Considering the nature of the subsistence crop as a commodity of basic need which must be satisfied first, it is assumed that

1. Impact of technological change in a subsistence crop. IRRI, 1975.

producers' households consume a given quantity of their produce irrespective of prices and sell the rest. D_M , D represents the market demand for the product—the horizontal difference between D_M , D and D_H , H measures the quantity purchased by nonfarmer households. The total demand for the crop is represented by D_H , D_M , D .

S_0 , O and S_1 , O are the supply schedules before and after a technical change. As the supply schedule shifts, the market equilibrium point correspondingly moves from A to B . Consumers enjoy the increased consumption (HQ_0 to HQ_1) at the reduced price (OP_0 to OP_1): consumers' surplus increases by area $ACGB$. On the other hand, producers' cash revenue changes from area $ACHQ_0$ to area $BGHQ_1$ while producers' home consumption stays the same, OH . The cost of production changes from area AOQ_0 to BOQ_1 .

Let us assume constant price elasticities of total demand and supply of rice, $-\eta$ and β , for the relevant ranges of analysis. A change in consumers' surplus corresponding to a k -percent shift in the supply schedule due to technical progress can be approximated by

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Area } ACGB &= \text{area } AP_0P_1B - \text{area } CP_0P_1G \\ &\cong p_0q_0 \frac{kr}{\beta + \eta} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where p_0 and q_0 represent the equilibrium price and quantity before the technological change; and r is the ratio of marketable surplus (total output minus home consumption) to total output. The above relation shows that consumers' gain from the technical progress is larger as r is larger or the production of the crop is more commercialized.

Correspondingly, the cash revenue of producers will change by

$$\text{area } BEQ_0Q_1 - \text{area } ACGE \quad (2)$$

$$= p_0q_0k \frac{(\eta - r)}{\beta + \eta}$$

and the cost of production by

$$\text{area } BOQ_1 - \text{area } AOQ_0 \quad (3)$$

$$\cong p_0q_0 \frac{k\beta(\eta - 1)}{(1 + \beta)(\beta + \eta)}$$

Consequently, with technological progress the cash income of producers will change by

$$\text{change in cash revenue} - \text{change in cost} \quad (4)$$

$$\cong p_0q_0k \frac{\eta - r + \beta(1 - r)}{(1 + \beta)(\beta + \eta)}$$

which indicates that producers' gains will be

larger if r is smaller (i.e. if the production of the crop is less commercialized).

Moving to the analysis of the impact of technical change on income distribution among producers, the diagram on the right of fig. 1 illustrates the changes in equilibrium points of individual farm producers corresponding to changes in market equilibrium points in the left diagram. $O'S_0^S$ and $O'S_0^L$ represent the supply curves of small and large farms, respectively, before the technological advance, which correspond to OS_0 in the left diagram. $O'S_1^S$ and $O'S_1^L$ represent the supply schedules of the small and large producers after the change in technology, which correspond to OS_1 . The quantity of home consumption is assumed to be the same for both small and large farmers.

Corresponding to the technological change and the change in market prices, the equilibrium of the small producers moves from A^S to B^S , with the corresponding changes in cash revenue by (*area* $B^SE^SQ_0^S Q_1^S$ - *area* $A^SC^GE^S$) and in cost by (*area* $B^SO^Q_1^S$ - *area* $A^SO^Q_0^S$). Likewise, the equilibrium of the big farmer moves from A^L to B^L , accompanied by the changes in cash revenue by (*area* $B^LE^LQ^L Q_0^L Q_1^L$ - *area* $A^LC^GE^L$) and in cost by (*area* $B^LO^Q_1^L$ - *area* $A^LO^Q_0^L$). The net effect on producers' income depends on the relative changes in revenue and cost, which, in turn, depend on the price elasticities of supply of individual producers relative to the aggregate demand elasticity.

The aggregate price elasticity of supply (β), which determines the market prices (in the left diagram), is the weighted average of the price elasticities of supply of individual producers:

$$\beta = \sum_i w_i \beta_i$$

where β_i is the price elasticity of supply of the i^{th} producer ($i = L$ for large producer and $i = S$ for small producer), and w_i is the share of the i^{th} producer in total output. Likewise, the rate of shift in the aggregate supply is an average of the rates of supply shift of individual producers,

$$k = \sum_i w_i k_i.$$

Approximation formulae for analyzing the impacts of k -percent shift in the aggregate supply function on the i^{th} producer are as follows:

$$(5) \text{ Change in cash revenue} \tag{5}$$

$$= p_o q_o (k_i - k \frac{\beta_i + r_i}{\beta + \eta});$$

$$(6) \text{ Change in production cost}$$

$$= p_o q_o \frac{\beta_i}{1 + \beta_i} (k_i - k \frac{1 + \beta_i}{\beta + \eta}); \text{ and} \tag{6}$$

$$(7) \text{ Change in income}$$

$$= p_o q_{oi} (k_i - \frac{k_i \beta_i}{1 + \beta_i} - \frac{k r_i}{\beta + \eta}) \tag{7}$$

where q_{oi} and r_i represent, respectively, the output and the marketable surplus ratio of the i^{th} producer before the shift in the supply function.

Equation (7) shows that as the value of r decreases the increase in income is larger (or the decline is smaller). In other words, the income position of farmers who sell a small portion of their produce in the market will improve relative to the incomes of those who sell a large fraction, given a technical change.

How then would the effects of a price decline in rice due to technical change differ among consumers? It depends on the importance of rice in total household consumption expenditure.

The rate of increase in real income (Y) due to a decline in the price of rice (p) can be approximated by

$$\frac{\Delta y}{y} \cong \frac{\Delta p}{p} \cong \frac{e k}{\beta + \eta} \tag{8}$$

where e is the ratio of expenditure for rice to total household income.

Since e is inversely correlated with per-capita income, the decline in the price of food staple due to the technical progress in its production has the effect of equalizing income among urban consumers.

Application to Philippine rice economy. To empirically apply our model to the Philippine economy, we must specify the parameters of the demand and supply functions, the rate of technological change (supply shift), and the marketable surplus ratio.

Table 1. Distribution of farms in Central Luzon, Philippines among the classes divided in terms of the marketable surplus ratio, 1972/1973 crop year.

r-classes	Sale ratio (av.)	Distribution of farms	
		No.	%
Total	0.39	58	100
0 to 0.25	0.13	31	53
0.26 to 0.50	0.40	17	29
0.51 to 0.75	0.61	8	15
0.76 to 1.00	0.79	2	3

Source: Sample survey conducted for Nov. 1973–May 1974.

Based on the aggregate time-series studies on rice demand and supply we adopt (-0.3) for η and 0.4 for β . We adopt 10 percent for k , primarily for the sake of illustration. National aggregate data are not available on the marketable surplus of rice. However, based on the results of a sample survey in Central Luzon (Table 1), we assume that r is 0.4 for the average of all farms, 0.2 for small farms, and 0.8 for large farms.

Table 2 shows economic benefits from progress in rice production technology and its distribution among consumers and producers in a semisubsistence economy by comparing the distribution of fully commercial economy ($r = 1.0$). In both cases the benefit of the new technology is a stream of economic welfare worth about U.S. \$22 million per year. However, the effects on the income distribution are totally different for the different r -values. In the semisubsistence economy ($r = 0.4$), about

80 percent of the new income stream goes to consumers and 20 percent to producers. In contrast, in the fully commercial economy ($r = 1.0$), consumers gain twice the value of the new income stream—half from the benefits of the lower cost technology and half as a transfer from producers whose losses equal the benefits of the technology. Technological progress in basic food staples in a fully commercial economy, such as that of the U.S., would result in an income transfer from farm producers to urban consumers. However, technological progress does not exert such an unfavorable distributional impact on producers in a semi-subsistence economy such as that of the Philippines.

The distribution of producers' gains among small and large farms is shown in Table 3. Case 1 assumes the same price elasticity of supply and the same rate of technical progress; Case 2 assumes a larger supply elasticity for the large farmers and the same rate of technical progress; Case 3 assumes the same supply elasticity and a higher rate of technical progress for the large farms; and Case 4 assumes a larger supply elasticity and a higher rate of technical progress for the larger farms.

In Case 1 (which seems to have most realistic assumptions for the Philippines), the 10-percent shift in the supply function due to the new technology increases the incomes of small farms and reduces the incomes of large farms by more than 4 percent. But, even when the rate of

Table 2. Distribution of gains in economic welfare due to technical progress in rice production (10 percent shift in supply function) among producers and consumers in the Philippines for different assumptions on marketable surplus ratio. Averages from 1969/70 through 1971/72 crop years.

Distribution of gains ^a	$K = 10, \beta = 0.4, \eta = 0.3$	
	$r = 0.4$	$r = 1.0$
	million US \$	
Welfare gains in money terms:		
Total	21.8	22.3
Consumers $P_o q_o \frac{kr}{\beta + \eta}$	17.7	44.4
Producers $P_o q_o \frac{\eta - r + \beta(1-r)}{(1+\beta)(\beta + \eta)}$	4.1	-22.1
	%	
Welfare gains in percentage terms:		
Total	100	100
Consumers	81	199
Producers	19	-99

^a $P_o q_o =$ US\$ 311 million assuming $P_o = 41.66$ US\$ per ton of paddy (ordinario) and $q_o = 27$ million tons: price and output values for 1969/70–1971/72.

Table 3. Estimates of the differential impacts of technical progress in rice production (10 percent shift in supply function) on small and large farms in the Philippines.

Case	Parameters specified			Change (%) in		
	$K = 10$	$\eta = 0.3$	$\beta = 0.4$	Cash revenue	Production cost	Cash income (1)-(2)
	r_i	i	k_i	$K_i - k \frac{\beta_i - r_i}{\beta + \eta}$ (1)	$\frac{\beta_i}{1 + \beta_i} (k_i - k \frac{1 + \beta_i}{\beta + \eta})$ (2)	
1						
Small	0.2	0.4	10	1.4	-2.9	4.3
Large	0.8	0.4	10	-7.1	-2.9	-4.2
2						
Small	0.2	0.3	10	2.9	-2.0	4.9
Large	0.8	0.5	10	-8.6	-3.8	-4.8
3						
Small	0.2	0.4	7	-1.4	-3.7	2.3
Large	0.8	0.4	14	-3.1	-1.7	-1.4
4						
Small	0.2	0.3	7	-0.1	-2.7	1.6
Large	0.8	0.5	14	-4.6	-2.5	-2.1

technical progress of large farms is twice as fast as that of small farms (Cases 3 and 4), the income of the small farms improves and the income of the large farms declines by about 2 percent. Thus, improved technology is a force tending to equalize incomes among rice producers (the decline in costs, despite increase in output, is due to technological improvement).

The differential impacts of technical change on the real incomes of urban households for different income classes are shown in Table 4. The results show that the percentage of increase in real income due to the decline in rice prices varies inversely with the share of rice in house-

hold expenditure (e). While the 10-percent shift in the rice supply function increases the real income of households with less than ₱1,500 (\$214) by about 4 percent, it increases the real income of the highest income classes, those with more than ₱15,000 (\$2,143), by only 1 percent. Thus, the relative gain in real income is larger for the households of low-income urban workers. It should be pointed out that large benefits of new rice technology are captured not only by urban workers but also by landless farm workers for whom rice is a major item of household expenditure.

Thus, our model and its application indicate

Table 4. Estimates of differential impacts of technical progress in rice production (10 percent shift in supply function) on the real income of urban households. Philippines, 1971.

Income ^a	Share of rice (%) in urban household expenditure ^b	Increase in real income $\frac{ek}{\beta + \eta} / 100$ ($k = 10, \beta = 0.4, \eta = 0.3$)
(₱)	(₱ equivalent)	(e)
Under 500	72	30.8
500- 999	72-142	29.0
1000- 1499	143-214	26.3
1500- 1999	215-285	20.9
2000- 2499	286-375	20.4
2500- 2999	376-428	20.4
3000- 3999	429-571	17.5
4000- 4999	572-714	16.3
5000- 5999	715-857	14.8
6000- 7999	858-1142	12.7
8000- 9999	1143-1428	11.4
10000-14999	1429-2142	9.6
15000-19999	2143-2857	8.5
20000 and over	2858 and over	6.8

^a 1 U.S.\$ = ₱7. ^b Includes other staple cereals and cereal products.

that the introduction of modern technology in the production of subsistence crops in semi-subsistence economies, such as modern rice varieties in tropical Asia, promotes more equal income distribution through downward pressure exerted on prices and, hence, on the incomes of those farmers with a large proportion of marketed surplus. It enforces the transfer of income from large commercial farmers and landlords to the urban poor and the rural landless classes.

CHANGES IN DISTRIBUTION OF FARM EARNINGS FROM RICE PRODUCTION

Agricultural Economics Department

We evaluated the changes in the distribution of earnings from rice production from 1966 to 1970 by restudying and updating data collected earlier and analyzing it for the 1974 wet season for a sample of farmers in Laguna province and in Central Luzon, Philippines (1970 Annual Report). The 1966 sample included 104 farmers but the numbers had decreased to 76 and 66 in 1970 and 1974, respectively. Most of the farmers in the sample grew only one crop of rice per year.

Share tenancy was predominant in 1966 (71 percent) but by 1974, 54 percent of the sample were leaseholders and only 28 percent were share tenants. The use of tractors for land preparation increased from about 20 percent of the sample in 1966 to about 60 percent in 1974. The new varieties were unknown to these farmers in 1966, but by 1974 they were being grown by almost 90 percent. With these changes, it would not be surprising if the distribution of earnings also changed. We were specifically interested in learning how earnings were distributed among the various classes of income earners—hired laborers, landlords, and farm operators.

Methodology. The conventional analysis of output distribution uses a factor-share approach. In that methodology, the proportion of total output that accrues to labor, land, and capital is calculated either by an accounting procedure or by estimating a production function and assuming that all factors are paid their marginal value products. This approach is valid, but factor shares do not reflect impli-

cations of personal income distribution as fully as does the alternative we have used.

Our basic approach is to calculate the real income and the share of output accruing to the three main classes involved in agricultural production—landlords, hired workers, and operators—and the share of output and real income transferred outside the agricultural sector to purchase current inputs. Changes in the earnings thus divided are one measure of changes in personal income distribution. Changes in the shares of earnings among groups can be caused by changes in the resources owned by each group as well as in the earning powers of the resources.

We carefully measured all costs and returns involved in production and the sharing between landlord and tenants. The value of crop production was apportioned into parts used as: 1) the wage payment to hired labor; 2) the cost to purchase current inputs such as fertilizers, insecticides, tractor services, and irrigation fees; and 3) the rent payment to landlords. The amount remaining after making all payments is the return to the operator's own labor, capital, and land, if any. We call this the payment to the operator. Dividing each payment by the total value of output gives the share going to each earner. Subtracting the payment to current inputs from the total gives the value added in agriculture, which is also allocated into shares going to each earner. Measuring shares in value added is useful, especially in a technologically dynamic setting because it "adjusts" for increases in output directly traceable to inputs manufactured by the industrial sector. Dividing each payment by an appropriate price index gives the real income going to each earner. In this case, we use the price of rice so the real income measure is equivalent to a given quantity of rice.

In addition to calculating income shares to personal earners, by making certain assumptions we can calculate factor shares directly by accounting procedures. The first step is to calculate imputed costs for family labor, owned land, and capital of farm operators. The imputed wage rate to family labor is calculated as the total cost of hired labor divided by the total man-days of hired labor for each farm.

Table 5. Average real earnings from rice production. Central Luzon, Philippines.

	Real earning (t/ha)		
	1966	1970	1974
<i>Allocated among earners</i>			
Landlord	0.66	0.78	0.47
Hired labor	0.43	0.57	0.41
Operator	0.96	0.88	0.85
Current inputs	0.23	0.36	0.41
Total	2.28	2.59	2.14
<i>Allocated among factors</i>			
Land	0.77	0.86	0.56
Labor	0.57	0.75	0.62
Operator's residual	0.71	0.62	0.55
Current inputs	0.23	0.36	0.41
Total	2.28	2.59	2.14

The imputed cost of land is calculated as the average rental paid by all farmers in the sample who rented land. The imputed cost of capital may be taken as depreciation plus repairs plus the opportunity cost of capital.

The share of land, labor, capital, and entrepreneurship in value added can be measured by dividing the payment to each by their sum.

2. Rice production and distribution before and after the introduction of modern varieties. Central Luzon (region) and Laguna province, Philippines.

It was impossible to directly calculate factor shares for our sample because of the lack of comparable capital data. Still, it was possible to determine the imputed wage rate and the imputed land rent and, therefore, to calculate the payment and shares of land and labor. The amount that remains after costs of current inputs, land, and labor are deducted is simply called operator's residual, which may be taken as a crude estimate of the earnings of capital.

Results of the analysis. The allocation of real earnings from the wet-season rice crop for the sample farms in 1966–1970 and 1974 is shown in Table 5. Only wet-season comparisons are available because there were relatively few dry-season irrigated farms in the early years. Yields increased from 2.3 to 2.6 t/ha from 1966 to 1970, but in 1974 yields were disappointingly low because of the number and intensity of typhoons that damaged the crop. As a result, yields in 1974 were slightly lower than in 1966 and considerably lower than in 1970. Since farmers had increased their use of current inputs in 1974, the low yields due to bad weather resulted in lower net returns and, hence, lower real earnings for all groups in 1974 than in either 1966 or 1970 (fig. 2).

Between 1966 and 1970, the real earnings of landlords, hired laborers, and current inputs increased. Real earnings spent on current inputs increased by nearly 60 percent and the earnings of hired labor, by about 30 percent. Landlords had 17 percent higher returns. The real earnings of farm operators fell by slightly less than 10 percent.

Between 1970 and 1974, the real payment to current inputs further increased by 15 percent, indicating a continuing trend of intensification of production. Other earners all suffered a reduction in real returns. The reduction in landlords' share can be traced to rent and tenure changes while the reduction in labor's share can be traced to the reduced yield in 1974.

The average percentage share of earnings distributed among owners and among factors is shown in Table 6. The share of current inputs increased while the share of landlords decreased over the period. The share of hired labor increased between 1966 and 1970, then de-

Table 6. Average percentage shares of earnings from rice production wet seasons, Central Luzon, Philippines.

	Share of earnings ^a (%)			
			1974	
	1966	1970	Actual yield	Expected yield
	<i>Allocated among earners</i>			
Landlord	29	30	22	21
Hired labor	19	22	19	20
Operator	42	34	40	47
Current inputs	10	14	19	13
Total	100	100	100	100
	<i>Allocated among factors</i>			
Land	34	33	26	25
Labor	25	29	28	28
Operator's residual	31	24	26	34
Current inputs	10	14	19	13
Total	100	100	100	100

^aFigures were rounded to the nearest whole number and may not add up to exactly 100 in each column.

creased. Operators' share declined between 1966 and 1970, but increased between 1970 and 1974, despite the bad yields of 1974.

Several interesting forces were at work between 1970 and 1974. An unusual number of typhoons depressed yields. Changes also occurred in tenure, labor use, and mechanization. In 1970, 51 per cent of the samples were share tenants; by 1974, only 28 percent were share tenants. The use of machinery for land preparation increased, but the total use of labor and the use of hired labor also increased (Table 7). We attempted to isolate the effects of several of these factors.

The effect of the depressed yield was calculated by asking farmers what they thought their yields would have been without the typhoon damage but with the current inputs they had used. Their responses indicated that about half expected substantially higher yields. We then

Table 8. Real earnings under actual and two alternative sets of assumed conditions. Central Luzon, Philippines, 1974.

	Real earnings (t/ha)		
	Actual	With expected yields	With 1970 tenure
Landlord	0.47	0.67	0.66
Hired labor	0.41	0.64	0.41
Operator	0.85	1.53	0.65
Current inputs	0.42	0.42	0.42

calculated what the shares would have been, on the assumption that the labor required for harvesting would increase in proportion to the yield and that share tenants would have paid their landlords greater rentals. The results indicate that operators would have substantially increased their share while current inputs share would have fallen (last column, Table 6). Table 8 and fig. 2 show the distribution of real earnings under this set of assumptions. Both landlords and hired labor would have increased their earnings by about 50 percent, while operators would have gained even more.

The share of hired labor declined somewhat between 1970 and 1974, while the amount of hired labor increased. This suggests a decline in the real wage rate, which is confirmed by the data. However, at least part of this decline occurred because harvesting labor, which commands a premium wage rate, was reduced in 1974, along with the depressed harvest. The actual wage was \$1.09/day while with the expected yield and the prevailing wage for harvesting, the actual wage would have averaged \$1.83/day.

We examined the impact of tenurial change by calculating what the earnings would have been, assuming the proportion of share and leasehold tenants had not changed between the

Table 7. Labor and machinery use. Central Luzon, Philippines.

Year	Labor (man-days/ha)							
	Land preparation		Pre-harvest		Total		Machine users (%)	
	All	Hired	All	Hired	All	Hired	Tractors	Threshers
1966	17	8	47	27	65	44	12	62
1970	9	4	46	29	66	44	42	61
1974	13	8	63	33	93	63	66	55

^aFor plowing.

Table 9. Average percentage share of value added from rice production. Central Luzon, Philippines.

	Share ^a (%)		
	1966	1970	1974
<i>Allocated among earners</i>			
Landlord	34	34	27
Hired labor	20	25	23
Operator	45	39	49
Total	100	100	100
<i>Allocated among factors</i>			
Land	38	38	32
Labor	32	34	35
Operator's residual	30	26	32
Total	100	100	100

^aFigures were rounded to the nearest whole number and may not add up to exactly 100 in each column.

two dates, using the actual 1974 rental rates, and assuming all other facts unchanged. From the data in Table 8, the switch to leaseholding has clearly benefited operators at the expense of landlords.

Table 9 shows the shares of value added for the 3 years. The percentage share of land and landlords in value added was constant between 1966 and 1970. (As pointed out above, the landlord's share would have been higher in Central Luzon through 1974 if the tenure of a substantial proportion of farmers had not changed). The share in value added of hired labor increased and the share of the operator decreased between 1966 and 1970. These trends reversed in 1974.

Comparisons for share tenants. Changes in tenure and the unusual weather of 1974 appear to have been major factors leading to changes in the share of earnings in the comparisons

Table 10. Allocation of earnings on shareholder operated farms. Central Luzon, Philippines.

	1966	1970	1974
<i>Real earnings (t) allocated among earners</i>			
Landlord	0.80	0.71	0.59
Hired labor	0.42	0.55	0.45
Operator	0.78	0.70	0.62
Current inputs	0.22	0.32	0.39
Total	2.22	2.28	2.05
<i>Share (%) allocated among earners</i>			
Landlord	36	31	29
Hired labor	19	24	22
Operator	35	31	30
Current inputs	10	14	19
Total	100	100	100

made above. We have attempted to abstract from these changes by various assumptions, but a direct comparison is more desirable. Share tenants made up the largest proportion of farm operators in the samples for 1966 and 1970, and they are a group whose welfare is of primary concern. There were not a large enough number of owner-operated or leasehold farms to make valid comparisons for those tenure classes. Therefore, we have compared the allocation of earnings for the two periods on the share-tenant farms.

Table 10 shows a very consistent pattern of changes in the allocation of earnings on share tenant-operated farms. Landlords' shares declined from 36 percent to about 29 percent; hired labor and operators' shares were roughly constant; and purchased inputs' share increased each period. Yields of the shareholders changed only marginally.

Reflecting this, the real incomes of share tenants and of landlords were reduced. The use of hired labor increased by more than 15 percent. The real earnings of hired labor working on share tenant-operated farms were higher in 1970 than in 1966, but lower in 1974 than in 1970.

The deterioration in the share and real earnings of landlords appears to be a function of the increased use of hired labor and of current inputs. Because the landlord shares in the cost of these inputs if they make up a larger share of output, his net remaining share declines. The same explanation holds for the share tenant operator.

These data gave little support to the hypothesis of radical changes in the shares of earnings going to various groups. There is no evidence that labor has suffered either an absolute or relative decline in earnings since the introduction of new varieties. Instead there seems to be evidence of increasing use of labor and increasing proportions of hired labor. Thus, if anything, the technology seems to be labor using. Landlords appear to be losing out, especially because of the shift from share to leasehold rentals, but even landlords of share tenants have suffered a reduction in their relative share of earnings.

PRICE SUPPORT VS. FERTILIZER SUBSIDY FOR SELF-SUFFICIENCY

Agricultural Economics Department

At the request of the Philippine government, we examined the reasons behind the recent decline in fertilizer consumption and evaluated alternative fertilizer price policies. Subsequently, a more detailed analytical framework was developed for evaluating the benefits and costs of price support vs. fertilizer subsidy for achieving self-sufficiency in rice production. The advantages and disadvantages of policy alternatives are discussed in terms of efficiency and equity criteria.

The policy alternatives considered in this analysis include a rice price support and three alternative fertilizer subsidy plans: plan A, with a subsidy for rice producers only involving a two-price system for fertilizer; plan B, with a single subsidy price for fertilizer applied to all crops; and plan C, the same as plan B but financed partly by an increase in the sugar export tax. Sugar and rice together account for more than 90 percent of the fertilizer consumed in the Philippines.

Policy evaluation model. A simple model of rice price support and fertilizer subsidy is presented in fig. 3. The line SS represents the domestic supply curve for rice. The vertical line D_hH represents the demand curve of the producers for home consumption. The producer's household consumes the same quantity of rice irrespective of price and sells the rest. The distance between D_mD and D_hH represents the quantity purchased by urban (nonfarmer) households. The total demand for rice is represented by D_hD_mD .

Normally, the world price of rice (OP_w) has been below the Philippine domestic equilibrium price (OP_e) that would have been established by the intersection of supply and demand (SS and DD). Without government intervention, the quantity AB would be imported. We assume for this analysis that the price for imported rice is exactly equal to the domestic sale price, although the model can easily be modified to reflect those situations where the price for imported rice is above or below the domestic price.

3. Model of price support and fertilizer subsidy for rice. IRRI, 1975.

Providing a total supply of rice OQ_c so that HQ_c can be sold to consumers at price OP_d is a necessary condition that has to be satisfied. There are three possible alternatives: 1) import AD ; 2) support the rice price at P_s ; and 3) subsidize fertilizer to shift the supply function from S to S' . The first alternative, which has been the traditional policy of the Philippine Government, served as a standard of comparison against which we measured the benefits and costs of rice support or fertilizer price subsidy.

Price support. Given the domestic supply schedule SS , self-sufficiency of rice can be achieved by supporting the producer price at OP_s . Since the government has to maintain the consumer price at OP_d , the self-sufficiency of rice by means of price support would involve a cost to the government represented by area $ACLM$, the difference between the procurement cost and the revenue from sales. An increase in the rice producers' income due to the government support is represented by the area $BCLM$. A net savings of foreign exchange is area ABQ_0Q_c minus the added cost of fertilizer import due to the increased fertilizer application stimulated by the more favorable fertilizer-to-rice price ratio.

4. Model of fertilizer subsidy for rice. IIRRI, 1975.

Fertilizer subsidy for rice. Self-sufficiency in rice can be achieved, without supporting the producer price of rice, by shifting the supply curve from SS to $S'S'$ in fig. 3. Since the supply curve represents a marginal-cost curve, it can be shifted to the right either by shifting the production function upward (technological change) or by lowering the price of the input.

Figure 4 shows for existing technology the production function (PF) relating rice output to fertilizer input (upper portion) and the demand function for fertilizer relating the price of fertilizer to the fertilizer input (lower portion). The fertilizer input required to produce self-

sufficiency in rice output is the quantity $X_s - X_o$. The point E shows the optimum point of fertilizer input given the unsubsidized fertilizer price P_{fo} and the unsupported rice price P_d . However, producers do not apply fertilizer at the optimum levels since at price P_{fo} they apply only the quantity X_o .

The needed increase in fertilizer input, $x_s - x_o$, can be achieved by lowering the fertilizer price from P_{fo} to P_{fs} as shown in the lower portion of fig. 4. The government cost for the fertilizer subsidy is represented by the area $KP_{fo}P_{fs}I$.

The rice producers would achieve a dual benefit: a) from being able to buy all their fertilizer at a lower cost as represented by the area $CP_{fs}P_{fo}D$, and b) from the output value less fertilizer cost from using the additional amount of fertilizer because of the more favorable price relationship: $P_d(q_c - q_o) - P_{fs}(x_s - x_o)$.

Net savings in foreign exchange may be calculated as the net reduction in foreign exchange expenditure for rice import, area ABQ_oQ_c in fig. 3, less the increase in foreign exchange requirement for increased fertilizer import, area $FGIK$ in fig. 4.

As with rice price support, the welfare of rice consumers does not change because they consume the same quantity of rice at the same price irrespective of the support or subsidy programs.

Fertilizer subsidy for sugarcane. Plan A (two-price system), provided that it is properly enforced, charges the market price for fertilizer (P_{fo}) to sugar producers, and hence involves no additional cost to the government and no change in income for the sugar sector. Under plans B and C (single-price system) the sugar sector benefits from the purchase of subsidized fertilizer and the government must bear the cost.

The increase in sugarcane production is due to the added fertilizer input stimulated by the subsidized price in the same manner as for rice. The added production is exported. The government receives a benefit through added revenue from the sugar export tax but this is more than offset by the cost of the government subsidy for fertilizer to the sugar sector.

As with rice, sugar producers (millers and growers) receive a dual benefit: 1) from being

able to buy all of their fertilizer at a lower cost, and 2) from output value less fertilizer cost for additional amounts of fertilizer applied as a result of the subsidized price. The net gain in foreign exchange is the added foreign exchange earnings from sugar export less the increase in foreign requirements for the import of fertilizer.

Plan C differs from plan B in that the export tax from sugar is raised to cover almost the entire government cost for the fertilizer subsidy to sugar. An increase in the export tax rate results in a decrease in the price received by producers, which in turn depresses the level of fertilizer application and results in a modest reduction in sugar output and export.

Parameters and data. This model allows us to calculate private and public sector benefits and costs for achieving self-sufficiency in rice for any of the four specified plans. To estimate the benefits and costs, certain parameters and data must be specified. For this analysis, we chose 1975 as the base year. Production and consumption relationships with respect to rice, sugar, and fertilizer are estimated for 1975 assuming no price support or subsidy program. The assumptions made and analysis conducted here are based on a "normal" relationship between sugar, rice, and fertilizer prices in both the international and domestic markets. Hence, it abstracts from the recent situation of abnormally high prices.

We define *self-sufficiency* requirement as the percent increase in output needed to avoid imports of rice in all but extreme situations such as occurred with the severe drop in domestic rice production due to the 1972-73 floods and droughts. Based on the records of the past 10 years, the added production requirement to achieve self-sufficiency appears to be about 5 percent of the total production or currently around 220,000 metric tons.

Assumptions with respect to parameters and data are summarized as follows:

Production requirement to achieve self-sufficiency	220,000 t
Total domestic consumption of milled rice in 1975	4,400,000 t
Total consumed in households of rice producers	2,640,000 t
Production of sugar	2,300,000 t

Export of sugar	1,500,000 t
Fertilizer for rice (41% of total)	300,000 t
Fertilizer for sugar (45% of total)	330,000 t
Domestic consumer and import price for rice ($p_d = p_w$)	\$ 300/t
Import price for fertilizer (26 N, 7 P ₂ O ₅ , 3 K ₂ O)	\$ 160/t
Export price of sugar	\$ 63/t
Elasticity of rice supply	0.3
Production elasticity of fertilizer for rice and sugarcane	0.1
Demand elasticity of fertilizer for rice and sugarcane	-0.5

The parameters and data specified above are, in effect, based on the premise that the current level of fertilizer input is much lower than the optimum level. Marginal value product (MVP) or return for 1 additional ton of fertilizer applied to rice and sugar calculated from the specified data and parameters is as follows:

MVP for rice = \$380

MVP for sugar = \$307

Both these values are substantially higher than the domestic retail price of fertilizer (\$160/t).

Benefits and costs for rice and sugar sectors.

The benefits and costs of price support and of fertilizer subsidy for the rice sector are presented in Table 11; those for the sugar sector are in Table 12. The calculations are made for two levels of rice self-sufficiency rate defined as the ratio of domestic output to domestic consumption (i.e. 97.5 and 100 percent). To attain those levels of self-sufficiency, domestic output of rice must be increased from 4,180 metric tons to 4,290 and 4,400 tons, implying that the rates of increase in output are 2.63 and 5.26 percent, respectively. Given output and price elasticity assumptions, these rates of increase can be achieved either by raising the rice price by 9.0 percent and 18.6 percent, respectively, or by lowering the fertilizer price by 40.6 and 64.1 percent, respectively.

The benefits and costs that result from a change in prices are reported for rice in Table 11 and for sugar in Table 12. However, to compare the benefits and costs between alternative plans, it is best to reorganize the data into another set of tables.

Table 11. Benefits and costs of price support and fertilizer subsidy for the rice sector. Philippines, 1975.

Self-sufficiency rate (%)	Domestic rice output (thousand t)	Rice import (thousand t)	Rate of support or of subsidy (%)	Price of paddy or of fertilizer (\$/t)	Nitrogen: paddy price ratio	Benefits (million \$)		
						Producers' income	Foreign exchange savings	Government support cost
<i>Rice price support</i>								
95.0	4180	220	0	143	3.0	0	0	0
97.5	4290	110	9.0	156	2.8	47	31	48
100.0	4400	0	18.6	169	2.5	100	62	106
<i>Fertilizer subsidy</i>								
95.0	4180	220	0	428	3.0	0	0	0
97.5	4290	110	40.5	254	1.8	44	19	25
100.0	4400	0	64.1	153	1.1	85	34	51

Evaluation of policy alternatives. The choice among policy alternatives can be based on the valuation of a number of criteria. These include: 1) the contribution of a policy in terms of net benefit to society; 2) the cost of the program to the government (or taxpayer); 3) the efficiency of the policy in terms of total benefits to the society relative to government cost for the program; 4) the distribution of benefits and costs among various sectors of society; and 5) the savings in foreign exchange.

The rice price support and the three plans for fertilizer subsidy are compared in Table 13 in terms of the first three criteria. Income redistribution effects are shown in Table 14, and the effect of alternative programs on foreign exchange in Table 15. All three tables are based on Tables 11 and 12. The results for rice price support and for plan A of the fertilizer subsidy are taken directly from Table 11. By adding the benefits and costs for the rice sector associated with fertilizer subsidy in Table 11 to those for the sugar sector in Table 12, we estimated the

total benefits and costs for plans B and C. In aggregating the benefits from the savings in foreign exchange into total social benefits, we have assumed the foreign exchange premium to be 5 percent, based on the difference between official and black market rates of exchange.

The findings from this analysis can be summarized as follows:

1) The total social benefit produced by the rice price-support program is quite large (\$103 million) but since the direct cost to government for the support is even larger (\$106 million), the net social benefit is negative (Table 13).

2) The larger net social benefit produced from the subsidy on fertilizer may at first seem to be an anomaly because price distortions due to government intervention in product or input markets usually result in inefficiency or net loss in social and economic welfare.

But here we are dealing with an economy characterized by suboptimality in farmers' application of inputs.

3) Among the alternatives for fertilizer price

Table 12. Benefits and costs of fertilizer subsidy for the sugar sector, Philippines, 1975.

Rice self-sufficiency rate (%)	Nitrogen: sugar price ^a ratio	Sugar output (thousand t)	Sugar export (thousand t)	Benefits (million \$)			
				Government export tax revenue	Producers' income	Foreign exchange earnings	Government subsidy cost (million \$)
<i>Plan B</i>							
95.0	1.2	2300	500	0	0	0	0
97.5	0.70	2360	1560	5	34	11	28
100.0	0.42	2421	1621	9	65	18	56
<i>Plan C</i>							
95.0	1.2	2300	1500	0	0	0	0
97.5	0.72	2357	1557	23	14	10	27
100.0	0.44	2416	1616	47	25	18	55

^aPrice of sugar is export price minus export tax.

Table 13. Benefits and costs associated with price-support and fertilizer-subsidized programs, Philippines, 1975.

Self-sufficiency rate (%)	Benefits and costs ^a (million \$)			
	Rice price support	Fertilizer subsidy plan		
		A	B	C
<i>Total social benefit</i>				
97.5	48	45	84	83
100.0	103	87	162	161
<i>Net social benefit</i>				
97.5	0 ^b	20	31	30
100.0	-3	36	54	54
<i>Direct government cost</i>				
97.5	48	25	53	53
100.0	106	51	108	106
<i>Net government cost</i>				
97.5	48	25	48	30
100.0	106	51	98	59
<i>Benefit-to-cost ratio</i>				
		(1)/(3)		
97.5	1.0	1.8	1.6	1.6
100.0	0.97	1.7	1.5	1.5
		(1)/(4)		
97.5	1.0	1.8	1.8	2.8
100.0	0.97	1.7	1.6	2.7

^aIncludes foreign exchange premium which is assumed as 5% of total foreign exchange savings/earnings. ^bLess than 1 million.

subsidies, the net social benefit for plan A (\$36 million) is lower than that for plans B and C (\$54 million each), but the direct government cost for plan A (\$51 million) is only about half that for the other alternatives (Table 13). However, plan A, based on a two-price system in which only rice (and corn) producers are entitled to purchase subsidized fertilizer, has proved difficult to implement administratively, especially when a fairly substantial gap between subsidized and nonsubsidized prices encourages black-market activities.

4) Despite the high direct government cost for the single-price system of fertilizer price subsidy, the net government cost can be reduced by increasing the export tax on sugar (\$59 million for plan C vs. \$98 million for plan B). Based on net government costs, the benefit-cost ratio for plan C (2.7) is higher than that for any of the other alternatives (Table 13).

5) Rice producers gain considerably in terms of income benefits in each of the four alternatives compared. Plans A, B, and C differ principally in the way costs and benefits are

Table 14. Income redistribution effects of price-support and fertilizer subsidy programs, Philippines, 1975.

Rice self-sufficiency rate (%)	Income redistribution effect (million \$)			
	Rice price support	Fertilizer subsidy plan		
		A	B	C
<i>Rice producers</i>				
97.5	47	44	44	44
100.0	100	85	85	85
<i>Sugar producers</i>				
97.5	0	0	34	14
100.0	0	0	65	26
<i>Government^a</i>				
97.5	-47	-24	-47	-28
100.0	-102	-50	-96	-57

^aDirect government cost of price support or subsidy program net of government tax revenue and foreign exchange premium (assumed as 5 percent of total foreign exchange savings/earnings).

Table 15. Total earnings/savings in foreign exchange due to rice price-support and fertilizer-subsidy programs, Philippines, 1975.

Rice self-sufficiency rate (%)	Total earnings/savings (million \$)			
	Rice price support	Fertilizer subsidy		
		A	B	C
97.5	31	19	29	29
100.0	62	34	52	52

partitioned between the government and sugar sector (Table 14). Under plan B, both rice and sugar producers gain in similar magnitude at a large cost to the government. Under plan C, the gain of rice producers is almost three times that of sugar producers.

6) Rice price support gives the largest contribution to foreign exchange savings since the import expenditure for rice is eliminated with a minimum additional expenditure for fertilizer import. However, the difference in savings between price support and plans B and C (\$62 vs. \$52 and \$52 million) is fairly modest (Table 15).

7) This analysis does not imply that achieving self-sufficiency through any of the alternatives discussed is a desirable policy goal for the Philippines. These programs must be weighed against alternative uses for capital. The goal of self-sufficiency in food can best be achieved, in

the long run, by improving the physical and institutional infrastructures, such as irrigation and research/extension systems, which would shift the production function. Because such programs require extremely large investments and

long gestation periods, however, governments are always tempted to adopt short-run policies such as those we have analyzed. We plan in the future to extend our model to include some of these longer run alternatives.

Machinery development and testing

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SUMMARY

The machinery development program has been reorganized into four complementary sections along functional lines: 1) machinery design; 2) mechanization systems; 3) mechanization research; and 4) industrial extension.

The IRRI 5- to 7-hp tiller, axial flow thresher, batch dryer, and power weeder continue to gain in popularity. We are refining the designs of the axial flow thresher and power tiller.

Several new projects were started in 1975. A simple deep-placement applicator which places liquid chemicals in the mud of lowland fields was designed and is being evaluated. A manually operated diaphragm pump for low-lift application successfully completed durability tests. We designed a motorized cart that can be used to transport the axial flow thresher or a 1-ton payload. It is being tested for performance and durability.

Continuing studies on the effect of different methods of land tillage indicate that the compaction layer deepens at a faster rate with large 4-wheel tractors than with other methods.

Sixty representatives from 19 countries in Asia, Africa, Europe, and the Americas participated in the International Workshop on Agricultural Mechanization and Indigenous Production of Agricultural Machines, organized and held at IRRI. Twenty trainees from 10 countries received formal instruction in the manufacture and utilization of IRRI machine during 1975.

We initiated a new industrial extension project. Extension teams will be located at regional centers in Pakistan, Philippines, and Thailand to encourage the manufacture of IRRI-designed machines in South and Southeast Asia.

MACHINERY DESIGN

Agricultural Engineering Department

Deep-placement chemical applicator. Entomology and agronomy research shows that deep placement of insecticides and fertilizers into the paddy mud is more effective than broadcast application.

We developed a two-row, push-type fertilizer applicator to deposit granular fertilizer at 10-cm

depth in puddled soils. The applicator has a rotary fluted feed mechanism mounted on a small skid with a furrow opener. Fertilizer is dropped into the furrow and covered by the furrow closer. In tests in farmers' fields, the opener did not penetrate fully on hard soils, making the machine difficult to push. Also, the granular fertilizer absorbed moisture around the metering mechanism, which interfered with uniform metering.

An alternate machine was developed (fig. 1) to apply liquid solutions. Use of liquids makes pushing easier because the furrow openers are narrower. Moisture absorption problems are eliminated and metering is more uniform. The drawback of liquid injection is that insoluble chemicals cannot be applied and considerable water is required.

The liquid injector consists of a long handle attached to a skid mounted with two applicator tubes. The applicator tubes open the furrow and the back of the skid closes it. The operator carries a 10-liter back-mounted tank which is connected to the two openings through a flexible tube. A flow-metering orifice in the tube maintains the desired rate of application.

Initial tests are encouraging. Most problems with the granular applicator have been overcome by the liquid applicator. It does not harm the transplanted seedlings and is not sensitive to varying field conditions.

1. The two-row liquid injector operates by gravity, depositing liquid solutions of fertilizer and insecticide below the paddy surface. IRRI, 1975.

2. Schematic drawing of a combination of the improved Savonius rotor windmill and the self-priming tubular pump. IRRI, 1975.

One man can fertilize about 1 ha/day with the simple two-row machine.

Tubular pump. We developed a T-shaped tubular pump for lowlift irrigation. It consists of two slightly curved horizontal delivery pipes connected to a vertical suction pipe. Two containers near the discharge outlets store sufficient water during operation to retain self-priming capability without foot valves, which clog easily when pumping dirty water.

We fabricated and evaluated the pumping performance and power requirements of two 2.4-m diameter tubular pumps with pipes that were 25 and 32 mm in diameter (fig. 2). Pumping characteristics are quite similar to those of

conventional centrifugal pumps. These pumps are self-priming up to a lift of 1.2 m. As much as 20 percent of the total power consumed is lost to wind drag. The tubular pump with 32-mm tubes gave an output from 2.2 to 1.9 times greater than the pump with 25-mm tubes, when number of revolutions per minute ranged from 50 to 70. The 32-mm tubular pump required from 1.3 to 1.6 times more power than the 25-mm pump.

To increase the self-primed lift capability to at least 4.6 m, a new tubular pump is being fabricated with a central storage container. The relative volume of the central container and of the air in the suction pipe is critical for self-priming at different heads. We are also attempting to develop a simple foot valve that will not easily clog or foul.

Diaphragm pump. The manually operated bellows pump performs well in low-lift irrigation, but the service life of the canvas bellows is short. We developed a double-chambered diaphragm pump to overcome this problem (fig. 3).

The pump casing consists of a light sheet-metal cylinder with a central partition to provide two chambers. Rubber flap valves are used on the intake and exhaust ports. The two rubber diaphragms are made from automotive inner tubes and are mounted so that they can easily be replaced.

3. Prototype of the manually operated diaphragm pump. The pump has two chambers covered by automotive inner tube material. IRRI, 1975.

A prototype pump satisfactorily completed laboratory and field tests. Production drawings will be released to manufacturers.

Vertical-axis windmill. The omnidirectional feature and the simple construction of Savonius rotor windmills would make them easy and economical to produce in developing countries. We tested several shapes of Savonius rotor models in a small wind tunnel with the following variables: shape of rotor blades; overlap between rotor blades; and separation distance between rotor blades. Tests indicated that a modified noncircular shape with 30 percent overlap between rotor blades performs best.

Based on the wind-tunnel results, we installed on a truck-mounted test stand a Savonius rotor 1.2 m high and 1.2 m in diameter. It generated a maximum power of $1.65 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}\cdot\text{sq m}^{-1}$ of projected area at winds of 11.15 m/s. A full-scale Savonius rotor, 1.2 m wide and 2.62 m high, was fabricated with 3.14 sq m frontal area and 30 percent overlap. This rotor was made from three 44-gal (166.54 liters) oil drums cut in half and welded end to end. The rotor was coupled to a tubular pump, 2.4 m in diameter with 32-mm diameter tubes. We installed the windmill on an irrigation ditch at the IIRI farm (fig. 2). This unit lifts 70 liters water/min at 0.95 m head in winds of 4.47 m/s (16 km/h). We are also attempting to couple this windmill to a 12-V alternator to provide electrical power for low-wattage applications.

Steering clutches for the 5- to 7-hp tiller. The original IIRI 5- to 7-hp tiller was designed with a single axle and no steering clutches. A survey

of owners indicated a desire for steering clutches to reduce handling and turning effort.

We developed externally mounted open steering clutches but found that clogging with mud was a serious problem.

Next, we designed and evaluated two enclosed straight-jaws clutches. On one, the drive-engaging sleeve slid on the hexagonal axle; on the other, it slid on a splined axle shaft. Mud did not interfere with operation of the clutch, but the relatively high torque of the axle shaft did not permit easy disengaging under full load.

To reduce sliding friction, we replaced the splined sliding sleeve with a sleeve with axial steel ball bearings (fig. 4). In tests, this clutch disengaged more easily under full load. The hexagonal axle shaft is split at the center with the final driven sprocket floating on the split shafts. Straight jaws are machined on both sides of the driven sprocket hub for engaging with the jaws on the sliding sleeves. The clutches are normally maintained in an engaged position by spring pressure for straight travel. For turning, the operator disengages the clutch on one side with a control lever on the handle. We are testing the clutch for durability before releasing it to manufacturers.

Four-wheel tractor. Small four-wheel tractors from the industrialized countries are expensive and difficult to purchase in developing nations. Further, these tractors are designed to develop adequate traction for pull-type implements used in dryland conditions, but are usually too heavy for wetland work. We initiated a project to develop an inexpensive 15- to 20-hp four-wheel tractor for use in both wet and dryland conditions. The basic tractor should be lightweight for wetland work with provisions to add inexpensive ballast weights so that it can also be used on dry land. We evaluated this concept using a lightweight lawn maintenance tractor at the IIRI farm. The 460-kg tractor was powered by a 14-hp gasoline engine. We modified it for additional ground clearance and modified a rotary tiller attachment to match the full width of the tractor.

The machine performed satisfactorily and encountered no mobility problems under wetland conditions for three continuous cropping seasons. Penetrometer readings indicated that

4. Experimental steering clutch for the IIRI 5- to 7-hp tiller. IIRI, 1975.

continuous use did not deepen the soil pan. We then designed a small riding tractor to closely conform with the specifications of the test tractor but using a two-cylinder 17-hp aircooled diesel engine and a transmission and differential that are readily available in most developing nations. Although the 500-kg machine is slightly heavier than the test tractor, it will be much easier to fabricate in developing nations.

We expect to field-test the machine soon. A range of implements are being developed for it. Manufacturers have shown keen interest in this project.

PTO thresher. We used data from earlier studies on the air movement zones in the housing of the straw thrower to modify the PTO (power takeoff) thresher. Inadequate transfer of pieces of straw from the rotary separator assembly to the straw thrower is a major cause of poor cleaning. To improve delivery of all straw and chaff into the thrower, we replaced the external cylindrical shell of the rotary separator with a frustum-shaped shell. The smaller end of the frustum matched the diameter of the neutral air zone in the intake opening of the straw thrower.

We studied the screening performance of each rotary screen and found that the inner two screens removed about 95 percent of the straw. To winnow the grain as it fell below the concave, we diverted the suction draft from the straw thrower opening by partially closing the concentric opening on the broader end of the frustum. This concentrated the air movement in the lower part where grain fell from the concave. We replaced the auger with an oscillating tray conveyor under the concave to convey grain toward the rotary screen. Grain separated by the rotary cleaner was elevated by a flap elevator to the delivery spout.

The machine's weight was considerably reduced and field mobility improved by the elimination of the grain auger, the smaller winnowing fan, one cylinder from the rotary separator, and the smaller outer cylindrical shell. Further work is needed to reduce the short straw pieces that now go with the grain. We are attempting to incorporate a simple oscillating cleaner at low cost.

Axial flow thresher. This machine continues

to be rapidly accepted in many Asian countries for threshing rice, sorghum, millet, and wheat. Several versions, based on the original IRRI thresher design, have been developed by manufacturers to improve performance and to better suit their production facilities. In response to requests to lower the cost of the thresher and to improve its cleaning performance, we evaluated designs of three cleaning mechanisms for use in varying crop and climatic conditions.

In one version, we replaced the rotary cleaner with a small, flat oscillating screen, driven by the auger shaft and installed at the auger outlet. The small 30- × 75-cm screen with 1.27-cm perforations was found adequate for removing residual pieces of straw from the threshed grain. The screen assembly was designed so that it could be swung upward and locked in position when transported over rough terrain.

In the second version, we added a small 20- × 55-cm oscillating screen at the delivery spout of the original rotary screen. Since rotary screen performance is better under extremely wet conditions, we felt that this dual-screen arrangement would serve both wet and dry threshing. The straw pieces that slip through the rotary screen perforations are separated before delivery by the small oscillating screen.

In a third version, we replaced the rotary screen, grain delivery auger, and collecting boards under the concave with a full-length, flat oscillating tray. The threshed material passing through the concave falls on the tray and is conveyed by oscillating motion to the screen part of the tray, where it drops to a collecting pan. A blower above the oscillating tray removes the light impurities from the threshed material.

To provide more versatility for threshing different crops, changes were also made in the concave assembly of the threshing drum. The upper concave was eliminated and five adjustable louvers were installed on the inside of the threshing drum cover. The adjustable louvers control the retention time of material inside the threshing drum, permitting adjustments for threshing a wide variety of crops. This version is the simplest and easiest to build of the three.

IRRI axial flow threshers are being widely used for contract threshing which necessitates

5. The motorized axial flow thresher, mounted in a self-propelled cart, can transport the thresher or a 1-t payload at a maximum speed of 15 km/h. IRRI, 1975.

repeated movement of the machine from one location to another. Contract threshing operators use power tillers, large tractors, jeeps, and trailers to move the thresher during contract work. We are working on two approaches to facilitate thresher transport.

Power tiller-thresher combination. In this arrangement, the power tiller engine is used to transport and power the thresher. A special hitch allows the tiller to be coupled to the thresher frame so that the tiller engine can drive the thresher using the same V-belt provided for the power tiller drive. This hitching arrangement offers an attractive low-cost package, but each type of power tiller will require an appropriate hitching arrangement.

Motorized cart-thresher combination. Threshers are used only during the harvest season and remain idle for the rest of the year. A thresher was designed in which wheels, engine, and part of the chassis could be separated to form a motorized cart (fig. 5). The engine was mounted on a front-pivoted wheel assembly with a simple chain-sprocket transmission for transport. With this configuration, the 7-hp engine can operate a cart of 1-t capacity at a maximum speed of 15 km/h on roads of up to 15 percent slope. The powered front wheel is equipped with a band brake that provides adequate braking for the loaded vehicle. The cart is stable with a full load of 1 t on rough country roads. Negative caster is built into the front-pivoted

wheel design to improve tracking. This increases the steering effort when turning under full load, but it enhances safety and stability.

The thresher chassis and drive was modified so it could be loaded on the cart and powered by the cart engine. The powered front wheel assembly is connected to the cart frame through a double-pivoted bracket so it can be swung 90° to align the engine pulley with the thresher drive pulley.

The same clutching system is used for both the transport and the threshing modes. A screw jack mechanism and two folding legs mounted on the thresher allow it to be loaded and unloaded by one man.

Solar heat collector. A variety of solar heat collectors have been developed in the industrially advanced countries, but most are expensive. We continued our efforts to develop a low-cost solar collector for use as an attachment to the IRRI batch dryer. On the basis of earlier work, the following guidelines were developed for a solar energy collector for use in developing countries: 1) factors such as low cost, light weight, and ease of production are more important than efficiency; 2) readily available, inexpensive materials such as wood, cardboard, paper, and bamboo must be used; 3) light weight (about 30 kg) is essential to facilitate transport and installation; 4) convenient stacking is desirable for efficient storage of the panel when not in use.

On the basis of earlier tests (1974 Annual Report), we developed a new cardboard collector panel from two standard 122- × 244-cm panels of corrugated cardboard. The collector panel was formed by folding one piece of cardboard to form an accordion-type collector and attaching it to a flat cardboard panel. The assembly is enclosed in a polyethylene plastic sheet to provide space for drawing air through the panel. The panel is being evaluated.

Oscillating grain cleaners. As rice production increases in Asia, traditional wooden winnowers are often inadequate for grain cleaning. We previously reported the development of a rotary screen cleaner (1970 Annual Report). Although this machine can clean 2.5 t of paddy/h at 98 percent purity, it is costly to fabricate.

We designed an oscillating grain cleaner with

2 t/h capacity (fig. 6). This machine has two flat screens with a collecting pan at the bottom, a centrifugal fan, and an auger with bagging elevator. The first screen removes larger impurities, such as chaff and straw pieces, and the lower screen removes fine impurities, such as dust and sand. Air from the blower removes light impurities as the grain cascades from the second screen. Cleaned grain is transferred by an auger to a grain thrower, which elevates it for bagging. This machine is simpler and more economical to fabricate than the rotary cleaner. Production prototype machines are being built in the Philippines and Sri Lanka.

A smaller oscillating cleaner is also being developed for farm-level operations and threshing floors. This machine has two major moving parts, a dual-screen oscillating assembly and a centrifugal fan. The horizontal screens are mounted in rubber to reduce costs, noise, and service problems. Tests of the prototype indicate a grain-cleaning capacity of 1 t/h at 96 percent purity. Further improvements are necessary before we release the design.

Rice whitening machine. We studied factors that affect the efficiency of rice whitening machines of the friction-jet air type. We tried various cylinder and feed screw configurations, screen types, cylinder speeds, and counter pressure levels.

We found that pitch of the feed screw and size of the feed gate opening were the major factors that affect radial pressure in the whitening chamber, the quantity and quality of milled rice, and the mechanical efficiency of the machine.

The shape of the screen that surrounds the whitening chamber had an important effect on whitening efficiency. Small protuberances on the screen significantly increased capacity and efficiency without reducing recovery of head rice and without developing excessive radial pressure.

An increase in cylinder speed from 380 to 820 rpm positively affected head rice recovery. The effect of cylinder speed on radial pressure, capacity, and machine efficiency produced contrasting results depending on the pitch of the feed screw.

Increasing the level of counter pressure

6. The oscillating grain cleaner has a cleaning capacity of 2 t/h. IRRI, 1975.

lowered the recovery of head rice and increased radial pressure, capacity, and machine efficiency at cylinder speeds of from 380 to 820 rpm.

We developed an empirical characteristics curve that shows the relationship of head rice recovery and machine capacity to internal radial pressure.

Engleberg rice mill. Work is continuing on the improvement of the performance of the Engleberg steel huller rice mills widely used in rural areas of South and Southeast Asia. We incorporated a number of changes into the mills and evaluated the performance of each. We are testing an adjustable weight-loaded gate that improves milling and quality and does not require repeated adjustment.

Rubber blades are being evaluated in place of steel blades, and work is underway to find a better arrangement to adjust paddy being fed into the machine.

The Engleberg-type mill hulls and polishes paddy in one pass. We are attempting to mount a centrifugal huller with a hull separator on top of the Engleberg machine so that hulling and polishing can be done separately. Previous studies indicate that using the Engleberg mill only as a polisher can considerably improve milling performance.

7. The experimental parboiling machine eliminates sand as a medium of heat transfer. IRRI, 1975.

Parboiling machine. Paddy is satisfactorily parboiled with the heated-sand continuous-flow parboiling machine, but some white belly is retained. The process involves soaking paddy in water at ambient temperature and flash-heating paddy by mixing it with hot sand at 200°C for 15–24 s. The flash-heating gelatinizes starch granules and simultaneously dries paddy. This rapid method offers many advantages in countries where parboiling is popular, but the thermal efficiency is low because heat must pass through a steel pan to heat the sand.

We are developing a parboiling machine

that eliminates sand as a medium of heat transfer (fig. 7). In this experimental machine, a screw feeder meters steeped paddy into a slowly rotating cylinder where it is flash-heated by tumbling for a short period in a stream of hot gases. We expect thermal efficiency to be higher since paddy will be directly heated from the hot gas without an intermediate medium for heat transfer.

MECHANIZATION RESEARCH

Agricultural Engineering Department

Through mechanization research, we are investigating machine utilization and testing design prototypes. Machinery utilization studies provide information to help select new projects for machinery development.

A project to study the long-term effects of different tillage practices on depth of soil-compaction layers in continuously cropped wetland fields was initiated in 1973. One field of Maahas clay soil on the IRRI farm was divided into four plots, and soil compaction layers were recorded at two cone penetrometer readings of 2.46 and 4.92 kg/sq cm.

The land preparation systems used were:

8. Effect of tillage practices on depth of compacted soil layer. IRRI, 1975.

Table 1. Almost 14,000 IRRI-designed machines were commercially produced in eight nations^a in 1975.

Country	Manufacturers (no.)	Machines (no.)				
		5- to 7-hp tiller	Axial flow thresher	Batch dryer	Power weeder	Multihopper seeder
Ghana	1	—	15	—	—	—
India	1	—	60	—	—	—
Japan	3	—	—	—	11,000	—
Pakistan	1	—	2	—	—	—
Philippines	14	2,178	275	33	—	56
Sri Lanka	2	60	—	—	—	—
Taiwan	1	—	—	200	—	—
Thailand	3	69	10	—	—	—
Total	26	2,307	362	233	11,000	56

^aDoes not include preproduction prototype machines produced by companies in India, Indonesia, Thailand, Guyana, Colombia, Ecuador, Philippines, Bangladesh, Malaysia, Egypt, and Sri Lanka.

40-hp four-wheel tractor and rototiller; 10-hp walking tractor and rototiller; 7-hp walking tractor and plow and comb harrow; and carabao and plow and comb harrow.

Figure 8 shows that the depth of the compaction layer has not yet stabilized in any tillage system after five cropping seasons, although some stabilization occurs during the dry seasons. The deepening of the compacted layer is much more pronounced in the plot where the four-wheel tractor is used than where the walking tractor is used. During land preparation for the fifth cropping season, the four-wheel tractor bogged for the first time. The study will continue for at least two more cropping seasons. Crops 1, 3, and 5 were grown during the wet season, and crops 2 and 4 were dry season crops.

INDUSTRIAL EXTENSION PROGRAM *Agricultural Engineering Department*

A new industrial extension project was initiated in 1975, with funding from the United States Agency for International Development (USAID). The purpose is to extend IRRI designs and provide liaison between IRRI design staff and collaborating manufacturers,

institutions, and governmental organizations.

The project will be staffed by teams, each consisting of an industrial extension engineer and support staff, in Pakistan, Philippines, and Thailand. Staff recruitment was about 50 percent complete at the end of 1975.

Each team will initially provide technical assistance to manufacturers in the host country and then gradually expand its area of activity to neighboring countries. The Philippine team will coordinate the activities of the teams.

The number of IRRI-designed machines produced in 1975 was 13,978, an increase of 39 percent over 1974. Most machines are being produced in the Philippines, Thailand, and Japan (Table 1). Interest in IRRI-designed machines was strongest in the Philippines, India, and Malaysia; 109 of 227 new inquiries received in 1975 came from these three countries. We sent 218 sets of drawings to manufacturers and institutions who had expressed an interest in evaluating IRRI-designed machines.

We surveyed manufacturers in 11 countries to determine the availability of machine components and production processes. IRRI engineers used this information to assist them in designing machines that can be constructed with locally available components and processes.

Post-Production Technology and Management of Rice

Agricultural Engineering Department

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SUMMARY

To evaluate the use of improved techniques, systems, and management in the rice post-production industry, we inventoried the nature and characteristics of practices used by farmers and rice millers in the Philippines. We found that farmers recognize threshing and drying as priority operations and that proper timing is essential to avoid the risk of loss from unfavorable weather and inadequate labor. But timing is difficult when using traditional techniques. Further, the lack of suitable price and quality incentives makes proper drying unprofitable to individual farmers.

Farmers considered location and ability to handle small lots as important factors in selecting rice mills, particularly for household consumption. We found that little grain was held for speculative purposes, largely because of inadequate storage facilities and an almost universal post-harvest demand for cash to liquidate debts.

Rice millers with small steel hullers were found at widely dispersed locations. They milled rice almost exclusively for household requirements, and performed no storage, trading, or credit functions. Milling was generally a family business to supplement earnings from farming or related occupations. In contrast, millers with

the larger disc-cono units mill primarily for commercial markets and usually store, transport, wholesale, or retail rice. Both mill types are underutilized; actual capacity average 64 percent of rated capacity.

Pilot trials were implemented in three villages to test the farm-level efficiencies of alternate techniques and systems of harvesting, handling, threshing, and drying. We found that improved techniques can substantially improve the quantity and quality of milled rice. More efficient and timely operations increased post-harvest yields by as much as 16 percent, and significantly improved head rice yields.

FARM-LEVEL POST-PRODUCTION SYSTEMS *Agricultural Engineering Department*

We surveyed 591 Filipino rice farmers in 1974 to examine commonly used practices, to identify constraints in field-level systems, and to analyze patterns of demand for alternate milling services.

Harvest. Rice farmers in Central and Southern Luzon and in Camarines Sur province continue to use traditional methods for most post-harvest operations. They harvest grain with a scythe or sickle and then lay the stalks loosely on the ground or bundle and stack them to facilitate field drying. The duration of field drying depends on the season, weather condi-

1. Time of harvest in relation to crop maturity on 591 farms. Central and Southern Luzon and Camarines Sur province, Philippines, 1974.

2. Method of threshing on 591 farms, Central and Southern Luzon and Camarines Sur province, Philippines, 1974.

3. Methods of drying paddy in three regions of the Philippines, 1974.

tions, local customs, and threshing methods.

Most farmers tried to harvest at or near the prescribed maturity dates of the varieties, although 35 percent harvested too late and 7 percent harvested too early (fig. 1). Most who harvested late said that rainy weather or inadequate labor, or both, caused the delay.

Threshing. The most common methods of threshing were the manual methods and those using animals (fig. 2). About 25 percent of the farmers used mechanical threshing; most were in Central Luzon where large stationary thresher machines have been used for many years. More of the wet-season than of the dry-season crop was mechanically threshed because farmers harvested the dry-season crop at the beginning of the monsoon rains, when mechanized equipment is difficult to move through the wet fields. The mechanical thresher also adequately cleans the crop, but farmers who use manual methods must clean the grain by hand.

Drying. Solar drying was the most common drying method practiced by farmers in all regions (fig. 3). One method was to leave harvested paddy in the field to dry for several days in loose bundles or small stacks. Another was to sun-dry high-moisture grain immediately after threshing on surfaces, such as concrete pavement, mats, plastic sheets, or canvas.

Storage. Farmers stored paddy for home consumption in sacks, metal or wooden boxes, bamboo baskets, cans or drums, or in bulk form

in their houses (Table 1). They stored paddy to be sold in their homes or in a warehouse. The marketable surplus was often sold immediately after harvest. Only 19 percent of all farmers stored paddy in a mill warehouse (21 percent in Central Luzon, 22 percent in Southern Luzon, and 14 percent in Camarines Sur).

Disposal. Half of the 743 farmers who sold paddy during 1974 sold it immediately after threshing; 30 percent delayed sale; and 20 percent sold or held paddy, depending on prices. Farmers usually sold paddy immediately after threshing because of an immediate need for cash (Table 2). But farmers who delayed selling their threshed paddy were usually speculating on higher prices.

Pricing. Farmers reported a price differential as well as a difference in weight between dry and wet paddy at the time of sale. The average price margin between dry and wet paddy ranged from ₱0.02 (\$0.03) to ₱0.25 (\$0.36) per kilogram, although farmers reported margins as high as ₱0.70 (\$0.10)/kg (Table 3). On a per-sack basis, the average price margin ranged from ₱1.00 (\$0.14) to ₱4.00 (\$0.56), with one farmer reporting a mark-up of ₱13.00 (\$1.86) per sack. In spite of the price and weight incentives, only 39 percent of 591 farmers dried their paddy during the wet season, and 39 percent in the dry season (Table 4).

The immediate need for cash was cited as a major reason for not drying paddy by 17 percent

Table 1. Methods used by 591 farmers to store paddy for home consumption and market sale. Philippines, 1973-74.

Type of storage	Farmers (%)							
	For home use				For sale			
	Central Luzon	Southern Luzon	Camarines Sur	Av.	Central Luzon	Southern Luzon	Camarines Sur	Av.
Sack	38	58	59	52	74	74	84	78
Box	30	8	30	30	12	6	10	9
Bamboo basket	25	17	9	17	—	8	—	3
Woven basket	—	7	—	2	10	2	5	6
Small granary	4	2	1	3	2	3	1	2
Bulk	1	8	1	3	1	7	—	2
Cans and drums	2	—	—	1	1	—	—	^a

^aLess than 1 percent.

Table 2. Reasons cited by 433 farmers who traded paddy for immediately selling or delaying sale of paddy. Philippines, 1973-74.

Reason	Farmers (%) reporting in				
	Central Luzon	Southern Luzon	Camarines Sur	Av.	
		<i>Immediate sale</i>			
Need cash	70	60	64	64	
Lack incentive	6	15	26	18	
Paddy ready	15	14	4	10	
Lack facilities	8	2	4	5	
Direct buying	1	6	1	2	
Common practice	—	3	1	1	
		<i>Delayed sale</i>			
Price speculation	62	43	24	45	
Paddy not ready	17	31	12	22	
Sell milled rice	11	13	54	22	
Required by buyer	—	13	10	8	
Paddy retained for emergency	10	—	—	3	

Table 3. Comparative weight and price differentials between dry and wet paddy reported by 433 farmers who traded paddy. Philippines, 1973-74.

Item	Farmers (%) reporting in				
	Central Luzon	Southern Luzon	Camarines Sur	Av.	
<i>Price differential</i>					
(\$/kg)					
(P/kg)					
\$0.003-\$0.036	(P0.02-P0.25)	91	75	93	90
\$0.037-0.07	(0.26-0.50)	6	25	7	8
\$0.073-0.10	(0.51-0.70)	3	—	3	2
Subtotal		34	9	24	26
<i>Price differential</i>					
(\$/sack)					
(P/sack)					
\$0.14-\$0.29	(P 1.00-P 2.00)	22	38	29	30
\$0.43-0.57	(3.00-4.00)	45	22	33	33
\$0.71-0.86	(5.00-6.00)	29	31	25	29
\$1.43-1.86	(10.00-13.00)	4	9	13	8
Subtotal		29	75	40	42
<i>Weight differential (kg/sack)</i>					
2		7	29	35	20
3		4	29	24	14
4		70	—	12	41
5		19	42	29	25
Subtotal		29	16	29	26
<i>Combination weight and price differential</i>					
Subtotal		8	—	7	6
Total		100	100	100	100

Table 4. Reasons cited for drying by 433 rice farmers who traded paddy. Philippines, 1973-74.

Item	Farmers (%) reporting in			Av.
	Central Luzon	Southern Luzon	Camarines Sur	
<i>Wet season</i>				
Farmers who sell paddy	97	100	100	99
Farmers who dry paddy	47	47	23	39
<i>Dry season</i>				
Farmers who sell paddy	50	79	89	72
Farmers who dry paddy	53	49	23	39
<i>Reasons for drying paddy^a</i>				
Price/weight differential	34	25	15	24
Required by buyer	4	7	2	4
Avoid deterioration	5	4	3	4
Combination of the above	8	12	2	7
Subtotal	51	48	22	39
<i>Reasons for not drying paddy^a</i>				
Need for cash	10	13	26	17
Paddy field-dried	32	15	2	15
Buyer does not require	6	18	17	14
Wet paddy heavier	1	3	31	13
Absence of dryer in the area	0	1	1	1
Other reasons	0	2	1	1
Subtotal	49	52	78	61
Total	100	100	100	100

^aRefers only to paddy intended for market sale.

of the farmers. Most had already committed their produce before harvest to landlords or to paddy traders for cash advances.

Harvesting and drying were indicated as the two major post-production problems by 60 percent of the farmers (fig. 4).

Unfavorable weather was the most commonly reported harvest problem. Delays in harvest because of poor weather resulted in quantitative and qualitative losses from lodging, shattering, rotting, discoloration, and grain sprouting. The

scarcity of labor aggravated these losses, especially during the peak harvest months. The total potential harvest was also reduced by pilferage and by pests, such as birds, insects, and rats.

Unfavorable or unpredictable weather was a major problem in drying operations. This was expected since most farmers dry by solar energy. In Southern Luzon and Camarines Sur, drying was reported as the most serious constraint.

Central Luzon farmers considered cleaning a minor problem, since they thresh and clean with

4. Post-harvest problems cited by 591 farmers. Philippines, 1974.

Table 5. Criteria cited by 591 rice farmers in choosing mill types for processing paddy. Philippines, 1973-74.

Criteria	Farmers (%) reporting in			
	Central Luzon	Southern Luzon	Camarines Sur	Av.
Availability and accessibility	42	44	36	41
Type of product required ^a	23	9	11	15
High milling recovery ^b	14	7	20	14
Attachment to the mill	10	18	9	12
Accepts small quantities	5	5	17	9
Privileges and discounts	1	7	1	3
Only mill available	1	3	3	3
Good public relations	1	1	1	1
Cooperative member	1	2	1	1
High moisture content, more paddy, different milling degrees	—	3	—	1
Others	2	1	1	c

^aIncludes increased rice, increased bran, etc. ^bRefers to high head rice recovery, fewer broken grains, and good-quality bran. ^cLess than 1 percent.

mechanical threshers. Farmers in Camarines Sur cited weather as a major deterrent, since most winnow with baskets.

Farmers were asked which of the two most common types of milling facilities they preferred, the steel huller (Engleberg mill) or the disc-cono mill. The responses indicated that a large number of factors condition preference, with a clear distinction between milling for home consumption and milling for market sale. Mill users considered accessibility and availability of the mill as their main criteria for the choice of mill type (Table 5).

Millers who preferred disc-cono units expected to obtain higher milling recoveries than with steel huller units. Conversely, those who used the huller mills identified the composition of output as a reason for their choice. While more grains were broken and less milled rice was recovered with the huller units, the by-products of broken rice, mixed husks, and bran were considered important for livestock feed.

Sixty-nine percent of the sample farmers used more than one type of mill. The highest percentage of dual users was in Central Luzon (81 percent); the lowest was in Camarines Sur (60 percent). The higher use of disc-cono mills in Central Luzon may be partially explained by the greater commercial orientation of rice farmers there. In almost all cases, farmers who milled only small quantities of paddy for home consumption used the steel hullers; paddy to be sold was processed in the larger disc-conos.

POST-PRODUCTION SYSTEMS AT MILL LEVEL

Agricultural Engineering Department

We surveyed owners of rice mills in the same area as that of the farm survey to determine the financial and economic elements of mill ownership and operation. The specific study objectives were to determine the performance of specific types and capacities of mills, and to identify the physical and economic factors that affect mill performance.

The 187 rice mills surveyed in Central Luzon, Southern Luzon, and Camarines Sur were stratified according to type (disc-cono or steel huller) and to the rated milling capacity per 12 hours of operation. We stratified disc-cono units into three output levels: 4.5 t/day and less; 5.0-8.5 t/day; and 9.0 t/day and more. We also segregated steel hullers into 2.0 t/day and less; 3.0-4.0 t/day; and 5.0 t/day and more. Included were 96 steel-huller mills used for village-level processing, principally for home consumption, and 91 disc-cono mills.

Most mills were owned by individuals (Table 6); the remainder, by partnerships or corporations. Diesel engines powered 88 percent of the mills and electricity only 12 percent.

Disc-cono mills are usually found in towns and market centers away from the sources of paddy, while huller mills are usually in rural areas near the paddy.

Only 34 percent of the mills had drying

Table 6. General information on 187 rice mills. Philippines, 1973-74.

Item	Mill types (%)		
	Disc-cono	Steel huller	Av.
<i>Type of ownership:</i>			
Individual proprietorship	88	96	92
Partnership	2	2	2
Corporation	6	2	4
Leased	4	—	2
<i>Fuel:</i>			
Diesel	78	98	88
Electric	22	2	12
<i>Distance from main road (km):</i>			
Roadside	91	75	83
2.9 and less	9	18	14
3.0-6.0	—	6	3
6.1 and more	—	1	^a
<i>Distance to source (km):</i>			
Within town or barrio	2	7	5
2.9 and less	36	76	56
3.1-6.0	36	15	25
6.1 and more	26	2	14
<i>Distance to market outlet (km):</i>			
Within town or barrio	6	—	5
3.0 and less	20	56	24
4.0-9.0	28	33	27
10.0-15.0	12	11	12
16.0 and more	34	—	32

^aLess than 1 percent.

facilities, which usually consisted of concrete pavement at the mill house for sun-drying. Only two mills had continuous-flow dryers. Most dryers were owned by disc-cono mills, and only 9 percent by Engleberg operators.

Disc-cono mills had higher drying capacities than huller mills (6.8 t versus 1.7 t) because the owners traded in paddy or rice, or both. Most of the paddy that was dried at disc-cono mills was owned by the mill owner and a few cus-

tomers, who either paid a fee or used the dryer without charge provided that they milled the paddy there. Huller mills seldom did custom drying because most paddy brought for milling had already been sun-dried.

Only 44 percent of the mills had storage facilities. Most were disc-cono units, with storage within or adjoining the mill houses. Paddy or milled rice stored in these warehouses was owned by either the miller or customers engaged in trading. Thirty-four percent of the disc-cono warehouses were bonded.

Only 12 percent of the steel huller operations had warehouses; none were bonded, since owners generally milled on a job-lot basis.

Fifty-six percent of the mills did not charge for shrinkage if the paddy deposited was milled internally. But once the deposit was withdrawn, a shrinkage allowance of from 1 to 2 kg paddy/sack was deducted.

Storage fees were paid under a similar arrangement. Forty-seven percent of the mills accepted deposits free if the paddy was processed in the mill. Once withdrawn, a storage fee was charged, ranging from ₱0.20 (\$.03) to as high as ₱2.00 (\$0.29) per sack of paddy.

Of 82 rice mills with warehouses, only two reported full utilization of storage facilities.

Irregularity of paddy supply accounted for 42 percent of warehouse underutilization (Table 7). This clearly indicates peak and slack months of storage. Fourteen percent of the millers claimed that their warehouses were underutilized because they used them solely for their

Table 7. Reasons cited by 187 rice mill owners for underutilization of storage capacity. Philippines, 1973-74.

Reason for underutilization ^a	Mill owners (%) reporting in			
	Central Luzon	Southern Luzon	Camarines Sur	Av.
Irregularity of supply	33	57	43	42
Limited storage space	23	7	9	14
Mill does not provide storage services	7	15	9	10
Inadequate capital to purchase paddy	7	—	15	8
Customers too demanding	13	—	6	7
Competition with other warehouses	—	—	18	6
Strict government regulations	7	—	—	3
Bulk storage only	7	—	—	3
Warehouse not bonded	—	7	—	2
Mill does not provide sacks	—	7	—	2
No trucks for hauling paddy	—	7	—	2
Warehouse not usable	3	—	—	1

^aNinety-six percent of the storage capacity of the rice mills surveyed in Central and Southern Luzon reported underutilization. In Camarines Sur, all the storage facilities were underutilized.

Table 8. Milling practices cited by 187 rice mill owners. Philippines, 1973-74.

Item	Mill types (%)		
	Disc-cono	Steel huller	Av.
<i>Type of user:</i>			
Farmer	51	99	75
Landlord	2	—	1
Retailer/wholesaler	32	—	16
Rice buyer	2	—	1
Harvester/thresher	2	1	2
Mill owner	11	—	5
<i>Mills mixed varieties:</i>			
Yes	28	52	43
No	72	48	57
Performs multipass milling	17	12	14
<i>Reports percent milling recovery:</i>			
By weight	64	57	61
By volume	53	46	49

own stocks. Others complained that depositors required larger storage areas to avoid mixing their stocks with others.

Disc-cono mills generally catered to traders and commercial farmers. Most customers at huller mills were small farmers who milled paddy for home consumption (Table 8).

Sixty-four percent of the disc-cono mills measured milling recovery by weight, and the remaining 36 percent by volume. But recovery at huller mills was usually measured by volume.

With huller mills, a single sack of paddy could be milled; sometimes, a fourth of a sack was adequate. The smallest lot required for operation of disc-cono mills ranged from 3 to 300 sacks, depending on size and complexity.

Milling recovery by weight and by volume

Table 9. Average milling capacity and percent utilization reported by 187 rice mill owners. Philippines, 1973-74.

Capacity specification of mill (kg/h)	Milling capacity (kg/h)		Utilization (%)
	Rated ^a	Actual ^b	
<i>Disc-cono</i>			
403 and less	291	215	74
404-732	519	420	81
733 and more	1147	896	78
Av.	656	515	79
<i>Steel huller</i>			
220 and less	178	100	56
221-328	269	127	47
329 and more	441	212	48
Av.	294	146	50

^aRefers to the manufacturer's volume specification for the milling machinery. ^bRefers to the maximum quantity of paddy that is actually milled.

was higher for disc-cono mills than for huller mills. Disc-cono mills reported a milling recovery of 64 percent by weight and 53 percent by volume. In contrast, the huller mills recovered 57 percent by weight and 46 percent by volume.

The average rated milling capacity of disc-cono mills was 656 kg/h, of which only 79 percent was actually used (Table 9). The average rated capacity of steel huller mills was 294 kg/h; actual milling capacity was 146 kg/h, or 50 percent utilization.

In spite of the higher degree of utilization of disc-cono mills, only 19 of 92 mills reported full utilization. For steel huller mills, only nine of 95 reported full utilization.

Inadequate paddy accounted for 40 percent of the underutilization. The problem was aggravated by an overconcentration of mills in some areas, resulting in intense competition. Twenty-seven percent of the mill owners claimed that their mills were in such poor condition that the manufacturers' capacity specifications could not be met. The rated capacity was also difficult to estimate, so the possibility for error was considerable.

Ninety-five percent of the millers reported mill operation problems of four types: financial and technical, operational, organizational, and policy.

Sixty-eight percent were financial and technical problems, including high cost, mill durability, and availability of parts in case the mills broke down. Paddy of poor quality affected milling outturn and quality.

Operational and customer problems accounted for 23 percent of the total. Of these, the lack of paddy was ranked most important. An increase in the number of mills in the area aggravated this problem.

The imposition of ceiling and floor prices on milled rice and paddy have had serious repercussions in the milling industry. Most disc-cono millers interviewed felt that economic operation was extremely difficult because of the low profit margins due to these pricing constraints, coupled with the underutilization of milling capacity. The steel huller units were affected less because millers often take payment in kind or in by-products.

5. Alternate post-production systems at the farm level. Philippines, 1975.

VILLAGE-LEVEL PILOT TRIALS

Agricultural Engineering Department

We used results from the farm-level survey to identify constraints in traditional systems and to plan and implement controlled field trials in three villages in Nueva Ecija province, Philippines. Five alternate post-production systems were used (fig. 5). The objectives of these pilot trials were to measure the quantitative and qualitative losses at each stage of the systems; to compare the benefits from improvements in elements of each system; and to evaluate and compare the overall technical and economic performance of each system. The trials focused on threshing and drying, which farmers identified as priority problems.

Trials were initiated during the 1975 dry-season harvest and continued through the wet season. From four to six farmer-members of the village cooperative at each site were chosen to participate (Table 10). Each farmer agreed to provide enough paddy to meet the needs of

each system. The cooperative purchased and operated the improved threshing and drying equipment used in the trials (fig. 6), kept records, and acted as marketing agent.

To obtain potential grain yield, crop cuts were taken from each plot. To obtain actual area yields, the plots were measured and grain from each plot was weighed following threshing and drying. All yield and weight measurements were corrected for moisture content and impurities. To determine quality of paddy, 200-g samples were taken following each operation in each system and later dried, milled, and analyzed in the laboratory. Records were also kept on labor employed in each operation within each system, costs to perform each operation, and time required to complete the entire sequence of operations.

Table 11 illustrates the relationship between time lapses from harvesting through drying and grain yield. In general, grain losses increase with increases in time after harvest that the grain remains unthreshed or undried, or both. More

6. Axial flow thresher used in village-level trials. Central Luzon, Philippines, 1975.

significant, however, are the yield differences between traditional systems and those that used one or more improved techniques for threshing and drying. Using a dryer in system II increased grain yield by 12 percent over system I (Table 11). Similar increases in yield were found in system III; however, with the use of the mechanical thresher, threshing yield increased by 10 percent over system I and II. System IV, which employed both the thresher and dryer in sequence, had the highest output. Variability was high in the observations from each system, largely because of failure to control all variables that affected the performance of the systems. Rain after harvest but before threshing often damaged grain that was stacked or bundled in

Table 10. Characteristics of three villages used as sites in post-production pilot trials. Nueva Ecija, Philippines, 1975-76.

Location	Season	Cooperators (no.)	Plots (no.)	Area (sq m/plot)	Yield ^a (t/ha)	Rices used
Soledad, Santa Rosa	Wet	5	80	771.4	3.3	IR20 IR26 IR1529 IR1561
Malapit, San Isidro	Wet	6	46	1423.2	3.6	IR26 IR30 IR579 IR1529 IR1561
Polilio, Cabanatuan	Dry	4	42	1242.3	3.1	IR26 IR30 C4-63G
Total/av.		15	168	1081.3	3.3	

^aFinal paddy weight after drying and adjusting for purity at 14% moisture content.

Table 11. Relationship among time from harvesting through drying, grain loss, and yield per hectare by alternate post-production systems. Philippines, 1975.

	System			
	I Manual threshing and solar drying	II Manual threshing and mechanical drying	III Mechanical threshing and solar drying	IV Mechanical threshing and drying
		<i>Time lapse (days)</i>		
Harvesting to threshing	1	1	0	0
Threshing to drying	1	0	2	2
Harvesting to drying	4	1	2	2
		<i>Grain loss (%)</i>		
Harvesting to threshing	11.0	11.8	1.7	2.5
Threshing to drying	15.3	1.2	11.4	8.2
Harvesting to drying	24.6	12.9	12.9	10.5
		<i>Grain yield (t/ha)</i>		
Harvesting	3.3	4.1	4.9	3.9
Threshing	2.9	3.6	4.8	3.8
Drying	2.5	3.5	4.2	3.5

Table 12. Quality characteristics of milled rice from alternate post-production systems. Sixteen plots, Philippines, 1975.

System	Quality characteristic (%)			
	Head rice	Broken rice	Milling recovery	
			Brown rice	Milled rice
Manual threshing and solar drying	77.4	20.2	63.0	59.3
Manual threshing and mechanical drying	84.5	14.1	67.4	63.4
Mechanical threshing and solar drying	90.6	8.8	70.5	65.6
Mechanical threshing and drying	89.9	9.2	68.4	64.4

Table 13. Labor requirements and labor productivity using alternate post-production systems. Philippines, 1975-76.

Yield ^a (t/ha)	Labor requirement (h/ha)				Labor productivity		
	Harvesting ^b	Threshing	Drying	Total	(kg/h)	(\$/h ^c)	
3.3	138.6	<i>System I Manual threshing and solar drying</i>				10.0	1.4
		131.4	21.7	291.7			
3.3	144.4	<i>System II Manual threshing and mechanical drying</i>				10.0	1.4
		132.0	10.5	286.9			
3.6	135.6	<i>System III Mechanical threshing and solar drying</i>				18.8	2.7
		30.2	23.9	189.7			
3.6	141.7	<i>System IV Mechanical threshing and drying</i>				19.1	2.7
		37.7	9.8	189.2			

^aBased on the final dry weight of paddy adjusted for purity and 14% moisture content. ^bIncludes cutting, bundling, hauling, and stacking of paddy that is ready for threshing. ^cPaddy is valued at P1/kg (\$0.14/kg).

the field. Subsequent operations could do little to rectify these effects. Better scheduling of operations for all systems would have reduced losses by cutting the time interval between harvesting and drying. We will further analyze these effects in continued operation of the pilot trials in 1976.

Table 12 shows differences in the quality of grain from each system. Although using the improved systems increased only slightly the overall recovery of milled rice, the percentage of broken, fermented, discolored, and immature grains was significantly reduced, particularly where the grain dryer was used. An inverse relationship was also observed between the time that elapsed between harvesting and final drying and the percentage of head rice recovery.

As expected, labor inputs were reduced most with the introduction of the mechanical thresher (Table 13). Use of the batch dryer had little effect because the manpower requirements were not greatly different from those of traditional solar drying. Using both the thresher and a dryer reduced total labor requirements to less than those of a traditional system. However,

the productivity of labor, expressed in kilograms per man-hour, or in dollars per man-hour, increased more than proportionally to the decrease because yields were higher with the improved systems.

Increased yields from using improved techniques and the effect on post-production requirements for labor bear directly on the importance of timeliness in post-production operations. Delay at any point in this sequence of operations increases losses regardless of the techniques used. This issue is important under a single-cropping pattern, particularly during the wet-season harvest. But it becomes even more critical as cropping systems are intensified. In intensified cropping, not only the post-production system but also the land preparation and planting operations for subsequent crops act as a constraint.

Table 14 is a series of cost estimates depicting the relative expense of each system, based on observed labor, fuel, and fixed investment requirements. These are expressed in dollars per ton of output to incorporate the loss differentials between alternate systems. We did not attempt

Table 14. Cost estimates in alternate post-production systems. Philippines, 1975-76.

Item	Cost estimate (\$/t)			
	System I Manual threshing and solar drying	System II Manual threshing and mechanical drying	System III Mechanical threshing and solar drying	System IV Mechanical threshing and drying
<i>Harvesting expense</i>				
Cash ^a			—	—
Non-cash ^b			6.14	6.14
Subtotal			6.14	6.14
<i>Threshing expense</i>				
	23.81 ^c	23.81 ^c		
Cash			1.86	1.86
Non-cash			1.43	1.43
Subtotal			3.29	3.29
<i>Drying expense</i>				
Cash	—	3.97	—	3.97
Non-cash	1.00	0.43	1.00	0.43
Subtotal	1.00	4.40	1.00	4.40
<i>Total post-production expense</i>				
Cash	—	3.97	1.86	5.83
Non-cash	24.81	24.24	8.57	8.00
Total	24.81	28.21	10.43	13.83

^aOperating and maintenance and depreciation expenses. ^bLabor cost, usually paid in kind. ^cUsing traditional methods, harvesting and threshing labor is usually paid on a contract basis at the rate of $\frac{1}{4}$ of the gross harvest.

to ascribe increased value to improvements in the quality that resulted from use of the mechanical system, although this would accentuate the differences.

While overall cash costs increased using the improved systems, the cost per ton decreased. The mechanical thresher gave the greatest economic return over traditional systems. When used independently, the batch dryer increased per-unit costs. Threshing costs are particularly sensitive to the wage rate ascribed to labor in

this operation. The cost for joint use of improved threshing and drying techniques was slightly higher than for mechanical threshing alone.

This series of trials indicates that improved mechanical technologies have a quantitative impact on output and grain quality, through more timely operations and reduced unit costs. The value of qualitative changes is not important unless price differentials for different grades of rice are recognized in the market and by rice millers.

Cropping systems program

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The program's research activities in cropping pattern evaluation, cropping systems economics, weed science, plant protection, and varietal evaluation further increased our ability to fit together technological components required for the adequate management of cropping patterns, while taking into account limitations set by the resource mix of the farmers at the site. The program also increased its capacity to specify the domain of adaptation of its designed cropping patterns in terms of site variables such as soil, climate, landscape, and the availability of labor and power.

CROPPING PATTERN MANAGEMENT AND AGRONOMY

Traditional cropping patterns used by many cooperating farmers continued to be studied, and feasible improvements such as intercropping patterns, residual interactions of crops in sequence, and management techniques for intensive patterns using farmer resources, were investigated. Cropping pattern production services to the various disciplinary teams in the cropping systems program increased markedly as the multiple cropping section provided experience in cropping pattern production in farmers' fields to allow weed control, entomological, and other studies.

Two additional sites were established to test the concepts of pattern design (based primarily on rainfall and soil texture) developed in the program, and to provide a test capability in lowland rainfed areas. Conceptually, the program shifted gradually from gaining expertise and know-how in cropping patterns and their productivity to seeking an understanding of where and under what conditions the cropping patterns would fit.

Intercropping. The common upland rice intercropping patterns are 30 to 40 percent more productive than monoculture when growing conditions are favorable, because the higher photosynthetic efficiency of corn during the early weeks of growth combines with the high efficiency of rice late in the growing season. Corn in intercrop combinations at wide spacing has a low incidence of both corn borer and downy

mildew, the two most important problems of corn in Asia. Nutrient uptake is more efficient under some conditions. Labor utilization is more efficient in long-duration intercrops if power is not available.

Crop interaction. The reluctance of farmers to plant legumes in sequence was justified repeatedly. A 20- to 40-percent yield reduction resulted from mung beans following mung beans, but no yield reduction was observed when other crops followed mung beans.

Cropping pattern potential. Although in upland rice areas, a wide range of crops can be worked around rice, grain sorghum and corn give the greatest economic returns where high-value crops have a limited market. In rainfed lowland rice areas where soil problems are not limiting and there are 5 months or more of rainfall, as in many rainfed areas, two crops of direct-seeded early-maturing varieties are possible. Cooperating farmers at the Iloilo, Philippines, site obtained yields that averaged from 7.0 to 10.2 t/ha for the two rice crops; these yields compared favorably with the local averages of 2 to 4 t/ha.

Soil conditions can restrict cropping potential; for example, calcareous soils in Pangasinan, Philippines, virtually eliminated the first crop of direct-seeded upland rice because of iron deficiency during seed establishment. Zinc deficiency occurred in the second crop of transplanted rice and the third crop of corn. Under rainfed conditions for the second rice crop, early-maturing rice varieties appeared to give better yields when direct seeded than when transplanted. Early-maturing rice varieties should be transplanted only in paddies where good water control is assured, to allow timely transplanting.

The cropping pattern must accommodate normal fluctuations in weather. Thus, a flexible approach is needed in both the basic design of the patterns and the techniques required for implementing them. When supplemental irrigation is a part of the cooperator's resources, it should be included in the cropping pattern design. In addition to climate and soil type, the position of the field or paddy in the landscape and the chemical conditions of the soil are

important factors in determining the most suitable intensive cropping pattern.

ECONOMICS OF CROPPING SYSTEMS

The economics of both existing systems and experimental patterns are studied. Present cropping patterns, farm resources, and the technology which links them are examined in order to: 1) recommend characteristics with respect to resource use which new patterns should have to be acceptable to farmers, 2) ascertain the benefits which farmers receive from present cropping patterns so that, by comparison, new patterns can be tested, 3) identify previously unknown biological and economic principles followed by farmers which might be more widely applied, and 4) obtain baseline information from which to later evaluate the impact of cropping systems research.

Analysis of experimental cropping patterns in Batangas, Philippines, indicated the profitability of two new patterns: rice followed by sweet potato-and-corn intercrop, and rice followed by sorghum. A study of major inputs into six existing cropping systems revealed that the highest marginal return to labor occurred in systems having the highest variation in weekly labor usage. Weekly cash flows indicated critical financial linkages among crop, livestock, and household sectors, which must be considered in designing new cropping patterns. Farmers' water control practices under rainfed conditions were identified as an important determinant of the cropping patterns on their fields. Farmers appeared to consistently overestimate land area and labor time from 5 to 10 percent.

The solutions to the problems related to economic institutions arising from the new multiple cropping technology were found to be unique to the locales where the technology was adopted. For example, marketing of new crops was identified as one such problem. However, such phenomena are outside the present area of research, which focuses on problems whose solutions have broad application. A general methodology for finding solutions to these site-specific problems is being formulated; it includes the development of methods for assessing the

effect of off-farm conditions upon the economic viability of cropping patterns.

PEST MANAGEMENT

The major and minor diseases and insect pests of rice, corn, and mung beans were determined in different cropping patterns. Yield losses caused by prevailing pest infestations were estimated for corn and mung beans, and economic threshold levels for control measures (use and frequency of use of insecticides and fungicides) were determined.

Fewer pest problems occurred when corn was seeded after rice than when corn was seeded before rice. Major infestations of corn borer could be avoided by using early-maturing corn varieties. Pest problems were fewer in early-season plantings of mung beans than in late-season plantings.

A low dosage of soil insecticide applied during the weeding of the rice crop before canopy closure provided the most efficient method for controlling white grubs in the upland rice-corn cropping pattern. A multitude of cropping patterns require study; hence we need to determine the most efficient experimental designs to maximize the information that can be obtained concurrently by the various disciplines of the cropping systems program team. Designs were developed and tested to identify site variables that determine the occurrence of key pests, to estimate yield losses from these pests, and to formulate the cost-to-benefit ratios of various control measures.

Apparently the farmer needs to know when the pests reach a level economically detrimental to his crop, and what his available options are once this level is reached. The researchers should provide the farmer with a set of options from which he can choose according to his management and economic ability. The complexity of pest occurrences strongly suggests that government-supported pest warning programs should be considered.

WEED SCIENCE

The integrated approach used in 1974 was

continued, taking into consideration all available methods of weed control. Major emphasis was placed on crop competition as an important and useful means of controlling the weeds that compete with crop plants. Cropping patterns, rather than individual crops, were examined to identify weed control practices that can be carried out with one crop and that can affect the weeds in a subsequent crop in a cropping sequence.

The combination of lowland crops with upland crops continued to be an important method of weed control. Reduced infestations of water-tolerant weeds in the lowland crop and of dryland weeds in the upland crop were noted. The weed control achieved with a low rate of herbicide followed by mechanical or manual weeding was as good as or superior to mechanical or chemical weed control alone. A new herbicide, MON 0358, showed excellent weed control in most of the crops (rice, corn, mung beans, cowpeas, and peanuts) considered suitable for adoption into multiple cropping programs in Asia. No herbicide was entirely satisfactory for sorghum. Varieties of crops such as mung beans and cowpeas were found to vary in their competitive ability against and capacity to suppress weeds. Yield reductions due to weeds were greater and showed more variation among cowpea varieties; differences were less obvious among mung bean varieties.

Future studies will seek to identify 1) a methodology for testing weed control techniques in multiple cropping systems, and 2) a methodology for establishing and conducting weed control trials in individual farmers' fields.

VARIETAL TESTING

Varietal testing trials for the most promising varieties and lines of cowpeas, peanuts, and sweet potatoes from the breeding program of the University of the Philippines at Los Baños (UPLB) and other country programs were

distributed to the collaborating countries starting September 1975. Most of the trials were evaluated in the test sites or at an experiment station near the test site. The others were conducted by other organizations involved in multiple cropping research.

The UPLB started varietal screening of corn, sorghum, and soybeans for specific cropping systems in December 1975; it is also evaluating the advance materials in its program in replicated trials. The most promising materials from the UPLB replicated trials will be increased in March and April 1976 to acquire seeds for the replicated yield trials in the network in September 1976. The entries will be changed every year.

CROPPING SYSTEMS NETWORK

Collaborative work in cropping systems was initiated with government agencies involved in research and production programs in several Asian countries to support the efforts of national programs to increase cropping intensities. A system is also being developed in each country to disseminate to the farmers research findings on topics ranging from research through production.

A network of test sites is being established in Asia. In 1975, six sites began operation: three in the Philippines, two in Indonesia, and one in Bangladesh. Additional test sites were identified in Thailand, Malaysia, Burma, and Sri Lanka.

The other major activity of the network is the training of research and extension personnel. In 1975, a total of 25 trainees from Indonesia, the Philippines, Thailand, Bangladesh, and Malaysia attended the 6-month training course at IRRI. Trainees are being selected for the 1976 training session; about 35 to 40 are expected to attend. In addition, about 12 candidates were identified for graduate training in different disciplines. Priority is given to candidates who are directly involved in collaborative projects and national research programs.

Cropping systems program

Upland rice cropping systems

Multiple Cropping and Soil Microbiology Departments (with the cooperation of the Economics, Weed Science, and Entomology components of the Cropping Systems Program)

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CROPPING POTENTIAL IN CALE,
BATANGAS, PHILIPPINES
Multiple Cropping Department

Since 1972, Cale has been the principal test site for IRRI's studies on upland rice-based cropping systems. After 3 years of study, a fairly complete understanding of the cropping potential of and the cropping patterns adapted to this region has been achieved. The following summary of investigations describes the agronomic performance of various crops and crop combinations in a common upland rice-growing area.

The average size of the farms of the 50 farmers who have been cooperating with the IRRI cropping systems research efforts since 1973 is 1.34 ha. About 20 percent of the farmers are sole owners of their farms; about 30 percent are part owners; the rest farm under sharing arrangements with landlords.

The net farm income for the 1974-75 crop year ranged from US\$520 to US\$707, the major portion of which came from the crop income (including value of produce consumed at home). The livestock enterprises (including home consumption) just broke even. The net farm income was supplemented by an average nonfarm income of \$192.

Each farm had an average of one ox, one pig, and 20 chickens. Draft power was produced and used on the farm. Although its value was not accounted for, it was a key factor in enabling the farmers to crop intensively.

Cale farmers use their land about 70 percent of the year, achieving a multiple cropping index of 180. About 94 percent of the cooperating farmers grow a rice-corn sequence, but many also grow vegetables for the nearby metropolitan market. Almost 60 percent raise vegetables on trellises—permanent wood, concrete, or wire structures—the year around.

The average farmer in Cale is 45 years old; both he and his wife have an average of 4 years of formal education. The average number of persons per household is about six; they supply annually an average of 22.4 months of labor. Men perform all the land-preparation tasks; afterwards, men and women share about equally in farm operations.

The topography in Cale is sloping hills with

slight terracing of fields through natural erosion, which is controlled by fence rows of trees, shrubs, and grass. The topography is typical of the other upland rice areas in the Philippines which also have a potential for animal or tractor tillage, and hence, for intensive cropping. The soil is a well-drained mollisol of volcanic deposit classified as Taal series; the texture ranges from sandy loam to clay loam. The soil pH ranges from 4.9 to 6.2, with an average of 6.0. The soil was tentatively classified as belonging to the Andeptic Hapludoll, loamy, mixed, isohyperthermic family.

Soil-associated determinants. The soil-associated determinants of the cropping pattern potential in Cale, Batangas, are described below:

- Rapid, internal water movement and a deep water table make rainfed lowland rice culture impossible.
- The occasional presence of low-lying fields, where drainage is temporarily retarded after heavy rains, reduces the potential for upland rice as well as for other upland crops; upland rice does not appear to tolerate frequent alternation between aerobic and anaerobic soil conditions. But neither are these areas sufficiently wet for lowland paddy except in the very lowest spots. Micro-relief is not a factor here as it is in lowland rice areas.
- The occasional occurrence of fields with soil having a pH below 5.5 restricts the potential for legumes, particularly mung beans.
- The relatively high tillage capability, with animal tillage possible during weeks with less than 40 to 50 mm of rain, makes intensive use of animal power possible.

Water availability. Rainfall determines the water-availability characteristics of Cale (fig. 1). From June through October the monthly average precipitation is above 200 mm; in May, November, and December, it is 100 to 200 mm, and from January through April, it is 50 mm. The three crop seasons are early, mid, and late wet season. The weekly mean rainfall in July, October, and November fluctuates markedly because of typhoons. In addition, the probability of obtaining at least as much as the mean for any given week varies during the other 9 months.

Yield potential for field crops. Yield potentials, when optimum planting dates are used and with the best available technology, are shown in Table 1. Generally the yields of farmer-managed fields were similar to those of the research fields because the farmers used the best available

technology under the supervision of research workers. With "crop potential" defined as the best yield possible with a given planting date, the actual average yields achieved were only 60 to 70 percent of crop potential. The somewhat lower yields may have been caused by insect or disease damage, poor management, planting on an incorrect date with too much or too little rain, or, as in the case of soybeans, the photoperiod response of the crop.

Results obtained in Cale, Batangas, allow the identification of the planting season of eight upland crops (fig. 1). The planting season was set at the period during which crop establishment was expected to result in a yield of at least 50 percent of that which would be obtained if the crop were established at the ideal time. Crop potential yield over planting dates will change depending on a given crop's response to changing environmental parameters, as shown for mung beans (fig. 2).

Because of the low probability of sufficient rain to maintain plant growth, no crop is planted before May 1. This date marks the beginning of the period during which the average rainfall is 100 mm/mo. Another reason for the delayed planting is the need for seedbed preparation. The fields are plowed during January through April when the soil is dry and cloddy and until it is slaked with the first rains prior to harrowing. Before these first rains, good seedbed preparation using animal power is impossible. In general, the yields expected from crops planted after January, except for mung beans and

1. Water availability and field crop patterns for upland rice farms of eastern Batangas, Philippines.

cowpeas, are low, as January marks the beginning of the 4-month period of less than 50 mm of rainfall monthly.

Corn, rice, and green cowpeas can be harvested during the wet period (200 mm or more

Table 1. Potential yields of field crops using the best available crop technology for upland rice farms in eastern Batangas, Philippines, as estimated from the highest recorded yields of research trials and farmer-managed trials. 1974-75.

Crop	Yield (t/ha)		
	Potential		Actual
	Research-managed	Farmer-managed	Farmer-managed
Upland rice	4.6	4.0	1.9 ^a
Corn (dry)	4.1	3.7	2.8
(green ears)	32,000 ^b	31,000 ^b	33,000 ^b
Sorghum (main crop)	4.2	4.2	3.1
(ratoon)	—	1.9	1.6
Cowpeas (green)	5.5	6.1	3.5
Mung beans	1.5	1.0	0.5
Sweet potatoes	15.0	12.0	9.3
Peanuts	1.0	0.9	0.9
Soybeans	1.1	1.1	0.6

^a Drought-affected. ^b Number of ears/ha.

2. Approximation of mung bean yield potential for Batangas, Philippines, as related to the rainfall between planting and the second priming.

rain/mo); in contrast, sorghum, mung beans, peanuts, and soybeans cannot be harvested without high yield loss when the rainfall exceeds 100 mm/mo. No upland crop can be planted when the expected rainfall exceeds 40 mm/wk. Those are the parameters which determine potential crop patterns. Thus, the early season is suited for plantings of corn, cowpeas, and sweet potatoes, while the late season is suited for drought-tolerant crops.

Crops. The potential of eight upland crops has been determined through 3 years of research in Batangas, Philippines.

Upland rice can be planted with the first rains, but its potential yield is obtained by planting in late May. The possibility of realizing 50 percent of the yield potential, or 2 t/ha, ends in mid-June. The yields become progressively lower as the time of harvest moves closer to the end of the year. Planting rice under upland conditions during months with 200 mm or more of rainfall is hazardous because of stand-establishment problems.

Corn can be planted from the first rains through November for dry grain or through December if it is to be used solely for dry stover for animals. For the latter crop, mid-October can be the earliest planting date. Dry corn stover is the principal cattle feed from February through May. Green ear corn is best harvested during months with rainfall exceeding 200 mm/

mo, but dry grain can be handled if the weekly rain does not exceed 40–50 mm. While the potential yield of 4.1 t/ha can be obtained with May plantings and with grain drying, it is more likely to be achieved with late October and early November plantings. Late, early, or midseason plantings can average about 50 percent of the crop potential, or 2.0 t/ha.

Cowpea is a versatile crop and, if harvested green, can be planted at any time during the growing season. It is subject to possible high insect damage during certain seasons. It tends to yield less during periods of very low light intensity, or during periods of heavy rain late in the year. An average of 50 percent of the potential, or 3 t/ha, can be achieved during most of the crop season.

Like cowpeas, sorghum yields well during most of the growing season, but the harvestable yield decreases rapidly when the rainfall exceeds 100 mm/mo. During its planting season (fig. 1), the average yield is 2.5 t/ha. Its potential, however, is 4.13 t/ha.

Mung beans can be grown only at the end of the rains. They yield well in the early season, but like sorghum, they cannot be harvested wet. The decrease in yield with increasing moisture during the growing period also limits the extent to which they can be planted in midseason (fig. 2). Mung beans will not tolerate waterlogging; thus, with poorly drained soils the yield potential drops sharply with increasing rainfall. The yield potential is 1.0 t/ha if the legume is planted on January 1, and 0.75 t/ha if planted on December 1. With irrigation to remove the effects of moisture stress, a yield of 2.0 t/ha can be realized.

Sweet potatoes tolerate heavy rain for the first 60 days of their growing season, but will rot if not harvested early (within less than 100 days) during wet periods. The crop is also quite tolerant of drought and can stand a wider range of moisture conditions than can mung beans, peanuts, or soybeans. Yields of 7 to 8 t/ha are more commonly achieved with the planting period indicated in fig. 1. It has a yield potential of 15 t/ha.

Peanuts tolerate heavy rain early in the season, but they will rot unless the precipitation is less than 100 mm/mo at harvest time. For this reason the crop has a short planting period in

Cale, but yields of 60 to 70 percent of the potential are common.

Soybeans have the shortest potential planting season among the crops studied. They have a yield potential of about 1 t/ha. They cannot be harvested without serious grain deterioration when the rainfall exceeds 100 mm/mo or 20 mm/wk. They need at least 10 to 15 mm rain/wk at the time of flowering. Because of the short photoperiod, they cannot be planted after November 15 without a sharp reduction in yield potential; thus, planting is limited to late October and early November. Since most varieties do not yield well during that period, soybeans are the least attractive crop option for eastern Batangas, Philippines.

To study the possible residual effects of other upland crops on the yield of upland rice grown the following year, fields that had been planted partly to corn and partly to another crop were chosen (Table 2). All crops were grown on 0.1 ha or larger plots under farmer management. Little, if any, effect of an upland crop on the yield of rice the next year could be found.

EXTRAPOLATION OF CROP POTENTIAL TO OTHER UPLAND RICE AREAS

Multiple Cropping Department

Changes in soil type across upland rice areas in the Philippines are reflected primarily in soil fertility and water-holding capacity; the drainage and tillage characteristics exhibit relatively small variations. An increase in the clay content would reduce the yield and tillage potentials during periods of heavy rainfall. While lower water availability in red soils would raise the minimum rainfall requirements slightly, the maximum levels would change little.

The length of the midseason is determined by the duration of rainfall. More corn can be grown when the midseason is long, as in parts of Mindanao, Philippines. A short rainy season will result in a short midseason which is suitable for legumes immediately after upland rice. Additional changes in the cropping pattern potential are caused by changes in the rapidity of onset or decline of the rains or by greater rainfall during the dry season.

Intercropping studies conducted in farmers'

Table 2. Grain yield of Dagge upland rice the year following late-season upland crops. Batangas, Philippines.

Crop pattern	Grain yield (t/ha)	
	Rice following late-season upland crop	Rice following corn check
Sorghum	2.29 ^a	2.13
Corn followed by cowpeas	2.57 ^a	2.54
Cowpeas	2.14 ^b	1.76
Mung beans	2.13 ^a	2.14
Sweet potato-corn intercrop	2.20 ^c	2.00

^aMean of 4 fields, 4 samples/field. ^bMean of 6 fields, 4 samples/field. ^cMean of 3 fields, 4 samples/field.

fields in Batangas, Philippines, showed mung beans-and-corn intercrop to have a 30-percent advantage in yield over either of its monoculture checks. The combination of soybeans and corn was 30 percent more productive and that of peanut and corn 20 percent more productive than the monoculture checks. These results are similar to those obtained at IRRI and are expected to be relatively stable in environments to which these crops are adapted.

CROP MANAGEMENT IN UPLAND RICE SYSTEMS

Multiple Cropping Department

The technology for intensive upland rice systems in Batangas depends entirely on an adequate and readily available supply of animal power. Large tractors could be used for primary tillage without radically changing the system, but draft animals are still needed. The technology does not apply in places where adequate power is not available, nor in upland areas where animals or tractors cannot easily be used.

Seedbed preparation in the early season involves two or more plowings before the May rains. With the rains, the fields are harrowed with the *kalmot* (spike tooth harrow) until the clods are broken. Furrows at 25-cm spacing are made with the *lithao* (wooden-type furrow opener for rice) and the seeds are broadcast and covered with a light *kalmot* pass. Three to four days after seeding, the soil crust is broken to permit seed emergence. When corn or cowpeas

Table 3. Response of local corn (Tinumbaga) to five levels of applied nitrogen. Batangas, Philippines, 1974-75 (late season).^a

Applied nitrogen (kg/ha)	Grain yield ^b (t/ha)
10	0.68 d
40	1.36 c
80	2.17 b
120	2.54 a
160	2.31 ab

^aMeans of 10 replications on 5 farms. ^bMeans followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

are planted immediately after rice, a single pass with a plow at 50- to 60-cm intervals opens a furrow for seed.

Weeds in rice are controlled with the *lithao* and *kalmot*; those in row-seeded crops, by hilling up. For late-sown sorghum, soybeans, or mung beans, the *lithao-kalmot* method saves labor at planting, but requires more seed. Row seeding permits subsequent intercultivation and better weed control. Little hand weeding is done except when a field is exceptionally weedy. Yield comparison between weed-free plots and farmer-managed fields showed little yield loss due to weeds in most farmers' fields for most crops.

As expected from the high levels of available P and K, rice and corn showed no response to

phosphorus or potassium fertilizer. Mung beans, soybeans, and peanuts showed little response to nitrogen fertilizer and no response above 30 kg N/ha. The yield of corn increased with increased levels of nitrogen applied at 10, 40, 80, and 120 kg N/ha, but no further yield response to levels above 120 kg N/ha was noted (Table 3).

ANCILLARY INTERCROPPING TRIALS

Multiple Cropping Department

IRRI's collaborative program in Indonesia involves studies in areas where corn is intensively intercropped with upland rice, peanuts, and soybeans. In areas of South Sumatra, thousands of hectares of corn are intercrop combinations. Basic studies were conducted at the IRRI farm to determine reasons for the use of these patterns and the merit of their continuance. The findings are relevant primarily to upland rice areas.

The total dry-matter production and grain yield of corn intercropped with rice were higher than those of either crop grown as a monoculture. In a dry-season planting, 2-m row spacing with a corn population of 40,000 plants/ha gave the highest productivity. The leaf area index (LAI) maximum was reached at 6 weeks after seeding in the three corn populations studied. The maximum LAI for rice was achieved about 12 weeks after seeding, or after the corn was harvested (fig. 3).

The photosynthetic efficiency, as determined (during the sixth through the eighth week after seeding) by the net assimilation rate was higher ($44 \text{ g} \cdot \text{sq m}^{-1} \cdot \text{wk}^{-1}$) for corn (1-m row, 40,000 plants/ha) than for rice ($26 \text{ g} \cdot \text{sq m}^{-1} \cdot \text{wk}^{-1}$). The net assimilation rate for the corn-and-rice intercrop (corn at 1-m row, 40,000 plants/ha) was $43 \text{ g} \cdot \text{sq m}^{-1} \cdot \text{wk}^{-1}$. Corn had a relatively low leaf area duration (leaf area integrated over time) and accumulated low levels of dry matter, while the corn-and-rice intercrop had a high leaf area duration and high level of dry-matter accumulation. Rice alone had a considerably higher leaf area duration, but it was not as efficient in terms of dry-matter production.

Total dry-matter accumulation was closely related to leaf area, and in this study, the dry-matter accumulation per unit leaf area for corn and rice as monocultures was similar to that for

3. Total leaf area index of rice and corn over the growing period. IRRI, 1975 dry season.

4. Nitrogen accumulation at various stages of crop growth with no nitrogen applied. Philippines.

corn and rice in the intercrop. The corn-and-rice intercrop was, therefore, a highly efficient combination, primarily because of the increased leaf area duration of the intercrop during the assimilation period.

The corn-and-soybean intercrop was compared with the corn-and-rice intercrop and with the monocultures of each for efficiency of nutrient uptake. The corn-and-soybean intercrop was more efficient in the total nutrient uptake of nitrogen, as measured by the nitrogen content of the aboveground plant parts. Without nitrogen, soybeans alone ranked second to the intercrop with corn (fig. 4). When nitrogen was applied at 180 kg/ha, the corn-and-soybean intercrop accumulated the most nitrogen followed by the corn-and-rice intercrop (fig. 5). The corn-and-rice intercrop was more efficient than either of the monocultures.

When only low levels of nitrogen were applied, the corn-and-soybean intercrop or soybeans alone were found to accumulate nitrogen more efficiently than the other cropping patterns. Soybeans had a more rapid leaf area development than corn. When no nitrogen was applied to the soil, the total yields of the intercrops were 60 percent higher than those of the monoculture

crops; at 180 kg N/ha, the yields were 40 percent higher (Table 4).

When corn was intercropped with rice, peanuts, or soybeans, the rows were spaced 2 to 2.5 m apart with 20,000 to 30,000 corn plants/ha. These low populations and wide rows were studied because they might reduce the incidence of corn borer and of downy mildew, the two most common and prevalent problems of corn in Indonesia.

Corn borer incidence was reduced significantly both by lower plant population and by intercropping (Table 5). The effects of the peanut and of the soybean intercrop were similar. The principal effect of intercropping was on the reinfestation potential of corn borer. The number of pupal cases per unit area was eightfold greater when corn was grown at 60,000 plants/ha as a monoculture than when intercropped with peanuts. The common corn intercropping in parts of Indonesia may be preventing a buildup of corn borer in those regions.

The incidence of downy mildew was lower in the corn-and-rice intercrop than in the monoculture check only at intermediate levels of infesta-

5. Nitrogen accumulation at various stages of crop growth with nitrogen application at 180 kg/ha.

Table 4. Grain yield of corn + rice, corn + soybean intercrops compared with corn and soybean monoculture at different levels of applied nitrogen. February-May, 1975. Los Baños, Philippines.

Crop and crop combination	Yield (t/ha)					
	Corn	Rice	Soybeans	Corn + rice	Corn + soybeans	LER ^a
<i>0 kg N/ha</i>						
Corn alone	1.36					
Rice alone		1.23				
Soybeans alone			1.23			
Corn + rice	1.01	1.04		2.06		1.60
Corn + soybeans	1.06		1.04		2.10	1.63
<i>45 kg N/ha</i>						
Corn alone	2.52					
Rice alone		2.51				
Soybeans alone			2.20			
Corn + rice	1.86	1.53		3.39		1.34
Corn + soybeans	1.93		1.59		3.51	1.50
<i>90 kg N/ha</i>						
Corn alone	3.79					
Rice alone		3.53				
Soybeans alone			2.11			
Corn + rice	2.76	2.14		4.90		1.34
Corn + soybeans	2.28		1.51		3.79	1.31
<i>180 kg N/ha</i>						
Corn alone	4.03					
Rice alone		4.51				
Soybeans alone			2.07			
Corn + rice	3.08	3.12		6.21		1.45
Corn + soybeans	2.84		1.44		4.29	1.41

^a Land equivalent ratio.

tion (fig. 6). Infestation was less at the low corn population (20,000 plants/ha intercropped with rice) than at the high corn population (30,000 plants/ha). At extremely high and low incidence of downy mildew in the monoculture check, the infestation on the corn intercrop and that on the monoculture were similar. Row spacing had no effect. The levels of downy mildew varied over the four seasons of the trial.

At the more common intermediate levels of downy mildew (60 to 80 percent) in monocul-

ture corn, the low population of the corn (20,000 plants/ha) intercrop had only 20 to 40 percent incidence of the mildew. The reduction of spores

Table 5. Effect of row spacing and intercropping of corn on corn borer incidence. February-May, 1975, Philippines.

Crop combination	Egg masses ^a		Pupal cases ^b	
	(no./50 plants)	(no./sq m)	(no./50 plants)	(no./sq m)
<i>Corn at 20,000 plants/ha</i>				
Corn + peanuts	2	0.08	26	1.04
Corn alone	8	0.32	32	1.28
<i>Corn at 40,000 plants/ha</i>				
Corn + peanuts	5	0.40	37	2.96
Corn alone	11	1.14	57	6.84
<i>Corn at 60,000 plants/ha</i>				
Corn + peanuts	17	2.04	74	8.88

^aAt 46 days after seeding. ^bAt 85 days after seeding.

6. Relationship between the incidence of downy mildew of corn on the monoculture control (60,000 plants/ha) in one season and the differences between the control and the best treatment (20,000 corn plants/ha intercropped with rice). Philippines.

ture corn, the low population of the corn (20,000 plants/ha) intercrop had only 20 to 40 percent incidence of the mildew. The reduction of spores

for re-infection could have a major role in preventing any increase in the incidence of mildew over a large area.

At high levels of the fungus disease (above 80 percent infection), the effect of intercropping disappeared, but these high levels of infection rarely occur in farmers' fields. The plant population-intercrop effect may be complementary to varietal resistance. In Indonesia, a change from the common intercropping of corn with other field crops to corn monoculture would probably increase the incidence of both corn borer and downy mildew.

CONTINUOUS CROPPING OF RICE AND OTHER UPLAND CROPS

Soil Microbiology Department

As indicated in previous annual reports, the growing of the same crop species continuously on the same land can impair succeeding crops; such a condition is described as "soil sickness." The effects of soil sickness are difficult to isolate because of the complicating effects of seasonal

changes, soil, soil fertility depletion, moisture stress, and a buildup of crop diseases.

In a study of the residual effects of crops, rice (IR2061-464-2 and IR747-B2-6-3), mung beans, cowpeas, corn, and sorghum were each planted continuously in the same plots for 1.5 years. A continuous fallow where no crop was grown was also maintained. To maintain an adequate level of soil fertility, 100-60-60 kg of N-P₂O₅-K₂O /ha was applied in 40-cm rows in the fallow plots. All crops were grown in rows. The spacing for rice was 20 cm between rows, that for corn and soybean was 75 cm, and that for legumes was 50 cm. The crops were sprinkler irrigated and the plots were replicated four times.

The reaction of the different crops to continuous cropping differed. The decrease in yield of upland rice was marked and continuous for consecutive croppings (Table 6); after two successive plantings the yields were low and the times of heading and of maturity were not uniform. In the third and fourth croppings, rice growth was normal at the early stages, but became increasingly poorer as the plants reached

Table 6. Upland crops in continuous cropping systems. IRRI, Los Baños, Philippines, 1974-75.

Crop	Month of planting	Maturity (days)	Plant ht (cm)	Grain yield (t/ha)
Rice (IR2061-464-2-4)	June	104	84	2.36
	November	106	56	1.09
	March	122	62	0.50
	August	108	56	0.38
Rice (IR747-B2-6-3)	June	85	75	1.77
	September	87	68	0.87
	January	108	51	0.97
	May	98	61	0.51
Mung beans (MG50-10A)	June	67	85	0.47
	August	64	85	0.11
	November	72	45	0.14
	February	77	65	1.29
	May	65	79	0.80
	August	68	57	0.66
Cowpeas (EG Green Pod #2)	June	107	243	1.08
	October	78	235	0.61
	February	77	173	1.01
	May	77	230	1.10
	August	82	107	0.46
	June	88	221	0.46
Corn (DMR 2)	September	92	198	1.77
	January	90	249	4.51
	May	85	286	3.78
	August	89	244	2.05
	June	105	157	2.69
Sorghum (Cosor 2)	October	86	137	2.34
	January	83	159	5.24
	May	108	174	3.00

Table 7. Growth and yield of continuous and first croppings of upland rice and mung beans. IRRI, Los Baños, Philippines, 1975 wet season.

Crop	Previous crop treatment	Maturity (days)	Plant ht (cm)	Grain yield (t/ha)
Rice (IR2061-464-2)	3 continuous rice crops	108	56	0.36
	14-month continuous fallow	108	82	1.31
	5 continuous mung bean crops (MG50-10A)	108	82	1.28
Mung beans (MG50-10A)	5 continuous mung bean crops	68	57	0.66
	3 continuous rice crops (IR2061-464-2)	68	72	0.68

the heading stage, producing a few, mostly empty, grains.

To ascertain "soil sickness" in rice under field conditions, IR2061-464-2 was also grown in other plots. The yield of upland rice grown in soil that was kept fallow for more than 1 year, or after mung beans, was three times larger than that of upland rice grown in soil where three continuous crops of rice had been grown (Table 7).

Although "soil sickness" was not consistent in legumes, it appeared as early as in the second crop which was characterized by poor seed germination. Seeds that germinated yielded pale, stunted plants; many plants wilted and died. Wilting was more severe with cowpeas, but it occurred only in specific areas of the plot. Replanting was not successful. The plants that survived after the first month usually recovered towards flowering.

As in rice, the reduction in mung bean growth was uniform throughout the plot. Cowpea plants that survived after the first month grew into normal plants. After a severe period of growth retardation, the growth and yield of cowpeas and mung beans improved in the February and May plantings, only to be followed again by a crop with reduced growth. "Soil sickness" in legumes appears to be compounded by seasonal variations and the buildup of plant diseases.

The growth and yield of mung beans in plots previously planted continuously to IR2061-464-2 rice were comparable to those in the plot continuously cropped to mung beans. Visual symptoms of "soil sickness" did not appear after five continuous croppings of corn or four crops of sorghum.

Cropping systems program

Lowland rice cropping systems

Multiple Cropping Department (with the cooperation of the Economics, Weed Science, and Entomology components of the Cropping Systems Program)

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OUTREACH SITES

In 1975, two lowland cropping systems outreach sites were established in the Philippines in cooperation with the Philippine Bureau of Plant Industry to evaluate the cropping potential of different climatic zones under rainfed and partially irrigated conditions. The experimental areas were in six *barangays* of the municipalities of Tigbauan and Oton, Iloilo province, and three *barangays* of the municipality of Manaoag, Pangasinan province.

Iloilo. The climate in Iloilo has, on the average, 4 consecutive dry months of less than 100 mm of rain and 5 consecutive wet months of more than 200 mm, with a rapid onset consisting of only 1 month between a month averaging less than 50 mm of rain and a month averaging more than 200 mm. No month has more than 500 mm of precipitation. The project area in 1975 was essentially rainfed, with only a small portion in Oton receiving supplemental irrigation during the rainy season and the early dry season. The soils were slightly acid with surface texture ranging from clay loam to heavy clay; in a few areas the soils contained lower amounts of clay. Although similar in soil texture, the areas differed in tillage capability.

Most of the plots in Tigbauan were on a nearly level plateau several meters above the flood plain of the Sibalon River. The plots in Barangay Cordova Norte were on the flood plain proper and, thus, had a higher water table and easier tillage than the plots on the plateau. Such conditions favor a high cropping intensity. In Oton, the plots were on more variable land forms, including side slopes, plateaus, low plains, and one swamp. Most farmers in the project area follow a fairly productive transplanted rice monoculture, with stubble broadcast grain legumes as an occasional low-management second crop. Only in the flood plain area of Cordova are upland crops intensively cultivated after rice.

Pangasinan. The climate of Pangasinan averages 6 consecutive dry months with less than 100 mm of rain, and 4 consecutive wet months with more than 200 mm of rainfall, with at least 1 month of rainfall exceeding 500 mm, with no rapid onset of rains. The effect of the early dry

months is greatly reduced because the supplemental irrigation system is effective during this period, depending on the proximity of individual fields to the irrigation canal.

The soils in the area are calcareous, and the pH ranges between 7 and 8. The alkaline pH, combined with oxidation-reduction reactions of the soil during flooding, markedly affects the availability of the two micronutrients iron and zinc. The soil condition severely restricts the rice-based cropping potential of the area. Farmers appear to have developed soil-water management practices to cope with the problem. They make little effort to maintain their dikes, or to thoroughly puddle their soils, claiming that when the soil remains flooded for prolonged periods, the rice becomes "sick." Field observation indicated there was whorl maggot damage.

Cultural practices of farmers circumvent difficulties in the availability of micronutrients by allowing the soils to be flooded long enough to reduce the iron and make it available to the rice plants, but not long enough for the zinc to become reduced and to precipitate into an unavailable form. Because the fields are flooded only intermittently (Table 1), they are weedy and subject to periodic drought stress and reduced nitrogen efficiency caused by nitrification-denitrification reactions normally associated with intermittent flooding. These practices are most probably the best possible management techniques for these soil conditions, in the absence of knowledge of chemical ameliorants.

Except for the micronutrient problems, the soils of Pangasinan are similar to those of Iloilo in that the texture ranges from clay loam to clay. The plots were divided between a plateau in Lipit Pao and a low plain with a high water table in Caaringayan. The cropping intensity in Pangasinan was higher but less productive than that in Iloilo. Portions of the plateau area were triple cropped to corn, rice, and mung beans, while part of the low plain was cropped the year round with rice followed by mung beans, tomatoes, tobacco, followed by corn, squash, and *upo* (*Lageneria siceraria*). Dry-season irrigation frequently came from small annually dug wells from which water was hand-lifted and applied to the individual plants, or from simple tube wells which tapped a gravel aquifer that under-

Table 1. Degree of flooding in comparable rice plots in Pangasinan, Luzon, Philippines, and in Iloilo, Visayas, Philippines.^a

Location	Sample points (no.)	Flood period		Dry period		Flooded (%)	Stress days (av. no.)
		No.	Av. days	No.	Av. days		
Lipit Sur	21	4.7	7.2	4.0	4.6	52	13.5
Caaringayan East	10	3.7	6.1	3.6	4.0	75	6.9
Caaringayan West	21	4.0	13.4	3.2	4.6	72	6.7
Iloilo	14	3.1	30.3	2.4	1.6	97	0.0

^a Includes only paddies with soil texture and geomorphic position comparable with those of Lipit Sur. No area in Iloilo was comparable to Caaringayan in both soil texture and geomorphic position.

lay the fine surface sediments at a depth of approximately 3 m.

Climate variation. Under predominantly rain-fed tropical conditions, the cropping potential of an area depends largely upon the availability of water, a factor that is determined by the annual rainfall. The initial design of cropping patterns must be determined by the normally expected rainfall for an area, but the cropping patterns must also be suited to the actual rainfall. Thus, a set of intensive cropping patterns should be sufficiently flexible to accommodate normal rainfall variations and must recognize the basic nature of the monsoon climate.

In general, monsoon rains alternate between

surges of intensive rain and lulls of little or no rain. In the early part of the rainy season these surges can be quite pronounced, becoming less distinct during the mid-season, and more pronounced again as the dry season approaches. While the total rain received in a given month might be ideal for a specific crop, the surges will be intensive enough in most years to cause water to collect on the soil surface in amounts sufficient to damage many upland crops such as corn, unless there is good surface drainage. Similarly, lulls that could cause drought stress in a lowland rice crop occur. The surges are well illustrated by the 1975 daily rainfall at Iloilo and Pangasinan (fig. 1).

1. Daily rainfall pattern for the 1975 cropping season at Iloilo and Pangasinan, Philippines, outreach sites.

The surge-and-lull behavior is not the same each year and may not be sufficiently predictable to be useful in designing agronomic practices. The farmers, therefore, adjust their activities to these variations as they occur in a given year. Some of the effects of such variations on the establishment and operation of the cropping patterns studied are discussed below.

Impact of 1975 rainfall in Iloilo. Iloilo in 1975 had its highest recorded April rainfall, over 200 mm compared with an average of only 40 mm. This is a rare occurrence and should not be considered in designing any cropping pattern for the region. The unusually heavy rains caused a shift in the first rice crop of the rice-rice pattern from dry-seeded rice (DSR) to wet-seeded rice (WSR) and contributed largely to the success of this crop.

May was essentially normal, but June was somewhat wetter than normal, allowing some cooperators with lower paddies to transplant their rice early. July and August were drier than normal, with 150 mm and 220 mm of rainfall compared with normal levels of 300 mm and 320 mm. These variations have a 20-percent probability of occurrence and need to be considered in designing cropping patterns for this area. The reduced rainfall delayed transplanting and lowered yields, particularly when early-maturing varieties had been transplanted. Precipitation in September and October was essentially normal. November was unusually dry; only 50 mm of rain fell compared with the normal 200 mm. The rice crop withdrew the residual moisture from the soil, which made it difficult to establish upland crops after rice. Since such an occurrence has only a 5-percent probability, it should not be considered in the cropping pattern design.

Impact of 1975 rainfall in Pangasinan. Pangasinan generally receives more total rain than Iloilo but within a shorter time. The rainfall intensity through the middle of the cropping season is greater, but the onset and the decline of the rains are sharper. The canal irrigation system in Lipit-Pao reduces the effect of water shortage after August and extends the cropping season by 2 to 4 months, depending on the proximity of the fields to the canal. In parts of Caaringayan, supplemental irrigation from shallow tube wells

can be used throughout the year to alleviate short dry periods during the wet season, and to irrigate upland crops throughout most of the dry season.

In 1975, the rainfall pattern in Pangasinan was essentially similar to that of Iloilo. Although May was somewhat wetter than normal and June was drier, the cropping patterns were not affected markedly; however, the waterlogging of early corn in Caaringayan would have been less severe had there been less precipitation in May. July and August were relatively dry (as in Iloilo) but within the expected range, and actual rainfall was not below the 200 mm needed for paddy rice. With adequate water supply and good land management, transplanting should not have been greatly affected by this rainfall. However, the prevailing water-land management practices, which use low bunds and hardly any puddling, delayed transplanting.

While September was also slightly drier than normal, rainfall was above average in October. As usual, the precipitation ended abruptly in November; by this time, however, the irrigation canals contained sufficient water to irrigate most of the area and extend the cropping season. The irrigation system allows the design of cropping patterns for a longer growing season than the natural rainfall would permit.

CROPPING PATTERN STUDIES

Rice-rice. The sequence originally specified for the rice-rice pattern, i.e. dry seeding the first crop and transplanting the second crop, was not generally followed (fig. 2). In Iloilo the unexpected early heavy rains allowed wet seeding of most of the first crop. Since wet-seeded rice (WSR) is agronomically easier to produce, the yields of most of the crops were good, averaging 4.2 t/ha. For the second rice crop, seven cooperators used WSR while only three transplanted, even though there was adequate rain during the turnaround period. The turnaround time for the 10 rice-rice cooperators in Iloilo averaged 20.5 days. The yield for the second crop averaged 4.4 t/ha, bringing to 8.8 t/ha the total for both crops.

The fact that seven of the 10 cooperators elected to wet-seed their second crop suggests the degree of instability in trying to harvest one

Cooperator	Barrio	Apr	May	Jun	July	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar
		ILOILO											
		RICE											
		RICE											
TIGUISON, C.	BITAS			IR 28 (94)	5.0 t/ha	13	IR 28 (94)	5.0 t/ha	21	IR 28 (91)	1.7 t/ha		
						22			21				
TRIO, P.	"			IR 28 (91)	5.1 t/ha	12	IR 28 (87)	3.8 t/ha	21	EG 2 COWPEAS			
TERANTE, R.	"			IR 28 (94)	4.6 t/ha	34	IR 28 (91)	5.3 t/ha		CO SOR 3 SORGHUM (relay)			
TURAO, C.	NAPNAPAN			IR 28 (84)	5.2 t/ha	9	IR 28 (89)	4.3 t/ha		EG 2 COWPEAS			
TUYA, J.	"			IR 28 (93)	4.9 t/ha	22	IR 28 (85)	4.4 t/ha	21	EG 2 COWPEAS			
TUBISA, J.	"			IR 28 (87)	4.7 t/ha	25	IR 28 (97)	4.8 t/ha		CES 55 MUNG (relay)			
						25							
TUMINLACO, J.	"			IR 28 (91)	3.1 t/ha	29	IR 28 (92)	4.1 t/ha	10	EG 2 COWPEA			
GAMON, P.	BURAY			IR 28 (90)	3.6 t/ha	18	IR 28 (86)	4.2 t/ha	3	LOCAL MUNG			
FUENTESPINA, W.				IR 28 (90)	4.0 t/ha	15	IR 28 (88)	4.3 t/ha					
LEDESMA, M.	BITAS			IR 28 (110)	3.5 t/ha	17	IR 28 (95)	3.3 t/ha	29	MG 50 MUNG			
									30				
		PANGASINAN											
VALDEZ, A.	CAARIINGAYAN			IR 28 (110)	4.4 t/ha	21	IR 28 (94)	3.4 t/ha	40	CES 14 + DMR2 Intercrop			
						15							
QUIBAN, V.	"			IR 28 (103)	5.4 t/ha	16	IR 28 (97)	5.3 t/ha	32	CES 101 PEANUTS			
						11							
QUISORA, L.	"			IR 28 (101)	4.9 t/ha	21	IR 28 (93)	4.0 t/ha	31	CES 14 + DMR2 Intercrop			
						17							
PAET, D.	"			IR 28 (102)	2.6 t/ha	15	IR 28 (102)	2.4 t/ha	15	CES 14 MUNG			
						11							
IDOR, T.	LIPIT			IR 28 (97)	3.0 t/ha	8	IR 30 (14)	2.6 t/ha	41	CES 14 + DMR2 Intercrop			
						31							
				IR 30 (108)	2.8 t/ha	13	IR 30 (100)	1.3 t/ha	7	CES 14 MUNG			
													33

2. Examples of the rice-rice cropping patterns tested in Iloilo and Pangasinan, Philippines, outreach sites, 1975.

crop and transplant a second. To be successful, the rapid harvest-transplant turnaround requires close coordination with the unpredictable surges and lulls in the monsoons. Without drying facilities, harvesting of the first crop requires a lull in the monsoon rains, while without water reserves, transplanting requires a surge in the monsoon rains. If the monsoons surge at harvest, a farmer will delay harvest until a lull because wet rice preserves better in the field than when cut and stacked. A lull in the monsoons allows the crop to be harvested, but land preparation

and transplanting are delayed. These delays result in the planting of old seedlings and cause a reduction in yields. Although it may be physically possible to harvest rapidly and transplant, it is difficult to execute the essential field operations with the unpredictable surges and lulls in the monsoons. Hence, the farmer elects to wet seed the second rice crop.

In Pangasinan, the first rice crop, which was dry seeded, emerged on time. In 2 weeks, however, all plots turned pale yellow with symptoms of what appeared to be iron deficiency. Most of

the rice remained stunted and could not compete with the weeds. When the field became flooded and the soil reduced, the plants recovered somewhat before developing the red mottles that characterize zinc deficiency. This further hindered crop growth, and more than half of the paddies had to be plowed under before harvest. Crops on 15 of the 31 paddies survived and yielded an average of 2.2 t/ha. Three paddies had a yield exceeding 4 t/ha and one yielded over 5 t/ha.

All the second crops were transplanted. A second seedbed using *dapog* seedlings supplied by the project was required because the original seedlings had become too old. The turnaround time in Pangasinan, 18 days, was shorter than the 20.5 days in Iloilo. The transplanted crop following the direct-seeded rice was more successful; it averaged 3.2 t/ha, allowing for an average production of 5.5 t/ha for the two crops. One cooperator achieved 10.7 t/ha for the two crops.

The third crop in the pattern at both Iloilo and Pangasinan was generally a low-input, low-

management, and low-return crop, intended to exploit whatever soil moisture remained available. In Pangasinan, supplemental irrigation was always needed for crop establishment.

Corn-rice. Eight cooperators in Iloilo and eight in Pangasinan tried a corn-before-rice pattern. Only four of the 16 trials were successful. Two factors contributed to the lack of success. In the Lipit-Pao area of Pangasinan, a heavy infestation of downy mildew destroyed the Early Thai Composite corn variety. A downy mildew-resistant variety of corn would appear well suited to the area, since many farmers there had successful corn before rice. In the other areas, monsoon surges caused sufficient waterlogging of the soil to destroy the corn. Successful plantings were limited to paddies that had good internal drainage or could be rapidly drained of excess surface water.

Since many paddy fields have poor internal drainage, the success of the corn-before-rice pattern depends largely on selecting paddies that have good surface drainage. One cooperator in Iloilo with experience in growing corn chan-

3. Examples of the rice-upland crop patterns tested in Iloilo and Pangasinan, Philippines, outreach sites, 1975.

nelled the furrows to lead the water to the paddy spillway. Another cooperator used a field that had not been planted to rice, and, in reality, had a corn-mung-corn cropping pattern. Since paddies successfully used for early corn have good drainage, they are often not the most suitable fields for paddy rice. Thus, the yields of rice that followed corn averaged only 2.8 t/ha, but those of the second rice crop in the rice-rice pattern averaged 4.4 t/ha during essentially the same growing period. More careful selection of paddies to assure good surface or internal drainage should greatly increase the chances of success for the corn-rice pattern.

Rice-upland crop. The rice-upland crop patterns were originally designed to have one crop of transplanted rice followed by corn, sorghum, sweet potatoes, melons, peanuts, cowpeas, or mung beans, or to have intercrop combinations of corn with peanuts or mung beans. In most cases the rice, either IR26 or IR30, was transplanted in July (fig. 3). A few low paddies were transplanted in late June, but several high paddies could not be transplanted until August. Two cooperators in Iloilo were unable to transplant until September; a few others with very high paddies were unable to transplant at all. They finally direct seeded IR28 in September or else transferred to lower paddies where an earlier wet-seeded rice crop had been harvested.

Transplanting in July and August was affected by dry weather and, frequently, old seedlings were used. In July, 25-day-old seedlings were transplanted in both locations. In August, 38-day-old seedlings were transplanted in Iloilo, and 41-day-old seedlings were used in Pangasinan. The age of the transplanted rice seedlings was negatively correlated with rice yields (fig. 4). Thus, the use of older rice seedlings appears to be an important reason for the decreased yields of fields established late in the season.

The frequent transplanting of older seedlings indicates the difficulties encountered by farmers in rainfed areas in accurately predicting the surges in monsoons that would permit transplanting on time. It also suggests that early-maturing rice varieties with short vegetative periods may be better suited for direct seeding than for transplanting under rainfed conditions, unless there is good water control for an indivi-

4. Relation between age of seedlings at transplanting and yield of IR30 in Pangasinan and Iloilo, Philippines.

dual paddy. In Iloilo, one cooperator confirmed that the unpredictable surge in monsoons compelled him to transplant the medium-maturing IR5 rice rather than the early-maturing IRR1 line IR1561-228-3. It is also the reason many cooperators elected to seed directly rather than to transplant their second IR28 rice crop. Direct seeding allows for more flexibility to accommodate the unpredictable monsoon rains.

After the rice harvest, the upland crops were planted starting in November. The turnaround between harvest and planting was longer than desired (fig. 5) and varied according to the month

5. Turnaround time between two crops as affected by month of harvest of the first crop. Iloilo and Pangasinan, Philippines, outreach sites, 1975.

6. Sequence of rice harvest and upland crop planting compared to weekly rainfall at Iloilo and Pangasinan, Philippines, outreach sites, 1975.

of harvest and the cropping pattern used. The upland crops were not planted until all the rice, except the double-cropped rice, had been harvested (fig. 6). The average turnaround period for Iloilo was similar to that for Pangasinan. When the crops were harvested in October, the turnaround time was longest, but similar to that found in irrigated areas of Nueva Ecija, Luzon, Philippines. The turnaround was shorter for crops harvested in the months preceding or following October.

There are several reasons for the long delays in October, the month in which the monoculture rice crop of most regions in the Philippines is harvested. Many cooperators were understandably more concerned about securing the crop in the field than about planting additional crops. Thus, they gave priority to the harvesting, threshing, and drying of rice over the planting of upland crops.

In September and early October, many paddies in Iloilo could not be planted because continuing monsoon surges kept the paddies flooded. However, by early November although the paddies were dry and could have been planted, they were not. Cooperators in Cordova delayed planting upland crops on the plateau area, because they managed additional holdings in the flood plains that are customarily planted to upland crops after rice.

The turnaround periods may be reduced in three ways. First, several cropping patterns may be used to stagger the harvest so that each crop can be secured and the paddy replanted before the next crop is ready for harvest. One cooperator in Iloilo used a different pattern on each of his four parcels of land to distribute his available resources evenly (fig. 7). By staggering the operations, he shortened the turnaround to an average of about 2 weeks. Second, part of

7. Sequencing of tasks from the variation in cropping patterns used by a single cooperators on different parcels of land, Iloilo, Philippines, outreach site, 1975.

the harvesting procedure may be mechanized. Threshing is probably the easiest activity to mechanize, particularly in Iloilo where rice is laboriously threshed by foot on elevated platforms. The labor and time saved could be applied to planting the next crops. Third, a low tillage technique may be used to reduce land preparation, which otherwise must frequently be delayed until the optimum soil moisture is available.

One cooperators in Iloilo with a rice-upland crop pattern transplanted IR28 to a low paddy position in June and harvested it in August. He then planted a second rice crop of IR28 by wet seeding and achieved 2.9 t/ha despite a severe drought in November. Twelve other cooperators in Iloilo who harvested in September, and five who harvested their first crop of rice in October, also attempted a second rice crop. But their crops were severely damaged by the November drought; only 1.8 t/ha was obtained from the crop planted in September and 0.5 t/ha from the crop planted in October. These averages include those for several fields that gave no yield and one that received supplementary irrigation and yielded 3.0 t/ha. A more normal rainfall in November would have greatly improved these crops. Because these cooperators attempted the extra rice crop and lost, they were unable to plant the originally planned upland crops, and were left with a rice monoculture for 1975.

The cooperators who did not attempt the

second rice crop found conditions too wet to plant the upland crops until sometime in early November. During the wet, fallow period, ratoon rice grew from the stubble and nearly matured before the cooperators were able to prepare the land for the upland crops. Eleven of about 60 cooperators in Iloilo and Pangasinan harvested the ratoon rice. The average yield was 1.0 and 0.8 t/ha with an average maturity of 53 and 44 days between the two harvests for Iloilo and Pangasinan, respectively.

Although the ratoon rice was not designed as part of the cropping patterns, it may have a distinct potential under these rainfed conditions despite the low yields obtained. Early-maturing, high-yielding varieties could often be harvested in late August or September. This is too late in the season for a good second rice crop, but still too wet for establishing upland crops. A good 40- to 50-day rice ratoon would be well suited to the climate, even if yields are less than 50 percent of the original crop.

Flexibility in alternative cropping patterns is desirable to distribute resource demands more evenly and the rice-ratoon-upland pattern could be a good complement to the double-rice cropping pattern. Should the dry season begin earlier than anticipated, the ratoons could always be canceled in favor of an earlier establishment of upland crops. With the cropping patterns tried, farmers who accepted the ratoon crop were able to establish their upland crops, but those who

planted a second rice frequently achieved neither a rice crop nor an upland crop. In Iloilo, however, the medium-maturing IR26 rice yielded an extra 1 t/ha, equivalent to the 1 t/ha provided by the ratoon crop of IR28 or IR30. Thus, with present technology, the total rice production from an early-maturing variety plus a ratoon crop and that from a medium-maturing variety alone are about the same. This suggests the need for further research to explore the possibility of improving the yields of ratoon rice.

The very dry November in Iloilo made the establishment of upland crops more difficult than usual except in Cordova, where the soils are easier to till and the high water table provides capillary water and supplemental irrigation. In Pangasinan, all post-paddy crops required irrigation either from the canal or from tube wells, as is usual in the area.

The upland crops following paddy rice were established by using several techniques, including stubble broadcasting, dibbling (drilling a hole in the soil, putting the seed in the hole, and covering it with soil), furrow planting, and complete tillage. The best stands were obtained with minimum tillage techniques that place the seeds below the soil surface. The stubble broadcast techniques were not effective in 1975 because of the very dry November. More normal November rains might have contributed to the success of this stand-establishment technique. The complete tillage techniques were frequently impossible on some of the heavy clay soils or required an extra month of turnaround time for proper land preparation. Longer turnaround meant the crops were grown in a drier, less favorable environment.

The best technique was to spray the herbicide paraquat and plant in small plow furrows, or dibble. Under the dry conditions of 1975, upland crops following rice had to be planted as early as possible with the seeds placed below the soil surface to obtain sufficient moisture for germination. In wetter years this practice might not be as critical, but it would not be harmful. In Caaringayan, particularly, the extra month gained by no tillage allowed for another short-season crop to be planted, even though yields of early and late plantings were not significantly different. In Lipit-Pao and most of Iloilo, an

extra crop would not be possible because no water is available from February to April.

The importance of geomorphic location to the success of many upland crops following paddy rice became apparent. Virtually all upland crops did better on low plains with water tables near the surface and with limited winds than on the high plateaus. Only the most drought-tolerant crops succeeded on the plateaus where the water table was deep and dry winds increased evapotranspiration. Under these conditions, the best crops were those with a low profile, like peanuts and melons. High bunds tended to protect these crops from desiccation by winds. In the Lipit-Pao area of Pangasinan, the potential for upland crops after rice depended on the proximity of the field to the irrigation canal, since the irrigated area decreased as the dry season advanced.

INDIVIDUAL UPLAND CROPS

The adaptability of the different upland crops varied considerably with local conditions. The performance of eight crops following paddy rice is summarized below.

Sorghum. Sorghum did well in fields with good tillage, but stand establishment was difficult with low tillage. The yield of sorghum grown on a plateau was fair; that of sorghum grown in low plains was better.

Corn. Corn was grown successfully only on the flood plain areas of Cordova where the soils were easily tilled. The area had a supplemental water supply and was protected from winds. In windy high plateau areas, corn wilted from loss of water caused by accelerated evapotranspiration. Corn could not be grown successfully after rice in Pangasinan because of a residual zinc deficiency possibly caused by the delayed reoxidation of precipitated zinc.

Sweet potatoes. Sweet potatoes yielded best where planted in low beds to promote root formation and recovery at harvest. The crop appeared to tolerate the delayed planting which resulted from the tillage required in preparing the beds. It was not successfully established with low tillage methods and on clay soils because of poor root formation.

Melons. Melons appear to have a good poten-

tial as a crop after paddy rice and are well suited for windy plateau areas because of their low profile. This crop is perishable and thus has a limited but high market value. It competes well with weeds, can be planted with minimum spot tillage, and can be initially spot irrigated by hand.

Soybeans. Soybeans appear to be the most unstable performer of the crops planted after rice in the Philippines. Because most soybean varieties are photosensitive, they must be planted by early November, or short days will cause early flowering, short plants, and low yields. Since this legume does not compete well with weeds, it may require high tillage which would delay planting until after the November day-length deadline.

In Iloilo the monsoon surges that can waterlog most paddies and leave standing water on the surface continued through November and restricted soybeans to a limited area where paddies have good internal or surface drainage. In Pangasinan, the rapid decline in the monsoons and an ability to control irrigation water may permit soybeans to be grown on large level areas.

Soybeans appear suitable only for paddies which have had sufficient weed control during the rice crop to allow the crop to be planted directly into the stubble.

Peanuts. Agronomically, peanuts appear well suited to the post-paddy climate. This crop's low profile allows it to thrive even in windy plateau areas where high bunds protect it. Peanuts require high tillage but can tolerate the delay needed to accomplish the tillage. The crop performs better on the less clayey soils; the kernel tends to become damaged when peanuts are grown on heavy clay soils. The major agronomic constraint appears to be the labor required at harvest particularly in the more clayey soils. Another major problem with peanut production seems to be the unauthorized premature harvesting by children.

Cowpeas. Cowpeas, which are extensively grown in the Philippines, are agronomically well suited for the post-paddy period. The crop can be grown under zero tillage and low management, but responds well to minimum tillage. It has good drought tolerance.

Mung beans. Mung beans are similar to cow-

peas in suitability for the post-paddy period. The crop is grown under conditions similar to those for cowpeas.

DEVELOPMENT OF CONCEPTS AND A PADDY CLASSIFICATION SCHEME

Concepts. Results of the cropping pattern studies and of observations made of the farmers in the research area led to several concepts:

- The design of a cropping pattern should be sufficiently flexible to allow cooperators to cope with the unpredictable surges and lulls of the monsoon rains.
- As the cropping intensity increases, co-operators will require, in the total cropping system, several cropping patterns that are specific to the individual paddies in their holdings.
- In addition to previously identified determinants, the cropping potential of any specific paddy also depends on its location and proximity to irrigation systems.

Classification of paddy position. A system to classify paddy position was developed and characterized for different cropping potentials. The difference in the cropping potentials among paddies is largely related to the availability of water and, to a lesser degree, to moisture demand. In paddy rice areas, a large portion of the water is retained on the surface, and its depth can usually be manipulated by controlling runoff.

The paddy position classification reflects the capability of a paddy to be drained and to accumulate water as determined by the geomorphic landscape and relative position of the paddy within the landscape.

In general, within a given geomorphic landscape, the cropping potential for wet puddled rice will increase in sequential blocks from the bottom of the slope to the top, although within a block the actual planting may proceed from high to low. Conversely the dry upland culture will proceed down the slope, from top to bottom. Thus, the higher paddies have the potential for upland crops, such as corn or DSR, prior to the wet rice crop, while the lower paddies are better suited for early WSR followed by a second WSR. There would be no need to try DSR in the

lower paddies since the shortness of the delay before wet seeding becomes feasible would make it pointless to face the extra problems associated with dry seeding. Dry seeding is really suited only for the upper paddies where the lag between a dry seeding date and the time when water is available to wet seed may be sufficient to justify the extra difficulties. This means that DSR fits the paddies that are most subject to drought stress, and have less yield potential than those using WSR on the other end of the slope. Between early DSR and WSR are the middle paddies in which resources (primarily water) are not adequate for the early wet rice crop but may be excessive for DSR. These paddies have the best potential for one rice crop followed by a long-term upland crop after rice.

The actual division of paddies into three relative positions is more closely associated with individual farms than with the total geomorphic landscape. The entire system shifts from year to year depending on the distribution and amount of rainfall. This is particularly true of the early WSR with double-cropping potential. In years of plentiful and early rains or an early typhoon, the WSR could occupy a large area of the middle paddies that normally would grow a single rice crop. In a dry year, the WSR double cropping may be restricted to the very low creekbeds and drainage ways. The paddies are divided into five classes (fig. 8).

Knolls. Knolls are small hilly areas which can be easily drained but cannot accumulate water. They frequently comprise loamy soils and have

8. Conceptual presentation of the effect of paddy position on cropping potential.

a low potential for rice in most years. Often they will not be banded. Here, all rices should be direct seeded rather than transplanted.

From a strict agronomic point of view, the best cropping pattern might exclude rice and concentrate on upland crops such as early corn, followed by sweet potatoes, sorghum, soybeans, or possibly peanuts. In these areas, wind could become a major factor in the dry season. Thus, as the dry season approaches, the best crops or varieties might be those with a low profile, such as peanuts and melons.

High plateaus. High plateaus are generally flat areas with deep water tables. The paddies are generally large and nearly square, with little vertical drop between them. They are difficult to drain, and surges in the monsoon tend to waterlog them. Waterlogging damages upland crops such as corn early in the rainy season, and delays the planting of upland crops late in the rainy season.

During the dry season, winds can substantially increase the evapotranspiration of exposed crops. The potential of the upland crops following rice is thus limited. During the rainy season the paddies should be used exclusively for rice, with relative position along the slope determining the cultural practices.

The high paddies would be best suited for DSR-WSR-legume, while the lower ones could be used for a more productive WSR-WSR-legume. The middle paddies could best be used for single crop rice or rice-ratoon followed by a drought-tolerant crop, such as sorghum or melons.

Side slopes. The side slopes can accumulate water and can be easily drained. Generally, the paddies are narrow, irregular rectangles with a greater vertical drop than have the plateau paddies. Again, upland crops will proceed down the slope, and puddling will proceed up the slope. Because of the surface drainage, the upper portion of these areas can be used for early corn followed by puddled rice.

The lower portion can be used for the puddled rice crops; even transplanting the second crop would be reasonable. These areas are generally protected from the winds, so there is less need for low-profile upland crops. Soybeans, mung beans, cowpeas, and sorghum can all be expected

to do well. Since surface drainage remains fairly good, such crops can be planted earlier than crops planted on more level areas. Early planting is important for soybeans, which respond adversely to the shorter day length near the end of the growing season. Sometimes the upper paddies may be used exclusively for upland crops without any rice in the patterns.

Low plains. The low plains include flood plains which have a high water table and in which soil water can be obtained by capillary movement or from shallow wells during the dry season. Like the plateau areas, the paddies are generally wide and nearly square, with a small vertical drop between them, making surface drainage difficult.

The cropping potential in the rainy season would be similar to that of the high terrace, but the upland crops following rice would be unlimited and could include many of the drought-sensitive as well as drought-tolerant crops.

The low plains are usually well protected, so wind does not become a problem. They are the only areas where corn can be grown successfully after rice. They frequently will have a variety of intensive indigenous cropping patterns.

Drainage ways. The drainage ways are the basal portion of the topographic sequence; they include intermittent waterways and swamps. Flooding during the wet season limits the use of short-statured rice varieties. Drainage ways are restricted to paddy rice during the wet season, but can frequently be used for three rice crops annually if the farmer uses short-statured early-maturing varieties for the early wet season or the dry season, and tall varieties, such as IR34, during the mid-wet season when the water becomes deep.

Upland crops are possible if the area dries out during the middle of the dry season.

SPECIAL STUDIES

Because of the zinc micronutrient problem encountered in Pangasinan, a special research-managed study investigated the effect of applying zinc, and its interaction with nitrogen. A randomized complete block design was used with no zinc and a seedling dip of 2 percent zinc oxide in the main plots, and with three rates of nitrogen in the subplots. The experiment used

9. Response of IR28 to zinc and nitrogen in Manaog, Pangasinan, Philippines, 1975 wet season.

dapog seedlings of IR28.

The IR28 rice plants responded to zinc and to nitrogen-plus-zinc (fig. 9), but not to nitrogen-without-zinc. The results indicate why farmers applied only 20 kg of N/ha; there was no response to additional nitrogen.

The response to nitrogen after the zinc treatment was not as large as expected. Perhaps the small rice seedlings did not receive a sufficient amount of zinc from the dip; an additional response might have been obtained from applying more zinc as a foliar spray.

Cropping systems program

Weeds

Agronomy Department

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VARIATION IN ABILITY OF CROPS TO COMPETE WITH WEEDS

Six upland crops grown at three different row spacings varied considerably in ability to compete with weeds. On the basis of the average weight of weeds for three row spacings, cowpeas were the most competitive and mung beans were the least competitive (Table 1). The crops at the widest row spacing were less competitive with the weeds. Because of weed competition, the yields of all crops except corn and mung beans decreased as the row spacing increased.

Weed competition did not reduce the yield of corn even at the widest row spacing of 150 cm, when more than 4 t of weeds/ha competed with the crop, probably because soil fertility was naturally high and 90 kg N/ha was added during crop growth. In general, the addition of nitrogen can partially overcome yield reductions caused by weeds in corn.

Weed competition caused about 50 percent reduction in mung bean yield. Weed weight was about the same for all three row spacings (33.3, 50, and 100 cm); it varied between 3.0 and 3.6 t/ha. Apparently, row spacing had little effect on the competitive ability of mung beans.

Except in corn and cowpeas, the average reduction in crop yield caused by weeds was related to the average weed weight; the lower the weed weight, the lower was the yield loss. Although cowpeas were the most competitive against weeds and had the fewest weeds growing with them, weeds reduced their yield more than

that of any of the five other crops tested. The few weeds in the cowpea crop appeared to be highly competitive.

Although the composition of the weed flora varied little as row spacing increased, it differed considerably among the six crops. When averaged across row spacings, the weed flora of corn and legumes comprised 50 percent broadleaves, 30 percent grasses, and 20 percent sedges. Broadleaved weeds also dominated the sorghum crop with a weed flora ratio of 75:20:5. On the other hand, grasses were the dominant weed type in rice, with a ratio of 30:50:20. The type of crop plant appears to affect both the weed weight and the composition of the weed flora.

DIFFERENCES AMONG CROP CULTIVARS' ABILITY TO COMPETE WITH WEEDS

Different crops vary in the ability to compete with weeds. To determine whether such differences exist among cultivars of the same crop, five cultivars each of cowpeas and mung beans were grown under weed-free and unweeded conditions.

At crop harvest the dry weight of the weeds that grew with the cowpea cultivars varied markedly, from 563 kg/ha for the most competitive cultivar, EG #1, to 2,302 kg/ha for the least competitive cultivar, California Black Eye (Table 2). The yield reduction caused by weeds was almost directly related to the weight of the weeds growing with the cultivar. Weeds reduced

Table 1. Effects of row spacing (16.7–150 cm) on weed weight and yield reduction caused by weed competition in six upland crops. IRRI, 1975 wet season.

Crop	Effect of row spacing							Av.
	16.7 cm	25.0 cm	33.3 cm	50.0 cm	75.0 cm	100 cm	150 cm	
			<i>Weed wt (kg/ha)</i>					
Corn (DMR 2)				931	1393		4231	2185
Soybeans (TK 5)			827	997		1813		1212
Sorghum (Cosor 2)			998	2947		2695		2213
Rice (C 22)	2826	2296		3899				3007
Mung beans (CES 55)			3316	2997		3603		3305
Cowpeas (EG #2)			213	220		551		328
			<i>Weed-caused yield reduction (%)</i>					
Corn (DMR 2)				0	0		0	0
Soybeans (TK 5)			14	29		43		29
Sorghum (Cosor 2)			7	19		71		32
Rice	1	67		69				46
Mung beans (CES 55)			50	57		49		52
Cowpeas (EG #2)			47	73		90		70

Table 2. The competitive abilities of five cowpea [*Vigna unguiculata* (L.) Walp.] cultivars. IRRI, 1975 wet season.

Cowpea cultivar	Yield (kg/ha)		Weed-caused yield reduction (%)	Weed wt (kg/ha)
	Weed free	Unweeded		
EG #1	249	127	49	563
EG #2	592	241	59	687
EG #3	763	236	69	1181
California Black Eye	374	74	87	2302
Virginia	564	59	89	2047

Table 3. Growth characteristics of five cowpea cultivars. IRRI, 1975 wet season.

Cowpea cultivar	100-seed wt (g)	LAI ^a (41 DAE ^b)		Reduction in LAI (%)	Av. plant ht (cm) (30 DAE)
		Weeded	Unweeded		
EG #1	16.3	2.01	1.39	31	46.7
EG #2	12.6	2.01	1.67	17	48.9
EG #3	13.0	2.06	1.89	8	44.4
California Black Eye	17.1	1.63	1.46	10	40.0
Virginia	11.8	1.05	0.72	31	44.0

^aLeaf area index. ^bDays after cowpea emergence.

Table 4. Competitive abilities of five mung bean (*Vigna radiata* L.) cultivars against weeds. IRRI, 1975 wet season.

Mung bean cultivar	LAI ^a (41 DAE ^b)		Reduction in LAI (%)	Weed wt (kg/ha)	Weed-caused reduction in crop yield (%)
	Weeded	Unweeded			
CES 14	1.09	0.84	23	3408	73
CES 55	0.79	0.69	13	2071	83
MG 50-10A (green)	0.53	0.32	40	3974	88
MG 50-10A (yellow)	0.55	0.41	25	3243	89
BPI Glabrous #3	1.21	0.79	35	2027	96

^aLeaf area index. ^bDays after crop emergence.

the yield of EG #1 cowpea by 49 percent and that of California Black Eye cowpea by 87 percent. The yield of Virginia cowpea, another poor competitor against weeds, was reduced by 89 percent.

Certain cultivars which may be more competitive against weeds were expected to show a yield reduction smaller than that of the less competitive cultivars, but their total yield was less because they have a lower yield potential than the less competitive cultivars. For example, EG #3, which was less competitive than EG #1, yielded more than EG #1 in an unweeded situation because its yield potential under weed-free conditions was much higher. Being less competitive than EG #1, other cowpea cultivars, such as California Black Eye and Virginia, outyielded EG #1 under weed-free

conditions but yielded less under unweeded conditions.

The difference in competitive ability of the various cowpea cultivars against weeds appears to be related to both the plant height and the leaf area index (LAI) (Table 3). Generally, a lower LAI and plant height were associated with a lower ability to compete with weeds. Differences in the LAI among cultivars were apparent in the first week of crop growth. Weeds reduced the LAI of all cultivars, but this reduction was not related to the competitive ability of the cultivar.

Mung bean cultivars also varied in their ability to compete with weeds (Table 4). The dry weight of weeds at mung bean harvest was associated with the LAI of the cultivar in the weeded plots; the lower the weed weight the

Table 5. Effect of mulching (with rice straw), row spacing, and weeding regime on soybean [*Glycine max* (L.) Merr.] yield and weed weight. IRRI, 1975 wet season.

Weeding treatment (wk after emergence)	Soybean yield ^a (kg/ha)		Weed wt ^a (kg/ha)	
	Unmulched	Mulched	Unmulched	Mulched
			<i>50-cm row spacing</i>	
No weeding	79	481	1404	689
Weeded at 3 wk	467	588	288	490
Weeded at 1 wk and 4 wk	630	541	97	343
			<i>75-cm row spacing</i>	
No weeding	43	324	1647	1100
Weeded at 3 wk	341	510	588	593
Weeded at 1 wk and 4 wk	527	532	220	317

^aAv. of three insecticide regimes.

higher the LAI, except for CES 14. As with cowpeas, the LAI was lower for all cultivars when weeds were present, but the extent of the reduction was not related to weed weight.

The reduction in mung bean yield caused by weed competition was not related to weed weight. The weeds that grew with BPI Glabrous #3 had the lowest weight, yet the yield reduction (96 percent) was greater in that cultivar than in the four other mung bean cultivars tested. On the other hand, CES 14 had the second highest weight of weeds but the lowest reduction in yield (73 percent). This pattern differs from previously observed patterns in which higher weed populations were associated with greater reductions in crop yield. The factors that cause this difference and the factors related to the improved competitive ability of the crop need to be examined further.

EFFECT OF MULCHING ON WEED CONTROL

Rice straw from a lowland ricefield was used as a mulch on an upland soybean crop grown in a different area. The practice of transporting mulch from one field to another is not recommended because of the time, labor, and cost involved. Ideally, the upland crop should be grown immediately after the rice in the same field, but soil conditions precluded it here.

In both mulched and unmulched plots, decreased row spacing increased soybean yields and decreased weed weight, especially in the unweeded check plots (Table 5). Yield was sixfold higher and weed weight 40 percent lower in unweeded plots that were mulched than in those that were not mulched. In fact, the

mulched, unweeded plots yielded as well as did the unmulched plots that had been weeded once.

Mulching also reduced the number of weedings required. The yields of mulched soybeans weeded once and of those weeded twice were similar. But among the unmulched plots, those weeded once yielded 30 percent less than those weeded twice. Mulching, using residues from a previous crop, appears to have considerable potential as a method of weed control in multiple cropping patterns.

WEED CONTROL IN UPLAND CROPS

A study was conducted to find a herbicide or herbicide combinations that would kill most of the weeds in the crops that are best suited for cropping systems programs in South and Southeast Asia. These herbicides can be tested later as a component of weed control practices for cropping patterns that use all available means of weed control.

Six crops were grown in strips across the slope of a gently rolling farmer's field in Batangas, Philippines. The excessive rains that fell during the first 20 days after planting washed away some soil in some plots and thus modified the results in terms of both effectiveness of herbicides and phytotoxic effects on the crops. Excessive moisture may have modified both weed density and weed regrowth.

The predominant weed species in the experimental site were *Echinochloa colona*, *Ageratum conyzoides*, *Bidens pilosa*, *Commelina benghalensis*, and *Cyperus rotundus*. *E. colona* had the greatest density. Nine herbicides were used. All except fluorodifen gave good initial control of

Table 6. Effects of nine liquid herbicides applied before crops and weeds emerge (3 days after seeding) on the yields of six upland crops in a farmer's field at Cuenca, Batangas, Philippines, 1975 wet season.

Treatment	Rate ^a (kg a.i./ha)	Grain yield ^b (t/ha)							Average
		Rice	Corn	Sorghum	Soybeans	Mung beans	Peanuts ^c		
Butralin	2.0	0 d	2.5 d	1.9 bc	1.7 bc	0.25 cd	1.2 de	1.2	
AC 92553	2.0	1.1 c	3.4 bcd	2.5 b	1.0 d	0.26 cd	1.7 cd	1.7	
Butachlor	2.0	0 d	5.0 ab	1.9 bc	2.1 b	0.28 cd	1.3 cde	1.8	
Piperophos + dimethametryn	1.6 + 0.4	0 d	4.3 bc	2.2 bc	1.9 b	0.56 ab	1.4 cde	1.7	
MON 0358	1.0	1.1 c	6.2 a	2.4 b	2.2 b	0.75 a	2.3 b	2.5	
Oxadiazon	1.0	0.4 d	4.4 bc	1.0 cd	2.1 b	0.29 cd	1.7 cd	1.6	
Fluorodifen	2.0	0 d	0 e	0.4 d	1.3 cd	0.12 d	1.0 e	0.5	
USB 3153	2.0	2.2 b	2.2 d	1.6 bcd	1.0 d	0.38 bc	1.8 c	1.5	
Dinitramine	2.0	1.2 c	3.2 cd	2.9 b	0.3 e	0.29 cd	2.7 ab	1.8	
Hand-weeded check	twice ^d	3.3 a	4.3 bc	4.3 a	2.8 a	0.73 a	3.1 a	3.1	
Untreated check	—	0 d	0 e	0.5 d	0.3 e	1.06 d	1.0 e	0.3	

^aa.i. = active ingredient. ^bAv. of four replications. In a column, any two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^cPod yield at constant moisture. ^dAt 20 and 35 days after crop emergence.

E. colona and *B. pilosa* and moderate control of *C. benghalensis*. The apparently low density of *A. conyzoides* and *C. rotundus*, despite poor control with the herbicides, was caused by the shading effects of the taller crops and by the poorer ability of the two weeds to compete with other vigorous weed species.

Herbicides found promising for upland rice were tested. MON 0358 appeared to be the most promising for all crops. The yields of MON 0358-treated crops averaged 2.5 t/ha. The hand-weeded check gave the highest average grain yield of 3.1 t/ha. Dinitramine and USB 3153 consistently provided good control of most weeds, particularly *E. colona*, in all six crops tested. However, some toxic effects caused yield reductions in several crops. Field observations revealed that four herbicides, MON 0358, butachlor, piperophos + dimethametryn, and butralin, were relatively harmless to all crops except sorghum. The other five herbicides were somewhat toxic to some. The crops, ranked in order of decreasing tolerance to herbicide toxicity, are peanuts, rice, corn, mung beans, soybeans, and sorghum. No chemical was entirely safe for sorghum.

USB 3153 gave consistently good control of weeds in upland rice, but because it caused 40 percent toxicity to the rice crop, the grain yield of the treated rice plants was significantly lower than that of the hand-weeded check (Table 6). In corn, the initial infestation of weeds was so heavy that the untreated control produced no grain. MON 0358 and butachlor gave impres-

sive initial control of weeds, producing grain yields of 6.2 and 5.0 t/ha, respectively. In fact, MON 0358-treated plants gave a significantly higher grain yield than the hand-weeded control. Of the nine herbicides tested, dinitramine, the least toxic to sorghum, produced the highest grain yield (2.9 t/ha). This yield was, however, significantly lower than that of the hand-weeded control. In soybeans, most of the other eight chemicals gave comparable yields; all yields, however, were significantly lower than the grain yield of this legume in the hand-weeded control.

In mung beans, MON 0358 and piperophos + dimethametryn treatments showed excellent selectivity and produced yields similar to those of the hand-weeded check. The herbicides that gave the best performances with peanuts were dinitramine and MON 0358. Of these two, only dinitramine treatment gave yields statistically similar to those of the hand-weeded check.

The results indicate that it is possible to identify herbicides that will control weeds for the six crops being considered for IRRI's cropping systems program. Nevertheless, the objective will be to develop suitable weed management techniques that will require the least amount of herbicides.

Initial screening of herbicides for upland crops. During the 1975 wet season, 21 herbicides were screened with five upland crops (rice, corn, mung beans, soybeans, and peanuts) in an experimental area at IRRI's new farm site, which had few grassy weeds. The predominant weed was *Portulaca oleracea*; some *Cyperus rotundus* was

also present. An experimental herbicide, Antor, looked promising and allowed the highest average grain yield for all crops. The herbicides M-3723 and M-3785 appeared excessively toxic to the legumes, but were safe on the cereals tested. The compound RH 2915, on the other hand, appeared safe on legumes but was toxic to cereals. WL29226 stunted the growth of mung beans at an early stage of growth. Frequent and excessive rains during the early stage caused considerable stand reduction in legumes, explaining the poor yields of soybeans, mung beans, and peanuts.

CROPPING PATTERNS AND LAND AND WATER MANAGEMENT FOR SHIFTING WEED SPECIES

Field experiments initiated in 1974 to study the shifting of weed species by weed management through cropping systems and land and water management were continued during the 1975 crop seasons at the IRRI farm. Under continuous lowland rice, the population of annuals and of the perennial sedge *Scirpus maritimus* increased sharply during the 1975 dry season (Table 7). *C. rotundus*, the perennial sedge that grows primarily under upland culture, was

absent. Without weed control, the grain yields remained stable at about 1.6 t/ha.

The total number of weeds was lower when upland crops were rotated with lowland rice with no weed control than when these crops were grown under continuous lowland rice culture (Table 7). However, the number of *S. maritimus* weeds was lower under alternating dry and wet conditions. *C. rotundus* was present only under upland crop culture. When lowland rice was rotated with upland crops, there was no *C. rotundus* infestation under lowland culture. Furthermore, without weed control, the grain yields of rice were somewhat higher than under continuous lowland rice cropping (Table 7).

In the third cropping pattern in which corn was followed by rainfed, direct-seeded, banded rice, corn yields were 9,500 marketable ears/ha during the 1974 dry season and 13,000 marketable ears/ha during the 1975 dry season (Table 7). Under this system, the buildup of annuals was phenomenal, reaching a total of 3,328 weeds/sq m during the 1974 wet season. During the 1975 wet season, some *S. maritimus* was present under upland crop culture because continuous rains fell during the wet season, keeping standing water in the banded paddies. *C. rotundus* was also present, but because it is shade

Table 7. Population of annual and perennial weeds and yield of rice and other crops in untreated checks under three cropping systems. IRRI, 1974 and 1975 dry and wet seasons.

Crop no.	Season	Crop	Weed population (no./sq m)			Grain yield ^b
			Annuals ^a	Perennials		
				<i>S. maritimus</i>	<i>C. rotundus</i>	
<i>Cropping system I</i>						
1	1974 dry	Lowland rice	415	289	0	3.2
2	1974 wet	Lowland rice	0	310	0	1.6
3	1975 dry	Lowland rice	725	406	0	1.6
4	1975 wet	Lowland rice	340	325	0	1.7
<i>Cropping system II</i>						
1	1974 dry	Corn + peanuts	208	59	90	16,500 + 146
2	1974 wet	Lowland rice	0	236	0	2.6
3	1975 dry	Corn + mung beans	1008	36	32	10,500 + 207
4	1975 wet	Lowland rice	364	167	0	2.2
<i>Cropping system III</i>						
1	1974 dry	Corn	171	65	99	9,500
2	1974 wet	Dry-sown rainfed-banded rice	513	29	38	0
3	1974 wet	Dry-sown rainfed-banded rice	3328	0	0	0
4	1975 dry	Corn	2386	35	53	13,000
5	1975 wet	Dry-sown rainfed-banded rice	1463	20	33	0

^aGrasses, broadleaved weeds, and sedges. ^bFor rice, t/ha; for corn, marketable ears/ha; for peanuts and mung beans, kg/ha.

sensitive, it caused no damage to the corn crop.

During the early stage of rainfed, direct-seeded, banded rice, the nutsedge contributed to the severe competition from annual weeds, preventing grain yields during the 1974 and 1975 dry-seeded rice crops, although crop emergence and initial establishment were adequate.

These results confirm previous findings (1974 Annual Report) that cropping systems involving upland crops with lowland rice contribute to

the shifting of weed species back and forth, making the buildup of any specific perennial weed difficult. Furthermore, shifting lowland to dry land preparations changes the density and composition of weeds, thereby minimizing farmers' risk of total failure in the absence of adequate weed control. This is perhaps one of the most obvious advantages of the cropping systems that involve the growing of more than one kind of crop annually.

Cropping systems program

Plant protection in cropping systems

Entomology Department

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New pest problems are often associated with changes to intensive cropping patterns that involve the annual planting of two or more crops. New intercropping, relay cropping, and sequential cropping patterns alter existing pest populations. The designing of new cropping patterns should therefore include considerations to minimize pest buildup. The active participation of plant protection specialists is desirable when cropping patterns are designed and tested. Pest control recommendations should be determined for the crops grown in their actual sequences or combinations and, if possible, tested under farmers' field conditions.

To be effective, pest management technology must fit the resource base of the farmer. Farmers with small landholdings and little capital cannot be expected to rely solely on pesticides to cope with each pest infestation. Although pesticides shall continue to be the mainstay of pest management programs, the development of more stable and less capital-intensive forms of pest control, such as resistant varieties, biological control, and cultural control practices, will reduce the level of usage of agricultural chemicals.

Initial field testing of the pest management technology currently available to farmers will involve mainly pesticides. More research is needed to develop minimum effective dosages of these pesticides and to integrate pesticides into an overall pest management system for cropping patterns.

WHITE GRUB

The toy beetle *Leucopholis irrorata* (Chev.) as a white grub feeds on the roots of many crops in well-drained soils. In Batangas, Philippines, the grubs can be observed when the rice stubble is plowed under in preparation for a corn crop. A high infestation of the grub in this area stunts rice growth and reduces yields. At harvest, the damaged rice plants, their root systems denuded, are easily pulled from the soil by hand. Fortunately, such cases are rare.

Generally, damage from white grubs occurs in October to corn seedlings which become purple and subsequently die. Most farmers use

no specific control methods against this pest. Some of them plant sugarcane in infested fields because the crop, according to farmers, is more tolerant of the pest. Other farmers use granular insecticides such as lindane to protect corn, but the high cost of this chemical prevents its use at levels that effectively control white grub. A few farmers use rock salt which is believed to be repellent.

Population dynamics. Monitoring the white grub population in three farmers' fields in Luta del Sur, Batangas, from May 1975 to February 1976 revealed that at the end of the dry season, the first soaking rains triggered the appearance of the adult insects. They emerged from the soil in early May and flew to nearby mango trees where they fed on the leaves, causing little damage.

The first adults collected on May 6 were sexually mature; 71 percent of 58 dissected females were gravid. Peak adult activity coinciding with heavy rains occurred in late May 1975 (fig. 1) when more than 1,000 adults/day were collected between May 20 and 29.

The female adults preferred to lay eggs in freshly tilled over crop-covered fields; the grub population of soil samples collected from nearby fallow or sugarcane fields was low. Both the preparation of ricefields and the toy beetle's egg laying coincided with the early rains. The white grubs matured in the rice crop (fig. 1); the first- and second-instar (larval stage) populations peaked in early and late June, respectively.

The long-lived, damaging, third-instar population peaked in November during the corn crop. As the rains ended in December the larvae burrowed deeper into the soil (30 to 55 cm) to pupate. No pupae were found in the soil samples that reached a 20-cm depth, but several deeper holes dug in February succeeded in unearthing pupae in the moist subsoil. There is one generation per year.

Damage. Mango trees located near homesteads along roadways attracted the adults. In October 1975, a survey was made of the visual damage to corn seedlings by white grubs in five cornfields situated next to groves in two villages where farms had a history of white grub infestation. Heavy white grub damage was found

1. Population dynamics of the adult and three larval instars of white grub *Leucopholis irrorata* (Chev.) in three farmers' fields, Luta del Sur, Malvar, Batangas, Philippines, 1975-76.

in two fields where the seedling losses were 27 and 9 percent. Seedling losses in the other survey fields were only 1 to 2 percent.

The white grub problem is more severe in some villages in Batangas than in others. In localities with perennial problems, proportionally less land is planted to rice. Egg-laying adults are not attracted to sugarcane during May and June as the crop already has a closed canopy. Sugarcane is harvested and replanted in the dry season when the adults are inactive. High populations of white grubs occurred in the relatively fewer ricefields within predominantly sugarcane and coconut areas (Luta del Sur, Balele, Natatas, San Fernando). In another village (Cale), proportionally more land is cultivated to rice than to sugarcane or coconut and the white grub is

not a problem. These observations show the close cause-and-effect relationship between the degree of white grub infestation and the dominant cropping patterns within a village.

Insecticide trials. To achieve effective chemical control, insecticides should be incorporated into the soil. In rice the best time to do so is during weed cultivation when the first-instar larvae emerge. In the corn crop the grubs are in the third instar and insecticides could be incorporated during seedbed preparation or during weed cultivation. It was hypothesized that white grub control should be aimed at the rice crop when the larvae are small. It would be expected that lower dosages would suffice. The large third-instar larvae present during the corn crop should require relatively higher dosages to kill.

Rice. Primary tillage is usually done in April or early May and coincides with egg laying. It is too early to apply insecticides at this time (fig. 1). Weed cultivation in Batangas is normally done by the "lithao-kalmot" method (two animal-drawn implements are alternately passed between and diagonally across rice rows, at 4- to 7-day intervals) two or three times before the leaf canopy cover in July.

Lindane 6 G and diazinon 10 G (granules), each at 1 and 4 kg a.i./ha., were broadcast into the open furrows on June 20 after a lithao pass in the field. The furrows were covered 7 days later by the kalmot. After the rice harvest in October, a sample count of the grubs to a depth of 20 cm in the soil showed that lindane at both levels gave 100 percent control. Diazinon gave 24 percent control at the 1 kg a.i./ha level and 45 percent control at the 4 kg a.i./ha level, but these percentages were not significantly better than those for the untreated control.

On June 9, in another field, chlordane 75 EC (emulsifiable concentrate) at 1 and 4 kg a.i./ha, and dieldrin 50 WP (wetttable powder) at 2 kg a.i./ha were jetted into the furrows with a knapsack sprayer without the disperser in the nozzle. Chlordane gave 90 percent control at 1 kg a.i./ha and 100 percent control at 4 kg a.i./ha. Dieldrin gave 99 percent control.

Lindane at 1 kg a.i./ha provided the most inexpensive control; 100 percent control was achieved at a cost of US\$9.86/ha. With chlor-

Table 1. Effects of four soil insecticides to control third-instar white grub (*Leucopholis irrorata*) larvae on corn. San Fernando, Malvar, Batangas, Philippines, 1975.

Chemical	Application rate ^a (kg a.i./ha)	Cost ^b (US\$/ha)	White grubs (no./soil sample ^c)		Control (%)
			Experiment 1 ^d	Experiment 2 ^e	
Diazinon	0.5	6.30	0.63 c		12
	1	12.60		0.57 c	41
	2	25.20	0.33 ab		54
	4	50.30		0.28 ab	71
Lindane	0.5	4.90	0.55 bc		31
	1	9.90		0.50 bc	48
	2	19.70	0.23 a		68
	4	37.40		0.33 abc	65
Carbofuran	0.5	15.60	0.50 bc		31
	1	31.10		0.38 abc	60
	2	62.30	0.25 a		65
	4	124.60		0.45 abc	53
Heptachlor	0.15	7.90	0.57 c		21
	0.3	15.70		0.40 abc	58
	0.6	31.40	0.20 a		72
	0.9	47.20		0.20 a	79
Control			0.72 c	0.96 d	

^aa.i. = active ingredient. ^bDiazinon 10 G, US\$12.41/10 kg; lindane 6 G, \$9.43/16 kg; carbofuran 3 G, \$15.63/16.7 kg; and heptachlor 16.5 EC, \$2.09/946 ml. ^cEach soil sample included 625 sq cm of soil area to a depth of 20 cm. Means in columns followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level of significance. ^dInsecticides were incorporated on November 26, 50 days after seeding during hilling-up (plow is drawn between the rows of corn) weed cultivation. Four replicates/treatment. Av. of three sampling dates: 17, 34, and 42 days after treatment; 8 samples/replicate. Rain (271 mm) fell after the insecticides were applied. ^eInsecticides were incorporated 39 days after seeding. Four replicates/treatment. Av. of two sampling dates: 27 days after treatment, 4 samples/replicate; 32 days after treatment, 12 samples/replicate. Rain (87 mm) fell after the insecticides were applied.

dane, the same level of control was obtained at US\$37.70/ha; 90 percent control, at a cost of US\$9.40. With dieldrin, the cost of 99 percent control was US\$31.24.

Corn. Two experiments were undertaken side by side in San Fernando, on a large cornfield with a high grub population. The insecticides were applied during the hilling-up weed cultivation. The granular formulations were spread at the base of the plants, and the sprayables were jetted as described above. The farmer then covered the insecticides by passing his plow between the rows.

In the first trial, four insecticides were applied on November 14, 39 days after corn seeding. In the second trial, the same insecticides were applied on November 26, 50 days after corn seeding. Diazinon 10 G, lindane 6 G, and carbofuran 3 G were applied at 1 and 4 kg a.i./ha in the first trial, and at 0.5 and 2 kg a.i./ha in the second trial. Heptachlor 16.5 EC was sprayed at 0.3 and 0.9 kg a.i./ha in the first trial, and at 0.15 and 0.6 kg a.i./ha in the second trial.

Higher and more costly levels of insecticides were required to protect the corn crop from damage by the third-instar larvae than to control the first- and second-instar larvae in rice. The

most effective insecticide, heptachlor, at the two highest rates applied, 0.6 and 0.9 kg a.i./ha, provided only 72 and 79 percent control, respectively (Table 1). Ample rain fell (87–271 mm) during the two experiments to activate the insecticides. Lindane at 1 kg a.i./ha, which gave 100 percent control of the first- and second-instar larvae in rice, killed only 48 percent of the third-instar larvae in corn.

Clearly, it would be more economical and more effective to apply insecticides in rice for grub control. Farmers in general are reluctant to buy insecticides because of the cost until they see large numbers of the grubs. The small grubs unearthed during the *lithao-kalmot* weeding operations in Batangas in rice can serve as an early warning, especially in fields where a history of white grub infestation is known. Since *L. irrorata* has only one generation per year, killing the grubs in the rice crop would protect all subsequent crops from damage.

INSECT-PEST COMPLEX AND CHEMICAL CONTROL IN COWPEAS—DRY SEASON

Unusually late rains in December 1974 (≥ 200 mm) and through January 1975 (36 mm) delayed

planting of the third crop, cowpeas, following rice and corn. Insect pests are a limiting factor on legumes, particularly cowpeas; farmers usually spray insecticides to protect this crop. A study was made of the insect-pest complex of cowpeas planted in the dry season, and the effectiveness of the natural enemies and predators of cowpea pests.

Insect-pest complex. Samples of insects were collected weekly between 16 and 72 days after seeding (DAS) from three farmers' fields planted to EG2 cowpeas in Luta del Sur and Natatas, Batangas. The collected insects included aphids, beanfly, flea beetle, other insect pests, and various beneficial predators.

Aphids. The black bean aphid (*Aphis craccivora* Koch) became abundant in all three fields, colonizing a maximum of 15.5 plants out of every 20 in one field, 37 DAS, and 14 plants out of 20 in a second field, 72 DAS. Predators, such as lady beetle, syrphid, and lacewing larvae, were present but were not abundant. No parasitized aphids were observed.

Beanfly. The number of larvae and pupae (per 20 cowpea plants) of the beanfly [*Ophiomyia* (= *Melagromyza*) *phaseoli* (Tryon)] increased steadily from the seedling stage, averaged over three fields (fig. 2). The larval population peaked between 30 and 35 DAS during the vegetative stage of the cowpea development, reaching an average of about 2 larvae/plant. The subsequent pupal population achieved a maximum number during flowering. The habit of the beanfly of ovipositing in young cowpea leaves explains why the population rose during the vegetative stage of the cowpea and declined after flowering when no new leaves were formed.

Two parasites were reared from beanfly pupae. The combined parasitization by *Trigonogastera stella* Giraut (Pteromalidae) and *Eurytoma poloni* Giraut (Eurytomidae) was low, averaging 4.3 percent over the cropping period. *E. poloni* had a fourfold greater recovery than *P. stella*.

Flea beetle. Defoliation by the flea beetle (*Longitarsus manilensis* Walker) was evident in all three fields, but was most prevalent in the field that had the maximum number of black bean aphid pupae. The maximum rating of 3.1 occurred 37 DAS. The damaging adult was

2. Pattern of beanfly larval and pupal infestation of cowpea (EG 2) by plant growth stage, Batangas, 1975 dry season.

active at night, chewing round holes in newly formed leaves.

Minor pests. Less prevalent pests included the leaf miner [*Stomopteryx subsecivella* (Zeller)] with a maximum infestation 73 DAS of 19 larvae/20 plants in the field. Other pests were the bean leaf roller (*Lamprosema indicata* L.), coffee leaf folder (*Homona coffearia* Nietner), bean pod borer [*Maruca testulalis* (Geyer)], and bean lycaenid (*Catochrysops cnejus* Fabr.).

Damage. The black bean aphid was the limiting pest on cowpeas during the dry season in the test area in Batangas. Natural predators were not sufficiently abundant to control the pest effectively. The beanfly attack was tolerated by the cowpea plants as evidenced by the low number of seedlings that died even under poor growing conditions caused by lack of rain. Beanfly and flea beetles were less important in this Batangas area, although they were prevalent at this time of the year. The main aphid buildup plus a lack of rain during the entire cropping period resulted in low yields.

Insecticide control. *Sprayables.* Insecticides were applied biweekly at the manufacturers' recommended rates with a knapsack sprayer on three farmers' fields in Batangas, Philippines. Each treatment was replicated twice within fields. The insect complex was sampled weekly on a per-plant basis.

Endosulfan 35 EC at 1 tablespoon (tbsp)/gal effectively reduced a high infestation of aphids

Table 2. Effects of nine sprayable insecticides on aphids, beanfly, and the yield of cowpeas in the fields of three farmers. Batangas, Philippines, 1975 dry season.

Chemical and formulation ^a	Rate (tbsp/gal.)	Plants with aphid colonies ^b (no./20 plants)	Beanfly larvae plus pupae ^b (no./20 plants)	Yield dry seeds (kg/ha)
<i>Fields of farmer 1^c</i>				
Carbaryl (85 WP)	2	14.7 c	23 a	186 c
Endosulfan (35 EC)	1	3.8 a	44 b	768 a
Methyl parathion (50 EC)	0.5	4.6 a	41 b	494 b
Control		10.6 b	51 b	392 b
<i>Field of farmer 2^c</i>				
Tetrachlorvinphos (75 WP)	1.5	10.1 b	67 a	75 c
Acephate (75 SP)	1	7.0 b	55 a	251 a
Diazinon (40 WP)	2	5.7 a	52 a	225 b
Control		7.4 a	59 a	185 b
<i>Field of farmer 3^c</i>				
Methomyl (80 WP)	1	0.8 a	37 a	380 a
Metasystox (25 EC)	1	2.1 ab	32 a	414 a
Monocrotophos (16.8 EC)	1	3.4 b	28 a	603 a
Control		4.1 b	42 a	255 a

^aWP = wettable powder; EC = emulsifiable concentrate; SP = soluble powder. ^bAv. from seedling through podding stages. ^cMeans in columns followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

on cowpeas and gave the highest crop yield of 768 kg/ha (Table 2). Carbaryl 85 WP at 2 tbsp/gal not only was ineffective against aphids but also reduced the population of the beneficial lady beetle predators. The cowpea yield of 186 kg/ha was significantly lower than the 392 kg/ha of the untreated control. When methyl parathion 50 EC was applied at 0.5 tbsp/gal, the crop yield (494 kg/ha) was not significantly different from that of the control (392 kg/ha).

Like carbaryl, tetrachlorvinphos 75 WP, applied at 1.5 tbsp/gal, gave a cowpea yield (75 kg/ha) lower than that of the control (185 kg/ha). The yield of plots treated with acephate 85 SP (soluble powder) at 1 tbsp/gal was significantly higher than that of the control, although it was relatively low at 251 kg/ha (Table 2). The plots treated with diazinon 40 WP (2 tbsp/gal) yielded 225 kg/ha, which was not significantly higher than the control.

Although the yield of the plots treated with monocrotophos 16.8 EC at 1 tbsp/gal was relatively high (603 kg/ha), it was variable and was not statistically different from that of the control (255 kg/ha). Both methomyl 80 EC (1

tbsp/gal) and metasystox 25 EC (1 tbsp/gal) were effective against aphids, but the cowpea yields from the treated plots (380 and 414 kg/ha, respectively) were not significantly different from that of the control.

Thus, endosulfan appeared to be the most effective insecticide tested, followed by monocrotophos, methyl parathion, and metasystox.

Effects of insecticides on beanfly parasites. Of the nine insecticides tested, endosulfan totally suppressed the beanfly parasites, none of which emerged from 289 pupae held (Table 3). The monocrotophos treatment also reduced the parasitization of the beanfly to 2.5 percent (4.3 percent for the untreated control). The other seven insecticides tested had no apparent effect on parasites. More effective beanfly parasites are known worldwide and may be considered as possible candidates for introduction in the future.

Soil moisture and activation of granular insecticides. Granular insecticides not only can control certain pests, such as the beanfly, more effectively than sprayables, but have other advantages including longer residual effectiveness.

However, under rainfed conditions, granular insecticides, like fertilizers, must dissolve before they can be taken up by the plant roots. Cowpeas can germinate and grow using only the residual soil moisture. Thus, a study was undertaken to determine whether two granular insecticides applied at planting could be activated by residual soil moisture, particularly under conditions of low soil moisture.

On February 5, 1975, EG2 cowpeas were seeded in one field. On some plots (11 m × 9 m), carbofuran 3 G was applied at 2 kg a.i./ha in the furrow with the seeds (basal). On February 18, carbofuran 3 G and metalkamate 3 G were sidedressed on other plots by raking the insecticides into the soil along the cowpea rows. The treatments were replicated twice. Plants were sampled 30, 44, and 50 DAS and the number of beanfly larvae and pupae was recorded. No rain fell during the experiment.

Carbofuran applied basally was activated by the residual soil moisture (which was adequate for seed germination) and prevented the beanfly from establishing itself in the cowpeas up to 30 DAS. No beanfly larvae or pupae were recovered from dissected cowpea plants; this finding was significantly different from the 10 larvae/10 plants in the control plots. Protection with carbofuran broke down at 30 DAS; no significant differences among treatments were found at 44 and 50 DAS.

The two sidedressing treatments were ineffective, giving no protection from the beanfly 30 DAS or afterwards.

NEMATODES

Effect of monoculture on reniform nematode population in seven field crops. The reniform nematode *Rotylenchulus reniformis* is the most prevalent plant-parasitic nematode on non-gramineous field crops in the Philippines. Nematode control by nematicides is costly and is generally beyond the means of local farmers. However, crop rotation as a cultural practice can effectively reduce nematode populations. Crop susceptibility and the rate of nematode buildup under monoculture must be known before rotational patterns can be designed and tested.

Table 3. Effects of nine sprayable insecticides on beanfly parasites on cowpeas in the fields of three farmers. Batangas, Philippines, 1975 dry season.

Chemical	Beanflies reared (no.)	Parasitization ^a (%)
Carbaryl	253	4.3
Endosulfan	289	0
Methyl parathion	376	3.7
Methomyl	218	6.4
Metasystox	182	3.8
Tetrachlorvinphos	596	4.3
Acephate	433	3.7
Diazinon	477	4.0
Monocrotophos	158	2.5
Control	970	4.3

^a 20% *Trigonogastra* (= *Paratrigonogastra*) *stella* Girault (Pteromalidae), 80% *Eurytoma poloni* Girault (Eurytomidae)

Sequential monoculture croppings in field plots containing mostly *R. reniformis* were established from June 1973 to May 1974, as three successive plantings each of corn (DMR 2), sorghum (Cosor 3), bush sitao (Los Baños 2), peanuts (CES 101), and sweet potatoes (BNAS 51), and four successive plantings each of mung beans (MG 50) and soybeans (TK 5). A fallow check was included. Except in the fallow plots, a nematicide (carbofuran) at 7.5 kg a.i./ha was incorporated into the soil during the last cropping period to suppress the active larval and adult stages, and to leave only the carryover egg stage. The extent of the carryover population was then determined by growing mung beans (May to July 1974) as an indicator crop.

The average larval and adult nematode populations in composite samples consisting of 400 cc of water and 1 g plant roots were measured at harvest or at the last priming of each planting. Because the crops have unequal growth durations, the nematode counts were made at different times. The absolute nematode population at any one time could not be determined because of the difficulty of egg extraction.

The initial *R. reniformis* population was low and homogeneous. Prior to the nematicide treatment, nematode buildup in susceptible crops, i.e. mung beans, soybeans, and sweet potatoes, was apparent after each cropping period (fig. 3). The seven crops tested were ranked from most to least susceptible, as follows: mung beans, soybeans, sweet potatoes, peanuts, bush sitao, sorghum, and corn. Three fallow periods successfully checked the popula-

3. Effect of seven field crops grown as monoculture on buildup of *Rotylenchulus reniformis* nematode over successive cropping periods, IIRI, 1974-75.

tion; only four reniform nematodes per sample were recorded in the indicator mung bean crop.

Effect of crop rotation, intercropping, and organic amendments on root-knot nematode. Several nonchemical methods are known to suppress the root-knot nematode *Meloidogyne incognita*. Planting a susceptible crop after a nonhost, such as corn, or leaving the field fallow are two alternatives. Organic soil amendments, such as chicken manure or rice straw compost,

are known to be unfavorable to nematode build-up. Certain plants, such as *Crotalaria* spp. or marigold (*Tagetes* spp.), are nonantagonistic to root-knot nematodes. *Crotalaria* is believed to act as a trap crop: the nematode actively attacks the roots but dies because of failure to complete its life cycle. The mechanism is unknown, but perhaps the marigold roots secrete nematicidal chemicals.

The effects of the following seven cultural control methods, replicated three times between fields, were compared with that of the nematode-susceptible tomato over four cropping periods from August 1974 to October 1975: corn (non-susceptible host), *Crotalaria*-tomato intercrop, marigold-tomato intercrop, marigold alone, tomato with preplant soil application of chicken dung (1 kg/sq m), tomato with preplant soil application of rice straw compost (0.4 kg/sq m), and fallow. The effect of each treatment over time was determined by forming subplot combinations through a rotation of each treatment on separate plots with tomato after one, two, and three cropping periods. Nematode population was determined from composite samples, each consisting of 450 cc soil and 1 g roots.

All treatments reduced the number of root-knot nematodes after three cropping periods (fig. 4). Best control was provided by corn and

4. Suppressive effects of seven cultural practices over three cropping periods on root-knot nematode infestation of soils initially planted to susceptible tomatoes. IIRI, 1974-75.

by the *Crotalaria*-tomato intercrop, followed by marigold (either as an intercrop or alone), chicken manure, and fallow. The rice straw compost incorporated into the soil before planting gave the least control. At least two cropping periods of all nematode-suppressive treatments,

except fallow, were needed to significantly reduce the root-knot nematode population. Three successive fallow periods were needed to significantly check the nematode population on a succeeding susceptible tomato crop.

Cropping systems program

Varietal testing

Multiple Cropping Department

BATANGAS OUTREACH **408**

PANGASINAN OUTREACH **410**

ILOILO OUTREACH **410**

A major component of a program designed to increase cropping intensity and yield per unit area on small farms is the development and identification of crops adapted for intensive cropping. Cropping systems research at IRRI focuses on grain and root crops: rice, corn, sorghum, soybeans, mung beans, cowpeas, peanuts, sweet potatoes, and cassava. Breeding programs for these crops are under way at a number of international agricultural research institutes and national research centers.

The University of the Philippines at Los Baños (UPLB), with funding from the International Development Research Centre of Canada, screens varieties and lines developed by national programs and by international agricultural research institutes and national centers. UPLB tests upland crops, such as corn, sorghum, soybeans, mung beans, sweet potatoes, tomatoes, and eggplant, for production characteristics of major importance in intensive cropping.

In addition to its major program of Genetic Evaluation and Utilization (GEU) to develop improved rice varieties, IRRI screens two upland crops, peanuts and cowpeas. The most promising varieties and lines from the screening are tested, together with locally developed varieties, in the Cropping Systems Network (CSN) of experimental sites throughout South and Southeast Asia. In addition, IRRI provides trials to institutions and organizations working on cropping systems in countries collaborating with the CSN. In 1975, between September and December, 85 trials were distributed to seven countries (Table 1).

The following organizations collaborated in the varietal testing program of the CSN in 1975:

Bangladesh Rice Research Institute, Bangladesh; the Central Research Institute for Agriculture, Indonesia; IRRI outreach sites in Batangas, Iloilo, and Pangasinan in cooperation with the Philippine Bureau of Plant Industry (BPI), Mindanao Institute of Technology, and Mountain View College, Philippines; Agricultural Research Station, Maha Illuppallama, Sri Lanka; Agricultural Research Institute and Office of the General Manager for Research, Burma; Malaysian Agricultural Research and Development Institute, Malaysia; and Thailand Department of Agriculture, Kasetsart University, and Khon Kaen University, Thailand.

The most promising varieties and lines were evaluated in the Philippines at the three outreach sites (Batangas, Iloilo, and Pangasinan) and at the IRRI headquarters in Los Baños, Philippines. Trials for each crop were conducted at the time the crop fitted appropriately into the cropping pattern. Rice was tested during the regular rice season under both upland and lowland conditions, and corn was evaluated during the wet season and before and after transplanted rice. Trials of rice and of corn before rice in Iloilo and during the wet season in Batangas are described in this report. Other upland crop trials were planted in November and December 1975 and will be harvested in early 1976.

BATANGAS OUTREACH

The upland rice variety currently used in the IRRI cropping pattern studies in Batangas is the local variety Dagge. Improved varieties suited to the conditions of cultural management and environment in Batangas are not available. Several promising improved varieties from the

Table 1. Trials (85) of lines and varieties of seven upland crops distributed to seven countries in South and Southeast Asia during 1975.

Upland crop	Entries (no.)	Trials (no.)							Total
		Thailand	Indonesia	Sri Lanka	Burma	Malaysia	Bangladesh	Philippines	
Corn	11	2	2	1	2	—	1	6	13
Sorghum	14	4	2	1	2	1	1	6	16
Soybeans	15	4	2	1	2	1	1	4	14
Mung beans	10	6	2	1	2	1	1	6	18
Peanuts	10	—	—	1	2	—	2	1	5
Cowpeas	11	4	2	1	2	1	1	6	16
Sweet potatoes	10	"	—	—	—	—	"	3	3

"Seed increase.

Table 2. Yield trials of promising IRRI selections under upland direct-seeded (UDS) conditions (Cale, Batangas, Philippines) and lowland transplanted (LTP) conditions (Manaoag, Pangasinan, Philippines) during the 1975 wet season.

Selection	Rank		Grain yield (t/ha)		Maturity (days)		Lodging (%)		Ht (cm)	Rice blast rating ^a
	UDS	LTP	UDS ^b	LTP ^c	UDS	LTP	UDS	LTP		
IR2071-625-1	1	5	3.47	4.45	116	109	0	0	61.2	2.0
IR28	2	7	3.16	4.32	107	104	0	0	77.7	2.3
IR2071-124-6	3	9	2.92	4.02	128	115	0	0	60.1	1.3
IR2061-465-1	4	4	2.63	4.49	113	109	0	0	69.0	1.7
IR2071-636-5	5	8	2.45	4.17	110	107	0	0	61.6	1.3
IR2153-14-1	6	10	2.03	4.02	119	103	0	21	65.5	2.0
IR30	7	12	2.03	3.08	122	105	0	0	67.4	2.7
IR2070-414-3	8	1	2.03	4.95	134	113	0	60	77.9	1.0
IR2328-300-2	9	6	1.91	4.44	128	117	0	0	58.9	2.3
IR2071-529-6	10	11	1.63	3.81	124	113	0	0	61.8	1.0
IR2061-628-1	11	2	1.24	4.75	120	109	0	0	70.1	2.0
IR1561-228-3	12	3	0.89	4.73	120	113	0	0	60.3	1.7
Dagge (UDS check)			2.66		123					

^aRice blast rating: 1 = resistant, 5 = susceptible. ^bLSD (0.05) = 0.90 t/ha; cv (%) = 19.8. ^cLSD (0.05) 0.58 t/ha; cv (%) = 7.8.

Table 3. Yields and agronomic characteristics of early corn varieties evaluated at Cale, Batangas, Philippines, during the 1975 wet season.

Pedigree	Yield ^a (t/ha)	Days to silking	Ht (cm)		Husk cover ^b	Lodging (%)	
			Plant	Ear		Stalk	Root
Thai Composite 1 Early	6.16	49	205	114	5.0	4.8	10.6
TC #1 DMR/Medok F ₃	5.55	45	211	104	4.0	7.7	7.1
Medium Early Composite 1	5.20	49	239	142	5.0	7.1	3.6
Philippine DMR Composite 2	5.04	50	194	120	1.0	10.0	5.5
(TC #1 DMR/Medok F ₃)/TC #1 DMR	5.02	49	219	128	5.0	5.7	4.7
TC #1 DMR/Penjalinan F ₃	4.97	45	216	128	5.0	10.1	5.0
G. Keitas	4.52	47	228	136	5.0	17.5	13.1
TC #1 (Thai Corn Early/Philippine DMR 1 F ₃)	4.48	49	224	137	5.0	12.8	5.6
Medium Early Composite 2	4.43	48	218	135	5.0	13.6	12.7
Philippine DMR Composite 1	4.36	49	215	131	2.0	22.5	11.5
G. Kretek	4.21	37	221	118	5.0	5.0	8.8
Tinumbaga	3.98	52	209	126	2.0	2.9	11.6
Early DMR Composite 2	3.86	49	211	120	4.0	9.9	6.9
G. Madura	3.85	38	173	93	5.0	1.5	8.1
Early DMR Composite 1	3.11	47	209	116	5.0	4.0	6.5

^aLSD (0.05) = 1.87 t/ha; cv (%) = 19.5. ^bHusk rating 1 to 5: 1 = tight, 5 = loose husk.

breeding programs of UPLB, BPI, and IRRI were evaluated in a replicated trial called the Farmers Evaluation of New Selections Applied Research Trial (FENSART), which is coordinated by UPLB. Two varieties, C166-135 and C171-136, tested in the 1975 wet season in Batangas, gave the best yields with 4.60 and 4.59 t/ha, respectively, about 72 percent more than that of Dagge (2.65 t/ha). The seed of both varieties is being increased for cropping pattern experiments in 1976.

The most promising lowland rice varieties developed by IRRI were also tested under upland conditions. Despite the drought, the yield of IR2071-625-1 was superior to that of Dagge,

the local check (Table 2).

Farmers plant corn, in addition to rice, in the wet season; some farmers intercrop corn with rice. In a trial of early-maturing corn varieties during the wet season, several varieties showed higher yields and matured earlier than the local variety Tinumbaga (Table 3). Although the yield of Thai Composite Early was better than that of Thai Composite (TC) # 1 DMR/Medok F₃, the latter is earlier and resistant to downy mildew (the major disease of corn in the Philippines and some parts of Indonesia). Seeds of TC # 1 DMR/Medok F₃ were increased so that the variety can be used in cropping pattern experiments in the 1976 wet and dry seasons.

PANGASINAN OUTREACH

In rainfed lowland rice areas that have 4 to 5 consecutive months with 200 mm rainfall per month, two crops of rice can be achieved by dry seeding (planting like upland rice) early-maturing varieties for the first crop, and transplanting or wet seeding the second crop. A dry-seeded FENSART yield trial was conducted in Pangasinan to identify early-maturing varieties of rice adapted to that type of culture. Zinc and iron deficiency problems caused very low yields. The most promising entry under these conditions was the IRRI selection IR1561-228-3, which is widely used in the dry seeding program of the Philippine Government. The early-maturing varieties IR28 and IR30 gave the lowest yields.

In a FENSART transplanted yield trial, IR2070-747 yielded 4.98 t/ha and IR28 4.76 t/ha (Table 4), but IR28 matured 36 days earlier. The yield and maturity of IR28 were superior to those of IR26 and IR30.

The promising IRRI selections were also evaluated in Pangasinan. The yields ranged from 3.08 to 4.95 t/ha (Table 2). Although IR2070-414-3 gave the best yield, it showed the highest percentage (60%) of lodging. All rice varieties tested in this trial matured earlier than the same varieties tested under upland conditions in Batangas. In the transplanted yield trials in Pangasinan, seedlings were dipped in a

Table 4. FENSART transplanted rice yield trials. Manaoag, Pangasinan, Philippines, 1975 wet season.

Selection	Yield ^a (t/ha)	Maturity (days)	White head ^b rating	Rice blast ^c rating
IR2070-747	4.98	135	0.9	1.0
IR28	4.76	99	3.0	1.7
IR2071-625-1	4.35	117	4.7	2.0
IR2071-588-5	4.27	134	0.7	2.3
IR2153-26-3	4.17	122	3.9	1.0
IR2061-231-2	4.07	130	1.0	2.3
C476-1	4.00	121	2.4	1.0
IR2035-290-2	3.84	139	0.5	2.0
C131-129	3.74	128	2.1	1.7
MRC-8	3.59	133	1.0	1.0
IR26	3.54	123	3.3	3.0
IR30	3.44	118	2.1	1.3
BPI Ri-2	3.42	120	3.9	1.0
C463-G	3.24	128	1.8	1.0
IR2070-423-2	2.49	135	0.8	1.3

^aLSD (0.05) = 0.50 t/ha; cv (%) = 17.6. ^bOn a scale of 1 to 5: 1 = resistant, 5 = susceptible. ^cOn a scale of 1 to 5: 1 = resistant, 5 = susceptible.

Table 5. Transplanted rice yield trials of early selections conducted as the second crop. Tigbauan, Iloilo, Philippines, 1975.

Selection	Maturity (days)	Yield (t/ha)
IR2061-427-1	110	5.80
IR28	104	5.70
BPI Ri-2	110	5.69
IR2061-628-1	108	5.50
IR2070-464-1	110	5.48
IR2071-625-1	108	5.40
IR1561-228-3	110	5.37
IR2061-465-1	110	5.27
IR30	102	5.18
IR2070-414-3	110	4.78
IR2071-636-5	108	4.75
IR2159-338-3	110	4.73
IR2061-522-6	110	4.38
IR747-B2-6-3	96	4.13
IR2070-820-2-3	110	4.09
IR2681-34-5	110	3.82

zinc oxide suspension to reduce the effects of zinc deficiency commonly encountered in soils of the area.

ILOILO OUTREACH

In a FENSART dry-seeded rice yield trial conducted in Iloilo, the yield (5.23 t/ha) of Kapopoy, a local variety, was about as good as or better than that of the improved varieties despite its relatively high percentage of lodging (15%). Of the 12 rice selections tested, IR1529-430-3 had the maximum yield (5.30 t/ha). Moreover, Kapopoy matured in 102 days, as did the early-maturing variety IR28. Two other local varieties, Speed 70 and Camoros, gave very low yields (2.67 and 2.63 t/ha, respectively).

The dry-seeded trial was followed in September by a transplanted yield trial of 16 promising early-maturing selections under rainfed conditions. All entries except BPI Ri-2 came from IRRI (Table 5). IR2061-427-1 gave the highest yield (5.80 t/ha) with 110 days to maturity, followed by IR28 (5.70 t/ha). Several of the early selections showed promise in this trial despite the drought during booting. Using IR28 during both the first and second seasons, it might be possible to achieve a yield of 10.3 t/ha annually in rainfed lowland areas where the climate is similar to that of Iloilo.

A FENSART transplanted yield trial conducted in Iloilo at the time farmers normally transplant their rice included entries from the

Table 6. Yields and agronomic characteristics of early corn varieties at Tigbauan, Iloilo, Philippines, planted before the 1975 wet season.

Rank	Pedigree	Yield ^a (t/ha)	Days to silking	Ht (cm)		Husk cover ^b	Lodging (%)	
				Plant	Ear		Stalk	Root
1	Philippine DMR Comp. 2	6.27	52	266	107	1.0	3.9	0
2	Thai Comp. 1 Early	5.58	54	262	110	1.0	4.7	3.1
3	Philippine DMR Comp. 1	5.39	53	261	109	1.0	2.6	0
4	Medium Early Comp. 1	5.38	49	235	92	1.0	5.3	0
5	Philippine DMR 1	5.35	53	260	112	1.0	6.6	0
6	Medium Early Comp. 2	5.03	51	253	98	1.0	4.2	0
7	Early DMR Comp. 2	5.00	50	247	91	1.0	6.0	3.0
8	Orange (local)	4.88	48	237	94	1.0	3.1	0
9	White (local)	4.73	52	252	95	1.0	2.7	0
10	Early DMR Comp. 1	4.57	50	241	95	1.0	6.0	0

^aLSD (0.05) = 1.74 t/ha; cv (%) = 1.59. ^bHusk rating 1 to 5: 1 = tight, 5 = loose husk.

breeding programs of UPLB, BPI, and IRRI. IR2071-1-252 gave the highest yield (4.3 t/ha) as it did in Batangas under upland conditions (2.5 t/ha). Although the three local varieties Speed 70, Kapopoy, and Camaros were early, their yields were lower than those of the improved rice varieties.

Some farmers in Iloilo plant corn in April and

May before planting the main rice crop. In an evaluation of promising early-maturing varieties of corn from the UPLB breeding program (Table 6), Philippine DMR Comp. 2 gave the highest yield (6.27 t/ha). It is being used in cropping pattern studies in Iloilo and Batangas, Philippines.

Cropping systems program

Economics research on cropping systems

Agricultural Economics Department (with the cooperation of the Multiple Cropping, Weed Science, and Entomology components of the Cropping Systems Program)

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Economic research on cropping systems in 1975 can be summarized in three categories: 1) developments in the methodology of research, 2) findings of descriptive studies, and 3) design and testing of new cropping patterns. Categories 2 and 3 embody three major phases of research—description, design, and testing—which are common to all the disciplines cooperating in the Cropping Systems Program. Economics studies have yet to be completed in the fourth major phase (introduction of new multiple cropping techniques) of cropping systems research.

METHODOLOGY FOR ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF CROPPING SYSTEMS

Advances in techniques of research realized in 1975 relate chiefly to: 1) data collection and processing, 2) calibration of instruments for information gathering, and 3) improvement of techniques for describing existing cropping systems to help in designing and testing new cropping patterns.

Data collection and processing. Construction of time series and cross-sectional, farm-level data sets to support other projects has received high priority in the past 3 years. In 1975, procedures to better accommodate automatic processing of data from different environments were established. A multiple-purpose form was used as a daily farm record (completed by farmers with the assistance of field technicians), a summary sheet for basic field analyses, and a code sheet for electronic encoding.

In the uniform coding schemes for crops and farm operations, certain digits in the code numbers are locale specific and other digits denote general classes of crops or operations for all locales.

Numbering of farmers' plots¹ was complex, but critical for identifying cropping patterns.² A five-digit system was devised to indicate the parcels³ within which crops (also intercrops and fallow) occur, and to identify the areas within parcels having concurrent or sequential differences in management.

¹ A plot is defined as a continuous land surface on which a single annual cropping pattern is planted.² An annual cropping pattern is tentatively defined as the temporal and spatial arrangement of cultivars which are uniformly managed at all times during one year.

³ A parcel is a continuous area of land under one farmer's management and one form of tenure.

Table 1. Comparison of labor time required for various operations on crops as estimated by stopwatch (SE) and as estimated from farmers' reports (FR). Cale, Batangas, Philippines, 1974-75.

Crop	Labor (man-days ^a /ha) required for																			
	Plowing		Harrowing		Furrowing		Planting		Ferti- lization		Hilling up		Spraying		Off- barring		Harvesting		Total	
	SE	FR	SE	FR	SE	FR	SE	FR	SE	FR	SE	FR	SE	FR	SE	FR	SE	FR	SE	FR
Sorghum	4.1	6.1	.9	2.3	1.4	1.9	3.6	5.7	1.5	4.2	1.3	1.5	N	N	1.7	2.9	18.6	23.5	32.5	48.1
Glutinous corn	3.6	4.2	1.2	2.8	1.1	1.3	4.9	5.8	2.8	4.7	1.9	2.3	N	N	2.0	2.2	6.6	7.2	21.4	26.0
Field corn	3.6	3.9	1.2	2.2	1.2	2.5	3.8	6.0	2.6	4.4	1.8	2.1	N	N	N	N	3.6	7.9	17.0	29.0
Sweet potato + corn	4.6	4.7	1.2	4.3	1.1	3.3	5.6	14.0	3.4	5.8	2.0	2.6	N	N	2.2	2.0	—	63.0 ^b	19.3	36.7
Mung beans	6.5	.9	1.9	1.3	1.8	4.7	5.4	1.9	2.9	N	N	3.3	5.8	2.4	3.0	43.4	48.0	58.5	75.3	
Soybeans	3.9	4.8	1.2	3.2	1.2	1.3	4.9	5.0	1.5	—	N	N	1.2	2.0	1.7	3.0	14.4	19.0	34.8	55.5
Cowpeas	4.5	6.6	1.2	3.8	1.7	1.7	5.0	6.7	2.0	2.1	N	N	8.3	13.6	1.5	1.3	86.6	105.8	102.5	141.6
Peanuts	4.4	2.9	1.8	3.8	1.4	1.6	9.32	12.5	1.5	3.2	N	N	N	N	1.7	4.6	N	63.7 ^c	18.9	28.6
Cowpeas after glutinous corn	1.9	6.5	1.5	3.2	1.3	2.4	3.9	7.2	1.3	2.5	1.4	1.1	0.7	0.8	1.4	1.1	26.5	31.8	42.8	55.5

^aOne man-day equals 8 man-hours. N = none; — = missing data. ^bNot included in the total man-days required by sweet potato and corn intercrop. ^cNot included in the total man-days required by peanuts.

Calibration of instruments. Since farmers' estimates of quantitative variables are frequently sources of information for analyzing cropping systems, it is desirable to test their accuracy.

Measurement of labor time. Farmers' estimates of labor time required for nine major farm operations (Table 1) were compared to stopwatch measurements of the same operations on seven crops planted in Cale, Batangas, Philippines, during the 1974-75 cropping season. The crops were sorghum, corn, sweet potatoes, soybeans, mung beans, peanuts, and cowpeas. The stopwatch measurements of field operations excluded time spent preparing for field work, going to the field, and resting. Because the farmers' estimates included these components, farmers' estimates were consistently higher than the stopwatch estimates. When the time required for each operation is converted to a proportion of total labor requirement, however, the methods of measurement are quite comparable, as seen in sorghum (Table 2).

Differences in management among nine crops and crop combinations are reflected in different labor requirements (Table 1). The greatest differences between farmers' and stopwatch estimates were for jobs requiring the shortest field time, suggesting that a minimum amount of labor, perhaps to prepare for field work, is associated with each operation (Table 2). Regression analysis was used to investigate the differences.

A linear equation (below) was fitted by least squares regression to show the relationship between stopwatch time and farmers' estimate:

$$\text{Farmer's estimate} = 0.33 + 1.67 (\text{stopwatch estimate})$$

Table 2. Labor time required for the culture of sorghum as estimated by stopwatch and as estimated from farmers' reports. Cale, Batangas, Philippines, 1974-75.

Operation	Stopwatch		Farmers' report		Stopwatch estimate × 100 Farmers' estimate	Labor requirement (% total)	
	Observations (no.)	Av. time (man-days/ha)	Observations (no.)	Av. time (man-days/ha)		Stop-watch	Farmers' report
Plowing (2x)	12	4.1	11	6.1	67	13	13
Harrowing	5	0.9	11	2.3	13	1	5
Furrowing	8	1.4	11	1.9	74	4	4
Planting	6	3.6	11	5.7	63	11	12
Fertilization	8	1.5	11	4.2	36	5	8
Hilling up	6	1.3	11	1.5	87	4	3
Off-barring	2	1.7	11	2.9	59	5	6
Harvesting	4	18.6	11	23.5	79	57	49
Total	51	32.5	88	48.1	68	100	100

The constant term (0.33) can be interpreted as the average time required by Cale, Batangas, farmers to prepare for field work and to go to and from the field (0.33 man-day or 2.6 man-hours). The coefficient (1.67) can be interpreted as the expansion factor to be applied to stopwatch estimates to adjust for rest time and other factors associated with field time. The R² of the regression was 0.66 and both coefficients were significantly different from zero at the 95-percent level of probability.

Measurement of land area. Farmers reported in baseline surveys the areas of parcels of land that compose the farms they operate. Steel tape measurements of these areas were subsequently taken and compared with the measurements reported by the farmers. Farmers' estimates of the areas of 182 parcels of land in Manaoag, Pangasinan, Philippines, were an average 8 percent higher than tape measurements. Their estimates of the areas of rented parcels (payment is made to the landlord according to parcel size) were 30 percent higher than those based on tape measurements (Table 3). This suggests that farmers operating land under the per-hectare rental system have perhaps been led to believe that the areas they rent are larger than they actually are. There is no expected gain or loss to owners or share-tenants resulting from errors in estimating land area. There are also mortgaging tenants who pay their landlords according to the area they lease, but this new form of tenancy is supervised by the Government of the Philippines under the land reform law and the land has been surveyed.

The differences between farmers' estimates and objective measurements of parcel areas are

Table 3. Errors in farmers' estimates of parcel sizes, by tenure and by parcel size. Manaoag, Pangasinan, Philippines. 1975.

Parcel size (ha), form of tenure	Parcels (no.)	Total area of parcels (ha)		Error	
		Farmers' estimate	Actual	Absolute	Percent
<i>By parcel size</i>					
0.01–0.50	99	35.79	31.89	3.9	12.7
0.51–1.00	63	47.42	44.26	3.2	7.1
1.01–1.50	14	19.90	18.85	1.1	5.6
1.51–2.00	6	9.69	9.37	0.3	3.4
<i>By tenure</i>					
Share-tenant	110	74.34	69.60	4.7	6.8
Owned	51	23.42	21.86	1.6	7.1
Leased	11	9.21	8.39	0.8	9.8
Rented	10	5.83	4.48	1.3	20.0
All farms	182	112.80	104.37	8.4	8.1

inversely related to parcel size. If the percentages of difference shown in Table 3 are found to be fairly constant from region to region, they can be used to obtain more accurate area estimates based on farmer responses.

Descriptive techniques. The descriptive phase of economics research on cropping systems focuses on: 1) determining in a locale the baseline values of variables that will later be used to measure the impact of cropping systems research, 2) assessing on-farm and off-farm conditions to be considered in designing new cropping patterns, 3) measuring the costs and returns of present cropping patterns to obtain a basis for evaluating new cropping patterns, and 4) identifying present multiple cropping practices that have wider applicability.

Cropping indices. The two additions to the standard techniques used in the descriptive phase of research are the Cropping Intensity Index (CII) and plot conformation analysis. CII values range between 0 and 1 and indicate the proportion of area-time available to a farmer that is used in crop production.⁴ The more common measure is the Multiple Cropping Index (MCI) which indicates the average number of crops per year on a land area regardless of the length of the growing period of crops. The CII is purely a measure of land use intensity while the MCI additionally reflects management intensity.

Plot conformation. Plot conformation refers

⁴ Merle Menegay, "Socio-Economic Factors Affecting Cropping Systems for selected Taiwan Farmers," Proceedings of the Cropping Systems Workshop, March 18–20, 1975. IRR1, Los Baños, Laguna.

to the arrangement of the soil surface and permanent structures attached thereto; it can be used as an indicator of conditions in the physical or economic environment, such as rainfall level and variability, slope, soil texture, or relative costs of inputs or products, or both. Plot conformation constrains the subsequent establishment of cropping systems. Such conformations as high rice terraces, trellises, and the *sorjan* method (regularly arranged upland and lowland surfaces) differentially affect the choice of crops and feasible power sources.

In 1975, the identification and description of plot conformations found in rainfed, rice-based systems was initiated. The principal measurements taken on the bunded paddy conformation are 1) thickness of bunds and height of both sides of the bunds, 2) dimensions of the enclosed growing surface, and 3) slope of the field. The height of the bund appears to be related to the variability of rainfall; higher bunds are found in Iloilo, Philippines, where the rainfall is more variable than in Manaoag, Pangasinan, Philippines, where bunds are lower.

Further studies. Methods for the economic analysis of cropping systems need improvement far beyond the few descriptive techniques that were developed in 1975 and presented above. A working group which met in Indonesia in November recommended the following guidelines for developing economics methodology.

- Analytical techniques for meeting the objectives of the four research phases—description, design, testing, and introduction of new multiple cropping technology

—should be made widely available in a looseleaf handbook to permit easy revision and additions.

- Sufficient methodology should be executable under field conditions to permit quick determination of the adequacy of data and to help field workers understand the research objectives.
- The methodology should include a range of sophistication tailored to low and high levels of the financial and human capacities to conduct economic research.

Part of the September 1976 Symposium on Cropping Systems to be held at IRRI, Los Baños, Philippines, has been planned to meet, in part, these requirements.

DESCRIPTIVE RESEARCH: FINDINGS

Resource availability and use. The ultimate test of a new pattern is its adoption by farmers. A new pattern's greater profitability compared with that of the prevailing pattern appears to be a major factor leading to its adoption. A number of expected and unexpected phenomena may affect the relative profitability of patterns, but the utilization of cheaper resources improves the potential profitability of a cropping pattern. Idle or nearly idle resources are implicitly cheaper, and new patterns that apply them are likely to be more profitable.

Economists and biological scientists are collaborating to identify underutilized resources and to incorporate them into new cropping patterns. While the major focus is on land, rainfall, and labor, increased attention is being directed towards cash liquidity, management, and power.

Water management. Investigations to improve the efficiency of using rainfall through multiple cropping patterns based on direct-seeded rice or early-maturing varieties, or both, were initiated in 1975. An assessment was undertaken of the methods used by farmers in Manaoag, Pangasinan, Philippines, to manage water in rainfed and partially irrigated regimes. Water depth gauges were placed in 63 paddies that met one of these three conditions: 1) high water table and heavy soil, 2) high water table and medium soil, and 3) deep water table and

medium soil. For studying each soil-water combination, seven gauges were placed at each of three relative plot elevations, high, medium, and low. The differences among these elevations were small due to the gradual slope in the area. Water depths were recorded daily and crop cuts were taken.

The average water depth at the intermediate plot elevation tended to be lower, particularly 3 to 5 days after rainfall. Concurrently, the yields at the intermediate position tended to be lower than those in either of the two other elevations. However, the differences in yield and water depth were not statistically significant. To better identify the relationship of farmers' water control practices to rainfall, relative plot elevations, plot conformation, soil texture, depth of water table, and yield, we plan a similar study where differences between relative plot elevations are greater.

Land resource. Farm size averages for three research sites in the Philippines (Batangas, Iloilo, and Pangasinan) were similar (0.93, 1.45, and 2.22 ha, respectively). However, fragmentation was more pronounced in Pangasinan, where the average number of parcels per farm was 4.4 (2.2 in Iloilo, and 3.0 in Batangas). In Pangasinan, the degree of fragmentation and the average size of the parcels appeared to be inversely related (Table 4).

Findings from the study of 50 farms in Batangas do not support the notion that farming intensity is inversely related to farm size. Variation in the Cropping Intensity Indices and

Table 4. Average parcel size by number of parcels per farm at Manaoag, Pangasinan, Philippines, 1975.

Parcels on the farm (no.)	Farms (no.)	Total parcels (no.)	Total area of parcels (ha)	Av. size of parcels (ha)
1	4	4	3.57	0.89
2	12	24	16.55	0.69
3	5	15	9.93	0.66
4	12	48	30.69	0.63
5	5	25	14.31	0.57
6	4	24	12.11	0.50
7	1	7	3.35	0.47
8	2	16	5.99	0.37
9	1	9	3.22	0.35
10	1	10	4.65	0.46
All farms	47	182	104.37	0.57

Table 5. Cropping systems in Cale, Batangas, Philippines, and indices of cropping intensity, 1974–75.

System no.	Crops by season		Farms (no.)	Av. farm size (ha)	Cropping Intensity Index ^b	Multiple Cropping Index ^c
	First	Second				
I	Rice	Corn	5	0.97	72	192
II	Rice, FV ^a	Corn, vine, vine-root intercrop	13	1.28	70	185
III	Rice, trellis	Corn, vine, vine-root intercrop, trellis	6	0.86	73	209
IV	Rice, FV	Corn, vine, vine-root intercrop, trellis	11	1.50	71	169
V	Rice, corn, FV	Corn, vine, vine-root intercrop, trellis	12	2.15	65	174
VI	Rice, sugarcane, trellis	Sugarcane, trellis	3	0.29	85	191

^aFV = fruit vegetable, i.e. eggplant, tomato, chili. ^bCropping Intensity Index shows the percentage that utilized land, expressed in hectare-weeks, is of total available land, similarly expressed. ^cMultiple Cropping Index shows the average number of crops per year obtained from the total cultivable area times 100.

the Multiple Cropping Indices among the six cropping systems studied was slightly, but insignificantly, associated with average farm size (Table 5). With each cropping system, the cropping indices varied among farmers because of different proportional mixes of the crops. Thus, it was possible to compare cropping indices with farm size (ranging from 0.5 ha to 2.5 ha) independently of the cropping system. No relation between farm size and cropping indices was evident.

In a study of 182 parcels of land operated by the 50 sample farmers in Cale, Batangas (1973–74), estimates of productivity were made using least squares regression of the total value of production on land, labor, and fertilizer. The coefficient representing land productivity was insignificant, but the coefficient of the labor input variable was high and statistically significant, indicating that in Cale the additional care given to crops through additional labor is a more certain method of raising production than is increasing the crop area.

High marginal returns to labor in Cale, in theory at least, may result from the high natural fertility of the land resource. The average of upland rice yields on 25 randomly sampled farms for 3 crop years from 1973 through 1975 was 1.7 t/ha (average of 1.9, 1.0, and 2.3 t/ha); about 1 t/ha was the peak national average between 1965 and 1970. Yields of upland rice in Cale equal the national average for lowland rice.

Labor resource. The fact that labor is a binding

constraint, while land apparently is not over the range of farm sizes examined (0.5 to 2.5 ha), carries two implications concerning labor utilization: 1) more labor can profitably be applied, perhaps through improved design of multiple cropping patterns, and 2) at the present stage of development, the effect on production of changes in the level of labor input cannot be offset by corresponding changes in the amount of land used (nonsubstitutability of land and labor over the observed range). The farmer's choice of the amount of labor to use per hectare is not associated with the level of land use. The economic stimulus is to use more labor regardless of farm size.

Increasing labor use through multiple cropping patterns. The estimates of marginal value productivity of labor noted above were based on regressions in which the total annual use of labor was entered as the labor variable. Labor use on the farm fluctuates during the year, and it is not clear from the preceding analysis during what periods of the year labor was added on the more intensive farms. If farmers increase the use of labor in nonpeak periods, then this increased use is reflected in a lower variance of labor utilization across weeks. In fact, negative, though low, correlation coefficients between the total labor use and variance were estimated from the 1973–74 and 1974–75 Cale data. Moreover, reduced variance in weekly labor use was found to be associated with lower value productivity of labor. Within existing systems, farmers appear

1. Weekly labor use in the rice-corn cropping system. Cale, Batangas Philippines, 1973-74.

to have responded to high marginal returns to labor by adding labor-using crop activities in nonpeak periods.

Further reduction of the variance of labor use can be accomplished by adopting multiple cropping patterns that distribute labor requirements more evenly throughout the year. Cale farmers mainly use vegetable cropping patterns

to even out their labor use (fig. 1 and 2) because of the ready access to metropolitan Manila markets (about 50 km from Cale).

Nonsubstitutability of land and labor. With the marginal value product of labor well above the wage rate for all patterns, increase in labor use is not likely to be associated with farm size or lower land-use intensity. Comparison of labor

2. Weekly labor use in the rice-corn-vegetable system. Cale, Batangas, Philippines, 1973-74.

3. Total weekly labor use by source, 36 farmers, Cale, Batangas, Philippines, 1975.

use per hectare in Cale, Batangas, Philippines, in 1974 with farm size and land use showed no association with farm size, but revealed a generally positive association between the CII and man-hours of labor per hectare. CII values of 70, 71, 72, and 85 were associated respectively with 723, 777, 855, and 1,091 man-hours. When

the use of labor becomes more evenly distributed, perhaps through the adoption of appropriate cropping patterns, the marginal value product of labor will likely decline and increasingly the substitutability of land and labor will become evident. Then, both land and labor will become binding constraints.

4. Total man-hours worked by week by source, 50 farmers, Cale, Batangas, Philippines, 1973-74.

5. Weekly labor utilization for major operations, 50 farmers, Cale, Batangas, Philippines, 1973-74.

Other aspects of labor. In Cale, Batangas, Philippines, adult males and females were found to supply almost equal components of labor for nursery, planting, weeding, harvesting, and post-harvest operations (weeks 16 through 42, fig. 3). Plowing operations were performed mainly by men (weeks 10 through 15, fig. 3).

There was little exchange labor, but substantial labor was hired and paid in kind at harvest time. Most work, however was performed by the family. Harvest time hiring was obligatory in weeks 38, 39, 43, 06, 07, and 08 (fig. 4) when the total labor need was clearly beyond the capacity of the family. Peaks in labor use occurred during planting of the first crop (weeks 22 to 23), weeding (weeks 26 to 32), harvest of the first crop and planting of the second crop (weeks 38 to 46), and harvest of the second crop (weeks 04 to 10) (fig. 5). The labor profile had strong implications for the design of alternative cropping patterns.

Cash input. Cash costs of crop production

were mainly for hired labor, seed, insecticides, and fertilizers, particularly the last two. Most hired labor was paid in kind and constituted a small component of cash costs. Although cash was not found to be an important constraint, a relationship between labor use per hectare, cash costs per hectare, and the average returns per hectare was evident. Increased use of labor occurred concomitantly with increased cash inputs and higher gross returns per unit of cash expenditure for crop inputs (Table 6). Farmers

Table 6. Labor use per hectare and gross returns per unit of cash input, by cropping system. Cale, Batangas, Philippines, 1974-75.

System number	Labor use (man-h/ha)	Gross returns per unit cash input (US\$/1US\$)	Cash inputs (US\$/ha)
I	409	2.42	100
II	723	2.71	118
V	728	2.90	132
IV	777	3.56	122
III	855	3.93	173
VI	1091	4.22	157

Table 7. Sources of farm cash income and types of cash expenditure by cropping system as percentages of total cash income and cash expenses. Cale, Batangas, Philippines, 1974-75.

Cropping system ^a	Farmers (no.)	Income (% of total) from					Expenses (% of total) on		
		Tree crops	Crops	Live-stock	Wages	Contributions from relatives	Crops	Live-stock	Household and other items
I	5	1	21	30	29	19	10	20	70
II	13	3	65	21	6	5	16	18	66
III	6	3	69	7	9	12	17	10	73
IV	11	3	67	11	7	12	15	11	74
V	12	2	65	14	12	7	21	11	68
VI	3	3	23	12	56	6	5	8	87

^aSee table 5 for definitions.

have apparently responded by increasing their cash input per hectare along with labor, but these inputs do not appear to be correlated with farm size.

Week-to-week cash liquidity of the farm was heavily influenced by the noncrop sector; it varied according to the cropping system used. Within the noncrop component, household income and expenses were proportionately quite sizeable (Table 7). The income derived from earned wages was substantial where the corn-*rice* and the rice-sugarcane cropping patterns were used.

Income and expenses were fairly well distributed over the year, except crop income, which came mainly from the sale of upland crops during December through March. The peak in crop income during week 11, reflecting the sale of corn, occurred with the five systems that included corn.

Level distribution over the year of wage components occurred with all cropping systems studied. A contraseasonal pattern relative to farm work peaks was expected, but did not occur. An unresolved aspect of the cash flow is that it was cumulatively negative for each study in Cale, Batangas, and during the first year of the study at Iloilo and at Pangasinan.

Macroeconomic variables. Prices. Input and product prices must be considered when designing new cropping patterns. Thus, during the descriptive phase of research, information on seasonal patterns and trends of prices was gathered and analyzed. Such analyses which were completed in 1975 for the Philippines, Bangladesh, Indonesia, and Thailand were accomplished in collaboration with economists from the three latter countries.

In the Philippines, seasonal factors for rice, corn, peanuts, mung beans, soybeans, sweet potatoes, potatoes, taro (*Colocasia esculenta*), and vegetable crops such as tomatoes, onions, garlic, ginger, and others were estimated for nine major market centers, using 1959-75 data. Estimates of seasonal price variation in the Manila markets for root crops, legumes, and some vegetables revealed little seasonal variation, and were lowest for rice and corn. On the other hand, large seasonal fluctuations were noted for such vegetable crops as tomatoes, onions, and ginger. These findings were consistent with those for the eight other markets studied.

6. Seasonally adjusted retail prices of major food commodities groups, Manila, Philippines, 1959-76. (1970-72 = 100)

Prices of all crops increased at an average of about 10 percent annually since 1959 (fig. 6). Since the rapid price rises of 1972-73, legume prices have remained relatively higher than rice and corn prices. Though crop prices increased quite rapidly in the Philippines during 1972-73, they moved either about as rapidly as or less rapidly than those in other Southeast Asian countries.

Markets. Marketing is a major consideration in the design and introduction of new cropping patterns. A case study of the marketing of a new crop was undertaken in connection with farmers' establishment of a rice-sorghum pattern in Tanauan, Batangas, Philippines. While marketing of sorghum may prove successful, the tentative conclusion was that most solutions to marketing problems are site specific and cannot be generalized to other locations. Therefore a more appropriate objective for cropping systems research is not the solution of marketing problems in general but the design of a step-by-step approach to site-specific solutions.

ECONOMIC CRITERIA FOR DESIGN AND TESTING

Design. Certain economic factors are identified, along with physical and agronomic factors, during the descriptive phase of research. Because these factors critically affect farmers' acceptance of new cropping patterns, they should be considered in the design of cropping patterns. One such factor is the difference between the time-distribution of labor availability and labor requirements.

A cropping system may consist of a number of cropping patterns, and the extent of use of different patterns strongly influences the variability of labor utilization within the year. To determine the tendency of prospective patterns to attenuate fluctuations in labor utilization within a system, a labor redistribution index was computed (using data gathered in Cale, Batangas) as the sum of the absolute differences, by week, between present labor use and the requirements of new patterns. Present use and new requirements are represented as the percentages that the weekly levels of labor use are of the respective annual labor peaks:

Table 8. Costs and returns per hectare of crops and crop combinations following upland rice, Batangas, Philippines, 1974-75.

Crops after rice	Farms (no.)	Av. plot size (sq m)	Av. yield (t/ha)	Cash costs (US\$/ha)							Total variable costs	Gross	Per-unit cash costs ^b	Per man-hour ^c	Above-variable costs	
				Seeds, cuttings	Fertilizer	Pesticide	Total including other	Non-cash costs ^a (US\$/ha)	All plots	2 highest farmers						
Sweet potato + corn intercrop	13	815	6.35	20	65	21	143	134	277	410	2.9	1.7	133	323		
Glutinous corn	9	888	12.496 ^d	13	65	26	116	46	162	205	1.8	1.6	43	236		
then cowpeas	7	980	29.452 ^d	47	29	18	97	117	214	262	2.7	1.2	48	68		
Peanuts	3	804	na ^e	115	41	14	172	125	297	371	2.1	1.4	74	167		
Soybean TK-5	3	750	0.80 ^f	86	25	9	128	80	208	350	2.7	2.4	142	175		
Soybean Multivar 80	2	752	0.20	91	30	5	128	61	189	90	0.7	-0.5	-99			
Mung beans	15	927	0.35	41	25	15	84	91	175	241	2.8	1.4	66	307		
Cowpeas	15	834	na	50	25	28	117	217	334	410	3.5	1.1	76	194		
First crop sorghum	11	885	2.46	4	65	1	101	69	170	316	3.1	2.2	146	204		
Ratoon sorghum	7	1011	0.98		76		84	25	109	126	1.5	1.2	17	60		
UPCA field corn	4	956	2.15		74		93	57	150	330	3.5	2.8	180	186		
Glutinous corn	7	867	24.828 ^d		65	2	72	38	110	183	2.5	2.2	73	187		
Popcorn	7	737	1.24		68		79	57	136	249	3.2	2.4	113	188		
Orange flint corn	17	859	1.53		65		70	57	127	257	3.7	3.0	130	297		
Upland rice	25	8164	1.40		28		62	76	138	434	7.0	4.0	141			

^aPrimarily unpaid labor. ^bComputed as value of product divided by cash costs. ^cComputed as value of product, less cash costs, divided by man-hours. ^dGreen marketable ears. ^eNot available. ^fUnshelled.

Table 9. Costs and returns of crops in a monoculture or in patterns. Iloilo, 1975 wet season.

Crop or pattern ^a	Costs and returns (US\$/ha)									
	Labor costs					Material costs	Total variable costs	Total returns	Net returns over variable costs	
	Land preparation	Nursery and transplanting	Hand weeding	Harvesting	Others ^b					
DS Rice (1st)	15	46	—	12	112	8	137	315	674	359
DS Rice (2nd)	13	49	—	10	95	9	126	289	570	281
TP Rice (1st)	80	43	33	2	75	8	105	266	555	289
TP Rice (2nd)	8	33	41	2	99	3	117	295	596	301
Rice-rice (DS)	13	90	6	13	218	15	278	620	1280	660
Corn before rice ^c	10	27	—	9	33	8	100	177	199	22
Corn-rice	7	63	36	21	127	12	212	471	769	298

^a DS = direct seeded, TP = transplanted. ^b Including seeding, fertilizing, spraying. ^c Seven of 10 crops were lost because of excessive moisture.

$$\text{Labor Redistribution Index} = \sum_{t=1}^{52} \left| \frac{R_t}{R_p} - \frac{L_t}{L_p} \right| \times 100;$$

where $t = 1, 2, \dots, 52$, R_t = labor requirements in week t for a new pattern, R_p = labor requirement in peak week for new pattern, L_t = actual labor use in week t for present crop activities, L_p = actual labor use in peak week.

The larger the index, the greater is the tendency of the pattern to redistribute labor use. Determination of the indices for four cropping patterns tried in Batangas (1974–75), namely rice-sweet potato + corn intercrop (656), rice-mung beans (658), rice-sorghum (778), and rice-corn-cowpeas (807) showed that the last-named pattern would have the greatest tendency to redistribute labor use. Improvements on this approach are being developed.

Design is currently the weakest aspect of methodology for the economic analysis of cropping systems. It is not a difficult concept—the objective of attenuating fluctuations in resource use, for example, is clearly understood by researchers. But incorporation of the concepts into simple and workable tools, though not difficult, has not been done. Much additional work is needed.

Testing. Costs and returns analysis of 1974–75 cropping pattern trials in Batangas, Philippines (Table 8), showed net returns from several patterns were well above the returns to farmers' usual second crops: popcorn, glutinous corn (sold fresh), and orange flint corn (sold dry). The more promising patterns were rice-sorghum and rice-sweet potato + corn.

Results of similar analyses of the wet-season trials in Iloilo, Philippines, showed that two strategies for obtaining an early rice crop were tried: 1) use of early-maturing varieties, and 2) direct seeding. Early rains resulted in a poor corn crop before rice (Table 9) and also in a switch to direct seeding on puddled rather than on dry soil.

The costs of labor (for land preparation, seeding, harvesting, fertilizing, weeding, spraying) and of materials used to produce the various rice crops were comparable. The high costs of weeding and of materials in the direct-seeded method were partly offset by transplanting costs of the transplanted rice crop. Returns to the crops differed substantially because of higher yields from the direct-seeded crops (Table 9). Farmers cooperating in the research trials obtained two crops of rice for the first time and received excellent net returns.

Cropping systems program

Applied research in cropping systems

Rice Production Training and Research Office

The applied research projects established in 28 locations throughout the Philippines placed special emphasis on solving problems that prevent farmers from growing an extra crop of either rice or one of seven different upland crops in the various rainfed areas in the Philippines. The research focused on: 1) identifying the best methods for establishing a direct-seeded crop of rice, 2) determining the feasibility of producing certain upland crops on light soils for a second crop after rice, and 3) growing a possible third upland crop of short duration or a third rice crop on heavy or light soils in areas where rain is adequate throughout the year.

The yields of rice sown in rows were similar to yields of broadcast-seeded rice (Table 1). Planting rice by broadcasting is faster than planting in rows; weed control can be difficult, however, unless herbicides are properly used.

In 1975, rainfall had a greater effect on rice yields than did the rice variety or the method of planting. (Type A rainfall pattern has a long dry period—6 months—, while Type G rainfall pattern has continuous rain throughout the year and can support three crops of rice in 1 year under rainfed conditions). With the low rainfall

Table 1. Grain yields of IR1561-228-3 and IR30 rices as affected by seven patterns of rainfall^a in the Philippines and by two methods of stand establishment by dry seeding.

Rainfall pattern	Grain yield (t/ha)			
	IR1561-228-3		IR30	
	DSL ^b	DSB ^c	DSL	DSB
A	3.8	3.8	2.7	2.8
B	1.9	2.7	1.8	1.9
C	4.4	4.0	3.9	3.6
D	2.4	2.4	1.7	1.7
E	3.2	3.2	2.5	2.5
F	5.0	5.4	5.5	5.6
G	4.5	4.7	4.5	4.9
Av.	3.6		3.3	

^aIn the Philippines, rainfall pattern Type A and Type B each have a long wet season (WS) during the high sun period (HSP) (April through September); pattern A has a 5-month dry season (DS) and pattern B has a 4-month DS. Type C and Type D each has a short DS (1 to 3 months). The DS of Type C occurs during the low sun period (LSP) (October through March), while the DS of Type D is during the HSP. Type E and Type F each have a marked WS of heavy rainfall; the WS of Type E occurs during the LSP and the WS of Type F is during the HSP. Type G has an even distribution of rainfall with no marked seasonality. ^bDSL = dry seeded in rows with *lithao* (a carabao-drawn farm implement with five teeth spaced at 20 cm, used primarily to make furrows in planting upland rice, and is indigenous to the provinces of Cavite and Batangas, Philippines). ^cDSB = dry-seeded, broadcast.

1. Total yield distribution of two consecutive crops of rice, IR30 (direct seeded), followed by IR1561-228-3 among 45 farms in the Philippines, 1975.

patterns (A, B, C, and D), the yields of IR1561-228-3 rice were consistently superior to those of IR30. In 1975, a prolonged dry period occurred in both rainfall zones B and D where the rice yields were low and where blast (*Pyricularia oryzae*) reduced grain production.

Two or three crops of rice can be grown successfully on light or heavy soils with normal Type G rainfall. A third crop of rice has been harvested in Cotabato, Mindanao, Philippines, on both heavy and light soils; yield results will be available soon. It appears that 18 to 20 tons of rice/ha can be grown in the southern part of the Philippines under rainfed conditions with three crops in 1 year on heavy or light soils.

The yields for two crops of rice grown under rainfed conditions ranged from 2 to 16 t/ha with most farmers producing 4 to 10 t/ha for the two crops (fig. 1). The relation between cropping pattern and soil texture indicated that on heavy soils, a dry seeded rice-transplanted rice pattern is feasible; on light soils, the second crop of rice failed in all cases. As a dry-seeded first crop, IR1561-228-3 gave a yield (2.7 t/ha) superior to that of IR30 (1.9 t/ha) because of its greater drought tolerance. However, the two rices as a second crop yielded the same when transplanted (3.8 t/ha for IR1561 and 3.9 t/ha for IR30).

A study of the yields of several upland crops

grown on light soils after the first rice crop in rainfall zones A and B showed that sorghum grew successfully in all locations tested. In addition, four other crops (sweet potatoes, corn,

soybeans, and peanuts) appear to be promising for successful cropping on light soils after rice, with reduced risk of crop failure caused by drought.

Cropping systems program

The Asian cropping systems network

Multiple Cropping Department

The Cropping Systems Network (CSN) is concentrated in Asia where more than 90 percent of the world's rice is grown. It was initiated with the government agencies involved in research and production programs in several Asian countries. It was designed to help national programs increase cropping intensities through collaborative work in cropping systems. IRRI participates in the CSN with national organizations to develop cropping systems technology for small farmers who are the most common rice producers in Asia.

Priority is given to rainfed (lowland and upland) and partially irrigated rice areas, which have great potential for increased cropping intensity. A system for disseminating research findings to the farmers (from research through production) is also being developed in each cooperating country. The conceptual framework being followed is one for cropping systems research and development programs that was developed by a cropping systems working group during its second meeting (fig. 1).

Since cropping systems technology is environment specific, research must be undertaken in different agroclimatic zones in Asian rice-growing areas. The network of experimental sites is designed to promote cropping systems

studies in collaboration with national programs in representative areas of major agroclimatic zones. The specification of the agroclimatic zones in which the sites are located will allow research findings to be extrapolated to areas with similar conditions.

The major efforts in 1975, which concentrated on establishing a network of test sites in Asia, brought six sites into operation: three in the Philippines, two in Indonesia, and one in Bangladesh. Additional test sites were identified in Thailand, Malaysia, Burma, and Sri Lanka (Table 1).

Two objectives of the CSN are to provide a mechanism for joint program planning and to review the major national programs and IRRI programs. To achieve these objectives, a working group was organized. It includes program leaders from the collaborating countries, an IRRI program leader and network coordinator, and two representatives from outside the region. The working group also serves as IRRI's link with national programs. It helps IRRI form guidelines to implement the collaborative work, to review the results, to evaluate and, where appropriate, to modify research plans, and to develop annual plans.

Representatives from Bangladesh, Indonesia,

1. The conceptual framework of the cropping systems research program.

Table 1. Location, area description, collaborators, and state of development of sites participating in the Asian network for cropping systems research and development.

Country	Location	Description	Site development	Collaborator
Philippines	Oton, Tigbauan, Iloilo	R-L, P-I	1 year active	Bureau of Plant Industry
Philippines	Tanauan, Batangas	U	3 years active	Bureau of Plant Industry
Philippines	Manoag, Pangasinan	R-L, P-I	1 year active	Bureau of Plant Industry
Indonesia	Bandarjaja, Gunung Sugih, Lampung	U, P-I	$\frac{1}{2}$ year active	Central Research Institute for Agriculture
Indonesia	Jatibarang, Indramayu	P-I	$\frac{1}{2}$ year active	Central Research Institute for Agriculture
Bangladesh	Joydebpur	P-I, I	$\frac{1}{2}$ year active	Bangladesh Rice Research Institute
Thailand	In Buri	R-L, P-I	initiated	Dept. of Agriculture, Technical Division and Division of Agricultural Economics
Thailand	Pi Mai	R-L	identified	Dept. of Agriculture, Rice Division and Division of Agricultural Economics
Thailand	Ubon	R-L	identified	Dept. of Agriculture, Rice Division and Division of Agricultural Economics
Thailand	Kampangsaen	R-L, P-I	identified	Kasetsart University
Sri Lanka	Anuradhapura District	U, R-L	identified	Department of Agriculture
Sri Lanka	Walagambahuwa, Anuradhapura	P-I-T	identified	Department of Agriculture
Sri Lanka	Alankara, Katupota, Kurunegala	R-L	initiated	Department of Agriculture
Burma	Yezin	P-I, R-L	identified	Agricultural Research Institute

^aU = upland, I = irrigated, R-L = rainfed lowland (bunded), P-I = partially irrigated, P-I-T = partially irrigated, tank fed.

Thailand, Sri Lanka, and the Philippines attended the first meeting March 17 to 19, 1975, at IRRI in Los Baños, Philippines. One representative from Malaysia and one from South Korea took part in the second meeting from November 3 to 8, 1975. The working group will hold its third meeting in Thailand, February 16 to 18, 1976.

At its first meeting the group summarized the papers presented during the February 1975 Cropping Systems Workshop held at IRRI and recommended a plan of action that included a framework for cropping systems research and extension. At the second meeting, the working group discussed plans for the outreach sites, research methodologies, and plans for a symposium. The group reformulated the "Conceptual Framework of Cropping Systems Research and Development" into a seven-stage process (fig. 1).

This Framework identified the organizational requirements of the CSN and the role of component technology research. Considered important was the design phase, assembling alternative cropping systems to realize efficient utilization of resources in a target area. Design criteria include the effect of physical and socioeconomic gradients on cropping systems components. Design capability for cropping

systems requires ready access to component technology and assumes the competence of the design team applying the technology.

The classification and mapping of climate, soil, and community-related variables are an important component of the cropping systems program. A climatic map of Bangladesh has been completed and soil-related information has been identified. The climatic map of Java, Indonesia, has been printed and similar work is continuing on the other major islands of Indonesia. The climatic classification of the Philippines is expected to be completed by mid-1976.

The CSN provides a forum where researchers can gather annually to discuss cropping systems. The March 18-20, 1975, workshop brought together Asian researchers to review the research in cropping systems, identify research needs and opportunities, establish priority areas, and determine the mechanism by which IRRI could collaborate effectively with national programs. The 82 workshop participants included the 25 trainees of the IRRI 6-month training program for cropping systems. Most of the 20 papers presented focused on the status of cropping systems research, research approaches, and potentials for maximizing utilization of rice areas. A limited edition of the proceedings was

published and has been distributed to participants and interested institutions.

Research information is exchanged among the researchers in Asia and other parts of the world through the CSN. Research papers on cropping systems are distributed to scientists involved in cropping systems research, extension, and production programs. While the majority of the papers came from IRRI in 1975, more contributions from other scientists in the region are anticipated for distribution within the network.

IRRI's major contribution to the national programs is training to develop a cadre of

dedicated scientists to implement collaborative research in the CSN. Scientists involved in the network and in national programs are given priority to participate in the training program. A total of 25 trainees from Indonesia, the Philippines, Thailand, Bangladesh, and Malaysia attended the 6-month program in 1975. Trainees are being identified to participate in a short course in September 1976. Eight students pursue graduate studies towards the M.S. and Ph.D. degrees. In addition, 12 candidates will begin graduate training in different disciplines in 1976.

Associated formal training

During 1975 a total of 208 scholars, fellows, and production trainees from 28 countries studied at IRRI (Table 1). The Institute provided 86.29 man-years of training during the year.

Three new training programs were first offered in 1975 in support of the Institute's international research networks: International Rice Testing Program (IRTP), International Rice Agro-Economic Network (IRAEN), and Agricultural Machinery Network. The Cropping Systems training program was modified to train the manpower needed for the Cropping Systems Network. A total of 78 trainees from 11 nations of Latin America, Africa, and South and Southeast Asia participated in these four training programs (Table 2).

RESEARCH PARTICIPANTS

The research-oriented programs accommodated 101 participants during 1975; 12 were postdoctoral fellows. All 13 of the research departments at IRRI provided training. About 66 percent of the participants studied in one of four areas of research: plant breeding, agronomy, agricultural economics, and entomology (Table 3). Over the past several years, the trend among the research-oriented participants had been toward degree programs. In 1975 approximately 70 percent of the research scholars and post-M.S. fellows combined their research training at IRRI with course work leading to graduate degrees. The majority were graduate students

Table 1. Countries that sent training participants to IRRI in 1975.

Country	Trainees (no.)					Total	Equivalent man-years of training
	Research-oriented			Production-oriented ^a	Others ^b		
	Scholars	Post-MS fellows	Postdoctoral fellows				
Bangladesh	2	4	—	2	6	14	6.12
Burma	2	1	—	3	2	8	3.54
Colombia	3	—	—	—	—	3	1.39
Ecuador	—	—	—	—	1	1	0.04
Egypt	—	1	—	—	—	1	0.67
England	1	—	—	—	—	1	0.33
Fiji	—	—	—	1	—	1	0.50
Ghana	—	—	—	—	2	2	0.08
India	1	8	7	3	6	25	12.46
Indonesia	10	7	—	2	23	42	16.83
Iran	2	—	—	—	—	2	0.92
Japan	1	3	2	1	—	7	4.00
Korea	4	3	—	—	—	7	3.54
Liberia	—	—	—	1	—	1	0.50
Malaysia	—	1	—	—	1	2	1.08
Mali	2	—	—	2	—	4	1.67
Netherlands	2	—	—	—	—	2	1.62
Nigeria	1	—	—	5	—	6	2.67
Pakistan	1	1	—	—	1	3	0.29
Philippines	4	2	1	3	10	20	8.46
Senegal	3	—	—	3	—	6	1.75
Solomon Islands	—	—	—	2	—	2	1.00
Sri Lanka	2	—	—	—	8	10	1.33
Sudan	—	—	1	1	—	2	0.83
Taiwan	5	—	—	—	—	5	3.25
Thailand	7	1	1	—	18	27	8.17
U.S.A.	2	1	—	—	—	3	2.25
Vietnam	—	1	—	—	—	1	1.00
Total	55	34	12	29	78	208	86.29

^aRice production training course. ^bMultiple cropping training program; genetic evaluation and utilization training program; international rice agro-economic network training program; agricultural engineering training program.

Table 2. Countries and their representatives who participated in the training programs designed to support four international research networks. IRRI, 1975.

Country	Training program ^a participants (no.)				Total
	GEU	Cropping systems	IRAEN	Agricultural engineering	
Bangladesh	2	2	—	2	6
Burma	1	—	—	1	2
Ecuador	—	—	—	1	1
Ghana	—	—	—	2	2
India	4	—	—	2	6
Indonesia	3	11	2	7	23
Malaysia	—	1	—	—	1
Pakistan	—	—	—	1	1
Philippines	—	5	3	2	10
Sri Lanka	2	—	2	4	8
Thailand	4	6	4	4	18
Total	16	25	11	26	78

^a GEU = genetic evaluation and utilization; IRAEN = international rice agro-economic network.

at the University of the Philippines at Los Baños (UPLB). Many others completed their course work at other universities and were conducting research projects at IRRI. These research projects will be submitted to their respective universities in fulfillment of the thesis requirement.

RICE PRODUCTION COURSES

Six-month rice production training program. Twenty-nine trainees from 13 countries attended the 11th annual 6-month rice production course in 1975. To date, 341 trainees from 31 countries have graduated from this course since it was initiated in 1964.

About 40 percent or 11 of the participants came from Africa; this is the largest number of trainees to attend the course outside of South and Southeast Asia. The West Africa Rice Development Association (WARDA) sent six of the trainees: one from Liberia, two from Mali, and three from Senegal. The International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA), another international agricultural research and training institute, located in Ibadan, Nigeria, recommended the other five trainees who work for the Nigeria National Accelerated Food Production Program (NAFPP).

Like their predecessors, the 1975 class scored low, with a mean of 24 percent (range: 2 to 69) in the practical examination and a mean of 34 percent (range: 15 to 78) for the written part of the preactivity evaluation. The postactivity evaluation reflected a significant improvement in their knowledge of rice production, with a mean of 89 percent (range: 71 to 98) in the practical examination and a mean of 74 percent (range: 40 to 95) in the written evaluation.

Three types of certificates were issued upon graduation; 12 of the participants received "completed with distinction"; 15 received "satisfactorily completed"; and 2 "participated in".

Short courses in rice production. Of the four 2-week rice production courses conducted in 1975, two were conducted for participants of the Genetic Evaluation and Utilization (GEU) training program and for participants of the International Rice Agro-Economic Network

Table 3. Research trainees and their areas of research at IRRI, 1975.

Research area	Research trainees (no.)			
	Scholars ^a	Post-M.S. fellows ^a	Postdoctoral fellows	Total
Agricultural economics	10 (10)	5 (5)	—	15
Agricultural engineering	4 (2)	2 (1)	—	6
Agronomy	13 (7)	4 (1)	1	18
Chemistry	—	1 (1)	2	3
Entomology	6 (2)	3 (3)	1	10
Multiple cropping	4 (3)	2 (2)	—	6
Plant breeding	10 (6)	7 (5)	3	20
Plant pathology	2 (2)	3 (3)	1	6
Plant physiology	3 (1)	2 (2)	2	7
Rice production training and research	—	1 (1)	—	1
Soil chemistry	—	—	1	1
Soil microbiology	—	2 (1)	1	3
Statistics	3 (2)	2 (2)	—	5
Total	55 (35)	34 (27)	12	101

^a Numbers in parentheses represent degree candidates at the University of the Philippines at Los Baños (UPLB) or candidates conducting a research project at IRRI to fulfill the thesis requirements at another university.

(IRAEN) training program.

A short course held in November was organized and implemented by the trainees of the 6-month rice production training course; it provided them with actual experience in organizing and conducting similar courses; experience they can apply upon return to their home countries, where they will train others in rice production.

The 2-week course conducted December 8 to 18 was designed to familiarize the Institute's scholars and fellows in the disciplinary research programs with the latest improved rice technology. Of the 42 participants who attended, most were from IRRI, and included IRRI senior staff members, research scholars, research assistants, research aides, and laboratory/field assistants.

INTERNATIONAL RESEARCH NETWORKS' TRAINING PROGRAMS

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization (GEU). This 4-month program was designed for individuals involved in the development of improved rice varieties and emphasized the need for a multi-disciplinary approach. A participant with a background in a specific discipline was expected to have a better understanding of the roles that other disciplines play in a team approach to varietal development. However, each trainee was afforded ample opportunity and time to devote to the specific problem area, e.g., screening for insect resistance, he or she was expected to concentrate on upon return to his or her country. Six countries from South and Southeast Asia sent 16 trainees to this training program.

International Rice Agro-Economic Network (IRAEN). This 2-month program trained agronomists and economists in the methodology and techniques being used to determine and measure the constraints preventing Asian rice farmers from exploiting the full potential of the modern rice varieties. The methodology was developed through use in sites in Thailand, Indonesia, and the Philippines. Eleven participants from four countries attended.

Agricultural Engineering. The 2-week training program deals with the manufacture and utiliza-

tion of IRRI-designed machinery. It is designed for engineers from organizations and manufacturers who cooperate with IRRI and who are currently, or plan to be, closely associated with the manufacture of IRRI-designed machinery. A total of 26 trainees from 10 countries in Africa, Latin America, and Asia attended the two courses given in 1975.

Cropping Systems. The previous cropping systems training program was modified in 1975 to provide trained manpower to implement the different applied research trials required at the various sites forming the rice-based Cropping Systems Network.

The 25 participants from five countries attending this 5-month course grew eight different applied research trials, using mung beans, peanuts, sweet potatoes, and corn in addition to rice. It provided an excellent opportunity for the trainees to learn how to perform all the operations required to produce these crops using the latest technology.

In 1975, IRRI, in cooperation with the Philippine Council for Agriculture and Resources Research (PCARR) and the Bureau of Agricultural Extension (BAE), organized a short course in cropping systems. This course was organized in conjunction with an applied research project that was conducted at 32 locations covering the seven rainfall patterns in the Philippines. A total of 34 trainees representing these 32 locations participated in a 1-week training in cropping systems to learn how to design, lay out, and manage these trials.

NAMES AND COUNTRIES OF PARTICIPANTS

The names, countries, and research project areas of individuals who completed their training during 1975 are presented. The list includes those individuals studying abroad under IRRI scholarships provided by the different country programs. An asterisk (*) indicates completion of the M.S. degree, two asterisks (**) completion of the Ph. D. degree, during the year.

RESEARCH SCHOLARS

Agricultural economics

Macan Markar*, Sri Lanka. Factors affecting marketable surplus of paddy: a study in Kurunegala District, Sri Lanka.

Romeo Obedoza, Philippines. Water adequacy at the farm level: its influence on input use and rice yield.

Domingo Tabbal*, Philippines. The distribution of water supply and water adequacy within a gravity irrigation system.

Agricultural engineering

H. H. Jamaluddin, Pakistan. A study of production performances of IRRI-designed agri-machines manufacturers. Mozammel Haque Khan*, Bangladesh. Improvement of savonious rotor-windmill.

Sang Ha No, Korea. Mechanical and operation factors affecting the efficiency of rice whitening machines.

Agronomy

Min Aung, Burma. Increasing fertilizer and insecticide efficiency in lowland rice.

H. A. Davanloo, Iran. Effects of different management levels (tillage, nitrogen, insect control, and weed control) on rice yield.

Dario Leal Monsalve*, Colombia. Screening of new herbicides for the control of nutsedge (*Cyperus rotundus* L.) in upland rice.

Chien-nan Yang*, Taiwan. Drought tolerance in rice and varietal screening.

Entomology

Elizabeth Ellenkamp, Netherlands. a) Survival test of *Nephotettix nigropictus* on 33 rice varieties; b) Yield loss of IR26 due to *Cnaphalociosis medinalis*, rice leaf folder.

Marianne Stapper-Bloemsa, Netherlands. a) Predation studies of *Lycosa pseudoannulata* on *Nilaparvata lugens*; b) Some studies on the multiple cropping projects (field experiments regarding bean fly and corn borer density).

Rezaul Karim*, Bangladesh. Resistance to brown plant-hopper, *Nilaparvata lugens*, in rice varieties.

Multiple cropping

Surasuk Sritunya*, Thailand. The intensive ditch and dike method of vegetable production in Thailand.

S. M. Thahir, Indonesia. General observation of the multiple cropping program.

Plant breeding

Bedyo Haryanto, Indonesia. General rice breeding.

H. H. Hung*, Taiwan. A study on the segregation of 3 marker genes in wide crosses involving upland and lowland rice varieties.

Dae-soo Kim, Korea. General rice breeding.

Mansur Lande*, Indonesia. The inheritance of tungro resistance in rice selection CR94-13 and allelic relationships of genes for tungro resistance in CR94-13 and IR833-6-2-1 lines.

M. J. Moeen, Iran. Selection and hybridization of improved breeding materials with traditional Iranian varieties.

Ammula Lakshminarayana*, India. Studies on the inheritance of resistance to brown planthopper in some rice varieties.

Johnson Olufowote*, Nigeria. Inheritance of resistance to bacterial blight, *Xanthomonas oryzae* (Uyeda and Ishiyama) Dowson in rice.

Adjiono Partoatmodjo, Indonesia. General rice breeding.

Rafael Robayo*, Colombia. Comparative evaluation of selection pathways for upland rice breeding.

Plant pathology

Chun-ming Yu*, Taiwan. Effect of nutritional and microclimatic conditions on the development of sheath blight disease of rice.

Plant physiology

Tetsuo Hara, Japan. Influence of air temperature and light in grain filling of an indica and a japonica rice in a controlled environment.

Statistics

Wahyudi, Indonesia. Analysis of statistical data.

Suk Hwan Chang*, Korea. Prediction of rice yield.

POST-M.S. FELLOWS

Agricultural economics

Masao Kikuchi, Japan. Land resource constraint.

C. Ranade, India. Study on impacts of changing rice technologies on income distribution at farm level.

Agricultural engineering

Jose Samuel**, India. Water jet pumps for low lift applications.

J. G. Sarwar, Pakistan. Comparative threshing performance of rasp-bar and wire-loop cylinders.

Agronomy

Moon Hee Lee, Korea. Interaction of weed control and fertilizer efficiency under different methods of nitrogen application.

S. P. Sarkar**, India. Screening techniques for drought tolerance in upland rice.

Chemistry

R. S. Marwaha**, India. Ammonium and nitrate metabolism in wetland rice plants.

Entomology

Ibrahim Manwan**, Indonesia. Resistance of rice varieties to yellow borer, *Tryporyza incertulas*.

Plant breeding

Sommai Amonsilpa, Thailand. General rice breeding.

Mahiul Haque*, Bangladesh. Varietal variation and evaluation procedures for ratoonability of rice.

Ohn Kyaw, Burma. General rice breeding.

B. H. Siwi**, Indonesia. Inheritance of resistance to the green leafhopper, *Nephotettix virescens* Distant, in some rice varieties.

S. Subijanto**, Indonesia. Studies on linkage relations of genes for disease and insect resistance and a kernel trait in rice.

S. C. Sur**, India. Identification and cytogenetical studies of primary trisomics in rice.

Plant pathology

Aminul Haque*, Bangladesh. Variation in cultural characteristics, physiology and pathogeneticity of field isolates of *Thanatephorus cucumeris* (Frank) Donk, the causal organism of rice sheath blight disease.

Plant physiology

Krishnamurthy Alluri**, India. Some desirable characteristics for upland rice varieties.

A. L. Patel, India. Effect of light, temperature, and humidity on rice growth at different stages in a controlled environment.

Soil microbiology

T. Yoneyama, Japan. Organic nitrogen in soil: its decomposition and availability to plants.

POST-DOCTORAL FELLOWS

Agronomy

George Ghobrial, Sudan. Effects of some herbicides on growth parameters and on population dynamics of weed flora of upland rice.

Chemistry

Aurea Almazan, Philippines. Separation of the rice proteins by gel-filtration; its application in the determination of changes in protein during maturation and storage of rice grain.

Plant breeding

C. Maneephong, Thailand. General rice breeding.

SCHOLARS ABROAD

Neville Edirisinghe, Sri Lanka. One-year diploma course in agricultural economics (marketing), Cornell University, U.S.A.

J. D. Mannaperuma, Sri Lanka. M.S. in agricultural engineering, Louisiana State University, U.S.A.

I. N. Oka, Indonesia. Ph.D. in entomology, Cornell University, U.S.A.

RICE PRODUCTION TRAINEES

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Charles Dembele, Agronomist, Institut d'Economie Rurale, Bamako, Mali.

Amadou Diarra, Agronomist, Institut d'Economie Rurale, Bamako, Mali.

Tahir Diop, Head of Entomology Section, Agriculture Department, Dakar, Senegal.

Aliyu Edogi, Agricultural Officer, Ministry of Agriculture, Kontagora, Northwest State, Nigeria.

Hassan Atitalla Hassan, Block Inspector, Sudan Gezira Board, Barakat, Sudan.

Kazuhiko Inoue, Staff, Agricultural Chemicals Research, Market Development Research Laboratory, Mitsubishi Chemical Industries, Ltd., Yokohama, Japan.

Md. Jalaluddin, Scientific Officer, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute, Dacca, Bangladesh.

Farhad Jameel, Scientific Officer, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute, Dacca, Bangladesh.

Babu Lal, Technical Officer, Department of Agriculture, Labasa, Fiji.

Ko Ko Latt, Township Manager, Agricultural Corporation, Monyin, Kachin State, Burma.

Ko Lay, Township Manager, Agricultural Corporation, Yaungche, Shan State, Burma.

Papa Cisse Lo, 829 Sicap Baobabs, Dakar, Senegal.

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Lawrence Ologide, Agricultural Officer, Grade I, Federal Department of Agriculture, Benin City, Nigeria.

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Bhubneswar Roy, Rice Agronomist, Agricultural Research Institute, Mitnapur Farm, Patna, Bihar, India.

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Lala Shashi B. Triar, Assistant Rice Entomologist, Agricultural Research Institute, Patna, Bihar, India.

Thaung Tin, Township Manager, Agricultural Corporation, Danubyu, Irrawaddy Division, Burma.

Virgilio de la Trinidad, Research Assistant, Department of Agronomy, College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines at Los Baños, College, Laguna, Philippines.

CROPPING SYSTEMS TRAINEES

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Antonio Yap, Supervising Agronomist, Bureau of Plant Industry, Region No. 7, Cebu City, Philippines.

GEU TRAINEES

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Sommai Amonsilpa, Rice Breeder, Bangkok Rice Experiment Station, Bangkok, Thailand.
Tulsi Das, Rice Breeder, Breeding Division, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute, Dacca, Bangladesh.
N. Gopalan, Pathologist, Rice Research Station, Pattambi, Kerala, India.
Md. Anwarul Islam, Scientific Officer, Breeding Division, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute, Dacca, Bangladesh.
K. I. James, Rice Breeder, Rice Research Station, Pattambi, Kerala, India.
Ohn Kyaw, Assistant General Manager (Rice Division), Agricultural Research Institute, Gyogon, Insein, Rangoon, Burma.
Wittaya Seetanun, Agronomist, Rice Division, Department of Agriculture, Bangkok, Thailand.
G. S. Sidhu, Assistant Rice Breeder, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana, Punjab, India.
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IRAEN TRAINEES

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Somporn Isvilanonda, Junior Lecturer, Department of Agricultural Economics, Kasetsart University, Bangkok, Thailand.
Jongjate Janprasert, Assistant Instructor, Department of Agricultural Economics, Kasetsart University, Bangkok, Thailand.

A. P. Jinadasa, Research Assistant, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Sri Lanka, Peradeniya, Sri Lanka.
Mak Nimgeon, Third Grade Agricultural Officer, Rangsit Experiment Station, Pathumthanee, Thailand.
Manuel Posas, Research Assistant, Visayas State College of Agriculture, Baybay, Leyte, Philippines.
Velupillai Premakumar, Research Assistant, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Sri Lanka, Peradeniya, Sri Lanka.
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AGRICULTURAL ENGINEERING TRAINEES

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Santi Boonyakunakasaem, Indonesia.
Anup Ranjan Bose, Production Engineer, Comilla Cooperative Karkhana Ltd., Ranir Bazar, Comilla, Bangladesh.
C. Boriboon, Owner and Manager, Kaset Thai Ltd., Patnanikom, Chonburi, Thailand.
S. R. De Zilwa, Research and Development Engineer, Colombo Commercial Company, Sir James Peiris Mawatha, Colombo, Sri Lanka.
A. B. Djanun, Head, Advance Planning, Metal Industries Development Center, Jl. Sangkuriang, Bandung, Indonesia.
Pedro Galzote, Production Engineer, Marsteel Corporation, Quezon City, Philippines.
K. Azharul Haq, Head, Engineering Division, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute, Dacca, Bangladesh.
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Octavio Jarrin, Project Manager for Mechanization of Rice Crops Program, USAID, Guayaquil, Ecuador.
T. S. Jinasena, Director, Jinasena Ltd., 57 Lane Crescent, Colombo 2, Sri Lanka.
H. C. Joshi, Assistant Engineer, G. B. Pant University of Agriculture and Technology, Pantnagar, Nainital District, U.P., India.
Suppiah Kathirkamathambay, Head, Agricultural Engineering Research and Development Division, Department of Agriculture, Peradeniya, Sri Lanka.
P. Ngamboonsueb, Plant Manager, J. Charaenchai Company, Bangkok, Thailand.
M. Saiyed, Engineer-In-Charge, Habib Industries, Commerce Bank Building, I. I. Chundrigar Road, Karachi-2, Pakistan.
M. Seidu, Assistant General Manager, North Development Corporation, Accra, Ghana.
H. H. Shah, Production Engineer, American Spring and Pressing Works, Malad, Bombay, India.
Ben Somera, Philippines.
Komar Sudjana, P.T. Pusri, P. O. Box 084, Palembang, Indonesia.
Dadang Tarmana, Project Officer, IRRI-DITNIK, Direktorat Tehnik Pertanian, Pasar Minggu, Jakarta, Indonesia.
Niyom Thunyaprasart, Agricultural Engineer, Engineering Division, Department of Agriculture, Bangkok, Thailand.

- A. Vamadevan, Agricultural Engineer, Department of Agriculture, Peradeniya, Sri Lanka.
- Sein Win, Deputy Workshop Head, Agricultural Mechanization Department, Union of the Socialist Republic of Burma, Rangoon, Burma.
- Gilbert K. Workey, Senior Technician, Bolts and Nuts Unit, Technology Consultancy Center, U. S. T., Kumasi, Ghana.
- Johanes Yuwono, Associate Researcher, Metal Industries Development Center, Jl. Sangkuriang, Bandung, Indonesia.

International activities

The international program of IRRI is designed to provide services to help improve national capabilities for rice research and to carry out collaborative research and network activities under a wide range of ecological conditions. The Institute maintains a close linkage with national programs to determine the types of service that IRRI can provide and to make the core research at IRRI more relevant to national needs.

The present pattern of IRRI's cooperation with national programs is the result of continuing evolution and has been influenced by the changing requirements of national programs that have gradually strengthened their capabilities for rice research. The international program includes four kinds of activities: 1) general services, 2) cooperative country projects, 3) regional programs, and 4) international networks.

GENERAL SERVICES

General services are normally available to all rice-growing countries and include conducting seminars, workshops, and conferences in which rice scientists are invited to participate; distributing published materials; furnishing genetic material requested by individual scientists; and training rice scientists. The IRRI training programs and the Institute's publications are described in other sections of this annual report.

During 1975, IRRI supplied 4,043 seed samples of *Oryza sativa* cultivars and related species from its genetic collection to 168 researchers in 31 countries. Also, it distributed 4,729 seed packets of breeding lines in response to requests from rice breeders from around the world. Individual requests for seeds are expected to decline with the establishment in early 1975 of a formal International Rice Testing Program (IRTP). The program is designed to systematically distribute and evaluate rice germ plasm

and improved genetic material at many locations across a wide range of ecological conditions where rice is grown.

In Egypt and in India, six IRRI lines were named and released by the national programs as varieties for commercial cultivation. A total of 42 IRRI experimental lines have been released as varieties in different countries in addition to the 11 lines that were named as varieties by IRRI.

Because of the marked expansion in national rice improvement programs and the development of international cooperation through the IRTP, IRRI announced that it will discontinue the practice of officially naming and releasing rice varieties. It will leave to the national organizations the responsibility for such releases.

Several conferences and workshops were held at IRRI to facilitate exchange of information and to develop plans for cooperative work.

Cropping Systems Workshop. This workshop, held March 18–20, was attended by 82 scientists from 19 countries, including heads of cropping systems programs in South and Southeast Asian countries. It initiated the establishment of a Working Group on Cropping Systems on a continuing basis. At the workshop, a conceptual framework for program organization was developed, priority problem areas concerning cropping systems that require research were identified, and the methodology that should be used in research on cropping systems was formulated.

The workshop emphasized the need for collaboration among national programs in South and Southeast Asia and helped to identify IRRI's role in collaborative work in rice-based cropping systems. The IRRI Cropping Systems program prepared a limited edition of the proceedings that was distributed to national research centers and institutions.

International Rice Research Conference. Some 130 scientists from 28 countries, attended the

International Rice Research Conference, held April 21–24, 1975. The conference focused on relevant research for increasing rice production.

Plant breeders, entomologists, and pathologists jointly examined the results of the 1974 international nurseries and exchanged information on recent developments in varietal improvement programs. Plans were completed for international nurseries, standardized methods, and types of nurseries to be grown; also, locations for testing were identified.

Agronomists and soil scientists discussed ways to improve fertilizer efficiency in rice and alternate sources of plant nutrients to cope with the worldwide shortage of fertilizer and the resultant increased costs of these agrochemicals. The relative importance of various types of problem soils was evaluated and ways to increase rice production in the vast areas where they are prevalent were discussed.

Scientists from countries where deep-water rice is grown planned a cooperative research program to develop high-yielding rices and appropriate technology for increasing rice production in deep-water areas.

Workshop on mechanization. Sixty participants from 19 countries in Asia, Africa, Europe, and the United States attended the May 6–9 International Workshop on Agricultural Mechanization and Indigenous Production of Agricultural Machines. The workshop gave engineers and manufacturers interested in producing IRRI-designed machines on a commercial basis an opportunity to exchange ideas and obtain information on recent developments.

In response to the increased interest of manufacturers in IRRI-designed farm equipment, a formal 2-week course was initiated to train engineers from developing countries in the use and manufacture of IRRI-designed machines.

International Rice Agro-Economic Network Workshop. A total of 48 participants and observers from six countries attended this workshop held in March in Bangkok, Thailand. The results of cooperative studies on agro-economic constraints to rice production were assessed. Additionally, the agro-economic

studies conducted at pilot sites in the Philippines and Thailand during the wet season of 1974 were reviewed. Potential participants were introduced to the approach and methodology involved in research on constraints to rice yields in farmers' fields.

The workshop stimulated expansion and formalization of the International Rice Agro-Economic Network (IRAEN) to cover nine sites in six countries.

A program for training IRAEN teams in agronomic, economic, and statistical procedures at IRRI was recommended. Twelve trainees from four countries participated in a 2-month training program at IRRI in September and October.

COOPERATIVE COUNTRY PROJECTS

Cooperative country projects are designed to assist individual countries to improve their capacity for rice research and training. Donor agencies, under special arrangements with IRRI and the host country, provide funds to support these projects. Each project features: 1) the assignment of one or more resident IRRI scientists to participate in local research, 2) the assignment of short-term consultants in the host country, 3) the training of rice scientists, and 4) the purchase of essential equipment and library books. In some cases, the cooperative projects have assisted with the development of improved facilities at rice research centers.

IRRI scientists working in cooperative country programs function as members of local research teams and the accomplishments of these teams are integrated into the total output of the national programs for rice research.

Summary reports of the cooperative research work in which IRRI scientists have actively participated are presented.

Bangladesh. The IRRI project in Bangladesh involves cooperative work with the Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRRI). Until the end of 1974, the project was funded mainly by a grant from The Ford Foundation, with additional support from the U.S. Agency for International Development (USAID) for overseas training. In late 1974, the International

Development Research Centre (IDRC) of Canada gave a 4-year grant to support the development of the BIRRI Rice Cropping Systems Division. The Ford Foundation grant terminated in November 1975.

During the year, the Government of Bangladesh granted to IRRI the status, privileges, and tax exemptions accorded to other international aid agencies. In November 1975, BIRRI and IRRI signed a Memorandum of Understanding, which defines clearly the relationship between these two institutes and their respective responsibilities and outlines the nature of cooperative activities to be carried out and the operating procedures.

Under the Memorandum of Understanding, BIRRI and IRRI developed jointly a new comprehensive project proposal based on BIRRI's total needs for institutional support to carry out an effective program of research on problems of established priorities and to strengthen the national capabilities in rice research and training. A number of donor agencies, including The Ford Foundation, the Canadian International Development Agency (CIDA), and the Australian Development Assistance Agency, will jointly support the project for 2 years beginning in December 1975. Under the project five IRRI scientists work at BIRRI, in addition to the one provided in the IDRC-supported project on rice-based cropping systems.

The cooperative project is designed to strengthen BIRRI financially, institutionally, and scientifically and to increase its capacity to develop and disseminate technology for increased grain production. The project also assists in developing improved experiment station facilities for field research. Coordinated interdisciplinary research in priority problem areas is crucial to attaining self-sufficiency of rice in the country.

Besides providing resident scientists, consultants, and technicians, the project made arrangements for overseas travel for national rice scientists and for advanced overseas training; furnished specialized equipment, supplies, and library materials; developed collaborative research programs; and exchanged data and breeding materials. During 1975,

one entomologist who serves as the IRRI team leader and representative, one agricultural engineer, and one rice production specialist worked in Bangladesh under The Ford Foundation grant; one agronomist for rice-based cropping systems worked under the IDRC grant.

IRRI scientists worked closely with BIRRI counterparts and assisted in preparing research, development, and training programs, and in implementing and evaluating these programs. The IRRI team leader assisted the BIRRI director in the overall planning of programs. Also, IRRI scientists helped select staff and candidates for training and advised on farm development and operational matters. Their work is an integral part of BIRRI's program.

As part of BIRRI's entomology research program, the IRRI entomologist worked on the population dynamics of rice stem borers, and, together with his counterparts, carried out a series of crop loss assessment experiments. Based on the return on investment, the use of insecticides was found to be unwarranted in some cases, especially in the winter and early summer months.

The agricultural engineer played an important part in planning and implementing farm development, in reorganizing and strengthening the workshop for improved maintenance and repair of machinery and equipment, in building a comprehensive supply of spare parts, and in the preliminary testing of several IRRI-designed machines (power tiller, bellows low-lift water pump, axial thresher). During the year, the IRRI and BIRRI engineers completed the development of the western section of the main farm at Joydebpur.

The rice production specialist who joined the IRRI team towards the end of 1974 began a new applied research program in farmers' fields, assisted in developing rice production training courses, and was involved in farm trials in a 148-sq-km area around Joydebpur.

A cropping systems agronomist joined the project shortly after the inception of the new division of cropping systems at BIRRI. He helped to develop a research program for the division, to survey existing cropping systems to develop methodology for cropping systems research,

to procure equipment and supplies, and to conduct a series of field experiments at BRRl stations and in farmers' fields.

Consultants, mostly from the IRRI staff at Los Baños, served in Bangladesh for periods ranging from a few days to several weeks. These consultants included specialists in farm development, plant breeding, agricultural economics, and multiple cropping.

The building of a core of highly qualified scientists and well-trained technicians for support services is essential for BRRl's development. During 1975, four BRRl staff members completed their Master's degrees. They conducted their research at IRRI and matriculated in the degree program at the neighboring University of the Philippines at Los Baños (UPLB). Six trainees completed nondegree courses at IRRI in rice production, genetic evaluation and utilization (GEU), and multiple cropping. Six Ph.D. fellows continued their studies at American universities; an additional four have been selected to begin their studies in 1976. Two candidates began course work for the M.S. degree at UPLB in 1975 and another two have been selected for 1976. Several BRRl scientists attended meetings arranged at IRRI and undertook study tours.

BRRl continued to achieve steady progress. The Government of Bangladesh increased its financial support for BRRl, and several new positions were created. The volume of research increased and concomitantly the quality of the field experiments improved markedly. Farm testing of different research findings and data collection activities on farmers' fields in the applied research project area around Joydebpur increased. The experiment station at BRRl's headquarters at Joydebpur developed steadily, and some progress was realized on the development of the Comilla substation.

Improvement in the research and training capabilities of BRRl was reflected in the five rice production courses for extension workers. Also, three rice scientists from Africa received training at BRRl, with special emphasis on deep-water rice. BRRl published and distributed the proceedings of its 1974 International Deep-Water Rice Seminar.

Major research achievements of BRRl

included the release of a new high-yielding variety, BR4, which has intermediate height and is suitable for cultivation in most areas during the monsoon season when the rice crop is often affected by flooding. Several advanced BRRl lines gave good performance and appeared ready for release in 1976. A previously released variety, BR3, performed well in international yield nurseries at locations in a number of different rice-growing countries.

Egypt. The 2-year project in which IRRI provided the services of a rice scientist to the Ministry of Agriculture, under a contract with The Ford Foundation Arid Lands Agricultural Development Program, ended in June 1975. The initial objectives were accomplished: introduction and evaluation of high-yielding, long-grained varieties from IRRI and standardization of the cultural and fertilizer requirements of these rices for optimum yields. Several Egyptian scientists were trained at IRRI under this project.

In the past, Egyptian farmers grew only japonica rice. The long-grained indica rice, IR22, was found to be suitable for cultivation in Egypt and is now being grown commercially on a small scale. IR579-48-1 and IR1561-228-3 were selected from among the new IRRI lines introduced and tested in Egypt and were released as Sakha 1 and Sakha 2, respectively, by the national program. Both were found to be superior to IR22, principally because of their short duration. The seed of Sakha 1 was multiplied during 1975 for commercial production.

Although long-grained varieties are available for general planting, the milling industry is not prepared to process these rices because the existing mills are equipped with disc shells which break during milling a greater percentage of long-grained rices than short-grained rices.

IR1008-16, IR1541-76, IR141-102-7, IR1615-2-2, IR1626-7, and IR1626-8 are high-yielding lines with good grain appearance that were identified in regional yield trials. IR1626-213 and Ratna, a variety from India, gave superior performance in advanced trials and will be evaluated further at different locations in Egypt. Progenies of the IR2061 cross appeared to be particularly promising among

the early-generation material, because of their earliness, vigorous growth, resistance to lodging, excellent grain appearance, and resistance to blast.

Several agronomic experiments were conducted during the 1974 rice season to determine the optimum time of seeding, age of seedlings, population density, rates and methods of applying nitrogen and phosphorus fertilizers, and procedures for weed control. Apparently, management practices for long-grained indica rices in Egypt should include: 1) seeding during the first half of May, 2) transplanting at 25 to 35 days after sowing, 3) transplanting in rows of 25 to 30 cm with 20 cm between hills (three or four seedlings may be transplanted in one hill), and 4) application of 50 to 75 kg of N/ha and 35 kg of P₂O₅/ha.

The application of zinc, either to the soil or by dipping seedlings (in a solution of zinc oxide), increased yields in most rice-growing areas of Egypt. With proper management, IRRI lines gave higher yields than did the japonica varieties currently recommended for cultivation in Egypt.

Indonesia. IRRI works with the Central Research Institute for Agriculture (CRIA) in Indonesia on a cooperative CRIA-IRRI program that consists of four different projects funded by individual donors. IRRI provided technical assistance and staff training and assisted with equipment procurement and research facility improvement and expansion. For this purpose, IRRI and CRIA used funds from both donor agencies and the Indonesian budget. Support for staff training, commodity procurement, and technical assistance was obtained from The Ford Foundation and the USAID, for a project at Bogor; from the Government of Netherlands, for a project at Maros; and from the International Bank for Reconstruction and Development (IBRD) (loan to the Indonesian government), for a project at Sukamandi.

IRRI and Indonesian scientists cooperated in research associated with four international networks. They jointly determined research priorities and developed programs to increase research efficiency, taking into consideration the limitations of the available resources. Major efforts were directed toward an integrated national varietal improvement program for

rice and toward a rice-based cropping systems research program.

During 1975, 12 IRRI staff members were posted in Indonesia. The IRRI representative was located at Bogor and support was provided by The Ford Foundation. Four scientists, including a rice breeder, a legume breeder, an agronomist, and a statistician/economist were also posted at the CRIA headquarters in Bogor, supported by USAID funds. An agronomist (team leader), an entomologist, and a pathologist were posted at Maros, South Sulawesi. A pathologist (team leader), an entomologist, a rice breeder, and a station development engineer were posted at the CRIA Branch Station, Sukamandi, West Java.

IRRI rice breeders participated in screening and evaluating genetic material for agronomic characters, drought tolerance, bacterial leaf blight (BLB), blast, grassy stunt virus, rice tungro virus, brown planthopper (BPH), gall midge, and stem borer. The screening activities are an integral part of the national varietal improvement program and involve scientists from several problem areas such as plant breeding, plant pathology, and entomology. The headquarters of the national program is located at Bogor where a hybridization facility, including a hybridization block, vacuum emasculator, and screened crossing cage, has been set up to facilitate making a large number of crosses. Parents for the crosses are selected by the varietal improvement team which includes rice scientists from stations outside of Bogor. F₁ materials are grown at Bogor, but F₂ materials are moved to screening nurseries at other locations as rapidly as manpower and facility constraints permit. Lines have been developed which have 1) BPH or grassy stunt resistance, or both, 2) tungro and BLB resistance, and 3) cold tolerance. Some of the lines have the potential of becoming commercial varieties. The breeding materials were evaluated in the national program and more than 100 elite Indonesian lines were also included in the IRTP. During the 1975 dry season and the 1975-76 wet season, Indonesian scientists screened 25 IRTP nurseries at nine locations.

In Java and South Sulawesi, IRRI pathologists participated in surveys of the major rice

diseases, including grassy stunt virus, tungro virus, bacterial blight, sheath blight, and narrow brown leaf spot. The surveys assessed the intensities and distributions of rice diseases to help identify research program priorities and locations for screening nurseries.

A comparison virulence of isolates of pathogen samples collected at Sukamandi demonstrated that some Indonesian BLB isolates from Java are more virulent than those used at IRRI in Los Baños. This result suggests that variety reactions expressed in Indonesia may show less resistance than those expressed in the Philippines.

Clear differences in virulence were found among the isolates of virus samples collected from several locations in an area in South Sulawesi where tungro is prevalent. In this area, CRIA and IRRI entomologists and pathologists screened approximately 2,000 lines and maintained disease pressure by using an improved screening technique. This technique involved growing a susceptible variety at intervals throughout the nurseries, releasing mass-reared tungro vectors (*Nephotettix virescens*), and using lights to attract vectors from neighboring fields.

Pathologists are concerned about the increasing prevalence of sheath blight. Epidemiological studies revealed a rapid increase in the disease after flowering. A local variety (Angkong) is less susceptible than IR5 or IR30 but is similar to both in the rate of disease development. Further studies are needed to determine yield reductions caused by various levels of infection at different stages of plant development.

IRRI scientists helped with surveys of BPH damage in Java and Bali, studies of BPH control methods, experiments with root zone applications of systemic insecticides, assessment of damage caused by the rice seedbug (*Leptocorisa acuta*), and screening for resistance to the white stem borer (*Tryporyza innotata*). Field trials at three locations on Java (Table 1), where BPH populations were critically high, demonstrated the importance of using both BPH resistant varieties and insecticides to maintain high yields. Pelita was susceptible to BPH, while IR26, IR28, and IR30 were resistant.

Table 1. Average yields and incidence of grassy stunt virus on four rice varieties, with and without insecticides, at three locations in Java, Indonesia, 1975.

Variety	Av. yield (t/ha)		Ratoon hills (%) infected by virus	
	Insecticide	No insecticide	Insecticide	No insecticide
Pelita	3.8	1.3	22	35
IR26	4.8	3.3	38	46
IR28	4.3	3.0	3	9
IR30	4.2	3.0	9	12

Root-zone applications of furadan and BPHC, in trials in South Sulawesi, showed no repellent effect on the feeding behavior of BPH. However, green leafhoppers and BPH are killed instantly upon feeding, and this appears to be the main reason why the inoculum transmitted to furadan-treated plants is insufficient to show virus symptoms after a normal incubation period. Apparently, the rice plant absorbs furadan only when its growing roots intercept soil that contains the insecticide.

In some areas of South Sulawesi, yield losses caused by the rice seedbug were estimated at 7.6 percent and 20.8 percent in the wet and dry seasons, respectively. Boiling harvested or almost mature rice panicles for 10 minutes in a 5 percent KOH solution facilitates the identification of grains damaged by the seedbug. Insecticide sprays appear to be justified when the density of the rice seedbug reaches 2 insects/sq m.

IRRI and CRIA scientists jointly investigated the agronomic aspects of rice-based cropping systems and fertilizer management for lowland and upland rice, two topics of major importance to the small farmer in Indonesia. Fertilizer management trials conducted at two locations in South Sulawesi over several seasons indicated that when all the fertilizer nitrogen is applied between active and maximum tillering, the grain yields are comparable with those obtained when the same level of nitrogen is applied in two or three split applications. Urea placement trials showed consistently that the mudball technique is more efficient than either briquet placement or broadcasting, with greater differences occurring at the lower levels of nitrogen. Nitrogen-source trials at those locations—two lowland and one upland—showed little dif-

ferences among the efficiencies of urea, ammonium sulfate, and sulfur-coated urea (37% N).

Cropping systems studies focused on specific problems in two areas, Central Lampung at the southern end of Sumatra and Indramayu on the north coast of West Java; both locations are included in the International Cropping Systems Network. Central Lampung is characterized by infertile red-yellow podzolic soils and savannah vegetation, typical of an estimated 46 million hectares of land in Indonesia. Management studies have demonstrated the potential productivity of these soils for rice-based cropping systems. Fertilizer, year-round vegetative cover, and incorporation of crop residues help to maintain soil fertility and reduce erosion losses.

The Indramayu area is characterized by low-lying coastal plains with only slight relief and predominantly heavy alluvial clay soils. The area experiences chronic food production shortages because of flooding in the wet season and water shortages in the dry season. Government water control projects (irrigation and drainage) are under way. Cropping systems are being developed through the IRRI-CRIA cooperative project for different durations of irrigation. Cropping patterns were developed for rainfed areas and for areas where irrigation is not reliable or is of short duration. These patterns use direct-seeded early-maturing rices at the beginning of the rainy season and a transplanted crop during the peak of the rainy season. Cropping system studies have demonstrated that an extra rice crop per year is possible in fully irrigated areas, while an extra rice and a secondary crop per year is feasible in areas with 7 to 9 months of irrigation.

The IRRI legume breeder, working with CRIA legume breeders and agronomists, concentrated on three crop plants often grown on residual moisture and rainfall following lowland rice crops, i.e. soybeans, peanuts, and mung beans. In addition to improving the agronomic practices for these legumes, the program introduced exotic germ plasm and subsequently screened and evaluated it to identify sources of resistance to different diseases and insects. Several mung bean lines exhibited tolerance or resistance to the shootfly (*Agromyza phaseoli*).

Genetic recombinations in the F₂ generation of an interspecific mung bean cross (*Vigna aureus* and *Vigna mungo*) incorporated resistance to bean scab. Locally adapted peanut varieties have been found to possess resistance to rust and *Cercospora*. Genetic male sterility is being introduced into soybean lines with the ultimate goal of using population improvement methods to combine disease and insect resistances with acceptable seed quality in high-yield plant types.

The application of stochastic dominance methods to results obtained from several cultural practices experiments indicated that yields from seedlings transplanted at 25 days of age would most likely be better than those from seedlings transplanted at 20 or 30 days of age. Similar analysis of data from wet-season trials revealed no improvement of returns from the use of closer hill spacing of 20 cm × 20 cm and its higher seed and labor costs. Data from dry-season trials suggested a slight advantage for the 20-cm × 20-cm spacing.

Analysis of data from 14 wet-season fertilizer trials conducted in farmers' fields on the north coast of West Java, showed that net returns from applications of 135 kg N and 20 kg P₂O₅ are most likely to be higher than combinations of 90 kg N and 0 kg P₂O₅, 90 kg N and 30 kg P₂O₅, or 180 kg N and 45 kg P₂O₅.

In addition to conducting research at CRIA, Bogor, and at regional research stations, IRRI scientists worked with Indonesian scientists to implement different international network programs. Two of these, the IRTP and cropping systems network were carried out entirely in cooperation with CRIA. The International Agro-Economic Network (IRAEN) was carried out at two sites, at one in cooperation with CRIA and at the other in cooperation with the Faculty of Agriculture, Gadjamada University. The Farm Machinery Network implemented in cooperation with the Directorate of *Bina Produksi* (Production Development) of the Department of Agriculture, emphasized the expansion of indigenous manufacturing of IRRI-designed implements appropriate for introduction into the Indonesia farming sector.

Philippines. IRRI, through a contract with USAID, assigned a crop production specialist

to work with the National Food and Agriculture Council (NFAC) to organize and incorporate the results of agricultural research into an effective extension program. The IRRI specialist served on the National Management Committee of the Philippine Masagana 99 Program for rice production and was a coordinator of farm trials conducted under the NFAC-sponsored Unified Rice Applied Research, Training, and Information Program (URARTIP). The URARTIP is an interagency cooperative program which provides leadership in high priority research on farmers' fields and helps to train extension workers and to disseminate information for the national rice production program.

The Masagana 99 program uses a package of modern rice production practices combined with supervised credit, price support, and trained extension workers. This program has helped the Philippines to regain rice self-sufficiency in 1975 and is acclaimed as highly successful. In 1975, Masagana 99 covered about half of the total rice area in the Philippines, 1.7 million ha. The average rice yields in the program area, which included 1.25 million ha of irrigated rice and 450,000 ha of rainfed rice, improved markedly.

The URARTIP conducted a series of trials on farmers fields to evaluate promising new rice selections and fertilizer and insecticide treatments. An early-maturing selection, IR2071-625-1, performed well in farm trials and was recommended by an Interagency Rice Working Group to the Philippine Seed Board for release in October 1975. Meanwhile, the Bureau of Plant Industry began multiplying this seed for distribution. Fertilizer trials during the 1975 wet season showed that the optimum rates of fertilizer application for the new selection were 60 kg N/ha and 30 kg P₂O₅/ha. Field experiments showed that zinc deficiency is becoming an important constraint on soils with high pH and on soils high in organic matter.

To promote the use of recommended amounts of fertilizer for high-yielding varieties in the Masagana 99 program, the URARTIP project prepared a printed set of instructions to accompany the 30,000 microkits for 0.005-ha areas. Also, to encourage more efficient use of

applied fertilizers, a series of 1,250 five-fertilizer-level kits for 0.1-ha areas, were distributed in late 1975. In addition, the URARTIP staff prepared and distributed material for adaptive trials on farmers' fields to evaluate spacing and fertilizer requirements of the early-maturing variety IR28 under irrigated transplanted culture.

Field observations confirmed the presence in the Philippines of two different biotypes of the brown plant hopper (BPH). IR26, which is widely grown in the Philippines, is resistant to the original biotype but is susceptible to the new biotype. Two hundred 1-kg seed kits of IR32, which is resistant to the new biotype, and 90 1-kg seed kits of IR2072-625-1, which is resistant to both biotypes, were distributed for trials to farmers in the affected area.

Sri Lanka. The cooperative project in Sri Lanka, supported by The Ford Foundation, continued to assist the Paddy Marketing Board (PMB) with its development activities. Two scientists were employed in the project. Training programs covering all aspects of the industry (paddy procurement, cleaning, drying, storage, parboiling, rice milling, and quality control) were conducted for PMB staff, including newly recruited engineers, technicians, operators, and administrative staff. Training seminars were also held for private rice millers.

The PMB staff carried out limited studies and equipment development work, using the facilities available at the training center. A survey of PMB stores was completed in 1975. This enabled the PMB to 1) quantitatively assess the value of storage losses, which amounted to 6.3 percent of the paddy purchased, and 2) more accurately determine the cause of these losses and subsequently plan action programs for reducing these losses.

The paddy harvesting studies (conducted jointly with the Department of Agriculture) showed that the real paddy production was higher (13 to 25 percent) when the new rice varieties were harvested at an optimum time. BG34-8 gave the maximum yield when harvested at 20 to 23.5 percent moisture content. When harvesting was delayed to lower the moisture content of the grain, the yield was progressively reduced; also, a greater percentage of the grains were broken during milling. Early harvesting

prevents the yield losses presently incurred by Sri Lankan farmers, and could thus provide more rice to the nation.

The consumer loss survey carried out with the assistance of the IRRI and PMB scientists has clearly shown the need for introducing improved quality control procedures. To meet the desire of the Government of Sri Lanka for a new quality control system to eliminate losses to the consumer, some of the PMB's storage operations, processing facilities, and quality control procedures will need to be changed.

The IRRI scientists continued to work closely with the PMB staff on its national evaluation of the present status of the post-production industry and on planning for future development. They completed a feasibility study and prepared a project proposal for new storage and processing complexes at two additional locations in Sri Lanka. The local costs of this "3-year-industry-development plan" will be financed by the Government of Sri Lanka, while a USAID loan is expected to cover the foreign exchange costs. This new project marks the beginning of a second phase of development of the post-harvest management industry in Sri Lanka. The initial development phase has been assisted by the IRRI-Ford Foundation project.

The project continued its support for the development of the PMB staff. One statistician participated in a 6-month training course at the Statistical Institute in New Delhi, India, and three other staff members completed Master's degree programs in rice process engineering, production engineering, and agricultural economics and marketing at American universities.

The IRRI project specialists continued to assist the PMB staff in its program of 1) construction of complexes, 2) upgrading of existing facilities, and 3) manufacturing of new equipment. For this third area, IRRI specialists helped with technical specifications and engineering drawings. Government and private manufacturing firms now produce paddy cleaners, dryers, conveying, parboiling and rice milling machinery.

Vietnam. The cooperative project was initiated under a USAID contract in 1972 with one rice breeder and one agronomist. In December

1974, a third IRRI scientist joined the team to develop rice-based cropping systems to maximize land use, food production, and net profits from the resources available to small farmers. However, war caused premature termination of the research activities in Vietnam at the end of April.

The BPH became a widespread problem in Vietnam. Of the two semidwarf varieties released in October 1973, TN73-1 (IR1529-60-3) failed to gain popularity because of its susceptibility to BPH. However, TN73 (IR1561-228-3) was widely cultivated in all production areas because of its earliness, resistance to BPH, and high yield potential. IR26 was named and released in January 1975, and farmers quickly adopted it because of its resistance to all major diseases and insects in Vietnam.

Among the new IRRI materials tested and evaluated in Vietnam, IR1514A-E597-2, IR1717-77-6, IR28, IR2151-957-5, and IR2153-43-2 were most promising. IR1717-77-6 was the first semidwarf glutinous line available in Vietnam with resistance to blast, bacterial blight, BPH, and green leafhopper. Other lines also showed resistance to major diseases and insects. The five experimental lines were submitted to the Vietnam Seed Board to be considered for release in 1975.

Damage from the white-backed planthopper increased in some areas and the commercial varieties currently grown were not known to possess genetic resistance to this rice pest. A special study project was being developed to screen genetic material for resistance to this insect.

About 300 new accessions were obtained through a major rice collection campaign of indigenous varieties. Construction of a seed storage facility was initiated. Only a portion of the samples had been processed and duplicates sent to the germ plasm bank at IRRI when the cooperative project was terminated in April.

Seven dry season-location and five wet season-location trials revealed no response of rice to phosphorus or potassium fertilizer. The application to broadcast-seeded lowland rice of all the fertilizer nitrogen during maximum tillering, or in split doses, half at the early seedling stage and half at panicle initiation,

gave high yields. The carbofuran 3G-mipcin spray combination gave better protection than did the diazinon-dolmix combination. The two herbicide combinations—buthachlor/2,4-D IPE and benthocarb/2,4-D IPE—gave favorable results for both broadcast-seeded lowland and transplanted rice. An experiment on broadcast seeding rates with and without herbicide showed that yields were not influenced by different seeding rates. These results need to be confirmed by further study.

REGIONAL COLLABORATION

As national research capabilities have strengthened and cooperative country projects have begun to phase out, IRRI is establishing a new kind of collaborative relationship with strong national programs and is developing collaborative arrangements with ongoing regional rice research and training programs. As the need arises, IRRI may locate a liaison scientist to work with national and regional programs to facilitate the exchange of information and material and collaborative research, including the operation of international networks.

India. The services of an IRRI representative who maintains liaison with the Indian rice program were provided through funding from The Rockefeller Foundation. Under a Memorandum of Agreement between the Indian Council of Agricultural Research (ICAR) and IRRI, collaborative work was conducted with major emphasis on the evaluation of germ plasm and genetic material under the International Rice Testing Program and on special problems, such as variations in the BPH and tungro virus and screening techniques for tungro. The Ford Foundation grant to IRRI for the collaborative program supported exchange of visits plus information and material and participation by Indian scientists in specially designed training programs and in tours to monitor cooperative nurseries in different countries.

The IRRI representative located in New Delhi worked closely with ICAR, the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project (AICRIP), and state research. The ultimate

objective of this collaborative program is to develop long-term linkages between IRRI and national programs in the Indian subcontinent, and to facilitate collaboration on a regional basis.

The activation of the Fifth Plan further expanded India's rice research and development program activities in late 1975. An increase in budget and staff was visualized for the centrally funded research units at AICRIP, Hyderabad, and at the Central Rice Research Institute (CRRI) at Cuttack. Likewise, some state research units previously supported by ICAR will receive additional funding. In addition to increased funds provided locally, The Ford Foundation gave a grant to strengthen rice research at AICRIP, at CRRI, and at state research centers in India.

Operational research units concerned with rice production carried adaptive research to the villages and linked their efforts with the developmental activities of the departments of agriculture of the respective states. These units were funded and activated in three states. The operational research for integrated pest control, activated at six centers in five states, initiated programs to deal realistically with various aspects of the pest management problems at the farm level. Most of these units have established benchmarks of performance by which the impact of the operational research can be measured.

Early in 1975, the resistance of IR26 to BPH was found to be ineffective to the BPH biotypes in India. Thus an active search of germ plasm was initiated to identify donors and progenies resistant to BPH. Several progenies of RP 1045 (RP31-49-2/Leb Mue Nahng) and a few progenies of crosses involving Ptb 18 and Ptb 21 as parents were found to be resistant both in the greenhouse and in the field. Other sources of resistance to the new BPH biotypes were identified in collections from Kerala and Assam.

While resistance to the Indian BPH has been successfully identified (Table 2), BPH damage was reported in nearly every state in the plains and in the peninsula of India. Alert protection measures taken in some states restricted damage to limited areas in a few states.

Breeding programs begun in 1975 used Ptb

Table 2. Reaction of selected rice varieties to biotypes of the brown planthopper at various locations in India, 1975.

Variety	Reaction ^a								
	Hyderabad	Cuttack	Pattambi	Pantnagar		IRRI biotypes			
				Strain 1	Strain 2	1	2	3	4
Co 9	7.0	4.0	4.4	9.0	9.0	1.7	7.7	1.0	9.0
Ptb 19	5.6	2.4	3.2	8.3	8.5	0.3	0.3	1.0	1.0
Ptb 21	6.4	3.2	5.6	8.5	8.8	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
Thella	8.5	8.8	7.4	9.0	9.0	1.0	9.0	9.0	9.0
ASD 7	7.4	6.5	5.8	9.0	9.0	0.7	1.0	9.0	9.0
Dalwa Sannam	7.9	9.0	5.6	9.0	9.0	3.0	5.5	1.0	9.0
Andaragahawewa	7.4	5.3	4.9	9.0	8.5	1.0	9.0	1.0	9.0
ARC 8650	2.3	1.7	2.9	0.2	5.5	3.0	4.3	4.3	3.0
Ptb 33	2.2	—	2.5	—	4.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0

^aOn a scale of 1 to 9, from resistant (1) to susceptible (9) in accordance with the standard scoring procedure.

33 and ARC 6650 as sources of BPH resistance. Screening of new hybrid material plus resistant progenies identified in the previous breeding material has provided encouraging results for coping with the BPH problem. Some progress was also achieved in the development of selections with multiple gene resistance to the BPH.

While some IRRI rice varieties showed a differential reaction to tungro virus in India, it may be that the strain of virus in India differs from that in the Philippines; the variation has yet to be demonstrated experimentally. The technique perfected by scientists at CRRI in Cuttack for field screening for tungro virus depends on the presence of the virus inoculum and of an adequate population of the vector, *Nephotettix virescens*, in the field. It makes use of a natural buildup of the vector towards the later part of the growing season and its transfer to freshly planted spreader material and, ultimately, to the test material. The field technique produced good infection at CRRI and in Indonesia. Under conditions of limited natural population, positive inoculation by viruliferous insects, using a technique developed at AICRIP, allows the virus reaction to be evaluated with precision by observing leaf color, delay in flowering, and yield.

The revision of AICRIP trials to provide greater service to state programs involved the development of a national screening nursery, which incorporated selected lines of breeders from many different centers throughout the country. Over 1,200 progenies were screened

for resistance to gall midge, BPH, tungro virus, bacterial blight, bacterial leaf streak, sheath blight, blast, *Helminthosporium*, and soil stress problems. The use of special screening centers should permit the new progenies to be evaluated for resistance to these stresses before the selections are evaluated for yield and other characteristics.

Breeding materials entering AICRIP nurseries were supplied to IRRI for evaluation, seed multiplication, and inclusion in the IRTP. The IRRI-India collaborative program included one-fourth of the total 457 IRTP nurseries distributed around the world, in addition to AICRIP nurseries and adaptive research trials at many locations. Monitoring tours enabled research personnel from different countries to join Indian scientists in making field assessments of a number of international and national nurseries. A total of 32 scientists from IRRI, Sri Lanka, Bangladesh, Thailand, Malaysia, and Indonesia participated in these tours to several locations.

The most significant contributions of the collaborative program in India include the systematic study of BPH biotypes, perfection of a field screening technique for rice tungro virus, and identification of new sources of BPH resistance and of new selections showing tolerance to salinity and alkalinity. Germ plasm collections from some states, including cold-tolerant materials from Kashmir and deep-water rices from West Bengal, were supplied to IRRI for further evaluation and preservation.

Thailand. IRRI continued its collaborative

work with the national program in Thailand, emphasizing deep-water rice. The Rockefeller Foundation supports a rice specialist who works with the Thai rice program and also serves as the IRRI representative in Thailand. Because there are no deep-water rice areas in the Philippines, IRRI established, as part of its core program, a collaborative deep-water rice program in Thailand. One rice breeder included in IRRI's core budget was stationed to work with local rice scientists of the Thailand Department of Agriculture, with the IRRI representative as the program leader.

The results of the IRRI-Thai collaborative program are discussed in greater detail in the section that deals with the Genetic Evaluation and Utilization Program. The collaborative program aims at developing varieties that will increase and stabilize grain yield in the deep-water rice areas of Thailand, Bangladesh, India, Burma, Laos, Cambodia, and Vietnam. In the program's efforts to develop rices with an improved plant type and tolerance to water depth of 1 meter or more, traditional floating varieties were crossed with semidwarf selections to combine improved plant type with the ability to elongate faster than the rising water level. Advanced breeding lines are being evaluated in different countries.

Thailand contributes significantly to the international deep-water rice program by providing facilities, manpower, and other support. The Thai rice program also continued to make rapid progress in developing high-yielding varieties for areas in the country where rice is grown under controlled water conditions.

In November, the national program released two new high-yielding varieties, RD7 and RD9. RD7 will probably replace the older varieties, RD1 and RD3, which have become increasingly susceptible to bacterial leaf blight. RD9 is intended for areas where the BPH causes serious rice crop losses.

Collaborative work between Thailand and IRRI also includes growing international rice nurseries at selected sites throughout the country as part of the IRTP and participation in the Cropping Systems Network, IRAEN, and the Machinery Development Network.

Latin America. IRRI continued to collaborate

with the Centro Internacional de Agricultura Tropical (CIAT) and national programs in the region by providing training to selected individuals and by supplying genetic material; 32 sets of international nurseries were supplied for evaluation in 1975. Four scientists from different national programs were in residence at IRRI for training.

CIAT has regional responsibility for rice research and training. Latin America grows 6.6 million ha of rice, 80 percent of which is rainfed upland and the rest, irrigated. Up to the present, CIAT and IRRI have concentrated on irrigated rice insofar as the Latin American requirements are concerned. IRRI's genetic material is well adapted to these conditions and many IRRI lines are now grown commercially in different countries. During the year, CIAT identified two new lines resulting from its breeding program and these lines are being multiplied for release.

To strengthen regional cooperation, CIAT and IRRI developed a joint program for rice research to meet effectively the needs of Latin America. Under the program, an IRRI scientist is to be located at CIAT headquarters to strengthen regional testing and evaluation, under a wide range of ecological conditions, of genetic material produced by the IRRI-CIAT program and national programs. IRRI has markedly expanded its research for the improvement of upland rice. Thus, the genetic material and associated technology developed at IRRI will undoubtedly have greater relevance to upland conditions in the region in the future.

Africa. The International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA) has major responsibility for rice research and training in Africa. The West Africa Rice Development Association (WARDA), with headquarters at Monrovia, Liberia, is an inter-governmental regional organization concerned with the coordination of applied research, extension, and development. IRRI collaborated with IITA and WARDA through exchange of research information, genetic material, visits by scientific personnel, and training of rice scientists. In 1975, IRRI supplied seeds of 65 international nurseries for evaluation and materials for 27 cooperative herbicide trials in Africa. Also, 15 scientists

from the region were in residence for training at IRRI. To ensure effective cooperation among IITA, WARDA, and IRRI, a Memorandum of Understanding is being developed to identify the role of each organization and the working relationships.

Germ plasm collection. In collaboration with national centers, IRRI continued the regional program of collecting indigenous rice germ plasm in South and Southeast Asia. The field advisor of IRRI collected 108 samples during his travels through rice-growing areas of South Vietnam during January and February. A total of 295 samples of yala¹-season rice varieties were collected in the wet zone in a joint venture in Sri Lanka. Visits to remote areas of northeast Bangladesh during December added another 163 samples to the germ plasm collection.

INTERNATIONAL NETWORKS

A primary goal of IRRI's international program is to establish effective linkages that will facilitate an exchange of ideas and the flow of information and genetic material among national and international centers in rice-growing regions. For this purpose, IRRI will establish and use networks to collaborate with national programs in carrying out location-specific and mutually beneficial research, as exemplified by the IRTP. Additionally, some of the conferences and workshops sponsored by IRRI are especially designed to support and stimulate international network activities through a process of joint review and planning. Detailed information on the four networks which began to operate on a formal basis in 1975 is presented under the core programs with which they are associated.

International Rice Testing Program. The IRTP was formalized in 1975 as a special project funded by the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP). The network has facilitated and systemized the flow of genetic material between IRRI and national programs as well as among national programs through IRRI's coordination. This network has greatly accelerated

the evaluation and dissemination of genetic material. A total of 457 sets of 12 yield and screening nurseries were supplied to 47 countries during 1975. This involved 83,000 seed packets of 1,800 entries, one-third of which was contributed by national programs and the balance, by IRRI.

Two scientists serving as coordinators of the IRTP provide the program leadership at IRRI. A small advisory group composed of members from different countries provides the leadership for developing strategy and plans and for reviewing the results. A larger group, representing all participating countries, meets annually in April to discuss and finalize the plans, methodologies, types of nurseries, and number of locations.

Special field books were designed for each type of nursery and a handbook for the standard evaluation system for rice was developed to ensure uniformity in the experimental procedures and data recording systems used at all locations. Regional monitoring tours by groups of scientists are an integral part of the network. As all operations of the IRTP are progressively standardized, data management systems are being designed to use computers to expedite analysis and dissemination of information among the network cooperators.

International Rice Agro-Economic Network. The IRAEN began operations during the year in the Philippines, Indonesia, Thailand, Bangladesh, Taiwan, and Sri Lanka, using funds provided by the IDRC. Its primary objective is to develop methodology to monitor problems that slow the farm adoption of improved rice varieties and technology. Field experiments conducted during 1975 were designed to identify the gap between the farmer's yield and the potential that could be achieved in the farmers' fields, as well as the contribution of different factors to the yield gap. By clarifying the nature of biophysical and socio-economic constraints to high yields, the network studies may help scientists to tailor research to overcome production constraints and serve as a feedback on the role of policies and institutional constraints in limiting rice yields.

Cropping Systems Network. This network provides a mechanism for joint program plan-

¹ Local name in Sri Lanka for the second growing season when the rice is planted in April-May and harvested in September-November of the same year.

ning and review of field research designed to determine the cropping systems potential in major zones of South and Southeast Asia and to enable IRRI to extend relevant methodologies and technology to national programs. In 1975, 14 experimental sites, representing different agro-climatic zones in the Philippines, Indonesia, Bangladesh, Thailand, Sri Lanka, and Malaysia, were identified in collaboration with national programs. Six of these sites were operational in the Philippines, Indonesia, and Bangladesh; the remainder will begin operations in 1976. A working group, which includes national program leaders, helps develop general plans as well as annual plans of work, and reviews and evaluates results. The network included studies of existing cropping patterns and socio-economic characteristics, and designing improved cropping systems and their subsequent testing across a wide range of ecological conditions on farmers' fields.

Farm Machinery Development Network. The network provides IRRI's Department of Agricultural Engineering with linkages for transferring designs for adaption to conditions prevailing in different countries. Previously, extension efforts were concentrated in the Philippines, while in other countries, subcontract arrangements were made with local organizations that were given the responsibility to evaluate and adapt IRRI-designed machines to local conditions and to encourage manufacturing companies to produce machinery locally.

In 1975, the scope of IRRI's industrial extension effort was broadened substantially with funds from the USAID. It includes the assignment of three IRRI agricultural engineers to Thailand, Pakistan, and the Philippines to assist manufacturers in adapting IRRI-designed machines to local farming and manufacturing conditions. These agricultural engineers will provide technical information, adaptive design and management assistance, comprehensive testing and evaluation, and economic and market information. Each will have support staff to help him carry out these activities. Satellite programs will be established in neighboring countries and subcontract activities will continue in countries not encompassed by the new project.

Different components of the international program indicate the types of services that are available from IRRI to national programs, as well as the collaborative activities in which national programs can participate.

Since national capabilities vary widely, no one pattern of cooperation can meet the requirements of the numerous rice-growing nations. Therefore, in consultation with national institutions, IRRI will continue to stimulate cooperative work on the significant problems limiting production over a wide range of ecological conditions, and to provide a blend of outreach services needed to meet the specific requirements of individual nations.

Information resources and experimental farm

LIBRARY AND DOCUMENTATION CENTER

International Bibliography. The 1974 Supplement to the *International Bibliography of Rice Research* published in 1975 provides worldwide coverage of rice research literature. The 386-page (including indexes) supplement contains 3,834 references to scientific rice literature, most of which appeared in journals in 1974. An additional 22 serial titles were scanned and searched in the compilation of the world's literature on rice research. The items of reference are classified according to subject matter, and an author and a manually produced keyword index are included. A list of 41 rice literature translations, mostly from Japanese to English, is included.

The bibliography is distributed to agricultural libraries and documentation centers of the rice-producing regions for the use of rice research workers and those responsible for disseminating information on rice. The basic volume and the annual supplements list technical literature on rice published since 1951. Essentially all the citations included in these bibliographies are available in the IRRI library.

Reference and circulation. Numerous requests for information and photocopying services were received during the year. The majority of the requests came from Indonesia, India, and Malaysia. As in previous years, there were more requests for Japanese literature on genetics and breeding than all other aspects of rice culture. The IRRI library furnished assistance in library organization and management in the selection and acquisition of agricultural materials, and in the processing of special materials such as microfilms, maps, and pamphlets. Requests for short, specific-subject bibliographies were also received.

The number of books and journals borrowed within the institute in 1975 increased markedly over the previous year's.

Library holdings. The addition of 2,934 monographs (books, pamphlets, and reprints) increased the total number in the monographic collection to 40,094. An additional 98 serial titles, which were received through subscriptions, exchanges and gifts, were added. Maps, translations, and microfilms were also added to the collection.

Other library activities. In 1975, the first supplement to the list of doctoral dissertations and theses on rice that are available in the IRRI library was issued.

To keep the scientists informed about the latest publications on rice, the library continued to circulate the table of contents of newly received journals. As in previous years, this service was extended to the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project in Andhra Pradesh, India; the Bangladesh Rice Research Institute; the Lembaga Penelitian Pertanian Maros in Indonesia; the Central Rice Research Institute for Agriculture, Sukamandi Branch, Indonesia; and the West Africa Rice Development Association in Liberia. A monthly listing of new acquisitions of books, serial titles, translations, reprints, and microfilm was also widely distributed.

Copies of English translations of foreign-language literature were sent regularly to the National Agriculture Library (NAL) of the U.S. Department of Agriculture. These translations are listed in the NAL Bibliography of Agriculture to make them readily accessible and available to rice scientists and others.

The library continued to purchase books for IRRI research scholars and trainees.

THE OFFICE OF INFORMATION SERVICES

The Office of Information Services (OIS) in 1975 continued to provide a program of support services for the research and training programs of IRRI and for workshops, seminars, and

international conferences held at the Institute. The support services include editorial services, printing and publishing, graphic arts and design, photography, audio-visual services, visitor services, and preparation and dissemination of information about the IRRI programs, progress, and publications plus the international distribution of IRRI publications.

Five issues of the *IRRI Reporter* newsletter were distributed to over 7,500 libraries, rice scientists, researchers, and others located in Asia, Africa, Latin America, and other parts of the world. Four new publications were issued and distributed: *Changes in Rice Farming in Selected Areas of Asia*, *Major Research in Upland Rice*, *Research Highlights for 1974*, and the 1974 *IRRI Annual Report*. Seven publications, including a second printing of the 1973 *IRRI Annual Report*, were reprinted.

About 11,000 copies of the English version of *Field Problems of Tropical Rice* and 21,860 copies of 35 other IRRI publications were distributed in 1975. Most were disseminated to libraries and rice researchers and workers in rice-growing nations in South and Southeast Asia.

More than 60 technical articles were edited for presentation by IRRI scientists at international meetings, workshops, and symposia and for publication in professional journals and periodicals. The information brochure about the Institute was revised. The publication about statistical procedures for agricultural research, with emphasis on rice, is in press. The proceedings of the 1974 Symposium on Climate and Rice and a publication of selected papers from the report *Changes in Rice Farming in Selected Areas of Asia* are in preparation. The 1969 IRRI publication *Flowering Response of the Rice Plant to Photoperiod—A Review of the Literature* is under revision.

Over 70 sets of the 92 color slides on the field problems of tropical rice, including insects, diseases, and nutritional disorders, were distributed in 1975. A set of color slides entitled "Rices of IRRI" was prepared with an accompanying script; it explains and documents the programs and progress of the Institute. More than 25 sets were distributed.

In cooperation with the IRRI Department of

Agricultural Engineering, the OIS assisted the Singapore-based CEPTA-TV educational films organization prepare a color film about the Institute's farm machinery research and development program, with its emphasis on machines for small farmers. The 20-minute film is scheduled for release in mid-1976.

The IRRI Department of Agricultural Engineering requested three photographic exhibits of black-and-white enlarged photographs with accompanying text, illustrating the IRRI farm machinery development program. One each was sent for display to the World Bank in Washington, D.C., and to Pakistan. The third exhibit was installed as a permanent display at the IRRI Department of Agricultural Engineering for the benefit of departmental visitors. Another photographic exhibit featuring IRRI and its goals and accomplishments was prepared for a special field day program at the neighboring University of the Philippines in Los Baños. Later, it was installed in the lobby of Chandler Hall at IRRI.

The OIS attended to about 12,000 visitors from 33 countries. The largest number of visitors came to IRRI in May (1,900) and August (1,500). The dual-screen slide presentation about IRRI and its programs was presented to IRRI visitors 433 times in 1975. The press kit (photographs, publications, and other materials about IRRI) continued to be distributed to members of the press and other media visiting IRRI.

EXPERIMENTAL FARM DEPARTMENT

During 1975, the Experimental Farm Department, with the assistance of three consultants, began the development of the upland area of the new farm land acquired in late 1974. The completion of a concrete bridge across the Maitim River facilitated the transport of heavy equipment, such as bulldozers, graders, and a payload, used in the land development.

Initially, 1,764 coconut trees were felled to clear the land. Rice, corn, cassava, sweet potatoes, sorghum, soybeans, and mung beans were planted on 39 ha of the cleared land. To control weeds, sweet corn was planted on areas not used for experiments.

The main roads and drainage ditches were built. A farm road and an upland perimeter road are under construction. Fencing of the upland farm is finished and fencing of the lowland area is near completion.

The Experimental Farm Department continued to support the work of the research departments by supplying all the labor needed and by providing services, such as land preparation, planting, weeding, harvesting, and pest control.

In the wet season, IR28, IR29, IR30, and the selection IR841 were planted for seed multiplication on 5.98 ha of the newly acquired lowland farm. The yield was 18.3 tons.

The total area planted for seed production in the dry season (24.6 ha) exceeded that planted in the 1974 dry season (6.3). More varieties and selections were sown for rapid multiplication at the request of the Plant Breeding Department. IR28, IR30, IR32, the selections IR2071-625-1, IR2153-26-3, IR2061-213-2, IR2035-290-2, and IR2071-588-1, and two Korean varieties, Milyang and IR317, were grown on the newly acquired lowland farm land

and on the rented farms outside the experimental farm. The total yield was 70.9 tons of dried paddy at 14 percent moisture content.

A total of 1.8 tons of IR28 and IR30 rice combined was exported to Indonesia and the British Solomon Islands. Seeds of IR22, IR26, IR28, IR29, IR32, and IR34 were sold locally in Luzon, Philippines, to seed growers.

There was a decrease in the use of all insecticides except carbofuran. The amount of fertilizer used increased concomitantly with the increase in the total area planted which increased from 114.9 ha in 1974 to 127.9 ha this year.

Contract labor constituted the major budget expense, with 43 and 41 percent of the total allocated for wages for bird boys and for laborers who prepared the land for planting, respectively.

Rat infestation was particularly severe during the wet months of November and December. Efforts to minimize rat damage included baiting with poison, dusting rat burrows with cyanogas, and supplying neighboring farms with poison baits.

Publications and seminars

PUBLICATIONS

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SEMINARS

The following were the topics of seminars held at IRRI during 1975. Unless otherwise stated, the speakers were staff members.

- Can there be another quantum jump in rice yields? Dr. J. B. Joshi, Director, Indian Agricultural Research Institute, New Delhi, India.
- Population and nutrition. Dr. Mercedes Concepcion, Director, Population Institute of the Philippines, Diliman, Quezon City, Philippines.
- Climate, time, and people in international agricultural development. Prof. A. H. Bunting, Professor of Agricultural Development Overseas, Plant Science Laboratories, University of Reading, England.
- Brazilian National Soybean Project with emphasis on entomology. Dr. Elvis A. Heinrichs, Entomologist, National Soybean Project, Brazilian Ministry of Agriculture / USAID International Agricultural Programs, University of Wisconsin, U.S.A.
- Organization for change: the concept of temporary cooperative systems for generating and diffusing agricultural knowledge. Dr. Rogelio Cuyno, Assistant Professor, Agronomy Department, University of the Philippines at Los Baños.
- The structure and biosynthesis of legume seed proteins in relation to screening for improved protein quality. Dr. Donald Boulter, Professor, Department of Botany, University of Durham, England.
- Plant selection based on photosynthetic efficiency. Dr. N. E. Tolbert, Professor of Biochemistry, Michigan State University, East Lansing, Michigan, U.S.A.
- Crop protection research program of Hoechst in the Philippines. Mr. Jules Guerassimoff, Agro-Research Manager, Hoechst Philippines, Inc.
- Predicting varietal performance. Dr. David R. MacKenzie, Associate Plant Pathologist, Pennsylvania State University, U.S.A.
- The role of yoga for the all-around upliftment of human society. Mr. Acharya Minaksi Sundaran Brahmachari, Regional Secretary, Ananda Marga Pracaraka Sangha Philippines, Inc.
- Impact of the international system on national research capacity: the IRRI and the CIMMYT training programs. Dr. Burton E. Swanson, Research Associate, Department of Continuing and Vocational Education, University of Wisconsin, Madison, Wisconsin, U.S.A.
- Hormonal control of plant growth. Prof. R. L. Wain, Director, Plant Growth Substance and Systemic Fungicide Unit, Agricultural Research Council, Wye College (University of London), Wye, Ashford, Kent, England.
- Mexico's influence on Philippine language, folklore, and trade. Prof. John W. Burton, Assistant Professor of Spanish, San Diego State College, South California, U.S.A.
- Campaign programs to increase rice production. Dr. Leo Dale Haws.
- Small farmers' agricultural production in Colombia. Dr. Hubert George Zandstra, Coordinator, Rural Development Program, International Development Research Centre (IDRC) at Colombia.
- The assessment of climate in agriculture. Dr. Jeremy Elston, Lecturer, Agricultural Botany, University of Reading, Whiteknights, England.
- Production research—→ critical (missing?) link in the agricultural development process. Mr. Charles Ross Bentley, Agronomist, Australian Department of Foreign Affairs.
- The production and development of a high-protein drink: Philsoy. Mr. Elias E. Escueta, Instructor, Department of Food Science and Technology, University of the Philippines at Los Baños.
- Rat control strategy for tropical agriculture. Mr. Michael W. Fall, Biologist, Rodent Research Center, University of the Philippines at Los Baños.
- Bacterial wilt of tomato. Dr. Tom Mew, Research Associate, Plant Pathology Department, Asian Vegetable Research and Development Center, Taiwan.
- Machinery for experimental plot work. Mr. Egel Ojord, President, Executive Committee, International Association on Mechanization of Field Experiments, Norway.
- Future outlook for the University of the Philippines system. Dr. Onofre D. Corpuz, President, University of the Philippines, Diliman, Quezon City.
- Nitrogen-fixing bacteria. Dr. G. Rangaswami, Vice Chancellor, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore, India.
- Large-scale mechanized rice farming in Guadalcanal, Solomon Islands, Mr. Francisco Gorrez, Jr., President and General Manager, Rice Production Management Services, Inc., Makati, Rizal.
- Paddy milling and processing in Asia. Dr. Chul Choo Lee, Visiting Agricultural Engineer, Agricultural Engineering Department, IRRI.
- The development of an analytical service laboratory for IRRI. Dr. John A. Varley, head, Tropical Soils Analysis Unit, Ministry of Overseas Development, London.
- Autoanalyzer—theory and practice. Dr. J.A. Varley, Tropical Soils Analysis Unit, Ministry of Overseas Development, London.
- Controlled environment—agriculture in arid zones. Dr. John C. O'Toole.
- Training strategies to meet manpower requirements for agriculture in the Philippines. Dr. Mauricio Leonor, Assistant Professor, Department of Agricultural Education, University of the Philippines at Los Baños.
- Science and the problems of modern society. Dr. Alexander King, Chairman, International Federation of Institute for Advanced Study, Paris, France.
- Food habits in multiple cropping barrios. Prof. Josefa Eusebio, Assistant Professor, Institute of Human Ecology, University of the Philippines at Los Baños.

The diffusion of IR26 through compact farming systems in the Philippines. Mr. Sagar Lall, Research Scholar, University of the Philippines at Los Baños.

Early history of rice culture. Dr. Te-Tzu Chang.

Irrigation and land development in the People's Republic of China. Dr. Amir U. Khan.

Some observations on agriculture in the People's Republic of China. Dr. Emil Javier, Associate Dean, College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines at Los Baños.

Nitrate reductase as a criterion for selection of superior cultivars. Dr. R. H. Hageman, Professor of Plant Physiology, Department of Agronomy, College of Agriculture, University of Illinois, Urbana-Champaign, Illinois, U.S.A.

The Yamamoto theory, the results of experiments on root development conducted jointly with the UPLB [University of the Philippines at Los Baños]. Dr. Takoma Yamamoto, President, Philippine Kiku Chemical Corporation, Cubao, Quezon City, Philippines.

Advantage in numbers: in defense of population growth. Mr. Reuben Mondejar, Administrative Secretary, Center for Research and Communications, Manila.

The Institute of Human Ecology: its organization and program. Dr. Gil Saguiguit, Dean, Institute of Human Ecology, University of the Philippines at Los Baños.

Integrated pest management in multiple cropping systems. Dr. James A. Litsinger.

Experiences with recent rice production projects in tropical Asia. Dr. Hans Ruthenberg, Head, Department of Land Use Economics in the Tropics and Subtropics, University of Hohenheim, Stuttgart, Germany.

Developments and trends in U.S. agriculture in the early 1970's. Dr. Edwin C. Price.

A model for optimizing crop production in small farms. Dr. Arturo A. Gomez, Project Coordinator, Multiple Cropping Section, Agronomy Department, University of the Philippines at Los Baños.

Order in complexity—the study of cropping systems in tropical Asia. Dr. Richard R. Harwood.

The social laboratory: an approach in rural development. Dr. Sotero L. Lasap, Jr., Assistant Professor, Department of Agricultural Education, University of the Philippines at Los Baños.

Rural development strategy in South China. Dr. Graham Johnson, Cornell University, Ithaca, New York, U.S.A.

Fissuring of the rice grain due to moisture absorption. Mr. Otto Kunze, Visiting Professor, Agricultural Engineering Department, Texas A & M University, U.S.A.

Finances

During 1975 the Institute received cash grants amounting to US\$11,203,537. The Ford Foundation gave \$1,533,100. Of this amount, \$750,000 was toward the core operating and capital expenditures of the Institute. The remainder was in support of the rice research and development programs of five countries: Sri Lanka — \$185,000 as part of a 2-year grant for the project on modernization of rice processing and distribution; Bangladesh — \$388,700 which is part of a 2½-year grant to provide support for the Bangladesh Rice Research Institute; Indonesia — \$42,900 which is part of a 2-year grant for an accelerated rice research program; Egypt — \$44,000 which is part of a 2-year grant for the services of a project specialist with the Arid Lands Agricultural Program in the Middle East; and India — \$122,500 which is part of a 2-year grant for collaborative research and development on rice production and processing in the Indian subcontinent.

The Rockefeller Foundation contributed \$750,500 during 1975. This amount included \$700,000 for the core operating and capital expenditure needs of the Institute. The Rockefeller Foundation released \$29,500 as part of a 3-year grant to support the program to develop and introduce improved rice technology to disadvantaged Asian rice farmers in upland and rainfed areas; \$14,000 as part of a grant for the collection of the world's rice germ plasm; and an \$8,000 grant toward publication costs of the *Manual for Rice Breeders*.

From various grants, the U.S. Agency for International Development (USAID) released a total of \$2,497,809. The Institute received \$1,925,000 for its core operations; \$25,456 for expansion, strengthening, and further institutionalization of the national Applied Research and Extension Program for Transplanted Rice; \$14,098 for industrial extension of small-scale agricultural equipment developed at IRRI; \$43,612 for agricultural equipment development research for tropical rice cultivation; and \$19,796 to assist in organizing and incorporating the results of agricultural research for the

Philippine National Food and Agriculture Council Production Programs. Since 1972, a contract between IRRI and USAID has supported a project for the accelerated development and utilization of improved technology in agriculture in Indonesia with a budget of \$640,050, in addition to a budget of Rp. 446,775,159 (approximately US\$1,116,938), which is managed by the USAID mission in Djakarta for 3½ years. In 1975, \$186,423 was reimbursed to the Institute. Since 1971, a contract with USAID supported a project to help the government of Vietnam accelerate rice research for 3½ years with a budget of \$464,000 in addition to a budget of VN\$43,070,000 (approximately US\$61,530). In 1975, \$65,364 was reimbursed to the Institute. The USAID contributed toward IRRI's training program by supporting scholars from various countries where USAID has active programs. The Institute received \$178,115 for this purpose in 1975. The USAID mission in Bangladesh released \$39,945 to finance the training of staff from the Bangladesh Rice Research Institute in the Philippines and in the U.S.

The Overseas Development Administration of the United Kingdom gave \$508,188 toward the support of IRRI's core program.

The International Development Research Centre (IDRC) of Canada gave \$867,845. As a part of a 2-year grant to the Institute for cropping systems research in the Philippines, in cooperation with the University of the Philippines at Los Baños, IDRC released \$621,811. The centre also made the following grants in 1975: \$99,740 as a part of a 3-year grant to enable IRRI to develop an appropriate procedure for identifying the critical factors that constrain the adoption and the productivity of new rice technology and to determine the degree to which the factors inhibiting the spread of the new technology are generally or locationally specific; \$19,720 for a 1-year grant for the operational support of two consultants to advise IRRI on the various rice soils of Asia; \$14,000 as a grant to enable IRRI to bring

together Southeast Asian agricultural program administrators to discuss the potentials and problems of managing cropping systems programs in their countries; \$92,931 as partial release of a 2-year grant to enable IRRI to conduct research in Indonesia in cooperation with the Central Research Institute for Agriculture (CRIA) to develop cropping systems for rainfed and partially irrigated rice areas and to adapt improved cropping systems through cooperative trials in farmers' fields; and a \$19,643 grant to enable IRRI to host a meeting in Manila at which representatives of countries in Southeast Asia undertaking multiple cropping programs can discuss their present work, the priorities for future research, and the development of a functional cropping systems research network for the region.

The Japanese government gave \$674,691 toward the training program of the Institute, to purchase equipment required for research activities, and to support the Institute's Plant Physiology Department.

The International Development Association gave \$2,030,000 toward the core operating expenditures of the Institute.

The West German government gave \$193,407 toward the Institute's core operations.

The Australian government gave \$437,125 to support the IRRI core budget; \$15,106 to support the improvement of the facilities at the phytotron; and \$21,389 as a grant toward IRRI's training program.

The Government of Indonesia, using a World Bank loan, released \$155,839 to IRRI as part of a 5-year contract toward the development of research facilities at the Sukamandi Branch of the Central Research Institute for Agriculture (CRIA) and toward scientific and technical assistance to rice research in this branch of CRIA.

In 1967 IRRI entered into a cost-reimbursement contract with the U.S. National Institutes of Health to study ways to increase the protein and essential amino acids of the rice grain through plant breeding. During 1975, \$4,000 was reimbursed to the Institute.

In 1975, the Netherlands government gave \$129,950 as part of a 5-year grant for a project for regional station development in Indonesia.

The United Nations Development Programme gave \$100,000 as a grant for the training of rice scientists and technicians and \$290,000 as part of a 5-year grant for the International Rice Testing Program.

The Canadian International Development Agency contributed \$340,200 for the construction of new conference and training facilities.

A technical assistance grant of \$300,000 was received from the Asian Development Bank to purchase laboratory and training equipment.

The United Nations Environmental Programme contributed \$70,000 to support the rice research program.

The names of other donors, along with the areas supported, and the amounts received during 1975 are given below:

National Science Development Board, evaluation of promising rice selections and management practices in the Philippines	\$ 3,849
Imperial Chemical Industries, weed control	5,000
Potash Institute of North America and International Potash Institute, soil fertility	2,200
Stauffer Chemical Company, weed control	3,000
International Minerals and Chemical Corporation, soil fertility and fertilizer efficiency	40,000
CIBA—Geigy, pest control	1,500
World Phosphate Rock Institute, IRRI research activities	10,000
Cyanamid Far East Limited, insect and weed control	8,000
HOECHST (Joint Stock) Company, institute operation	3,325
FMC International S.A., pesticide research	2,000
Shell Chemical Company, research grant to IRRI	5,714

Staff changes

January:

Dr. Edwin C. Price, Jr. joined the Department of Agricultural Economics as associate agricultural economist in the cropping systems program.

Dr. Iwao Watanabe joined the Department of Soil Microbiology as soil microbiologist and department head.

March:

Mr. Donald O. Kuether joined the Department of Agricultural Engineering as associate agricultural engineer.

April:

Dr. Richard L. Tinsley, an associate agronomist from the IRRI Cooperative Vietnam Rice Project, joined the Multiple Cropping Department as visiting associate agronomist in the cropping systems program.

May:

Dr. Dwight G. Kanter, a rice breeder from the IRRI Cooperative Vietnam Rice Project, joined the International Rice Testing Program (IRTP) as visiting associate plant breeder.

June:

Dr. Frank H. Haramoto began a 6-month stay with the Entomology Department as visiting scientist.

Dr. Chul Choo Lee completed a 14-month assignment as a visiting associate engineer in the Department of Agricultural Engineering.

Dr. Keith Moody joined the Agronomy Department as associate agronomist, working in the cropping systems program.

July:

Dr. Gurdev S. Khush, plant breeder, began a 1-year study leave in the Department of Agronomy at Colorado State University, Fort Collins, U. S. A.

Mr. John A. McMennamy joined the Agricultural Engineering Department as associate agricultural engineer.

Dr. Felix N. Ponnampereuma, soil chemist, began a 1-year study leave.

August:

Dr. Elvis A. Heinrichs joined the Entomology

Department as entomologist and department head.

Dr. Tom Mew joined the Plant Pathology Department as associate plant pathologist.

Dr. D. L. R. Neeley finished his 12-month visit with the Statistics Department as visiting associate statistician.

September:

Dr. Thomas H. Wickham rejoined the Department of Agricultural Economics as associate agricultural economist following a 1-year leave.

October:

Dr. Shohei Matsumoto completed his 12-month stay in the Department of Plant Pathology as visiting plant pathologist.

November:

Dr. Hubert G. Zandstra joined the Multiple Cropping Department as agronomist.

December:

Dr. David R. Bouldin began a 6-month stay with the Department of Soil Microbiology as visiting soil scientist.

Dr. Tetsuo Satake joined the Plant Physiology Department as visiting scientist for 6 months. There were changes in the institute staff in international programs.

Dr. Peter R. Hobbs joined the IRRI-Ford Foundation-Bangladesh Rice Project in January as agronomist.

Dr. Robert P. Bosshart, soil scientist and agronomist, resigned in April from the IRRI Cooperative Vietnam Rice Project (CVRC).

Dr. Dwight Kanter, rice breeder, transferred in April from the IRRI/CVRC to the IRRI/IRTP as visiting scientist.

Dr. Richard L. Tinsley, associate agronomist (Multiple Cropping), in April transferred from the IRRI/CVRC to the IRRI Department of Multiple Cropping as visiting scientist.

Mr. William G. Golden, Jr., rice specialist, resigned from IRRI-Ford Foundation-Bangladesh Rice Project in May.

Dr. Robert I. Jackson left the IRRI-Indonesia Cooperative Project in May.

Dr. Kunio Toriyama completed his assignment as project specialist in Egypt in June.

Crop weather

The amount of precipitation in 1975 at the experimental farm of the International Rice Research Institute, Los Baños, Laguna, Philippines was 1,860 mm. This is lower than both the 2,492 mm recorded in 1974 and the 9-year average (1966–1974) of 2,063 mm. The even and regular distribution of the rainfall in 1975, with at least 200 mm/month in each of the last 6 months of the year, was good for the rice crop, particularly for the rainfed crops, and contributed to the achievement of a normal yield from the rainfed rice experiments at the IRR I farm. A promising selection, IR2721-105-9, produced in one experiment the highest yield—4.8 t/ha—under rainfed lowland conditions.

This favorable distribution of rainfall at the IRR I farm and in other areas of the Philippines was, in general, part of the overall good weather pattern that prevailed in 1975 in most of South and Southeast Asia, and contributed, in large part, to the high production of rice in many Asian nations.

The 139 mm of rain that fell in Los Baños in April 1975 was substantial compared with the negligible (3 mm) rain in April 1974 or with the 9-year average (1966–74) of 15 mm for April. This precipitation level was similar to the rainfall pattern in 1975 in many parts of the Philippines and gave ample opportunity to achieve a productive dry-seeded rainfed program with banded rice in the Philippines. This system of rice culture depends primarily on the early establishment of a good stand of rice. The level of precipitation in Los Baños during December 1975 was greater than the 9-year average for December between 1966 and 1974 (fig. 1). However, the December rain did not significantly affect rice crop performance because most of the wet-season crops were harvested by November.

Only six tropical depressions were recorded in Los Baños as compared with 14 in this area in 1974. These six cyclones occurred in 4 different months, two in both August (6 and 8–9) and October (3 and 18) and one on 19 November and another on 27 December.

1. Rainfall (three-point moving weekly average) at IRR I at Los Baños, Philippines, av. 1966–1974 and 1975.

2. Solar radiation (three-point moving weekly average) at IRR I at Los Baños, Philippines, av. 1966–1974 and 1975.

The solar radiation value of 27.8 kcal recorded during April and May 1975, the ripening period for the dry-season rice crop, was similar to the 27.6 kcal registered during April and May in 1974, but was lower than the 31.2 kcal average for these 2 months during the 9 years between 1966 and 1974. The solar radiation for the entire growing period during the 1975 wet season was lower than the 9-year average (1966–1974) for the comparable wet-season period (fig. 2). Although the rainfall was normal during the 1975 wet season, because of the relatively low solar radiation, no record rice yields were reached for the season.

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RESEARCH HIGHLIGHTS

GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION (GEU) PROGRAM

CONTROL & MANAGEMENT OF RICE PESTS

IRRIGATION & WATER MANAGEMENT

SOIL & CROP MANAGEMENT

ENVIRONMENT & ITS INFLUENCE

CONSTRAINTS ON RICE YIELDS

CONSEQUENCES OF NEW TECHNOLOGY

MACHINERY DEVELOPMENT & TESTING

POST-PRODUCTION TECHNOLOGY & MANAGEMENT FOR RICE

CROPPING SYSTEMS